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A Framework for Scenario-Based Hydrodynamic Design Optimization of Hard Chine Planing Craft

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Abstract

An optimization framework for the design of hard chine planing craft incorporating resistance, seakeeping and stability considerations is presented. The proposed framework consists of a surface information retrieval module, a geometry manipulation module and an optimization module backed by standard naval architectural performance estimation tools. Total resistance comprising calm water resistance and added resistance in waves is minimized subject to constraints on displacement, stability and seakeeping requirements. Three optimization algorithms are incorporated in the optimization module: Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm (NSGA-II), Evolutionary Algorithm with Spatially Distributed Surrogates (EASDS), and Infeasibility Driven Evolutionary Algorithm (IDEA). The individual performance of each algorithm is reported. The proposed framework is capable of generating the optimum hull form, which allows for a better estimate of performance compared to methods that generate only the optimum principal dimensions. The importance and effects of the vertical impact acceleration constraint on manned and unmanned missions are also discussed.

Nomenclature

B	Beam (m)	L	Length (m)
C_v	Speed coefficient	LCB	Longitudinal centre of buoyancy (m)
$Disp.$	Displacement (kg)	R_A	Added resistance (N)
Fn	Froude number	R_C	Calm water resistance (N)
GM	Metacentric height (m)	R_T	Total resistance (N)
$H_{1/3}$	Significant wave height (m)	T	Draft (m)
I_e	Half angle of entrance (degrees)	$Vol.$	Displaced volume (m ³)
I_a	Vertical impact acceleration (g)		

1. Introduction

Ship design involves the practice of satisfying requirements based on a vessel's intended tasks and rationalization, *Schneekluth and Bertram (1998)*. The design of a ship should meet statutory requirements, mission requirements, economic criteria, safety requirements and so on. The choices of main dimensions of the ship affect the hydrostatic and hydrodynamic performance of the ship such as its resistance and response in the seaway. Ship design optimization allows the tradeoff between various performance requirements and is an indispensable element of modern day design processes. Consideration of seakeeping performance during the phase of design has been reported in a number of recent studies. *Sarioz and Narli (2005)* presented an example of seakeeping assessment under various vertical acceleration regimes outlined in ISO 2631, *Mason and Thomas (2007)* illustrated the use Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) and Genetic Algorithm (GA) for the optimization of International America's Cup Class (IACC) yachts, *Peri and Campana (2003)* designed a naval surface combatant with total resistance and seakeeping considerations. Other examples involving multiple design aspects i.e. resistance, seakeeping, cost and safety optimization based on specific scenarios have been presented by *Smith (1992)*, *Ray (1995)*, *Ganesan (1999)*, *Neti (2005)* and *Bersenoff et al. (2009)*.

Most of the above studies focused on displacement crafts and there are only a handful studies dealing with planing crafts. Minimization of calm water resistance for planing crafts appears in *Almeter (1995)* and *Mohamad Ayob et al. (2009)*. Presented in this paper is a scenario based hydrodynamic

optimization of planing craft in seaway operations. An integrated approach is taken that simultaneously considers resistance and motions in a seaway. A number of efficient optimization algorithms are employed for solving the problems posed. The Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm-II (NSGA-II) by *Deb et al. (2002)* is incorporated in the planing craft optimization framework. In addition to NSGA-II, a surrogate assisted optimization scheme (referred here as EASDS) by *Isaacs et al. (2007)* and an Infeasibility Driven Evolutionary Algorithm (IDEA) *Ray et al. (2009)* is incorporated for increased efficiency.

In order to support design optimization of planing craft, the underlying framework should:

1. allow easy incorporation of different scenarios, design criteria etc. with alternate analysis modules providing different levels of fidelity;
2. allow shape representation and manipulation that is able to generate different variants of hull forms with the required fairness and chine definitions; and
3. include an optimization method that is capable of dealing with single and multi-objective optimization problems with constraints. Furthermore, since the performance evaluations are computationally expensive, the optimization algorithms employed should be efficient.

The proposed framework is built using a modular concept with the Microsoft[®] COM interface as the underlying communication platform between applications. A modular design in any optimization framework opens the possibility of conducting more complex analysis, *Ray (1995)*, where other optimization schemes and high fidelity multidisciplinary analysis tools can be added and executed for comparative purposes. A number of researchers have discussed helpful proposals for integration of different tools within a ship design framework. *Neu et al. (2000)* applied Microsoft[®] COM interface in containership design optimization. *Mohamad Ayob et al. (2009)* used Maxsurf Automation, *Maxsurf (2007)* (a form of Microsoft[®] COM interface) for planing craft design optimization. *Abt et al. (2009)* presented a broader aspect of integration between tools, including integration of in-house and commercial codes using XML files, generic templates and Microsoft COM interface.

2. Optimization framework components

The optimization framework proposed in this paper consists of three applications namely Matlab, Microsoft[®] Excel and Maxsurf. Maxsurf Automation Library built upon Microsoft[®] COM interface is used as a medium of communication (inter-process) between applications. Presented in Fig. 1 is a generic sequence diagram to illustrate the workflow of the current optimization framework. The inter-process communication is initialized with the selection of principal dimensions (L , B , T) by the optimizer module in Matlab. Parametric transformation is invoked to generate a candidate hull followed by evaluation of the hydrostatics and calm water resistance of the candidate hull in Maxsurf using the methods of *Savitsky (1964)*. Finally the seakeeping performance is evaluated using the *Savitsky and Koelbel (1993)* method. This completes one workflow loop. The detail flowchart on the optimization framework is presented in Fig. 2 with further discussion of this provided in subsequent sections.

Fig. 1: Inter-process communication flow between applications

Fig. 2: Detail flowchart on the optimization framework

2.1. Geometry tools

The geometry tools consist of a *surface information retrieval module* and a *geometry manipulation module*. Shown in Fig.2, the surface information retrieval module is employed to generate B-spline representation of the hull while the geometry manipulation module changes the shape of the hull based on principal dimensions given by the optimizer.

The formulation of surface information module is based on the inverse B-spline method, *Rogers and Adams (1990)*. A set of known surface (offset) data is used to determine the defining polygon net for a B-spline surface that best interpolates the data. This method is further expanded to yield a representation of a hard chine form that normally represents a planing craft, *Mohamad Ayob et al. (2009)*. Three B-spline surfaces defined by their own respective polygon nets station-wise with the exclusion of the bow are connected to produce hard chines of the planing craft as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Three-dimensional view of the planing craft with governing control points

Since the work of *Lackenby (1950)*, the parametric transformation method has been used widely by naval architects to modify the form parameters of an existing parent hull form. While LCB and C_p values of the resulting hull can be maintained when the hull sections are moved forward and aft, the displacement value of the hull is changed in the process. In this study the parametric transformation module of Maxsurf is considered as it offers the capability to produce new candidate hull forms while maintaining the displacement and coefficient values of the parent hull, *Maxsurf (2007)*. Control points defining the non-uniform rational B-splines surface (NURBS) of the ship are moved in a smooth fashion producing an acceptable fair surface of the resulting hull. An elaborate discussion on the development of Maxsurf parametric transformation can be found in *Mason and Thomas (2007)*.

2.2. Resistance estimation module

Calm water resistance estimation of planing craft is bounded by certain validation criteria. The details of the range of validation is discussed in the work of *Savitsky (1964)* and *Savitsky and Ward Brown (1976)* and in this study will be employed as constraints to the optimization problem. The details of the planing craft studied in this paper are presented in Table I. As discussed in *Savitsky and Ward Brown (1976)*, a craft is in full planing mode for speed coefficient $C_v > 1.5$. In this regime, the resulting dynamic forces cause a significant rise of the center of gravity, positive trim, emergence of the bow and the separation of the flow from the hard chines.

Table I: Characteristics of the planing craft

Displacement	7204.94 kg
Length	10.04 m
Beam	2.86 m
Draft	0.7 m
Metacentric height (GM)	2.0 m
Speed	20.81 kts
$C_v = V/(g \times B)^{1/2}$	2.02

2.3. Seakeeping estimation technique

The method described in Section 2.2 is suitable for calm water resistance. However, an additional formulation is required in order to calculate the total resistance, R_T of the planing craft operating in a seaway. *Fridsma's (1971)* experimental tank test data on planing craft operating in rough water has been reworked by *Savitsky and Ward Brown (1976)* in a form of equations suitable for computer programming. The estimation modules discussed serve as mathematical model in order to search for the optimum design inside the framework. Total resistance and average vertical impact acceleration over irregular waves having energy spectrum of Pierson-Moskovitz is used in this study.

2.4. Maxsurf Automation

Maxsurf Automation is an interface that provides extensive possibilities of integration between different naval architectural tools, whether developed in-house or commercially, *Maxsurf (2007)*. The automation library is built upon the Microsoft® COM framework, thus allowing automation of calls between compatible applications.

2.5. Optimization algorithms

In this framework, three state of the art optimization algorithms have been used namely NSGA-II, EASDS and IDEA. The algorithms are written in Matlab and integrated via the Microsoft® COM interface discussed earlier.

An elitist, population-based, zero-order, stochastic algorithm known as the Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II (NSGA-II) is used as the underlying optimization algorithm. NSGA-II is known

to be able to solve a wide range of engineering problems. The algorithm starts with a population of solutions that undergo crossover and mutation to generate offsprings. The current population and current offspring population are sorted based on non-domination and only the best N individuals are selected, where N is the population size. For complete details the readers are referred to the work of *Deb et al. (2002)*.

Most forms of evolutionary algorithm including NSGA-II require the evaluation of numerous candidate solutions prior to its convergence, thus their applicability is restricted for computationally expensive optimization problems. In order to overcome the problem of lengthy computational time, surrogates or approximations can be employed. In this study an evolutionary algorithm with spatially distributed surrogates (EASDS) is employed. The evolutionary algorithm is embedded with multiple surrogates such as the ordinary response surface method (ORSM), the normalized response surface method (RSM), the ordinary radial basis function (ORBF), the normalized radial basis function (RBF) and the kriging method (DACE). The algorithm performs actual analysis for the initial population followed by periodical evaluations in every few generations. A new candidate solution is predicted by the surrogate model with the least prediction error in the neighbourhood of that point. The complete details of the algorithm are explained in *Isaacs et al. (2007)*.

Solutions to real-life constrained optimization problems lie often on constraint boundaries. In reality, a designer is often interested in looking at the solutions that might be marginally infeasible. Most optimization algorithms including NSGA-II intrinsically prefer a feasible solution over an infeasible solution during the search. However, some recent works suggest that effectively utilizing the marginally infeasible solutions during the search can expedite the rate of convergence. To this effect, Infeasibility Driven Evolutionary Algorithm (IDEA) by *Ray et al. (2009)* is also used in this study.

3. Numerical experiments

In this section, the definition of the seaway operability condition, optimization problem formulation and results for various scenarios are presented. The significance of various design criteria are further discussed in the following subsections.

3.1. Definition of the seaway and operability condition

The case study refers to a design around coastal waters of Visakhapatnam in India. The wind speed data for the above location is obtained from *Shreeram and Rao (2005)*. An approximate value of the significant wave height, $H_{1/3}$ data is estimated along the range of 12 nautical miles (22 km) and is presented in Table II. The location of interest is shown in Fig. 4.

Table II: Chosen significant wave height data for numerical experiment

Wind Speed	Sea State Code	Significant Wave Height
4 m/s	1	0.4 m
5 m/s	2	0.6 m
6 m/s	2	0.8 m
7 m/s	3	1.1 m

Habitability of a craft can be assessed by means of *ISO (1985)* where vertical acceleration, exposure time and frequency are linked together to yield the seakeeping criteria. An example of its applicability was illustrated by *Sarioz and Narli (2005)*.

Fig.4: Territorial waters of India near Visakhapatnam, 12 nautical miles from the coastal line

3.2. Optimization problem formulation

The optimization problem is posed as the identification of a planing craft with minimum total resistance subject to the constraints on displacement, stability (transverse metacentric height) and impact acceleration corresponding to the operational sea-states. The planing craft used in this study represents a craft similar to U.S. Coast Guard (USCG) Surf Rescue Boat (30-foot SRB) (*Halberstadt (1987)*). The ship is designed to operate in sea up to 3 m waves, with a maximum speed of 30 knots. The seaway scenarios are expressed in Table II by significant wave heights $H_{1/3}$ assuming Pierson-Moskovitz spectra. The objective functions and constraints are listed below, where subscripts B , I , T , C and A resemble basis hull, candidate hull, total resistance, calm water resistance and added resistance due to waves, respectively.

Minimize: $f = R_T$, where $R_T = R_C + R_A$

Design variables: $9\text{m} < L < 11\text{m}$ ($L_B = 10.04\text{m}$) ; $1.8\text{m} < B < 3.8\text{m}$ ($B_B = 2.862\text{m}$) ; $0.6\text{m} < T < 0.8\text{m}$ ($T_B = 0.7\text{m}$)

Constraints: $g(1) : Disp_I > Disp_B$; $g(2) : GM_I \geq GM_B$; $g(3) : 3.07 < L/Vol_I^{1/3} < 12.4$
 $g(4) : 3.7^\circ < I_{el} < 28.6^\circ$; $g(5) : 2.52 < L/B_I < 18.28$; $g(6) : 1.7 < B/T_I < 9.8$

A vertical impact acceleration limit is part of the seakeeping assessment criteria. Based on *Savitsky and Koelbel (1993)* the maximum vertical impact acceleration chosen at any location of the planing craft for one or two hours of operation is $1.5g$. Thus, an additional constraint $g(7) : I_a < 1.5g$ is imposed. This additional criterion is a crew performance criterion, and not a hull design criterion.

3.3. Optimization results

For each algorithm (NSGA-II, IDEA and EASDS), 10 independent runs are performed. A population size of 40, crossover probability of 1, mutation probability of 0.1, crossover distribution index of 10, and mutation distribution index of 20 were used for each algorithm. The number of function evaluations used by each algorithm is kept approximately equal for a fair comparison. The surrogate models used are restricted to RSM, ORSM, RBF, ORBF and DACE. A training period of 3 and prediction error of 0.05 has been used for EASDS.

The R_T value corresponding to the best run of each algorithm (EASDS, IDEA and NSGA-II) is plotted against function evaluations for sea state 1 in Fig. 5(a). All the algorithms are in general able to derive savings in R_T as compared to the basis hull while satisfying the constraint on vertical impact

acceleration. Similar results were obtained for studies conducted at sea state 2. In the case of designs under sea state 3 conditions as shown in Fig. 5(b) and Table V to VII, the basis hull has vertical impact acceleration larger than 2g violating the constraint. Runs of all the algorithms are able to achieve feasible designs while satisfying the constraint on impact acceleration, though at a cost of an increased R_7 .

(a) Sea-state 1 ($H_{1/3} = 0.4\text{m}$)

(b) Sea-state 3 ($H_{1/3} = 1.1\text{m}$)

Fig. 5: Optimization progress plot of ship with vertical impact acceleration constraint

(a) Sea-state 1 ($H_{1/3} = 0.4\text{m}$)

(b) Sea-state 2 ($H_{1/3} = 0.6\text{m}$)

(c) Sea-state 2 ($H_{1/3} = 0.8\text{m}$)

(d) Sea-state 3 ($H_{1/3} = 1.1\text{m}$)

Fig. 6: Optimization progress plot of ship without vertical impact acceleration constraint

The value of impact acceleration and R_T of the basis hull at sea state 3 is 2.11g and 13545.90 N respectively, while all optimized designs have impact acceleration 1.5g and R_T of 21830.67 N, 21829.52 N and 21833.40 N for NSGA-II, EASDS and IDEA, respectively. The optimized hull forms found by the optimizers have similar characteristics where larger values of L , B and T result in a larger displacement in order to satisfy the vertical impact acceleration constraint. The details on the dimensions are highlighted in Tables V to VII.

The results for the optimization without the impact acceleration constraint are shown in Fig. 6. Total resistance values of the best run of each algorithm (EASDS, IDEA and NSGA-II) are plotted against function evaluations for typical sea states of 1, 2 and 3. In all sea-states, EASDS was able to converge faster than IDEA and NSGA-II. One can observe by comparing Fig. 5(b) and Fig. 6(d) that an increase of R_T as high as 61% is necessary to satisfy the impact acceleration constraint, as compared to a reduction by 2.97% when the impact acceleration constraint is ignored.

Shown in Fig. 7 is the progress for the median designs obtained using NSGA-II, EASDS and IDEA for sea-state 1. Given the approximately same number of function evaluations, IDEA converges faster than the other two algorithms while EASDS converges better than NSGA-II. A more comprehensive comparison between algorithms can be observed in Tables III and IV where the best values of median designs at all sea-states are depicted in bold type. EASDS consistently performs better than NSGA-II and IDEA in solving the minimization problem with the impact acceleration constraint, while IDEA outperforms the other two algorithms for the problem without the impact acceleration constraint.

Fig 7: Median design obtained using EASDS, IDEA and NSGA-II

Table III: Comparison between R_T (N) of median designs with I_a constraint

	Sea-state 1 (0.4m)	Sea-state 2 (0.6m)	Sea-state 2 (0.8m)	Sea-state 3 (1.1m)
NSGA-II	12060.96	12460.96	13858.59	21844.52
EASDS	11955.90	12415.75	13314.61	21842.02
IDEA	11933.19	12549.24	13709.51	21871.29

Table IV: Comparison between R_T (N) of median designs without I_a constraint

	Sea-state 1 (0.4m)	Sea-state 2 (0.6m)	Sea-state 2 (0.8m)	Sea-state 3 (1.1m)
NSGA-II	12065.10	12460.96	12968.60	13506.20
EASDS	11999.19	12415.75	12916.91	13468.44
IDEA	11962.04	12445.15	12880.76	13315.37

3.4. Scenario results

Two different scenarios are considered in this section. The first refers to the minimization of R_T with the impact acceleration constraint, while the second refers to the minimization of R_T without the impact acceleration constraint. The former is common for rescue missions where ship crews engage in life saving procedures while the latter scenario is suitable for unmanned surveillance missions where the craft need to be operated at high speeds and seasickness and personal injury caused by vertical impact acceleration is not a consideration. The percentage of resistance minimized is determined using the expression below:

$$\% \text{ of Minimized } R_T = \frac{\text{Basis Hull } R_T - \text{Optimized Hull } R_T}{\text{Basis Hull } R_T} \times 100\%$$

3.4.1. Minimization of R_T with vertical impact acceleration constraint

Results for minimization of R_T with vertical impact acceleration constraint obtained using NSGA-II, EASDS and IDEA are tabulated in Table V to VII, respectively. In the case of designing under sea state 1 conditions, all the three algorithms were able to reduce the R_T when compared with the basis hull. However at sea-state 2 ($H_{1/3} = 0.8\text{m}$) and sea-state 3 ($H_{1/3} = 1.1\text{m}$) the basis hull violated the study imposed vertical impact acceleration limit.

Table V: Minimization of R_T with I_a constraint (NSGA-II best design)

	Sea-state 1 (0.4m)		Sea-state 2 (0.6m)		Sea-state 2 (0.8m)		Sea-state 3 (1.1m)	
	Basis	Optimized	Basis	Optimized	Basis	Optimized	Basis	Optimized
<i>Disp.</i> (kg)	7204.94	7206.36	7204.94	7206.90	7204.94	7333.90	7204.94	11579.56
<i>L</i> (m)	10.04	10.87	10.04	10.99	10.04	9.10	10.04	10.99
<i>B</i> (m)	2.86	3.07	2.86	2.79	2.86	3.59	2.86	3.71
<i>T</i> (m)	0.70	0.60	0.70	0.66	0.70	0.63	0.70	0.79
<i>GM</i> (m)	2.00	2.56	2.00	2.04	2.00	3.22	2.00	2.73
R_C (N)	11547.02	9838.28	11547.02	10175.79	11547.02	11065.94	11547.02	17466.37
R_A (N)	1343.84	2081.25	1570.54	2198.95	1761.35	2348.19	1998.88	4364.30
I_a (g)	1.01	1.03	1.32	1.27	1.64	1.50	2.11	1.50
R_T (N)	12890.86	11919.53	13117.56	12374.74	13308.37	13414.13	13545.90	21830.67
Minimized R_T (%)	7.54		5.66		(-) 0.79		(-) 61.16	

Table VI: Minimization of R_T with I_a constraint (EASDS best design)

	Sea-state 1 (0.4m)		Sea-state 2 (0.6m)		Sea-state 2 (0.8m)		Sea-state 3 (1.1m)	
	Basis	Optimized	Basis	Optimized	Basis	Optimized	Basis	Optimized
<i>Disp.</i> (kg)	7204.94	7206.05	7204.94	7205.06	7204.94	7229.68	7204.94	11581.66
<i>L</i> (m)	10.04	10.99	10.04	10.98	10.04	9.21	10.04	10.99
<i>B</i> (m)	2.86	3.04	2.86	3.04	2.86	3.65	2.86	3.72
<i>T</i> (m)	0.70	0.60	0.70	0.60	0.70	0.60	0.70	0.79
<i>GM</i> (m)	2.00	2.52	2.00	2.52	2.00	3.43	2.00	2.75
R_C (N)	11547.02	9752.45	11547.02	9768.31	11547.02	10546.33	11547.02	17438.15
R_A (N)	1343.84	2088.51	1570.54	2590.41	1761.35	2561.58	1998.88	4391.37
I_a (g)	1.01	1.02	1.32	1.33	1.64	1.50	2.11	1.50
R_T (N)	12890.86	11840.96	13117.56	12358.72	13308.37	13107.91	13545.90	21829.52
Minimized R_T (%)	8.14		5.78		1.51		(-) 61.15	

Shown in Table V is an increase of 0.79% over the total resistance of the basis hull at sea-state 2 ($H_{1/3} = 0.8\text{m}$) for NSGA-II. However, Tables VI to VII show that EASDS and IDEA are able to identify a design with a lower R_T as compared to the basis hull, while satisfying the impact acceleration constraint. This highlights the efficiency of EASDS and IDEA in solving the constrained optimization problems considered here. The highest percentages in savings are presented in bold type inside the table.

For sea-state 3 ($H_{1/3} = 1.1\text{m}$), all the algorithms are able to identify designs satisfying the vertical impact acceleration constraint but with an increase in R_T as compared to the basis hull. The increase of R_T percentage is symbolized using minus sign (-) inside of the table.

Table VII: Minimization of R_T with I_a constraint (IDEA best design)

	Sea-state 1 (0.4m)		Sea-state 2 (0.6m)		Sea-state 2 (0.8m)		Sea-state 3 (1.1m)	
	Basis	Optimized	Basis	Optimized	Basis	Optimized	Basis	Optimized
$Disp.$ (kg)	7204.94	7213.11	7204.94	7213.99	7204.94	7260.53	7204.94	11572.02
L (m)	10.04	10.98	10.04	10.98	10.04	9.21	10.04	10.97
B (m)	2.86	3.03	2.86	2.82	2.86	3.65	2.86	3.72
T (m)	0.70	0.61	0.70	0.65	0.70	0.60	0.70	0.79
GM (m)	2.00	2.49	2.00	2.09	2.00	3.41	2.00	2.75
R_C (N)	11547.02	9798.61	11547.02	10151.34	11547.02	10619.00	11547.02	17462.53
R_A (N)	1343.84	2071.26	1570.54	2247.15	1761.35	2557.62	1998.88	4370.87
I_a (g)	1.01	1.02	1.32	1.28	1.64	1.50	2.11	1.50
R_T (N)	12890.86	11869.87	13117.56	12398.49	13308.37	13176.62	13545.90	21833.40
Minimized R_T (%)	7.92		5.48		0.99		(-) 61.18	

3.4.2. Minimization of R_T without vertical impact acceleration constraint

The results for minimization of R_T without vertical impact acceleration constraint using NSGA-II, EASDS and IDEA are tabulated in Table VIII to X, respectively. All three optimization algorithms are able to find candidate designs with low value of R_T while meeting the requirements for displacement and GM .

Table VIII: Minimization of R_T without I_a constraint (NSGA-II best design)

	Sea-state 1 (0.4m)		Sea-state 2 (0.6m)		Sea-state 2 (0.8m)		Sea-state 3 (1.1m)	
	Basis	Optimized	Basis	Optimized	Basis	Optimized	Basis	Optimized
$Disp.$ (kg)	7204.94	7210.96	7204.94	7206.90	7204.94	7207.41	7204.94	7206.30
L (m)	10.04	10.88	10.04	10.99	10.04	10.98	10.04	10.97
B (m)	2.86	3.07	2.86	2.79	2.86	2.80	2.86	2.81
T (m)	0.70	0.60	0.70	0.66	0.70	0.65	0.70	0.65
GM (m)	2.00	2.56	2.00	2.04	2.00	2.06	2.00	2.07
R_C (N)	11547.02	9850.25	11547.02	10175.79	11547.02	10172.77	11547.02	10166.02
R_A (N)	1343.84	2081.75	1570.54	2198.95	1761.35	2556.53	1998.88	2996.65
I_a (g)	1.01	1.03	1.32	1.27	1.64	1.58	2.11	2.05
R_T (N)	12890.86	11932.00	13117.56	12374.74	13308.37	12729.30	13545.90	13162.67
Minimized R_T (%)	7.44		5.66		4.35		2.83	

At sea-state 2 ($H_{1/3} = 0.8\text{m}$) and sea-state 3 ($H_{1/3} = 1.1\text{m}$), the basis hull has a vertical impact acceleration value larger than 1.5g. If the operating condition permits high values of vertical impact acceleration such as unmanned surveillance and ruggedized shock mounted equipment, a reduction of R_T could be realized. In sea-state 1 ($H_{1/3} = 0.4\text{m}$), NSGA-II, EASDS and IDEA result in reductions of R_T by 7.44%, 7.62% and 7.8 % respectively. For sea-state 2 ($H_{1/3} = 0.6\text{m}$), NSGA-II, EASDS and IDEA result in reductions of R_T by 5.66%, 5.78% and 5.57% respectively. For sea-state 2 ($H_{1/3} = 0.8\text{m}$), NSGA-II, EASDS and IDEA result in reductions of R_T by 4.35%, 4.47% and 4.19% respectively. Finally for sea-state 3 ($H_{1/3} = 1.1\text{m}$), NSGA-II, EASDS and IDEA result in reductions of R_T by 2.83%, 2.97% and 2.62% respectively. EASDS consistently performs better than NSGA-II and IDEA in this particular example.

Table IX: Minimization of R_T without I_a constraint (EASDS best design)

	Sea-state 1 (0.4m)		Sea-state 2 (0.6m)		Sea-state 2 (0.8m)		Sea-state 3 (1.1m)	
	Basis	Optimized	Basis	Optimized	Basis	Optimized	Basis	Optimized
$Disp.$ (kg)	7204.94	7205.29	7204.94	7205.06	7204.94	7206.40	7204.94	7205.98
L (m)	10.04	10.88	10.04	10.98	10.04	11.00	10.04	10.98
B (m)	2.86	3.08	2.86	3.04	2.86	2.80	2.86	2.79
T (m)	0.70	0.60	0.70	0.60	0.70	0.65	0.70	0.66
GM (m)	2.00	2.59	2.00	2.52	2.00	2.06	2.00	2.04
R_C (N)	11547.02	9814.42	11547.02	9768.31	11547.02	10143.50	11547.02	10189.59
R_A (N)	1343.84	2094.60	1570.54	2590.41	1761.35	2569.75	1998.88	2954.54
I_a (g)	1.01	1.03	1.32	1.33	1.64	1.58	2.11	2.04
R_T (N)	12890.86	11909.02	13117.56	12358.72	13308.37	12713.24	13545.90	13144.12
Minimized R_T (%)	7.62		5.78		4.47		2.97	

Table X: Minimization of R_T without I_a constraint (IDEA best design)

	Sea-state 1 (0.4m)		Sea-state 2 (0.6m)		Sea-state 2 (0.8m)		Sea-state 3 (1.1m)	
	Basis	Optimized	Basis	Optimized	Basis	Optimized	Basis	Optimized
$Disp.$ (kg)	7204.94	7222.10	7204.94	7209.79	7204.94	7210.17	7204.94	7207.62
L (m)	10.04	10.99	10.04	10.98	10.04	10.97	10.04	10.99
B (m)	2.86	3.04	2.86	2.80	2.86	2.83	2.86	2.84
T (m)	0.70	0.60	0.70	0.66	0.70	0.65	0.70	0.64
GM (m)	2.00	2.52	2.00	2.05	2.00	2.10	2.00	2.13
R_C (N)	11547.02	9787.54	11547.02	10190.18	11547.02	10146.15	11547.02	10081.61
R_A (N)	1343.84	2089.12	1570.54	2197.11	1761.35	2604.18	1998.88	3109.66
I_a (g)	1.01	1.02	1.32	1.28	1.64	1.59	2.11	2.06
R_T (N)	12890.86	11876.67	13117.56	12387.29	13308.37	12750.33	13545.90	13191.27
Minimized R_T (%)	7.87		5.57		4.19		2.62	

4. Summary and conclusions

A hydrodynamic optimization framework for a hard chine planing craft in seaway operations is presented in this paper. The proposed framework incorporates three evolutionary algorithms, namely NSGA-II, EASDS and IDEA. The hull form optimization problem is formulated through minimization of R_T in four sea-states, with $H_{1/3}$ of 0.4m, 0.6m, 0.8m and 1.1m with and without vertical impact acceleration constraints to illustrate scenarios for manned and unmanned missions.

The framework allows an easy integration of various analysis modules of varying fidelity. The ability to generate an optimum hull form rather than the optimum principal dimensions allows for a better estimate of performance, while at the same time providing offsets directly to support other detailed analysis and even direct construction.

The inclusion of surrogate models through EASDS allows the possibility to identify better designs for the same computational cost as highlighted in the case studies. The proposal to accelerate the rate of convergence through the use of IDEA for constrained optimization problems is also illustrated. The importance and effects of the impact acceleration constraint on manned and unmanned missions are discussed. The proposed framework being modular in nature, allows for the possibility of including other underlying optimization schemes or high fidelity multidisciplinary analysis tools to support design of hard chine planing crafts.

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Aspects of Selecting the Appropriate CAD and CFD Software

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Abstract

This paper discusses some general aspects to be considered when selecting CFD software. A German industry guideline for CAD software selection and implementation within the specific context of CFD systems in the marine industry is presented. A systematic procedure for software selection is described. At the core of the selection scheme is a trade-off between costs and benefits in the long-term; the importance of staff costs is underlined.

1. Introduction

In highly complex industries, such as modern shipbuilding, CAD (computer aided design) systems play a fundamental role in achieving and maintaining a competitive advantage. Central design systems use an assortment of simulation software to assess design alternatives. *Fach (2006)* illustrates the variety of simulation software used in the modern ship design process. This includes advanced flow simulation software grouped together under the term CFD (computational fluid dynamics).

The procedures described in this paper are neither original nor are they limited to the selection of software packages for the shipbuilding industry. Many of the recommendations are adapted from previous consulting experience and from guidelines relating to software selection in the German automotive and mechanical industry, *VDI (1990)*. However, the selected topics and examples focus on software used widely in the shipbuilding industry. The term CAD will be used in a wide sense, including the broad spectrum of all simulation software used in the design process.

2. In-house or Outsource

A key decision, to be made early on in a project, is whether the engineering task should be performed in-house or outsourced: i.e. should the work be carried out by one's own company (requiring the development or licensing of specialised software) or should the work be outsourced to specialists external to the organisation. If the engineering task is outsourced, the software selection decision is shifted to the consultant providing the service.

Since the focus of this paper lies on the software selection process, we will only briefly describe the reasoning behind outsourcing engineering tasks, in particular CFD simulations. See *Bertram (1993)* for a more detailed discussion; despite the progress in CFD systems, the fundamental economic considerations have not changed.

If CFD calculations are undertaken infrequently, there can be large savings to be made by outsourcing. This is due to the high fixed costs of hardware, software and especially training (which is often not considered at all). However, if several computations are performed annually, considerable economies of scale can be achieved: if ten computations are performed per year, the unit cost will be reduced by 80% compared with the unit cost if only a single computation is performed in the same period. This makes CFD computations for occasional, or first-time, users far more expensive than buying the service from third parties who themselves can profit from these considerable economies of scale due to frequent usage.

For the rest of this paper we shall examine how to assess the cost of in-house analysis.

3. The software selection process

The software selection task can be greatly facilitated by breaking down the analysis into small, self-contained areas containing a limited number of staff / departments. In each area of concern, “preliminary analysis” and “assessment and decision” phases will consider organizational, technical, and economic aspects of software implementation. These will be treated in more detail later in this paper.

The two main phases of this process, which will be described in some length, are:

- Primary phase: Analysis
- Secondary phase: Assessment and Decision

3.1. Primary Phase: Analysis

The selection of a software system should be based on economic and strategic aspects. It is advisable to structure the decision process by the assessment of related aspects:

- External aspects: Market situation, software product survey
- Internal aspects: Business strategy, product spectrum

While we evaluate software largely in terms of features and associated costs, it is worth contemplating the psychological effects of introducing new software. The early involvement of the eventual end users of the software will help to increase its acceptance and avoid extended disputes (in the extreme “guerrilla warfare”) during the software implementation phase. A labour force trained in the use of advanced software may be entitled to higher wages and such an effect should not be overlooked in later cost-benefit analyses.

Effective and well-designed user interfaces generally facilitate acceptance and reduce transition costs in introducing new software. *Bruce (2009)* aptly describes the problem, albeit for a different application:

“A bigger obstacle has been the interface to the user. All too frequently, GUI’s (graphical user interfaces) reflect the needs of the software developer, rather than the needs of the user. They cause user confusion and distrust which hamper adoption. The art of GUI design is maturing to a point where genuinely friendly interfaces are available.”

As a general rule, modern commercial systems, with a large user base, have better designed and more user-friendly interfaces than academic systems. During software development, the user interface can take over 80% of the effort to design and implement; academic codes, which are typically used by a small number of expert users, often lack user-friendly interfaces. This is because the focus of the software development is on the implementation of the engineering analysis and not on the user interface.

3.1.1. Defining “Where are we now?”

An analysis of one’s own company serves to prepare a profile for the desired CAD or simulation software. At this point a SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) analysis might also prove to be enlightening. For this investigation, both internal and external factors should be considered:

- Competitive position of the business
 - Current and anticipated future market share of (current and planned) products
 - State of software usage by major competitors
 - Customer pressure to introduce software systems

- Value delivery chain
 - Identify processes that have great potential for increased productivity (drawing, analyses)
 - Forward integration (interfacing/integration to structural design, piping, production)
- Work force profile
 - Activity distribution of work force (difficult to assess as staff are likely to hide true figures)
 - Staff qualification profile, training requirements, motivation, morale
- Product and service spectrum (current and planned)
 - e.g. requirement for analysis of: propeller flow; seakeeping; aerodynamics; fire; etc.
 - Standardisation of documents or services
- Current IT environment

3.1.2. Defining “Where do we want to go?”

The requirements for the CAD or simulation software system should be grouped in categories, using, for example the MoSCoW system:

- M *MUST* have.
- S *SHOULD* have if at all possible.
- C *COULD* have if it does not affect anything else.
- W *WON'T* have this time but *WOULD* like in the future.

Any system not fulfilling the “Must have” requirements can be automatically removed from the list; the remaining alternatives can be classified by how many of the other requirements they meet.

The requirements themselves can address different aspects:

- Functional requirements
 - Ability to handle industry specific geometries (free form shapes for ships)
 - Supported technical features such as analysis techniques
 - Supported import / export data formats
 - Potential for future extension (modularised software; not hardware limited; open system that allows custom integration of in-house or third-party software)
- System requirements:
 - System architecture: If the system supports parallel processing, then powerful multi-node computers can be built at quite low cost and this can provide a very effective way of increasing the processing capabilities of the system (by adding more nodes, rather than replacing the hardware).
 - Scalability
 - Operating system (this is likely to depend on the system architecture)
 - Additional software (such as pre- and post-processing tools).
- Quantitative requirements:
 - These requirements concern the amount of data to be handled by the system: processing power, short-term storage, long-term storage and working memory should all be assessed.
 - Likely requirement due to anticipated future expansion of the system should be assessed. This can be very challenging since it can be very hard to estimate how software and hardware will develop except in the quite short-term.
- Strategic requirements: CAD investments often bind a company to their selected product for more than one decade! Disregard of strategic aspects is one of the most frequent reasons for fatal decisions in IT investments. It is crucial to contemplate the following points:

- Development capacity of CAD vendor
- Economic situation (market position) of CAD vendor
- Number (present and development) of installations
- Training and after-sales service provided by the CAD vendor
- Ergonomic requirements
 - Software (user interface, help system, training, manuals/documentation, user macros, response time, system stability)
 - Hardware (screen, keyboard, desk, chair, lighting, etc.)

3.1.3. Market Analysis

A broad review of the software market should be made. A first impression of the market: the available products and their relative capabilities may be gained by visits to other users, technical brochures and websites, exhibitions, conferences, and external consultants. Obvious starting points are COMPIT (www.compit.info) for marine CAD systems and Numerical towing Tank Symposium (NuTTS) for marine CFD applications.

A review of shipbuilding-specific software is relatively easy due to the fairly small number of available software systems, see for example: *Couser (2007, 2006)* and *Bertram and Couser (2007)*. A list of available systems should be drawn up and their capabilities compared with the list of requirements. Any systems which fail to provide all of the “Must have” requirements can be eliminated at this early stage. For the remaining systems, the other requirements can, at this stage, be given a simple “yes” / “no” answer without trying to quantify the extent to which a requirement is fulfilled. This enables a coarse ranking of the alternative software systems to be made, highlighting which systems are viable and where more information is required.

3.1.4. Assessment of Economic Benefits

For a first estimate of the expected economic benefits due to the implementation of a new CAD system, a simple cost-benefit comparison may suffice. For this simple analysis, costs can be considered as global sums and the benefits considered just as reduced man hours. To be beneficial, the reduced man-hours must at least compensate for the additional costs. This conservative estimate considers only the direct costs and benefits due to the implementation of the CAD system, but neglects possible indirect benefits and savings due to reduced errors etc. For simulation software, like CFD, this simple approach does not work and the expected additional income through the ability to offer a wider scope of services must be also considered.

3.1.4.1. Economic Benefits of CAD

VDI (1990) gives a comparison of CAD versus manual work. Today, “manual” should, in most cases, be replaced by “using the existing CAD system”. However, the generic approach is still applicable: for a fixed amount of annual drawings and constant personnel costs per hour, L , for CAD or manual procedures, a minimum factor for increasing productivity from a cost point of view, $C_{p,\min}$, may be derived:

$$C_{p,\min} = \frac{L + B_c + M}{L + B_m}$$

B denotes the system operating costs per hour with the index c indicating CAD work (with the new CAD system) and the index m indicating manual work (or work with the old CAD system). M is the additional fixed costs per hour for the new system. These fixed costs include: yearly licence fees (or depreciation of initial cost over the expected period of use or before the purchase of an upgrade is re-

quired); installation, training and maintenance costs; and interest on loans (or opportunity cost on bound capital).

During formal training, the costs for each user include: the appropriate fraction of the cost of the trainer; the operating costs of the CAD system used for training; opportunity costs since the trainees cannot work productively during the training period. Where users are self-taught, the costs arise due to low user productivity during the training period. Training time and costs are frequently underestimated. Amounts suggested by vendors and other users are generally too low. In many cases several man-months are needed for staff to become fully productive using the new software. The disparity in the training costs of different systems (due to, often considerable, differences in user-friendliness, technical support and quality of training) may significantly outweigh the differences in the licence fees alone. Cheap software frequently turns out to be expensive if all costs (including training and opportunity costs) are considered.

3.1.4.2. Economic Benefits of CFD

The value of computer technologies can be classified according to time, quality and cost aspects. The main benefits of CFD in these respects are, according to *Bertram (1993)*:

- Problems solved more quickly than when using conventional approaches, due to better (direct) insight into design aspects. CFD analyses of ship hulls and appendages before final model testing are now standard practice in ship design. CFD can also help with much faster trouble shooting in cases where problems are found. For example: hydrodynamically excited vibrations as described by *Menzel et al. (2008)*.
- Improved designs through detailed analysis and / or formal optimisation, e.g. *Hochkirch and Bertram (2009)*.
- The speed of CFD now allows its applications during preliminary design. The use of CFD early in the design phase reduces the potential risk associated with the development of new ships. This is especially important when exploring niche markets for unconventional ships where the design cannot be based on previous experience, e.g. *Ziegler et al. (2006)*.
- CFD does not significantly reduce the cost of the actual design process, but it improves quality and helps with the early detection of design flaws and this can lead to significant cost savings. Within the first weeks of design, 40% to 60% of the total ship production cost is determined, *Johnson (1990)*. The costs of design modifications increase by orders of magnitudes the further into the project they are made; ideally no fundamental modifications should be made after the conceptual design phase. Achieving this goal can be greatly facilitated by the use of CFD. If CFD is employed consistently to determine the final hull form at an earlier stage, numerous decisions that influence the production costs can be made earlier in the design process, thus reducing the risk of expensive design modifications being necessary later in the project. This is especially important in the context of modern workflow methodologies (e.g. concurrent engineering and lean production).

When assessing the economic benefits of CFD, merely considering cost aspects will therefore lead to incorrect strategic decisions. We can assess the benefits of CAD by using an analogy with another computer technology: CIM (Computer-Integrated Manufacturing), aptly put by *Dietrich (1988)*:

“In other words, when taking CIM decisions, the question of ‘What will we save in the short term?’ is not the right one to ask. The real issue is rather ‘How will our operational situation develop if we do not introduce CIM?’ ”

3.2. Secondary Phase: Assessment and Decision

Areas suitable for the application of CAD (and / or CFD) may be selected considering:

- Departments / groups suited to CAD work; and
- Applications (products, processes).

An economic assessment should compare costs and benefits (benefits being savings and increased turnover). Naturally, costs are easier to quantify than benefits. However, it is necessary (and possible) to estimate most costs and savings to provide a sound basis for deciding on a CAD investment. Splitting the total costs into individual items and estimating these items separately reduces the risk of gross errors when estimating the total costs. Once costs and benefits have been (approximately) quantified, a traditional assessment of the economic aspects (profitability) based on a dynamic method (discounted cash flow) of the investment is trivial using a spreadsheet.

3.2.1. Costs Analysis

In introducing CAD systems, one should contemplate the following initial and running costs as detailed below.

Initial costs:

- Purchase of hardware and software. (Leased software contributes to running costs.)
- Physical site installation (partitioning, furniture, lighting, air-conditioning, etc.)
- Hardware installation: cables, networks
- Software selection process (staff costs, travelling costs)
- Implementation
- Initial training, including opportunity costs due to loss of productive time
- Inferior performance (until the expected productivity gain is realized)
- Installation and integration of the software system (customised set-up, macros, interfaces)
- Data input: creation of fundamental databases and libraries

Running costs:

- Consumables, energy
- Maintenance and repair and updates to hardware that may be necessary to run the updated software
- Software maintenance / updates
- Insurance
- Interest on bound capital
- Rental costs (rooms, data lines, hardware, software)
- Ongoing training, including opportunity costs due to lost productivity during training
- Staff cost (user and IT support staff)
- Data security and backup

Some of these costs may be negligible in which case they may then be omitted; this exhaustive list is intended to prevent any cost items being overlooked.

3.2.2. Benefits Analysis

Now the more difficult task of estimating the benefits must be undertaken. Information on benefits that might realistically be expected should not be based solely on the promises of software vendors, although these may sometimes supply valuable information based on their experience with other customers. The experience of other users within the same industry should be assessed and can be found in publications, personal interviews and demonstrations. Software vendors may be able to help with introductions to such users. Benchmark tests are useful to test individual systems under real conditions. These tests should be selected by users to exercise the software's capabilities using representative examples of actual products and processes.

Users should quantify (and verify with the use of benchmark tests) the expected benefit that will be provided by the software based on the following criteria:

- Modelling (for CAD: solid models, surface representation, hidden line removal, multiple view techniques, maximum number of data structure elements, etc.; for CFD: grid techniques, grid generation, turbulence modelling, cavitation modelling, free-surface technique, etc.)
- Programming (capability and user-friendliness of command language)
- Ergonomics (user-friendliness, GUI, help system)
- Additional applications for CAD systems (geometric and physical analyses, integrated NC (numerical control) module, finite element analysis (FEA) pre- and post-processing, etc.)
- Display options (export of graphics, virtual reality models, videos, etc.)
- Interfaces for data exchange (STEP, IGES, VDA-FS, etc.; compatibility with common CFD formats, e.g.: CCM+, Fluent, etc.)

While improvements in productivity due to implementation of a CAD system (in design, structural design, production scheduling, assembly, etc.) may be estimated quite reliably, improvements in quality and flexibility of workflow and capability are difficult to quantify. The following list gives some items to contemplate in this context:

- Reduced time and costs for provision of existing products / services
- Potential for increased turnover due to ability to provide new products / services (due to the extra capabilities of the software)
- Increased quality of products / services; reduced cost of quality control
- Improved product development (design)
- Greater level of detail available at concept design stage; e.g.: when bidding for tenders

There are various methods to quantify improvements in productivity for individual activities (e.g. drawing or standard CFD analyses) that allow estimation of a PIF (productivity increase factor). While the estimates for individual activities may have considerable error (or uncertainty), the average PIF, obtained as the sum of all estimates, is usually accurate enough for the estimation purposes required at this stage. The individual activities are weighted according to their frequency (time share) in the usual operation of the company.

Further points in assessing the effect of CAD on profitability are listed below:

1. CAD improves product quality for constant capacity.
2. CAD improves productivity, i.e. unless staffing levels are reduced, CAD results in extended capacity; if there is no corresponding increase in demand and staffing levels cannot or must not be reduced, CAD investments will not pay off!
3. Flexible work hours increase CAD profitability.

For a better understanding of the cost of CFD use, it is useful to take a closer look at the workflow pattern for CFD analyses:

1. Pre-processing (grid generation; specification of boundary and initial conditions; specification of control parameters for the computation)
2. Computation
3. Post-processing (results interpretation; graphical output; report preparation)

These individual steps sometimes have to be performed repeatedly, in an iterative cycle. Cost aspects will be discussed separately for each step:

1. Pre-processing:
Pre-processing requires staff that are familiar with specialist software for grid generation especially on vessel hulls. This requires at least a basic understanding of the subsequent CFD computations that will be performed. Grid generation is best performed on workstations or fast personal computers. Time and labour costs of this step are mainly determined by the user's experience and the user-friendliness of the grid generation software. Pre-processing represents the major part (40% to 80%) of the duration of most CFD projects. Staff training and software (in-house development or licences) are the main fixed costs.
2. Computation:
The computation involves almost no man-hours except for computer supervision. State-of-the-art computations employ parallel computers. The fixed costs for these hardware architectures are relatively small: for frequent (professional) users, typically less than 5% of total costs.
3. Post-processing:
Post-processing involves production and interpretation of numerical, graphical and video output from the CFD computations. The software required for the majority of post-processing tasks is relatively inexpensive and often comes as part of an integrated CFD package. High-quality, photo-realistic or interactive virtual-reality post-processing requires dedicated software and user training, but their use remains, so far, the exception in maritime applications. Post-processing also involves interpretation of results by experts and their documentation for clients. User-friendliness of post-processing software and the use of standard graphical output and report templates contribute to keeping time and cost requirements to a minimum.

4. The CFD Software Market from a Strategic Management Point of View

The CFD market is in a transitional phase from a young market to a mature market. The problems in the pioneering days of CFD software can be attributed to the special features of highly-competitive, immature markets as discussed, in a general way, by *Porter (1980)*. These features can be summarised as follows:

- Customer confusion due to contradicting statements from different providers
- Product reliability and quality problems
- Hesitant customers waiting for the next (cheaper and better) release
- Lack of standards and compatibility
- High fixed costs and low turnover for the providers, leading to high investment costs and insufficient development power

Fortunately these problems have been largely overcome. A consolidation process has reduced the number of serious suppliers to a point where stable conditions, benefiting the whole industry, appear feasible.

However, there is always the opportunity for "new players" to arrive on the scene. This is particularly true of universities who can often, relatively cheaply, develop new products (software modules) that reflect the latest technologies and are often superior to existing software in terms of functionality.

However, if companies follow the guidelines suggested in this paper, especially if they consider strategic and economic aspects, they will, almost always, decide in favour of established companies and products. The high complexity of today's software products and customer service requirements simply do not favour "cowboy" software development companies. We may thus see a trend similar to the aviation industry where, in the end, only a handful of companies will survive. In the long run, this should be rather beneficial for the industry as a whole: fewer suppliers mean more customers per supplier, i.e. more development power and the burden of development costs shared by more shoulders. It

also means that agreements on standards and data transfer between different products are easier to achieve.

Recently, the open-source CFD package OpenFOAM, has attracted a lot of attention in the maritime CFD community, *Schmode and Bertram (2009)*. In the hands of well-trained users, OpenFOAM yields good results for a variety of complex maritime flows (seakeeping with six degrees of freedom; cavitating flows around propellers; sloshing with breaking waves; etc.), see e.g. the 2009 Numerical Towing Tank Symposium, www.uni-due.de/imperia/md/content/ist/nutts_12_2009_cortona.pdf. Zero licensing fees, wide scope of applicability and access to source code for personal modification and research (that may lead to doctoral degrees) make OpenFOAM very attractive, particularly in the academic environment. Industry users, on the other hand, should take a more prosaic perspective: savings in license fees may be far less than the added costs of training. Experienced CFD users have reported (in personal communication) that it took them several months to two years to come to terms with OpenFOAM. Nevertheless, Germanischer Lloyd has decided to employ both commercial CFD software (CCM+ developed by CD-adapco) and OpenFOAM in parallel. The investment of considerable resources in a “free” software package was motivated by co-operative projects with several academic partners. However, it is fair to say that the bulk of professional consulting work continues to be based on the use of commercial software products.

5. Conclusions

A systematic approach to software selection is recommended. The outlined procedure is intended to prevent important items from being overlooked. Specifically labour cost associated with training and lack of productivity are frequently underestimated. Companies should select software based on how long training will take and how much man-time will be required for a trained user to complete a typical project. This in turn depends on user-friendliness, software user community networks, vendor support, etc. For key software, strategic considerations are important to ensure long-term support by vendors.

For professional CFD applications, labour costs are decisive. Therefore vendors should focus on faster (i.e. more automated) grid generation and post-processing.

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Optimisation of Single and Multi-Component Propulsors

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Abstract

The paper describes the optimisation of a conventional propeller and a multi-component propulsor. The last one can be used to satisfy high acoustic requirements. Both propulsors are optimised concerning efficiency and cavitation behaviour for a ship with a given resistance at a ship speed of 20 knots. As thrust-fluctuations of a single blade can cause vibration and acoustic emissions, the optimisation criteria is extended to include the minimisation of the amplitude of the unsteady blade thrust force during one revolution in the investigated wake field.

1. Introduction

Modern ships require efficient propulsors with low sensitivity to cavitation within their operation range. Up to a certain ship speed the mostly used propulsor is the conventional propeller which reaches high efficiencies, but encounters cavitation problems at high speeds. One of the most common propulsors for high ship speeds is the waterjet, with good performance characteristics at high speeds on the one hand but with a significantly decreasing efficiency at low velocities on the other hand. Kim (2006) shows typical propulsive efficiencies of the mentioned propulsors and also of super-cavitating and surface-piercing propellers. The latter two propulsors are not treated here, as they are just feasible for small ships.

Between the operational speed ranges of conventional propellers and waterjet propulsors there is a field, where multi-component-propulsors appear to be advantageous. Such a propulsor, sometimes also called pumpjet or linearjet, is called multi-component-propulsor in the present study. It consists of the four components, Figs.1 and 2: rotor, hub, duct and stator.

Fig.1: Five-bladed multi-component propulsor

Fig.2: Seven-bladed multi-component propulsor

In a certain way, a multi-component-propulsor can be treated as a combination of a conventional propeller and a waterjet. The water passes through the propulsor without being lifted to a higher level as in the case of the waterjet. Therefore the theoretically attainable efficiency of a multi-component-

propulsor should be higher than that of a waterjet. The aim is to take advantage of having the duct to achieve an increased pressure level at the rotor-position in order to avoid cavitation. Raising the pressure level inside the propulsor, increases the risk of a raised rate of bypassing flow. In this case the propulsor would not perform satisfactorily, as the mass flow rate would decrease and the intended design point cannot be reached.

Compared to the conventional propeller, the duct reduces the strength of the tip vortex and the stator helps to recover a part of the swirl energy from flow behind the rotor. These details provide good prerequisites for the design of a high-performance propulsor. As the interactions among the single components of the propulsor are quite complex, an appropriate technique has to be developed for the design of such a propulsor.

Jürgens and Heinke (2006) carried out an experimental and numerical investigation to study the effect of the design variables on the performance of the propulsor. The results show that a variation of the rotor's pitch-ratio and the hub-diameter influences the hydrodynamic properties strongly, whereas the blade-number has a secondary effect. Cavitation occurs primarily at the gap between the inside wall of the duct and the rotor blade's tip.

A design procedure for waterjet propulsors was described by *Kerwin (2006)*. The paper describes a potential theory based solver with the consideration of the inhomogeneous wake field entering the duct. The influence of the duct on the flow field around the rotor and the stator is considered by coupling the potential flow solver with an Euler code. The forces of rotor and stator are transferred to the Euler solver to simulate the effect of the accelerated flow inside the duct due to the generated thrust. A similar body-force model was included in the RANSE simulations performed here.

2. Optimisation Algorithms

Two different evolutionary algorithms are used in this study. Evolutionary algorithms apply the principle of the biological evolutionary process to mathematical problems. The optimiser generates several sets of parameters, where each set describes a propulsor design. Each design is called individual, with its chromosomes, the parameters. Evolutionary algorithms typically create several individuals at once, which have to be evaluated afterwards. Such a group of individuals, each individual standing for a certain propulsor design, is called a generation. After the designs of a generation have been evaluated, the best are selected; the chromosomes of the selected individuals are exchanged and slightly varied to prevent stagnation. With these three steps - selection, recombination and mutation - the fittest individuals survive and better individuals should be generated.

The evaluation of an individual means that the performance of a design has to be calculated and its quality regarding an objective function has to be evaluated. An objective function, which has to be defined by the designer, expresses all important design criteria and should reach a minimum value for the optimal desired propulsor. A better design will obtain a smaller value, and hence it will be preferred during the selection. Besides the single objective optimisation, where all design criteria are integrated into one objective function, some optimisation algorithms use multi-objective optimisation, where dependencies between design criteria can be identified.

The first optimisation algorithm used in the present study is the NSGAI (Non-dominated Sorting Algorithm). It is able to optimise multi-objective problems and can be applied in single and multi objective mode. In the present study, 20 generations are considered with eight individuals each.

The second algorithm applied in this study is the MAEA (Metamodel Assisted Evolutionary Algorithm). It solves single objective problems. Meta-model is a general function defined in the optimisation algorithm, which allows an estimation of the fitness of an individual, without calculating the hydrodynamic performance explicitly. The meta-model is based on the results calculated during the optimisation and relates the parameters of the evaluated individuals to the corresponding value of the objective function. Only those individuals with a promising result in the meta-model are evaluated

with the more precise flow solver. This strategy aims to minimize the number of time consuming flow calculations. The Meta-model Assisted Evolutionary Algorithm was developed at the Department of Computer Science, Chair of Algorithm Engineering TU Dortmund. The integration of the MAEA optimisation algorithm into a propulsor optimisation process is described by *Hundemer et al. (2006)*.

3. Flow Solvers

Two different solvers are used in the present study. In all optimisation processes the in-house potential theory solver *ISThydro* is included, which is a first-order 3D- panel method. The *ISThydro* solver represents the propulsor by a distribution of constant strength sources and dipoles on the panelised geometry. The strength of the sources and dipoles are to be determined during the calculation. The method can be applied to simulate steady or unsteady flow problems.

The used RANSE solver is the commercial code ANSYS-CFX, www.ansys.com. It is utilised to optimise the duct geometry and the hub of the propulsor. The SST-turbulence model is applied and a hexahedral mesh is employed for the viscous flow calculations in the study.

4. Optimisation Process

The optimisation starts with the generation of a set of design variables. Then this set is used to create the first geometry and a mesh for the numerical computation. The mesh is passed to the solver, which simulates the flow generated by the propulsor which finally leads to its hydrodynamic performance. The calculated performance data is used to estimate the objective function. For an automatic optimisation of a propulsor geometry, all these steps are combined in one optimisation process.

For a successful realisation of an optimisation process the geometry of the propulsor has to be described by an appropriate parametric model, which does not necessarily follow the common description of a propeller blade in cylinder coordinates. Such a parametric model is only valid in a certain range, in which the parameters may vary during the optimisation. This range has to be defined before starting the optimisation. The number of design variables should be kept as small as possible; otherwise the optimisation algorithm will not be able to handle the large number of design variables efficiently. Furthermore an appropriate objective function has to be defined, which represents the optimisation targets in a satisfactory way.

The propeller blade is parameterized according to *Hundemer et al. (2006)*. This can be summarised for the case of chord length as follows: The radial chord distribution can be considered as a product of two functions and a factor, which allows adjusting the blade area to a desired aspect ratio.

$$f\left(\frac{r}{R}\right) = f_1\left(\frac{r}{R}\right) \cdot f_2\left(\frac{r}{R}\right) \cdot c_1$$

f_1 is a square root function, which describes the general shape of the blade. The square root enables a round tip with a chord length reducing to zero at the tip. f_2 is a spline curve defined by its values at hub and tip and the derivation at both points. While the value of the function at the hub is set to 1, the three other values are considered as parameters. Factor c_1 scales the function so that a desired expanded blade area ratio is obtained. The radial pitch distribution is generated in a similar way. The pitch is defined by the product of a factor c_2 and B-spline curve g_1 . The points defining the spline curve are related to each other, so that a typical pitch distribution with an unloaded tip and a reduced hub loading is achieved.

$$g\left(\frac{r}{R}\right) = g_1\left(\frac{r}{R}\right) \cdot c_2$$

Factor c_2 scales the pitch distribution to obtain a desired pitch at the relative radius $r/R = 0.7$.

The propeller geometry is modified by varying the radial distribution of the chord length and the pitch while the propeller diameter, number of blades, number of revolution and skew are fixed. The profile geometry is kept also constant. The investigated propeller in this study is a seven bladed one.

The FRIENDSHIP Framework software developed by FRIENDSHIP Systems GmbH is applied for the propeller optimisation, www.friendship-systems.com. The geometry description of the propeller and its mesh are modelled parametrically within the FRIENDSHIP Framework, which also controls the optimisation algorithm. For the propeller optimisation the implemented NSGAI algorithm is used. In the present study two different propeller optimisation runs are realised. During the first propeller optimisation the objective function consists of three sub-functions. The aim of the first one is to achieve a targeted thrust, the second and the third are used to minimise cavitation and to maximise the efficiency. During the second run the multi-objective optimisation algorithm NSGAI is applied. An additional second objective function is defined to minimise the thrust amplitude of a single blade axial force during one rotation.

For the optimisation of the multi-component-propulsor MAEA algorithm is applied. An overview of the total optimisation process is given in *Steden et al. (2009)*. Geometry and mesh are generated by an in-house CAD routine. The propulsor geometry is varied by changing the parameters of all four components hub, duct rotor and stator. The geometry of rotor and stator blades and duct are varied by changing their camber line. The duct geometry in addition is changed by modifying the thickness ratio. The objective function of the multi-component-propulsor optimisation is defined in such a way, that a certain thrust has to be achieved, cavitation is minimised and efficiency is maximised.

Four propulsor geometries were developed for the same operation condition during the present study, two propellers and two multi-component-propulsors. To investigate the influence of the number of rotor blades on the unsteady behaviour of the thrust force of multi-component-propulsors, two rotor geometries were developed, one with five and one with seven blades. The number of stator blades is six for both. The rotor and the stator blades are surrounded by the duct and fixed to the hub. The design was optimised in two steps. In the first step the duct geometry was optimised under consideration of a constant radial thrust distribution in the rotor plane with the help of the RANSE solver. In the second step, the rotor and stator were optimised by means of the potential flow code for a fixed duct and hub geometry. For both steps the MAEA optimisation algorithm was used. To evaluate the calculated unsteady thrust behaviour of a single blade and the propulsor a frequency analyse was applied.

5. Results

The estimation of the unsteady behaviour of the propellers in the ship wake requires that all blades are modelled in the numerical calculation. In this case the number of the applied panels is equal to the number of panels per blade times the number of blades, as a periodic boundary condition cannot be applied. The computation time can be reduced significantly, if only one blade is resolved with a fine grid, while a coarse grid is applied to the other propeller blades. The blade with the fine grid resolution is used to calculate the forces acting on the blade. For consideration of the interaction with other blades, the accuracy of the applied coarse grid results is sufficient for the aim of the study.

Table 1: Influence of the numerical grid on the calculated thrust

		Configuration I	Configuration II	Configuration III
Fine grid:	u-direction:	20	20	20
	v-direction:	17	17	17
Coarse grid:	u-direction:	20	17	15
	v-direction:	17	15	15
Results:	Thrust:	100	99.94%	100.72%
	Thrust difference:		-0.06%	0.72%
	Calculation Time:	48 min	41 min	29 min

Before the beginning of the propeller optimisation a grid sensitivity study was made to analyse the influence of the different grid strategies on the results. So the thrust coefficient was calculated for a propeller geometry with three different grid configurations. The calculated results and applied grid resolutions are presented in Table 1. Due to the considerable reduction of calculation time (about 40 %) and the limited influence on the accuracy of the estimated thrust (less than 1%), grid configuration III was selected for the further calculations.

Fig.3: Propeller design “Optim I”

Fig.4: Propeller design “Optim II”

The optimised propeller geometries I and II are shown in Figs.3 and 4. Propeller I is optimised by employing a single criterion target function without taking into account the minimisation of the thrust amplitude of a single propeller blade. This additional criterion is considered during the optimisation of propeller II. In both cases the NSGAI optimisation algorithm is used.

Fig.5: Radial distribution of pitch ratio

Fig.6: Radial distribution of chord length ratio

Table 2: Comparison of two propeller designs

	Propeller “Optim I”	Propeller “Optim II”
Cavitation:	0.40 %	1.80 %
Efficiency:	66.3 %	63.6 %
Amplitude / Target Thrust:	35.6 %	31.6 %

The calculated radial pitch and chord length for the two propellers are shown in Figs.5 and 6. While propeller I has a relatively high blade area and a low pitch, the propeller II shows the vice versa

behaviour for both parameters. Table 2 includes the efficiency, the amplitude of blade thrust fluctuation and the calculated cavitation area, where pressure on the blade is lower than vapour pressure. The cavitation area is given in percent of the total blade area.

The comparison of the both designs shows that the reduction of thrust fluctuation can be achieved by increasing the pitch angle. The thrust fluctuation is a result of the variation of the inflow angle due to the three-dimensional wake field. A high pitch angle of the blade reduces the effect of the inflow angle fluctuation on the total angle of attack of the profile. The smaller blade area leads to higher loaded blades, as thrust remains the same for both designs. The high induced velocities by the propeller blades of the second design will reduce the influence of the fluctuation component of the inflow velocity on the total angle of attack of the profile. Therefore a reduction of the amplitude of blade thrust fluctuation should be expected. This advantage is achieved on the cost of cavitation behaviour and efficiency, see Table 2. The calculated hydrodynamic performance of both geometries is shown also in Fig.7.

Fig.7: Performance characteristics of the optimised propellers

The first optimised multi-component-propulsor geometry has a five-bladed rotor, which is shown in Fig.1. The main parameters affecting the geometry of the duct are flow rate and mean radial circulation distribution in the rotor domain. Since both multi-component-propulsor geometries are developed for the same operating point, the parameters for the duct design are identical. That allows the use of one optimised duct geometry for two rotors. Figs.8 and 9 show the mean radial thrust distribution in the rotor domain and the developed duct geometry.

Fig.8: Mean radial distribution of rotor circulation

Fig.9: Duct and hub geometry

There are many requirements to be met during the duct optimisation. Flow separation on the leading edge of the duct must be avoided and the ratio between the inlet and outlet area has to be achieved. The increase of the pressure level in the rotor domain leads automatically to an increase of the duct resistance, Fig.10. Each point in the figure shows the resistance of the duct geometry in percent of the total thrust and the corresponding pressure level inside the rotor domain. The calculated results show

that high pressure level in the rotor domain is coupled with high duct resistance. Therefore based on the aim of the design it is important to achieve an acceptable compromise between the duct resistance and pressure level in the rotor domain. In the presented case the resistance of the selected duct is less than 0.5% of the total thrust.

Fig.10: Relation between duct resistance and pressure increase in rotor domain

A comparison of the radial distribution of pitch ratio and chord length ratio for both designs is given in Figs.11 and 12. The propulsor with the five-bladed rotor shows a higher pitch distribution on almost radii range, while for the chord length the situation is contrary. The thrust oscillation for the considered wake field over 360° is calculated by quasi-steady technique. Similar numerical investigations show that quasi-steady computations overestimate the thrust oscillation in comparison to unsteady ones. However the quality of the quasi-steady results is adequate to compare two designs.

Fig.11: Radial distribution of pitch ratio for the optimised multi-component propulsors

Fig.12: Radial distribution of chord length ratio for the optimised multi-component propulsors

Fig.13 represents the thrust oscillation for a single rotor blade. The calculated results are normalised by the averaged thrust of one rotor blade. The oscillation of the total thrust is estimated by superpositioning the thrust of all rotor blades under considering the relative angular positions between the propeller blades, Fig.14. The target thrust is used to normalise the data. The comparison of the results in Figs.13 and 14 shows the similar tendency as in the propeller optimisation. The thrust oscillation of one rotor blade can be reduced by increasing the pitch. As expected, in the case of considering all rotor blades, the oscillation of the total thrust with the high number of blades is lower.

The results of the frequency analysis of both designs are included in Figs.15 and 16. The analysis is carried out by applying Fourier transformation technique. The results of single rotor blade show that the dominating orders are the first and the third one, Fig.15. Considering all rotor blades, the five-bladed design shows significantly higher amplitudes of the first order. Another advantage of the design with the seven-bladed rotor is the higher efficiency in comparison to the five-bladed configuration, see Table 3 and the open-water performance characteristics in Fig.17.

Fig.13: Thrust oscillation for single rotor blade for the optimised multi-component propulsors

Fig.14: Thrust oscillation for all rotor blades for the optimised multi-component propulsors

Fig.15: Frequency analysis for the thrust force of single rotor blade

Fig.16: Frequency analysis for the total thrust force of the rotor blades

Fig.17: Performance characteristics of the optimised multi-component propulsors

Table 3: Comparison of two multi-component-propulsor designs

	Multi-Comp. I	Multi-Comp. II
Cavitation:	0.39 %	0.0 %
Efficiency:	68.6 %	73.6 %

6. Conclusion

In comparison to a conventional propeller the design of a multi-component-propulsor is more sophisticated. The application of modern optimisation methods is necessary to achieve a design, which is able to fulfil the most important design requirements.

The drawback of applying optimisation methods is the over-proportional increase of computation effort. Due to the high number of design variables of a multi-component-propulsor, a huge quantity of designs has to be created in order to estimate the influence of design parameters on the performance of the developed geometries. Therefore it is important to combine the advantages of calculation methods for potential and for viscous flow to reduce the computation time and accelerate the optimisation.

From the hydrodynamic point of view multi-component propulsors are more efficient than propellers at a certain ship speed range and for certain applications. The employing of the duct can be helpful also for ships working in extremely shallow water because the duct protects the propeller in grounding case. Another important advantage of the employing of the duct is the expected reduction of the hydro-acoustic impact on the environment. The expected high manufacturing costs make multi-component propulsors for conventional commercial applications too expensive.

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Training Complex for Training Submarine Motion Control Skills on the Basis of Virtual Dynamic Systems

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Abstract

Problems arising during development of training aids for training submarine crews in training centres are considered in the first part of the presentation. Results of development work for tools and computer-aided technologies are covered in the second part. They make it possible to display in interactive manner the submarine control systems that were used for the development of the training facility to exercise tasks for control of modern submarine motion systems and optimization of control algorithms. This training facility may be used for both individual training of operators of submarine motion control in training centres and for optimization of control algorithms in design engineering firms.

1. Introduction

Navy has been using instructional/training aids for training of submarine crews. These aids ensure an adequate training both of single specialists and the entire crew. Many enterprises such as design bureaus, research institutes, instrument-making research-and-production concerns and training centres are usually involved in the accomplishment of this challenging task.

The main line of activities in this field consists in making by the above-mentioned enterprises of information/technical training aids represented by special-purpose and multi-purpose training facilities. Thereafter these products are supplied to the Navy Training Centre to be used for training of submarine crews. Officer personnel, junior officers and seamen being in service on a contract basis are enabled to get practical skills in maintaining the technical facilities in normal conditions of operation and in case of emergencies. The important activity includes works on mastering of modern computer technologies which are promising for further development and improvement of instructional/practical training aids for submarine crews. Computer technologies make it possible to represent the information about the submarine dynamic state in visual pictorial form that is required for high-quality training of the crew.

2. Aids for training of submarine crews

Real consoles of submarine and submarine technical facilities control (including front panels of consoles of automatic motion control systems, monitors with video frames, repeaters and tableau buttons, keyboards, etc. connected to simulators of signals generated by various systems on the basis of mathematical modelling) are normally used for training of submarine crews at Training Centres. In some cases, facilities used for displaying the information about a submarine and elements of control systems are complicated systems consisting of computers, monitors and signal simulators clustered in a local network.

The console of submarine motion control system is shown in Fig.1. The control from the console shown in Fig.1 and similar consoles is performed both by using physical controls and virtual controls, one or another type of control being displayed in video frames similar to the one shown in Fig.2.

Fig.1: Console of Submarine Motion Control System

Fig.2: Video Frame Displayed on Console of Submarine Motion Control System

3. Basic Principles of Training Complex for Training Submarine Motion Control Skills

3.1 Work of Operators of Submarine Control Systems

Submarine operators have to work in difficult conditions characterized by insufficient information support, action of extreme factors, tight limitations on time for taking of decisions. E.g., the operators are forced to assess the surrounding situation based on instrument readings and technical system indications. In some cases, the complexity of tasks to be performed, large scope of incoming data and insufficient time for taking decisions result in failure of a human operator being a “decisive element” in the decision-taking loop (since it is the operator who implements the algorithm of the on-line search for control decisions) to meet the requirements for efficient process of the on-line control of submarine motion and technical facilities operation. This situation leads to decrease in control efficiency and does not ensure an appropriate safety level as illustrated by actual submarine accidents. Therefore increased information support for operators of submarine manoeuvring control systems remains an important issue as more advanced control systems are being developed.

3.2 Virtual Dynamic Systems

With the appearance of new computer facilities and technologies, the representation of information about the state and position of submarine control systems by using virtual dynamic systems became a

feasible option to improve the training of operators of motion control systems. Virtual dynamic systems enable an integral representation of minimum information required for performing a specific task in pictorial and easy-to-understand form. They simulate input for human senses similar to those felt in reality or visualize information about ongoing processes.

The possibility to study the behaviour of one or another object by using the pictorial representation of object and environment where the processes take place in the clearest and most realistic form is an essential advantage of virtual dynamic systems. Three-dimensional representation and software tools allow the simulation of the surrounding situation in dynamics from different viewpoints of observer play an important role. The virtual dynamic systems allow keeping likeness of simulated processes to real processes taking place onboard an object and represent these processes within specified spatial and time limits. This property is essential for successful training in control, prediction of complex emergencies, development of intuition as well as for design and improvement of systems being newly developed.

The virtual dynamic systems created by means of tools available now are dedicated software products of high cost and insufficient versatility. They cannot be used for similar objects without significant modifications by highly qualified software engineers. Special tools will allow creating virtual dynamic systems in short time and at minimum expenses for systems representing the information of various purposes including research simulators for submarines.

Therefore when creating the training complex on the basis of virtual dynamic systems, the task was to develop scientific/methodological fundamentals for making tools for interactive construction of virtual dynamic systems. A block-hierarchical structure would reduce time and cost of developing full-scale training facilities for virtual submarine prototypes. Blocks contain computing algorithms for pictorial representation of the submarine state and the surrounding situation.

3.3 Software Package for Dynamic System Calculation

At present, based on the results of joint activities of V.A. Trapeznikov Institute of Control Sciences, CDB ME “Rubin” and “Aurora” Corporation Science & Production” has developed a training complex for submarine manoeuvring control with visualization elements of environment on the basis of virtual dynamic systems. The training complex shown in Fig.3 was exhibited at the International Maritime Defence Show in St. Petersburg in 2009 and aroused interest among specialists.

Fig.3: Training Complex of Manoeuvring Control System

The proposed training complex is based on the software tool package developed by the Institute of Control Sciences named after V.A.Trapeznikov (Dynamic System Calculation), *Dorri et al. (2006)*. In the course of creation of the package, its overall structure which consists of a shell executive program (development environment) and set of block-modules performing different tasks has been determined.

The type and composition of modules in use depend on the purpose of virtual dynamic system under development and customer's requirements. As a result of module construction analysis, the data structure of all-purpose block of the system and data structure of sub-systems were determined. The form and type of data flow transmitted through links were selected. The necessity for conditions to be created for automatic compilation of executive programs of blocks was shown.

The arrangement principles of software tool package for calculation of dynamic systems have been addressed including such aspects as:

1. Modes of package operation and general principle of virtual dynamic system calculation
2. Data transmission through buses
3. Vector images of blocks
4. Control of blocks and links actuation
5. Split of structure into layers
6. Group assignment and setting of block parameters
7. Running of package on several computers
8. Interaction of package with other programs
9. Connection with real equipment

Fig.4 shows fragments of operator's virtual station for manoeuvring control system made by using the software package of dynamic system calculation. The screen displays the video frames pertaining to the control of the operator consoles for submarine planes and rudders. These in turn control the submarine motion. In the left part of the video frame, the usual representation of the submarine course is kept in the form of rotating compass card with rough and fine readings. The information about rate of course change is displayed additionally. The submarine position in space with respect to list is displayed in dynamics as a submarine cross section in the upper left part of the video frame. The submarine position with respect to depth and trim is displayed in the right part of the video frame. The submarine image moves vertically along the depth scale and concurrently changes its angle of inclination depending on trim. When the submarine enters the depth stabilization zone, the precision scale is displayed. For displaying accurate current and specified values of all parameters, there is a common panel in the upper right part of the video frame. The same panel is used for entering the specified values. Using the keyboard, one can get to the line "SPECIFIED" and thereafter select a desired parameter to be changed.

Fig.4: Video Frames of Training Complex of Manoeuvring Control System,
Left: Main Video Frame, Right: Additional Video Frame

Limitations on parameters of submarine motion and angles of control surfaces are changed in a similar way.

In addition, the submarine's animated three-dimensional image is shown in Fig.5. The motion parameters of this image relative to imagined sea and bottom surfaces as well as the imagined centre of gravity are changing in compliance with those controlling actions by controls that are set using the video frame of the manoeuvring control system and master video frame shown in Fig.4 and Fig.7 respectively.

Fig.5: Representation of Spatial Motion, Left: Main Video Frame, Right: Additional Video Frame

Fig.6: Representation of Spatial Motion in Surface position, Additional Video Frame

The video frame shown in Fig.5 is meant for representation of the submarine state. This video frame contains minimum required, but still sufficiently full information about control facilities and submarine state in space. The power is given to the operator to assess the situation using the three-dimensional image shown in Fig.5 and refine the values of motion parameters by scale instruments. Fig.7 shows fragments of the master video frame for setting the submarine motion control algorithms.

Fig.7: Fragment of Master Video Frame

Fig.7 shows the submarine main controls – control surfaces, tanks and propulsor (screw propeller). By using these controls and setting the control actions in the subsystem, the tasks of submarine control can be performed both in operating and special navigation conditions and also in emergency conditions (jamming of control surfaces, flooding of pressure hull compartments, mistakes made by control system operator, etc.). Parameter indicators are specially zeroed. The images of all equipment

units are animated by using tools of the software package. A change in position of control surfaces, water levels in tanks, air pressure in bottles, opening and closing of valves and kingstons are represented in sketch form. In addition, vectors of forces acting on a submarine are shown symbolically and various numerical indicators are displayed.

Of course it is possible to turn off some screens after explanation of the essence of ongoing events, keeping in operation only those screens that are available onboard a submarine and then practise actions of operators when the information about submarine equipment units and gears is incomplete. Any wrong actions of operators can be analyzed later using more thorough simulation screens. Such training will contribute to intelligent actions of crew members in difficult control conditions and emergency situations without hampering exercises with full-scale training facilities.

A full-scale training facility could include subsystems shown in Fig.3 to 5. They would represent processes of submarine motion on a set of monitors from the point of view being of interest for different specialists, *Dorri et al. (2007)*. Using the training facility, it would be possible to enter various control and disturbance actions and observe processes in progress. Ideally, the training facility could have synthesizing and optimizing algorithms of automatic control theory in its arsenal.

For an operator, a simulated system looks like a structural diagram where links between blocks are represented graphically in the form of lines. The external view of blocks can vary in the process of simulation, making the information about the results of calculation and system state more demonstrative for the user. The results of calculation can be generated in the form of numbers, graphs, indicators, etc. In addition, the user can intervene in the system operation directly during the simulation by changing parameters of blocks and observing the results caused by these changes. The whole system of dynamic system calculation is constructed under Windows environment using C++Builder and employs service facilities that are comfortable for majority of users.

The visualization of the process of tank blowing-out and changes in compressed gas weight in bottles is developed within the software package in the visualization module of tank flooding/blowing dynamics. Values of pressure in tank and bottle, outboard pressure and water volume in tank are displayed on indicators. Processes of water intake to and discharge from the tank are represented on graphs.

Non-linear characteristics of different modules of the training complex are specified in the form of piecewise linear functions. Standard program modules have been developed for the purpose of specification of non-linear characteristics of controlled object and control facilities. Employing the matrix-editing block which output is connected to the interpolation block input the user enters a matrix that contains coordinates of piecewise linear function points.

Employing the specialized software product OpenGL the submarine three-dimensional motion has been simulated in the subsystems which simulate submarine three-dimensional motion. The forms have been developed using which dimensions, colours and other characteristics of submarine three-dimensional motion can be selected. These forms make it possible to vary and refine the data in the interactive mode and demonstrate the result on the monitor screen.

The software package is able to simulate systems represented in the form of a set of interconnected modules each of which can contain the calculation program that determines the interaction with other system modules and response to user actions. The groups of functionally related blocks can be combined in composite blocks (subsystems) which can contain their own program in addition to those contained within the subsystem of blocks. An example of visualization of such a module for control of aft planes is shown in Fig.8.

All programs of blocks are loaded from external libraries that can be modified independently of master program.

Fig.8: Visualization of Operation of Plane Control Module

The main advantages of the software package are as follows, *Dorri et al. (2005)*:

1. It is possible to provide a simple and demonstrative image representation of each system block.
2. A wide range of types of information transfer between blocks is acceptable when making models.
3. A provision is made in the package to create models and their interfaces at different visibility layers.
4. The package admits a hierarchical structure of blocks and use of complex modules on a par with simple modules.
5. The package allows specifying the logics of operation of blocks and thus simulating any logically constructed system like algorithm block diagrams and Petri nets.
6. The package has facilities to control the process and intervene in progress of the dynamic process directly from the monitor screen.
7. It is allowed that auto compilation blocks are created by designers of control systems.
8. There are facilities for visualization of control processes and behaviour of controlled objects.
9. It is possible to solve problems using fast-time scale and in real time that facilitates the use of the package for constructing the package links with real equipment of submarines.
10. It is possible to develop and check the algorithms and software for modern control systems of submarines working with real facilities in conditions of pseudo full-scale simulation.
11. It is possible to apply modern methods of control theory to development and improvement of submarine motion control systems.
12. It is possible to provide the virtual development environment for operators where the effects caused by one or another disturbance and failure in operation of equipment are clearly demonstrated.

4. Field of Application of Training Complex

The training complex can be used for optimization of control task at design institutions. The experience of working with the complex gained at CDB ME “Rubin” in the process of optimization of submarine control tasks and writing of control instructions has shown that the simulator is efficient when it is used for development and evaluation of algorithms of submarine motion control in different motion modes. Usually before developing the control instructions the optimization of submarine control is being carried out using the simulation systems that make possible the quantitative and

qualitative evaluation of successful performance of submarine control tasks in various conditions for different modes. However the visual presentation of submarine control systems is not available. This is feasible only onboard a submarine or at Training Centres. The employment of the suggested training complex makes it possible to reject expensive and large-size equipment of full-scale training facilities used in training centres.

Also the training complex can be used for individual preliminary training of operators of submarine motion control consoles before they start their training at Training Centres. At the same time the employment of the training complex as a facility of preliminary training of operators does not depreciate the importance of training at Training Centres. Quite on the contrary, such a way allows acquiring skills in control of submarine technical facilities faster. There is no doubt that final skills in motion control are to be mastered at Navy Training Centres using real consoles that simulate working places of operators of submarine control systems. Nevertheless, the training complex considerably reduces the duration of operator training and improves the quality of training because it helps trainees in deeper understanding of submarine control processes. The training complex is developed for manoeuvring control system of a specific submarine. It is possible to make a similar simulator which simulates the operation of control system of submarine technical facilities and is intended for optimization of control of submarine technical facilities, e.g. in the process of submarine diving and surfacing. On such a training complex (like on a real control console) it is possible to perform operations, e.g. blowing and flooding of tanks, and master the modes of submarine diving and surfacing. The training complex can also be employed when adjusting separate training tasks for full-scale training facilities at Training Centres, including the verification of mathematical models of submarine behaviour and operation of technical facilities in the course of delivery/acceptance of large training complexes intended for training of submarine crews. Besides, the training complex is essential for a rapid analysis of field tests which is to be conducted directly onboard the submarine and concerns the results obtained in the course of acceptance tests both of a submarine proper and various systems fitted onboard.

5. Conclusions

The training complex which can be constructed using the software package of dynamic system calculation for a maximum possible number of submarine control systems would be very useful for developing the skills of submarine personnel in control of submarine technical facilities.

An essential difference of the training complex designed for optimization of tasks of modern submarine motion control and operation of submarine technical facilities from fixed training equipment is its compact size and easy use. The training complex requires neither complicated hardware (computer system, special rooms, etc.) nor skills in programming to make some kind of changes and additions to the training complex software.

The training complex not only facilitates the writing of submarine operating instructions in effective and proper manner, but it can also be an interlink between a design institution and training centre because the real processes being represented correctly but in a simplified form will help to cope with operation of full-scale training complexes at training centres.

Modern visualization facilities make it possible to develop virtual dynamic systems which simulate on-going processes and thus clearly explain the effects caused by one or another action of operators dealing with the submarine control.

The illustrative images of consoles and training complex included in this paper give an idea about search for and advancement of ways of information representation in dynamics used for evaluation of operation of control facilities and submarine state in space.

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Ship Structural Optimization under Uncertainty

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Abstract

This article discusses the application of Genetic Algorithms to ship structural optimization and the treatment of variables with a degree of uncertainty. The variable uncertainty is included in the simulation using a Monte Carlo approach. The software ModeFrontierTM is applied in the case study for a double-hull tanker midship section design.

1. Introduction

Optimization problems are problems in which one seeks to minimize or maximize a real-valued objective function by systematically choosing the values of real or integer variables from within an allowed set, which may be subject to constraints. Many real problems present uncertainty in their variables: They are inherent to the majority of physical, chemical, biological, geographical systems, etc. Stochastic optimization methods are optimization algorithms which incorporate probabilistic (random) elements, either in the problem data (the objective function, the constraints, etc.), or in the algorithm itself (through random parameter values, random choices, etc.), or in both. The concept contrasts with the deterministic optimization methods, where the values of the objective function are assumed to be exact, and the computation is completely determined by the values sampled so far. There are many stochastic optimization techniques. We will use here Genetic Algorithms (GAs) and Monte Carlo simulation.

Our objective is to minimize the section area of a double-hull tanker ship as a measure of weight. We use classification society based rules and investigate the possibility of uncertainty in some plate thickness. The main origin of the uncertainty could be the shipbuilding process and the corrosion behavior.

2. Methodology

2.1. Genetic algorithms

Genetic Algorithms are adaptive heuristic search algorithms built on the idea of genetics, natural selection and evolution. The basic concept of GAs is designed to simulate processes in natural system necessary for evolution, specifically those that follow the principles of survival of the fittest. As such they represent an intelligent exploitation of a random search within a defined search space to solve a problem.

The selective mechanisms carry out the changes that determine the evolution of a population over the generations. Such changes can occur due to the interactions between the individuals or due to the influence of the environment on the individual. Three basic mechanisms derive from this: crossover, reproduction and mutation. They are called genetic operators and are responsible for carrying out the evolution of the algorithm. The application of these operators is preceded by a selection process of the best adapted individuals, which uses a function called the fitness function (a.k.a. adaptation function).

An implementation of a genetic algorithm begins with a random population of chromosomes, i.e. the initial population can be obtained by choosing a value for the parameters or variables of each chromosome randomly between its minimum and maximum value. Then each individual is evaluated through the objective function. The fittest individuals (with the best adaptation values) have the greatest probability of reproducing (selection). Then genetic crossover and mutation operators work on the ones selected. The new individuals replace totally or partially the previous population, thus concluding a generation.

The selection operator allows the transmission of some individuals from the current population to the next one, with greater probability for the individuals with a better performance (fitness value), and with less probability for individuals with a worse performance. Crossover operators interchange and combine characteristics of the parents during the reproduction process, allowing the next generations to inherit these characteristics. The idea is that the new descendent individuals can be better than their parents if they inherit the best characteristics of each parent. The mutation operator is designed to introduce diversity into the chromosomes of the population of the GA, in order to ensure that the optimization process does not get trapped in local optima. In addition to these, there are other factors that influence the performance of a GA, adapted to the particularities of certain classes of problems.

2.2. Monte Carlo simulation

The present study uses the Monte Carlo simulation technique to deal with uncertainty concerning variables in optimization. The Monte Carlo method is a simulation technique used to solve probabilistic problems in which the input variables have probability distributions by means of a random process and obtaining as a result the distributions of probabilities of the output variables. The random process used consists in generating random numbers to select the values of each input variable for each attempt. This process is repeated many times, obtaining many results from which one builds a probability distribution of the output variables.

A random variable X has a normal distribution, with mean μ ($-\infty < \mu < +\infty$) and variance $\sigma^2 > 0$, if there is a density function:

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{(x-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}} \quad (1)$$

The notation $X \sim N(\mu, \sigma^2)$ indicates that the random variable X has normal distribution with mean μ , and variance σ^2 .

The mean of the normal distribution is determined, making $z = (x - \mu)/\sigma$ in the following equation:

$$E(X) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{x}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{(x-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}} dx \quad (2)$$

$$E(X) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} (\mu + \sigma z) e^{-\frac{z^2}{2}} dz = \mu \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{z^2}{2}} dz + \sigma \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} z e^{-\frac{z^2}{2}} dz$$

The normal density appears when integrating the first integral, with $\mu = 0$ and $\sigma^2 = 1$, with this value being equal to one. The second integral has a zero value.

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} z e^{-\frac{z^2}{2}} dz = -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{z^2}{2}} \Big|_{-\infty}^{\infty} = 0$$

$$E(X) = \mu[1] + \sigma[0] = \mu \quad (3)$$

The variance is determined, making $z = (x - \mu)/\sigma$ in the following equations:

$$V(X) = E[(X - \mu)^2] = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (x - \mu)^2 \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{(x-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}} dx = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \sigma^2 z^2 \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{z^2}{2}} dz = \sigma^2 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{z^2}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{z^2}{2}} dz$$

$$= \sigma^2 \left[\frac{-ze^{-\frac{z^2}{2}}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \Big|_{-\infty}^{\infty} + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{z^2}{2}} dz \right] = \sigma^2 [0+1]$$

$$V(X) = \sigma^2 \tag{4}$$

Applying in the density equation an average equal to zero and variance 1, and making $Z \sim N(0,1)$, one has a standardized normal distribution.

$$\phi(z) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{z^2}{2}}, \quad -\infty < z < \infty \tag{5}$$

The corresponding distributed function is given by:

$$\phi(z) = \int_{-\infty}^z \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{u^2}{2}} du \tag{6}$$

And one can say that:

$$F(x) = \phi\left(\frac{x-\mu}{\sigma}\right) = \phi(z) \quad \text{with } Z = \frac{X-\mu}{\sigma} \tag{7}$$

For example, suppose that $X \sim N(100,4)$ and we wish to find the probability of X being less than or equal to 104; that is to say, $P(X \leq 104) = F(104)$. Standardizing the point of interest $x = 104$, we obtain:

$$z = \frac{x-\mu}{\sigma} = \frac{104-100}{2} = 2$$

$$F(104) = \phi(2) = 0.9772$$

Thus the probability of the original normal random variable X , being less or equal to 104, is equal to the probability of the standardized normal random variable being less or equal to 2. There are tables where we can find accumulated standardized normal probability values for various values of z .

3. Double Hull Tanker Midship Section

The 1978 MARPOL Protocol introduced the concept known as protective location of segregated ballast tanks. The ballast tanks (which are empty on the cargo-carrying leg of the voyage and only loaded with water ballast for the return leg) are positioned where the impact of a collision or grounding is likely to be greatest. Thus the amount of cargo spilled after such an accident will be greatly reduced. The 1983 MARPOL amendments ban the carriage of oil in the forepeak tank - the ship's most vulnerable point in the event of a collision.

In 1992 MARPOL was amended to make it mandatory for tankers of 5000 dwt and more ordered after 6 July 1993 to be fitted with double hulls, or an alternative design approved by IMO (Regulation 13F (regulation 19 in the revised Annex I which entered into force on 1 January 2007) in Annex I of MARPOL 73/78). The requirement for double hulls that applies to new tankers has also been applied to existing ships under a program that began in 1995 (Regulation 13G (regulation 20 in the revised Annex I which entered into force on 1 January 2007) in Annex I of MARPOL 73/78). All tankers would have to be converted (or taken out of service) when reaching a certain age (up to 30 years old). This measure was adopted to be phased in over a number of years because shipyard capacity is limited and it would not be possible to convert all single hulled tankers to double hulls without causing immense disruption to world trade and industry.

This paper uses as case study the midship section design of a double-hull tanker to highlight the optimization procedure considering uncertainty in some variables. Optimization can be applied in many design phases, including preliminary design and detailed design. We focus here on the structural design phase, in particular the section modulus optimization under uncertainty. We assume the ship as beam. The section modulus is directly associated with the beam strength and the geometric material distribution.

$$SM = I / y \quad (8)$$

$I [m^4]$ denotes the moment of inertia and $y [m]$ the distance from the neutral axis. The minimum and required SM following ABS (American Bureau of Shipping) rules are established in part 3, chapter 2, section 1 item 3.7.1 b as follows:

$$SM = C_1 C_2 L^2 B (C_b + 0.7) \quad (9)$$

$$C_1 = 10.75 - \left(\frac{300 - L}{100} \right)^{1.5} \quad \text{for } 90 \leq L \leq 300 \text{ m}$$

$$C_2 = 0.01$$

The required SM is calculated by:

$$SM = \frac{M_t}{f_p} = \frac{M_{sw} + M_w}{f_p} \quad (10)$$

M_t denotes the total bending moment, composed of the calm-water moment M_{sw} and the wave moment M_w . $f_p = 17.5 \text{ kN/cm}^2$. The wave moment is calculated by:

$$\begin{aligned} M_{ws} &= -k_1 C_1 L^2 B (C_b + 0.7) \times 10^{-3} \text{ Sagging Moment} \\ M_{wh} &= +k_2 C_1 L^2 B C_b \times 10^{-3} \text{ Hogging Moment} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

With $k_1 = 110$ and $k_2 = 190$.

We must also calculate the calm-water moment in hogging and sagging condition. We use the DNV (Det Norske Veritas) rules to calculate the M_{sw} moment:

$$\begin{aligned} M_{sw} &= -0.065 C_{wu} L^2 B (C_b + 0.7) \text{ (KNm) in sagging} \\ M_{sw} &= C_{wu} L^2 B (0.1225 - 0.015 C_b) \text{ (KNm) in hogging} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

$$C_{wu} = C_w \text{ for unrestricted service, with } C_w = \begin{array}{ll} 0.0792 L & \text{for } L \leq 100 \\ 10.75 - [(300-L)/100]^{3/2} & \text{for } 100 < L < 300 \\ 10.75 & \text{for } 300 \leq L \leq 350 \\ 10.75 - [(L-350)/150]^{3/2} & \text{for } L > 350 \end{array}$$

4. Case Study

To illustrate the application of optimization under uncertainty techniques, we select a ship section modulus calculation. This normally is done in a spreadsheet. Fig. 1 presents the section used as case study. The main elements selected to optimize in this case study were: bottom, double bottom, deck side hull, side and bilge thickens plates.

Fig. 1: Double Hull Tanker Midship Section

The optimization algorithm used is a single and multi objective simulated annealing (MOSA) algorithm. The main features are:

- a) Obeys boundary constraints on continuous variables
- b) Allows user defined discretization (base)
- c) Enforces user defined constraints by objective function penalization
- d) Allows concurrent evaluation of the n independent points

Fig. 2 presents the ModeFrontier™ model showing the variables, objectives and the mathematical model built in Excell™.

Fig. 2: ModeFrontier™ optimization model

The mathematical model includes eight variables and two objectives. The cost objective is represented by area (area of material or sectional material area) and the second objective represents the ratio between the calculated section modulus and the required section modulus. This indicates a safety aspect. Uncertainty was included in the eight variables with normal distribution with standard deviation of 5% in each thickness plate. The mathematical model is written in the Excell™ spreadsheet.

Genetic Algorithms are always time consuming and it was not different in this case. The model ran in a computer with 2 processors Quad-core (2.27 GHz) and took 3 hours and 10 minutes to calculate 2250 feasible models (in robust approach – which runs 10 times in uncertainty procedure) and

indicates the Pareto frontier with 42 designs. Fig. 3 shows the Pareto frontier for mean inertia and mean area ratio. Fig. 4 shows the bottom and deck thickness relation for all feasible designs. The selected designs in the Pareto frontier are indicated in green.

Fig 3: Mean Inertia and mean area Pareto frontier

Fig 4: Mean Deck thickness and mean bottom thickness

Deb (2001) highlights the necessity to find a unique solution in almost all engineering and practical problems. The Pareto frontier was extracted from the feasible designs, Fig. 5. As a typical multi-objective problem, the increase in safety (mean ratio) means an increase in mean material area. The decision maker must select the best design and other aspects should also be considered. *Deb (2001)* called this phase as “Choose one of the obtained solutions using higher-level qualitative information”.

To illustrate the final process, Fig. 5 highlights four designs. Design 1 shows the lowest ratio and also the minimum mean area. This can be established as the most “optimistic” design. Design 4 in the other hand presents the highest safety aspect but also the most expensive. Design 2 is a good choice with 50% of “safety factor” and a very low mean area.

Design 3 with 5% more area (17000 to 18000) increases the “safety factor” from 50% to 100%. Also increasing the area after the point indicated by design 3 does not indicate a substantial gain in the “safety factor”. Table I presents the main elements of designs 2 and 3.

Fig 5: Feasible designs in Pareto Frontier

Table I: Main Elements with mean, maximum and minimum values

DESIGN ID (42 Feasible Designs in Pareto Frontier)	2186	2014
Long. Bulkhead Max	13	12
Long. Bulkhead Mean	12	11
Long. Bulkhead Min	11	10
Long. Bulkhead STDEV	1	0
Bilge.Max	15	13
Bilge.Mean	14	11
Bilge.Min	13	10
Bilge.STDEV	1	1
Deck Plate Max	22	32
Deck Plate Mean	20	30
Deck Plate Min	18	26
Deck Plate STDEV	1	2
Bottom Plate Max	13	13
Bottom Plate Mean	12	12
Bottom Plate Min	11	11
Bottom Plate STDEV	1	1
Double Bottom Plate Max	5	6
Double Bottom Plate Mean	5	6
Double Bottom Plate Min	4	6
Double Bottom Plate STDEV	0	0
Side Plate Max	14	17
Side Plate Mean	12	16
Side Plate Min	11	14
Side Plate STDEV	1	1
Double Side Plate Max	10	11
Double Side Plate Mean	10	10
Double Side Plate Min	9	9
Double Side Plate STDEV	0	1

Centre Girder.Max	29	28
Centre Girder.Mean	27	26
Centre Girder.Min	25	24
Centre Girder.STDV	1	1
area.Max	16736	18912
area.Mean	16534	18617
area.Min	16034	18136
area.STDEV	242	309
ratio.Max	1,53	2,12
ratio.Mean	1,46	2,00
ratio.Min	1,34	1,77
ratio.STDEV	0,06	0,26

5. Conclusion

The method presented here indicates the possibility to handle optimization problems where uncertainty should be attributed to any variable. The Monte Carlo method associated with genetic algorithms, as optimization procedures, worked well to solve the mathematical model with uncertainty.

The problem we faced was the time consumed using a common computer with duo core processor. The application for a section modulus calculation although simple, highlights the main methodology appliance. Naval Architecture designer can expect an interval of confidence for his section modulus and also evaluate the hull resistance characteristic in a risk approach.

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Multi-criterion Scantling Optimisation of Passenger Ships

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Abstract

In the scantling design of a passenger ship, minimum production cost, minimum weight and maximum moment of inertia (stiffness) are conflicting objectives. For that purpose, recent improvements were made to the LBR-5 software (French acronym of “Stiffened Panels Software”, version 5.0) to optimize the scantling of ship sections by considering production cost, weight and moment of inertia in the optimisation objective function. A real multi-criterion optimisation of a passenger ship is presented in this paper. Results highlight that LBR-5 is competitive software to optimise scantling of ships at very early design stage with management of critical problems studied normally at a later step of the design.

1. Introduction

1.1 Outline

Sustainability of technologies has been the central focus of many international debates, seminars and forums. Designing for sustainability requires the consideration of social, economical and environmental factors throughout the product life. The Life Cycle Performance (LCP) as a measure of sustainability and competitiveness covers a number of key aspects, such as Life Cycle Cost (LCC), environmental friendliness, end-of-life impacts or safety.

In the early stages of design and development all technical and ecological requirements have to be considered in terms of their long-term impacts on the entire ship life cycle. An engineering design should not only transform a need into a description of a product but should ensure the design compatibility with related physical and functional requirements. Therefore it should take into account the life of the product as measured by its performance, effectiveness, producibility, reliability, maintainability, supportability, quality, recyclability, and cost.

Life cycle optimisation – in a sense selecting the right design options on ship and system levels – is poorly applied. Methods and tools are needed, which connect technical design parameters to life cycle performance, allowing technical experts to quickly assess the impact of design options and parameters on the overall ship performance. An integrated view requires dedicated methods to compare production and operational costs, safety and environmental aspects as well as tools for life cycle optimisation in the different design and production phases of a ship. The closer inter-dependencies between design, life cycle performance and fabrication techniques have been highlighted in a lot of papers *Borzecki et al. (2003)*, *Bruce et al. (2006)*, *Caprace et al. (2009)*. These interactions are bidirectional:

- Construction cost and manufacturing conditions are to a large extent defined in early design phases. It is therefore important that the designer is provided with methods and tools which enable him to sufficiently consider design alternatives, cost aspects, new fabrication technologies and materials in his work.
- Manufacturing quality, imperfections and accuracy have a significant impact on structural performance, repair and maintenance and life cycle cost.

Nowadays, market drivers induce permanent innovation through better designs and more efficient fabrication techniques. Fuel costs force better hydrodynamics efficiency, harbour environmental concerns force lower slow-speed propeller wash, navigational constraints force better manoeuvring and control systems, steel cost force better optimisation of the hull structures, etc.

Though a holistic approach to the ship design problem appears theoretically well established, it remains for the researchers and engineers to develop and implement a long list of applications, addressing the complex problem of ship design for life-cycle. This is a long term task of decades, requiring profound skills and understanding of the physics, technology and design of ships, a clear domain of properly trained naval architects. This paper deals with the development of scantling optimisation software (LBR-5) integrating different life aspects of ships.

1.2 The scantling optimisation

To be attractive for shipyards, scantling optimisation has to be performed at the preliminary design stage. It is indeed the most relevant period to assess the construction cost, to compare fabrication sequences and, to find the best frame/stiffener spacing's and most suitable scantlings to minimize the life cycle cost of ships.

In the scantling design of a passenger ship, minimum production cost, minimum weight and maximum moment of inertia (stiffness) are conflicting objectives. For that purpose, recent improvements were made to the LBR-5 software (French acronym of "Stiffened Panels Software", version 5.0) to optimize the scantling of ship sections by considering production cost, weight and moment of inertia in the optimisation objective function.

A new module has been recently integrated to improve the quality of the optimised scantling solution. This module allows the optimisation of several sub-sections of the ship simultaneously (not only the amidships section).

A real multi-criterion optimisation of a passenger ship is presented in this paper. Results highlight that LBR-5 is competitive software to optimise scantling of ships at very early design stage with management of critical problems studied normally at a later step of the design.

2 Overview of optimisation problem

2.1 Introduction

What is the primary objective of a shipyard? As every business school in the world has taught us, the primary goal is to maximize free cash flow to investors. The free cash flow is primarily driven by profit, so that the first objective of the shipyard becomes to increase profit by reducing the production cost. Many people may argue that safety, ship performance, and delivery should be the shipyard's main goals. No doubt these are important goals. However, these are simply important requirements that must be met. Minimising life cycle cost should be the goal. The ship design is a complex multidimensional space. Safety, quality, environmental, productibility, and other product attributes are constraints that must be met to some target level in order for the ship to be viable in the market.

Because the ship design is a non-linear complex space, there are multiple regions of localized minimum for LCC. Some of these targets are blocked by the constraints. Within a holistic ship design optimisation we need to mathematically understand exhaustive multi-objective and multi-constrained optimisation procedures. Optimisation problems and their basic elements may be defined as the following:

- **Design variables** – This refers to a list of parameters characterizing the design being optimized; for ship design this includes ship's main dimensions, unless specified by the ship owner's requirements and may be extended to include a ship's hull form, arrangement of spaces, structural elements and networking elements (piping, electrical, etc), depending on the availability of the input data.
- **Design objective function** – A function associated with an optimisation problem which determines how good a solution is, for instance, the total Life Cycle Cost of a ship.

- **Design constraints** – This mainly refers to a list of limits mathematically defined in order to keep a feasible solution at the end of the optimisation process. Basically these limits result from regulatory frameworks related to safety (stability limit, yield stress of steel, etc.) and may be expanded by the cost of materials (for ships: cost of steel, fuel, labour) and other case specific constraints.
- **Optimal solution** – A feasible solution that minimizes (or maximizes, if that is the goal) the objective function is called an optimal solution. For multi-criteria optimisation problems, optimal design solutions are called Pareto front and may be selected on the basis of trade-offs by the decision maker.

2.2 Single Criterion Problem

The following overview is adapted directly from *Parsons and Scott (2004)*. The single criterion optimisation problem is usually formulated as

$$\min_{\mathbf{x}} F(\mathbf{x}) = F_1(\mathbf{x}), \quad \mathbf{x} = [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N]^T$$

subject to the equality and inequality constraints

$$\begin{aligned} h_i(\mathbf{x}) &= 0, i = 1, \dots, I \\ g_j(\mathbf{x}) &\geq 0, j = 1, \dots, J \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where there is a single optimisation criterion or objective function $F_1(\mathbf{x})$ that depends on the N unknown design independent variables in the vector \mathbf{x} . For a practical engineering solution, the problem is usually subject to I equality constraints and J inequality constraints $h_i(\mathbf{x})$ and $g_j(\mathbf{x})$, respectively, that also depend on the design variables in the vector \mathbf{x} . The minimization form is general because a maximization problem can be solved by minimizing the negative or the inverse of the cost function.

2.3 Multi-criterion Optimisation

The multi-criterion optimisation problem involves $K > 1$ criteria and can be formulated as

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\mathbf{x}} F(\mathbf{x}) &= [F_1(\mathbf{x}), F_2(\mathbf{x}), \dots, F_K(\mathbf{x})], \\ \mathbf{x} &= [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N]^T \end{aligned}$$

subject to equality and inequality constraints

$$\begin{aligned} h_i(\mathbf{x}) &= 0, i = 1, \dots, I \\ g_j(\mathbf{x}) &\geq 0, j = 1, \dots, J \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where there are now K multiple optimisation criteria $F_1(\mathbf{x})$ through $F_K(\mathbf{x})$ and each depends on the N unknown design variables in the vector \mathbf{x} . The overall objective function F is now a vector. In general, this problem has no single solution due to conflicts that exist among the K criteria.

2.4 Pareto Optimum Front

When conflicting multiple criteria are present, the most common definition of an optimum is Pareto optimality. This was first articulated by the Italian-French economist V. Pareto in 1906. This is also referred to today as Edgeworth-Pareto optimality: A solution is Pareto optimal if it satisfies the constraints and is such that no criterion can be further improved without causing at least one of the other criteria to decline. This emphasizes the conflicting or competitive interaction among the criteria. These definitions typically result in a set of optimal solutions rather than a single unique solution. A design team, of course, typically seeks a single result that can be implemented in the design. This result should be an effective compromise or trade-off among the conflicting criteria. Often this can be reached by considering factors not able to be included in the optimisation model.

2.5 Global Criterion Optima

Engineering design requires a specific result for implementation, not a set of solutions as provided by the Pareto optimal set. The more intuitive ways to achieve an effective compromise among competing criteria are, among others, the weighted sum, the min-max and the nearest to the utopian solutions. These solutions can be found through the global criteria:

$$P[F_k(\mathbf{x})] = \left\{ \sum_{k=1}^K \left[w_k \left| \frac{F_k(\mathbf{x}) - F_k^0}{F_k^0} \right|^\rho \right] \right\}^{1/\rho},$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^K w_k = 1 \quad (3)$$

F_k^0 is the value of the criterion F_k obtained when that criterion is the single criterion used in the optimisation - the best that can be achieved with that criterion considered alone. The scalar preference function $P[F_k(\mathbf{x})]$ replaces $F(\mathbf{x})$ in Eq. 1 for numerical solution.

The weighted sum solution results from Eq. 3 when $\rho = 1$, whereas the nearest to the utopian solution results when $\rho = 2$ and the min-max solution when $\rho = \infty$. The numerical implementation for the min-max solution uses the equivalent of Eq. 3 with $\rho = \infty$,

$$P[F_k(\mathbf{x})] = \max_k \left[w_k \left| \frac{F_k(\mathbf{x}) - F_k^0}{F_k^0} \right| \right] \quad (4)$$

Moreover, a solution could be obtained for a number of values of ρ and then the design team could decide which solution best represents the design intent.

2.6 Mapping the Entire Pareto Front

In dealing with multi-criterion problems, it is highly desirable to be able to study the entire Pareto front. This allows the design team to consider all options that meet the Pareto optimality definition. The final design decision can then be based on the considerations modelled in the optimisation formulation as well as the many additional considerations, factors, and constraints that are not included in the model. This is practical when there are two criteria, but rapidly becomes impractical, for computational time and visualization reasons when the number of criteria increases beyond two.

To map the entire Pareto front, the three following methods can be used:

- *Repeated weighted sum solutions.* If the feasible object function space is convex, weighted sum solutions can be obtained for systematically varied weights.
- *Repeated weighted min-max solutions.* If the feasible object function space does not have a slope that exceeds w_1/w_2 , weighted min-max solutions can be obtained for systematically varied weights.
- *Multi-criterion optimisation methods.* Multi-criterion implementations of Generic Algorithms (MOGA), Evolutionary Algorithms, Particle Swarm Optimisation, etc. can obtain the entire Pareto front in one optimisation run.

3 LBR-5 software

This paper is related to the development of the optimisation software LBR-5. This tool allows the optimisation of ship structures following different objectives such as the highest inertia, least weight and/or least cost. The scantling design of ships is always defined during the earliest phases of the project. At this time, few parameters (dimensions) have been definitively fixed, and standard FEM is often unusable, particularly for design offices and modest-sized shipyards. An optimisation tool at this

stage can, thus, provide precious help to designers. This is precisely the way the LBR5 optimisation software was conceptualized, *Rigo (2001)*.

No initial preliminary sizing is required so that the engineer can directly start with an automatic research of the optimal design. It is not necessary that the initial scantlings correspond to an admissible solution although the convergence will be facilitated if the initial scantling is not too far from the feasible domain.

The main features of the software are:

- The scantling optimisation of hydraulic and naval stiffened structures
- The 3D analysis of the mechanical behaviour of the structure
- The use of all the relevant limit states of the structure (service limit states and ultimate limit states)

3.1 Scantling Design Variables

In LBR-5, a structure is modelled with stiffened plate elements, Fig. 1. For each element, nine design variables are available:

- Plate thickness.
- For longitudinal members (stiffeners, crossbars, girders, etc.),
 - web height and thickness,
 - flange width,
 - spacing between two longitudinal members.
- For transverse members (frames, transverse stiffeners, etc.),
 - web height and thickness,
 - flange width,
 - spacing between two transverse members (frames).

Fig. 1 : LBR-5 Stiffened Plate Element

3.2 The new multi-structures module

The structural module of LBR5 allows only the analysis of 2.5 D structures, obtained from the definition of a 2D model and extruded through the longitudinal direction. It is obvious that a fore and aft sections of a ship could not be analyzed and optimized together with the amidships section, but this optimisation is possible independently. The main inconvenient of an independent optimisation is that several design variables (for example the stiffeners spacing or the plate thickness of decks) that should be the same for the considered structures, may have different values at the local optimum. The multi-structures module allows to LBR-5 to optimize several structures simultaneously. The main interest is to link design variable between these structures, for example the amidships section with fore and aft section of a passenger ship. The multi-structures module optimizes simultaneous the three

sections in order to obtain compatible design variables, but only several common design variables can be taken into account. The link between the various sections is done only by design variables: new equality constraints are added between variables. There is no link about the strain or stress. In practice, the three sections are optimized independently but some design variables are linked together in order to find a realistic solution.

3.3 Multi-criterion Optimisation

Production cost, weight and moment of inertia can be used as objective function in LBR-5. They are considered simultaneously through Eq. 4 in a multi-criterion problem. The Pareto Front can be mapped in LBR-5 by using the repeated weighted sum solutions method described above.

4 Applications

4.1 Geometry and load cases

Three amidships sections of a passenger ship has been simultaneously implemented inside LBR-5. The central one has been imported from Mars2000 (scantling verification software based on Bureau Veritas rules). The sections are characterized by 14 decks, 40 m breadth and 42 m height. Fig. 2 shows the three considered sections. Based on structure symmetry, only the half structure was modelled.

Fig. 2 : Three amidships section of a cruise ship

For each section five load cases were considered in the calculation. Loads are: hydrodynamic pressures, deck loads, deadweight and bending moment. Difficulty of the modelling is to get adequate moment and shear forces in the aft and the fore ship section. Indeed shear force is a resultant force coming from the general behaviour of the ship. It is influenced by its length, weight and water pressures. If we model only a part of the ship, we do not have the same behaviour: the shear force and moment in the studied section are not the same as in reality. To solve the problem we have artificially modified the bending moment applied and the length of our model to get the adequate couple moment/shear force in the studied section.

4.2 Design Variables

Five scantling design variables were activated in each LBR-5 stiffened plate element:

- Plate thickness
- For longitudinal stiffeners,
 - web height and thickness,
 - flange width,
 - spacing between two longitudinal stiffeners.

4.3 Objective function

Production cost and least weight were the two objectives considered in this application. The production cost was calculated with an advanced cost module that takes into account a detailed shipyard database. About 60 different fabrication operations are considered, covering the different construction stages, such as girders and web-frames prefabrication, plate panels assembling, blocks pre-assembling and assembling, as well as 30 types of welding and their unitary costs, *Richir et al. (2007)*.

4.4 Constraints

The problem is strongly constrained and the adequacy of these constraints can influence greatly the solution found. Constraints used in the model can be divided into three categories: geometrical constraints, structural constraints and global constraints. Firstly geometrical constraints are used on each panel to ensure feasibility of the solution from a technical point of view. Thicknesses of the plates and of the stiffeners cannot be too different for welding reasons. Ratio between flange and web of stiffeners should also respect certain rules, etc. Secondly we need to impose structural constraints. These constraints are the most important to ensure the integrity of the ships over ages. Classical Von Mises stresses constraints are used, but also some more sophisticated as buckling and yielding constraints – of plates and stiffeners. Deflections are also important and limitations are imposed on each beam. Finally, we have also imposed a limitation to the variation of the gravity centre to avoid stability problem.

To facilitate the production equality restrictions are often added to avoid discontinuity of design variables. Panels of a same deck have normally the same thickness, stiffeners spacing's are often homogeneous, etc. Here we did not apply any equality restrictions to let a total freedom to the design engineer.

5 Results and Pareto front

The entire Pareto front was obtained using a process that altered the weights in the weighted sum solution and solved the optimisation problem for each of these problems. The resulting convex Pareto front is shown in Fig. 3. 50 points were calculated. The Pareto front was generated in about 28 hours with a laptop Pentium Dual Core 2.52 GHz and 3 Go of RAM.

The utopian point, the min-max solution ($\rho=\infty$), and the initial solution are also shown in Fig. 3. Min-

Max solution has been obtained for a weighting factor equal to 0.59 for the production cost and 0.41 for the weight. This analysis has highlighted that the initial design is relatively far from the Pareto front. Using Fig. 3, the design team is now able to choose a compromise solution from the Pareto front, by considering additional factors and constraints that are not included in the optimisation problem.

Fig. 3 : Pareto front

Table I gives the cost and steel weight savings between the min-max solution and the initial design. Note that the initial scantlings did not satisfy all structural constraints.

Table I: Cost and Steel Weight Savings

	<i>Cost Optimisation</i>	<i>Weight Optimisation]</i>	<i>Min-Max Solution</i>
	Saving (%)	Saving (%)	Saving (%)
Production cost	7.6%	4.4%	6.2%
Steel weight	3%	12.1%	6.4%

6 Conclusions

Thanks to the recent developments outlined here, the LBR-5 software allows performing multi-criterion optimisation by considering production cost and weight in the optimisation objective functions. The entire Pareto front can be mapped by using a process that randomly alters the weights in the weighted sum solution and solves the optimisation problem for each of these problems. Useful

specific compromise solutions from the Pareto front, e.g. the nearest to the utopian and min-max solutions, can be easily calculated.

Moreover, with the new multi-structures module, it is now possible to simultaneously optimise different sections of a ship guarantying the compatibility of the design variables between the different sections.

These new developments improve significantly the capacity of the software to provide optimal scantling solution at the early stage of the design process.

6 Acknowledgements

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Operator Decision Modeling in a Submarine

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Abstract

This article presents a method to model operator decision in simulations. This method allows to reason about incomplete, revisable and uncertain information: An operator has only partial information about his environment and must revise his decisions. Our method uses a non-monotonic logic, the default logic. This method has been implemented in Prolog, interfaced to a DCNS simulator framework and applied to a scenario involving two adverse submarines.

1. Introduction

Naval action simulations estimate the operational performance of warships or submarines for a given scenario. At DCNS, the simulator framework ATANOR models complex scenarios involving several platforms with combat system and equipment, *Toulgoat et al. (2009)*. In this simulator framework, the behaviour is modelled with Petri nets, *Petri (1962)*, composed of places (in Fig. 1 A,B,C,D), which model the equipment states and the transitions between these places. These transitions are activated by internal and external events. A flag determines the current place of the Petri net. Only one place is activated at the same time, it forbids the parallel functioning.

The modeling of behaviour rules with Petri nets provides automatic reactions of the combat system to a tactical situation. This is not realistic: In a tactical situation the decision of an operator is a key aspect, what can provide unexpected reactions. Moreover, a disadvantage of the modeling with Petri nets is to have to revise its implementation for any new behavior, *Ferber (1995)*.

Fig. 1: Petri net

The purpose of this work is to develop a system allowing modeling the behaviour of an operator in the performance simulations. This system has to answer several requirements:

- To be able to model the behaviour rules of this operator.
- To be able to reason with incomplete, revisable and uncertain information. Indeed, an operator only has a partial sight of his environment, and therefore must reason with uncertain and incomplete information and his decisions must be revised with the arrival of new information, *Sombé (1989)*.

- It can propose several actions for a given situation. It must choose between the different proposals, by selecting one or several actions.
- To allow the addition of new behaviour rules, without having to modify the knowledge representation and without being called into question the previous rules (unlike the Petri nets, in which the modifications are complicated).
- To be able to reason with general rules, without having to compile in a very precise way all the information. It is not necessary for the user to describe all the possibilities.

In the following, we will first present a case study and some behaviour rules. Then we present the formalization of these rules with the default logic. Finally, we present some results.

2. Case study: Submarine detection and tracking

In a scenario including two submarines, we model the decision of an “on the watch officer” in the submarine according to the events perceived on the tactical situation. For this purpose, we questioned submariners about this situation and defined behaviour rules. Here are some examples of the rules:

Rule 1: As long as the submarine has no detection, it continues a random search trajectory in its patrol area. During that process, the submarine makes successive straight sections: it goes straight ahead and sometimes it changes course. The submarine is deaf in its rear (behind the submarine, the sonar’s reception is decreased for several reasons). The manoeuvre allows checking that it is not tracked. With this manoeuvre, the submarine covers the entire zone, in order to increase its chance to detect an intruder.

Remark: It is a rule of minimal change, *Cordier and Siegel (1992)*, *Ginsberg and Smith (1987)*, *Winslett (1988)*. This rule is applied as long as the submarine has no new information.

Rule 2: If the submarine detects another submarine, the officer engages the following actions:

- Collision avoidance manoeuvre: He manoeuvres in order to have the enemy in a relative bearing (angle between the detection direction of the enemy and the submarine course) close to 150° or 210° .
- Elaboration of the solution manoeuvre: He manoeuvres in order to confirm his information about the distance, the course and the speed of the enemy.
- Bypassing of the enemy manoeuvre: When the officer is sure not to be detected, he gets closer the enemy’s rear, position in which he will not be detected.
- Tracking manoeuvre: when the submarine is in the enemy’s rear, he begins the tracking, he makes straight sections in the enemy’s rear, avoiding to be detected and keeping good information about the enemy’s kinematics.

Rule 3: If the submarine is detected when it makes one of the following manoeuvres: elaboration of the solution, bypassing of the enemy or tracking, it must escape. The officer manoeuvres in order to have the enemy in a relative bearing of 150° , by increasing his speed, aiming to make the enemy lose contact.

Rule 4: If the submarine is a diesel submarine and more than four hours passed since the last battery charge, it must rise to the surface and use the snorkel to take air from the surface and evacuates exhaust gas.

Rule 5: If the submarine loses the contact during the tracking, the officer keeps the last position of the adversary in memory. He aims at this position. If he finds it, he resumes the tracking actions (Rule 2). If after one hour he has not found him, he resumes the random search trajectory (Rule 1). During this research hour, the submarine cannot rise to the surface and use the snorkel to take air from the surface and evacuate exhaust gas (Rule 4).

Rule 6: With the MOAS sonar (Mine and Obstacle Avoidance System), the submarine can detect mines, big rocks, cliffs. The MOAS has a detection range between 1500 m and 3000 m. If the submarine detects a big rock, it changes course in order to place the rock to one side.

These rules can be in competition: At a given time, it is possible that the submarine needs to do two actions. For example, it needs to rise to the surface and use the snorkel and it also needs to continue the tracking. The system must manage these alternative choices.

3. Classic logic and its limits

The classic logics, as the mathematical logic or the propositional logic, are monotonic logics: if we add information or a formula E' to a formula E , everything which was deduced from E will be deduced from $E \cup E'$. In monotonic logic, anything deduced from a fact will always be true. This monotony property is a problem when reasoning with incomplete, uncertain and revisable information. In this case, it will be common to invalidate previously established conclusions when we will have new information or when the information will be changed.

- The classic logic does not allow reasoning about incomplete information. Let us take the rule: “Generally, birds fly”. This rule expresses incomplete information, because it does not specify to which types of birds it is applied. It is a general rule tolerating exceptions.

At first sight, we can express this type of information with first-order logic. “Generally, birds fly” will be translated by “All birds fly”.

$$\forall x, Bird(x) \rightarrow Fly(x)$$

This formulation is coherent if the only known information is "Titi is a bird".

This rule has exceptions: For example, penguins do not fly. It is then necessary to modify the rule:

$$\forall x, Bird(x) \wedge \neg Penguins(x) \rightarrow Fly(x)$$

This formulation has inconveniences. It is difficult to manage general rules containing an important number of exceptions. Furthermore, it is impossible to deduct with this rule that a bird flies if we do not establish whether it is a penguin or not.

- The classic logic does not allow reviewing the information. It does not plan to review some previously established deductions. Let us take the following rules:

“Generally, birds fly”
 “Penguins do not fly”
 “Titi is a bird”
 “Penguins are birds”

We can express these rules with the first-order logic:

$$\begin{aligned} &\forall x, Bird(x) \rightarrow Fly(x) \\ &\forall x, Penguin(x) \rightarrow \neg Fly(x) \\ &Bird(Titi) \\ &\forall x, Penguin(x) \rightarrow Bird(x) \end{aligned}$$

Knowing that birds fly and that Titi is a bird, we can deduct that “Titi flies”. But, if we know that Titi is a penguin, we conclude “Titi does not fly”.

We have two conclusions which are not consistent. The classic logic does not allow reviewing the reasoning and the conclusions. This kind of reasoning is common in artificial intelligence, as well as in the daily life.

Let us take another example, with the rule “Generally, an officer has to ensure the protection of his submarine”. If we add the information that the officer is a kamikaze, we cannot deduct that he will ensure his protection.

Moreover, we need a logic to reason about uncertain information. For example, when the submarine loses the detection of the enemy, the officer estimates its trajectory with the last position known, its course and its speed. This estimation is uncertain information, because he supposes that the enemy did not change its trajectory.

The classic logic does not allow reasoning about incomplete, uncertain and revisable information. In the case of a submarine, blind in submersion, the only information comes from the passive sonar system. This information is uncertain and incomplete, *Prouty (2007)*. The officer must be able to revise the decisions with the arrival of new information.

4. A non-monotonic logic and the default logic

A non-monotonic logic allows eliminating the monotony property of the classic logic: it means that, if a reasoning gives some conclusions with some knowledge, these conclusions could be reviewed with the addition of new knowledge. A non-monotonic logic allows taking the incomplete, revisable, uncertain information into account. It allows to revise the information and to revise the conclusions. The non-monotonic logic has a natural similarity with human reasoning: due to a lack of information or a lack of time, a person can reason with partial knowledge and revise the conclusions when he has more information. This logic is called non-monotonic because all the conclusions made with a knowledge base will not increase with the knowledge base, contrary to the monotonic logic.

The default logic, introduced by *Reiter (1980)*, is the most used model of non-monotonic logic. It was introduced as a formalism of reasoning in the absence of information. It formalizes the default reasoning: sensible conclusions can be made, in the absence of opposite proof. A default logic is defined by $\Delta = (D, W)$, W is a set of facts (formulae from the propositional logic or the first-order logic), and D , a set of defaults, (inference rules with specific content). The defaults allow handling uncertainty.

4.1. Definition: Default

A default is an expression of the form: $\frac{A(X):B(X)}{C(X)}$, where $A(X)$, $B(X)$ and $C(X)$ are formulae and X is a set of variables. $A(X)$ is the prerequisite, $B(X)$ is the justification and $C(X)$ is the consequent. Intuitively, the default $\frac{A(X):B(X)}{C(X)}$ means: if $A(X)$ is true, if it is possible that $B(X)$ is true ($B(X)$ is consistent), then $C(X)$ is true.

If $B(X) = C(X)$, the default is normal (the justification and the consequent are the same). The normal defaults mean “Allowing for exceptions, the A are B”, “Normally, the A are B”.

For example, the default $\frac{Bird(x):Fly(x)}{Fly(x)}$ means “Generally, birds fly”, or “If x is a bird, and if it is not contradictory that x flies, x flies”.

4.2. Definition: Extension

The use of defaults allows deducting more formulae from a knowledge base W . In this order, we calculate extensions, which are defined as following:

E is an extension of Δ if and only if $E = U_{i=0, \infty} E_i$, with $E_0 = W$, and for $i \geq 0$,

$$E_{i+1} = Th(E_i) \cup \left\{ C \mid \left(\frac{A : B}{C} \right) \in D, A \in E_i, \neg B \notin E_i \right\}$$

where $Th(E_i)$ is the set of theorem obtained in a monotonic way from E_i .

It is important to notice that E appears in the definition of E_{i+1} . So, we need to know E to find E_{i+1} , it is not possible to obtain the extensions with an incremental algorithm.

If we work with normal defaults, the definition of an extension is changed, we verify that $\neg B \notin E$:

E is an extension of $\Delta = (D, W)$, with D a set of normal defaults, if and even if $E = U_{i=0, \infty} E_i$ with $E_0 = W$, and for $i \geq 0$,

$$E_{i+1} = Th(E_i) \cup \left\{ B \mid \left(\frac{A : B}{B} \right) \in D, A \in E_i, \neg B \notin E_i \right\}$$

where $Th(E_i)$ is the set of theorems obtained in a monotonic way from E_i .

4.3. Example of extension calculus

Let $\Delta = (D, W)$ be a default theory with: $W = \{\forall x, Penguin(x) \rightarrow Bird(x), Penguin(Titi)\}$

$$D = \left\{ d_1 : \frac{Bird(x) : Fly(x)}{Fly(x)}, d_2 : \frac{Penguin(x) : \neg Fly(x)}{\neg Fly(x)} \right\}$$

The set of facts W means that the penguins are birds and that Titi is a penguin.

The two defaults means: d_1 : Allowing for exceptions, birds fly.
 d_2 : Allowing for exceptions, penguins do not fly.

We calculate the extensions:

- Case 1 : We apply the default d_1 to W :

$$E_0 = \{Penguin(Titi) \rightarrow Bird(Titi), Penguin(Titi), Bird(Titi)\}$$

$$E_1 = Th(E_0) \cup \left\{ Fly(Titi) \mid \frac{Bird(x) : Fly(x)}{Fly(x)} \in D, Bird(Titi) \in E_0, \neg Fly(Titi) \notin E_0 \right\}$$

The default d_1 can be applied and Fly (Titi) can be added in the extension. Next, we cannot apply the default d_2 because the justification of this default is not consistent.

Therefore, we have an extension:

$$E = Penguin(Titi) \rightarrow Bird(Titi), Penguin(Titi), Bird(Titi), Fly(Titi)$$

- Case 2 : we applied the default d_2 to W :

$$E_0 = \{Penguin(Titi) \rightarrow Bird(Titi), Penguin(Titi), Bird(Titi)\}$$

$$E_1 = Th(E_0) \cup \left\{ \neg Fly(Titi) \mid \frac{Penguin(x) : \neg Fly(x)}{\neg Fly(x)} \in D, Penguin(Titi) \in E_0, Fly(Titi) \notin E_0 \right\}$$

The default d_2 can be applied and $\neg\text{Fly}(\text{Titi})$ can be added in the extension. Next, we cannot apply the default d_1 because the justification of this default is not consistent.

Therefore, we have the following extension:

$$E = \text{Penguin}(\text{Titi}) \rightarrow \text{Bird}(\text{Titi}), \text{Penguin}(\text{Titi}), \text{Bird}(\text{Titi}), \neg\text{Fly}(\text{Titi})$$

We can see this reasoning on the following tree structure:

Fig. 2: Tree structure of solution for the extension calculus

Fig 3. Algorithm of extensions calculus

We obtain two extensions, which are contradictory. If we try to answer the question: “Does Titi fly?”, we must choose between these two extensions. We can, for example, prefer the most specific default, or establish preferences between the defaults.

We write down the default D_i : $D_i = \frac{A_i(X) : B_i(X)}{C_i(X)}$.

The extension calculus is made with the algorithm shown in Fig. 3. The “backtracking” is a general algorithm for finding all solutions to the problem; it allows to find all the extensions.

5. Rules formalization with the default logic

5.1. Consideration of time

To formalize the rules of behaviour, we used the default logic and we added a consideration of time. In fact, we have the submarine’s data at time t , and we have to deduct the submarine’s instruction at the next time $t+1$, according to the state of the submarine and the new information. This problem of consideration of time was broached by *Cordier and Siegel (1992)*. They dealt with the revision’s problem: How to keep up to date with a dynamic knowledge base (which evolves with time), how to revise the information. We need the time consideration in the definitions of the facts W and of the defaults D of the default logic $\Delta = (D, W)$.

5.2. Fact definition

The set of facts W is defined with formulae from the propositional logic or the first order logic. We use only Horn clauses. A Horn clause is a disjunction of literals; it is a formula $(l_1 \vee l_2 \vee \dots \vee l_n)$ where every l_i is a literal. A literal is a propositional variable or its negation. A Horn clause has at most one positive literal.

The Horn clauses allow us to write two types of rules:

- A Horn clause with a positive literal is written as follows: $(g \vee \neg f_1 \vee \dots \vee \neg f_k)$. This formula can also be written with an implication $(f_1 \wedge f_2 \wedge \dots \wedge f_k \rightarrow g)$, where the f_i and g are positive literals. This type of rules allows defining rules which are always true; these are classic rules of expert systems. We add the time consideration: $f_1(t) \wedge f_2(t) \wedge \dots \wedge f_k(t) \rightarrow g(t)$. Example: We formalise the rule “If the submarine has a random research trajectory, it turns with an angle between α and β ”, as follows: $random_trajectory(X_t) \rightarrow turn(X_t, (\alpha, \beta))$.
- A Horn clause with no positive literal is written as follows: $(\neg f_1 \vee \neg f_2 \vee \dots \vee \neg f_k)$. This is equivalent to: $\neg(f_1 \wedge f_2 \wedge \dots \wedge f_k)$. These rules allow defining mutual exclusions; these are the predicates which cannot be executed at the same time. We add time consideration to this formula: $\neg(f_1(t) \wedge f_2(t) \wedge \dots \wedge f_k(t))$. Example: We formalize the rule “The submarine X cannot make at the same time a random research trajectory and rise to use the snorkel” as follows: $\neg(random_trajectory(X_t) \wedge snorkel(X_t))$

5.3. Defaults definition

The defaults D are inference rules with specific content. They allow managing uncertainty. They express the fact that, if there is no contradiction to execute an action, the submarine can do it. We use here only normal defaults. They allow us to formalize rules like “If the submarine has no detection, then it makes a random research trajectory.” as follows:

$$\frac{\neg detection(X_t) : random_trajectory(X_{t+1})}{random_trajectory(X_{t+1})}$$

The formula $\neg detection(X_t)$ means “The submarine X has no detection at the time t”. This default means: “If the submarine has no detection at time t and if it can make a random research trajectory at time t+1, it makes a random research trajectory at time t+1” The defaults allow us defining rules on the general behaviour of the submarine (rise to the surface to use snorkel, collision avoidance, tracking...). Then, the set of facts allow specifying, for each behaviour, the action to realize (change course, speed, submersion) as well as the mutual exclusions between the behaviours.

5.4. Extension calculus

Extension calculus allows studying all the defaults and to retain the defaults which answer to the problem and which are consistent. Each extension is a possible solution to the problem: according to the submarine state at the time t, an extension gives a possible solution of action for the submarine at the next time t+1. The algorithm is described in Fig. 3. The normal defaults allow assuring the existence of at least one extension. Generally, we will have several extensions for the same knowledge base. We called our program NoMROD for Non-Monotonic Reasoning for Operator Decision.

5.5. Selection of an extension

After the extension calculus, we have to select among the set of extensions the one to retain for the final instruction of movement for the submarine.

We have therefore defined a select function. We attribute weight to the defaults, indicating the default’s importance. E.g. the submarine protection is ensured with the collision avoidance manoeuvre. This action will be weighted with an important weight. We find the weighting with the preferences on rules, with the non monotonic reasoning, following *Brewka (1994), Delgrande et al. (2004)*. The weights can be fixed or variable, depending of the scenario evolution. E.g. we fix a weight for the rule 4: “If the submarine is a diesel submarine and more than four hours passed since the last battery charge, it must rise to the surface, use the snorkel to take air from the surface and evacuate exhaust gas.” The weight of this rule will increase until it is executed.

We define the score of each extension, which is the sum of the defaults weight. The selected extension is the one with the maximum score. This solution is a first approach. Our future research will deal with the selection function and the way to have a general method to fix the weight and to select an extension.

5.6. Example of extension calculus:

To illustrate this formalization of rules with the default logic, let us take for example rules 1 and 4, defined in the Section 2.

We translate Rule 1 as follows: We define the time T_a which the submarine decides to change course. As long as this time is not reached, the submarine goes straight ahead. When this time is reached, it changes course. The new course is chosen randomly (e.g. a random angle between 60° and 120°).

Let T_{ds} be the time passed since the last time the submarine went near the surface and used the snorkel. We add the following rule of mutual exclusion: “The submarine cannot, at the same time, rise to the surface and use the snorkel, and make a random research trajectory.” We translate Rule 4 and this rule with the default logic $\Delta = (D,W)$.

- We define the set of facts W :
 - $w_1 : \neg (random_trajectory(X_t) \wedge snorkel(X_t))$
 - $w_2 : random_trajectory(X_t) \wedge (Tc(X_t) < Ta(X_t)) \rightarrow turn(X_{t+1}, (0,0))$.
(The predicate $turn(X_{t+1}, (0,0))$ means that the submarine goes straight ahead).
 - $w_3 : random_trajectory(X_t) \wedge (Tc(X_t) \geq Ta(X_t)) \rightarrow turn(X_{t+1}, (60,120))$.
 - $w_4 : snorkel(X_t) \rightarrow surface(X_{t+1})$.

- We define the defaults D:

$$d_1 = \frac{\neg detection(X_t) : random_trajectory(X_{t+1})}{random_trajectorynorkel(X_{t+1})}$$

$$d_2 = \frac{T_{ds}(X_t) \geq 4 : snorkel(X_{t+1})}{snorkel(X_{t+1})}$$

Suppose that we have the following information on the submarine at the time t:

- The submarine is called sm_1
- The time passed since the last time the submarine went near the surface and used the snorkel is higher than for hours: $T_{ds}(sm_{1t}) > 4$.
- The submarine has no detection: $\neg detection(sm_{1t})$
- The submarine has not reached the time fixed for the next change of course ($T_c(sm_{1t}) < T_a(sm_{1t})$)

The extensions calculus is made as following:

- Case n°1 :

We use the default d_1 :

$$E_0 = \{ \neg detection(sm_{1t}), T_{ds}(sm_{1t}) > 4, (T_c(sm_{1t}) < T_a(sm_{1t})) \}$$

$$E_1 = Th(E_0) \cup \left\{ \frac{random_trajectory(sm_{1,t+1}) / \frac{\neg detection(sm_{1t}) : random_trajectory(sm_{1,t+1})}{random_trajectory(sm_{1,t+1})} \in D,}{detection(sm_{1t}, 0) \in E_0, \neg random_trajectory(sm_{1,t+1}) \notin E_0} \right\}$$

The default d_1 can be applied and we add $random_trajectory(sm_{1,t+1})$ in the extension. Now we cannot apply the default d_2 , because we have a mutual exclusion w_1 . We have the following extension:

$$E = \{ detection(sm_{1,t}, 0), T_{ds}(sm_{1t}) > 4, (T_c(sm_{1t}) < T_a(sm_{1t})), random_trajectory(sm_{1,t+1}), turn(sm_{1,t}, (0,0)) \}$$

- Case n°2 :

We use the default d_2 :

$$E_0 = \{ \neg detection(sm_{1t}), T_{ds}(sm_{1t}) > 4, (T_c(sm_{1t}) < T_a(sm_{1t})) \}$$

$$E_1 = Th(E_0) \cup \left\{ \frac{snorkel(sm_{1,t+1}) / \frac{T_{ds}(sm_{1t}) \geq 4 : snorkel(sm_{1,t+1})}{snorkel(sm_{1,t+1})} \in D,}{T_{ds}(sm_{1t}) \geq 4 \in E_0, \neg snorkel(sm_{1,t+1}) \notin E_0} \right\}$$

$$T_{ds}(sm_{1t}) \geq 4 \in E_0, \neg snorkel(sm_{1,t+1}) \notin E_0 \}$$

The default d_2 can be applied. As previously, we cannot apply the default d_1 because we have the mutual exclusion w_1 . We have then the following extension:

$$E = \{ \neg detection(sm_{1t}), T_{ds}(sm_{1t}) > 4, (T_c(sm_{1t}) < T_a(sm_{1t})), snorkel(sm_{1,t+1}), surface(sm_{1,t+1}) \}.$$

The officer will have to choose between the two possible actions: rise to the surface to take air or make a random trajectory,

The rule of the random research trajectory (rule n°1) is a rule of minimal change: It is applied, as long as the submarine has no new information. In this example, the submarine needs to rise to the surface to take air, the officer will prefer executing this action.

5.7. Implementation with Prolog

The implementation was realized with the programming language Prolog. The Horn clauses are easily implemented with this language. Furthermore, the negation by failure allows to write more complex predicates (e.g. the mutual exclusions). The backtracking of Prolog allows to implement simply the algorithm of extension calculus.

6. Interface with the simulator framework and results

An interface has been implemented between NoMROD and the simulator framework ATANOR. ATANOR sends to NoMROD information about:

- the submarine with the behaviour rules (course, speed, submersion, position)
- the enemy submarine (detection, position, speed...).

NoMROD compiles the behaviour rules, selects an extension and sends back the instruction of course, speed and submersion to the simulator framework.

Fig. 4 shows an example of execution of NoMROD, interfaced with the simulator framework. SM1 denotes the submarine to which we apply the behaviour rules with NoMROD. SM2 denotes the enemy submarine with behaviour defined by ATANOR. The goal for the enemy submarine is to cross the patrol area without being detected. This transit is modeled with straight sections, where the course is selected to match an average course. In this scenario, the submarine SM1 makes random search trajectory, because it has no detection. When it detects the enemy, the officer makes the sequence of actions: collision avoidance, elaboration of the solution, bypassing the enemy and tracking. The trajectory evaluated at the beginning is far from the real trajectory of the submarine SM2. The manoeuvre of elaboration of the solution allows obtaining a better estimation of this trajectory.

Fig. 4: Detection and tracking of a submarine

7. Conclusion.

The default logic allowed formalizing the behaviour rules of an officer in a submarine, by handling the incomplete, uncertain and revisable information on the environment. The formalization in default logic allows writing general rules, the defaults, without having to care about rules previously established. We have just to manage the writing of the mutual exclusions between the different behaviours. Then the obtained system compiles the available information and gives all the possibilities of actions with the extensions. Our first approach to select an extension uses weights for default and selects the extension with the maximal weight. We will now work on a general method to fix these weights and to select the extension.

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Two-stage Stochastic Programming Formulation for Ship Design Optimization under Uncertainty

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Abstract

The paper presents a two-stage approach for ship design optimization under uncertainty. The uncertainties considered in the present work are related to those stochastic parameters that cannot be controlled by the designer, with emphasis on probabilistic environmental and operating conditions. In order to formulate the decision problem under uncertain environmental and operating conditions, the designer decision is partitioned into two sets. The first decision set contains the so-called first-stage variables. The latter have to be decided before the onset of any uncertain condition and, generally, have to be decided once and forever. The second decision set involves the so-called second-stage or recourse variables that may be decided once the random events have presented themselves. The aim of the present approach is to choose the first stage variables such that the sum of the first-stage cost and the expectation of the second-stage cost is minimized. The implementation of the latter decision problem reduces to a two-nested-loops minimization problem and the final solution is able to combine robustness (of the first-stage decision) with flexibility (of the second-stage decision). The uncertainties involved in the optimization process are addressed and taken in to account by means of their probabilistic distribution. The expectation of the overall cost function is assessed and taken as the optimization objective, whereas the design constraints are evaluated in the worst-case scenario. Specifically, the paper presents numerical applications to a bulk carrier conceptual design optimization, subject to uncertain operating conditions (such as fuel price, port handling rate, and round trip distance).

1. Introduction

The paper presents an approach for ship design optimization under uncertainty. Managing uncertainty represents a typical need in the context of ship design, since the operative conditions of the ship depend on a number of uncertain parameters, like payload, sea state, fuel price, etc. Under this perspective, a firm selection of usage, environmental and other external conditions (deterministic approach) may be inadequate and lead to a specialized solution, unable to satisfactorily face any onset of random events. To overcome this limitation, the optimization problem may be solved under a probabilistic standpoint. In general, the expected value and the variance of the original cost function may be used as objectives of the optimization problem, aiming at the identification of a ship configuration having satisfactory performance under a probabilistic variety of different conditions (robust solution). The drawback of this approach is a larger computational effort needed for the evaluation of expected value and variance of the cost function. In the standard robust design optimization the original (deterministic) cost function is replaced by its expectation with respect to the stochastic variation of the uncertain parameters addressed in the analysis. In addition, the standard deviation of the original (deterministic) objective can be included in the optimization, and the problem may be solved as a two-objectives minimization procedure (see, e.g., Diez and Peri, 2010). The latter standard approach gives the best solution in terms of minimum cost expectation (or standard deviation). The optimal variables set represents the best choice the designer can make, within the stochastic operating scenario considered. A limitation of the standard robust approach to optimal design is that the variables are all considered as *design-level* variables and has to be decided once and forever. There is not a differentiation between design-level and *operational-level* decisions, resulting in a single-stage decision problem, in which further operational corrections or recourses against any onset of uncertainty realization are not considered nor allowed.

To overcome the latter limitation, the formulation presented here takes advantage of the two-stage stochastic programming paradigm (see, e.g., Sahinidis, 2004). Specifically, the designer decision is

partitioned into two sets as follows. The first decision set contains the so-called *first-stage* variables. The first-stage variables have to be decided once and forever and before the onset of any uncertain condition. The second decision set contains the so-called *second-stage* or *recourse* variables that can be decided once the random events have presented themselves. Generally, the second stage variables pertain corrective measures or recourses against the actual realization of the uncertain parameters, and may be interpreted as operational-level decisions. In other words, the second stage decision problem may be seen as an operational-level decision problem following a first-stage decision and the uncertainty realization. The aim of the present approach is to choose the first stage variables such that the sum of the first-stage cost and the expectation of the second-stage cost is minimized. The implementation of the latter problem reduces to a two-nested-loops minimization problem and the final solution is able to combine the robustness of the first-stage decision with the flexibility of the second-stage decision. The drawback, again, is an increase in the computational effort due to the nesting of the two optimization problems, combined with the evaluation of the cost expectation.

The uncertainties involved in the optimization process are taken into account by means of their probabilistic distribution and the expectation of the overall cost function is assessed and taken as the only optimization objective. The design constraints are evaluated in the worst case, following a conservative approach.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents an overview on optimization problems subject to uncertainty. In Section 3, the reader is provided with the formulation of the two-stage stochastic programming algorithm for robust design optimization, whereas numerical results are given in Section 4. Section 5 presents concluding remarks on the present work. Finally, Appendix A provides an overview of the analysis tool used for the bulk carrier conceptual design.

2. Optimization under uncertainty

Depending on the application, different kind of uncertainties may be addressed. A comprehensive overview of optimization under uncertainties may be found in *Beyer and Sendhoff (2007)*, *Park et al. (2006)*, *Zang et al. (2005)*. In order to define the context of the present work, we may define an optimization problem of the type,

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{minimize w.r.t. } x \in A, & f(x, y) & \quad \text{for } y = \hat{y} \in B \\ & \text{subject to} & g_n(x, y) & \leq 0 \quad \text{for } n = 1, \dots, N \\ & \text{and to} & h_m(x, y) & = 0 \quad \text{for } m = 1, \dots, M \end{aligned}$$

where $x \in A$ is the design variables vector (which represents the designer choice), $y \in B$ is the design parameters vector (which collects those parameters independent of the designer choice, like, e.g., environmental or usage conditions defining the operating point), and $f, g_n, h_m: \mathbb{R}^k \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, are respectively the optimization objective, the inequality and equality constraints functions. In the latter problem the following uncertainties may occur (the interested reader is referred to *Diez and Peri, 2010*).

a) Uncertain design variable vector. When translating the designer choice into the “real world,” the design variables may be affected by uncertainties due to manufacturing tolerances or actuators precision. Assume a specific designer choice x^* and define $\xi \in \Xi$ the error or tolerance related to this choice.¹ Assume then ξ as a stochastic process with probability density function $p(\xi)$. The expected value of x^* is, by definition,

$$\bar{x}^* := \mu(x^* + \xi) = \int_{\Xi} (x^* + \xi) p(\xi) d\xi$$

It is apparent that, if the stochastic process ξ has zero expectation, i.e.

¹ The symbol * is used in the present formulation to denote a specific designer choice. While x represents all the possible choices in A , x^* defines a specific one.

$$\bar{\xi} := \mu(\xi) = \int_{\Xi} \xi p(\xi) d\xi = 0$$

we obtain $\bar{x}^* = x^*$. In general, the probability density function $p(\xi)$ depends on the specific designer choice x^* .

b) Uncertain environmental and usage conditions. In real life applications, environmental and operational parameters may differ from the design conditions \hat{y} (see the minimization problem above). The design parameters vector may be assumed as a stochastic process with probability density function $p(y)$ and expected value or mean

$$\bar{y} := \mu(y) = \int_B y p(y) dy$$

In this formulation, the uncertainty on the usage conditions is not related to the definition of a specific design point. Environmental and operating conditions are treated as “intrinsic” stochastic processes in the whole domain of variation B , and the designer is not requested to pick a specific design point in the usage parameters space. For this reason, we do not define an “error” in the definition of the usage conditions, preferring the present approach which identifies the environmental and operational parameters in terms of their probabilistic distributions in the whole domain of variation.

c) Uncertain evaluation of the function of interest. The evaluation of the functions of interest (objectives and constraints) may be affected by uncertainty due to inaccuracy in computing. Collect objective function and constraints in a vector $\varphi := [f, g_1, \dots, g_N, h_1, \dots, h_M]^T$, and assume the assessment of φ for a specific “deterministic” design point, $\varphi^* := \varphi(x^*, \hat{y})$, be affected by a stochastic error $\omega \in \Omega$. Accordingly, the expected value of φ^* is

$$\bar{\varphi}^* := \mu(\varphi^* + \omega) = \int_{\Omega} (\varphi^* + \omega) p(\omega) d\omega$$

In general, the probability density function of ω , $p(\omega)$, depends on φ^* and, therefore, on the design point (x^*, \hat{y}) .

Combining the above uncertainties, we may define the expected value of φ as

$$\bar{\varphi} := \mu(\varphi) = \iiint_{\Xi B \Omega} [\varphi(x^* + \xi, y) + \omega] p(\xi, y, \omega) d\xi dy d\omega \quad (1)$$

where $p(\xi, y, \omega)$ is the joint probability density function associated to ξ , y , and ω . It is apparent that $\bar{\varphi} = \bar{\varphi}(x^*)$; in other words, the expectation of φ is a function of the only designer choice. Moreover, the variance of φ with respect to the variation of ξ , y , and ω is

$$V(\varphi) := \sigma^2(\varphi) = \iiint_{\Xi B \Omega} \{[\varphi(x^* + \xi, y) + \omega] - \bar{\varphi}(x^*)\}^2 p(\xi, y, \omega) d\xi dy d\omega \quad (2)$$

resulting, again, a function of the only designer choice x^* . Equations 1 and 2 give the general framework of the present work. Specifically, in the following we will concentrate on the stochastic variation of the operating and environmental conditions, thus referring to uncertainties of the *b* type. The expectation and the standard deviation of the relevant functions reduce, in this case, to

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\varphi} &:= \mu(\varphi) = \int_B \varphi(x, y) p(y) dy \\ V(\varphi) &:= \sigma^2(\varphi) = \int_B [\varphi(x, y) - \bar{\varphi}(x)]^2 p(y) dy. \end{aligned}$$

3. Two-stage stochastic programming for robust design optimization

According to the standard two-stage stochastic programming paradigm, the designer decisions (design variables) are partitioned into two sets (the interested reader is referred to, e.g., *Sahinidis, 2004*). The *first-stage* variables are those that have to be decided before the actual realization of the uncertain parameter, and, generally, once and forever. Once the random events have presented themselves, further design or operational policy improvements can be made by properly selecting the *second-stage* or *recourse* variables. Accordingly, the second-stage variables are related to corrective measures or recourses (operational-level decisions) against the onset of the uncertain conditions. Specifically, the second stage decision problem may be interpreted as an operational-level decision problem, having as an input the first-stage decision and the uncertainty realization. Within the stochastic programming approach, the aim is that of choosing the first stage variables such that the expectation of the overall cost is minimized. Specifically, if we denote with u the first-stage variables and with w the second-stage variables (it is $x = [u, w]^T$), and with y the uncertainty related to environmental or operating conditions as introduced in the previous section, the decision problem may be formulated as

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{minimize w.r.t. } u \in U, \quad \mu[f(u, \hat{w}, y)]_{y \in B}, \quad \text{with } \hat{w} = \arg \min [f(u, w, y)]_{w \in W} \\ & \text{subject to} \quad \sup [g_n(u, \hat{w}, y)]_{y \in B} \leq 0 \quad \text{for } n=1, \dots, N \\ & \text{and to} \quad \mu[h_m(u, \hat{w}, y)]_{y \in B} = 0 \quad \text{for } m=1, \dots, M \end{aligned}$$

where $\mu[f]$ is the expectation of the overall cost function, and the constraints are evaluated in the worst case (following a conservative approach). The implementation of the latter problem reduces to a two-nested-loops minimization problem, as summarized in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Scheme of the two-stage stochastic programming algorithm for robust design optimization.

Along with the two-nested loops for the first and second stage decisions u and w , an integration scheme over the uncertainty domain is required (in order to evaluate the expectation of the overall cost). In the present work, we use a Gauss-Legendre quadrature scheme with seven abscissas along the uncertainty axis (a one-dimensional assessing of the uncertainty domain is assumed).

4. Numerical application to a bulk carrier conceptual design

In this section we provide the reader with numerical applications of the two-stage stochastic programming formulation to the optimization of a bulk carrier conceptual design subject to uncertain usage and operating conditions. Specifically, uncertain fuel price, port handling rate and round trip

distance are taken into account as independent and separate stochastic parameters, Table I. The analysis tool used for the bulk carrier conceptual design is that introduced by *Sen and Yang (1998)* and used by *Parsons and Scott (2004)*, slightly modified to take in to account the mortgage cost. Specifically, a loan model has been included in the original analysis tool. More details may be found in Appendix A.

Accordingly to the formulation presented in the previous section, the designer choice is partitioned into two sets. The optimization variables used respectively as first- and second-stage decisions are shown in Table II. As a design requirement, the maximum speed is set to 20 knots. The expectation of the unit transportation cost is taken as the only optimization objective and a particle swarm optimization algorithm (*Kennedy and Eberhart, 1995, Campana et al., 2006 and 2009*) is applied for the first- and second-stage minimization problem, Fig. 1.

Table I: Uncertainties distribution.

<i>Uncertain parameter</i>	<i>Unit</i>	<i>Distribution type</i>	<i>Lower bound</i>	<i>Upper bound</i>
Fuel price	GBP/ton	Uniform	100.00	900.00
Port handling rate	ton/day	Uniform	1,000.00	15,000.00
Round trip	nm	Uniform	5,000.00	15,000.00

Table II: Optimization variables.

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Unit</i>	<i>Decision stage</i>	<i>Lower bound</i>	<i>Upper bound</i>
Lenght	m	First	100.00	600.00
Beam	m	First	10.00	90.00
Deep	m	First	5.00	30.00
Draft	m	First	5.00	30.00
Block coefficient		First	0.50	0.90
Cruise speed	kn	Second	5.00	20.00

The idea behind the partition of the variables set is that of taking as first-stage variables all those decisions that have to be defined once and forever, like, for instance, the variables related to the architectural elements. Conversely, the second-stage or recourse set includes all those decisions that can vary upon the uncertainty realization, like, as an example, operational variables. The idea behind the two-stage approach is that the optimal second-stage or recourse variables vary significantly, depending on the uncertainty realization. The framework considered is that in which the operator is able of choosing the best operating point, depending on the specific uncertain condition; the best design is then chosen taking into account the above flexibility of the final product.

As shown in the following, the greater is the variation of the optimal second-stage decisions with respect to the stochastic parameters variation, the greater is the advantage to approach the robust design optimization task as a two-stage stochastic programming problem. Within the application presented here, we will show how the greatest advantages in using the present formulation arise when considering fuel price variations. Conversely, when considering the stochastic variations of port handling rate (per ship) and round trip distance, the advantages of the two-stage approach do not emerge. As shown in the following, this is due to the fact that, in the latter cases, the optimal second-stage decision is almost independent of the stochastic parameter. In this case the problem reduces to a standard single-stage robust optimization problem (as presented in *Diez and Peri, 2009 and 2010*).

The first example shown here deals with an optimization procedure subject to uncertain fuel price. In order to have a preliminary idea of the problem at hand, a parametric analysis is performed, showing the unit transportation cost as a function of the cruise speed (used later as a second-stage decision), for different values of the fuel price, Fig. 2. Moreover, Fig. 3 shows the optimal cruise speed as a function of the fuel price. Within the range of variation of the fuel price considered, the minimum-cost cruise speed varies (significantly) from almost 17 kn to almost 9 kn. When considering the latter variation in the optimization procedure as proposed in the scheme of Fig. 1, the transportation cost

drops and the two-stage stochastic programming paradigm is exploited. Figure 4 shows a parametric analysis for the optimal configurations obtained using a deterministic standard approach (uncertainties are assumed equal to their expectations), a standard robust approach (the variables set is not partitioned, resulting in a single-stage decision problem), and finally a two-stage approach, varying the fuel price. The benefits of approaching the problem according to the two-stage procedure are visible.

A careful discussion has to be made on the optimal first-stage variables shown in Fig. 5. As apparent, they almost coincide. This is due the fact that (i) the dependence of the cost on the fuel price is linear, and (ii) the minima of the single- and two-stage stochastic approach coincide. Sentence (i) implies that the deterministic and the single-stage stochastic solutions are the same. According to (ii), the three solutions collapse in the same point. Therefore, here the advantage of using the two-stage stochastic approach resides only in addressing the cruise speed as a second-level decision variable, chosen according to the minimum-cost criterion. In other words, while in the standard deterministic and robust approaches all the variables are chosen once and forever and can not vary upon the uncertainty realization, in the two-stage paradigm a set of variables are flexible about uncertainties and are chosen according to optimality criteria. This leads to a lower value of the overall cost expectation as shown in Fig. 4 (see also Table III).

Fig. 2: Unit transportation cost as a function of cruise speed, for different values of the fuel price.

Fig. 3: Optimal cruise speed as a function of fuel price.

Fig. 4: Unit transportation cost as a function of fuel price for optimal configurations.

Fig. 5: Non-dimensional first-stage variables for optimal configurations with uncertain fuel price.

In the second numerical example presented here, we take into account the stochastic variation of the port handling rate per ship. As in the previous case, a preliminary parametric analysis has been conducted and the results are shown in Figs. 6 and 7. It is evident how, in this case, the optimal cruise speed may be assumed constant with respect to the stochastic parameter variation. Figures 8 and 9, showing respectively the optimal configurations performances and the optimal non-dimensional first-stage variables, reveal how, in the present case, single- and two-stage approaches coincide. In the present problem, indeed, there is no need for a second stage decision, being the optimal second stage variable (cruise speed) independent of the uncertain parameter. In this case, the two-stage approach reduces to a standard single-stage robust formulation, as confirmed by the numerical results.

Fig. 6: Unit transportation cost as a function of cruise speed, for different values of port handling rate.

Fig. 7: Optimal cruise speed as a function of port handling rate.

The last example shows the result of an optimization procedure aimed at minimum transportation cost when the round trip distance is an uncertain parameter. Again, a preliminary parametric analysis has been performed and the results are shown in Figs. 10 and 11. In this case as well, the optimal cruise speed does not vary with the round trip distance. Therefore, also in this case, the two-stage approach reduces to a standard single-stage stochastic approach. According to the fact that the dependence of the transportation cost on the round trip measure is linear, the latter procedure coincides with a standard deterministic optimization where the uncertain parameter is taken equal to its expectation. Figs. 12 and 13 confirm that, for the present problem, the three approaches coincide.

Fig. 8: Unit transportation cost as a function of port handling rate for optimal configurations.

Fig. 9: Non-dimensional first-stage variables for optimal configurations (uncertain port handling rate).

Table III summarized the above results in terms of transportation cost expectation, for the different optimization approaches. The results related to coincident approaches (as emerging in the specific cases considered) are displayed with the same background colour. As already pointed out, the advantage in approaching the design optimization as a two-stage decision problem, emerges in the uncertain-fuel-price case, with sensitive variation of the optimal second-stage decision with respect to the uncertain parameter. The two-stage stochastic approach reduces to a single-stage stochastic problem for the uncertain port-handling-rate case, in which no significant variation of the optimal second-stage decision is observed. When considering uncertain round trip, deterministic, single- and second-stage stochastic approaches all coincides, due to the fact that the second-stage optimal decision is constant with respect to the stochastic parameter and the dependence of the cost on the latter parameter is linear.

Fig. 10: Unit transportation cost as function of cruise speed, for different values of round trip distance.

Fig. 11: Optimal cruise speed as a function of round trip distance.

Table III: Uncertainties distribution.

<i>Decision problem</i>	<i>Transportation cost expectation (GBP/ton)</i>		
	<i>Deterministic approach</i>	<i>Single-stage stoch. approach</i>	<i>Two-stage stoch. approach</i>
Uncertain fuel price	4.52	4.52	4.46
Uncertain port handling rate	5.58	5.46	5.46
Uncertain round trip	4.52	4.52	4.52

Fig. 12: Unit transportation cost as a function of round trip distance for optimal configurations.

Fig. 13: Non-dimensional first-stage variables for optimal configurations (uncertain round trip).

5. Concluding remarks

A formulation for two-stage stochastic programming robust optimization of ship design has been presented and applied to the conceptual design of a bulk carrier under uncertain operating conditions. The numerical results confirm that the two-stage approach can be successfully exploited if the optimal second-stage decisions vary significantly upon uncertainty realizations. In this case, the present formulation gives lower values of the overall costs expectation.

Some further remarks can be made in order to better clarify the impact of such an approach on the robust design optimization. The advantage in applying the two-stage stochastic paradigm is conditional on the dependence of the second-stage decision on the uncertainties variation. Specifically, the greater is the variation of the optimal second-stage decision with respect to the stochastic parameters variation, the greater is the advantage to approach the robust design optimization task as a two-stage stochastic programming problem. Conversely, if the optimal second-stage decision is constant with respect to the uncertainty realizations, then a standard single-stage stochastic approach is more convenient (because saving computational time).

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Appendix A: Bulk carrier conceptual design tool

In this Appendix, the bulk carrier conceptual design tool used by *Parsons and Scott (2004)* is briefly recalled. In the present work, we extend the analysis, including a loan model in order to take into account the mortgage cost.

Independent variables:

L	= length [m]
B	= beam [m]
D	= depth [m]
T	= draft [m]
C _B	= block coefficient
V _k	= cruise speed [knots]
V _{k,max}	= maximum cruise speed [knots]

Analysis tool:

capital costs = 0.2 ship cost
 ship cost = $1.3 (2,000 W_s^{0.85} + 3,500 W_o + 2,400 P^{0.8})$
 steel weight = $W_s = 0.034 L^{1.7} B^{0.7} D^{0.4} C_B^{0.5}$
 outfit weight = $W_o = L^{0.8} B^{0.6} D^{0.3} C_B^{0.1}$
 machinery weight = $W_m = 0.17 P_{max}^{0.9}$
 displacement = $1.025 L B T C_B$
 power = $P = \text{displacement}^{2/3} V_k^3 / (a + b Fn)$
 power max. = $P_{max} = \text{displacement}^{2/3} V_{k,max}^3 / (a + b Fn)$
 Froude number = $Fn = V / (gL)^{0.5}$
 Froude number max. = $Fn_{max} = V_{max} / (gL)^{0.5}$
 $V = 0.5144 V_k \text{ m/s}$
 $V_{max} = 0.5144 V_{k,max} \text{ m/s}$
 $g = 9.8065 \text{ m/s}^2$
 $a = 4,977.06 C_B^2 - 8,105.61 C_B + 4,456.51$
 $b = -10,847.2 C_B^2 + 12,817 C_B - 6,960.32$
 running costs = $40,000 \text{ DWT}^{0.3}$
 deadweight = $\text{DWT} = \text{displacement} - \text{light ship weight}$
 light ship weight = $W_s + W_o + W_m$
 voyage costs = (fuel cost + port cost) RTPA
 fuel cost = $1.05 \text{ daily consumption} * \text{sea days} * \text{fuel price}$
 daily consumption = $0.19 P / 24 / 1,000 + 0.2$
 sea days = $\text{round trip miles} / 24 V_k$
 round trip miles = $5,000 \text{ (nm)}$
 fuel price = 100 (£/t)
 port cost = $6.3 \text{ DWT}^{0.8}$
 round trips per year = $\text{RTPA} = 350 / (\text{sea days} + \text{port days})$
 port days = $2[(\text{cargo deadweight} / \text{handling rate}) + 0.5]$
 cargo deadweight = $\text{DWT} - \text{fuel carried} - \text{miscellaneous DWT}$
 fuel carried = $\text{daily consumption} (\text{sea days} + 5)$
 miscellaneous DWT = $2.0 \text{ DWT}^{0.5}$
 handling rate = $8,000 \text{ (t/day)}$
 vertical center of buoyancy = $KB = 0.53 T$
 metacentric radius = $\text{BMT} = (0.085 C_B - 0.002) B^2 / (T C_B)$
 vertical center of gravity = $KG = 1.0 + 0.52 D$

Loan model:

loan = 0.8 ship cost

rate of return = $R_r = 0.100$

rate of interest = $R_i = 0.075$

number of repayments per year = $P_y = 1$

number of years = $N_y = 20$

$$\text{annual repayment} = \frac{\text{loan} (1 + R_i/P_y)^{P_y N_y} R_i/P_y}{(1 + R_i/P_y)^{P_y N_y} - 1}$$

$$\text{net present value} = \text{capital cost} + \sum_{k=1}^{N_y} \frac{\text{voyage cost} + \text{running cost} + \text{annual repayment}}{(1 + R_r)^k}$$

annual transportation cost = net present value / N_y

annual cargo capacity = DWT * RTPA

unit transportation cost = annual transportation cost / annual cargo capacity

Constraints:

$$L/B \geq 6$$

$$L/D \leq 15$$

$$L/T \leq 19$$

$$T \leq 0.45 \text{ DWT}^{0.31}$$

$$T \leq 0.7 D + 0.7$$

$$25,000 \leq \text{DWT} \leq 500,000$$

$$F_{n_{\max}} \leq 0.32$$

$$\text{GMT} = \text{KB} + \text{BMT} - \text{KG} \geq 0.07 B$$

$$V_k \leq V_{k_{\max}}$$

Development of Ship Design Support System in Consideration of Uncertainty in Product Information

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Abstract

A higher degree of uncertainty is involved in the early design stage of any manufacturing product. In multidisciplinary products like ships, the uncertainty in design information adversely affects the cost and performance of the product throughout its life cycle. However product information is expressed as a fixed value in the present design support systems and the systems can not deal with the uncertainties involved in the design information and design process. This study develops a new design support system considering uncertainties in the product information. Moreover, improvement of ship design also is discussed in consideration of uncertainties.

1. Introduction

Decision of finalizing the principal dimensions is a primary task in the ship design process. The uncertainties and errors involved in the design are considered as the root causes of redoing the design and deterioration of performance of the ships. In the studies of *Yang et al.* (2006) it is pointed out that conventional methods of preliminary ship design, can not give optimally balanced solutions. Moreover intuition of an experienced designer plays an important role in the extant design method but such skilled engineers are decreasing rapidly. The uncertainties in the design information are not considered in an effective manner, in the present design practice. If we follow existing design method, sometimes it can be observed that we get a satisfactory design solution in the early design stage but the same one may be evaluated as an inadequate/over design in the succeeding design stages.

Certain error margins are considered in the case of some input data used in design. For example, error margins are considered based on past experience in the calculation of ship weight during the design of principal dimensions. However studies by *Hamada et al.* (2008) pointed out that such error margins are not good enough to give a robust solution. Therefore a new design paradigm is proposed in this paper to deal with the limitations of current design process.

In contrast to the existing design method, various design data and product information are treated as indeterminate values in our new design approach. Design of principal dimensions is formulated as a multi objective optimization problem and a design support system is developed using an evolutionary multi objective optimization algorithm.

2. Design of Principal Dimensions and Uncertainty Factors

2.1. Design of principal dimensions

According to *Motozuna et al.* (1982) design of principal dimensions is summarized as;

- 1) *Deduce an initial design plan:* A design plan is deduced from empirical/statistical relations.
- 2) *Analyze the design plan:* Preliminary check on deadweight, stability, capacity etc... is executed.
- 3) *Modify design:* Design plan is modified, if requirements are not satisfied.
- 4) Design modifications and analyses are repeated until a feasible design is achieved.

2.2. Uncertainties in analyses

In the design of principal dimensions, so many analyses are involved. The data used in the analyses are not free from errors and uncertainties (Fig 1(a)). Therefore, error free outputs cannot be expected.

The effect of analyses with uncertain data can be understood from the flow of data processing in design, shown in Fig. 1(b). The notable fact is that the errors in analyses are propagated to the final design solution and need for design changes (Fig. 1 (c)) may arise in the succeeding design stages.

3. Design Scenario Considering Uncertainties

3.1. Definitions of uncertainties in product information

(1) Fixed and Unfixed product information

Fixed product information is one which can not be modified to make the design solution feasible or more optimal in nature. Fixed product information in a design solution can assume only a single numerical value. On the other hand unfixed product information can be changed to improve the feasibility or optimality because it can assume more than one numerical value.

(2) Representation of Unfixed information

In order to express product information as unfixed ones, adjustment parameters are used in the new design system.

An example of expressing the principal dimensions using the concept of fixed and unfixed product information is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1: Influence of uncertainty in design

Product information	L (m)	B (m)	D (m)	d (m)	MCR (PS)
Values of Product information	180	30	20	10	15000
Values of Adjustment parameters	± 0.2	0	0	0	0

L (m)	B (m)	D (m)	d (m)	MCR (PS)
179.8	30	20	10	15000
180	30	20	10	15000
180.2	30	20	10	15000

Fig. 2: Principal particulars (Fixed and Unfixed information)

In Fig. 2, value of 'L' is the only unfixed information. To keep it as unfixed, a nonzero value i.e. '±0.2' is given as adjustment parameter. Because of this 'L' can take the values 179.8, 180 and 180.2. For all other product information which is fixed, adjustment parameter has a value of '0'.

3.2. Design scenario

In the present design method, uncertainty factors are not considered properly. But a trial and error method or design modification is executed to achieve a satisfactory design solution. Because of this there are possibilities to arise problems of inadequate/over design. An attempt is made for the positive use of uncertainty in the proposed design method. There are two stages in the design of principal dimensions.

(1) Stage 1: Initialization

In this stage the following decisions are carried out.

- Selection of Fixed and Unfixed product information.
- Values of the adjustment parameters are set for the unfixed product information.
- Values of the principal dimensions are generated.
- Based on above decisions design solutions are created.

(2) Stage 2: Detailed examinations and design changes

In this stage the following activities are carried out.

- A detailed evaluation of design plans is executed to understand the feasibility and optimality.
- Fix the unfixed information within the restrictions of Stage 1 based on the results from detailed examinations.

The new concept is shown in Fig. 3, which is capable to give a robust design plan, because there are options to increase the feasibility as well as optimality and reduce re-design work.

Fig. 3: Design Scenario

3.3. Requirements to the system

When a design support system is developed based on the new concept, attention should be given to following facts.

- Large number of unfixed product information will increase the design time and complexity.
- The optimality and robustness of the solution achieved from design varies with;
 - The product information treated as unfixed/fixed.
 - Values of product information.
 - Values of adjustment parameters.

Considering above realities, it is necessary to develop a system with following requirements.

- Support the decisions on;
 - What should be fixed and what should be unfixed product information.
 - Values of product information and adjustment parameters.
 - Generation of various design solutions by changing the values of product information and adjustment parameters.
- Pay due attention to the criteria such as;
 - Performance of ship.
 - Feasibility of design plans.
 - Simplicity of design.
- Consider uncertainties involved in various analyses and calculations used in the design.

4. Overview of Design Support System

4.1. Problem definition

The design problem is defined as a multi objective optimization problem. The design variables, constraints and objective function are given in Table I.

4.2. Calculations of objective functions and constraints

In order to deal with the uncertainty Monte Carlo simulation is used in the evaluation of constraints objective functions and so on in this study. The evaluation of dead weight and feasibility using Monte Carlo simulation along with the calculation method in the present design process is shown in Fig. 4.

It is clear that Monte Carlo method gives an expected value of dead weight and percentage of feasibility. Calculation of objective functions and constraints using new concept for a solution with only one product information i.e. 'L' is unfixed; is shown in Fig. 5.

Table I: Design variables, constraints and objective functions

Design Variables	L, B, D, d, MCR and Adjustment parameters for L, B, D, d and MCR
Constraints	Deadweight $\rightarrow DWT \geq 45,000$ (t)
	Maneuverability $\rightarrow Cb/(L/B) \leq 0.16$
	Cruise speed (15.4 Knots) $\rightarrow MCR \geq BHS$
	Freeboard $\rightarrow 0 \leq (\text{max. allowable draught} - d)$
	Cargo hold volume $\rightarrow K_1(L \cdot B \cdot D) \geq 43,500 \cdot 42 \cdot 0.3048^3 / 1.016$
	Bow height $\geq 56L_f(1 - L_f/500) \cdot 1.36 / (C_{b85} + 0.68)$
Objective Functions	Light Ship Weight \rightarrow Minimize
	Percentage of Feasibility \rightarrow Maximize
	Number of unfixed product information \rightarrow Minimize

Fig. 4: Calculation of deadweight and feasibility (Present and proposed methods)

Fig. 5: Calculation of feasibility and expected value using Monte Carlo simulation

There are three design plans (1), (2) and (3) corresponding to the design solution given in Fig. 5. During each simulation deadweight and light ship weight are evaluated and feasibility is checked for each design plan. If only one of the plans is evaluated as feasible for a simulation, then the feasibility is decided as ‘Yes’ and that plan is considered for the evaluation of expected values of deadweight and light ship weight. If more than one plan is feasible for a simulation, the plan with minimum light ship weight is selected for the evaluation of expected values. Here, decision is based on value of light ship weight, because it is an objective function.

4.3. Optimization engine

In the proposed design support system, a Niche Pareto Genetic Algorithm2 (NPGA2) works as the optimization engine. The NPGA2 is almost same as simple GA in all aspects except the process of selection. A special tournament selection based on ranking and sharing methods is used to pick the candidates to generate new offspring. The selection process adopted by NPGA2 is summarized as;

- 1) *Ranking*: Pareto ranking (Fig. 6 (a)) is carried out after the evaluation of population.
- 2) *Rank based selection*: Two candidates are picked randomly. Out of these two, one with higher rank is selected. This is useful to pass superior candidates to next generation
- 3) *Sharing*: If it is not possible to find a clear winner from the two randomly picked candidates, as mentioned in above 2), that means a tie, then sharing method (Fig. 6 (b))) is adopted to select a candidate. In sharing method, a candidate with less crowded neighborhood is selected. The candidate with smaller niche number, proposed by *Erickson et al.* (2001), has a smaller number of candidates surrounded by it. Sharing helps to maintain the diversity of solutions.

Fig. 6: Ranking and sharing methods

Fig. 7: Optimization system using NPGA2

4.4. System configurations

The information processing in the optimization system is as shown in Fig. 7. In the optimization system, product information and adjustment parameters are treated as design variables. Monte Carlo Simulation is used in the calculation of first two objective functions; those are expected value of light ship weight and percentage of feasibility. The third objective function is the number of unfixed product information. In order to achieve solutions with minimum number of unfixed product information; a simple search is performed over the Pareto optimal solutions.

5. Examples

In order to show the applicability of the new system, design of principal dimensions for a bulk carrier of 45000 (t) DWT, is executed. For design variables, constraints and objective functions see Table 1.

5.1. Example 1

Optimization is executed within the design domain given in Table II and results are shown in Fig. 8.

From the results, it is clear that optimality increases with the number of unfixed product information. However more number of unfixed information increases complexity and duration of optimization Therefore it is better to keep the unfixed product information less than or equal to three.

Table II: Design domain

	Product Information					Values of adjustment parameters				
	L (m)	B (m)	D (m)	d (m)	MCR (PS)	L (m)	B (m)	D (m)	d (m)	MCR (PS)
Upper Limit	200	33	20	15	12000	1	0.5	0.5	0.5	500
Lower Limit	170	25	15	10	15000	0	0	0	0	0
Step	1	0.5	0.5	0.5	500	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	100

Fig. 8: Pareto Optimal Solutions

Table III: Solutions from present design method and new design support system

		Light ship weight (t)	Feasibility(%)	L (m)	B (m)	D (m)	d (m)	MCR (PS)	Comments
(a)	Present design method	9866	80.9	183	31.5	17.5	11	14800	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 2 % margin in weight is assumed. ● Feasibility corresponds to the point 'P1' in Fig. 8.
(b)	New method (Point 'P2' in Fig. 8)	9738	80.4	180	32.5	17.5 ± 0.5	11.5	14500	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● A reduction of 128 (t) in Light ship weight compared to present design method
(c)	New method (Point 'P3' in Fig. 8)	9656	78.7	178 ± 0.8	32.5	17.5 ± 0.5	12	15000	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● A reduction of 210 (t) in Light ship weight compared to present design method

Table III compares the solutions of present design method and selected solutions from proposed method. A weight margin of 2% is considered in the present design method. From the results obtained from proposed method, it is observed that the feasibility of solution of present method is 80.9% (Table III(a)). A considerable reduction in light ship weight is possible when proposed design method is used. This is clear from Table III(b) and (c) respectively.

5.2. Example 2

In this example, one of the product information is treated as unfixed whereas all others are kept fixed and optimizations are executed. This process is repeated for all product information one by one.

From the result (Fig. 9), the influence on the optimality of the design solution when different product information is kept unfixed is clear. As the value of adjustment parameter increases lightship weight decreases. It is also visible, when the product information 'D' is treated as unfixed the light ship weight is reduced considerably in comparison to other product information.

Fig. 9: Light ship weight vs. Values of adjustment parameters

6. Conclusions

A new design support system for the design of principal dimension is developed in this study. Conclusions of this paper are summarized as follows;

- A design methodology which deals with the uncertainty and the errors involved in the design data, analyses and product information is presented.
- A new design support system is developed based on the proposed concept for the design of principal dimensions of conventional ships.

The validity and applicability of the system is demonstrated by solving an example problem.

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Effects of Uncertainty in Fuzzy Utility Values on General Arrangements Optimization

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Abstract

The Intelligent Ship Arrangements (ISA) system, under development at the University of Michigan, is a Leading Edge Architecture for Prototyping System (LEAPS) compatible software system that assists the designer in developing rationally-based arrangements. These arrangements satisfy the design specific needs, general Navy requirements and standard practices to the maximum extent practicable. This software system is intended to be used following or as a latter part of Advanced Ship and Submarine Evaluation Tool (ASSET) synthesis. The impacts of uncertainty on results for general arrangements optimization is presented in this paper. In the ISA application, the optimization core makes use of fuzzy programming to provide the framework upon which the objective function and constraints are based. At the heart of this methodology are fuzzy utility functions that represent the satisfaction of goals and constraints for the various design considerations in the solution space. This methodology allows for a very powerful and generic foundation for describing the problem. The uncertainty of the fuzzy utility preference values and the corresponding impacts on design optimization are discussed. Uncertainty of the fuzzy utility values is achieved via inserting a stochastic perturbation to the fuzzy utility values with a normal distribution. The resulting experimental grid is analyzed from a robustness of solution standpoint.

1. Introduction

The Intelligent Ship Arrangements (ISA) system, under development at the University of Michigan, is a Leading Edge Architecture for Prototyping System (LEAPS) compatible software system that assists the designer in developing rationally-based arrangements. These arrangements satisfy the design specific needs, general Navy requirements, and standard practices to the maximum extent practicable. It is a native C++ / Microsoft Foundation Class (MFC) application, intended to be used as in post-processing or as a latter phase, of the U.S. Navy's ASSET synthesis process (ASSET 2007). This allows the users to gain insight into the general arrangements of the vessel at a much earlier stage in the design process during the Analysis of Alternatives level of design. ISA gets its inputs from an ASSET generated LEAPS database (LEAPS 2006), and a ship specific template library, Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: ISA Overall Schematic

The ASSET / LEAPS database provides the ship geometry as well as manning, major components, etc. The ship specific template library database, or ISA Library, provides a set of template spaces and accompanying constraints for that specific ship type to be used in the population of the model. From these two sources of information the ship model is created and the optimization on the general arrangements for the vessel can be performed. The arrangements optimization is handled by a Hybrid

Genetic Algorithm – Multi-Agent System (HGA-MAS). Resulting arrangements can then be exported back into the LEAPS database repository as new Concept objects.

At the heart of ISA’s modeling of general arrangements and optimization algorithms is the method of Fuzzy Optimization. Unlike standard optimization methods with linear and nonlinear objective functions and constraints, Fuzzy optimization uses fuzzy utility functions to model the systems of equations. When modeling with fuzzy utility preference functions, it is reasonable to ask how much impact do the utility values have on the output of the optimization engine and the robustness of the optimal solution(s) generated. This topic is the discussion of the remainder of this paper. The goal of this research is to test the ISA platform with uncertainty modelled in the underlying fuzzy utility functions to see the impacts on the general arrangements it gives. The test ship database used is the habitability ship from *Parsons (2008)*. This database was chosen because it is unrestricted and provides continuity with the previous work done by the University of Michigan Advanced Naval Design Laboratory (ANDL).

2. Uncertainty Modeling in ISA

At the heart of all of the Fuzzy Optimization Methodologies (Fuzzy Non-Linear Programming, Fuzzy Linear Programming, Fuzzy Inference Programming) is the fuzzy membership function or that quantifies the variable(s) relationships of interest. Fuzzy membership functions come in two primary different flavors, Type I Fuzzy Membership Functions and Type II Fuzzy Membership Functions. Type I fuzzy membership functions model the information being “fuzzified” by an arbitrary shape function that is bounded $0 \leq U(x) \leq 1$. Type II fuzzy membership functions are “fuzzy fuzzy” functions in which the description of the underlying Type I function itself is fuzzy. Type II fuzzy membership functions provide a means of representing uncertainty in the underlying Type I membership function. Fuzzy membership functions offer a means of desires and goals for information that is inherently subjective in nature.

As mentioned, Type II fuzzy utility functions are typically used to represent uncertainty in fuzzy preference functions and surfaces. Essentially the fuzzy utility function has statistical distributions associated at each point of evaluation and generates a “footprint of uncertainty” for the utility values at a certain independent variable x , Fig. 2. In practical computational modeling of Type II fuzzy utility functions, an interval approach is often taken where the fuzzy utility function is “sliced” with respect to the input variables and a pdf of the possible utility values is generated. This approach is a “simulated Type II” fuzzy utility function. It allows the user to generate Type II surface behaviour without the computational expense of developing an entire Type II fuzzy set.

Fig. 2: Example Type II Fuzzy Utility Function

In this study, the team used this Interval Simulated Type II approach to generate uncertainty (*Mendel 2007*). For every utility value, discrete or continuous, a hybrid Gaussian /uniform distribution function was used to simulate the uncertainty of the utility value. This concept is best shown by example. The utility value that is returned at any given point in time is the defined function value U^* plus an epsilon that has a Gaussian-Uniform Hybrid distribution with 0 mean and σ standard deviation, see Eq. (1).

$$U = U^* + \varepsilon \tag{1}$$

ε is a number with $\text{GNU}(0,\sigma)$ and $U \in [0,1]$

Since the bounds on the output utility value are $[0, 1]$, a standard Gaussian distribution cannot be used because its infinite tails. It was decided by the team that the acceptance / rejection method of random variate generation would make the best candidate for use in generating epsilons. For any given Utility value U^* , a $G(0, \sigma)$ epsilon is generated. If the resulting U is outside the bounds, a random number generator rejects the epsilon and generates another in the same manner. As a practical measure due to the limitations of the random number generator used, if 20 unsuccessful tries have been taken, the generator switches from Gaussian to a Uniform number generator and generates a uniform epsilon that is scaled properly to guarantee fitting within the bounds.

Fig. 3: Gaussian - Uniform Random Utility Generation Example

The design of this hybrid distribution is to ensure smooth transition from Gaussian distribution to a uniform distribution with a single parameter as sigma increases. The example of this method, Fig. 3, has a base utility value (U^*) is 0.85. Ten thousand random utility values were generated based on the Gaussian – Uniform Hybrid method and the histograms of the values were taken over increasing sigma. As shown, there is a smooth transition from the Gaussian distribution to the Uniform distribution as sigma increases. A sigma of 1 is a good practical upper bound for the studies because

that is saying that one standard deviation covers the entire feasible utility value space, i.e. the user is completely uncertain of the shape and values of the fuzzy utility function.

3. Design of Experiments

It was decided that in order to study the effects of uncertainty in ISA, that two separate but related studies needed to be addressed. The first study was focused on the overall impact of increasing sigma on the utility values of the objective function and the behavior of the solution space from a mathematical perspective. The second study was to study the effects of increasing uncertainty on the actual arrangements.

To measure the impact of increasing sigma in the first study, it was decided to run the optimization of the habitability ship at $\text{Sigma} = \{0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0, 5.0, 10.0\}$. In addition to this, a version of the code was modified to run utility preference values with a completely uniform distribution. In other words, exploring what happens when there is no shape to the utility functions at all.

For the general arrangements portion of the study it was decided to run the code with no randomness as a baseline, then run sigma settings of 0.05 and 0.1. Sixty replications for each setting were run and the elite chromosomes and time histories were collected. A special piece of code was written to generate probability maps of where the individual spaces were located by the optimization algorithm and the results were qualitatively assessed for the 103 spaces of the habitability ship.

4. Effects of Utility Function Uncertainty

The analysis results indicate that increasing the sigma transition has a dramatic effect on the values of the output chromosome fitness. As sigma increases, the overall fitness of the elite chromosome decreases until it approaches the value of the Uniform distribution based simulation, Fig. 4. This makes intuitive sense because with the hybrid Gaussian – uniform random number generator, as sigma increases the generation smoothly transitions from a Gaussian based distribution to a uniform distribution. Essentially, the fuzzy utility functions lose their shape as sigma increases.

From *Parsons (2008)*, we note that the Total chromosome fitness is made up of three components, minimum zone deck utility (U_1), average zone deck utility (U_2), and weighted average space minimum utility (U_3), see Eq. (2).

$$\begin{aligned}
 U &= \max(U_1 \times U_2 \times U_3) \leq 1.0 \\
 \text{Where:} \\
 \text{M is the number of constraints for} \\
 \text{an individual space} \\
 \text{N is the number of spaces} \\
 \text{K is the number of zone decks} \\
 \text{Z-dk means zone deck} \\
 U_1 &= \min(U_{Z-dk}) \\
 U_2 &= \frac{\sum_{i=1}^K U_{Z-dk}}{K} \\
 U_3 &= \frac{\sum_{j=1}^N w_j \times \min(U_{j1}, U_{j2}, \dots, U_{jM})}{\sum_{j=1}^N w_j}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

Table I indicates the components of the elite chromosome fitness objective function as sigma increases. An interesting trend is that the minimum and average zone deck utilities remain relatively constant and close to a utility value of one. The average of the minimum space utilities is the component that is dropping as sigma increases. The implication of this information is that as sigma increases and uncertainty in the constraints increases, the problem shifts to a pure bin packing problem. In other words the zone deck terms (area utilization) remain strong, but the topological relationships between spaces weaken considerably as sigma increases.

Fig. 4: Increasing Sigma Effects on Elite Chromosome Time History

Table I: Elite Chromosome with increasing Sigma

Sigma	Fitness	Min ZD U_1	Avg ZD U_2	Min SP	Avg SP U_3
0.01	0.759424	0.978708	0.997522	0.000849	0.777873
0.05	0.739343	0.978963	0.997303	0.046964	0.757272
0.1	0.673707	0.949757	0.993092	0.006292	0.714281
0.2	0.602322	0.957526	0.994425	0.001015	0.632567
0.4	0.398585	0.960883	0.995801	0.001664	0.41656
0.6	0.294592	0.978963	0.997252	0.001958	0.301752
0.8	0.189575	0.972598	0.996502	0.000137	0.195601
1	0.202653	0.967053	0.995716	0.001177	0.210459
5	0.240944	0.949757	0.994079	9.16E-05	0.255201
10	0.238263	0.931423	0.990777	0.00107	0.258187
Uniform	0.226251	0.978708	0.997167	0.001312	0.23183

5. Uncertainty Effects on General Arrangements

With the question of the effect of uncertainty on the values of the objective function addressed, the next question is what does the increase of sigma (increase of uncertainty) do to the actual arrangements and the quality of the arrangements that are generated. In order to evaluate this question, two approaches are taken. The first approach is to look at the spaces individually and generate probability maps of where in the ship they were located over the multiple runs. With this approach the user is interested in the probability distribution as well as changes in the modality of the distribution. This analysis was performed for all 103 of the spaces in the habitability ship. Only a few representative cases are presented here. Fig. 5 shows the overall utility distributions of the arrangements discussed. Each of the distributions has roughly a sigma of 0.01. The distributions are normal in shape.

Table II: Fitness Distribution Statistics

Sigma	Mean Elite Fitness	St. Dev.	Max	Min
0	0.75315	0.01445	0.77160	0.72656
0.05	0.72910	0.01197	0.75427	0.69258
0.1	0.68615	0.01095	0.70636	0.65482

Fig. 5: Elite Utility Distributions

	SUBDIV 7	SUBDIV 6	SUBDIV 5	SUBDIV 4	SUBDIV 3	SUBDIV 2	SUBDIV 1
DECK 6			SZD 29 CENTER	SZD 21 CENTER	Space Index	Space Name	
					40	Galley & Scullery	
DECK 5		SZD 36 CENTER	SZD 28 CENTER	SZD 20 CENTER	Sigma		0
DECK 4	SZD 40 PORT	SZD 34 PORT	SZD 26 PORT	SZD 18 PORT	SZD 12 PORT		
DC DECK	SZD 39 CENTER	SZD 33 CENTER	SZD 25 CENTER	SZD 17 CENTER	SZD 11 CENTER	SZD 07 CENTER	SZD 03 CENTER
		0.706	0.059	0.235			
	SZD 41 STARBOARD	SZD 35 STARBOARD	SZD 27 STARBOARD	SZD 19 STARBOARD	SZD 13 STARBOARD		
DECK 3	SZD 38 CENTER	SZD 32 CENTER	SZD 24 CENTER	SZD 16 CENTER	SZD 10 CENTER	SZD 06 CENTER	SZD 02 CENTER
DECK 2	SZD 37 CENTER	SZD 31 CENTER	SZD 23 CENTER	SZD 15 CENTER	SZD 09 CENTER	SZD 05 CENTER	SZD 01 CENTER
DECK 1		SZD 30 CENTER	SZD 22 CENTER	SZD 14 CENTER	SZD 08 CENTER	SZD 04 CENTER	SZD 00 CENTER
DECK 6	SUBDIV 7	SUBDIV 6	SUBDIV 5	SUBDIV 4	SUBDIV 3	SUBDIV 2	SUBDIV 1
			SZD 29 CENTER	SZD 21 CENTER	Space Index	Space Name	
					40	Galley & Scullery	
DECK 5		SZD 36 CENTER	SZD 28 CENTER	SZD 20 CENTER	Sigma		0.05
DECK 4	SZD 40 PORT	SZD 34 PORT	SZD 26 PORT	SZD 18 PORT	SZD 12 PORT		
DC DECK	SZD 39 CENTER	SZD 33 CENTER	SZD 25 CENTER	SZD 17 CENTER	SZD 11 CENTER	SZD 07 CENTER	SZD 03 CENTER
		0.833	0.050	0.117			
	SZD 41 STARBOARD	SZD 35 STARBOARD	SZD 27 STARBOARD	SZD 19 STARBOARD	SZD 13 STARBOARD		
DECK 3	SZD 38 CENTER	SZD 32 CENTER	SZD 24 CENTER	SZD 16 CENTER	SZD 10 CENTER	SZD 06 CENTER	SZD 02 CENTER
DECK 2	SZD 37 CENTER	SZD 31 CENTER	SZD 23 CENTER	SZD 15 CENTER	SZD 09 CENTER	SZD 05 CENTER	SZD 01 CENTER
DECK 1		SZD 30 CENTER	SZD 22 CENTER	SZD 14 CENTER	SZD 08 CENTER	SZD 04 CENTER	SZD 00 CENTER
DECK 6	SUBDIV 7	SUBDIV 6	SUBDIV 5	SUBDIV 4	SUBDIV 3	SUBDIV 2	SUBDIV 1
			SZD 29 CENTER	SZD 21 CENTER	Space Index	Space Name	
					40	Galley & Scullery	
DECK 5		SZD 36 CENTER	SZD 28 CENTER	SZD 20 CENTER	Sigma		0.1
DECK 4	SZD 40 PORT	SZD 34 PORT	SZD 26 PORT	SZD 18 PORT	SZD 12 PORT		
DC DECK	SZD 39 CENTER	SZD 33 CENTER	SZD 25 CENTER	SZD 17 CENTER	SZD 11 CENTER	SZD 07 CENTER	SZD 03 CENTER
		0.883	0.033	0.083			
	SZD 41 STARBOARD	SZD 35 STARBOARD	SZD 27 STARBOARD	SZD 19 STARBOARD	SZD 13 STARBOARD		
DECK 3	SZD 38 CENTER	SZD 32 CENTER	SZD 24 CENTER	SZD 16 CENTER	SZD 10 CENTER	SZD 06 CENTER	SZD 02 CENTER
DECK 2	SZD 37 CENTER	SZD 31 CENTER	SZD 23 CENTER	SZD 15 CENTER	SZD 09 CENTER	SZD 05 CENTER	SZD 01 CENTER
DECK 1		SZD 30 CENTER	SZD 22 CENTER	SZD 14 CENTER	SZD 08 CENTER	SZD 04 CENTER	SZD 00 CENTER

Fig. 6: Galley and Scullery IB Probability Map

Space Importance: 20 → scale (1 least important ... 20 most important)

Required Area (m²): 54

5.1. Space # 040: Galley and Scullery

Fig. 6 gives inboard profiles of the habitability ship (bow to the right) projected onto a grid style representation for ease of reading. Each sub zone deck is labeled by its index number. The cell below the sub zone deck name contains the percentage of the time that the space of interest resided in that location over the replications performed in the DOE. If no number is in the cell, then the space was never allocated to that particular sub zone deck. On the left hand side, Fig. 6 indicates on which deck the various sub zone decks are located. Along with each figure, the relative importance of the space and its required area are listed. This is to provide the reader with an indication of size and precedence that the space has on the arrangement. The galley and scullery is a good example of a high importance and large area space. It is also a good example of modal reduction as sigma increases. With sigma 0, the galley and scullery has a bi modal space distribution split between Sub Zone Deck (SZD) 33 and SZD 17. As sigma increases to 0.1 the distribution shifts to a primarily unimodal shape with 88% of the allocations going to SZD 33 in the aft midship of the damage control deck. This location is a good centralized location with low motions for the space. Also having a centralized location provides ease of access for storage it relies on, and the dining spaces that it services.

5.2. Space # 015: Cleaning Gear Storeroom

	SUBDIV 7	SUBDIV 6	SUBDIV 5	SUBDIV 4	SUBDIV 3	SUBDIV 2	SUBDIV 1
DECK 6			SZD 29 CENTER	SZD 21 CENTER	Space Index	Space Name	
					15	Cleaning Gear Storeroom (Below Decks)	
DECK 5		SZD 36 CENTER	SZD 28 CENTER	SZD 20 CENTER	Sigma		0
DECK 4	SZD 40 PORT	SZD 34 PORT	SZD 26 PORT	SZD 18 PORT	SZD 12 PORT		
DC DECK	0.137		0.176	0.078	0.059		
	SZD 39 CENTER	SZD 33 CENTER	SZD 25 CENTER	SZD 17 CENTER	SZD 11 CENTER	SZD 07 CENTER	SZD 03 CENTER
	0.098	0.098	0.078	0.039	0.020		
	SZD 41 STARBOARD	SZD 35 STARBOARD	SZD 27 STARBOARD	SZD 19 STARBOARD	SZD 13 STARBOARD		
	0.078	0.020	0.020	0.078	0.020		
DECK 3	SZD 38 CENTER	SZD 32 CENTER	SZD 24 CENTER	SZD 16 CENTER	SZD 10 CENTER	SZD 06 CENTER	SZD 02 CENTER
DECK 2	SZD 37 CENTER	SZD 31 CENTER	SZD 23 CENTER	SZD 15 CENTER	SZD 09 CENTER	SZD 05 CENTER	SZD 01 CENTER
DECK 1		SZD 30 CENTER	SZD 22 CENTER	SZD 14 CENTER	SZD 08 CENTER	SZD 04 CENTER	SZD 00 CENTER
	SUBDIV 7	SUBDIV 6	SUBDIV 5	SUBDIV 4	SUBDIV 3	SUBDIV 2	SUBDIV 1
DECK 6			SZD 29 CENTER	SZD 21 CENTER	Space Index	Space Name	
					15	Cleaning Gear Storeroom (Below Decks)	
DECK 5		SZD 36 CENTER	SZD 28 CENTER	SZD 20 CENTER	Sigma		0.05
DECK 4	SZD 40 PORT	SZD 34 PORT	SZD 26 PORT	SZD 18 PORT	SZD 12 PORT		
DC DECK	0.200	0.067	0.050	0.100			
	SZD 39 CENTER	SZD 33 CENTER	SZD 25 CENTER	SZD 17 CENTER	SZD 11 CENTER	SZD 07 CENTER	SZD 03 CENTER
	0.067	0.050	0.017	0.017			
	SZD 41 STARBOARD	SZD 35 STARBOARD	SZD 27 STARBOARD	SZD 19 STARBOARD	SZD 13 STARBOARD		
	0.167	0.050	0.033	0.150	0.033		
DECK 3	SZD 38 CENTER	SZD 32 CENTER	SZD 24 CENTER	SZD 16 CENTER	SZD 10 CENTER	SZD 06 CENTER	SZD 02 CENTER
DECK 2	SZD 37 CENTER	SZD 31 CENTER	SZD 23 CENTER	SZD 15 CENTER	SZD 09 CENTER	SZD 05 CENTER	SZD 01 CENTER
DECK 1		SZD 30 CENTER	SZD 22 CENTER	SZD 14 CENTER	SZD 08 CENTER	SZD 04 CENTER	SZD 00 CENTER
	SUBDIV 7	SUBDIV 6	SUBDIV 5	SUBDIV 4	SUBDIV 3	SUBDIV 2	SUBDIV 1
DECK 6			SZD 29 CENTER	SZD 21 CENTER	Space Index	Space Name	
					15	Cleaning Gear Storeroom (Below Decks)	
DECK 5		SZD 36 CENTER	SZD 28 CENTER	SZD 20 CENTER	Sigma		0.1
DECK 4	SZD 40 PORT	SZD 34 PORT	SZD 26 PORT	SZD 18 PORT	SZD 12 PORT		
DC DECK	0.167	0.067	0.017	0.067	0.033		
	SZD 39 CENTER	SZD 33 CENTER	SZD 25 CENTER	SZD 17 CENTER	SZD 11 CENTER	SZD 07 CENTER	SZD 03 CENTER
	0.083	0.100	0.033	0.017			
	SZD 41 STARBOARD	SZD 35 STARBOARD	SZD 27 STARBOARD	SZD 19 STARBOARD	SZD 13 STARBOARD		
	0.150	0.050	0.017	0.217			
DECK 3	SZD 38 CENTER	SZD 32 CENTER	SZD 24 CENTER	SZD 16 CENTER	SZD 10 CENTER	SZD 06 CENTER	SZD 02 CENTER
DECK 2	SZD 37 CENTER	SZD 31 CENTER	SZD 23 CENTER	SZD 15 CENTER	SZD 09 CENTER	SZD 05 CENTER	SZD 01 CENTER
DECK 1		SZD 30 CENTER	SZD 22 CENTER	SZD 14 CENTER	SZD 08 CENTER	SZD 04 CENTER	SZD 00 CENTER

Fig. 7: Cleaning Gear Storeroom IB Probability Map

Space Importance: 2
 Required Area (m²): 2

The cleaning gear store room is a good example of a dispersion pattern for arrangement. Because it is of small importance and small required area, it is often used as a “filler” space and allocated wherever area is available. In this case, the patterns of where it is located are consistent across the varying sigmas. The modal locations do shift some as sigma increases. Any of these locations on the damage control deck are good locations for the cleaning gear storeroom as it provides easy access to cleaning materials for the spaces it is servicing.

5.3. Space # 004: Auxiliary Propulsion Room

	SUBDIV 7	SUBDIV 6	SUBDIV 5	SUBDIV 4	SUBDIV 3	SUBDIV 2	SUBDIV 1
DECK 6			SZD 29 CENTER	SZD 21 CENTER	Space Index	Space Name	
					4	Auxiliary Propulsion Room	
DECK 5		SZD 36 CENTER	SZD 28 CENTER	SZD 20 CENTER	Sigma		0
		0.039		0.078			0.216
DECK 4	SZD 40 PORT	SZD 34 PORT	SZD 26 PORT	SZD 18 PORT	SZD 12 PORT		
DC DECK				0.020		0.020	
	SZD 39 CENTER	SZD 33 CENTER	SZD 25 CENTER	SZD 17 CENTER	SZD 11 CENTER	SZD 07 CENTER	SZD 03 CENTER
	0.020		0.020				
	SZD 41 STARBOARD	SZD 35 STARBOARD	SZD 27 STARBOARD	SZD 19 STARBOARD	SZD 13 STARBOARD		
					0.020		
DECK 3	SZD 38 CENTER	SZD 32 CENTER	SZD 24 CENTER	SZD 16 CENTER	SZD 10 CENTER	SZD 06 CENTER	SZD 02 CENTER
	0.118	0.020					
DECK 2	SZD 37 CENTER	SZD 31 CENTER	SZD 23 CENTER	SZD 15 CENTER	SZD 09 CENTER	SZD 05 CENTER	SZD 01 CENTER
					0.216		0.196
DECK 1		SZD 30 CENTER	SZD 22 CENTER	SZD 14 CENTER	SZD 08 CENTER	SZD 04 CENTER	SZD 00 CENTER
	SUBDIV 7	SUBDIV 6	SUBDIV 5	SUBDIV 4	SUBDIV 3	SUBDIV 2	SUBDIV 1
DECK 6			SZD 29 CENTER	SZD 21 CENTER	Space Index	Space Name	
					4	Auxiliary Propulsion Room	
DECK 5		SZD 36 CENTER	SZD 28 CENTER	SZD 20 CENTER	Sigma		0.05
		0.083					0.133
DECK 4	SZD 40 PORT	SZD 34 PORT	SZD 26 PORT	SZD 18 PORT	SZD 12 PORT		
DC DECK							
	SZD 39 CENTER	SZD 33 CENTER	SZD 25 CENTER	SZD 17 CENTER	SZD 11 CENTER	SZD 07 CENTER	SZD 03 CENTER
	0.017		0.050				
	SZD 41 STARBOARD	SZD 35 STARBOARD	SZD 27 STARBOARD	SZD 19 STARBOARD	SZD 13 STARBOARD		
		0.017			0.033		
DECK 3	SZD 38 CENTER	SZD 32 CENTER	SZD 24 CENTER	SZD 16 CENTER	SZD 10 CENTER	SZD 06 CENTER	SZD 02 CENTER
	0.133	0.017			0.017		
DECK 2	SZD 37 CENTER	SZD 31 CENTER	SZD 23 CENTER	SZD 15 CENTER	SZD 09 CENTER	SZD 05 CENTER	SZD 01 CENTER
				0.017	0.350		0.133
DECK 1		SZD 30 CENTER	SZD 22 CENTER	SZD 14 CENTER	SZD 08 CENTER	SZD 04 CENTER	SZD 00 CENTER
	SUBDIV 7	SUBDIV 6	SUBDIV 5	SUBDIV 4	SUBDIV 3	SUBDIV 2	SUBDIV 1
DECK 6			SZD 29 CENTER	SZD 21 CENTER	Space Index	Space Name	
					4	Auxiliary Propulsion Room	
DECK 5		SZD 36 CENTER	SZD 28 CENTER	SZD 20 CENTER	Sigma		0.1
		0.017					0.100
DECK 4	SZD 40 PORT	SZD 34 PORT	SZD 26 PORT	SZD 18 PORT	SZD 12 PORT		
DC DECK					0.033		
	SZD 39 CENTER	SZD 33 CENTER	SZD 25 CENTER	SZD 17 CENTER	SZD 11 CENTER	SZD 07 CENTER	SZD 03 CENTER
	0.017		0.150				
	SZD 41 STARBOARD	SZD 35 STARBOARD	SZD 27 STARBOARD	SZD 19 STARBOARD	SZD 13 STARBOARD		
			0.050				
DECK 3	SZD 38 CENTER	SZD 32 CENTER	SZD 24 CENTER	SZD 16 CENTER	SZD 10 CENTER	SZD 06 CENTER	SZD 02 CENTER
	0.167						
DECK 2	SZD 37 CENTER	SZD 31 CENTER	SZD 23 CENTER	SZD 15 CENTER	SZD 09 CENTER	SZD 05 CENTER	SZD 01 CENTER
				0.067	0.267		0.133
DECK 1		SZD 30 CENTER	SZD 22 CENTER	SZD 14 CENTER	SZD 08 CENTER	SZD 04 CENTER	SZD 00 CENTER

Fig. 8: Auxiliary Propulsion Room IB Probability Map

Space Importance: 5
 Required Area (m²): 20

The auxiliary propulsion room is a good example of how this methodology could be used to help “debug” or quality check the constraint database. The outliers in the upper decks indicated that there was a problem with the auxiliary propulsion room. Upon closer inspection of the constraints relating to the auxiliary propulsion room, the source of the problem was found. One of the relative separation constraints between the auxiliary propulsion room and the BC Medical facility was accidentally set as an adjacency constraint. This constraint tended to pull the space up into the ship instead of keeping it on the hold level where it belongs. This error was noticed after the full DOE was conducted. The DOE was not repeated due to time limitations and the fact that this was a low importance space. The fix was, however implemented for the long term runs that will be discussed in the next section.

5.4. Long Term Study of Optimization

As a further investigation of the impact of the stochastics on the general arrangements, three long term runs were conducted with 4000 generations at sigma settings of 0, 0.05, and 0.1. The goal was to compare more global features of the arrangements to one another and look for qualitative signs of degradation of the arranging capability optimization engine. A full DOE with replications was not conducted due to time limitations on this study. The general feature similarities will be discussed first, and then weaknesses in the individual arrangements will be discussed in a “red ink review” of the arrangements. As a baseline for the discussion, the ASNE (*Parsons 2008*) allocation will be used for comparison. Due to space limitations the Sigma 0 run will not be discussed. The time histories of the elite chromosomes for the runs are shown in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9: Long Term Run Time Histories

5.5. Arrangement Global Comparison

Fig. 10: Habitability Ship Inboard Profile with SZD Indexes

The three arrangements under comparison exhibit a number of similarities in design which will now be discussed. The arrangements being discussed are shown in Fig. 11, Fig. 12, and Fig. 13.

- All four arrangements allocate the Medical Complex spaces to SZD 28 right in front of the helicopter landing pad on Deck 5.
- Officer berthing (Male) in all arrangements are primarily clustered in SZD 29 and SZD 20.
- Officer berthing (Female) in all arrangements are primarily clustered in SZD 28 and SZD 36.

- With the exception of a couple of outliers, Specialist berthing is primarily in the 3rd and 4th subdivisions starting from the 1st Deck on up to the DC Deck.
- With the exception of the Sigma 0.1 run, the clustering of berthing spaces was good.
- Food Services complexes are centralized around SZD 33. However actual dining room configurations and storage configurations differ.
- Mechanical services spaces (Sewage Treatment, Trash, Workshops, Pump Rooms, etc. Are located on either the hold deck or at the aft end of the 1st Deck below the DC Deck.
- Other habitability services spaces (Library, Recreation, Training, etc.) are more distributed, but do exhibit a tendency towards the DC Deck or the 1st Deck near amidships. This provides good access to those spaces which are heavily used by the crew.

5.6. ASNE Inboard Profile Critique

- While a dumb waiter can be used with the current configuration, it would be preferred that the Cool, Cold, and Dry Provisions (Space 18) on SZD 32 be on the same deck as the galley and scullery that is currently one deck above in SZD 33.
- The Electrical Switchboard (Space 89) in SZD 6 should be further aft in the ship. There are no substantial electrical loads at the bow. A better placement would be further aft, if area was available.
- Specialist Cabins (female)(Space 84 and Space 85) should be grouped together in the same zone deck

5.7. Sigma 0.05 Long Term Run Critique

- While a dumb waiter can be used with the current configuration, it would be preferred that the Cool, Cold, and Dry Provisions (Space 18) on SZD 32 be on the same deck as the galley and scullery that is currently one deck above in SZD 33.
- The Wardroom (Space 96) in SZD 17 should be closer to the Galley and Scullery
- Specialist Cabins (female)(Space 84 and Space 85) should be grouped together in the same zone deck

5.8. Sigma 0.1 Long Term Run Critique

- Specialist Cabin (Space 83) is located poorly, isolated and on the hold deck in SZD 31.
- Specialist Cabin (Space 82) is located poorly, isolated and on the hold deck in SZD 9
- Majority of PO Dining facilities (Space 60, Space 61, Space 62) in SZD 17, and SZD 19 are slightly too far from the Galley that services them.
- The lone Specialist Cabin (male)(Space 81) on SZD 10 should be separated from the female specialist cabins if area permits. Otherwise a segregation access / bulkhead should be employed between female and male berthing.

Deck	SubDiv7	SubDiv6	SubDiv5	SubDiv4	SubDiv3	SubDiv2	SubDiv1
Deck 6			<p>SUBZONEDECK 29: zoneDec0023: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 29: Engineer Officer Cabin SPACE 30: Fan Room (Deckhouse) SPACE 48: Officer Cabin (Male)(2) & Bath GpA SPACE 49: Officer Cabin (Female)(2) & Bath GpA SPACE 50: Officer Cabin (Male)(2) & Bath GpA SPACE 51: Officer Cabin (Male)(2) & Bath GpA SPACE 57: XO Cabin & Bath</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 21: zoneDec0007: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 12: Bridge SPACE 19: Electrical Equipment Room SPACE 32: Officer Cabin (Male)(2) & Bath GpB</p>			
Deck 5		<p>SUBZONEDECK 36: zoneDec0028: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 7: Boat Gear Locker SPACE 11: Bosun Storeroom (MainDeck) SPACE 12: Electrical Equipment Room SPACE 14: Medical Room SPACE 26: Fan Room (Hull) SPACE 37: Officer Cabin (Female)(2) & Bath SPACE 68: PO Cabin (Female)(4) & Bath</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 28: zoneDec0022: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 6: BC Medical Facility SPACE 25: Electrical Equipment Room SPACE 44: Medical Consultation Room SPACE 56: Officer Cabin (Female)(2) & Bath SPACE 58: Officer Cabin (Female)(2) & Bath SPACE 77: Sick Bay</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 20: zoneDec0006: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 10: Bosun Storeroom (MainDeck) SPACE 16: CO Cabin & Bath SPACE 28: Electrical Equipment Room SPACE 38: Fan Room (Hull) SPACE 53: Officer Cabin (Male)(2) & Bath GpB SPACE 54: Officer Cabin (Male)(2) & Bath GpB SPACE 55: Officer Cabin (Male)(2) & Bath GpB</p>			
Deck 4	<p>SUBZONEDECK 39: zoneDec0031_c RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 8: Bosun Storeroom (Aft Mooring) SPACE 61: PO & Specialist Dining Room</p> <p>SUBZONEDECK 40: zoneDec0031_p RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 35: Fan Room (Hull) SPACE 46: Mooring Area & Gear Storeroom (Aft)</p> <p>SUBZONEDECK 41: zoneDec0031_s RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 31: Fan Room (Hull) SPACE 47: Mooring Area & Gear Storeroom (Aft)</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 33: zoneDec0027_c RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 27: Electrical Equipment Room SPACE 40: Galley & Scullery</p> <p>SUBZONEDECK 34: zoneDec0027_p RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 34: Fan Room (Hull) SPACE 71: Daily Provision Room</p> <p>SUBZONEDECK 35: zoneDec0027_s RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 102: PO & Specialist Dining Room</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 25: zoneDec0021_c RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 33: Fan Room (Hull) SPACE 72: Recreation Room SPACE 96: Wardroom</p> <p>SUBZONEDECK 26: zoneDec0021_p RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 15: Cleaning Gear Storeroom (Below Decks) SPACE 62: PO & Specialist Dining Room</p> <p>SUBZONEDECK 27: zoneDec0021_s RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 21: Electrical Equipment Room SPACE 60: PO & Specialist Dining Room</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 17: zoneDec00015_c RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 63: PO Cabin (Male)(4) & Bath GpA SPACE 64: PO Cabin (Male)(4) & Bath GpA SPACE 65: PO Cabin (Male)(4) & Bath GpA</p> <p>SUBZONEDECK 18: zoneDec00015_p RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 24: Electrical Equipment Room SPACE 31: Fan Room (Hull) SPACE 38: Foul Weather Gear Locker</p> <p>SUBZONEDECK 19: zoneDec00015_s RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 26: Electrical Equipment Room SPACE 32: Fan Room (Hull) SPACE 90: Electrical Switchboard Room</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 11: zoneDec00011_c RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 81: Specialist Cabin (Male)(6) GrpB</p> <p>SUBZONEDECK 13: zoneDec00011_p RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 9: Bosun Storeroom (Fwd Mooring) SPACE 24: Electrical Equipment Room SPACE 31: Fan Room (Hull) SPACE 38: Foul Weather Gear Locker</p> <p>SUBZONEDECK 13: zoneDec00011_s RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 94: Library</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 7: zoneDec0007: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 3: Anchoring & Mooring SPACE 45: Mooring Area & Gear Storeroom (Fwd)</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 3: zoneDec0003: RESIDENT SPACES:</p>
Deck 3	<p>SUBZONEDECK 38: zoneDec0030: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 5: Battery Locker and Charging SPACE 69: POL & Paint Locker (Storage) SPACE 70: POL & Paint Locker (Service) SPACE 67: Steering Gear Room SPACE 88: Steering Gear Room SPACE 92: Electrical Switchboard Room SPACE 95: Trash Room</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 32: zoneDec0026: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 18: Cool Cold Dry Provisions SPACE 41: General Storage SPACE 42: Linen Locker SPACE 73: Refrigerator Machinery Room SPACE 86: Laundry (Specialist)</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 24: zoneDec0020: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 99: MMR Diesel (LftPlatform)</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 16: zoneDec0004: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 66: PO Cabin (Male)(4) & Bath GpB SPACE 67: PO Cabin (Male)(4) & Bath GpB SPACE 74: SD Storeroom SPACE 79: Specialist Cabin (Male)(6) GrpA SPACE 80: Specialist Cabin (Male)(6) GrpA SPACE 85: Specialist Cabin (Female)(6)</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 10: zoneDec00010: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 82: Specialist Cabin (Male)(6) GrpB SPACE 83: Specialist Cabin (Male)(6) GrpB SPACE 84: Specialist Cabin (Female)(6)</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 6: zoneDec0006: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 13: Chain Locker SPACE 89: Electrical Switchboard Room</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 2: zoneDec0002: RESIDENT SPACES:</p>
Deck 2	<p>SUBZONEDECK 37: zoneDec0029: RESIDENT SPACES:</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 31: zoneDec0025: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 0: Aft Pump Room SPACE 91: Electrical Switchboard Room SPACE 101: Mechanical Workshop (General)</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 23: zoneDec0019: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 98: MMR Diesel (Hold)</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 15: zoneDec00013: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 1: Air Conditioning Room SPACE 39: Fwd Pump Room SPACE 100: AMK</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 9: zoneDec0009: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 2: Air Conditioning Room SPACE 10: AMK</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 5: zoneDec0005: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 4: Auxiliary Propulsion Room SPACE 14: Chain Locker Sump</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 1: zoneDec0001: RESIDENT SPACES:</p>
Deck 1		<p>SUBZONEDECK 30: zoneDec0024: RESIDENT SPACES:</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 22: zoneDec0018: RESIDENT SPACES:</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 14: zoneDec0012: RESIDENT SPACES:</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 8: zoneDec0008: RESIDENT SPACES:</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 4: zoneDec0004: RESIDENT SPACES:</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 0: zoneDec0000: RESIDENT SPACES:</p>

RUN	Fitness	Min. ZD	Avg. ZD	Min. SP	Avg. SP
ASNE	0.778	0.987	0.999	0.300	0.790

Fig. 11: ASNE 2008 Inboard Profile

Deck	SubDiv7	SubDiv6	SubDiv5	SubDiv4	SubDiv3	SubDiv2	SubDiv1
Deck 6			<p>SUBZONEDECK 29: zoneDec0023: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 28: Electrical Equipment Room SPACE 29: Engineer Officer Cabin SPACE 37: Fan Room (Deckhouse) SPACE 48: Officer Cabin (Male)(2) & Bath GrpA SPACE 49: Officer Cabin (Male)(2) & Bath GrpA SPACE 50: Officer Cabin (Male)(2) & Bath GrpA SPACE 51: Officer Cabin (Male)(2) & Bath GrpA SPACE 97: XO Cabin & Bath</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 21: zoneDec0017: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 12: Bridge SPACE 19: Electrical Equipment Room SPACE 20: Electrical Equipment Room SPACE 36: Fan Room (Deckhouse) SPACE 32: Officer Cabin (Male)(2) & Bath GrpB</p>			
Deck 5		<p>SUBZONEDECK 36: zoneDec0028: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 7: Boat Gear Locker SPACE 10: Boson Storeroom (MindDeck) SPACE 11: Boson Storeroom (MindDeck) SPACE 23: Enclosed RB Storage SPACE 38: Officer Cabin (Female)(2) & Bath SPACE 68: PO Cabin (Female)(4) & Bath</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 28: zoneDec0022: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 6: BC Medical Facility SPACE 21: Electrical Equipment Room SPACE 22: Medical Consultation Room SPACE 44: Medical Equipment Room SPACE 56: Officer Cabin (Female)(2) & Bath SPACE 57: Officer Cabin (Female)(2) & Bath SPACE 77: Sick Bay</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 20: zoneDec0016: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 16: CO Cabin & Bath SPACE 17: CO Storeroom SPACE 18: Electrical Equipment Room SPACE 53: Officer Cabin (Male)(2) & Bath GrpB SPACE 54: Officer Cabin (Male)(2) & Bath GrpB SPACE 55: Officer Cabin (Male)(2) & Bath GrpB SPACE 85: Specialist Cabin (Female)(6)</p>			
Deck 4	<p>SUBZONEDECK 39: zoneDec0031_c RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 24: Electrical Equipment Room SPACE 24: PO Cabin (Male)(4) & Bath GrpB SPACE 67: PO Cabin (Male)(4) & Bath GrpB</p> <p>SUBZONEDECK 40: zoneDec0031_f RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 38: Fan Room (Hull) SPACE 46: Mooring Area & Gear Storeroom (AH)</p> <p>SUBZONEDECK 41: zoneDec0031_s RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 8: Boson Storeroom (Aft Mooring) SPACE 47: Mooring Area & Gear Storeroom (AH)</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 33: zoneDec0027_c RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 10: Galley & Scullery SPACE 34: zoneDec0027_f RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 39: Fan Room (Hull) SPACE 71: Daily Provision Room SPACE 72: Recreation Room SPACE 95: Fuel Weather Gear Locker SPACE 96: Ship Office SPACE 99: Electrical Switchboard Room</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 25: zoneDec0021_c RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 60: PO & Specialist Dining Room SPACE 61: PO & Specialist Dining Room SPACE 62: PO & Specialist Dining Room SPACE 26: zoneDec0021_f RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 32: Fan Room (Hull) SPACE 33: Fan Room (Hull) SPACE 73: Recreation Room SPACE 27: zoneDec0021_s RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 25: Electrical Equipment Room SPACE 102: PO & Specialist Dining Room</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 17: zoneDec0015_c RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 96: Wardroom SUBZONEDECK 18: zoneDec0015_f RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 15: Cleaning Gear Storeroom (Below Decks) SPACE 22: Electrical Equipment Room SPACE 94: Library SUBZONEDECK 19: zoneDec0015_s RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 31: Fan Room (Hull) SPACE 93: Training Room</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 11: zoneDec0011_c RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 9: Boson Storeroom (Fwd Mooring) SUBZONEDECK 12: zoneDec0011_f RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 27: Electrical Equipment Room SPACE 84: Specialist Cabin (Female)(6) SUBZONEDECK 13: zoneDec0011_s RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 34: Fan Room (Hull) SPACE 90: Electrical Switchboard Room</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 7: zoneDec0007: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 3: Anchoring & Mooring SPACE 45: Mooring Area & Gear Storeroom (Fwd)</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 3: zoneDec0003: RESIDENT SPACES:</p>
Deck 3	<p>SUBZONEDECK 38: zoneDec0030: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 5: Battery Locker and Charging SPACE 69: POL & Paint Locker (Storage) SPACE 70: POL & Paint Locker (Service) SPACE 87: Steering Gear Room SPACE 88: Steering Gear Room SPACE 91: Electrical Switchboard Room</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 32: zoneDec0026: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 41: General Storage SPACE 42: Linen Locker SPACE 99: Laundry (Officer & PO) SPACE 78: Refrigerator Machinery Room SPACE 74: SD Storeroom SPACE 86: Laundry (Specialist)</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 24: zoneDec0020: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 98: MMR Diesel (1st Platform) SUBZONEDECK 23: zoneDec0019: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 98: MMR Diesel (Hold)</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 16: zoneDec0014: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 63: PO Cabin (Male)(4) & Bath GrpA SPACE 64: PO Cabin (Male)(4) & Bath GrpA SPACE 65: PO Cabin (Male)(4) & Bath GrpA SPACE 81: Specialist Cabin (Male)(6) GrpB SPACE 82: Specialist Cabin (Male)(6) GrpB SPACE 83: Specialist Cabin (Male)(6) GrpB</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 10: zoneDec0010: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 79: Specialist Cabin (Male)(6) GrpA SPACE 80: Specialist Cabin (Male)(6) GrpA SPACE 80: Specialist Cabin (Male)(6) GrpA</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 6: zoneDec0006: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 87: Chain Locker SPACE 88: Electrical Switchboard Room</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 2: zoneDec0002: RESIDENT SPACES:</p>
Deck 2	<p>SUBZONEDECK 37: zoneDec0029: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 10: Air Pump Room SPACE 75: Sewage Treatment Machinery Room SPACE 95: Trash Room</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 31: zoneDec0025: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 10: Air Pump Room SPACE 75: Sewage Treatment Machinery Room SPACE 95: Trash Room</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 23: zoneDec0019: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 98: MMR Diesel (Hold)</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 15: zoneDec0013: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 2: Air Conditioning Room SPACE 100: AMR</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 9: zoneDec0009: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 30: Fwd Pump Room SPACE 101: Mechanical Workshop (General)</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 5: zoneDec0005: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 4: Auxiliary Propulsion Room SPACE 14: Chain Locker Sump</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 1: zoneDec0001: RESIDENT SPACES:</p>
Deck 1		<p>SUBZONEDECK 30: zoneDec0024: RESIDENT SPACES:</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 22: zoneDec0018: RESIDENT SPACES:</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 14: zoneDec0012: RESIDENT SPACES:</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 8: zoneDec0008: RESIDENT SPACES:</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 4: zoneDec0004: RESIDENT SPACES:</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 0: zoneDec0000: RESIDENT SPACES:</p>

RUN	Fitness	Min ZD	Avg ZD	Min SP	Avg SP
Run 02	0.746864	0.978951	0.997173	0.00197	0.765086
Without Uncertainty	0.775932	0.978951	0.997173	5.00E-02	0.794862

Fig. 12: Sigma 0.05 Long Term Run Elite

Deck	SubD7	SubD6	SubD5	SubD4	SubD3	SubD2	SubD1
Deck 6			<p>SUBZONEDECK 29: zoneDec0023: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 34: Electrical Equipment Room SPACE 36: Fan Room (Dichhouse) SPACE 52: Officer Cabin (Male)(2) & Bath GrpB SPACE 53: Officer Cabin (Male)(2) & Bath GrpA SPACE 54: Officer Cabin (Male)(2) & Bath GrpB SPACE 55: Officer Cabin (Male)(2) & Bath GrpB SPACE 57: XO Cabin & Bath</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 21: zoneDec0017: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 19: Electrical Equipment Room SPACE 20: Officer Cabin (Male)(2) & Bath GrpA SPACE 30: Officer Cabin (Male)(2) & Bath GrpA SPACE 31: Officer Cabin (Male)(2) & Bath GrpA</p>			
Deck 5		<p>SUBZONEDECK 36: zoneDec0028: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 17: Boat Gear Locker SPACE 20: Electrical Equipment Room SPACE 20: Enclosed RIB Stowage SPACE 37: Fan Room (Dichhouse) SPACE 38: Officer Cabin (Female)(2) & Bath SPACE 38: Officer Cabin (Female)(2) & Bath</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 28: zoneDec0022: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 6: BC Medical Facility SPACE 10: Bosun Storerom (MainDeck) SPACE 11: Bosun Storerom (MainDeck) SPACE 43: Medical Consultation Room SPACE 44: Medical Consultation Room SPACE 68: PO Cabin (Female)(4) & Bath SPACE 77: Sick Bay</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 29: zoneDec0016: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 16: CO Cabin & Bath SPACE 17: CO Storerom SPACE 28: Engineer Officer Cabin SPACE 48: Officer Cabin (Male)(2) & Bath GrpA SPACE 66: PO Cabin (Male)(4) & Bath GrpB SPACE 67: PO Cabin (Male)(4) & Bath GrpB</p>			
Deck 4	<p>SUBZONEDECK 39: zoneDec0031_c RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 18: Cool Cold Dry Provisions SPACE 31: Fan Room (Hull)</p> <p>SUBZONEDECK 40: zoneDec0031_p RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 46: Mooring Area & Gear Storerom (AH)</p> <p>SUBZONEDECK 41: zoneDec0031_s RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 24: Electrical Equipment Room SPACE 47: Mooring Area & Gear Storerom (AH) SPACE 75: Refrigerator Machinery Room</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 32: zoneDec0027_c RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 40: Gallery & Scullery</p> <p>SUBZONEDECK 34: zoneDec0027_p RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 26: Electrical Equipment Room SPACE 26: Electrical Equipment Room SPACE 26: Electrical Equipment Room SPACE 38: Foul Weather Gear Locker</p> <p>SUBZONEDECK 35: zoneDec0027_s RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 71: Daily Provision Room SPACE 31: Electrical Switchboard Room</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 17: zoneDec0015_c RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 35: Fan Room (Hull) SPACE 60: PO & Specialist Dining Room SPACE 62: PO & Specialist Dining Room</p> <p>SUBZONEDECK 18: zoneDec0015_p RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 15: Cleaning Gear Storerom (Below Decks) SPACE 76: Ships Office SPACE 93: Training Room</p> <p>SUBZONEDECK 19: zoneDec0015_s RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 33: Fan Room (Hull) SPACE 90: Electrical Switchboard Room SPACE 81: PO & Specialist Dining Room</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 11: zoneDec0011_c RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 9: Bosun Storerom (Fwd Mooring)</p> <p>SUBZONEDECK 12: zoneDec0011_p RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 25: Electrical Equipment Room SPACE 25: Electrical Equipment Room SPACE 72: Recreation Room</p> <p>SUBZONEDECK 13: zoneDec0011_s RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 33: Fan Room (Hull) SPACE 90: Electrical Switchboard Room</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 7: zoneDec0007: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 3: Anchoring & Mooring SPACE 45: Mooring Area & Gear Storerom (Fwd)</p>		<p>SUBZONEDECK 3: zoneDec0003: RESIDENT SPACES:</p>
Deck 3	<p>SUBZONEDECK 38: zoneDec0030: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 2: Air Conditioning Room SPACE 69: POL & Paint Locker (Storage) SPACE 70: POL & Paint Locker (Service) SPACE 87: Steering Gear Room SPACE 88: Steering Gear Room SPACE 89: Electrical Switchboard Room</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 32: zoneDec0026: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 1: Air Conditioning Room SPACE 41: General Stowage SPACE 42: Linen Locker SPACE 59: Laundry (Officer & PO) SPACE 86: Laundry (Specialist)</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 16: zoneDec0014: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 63: PO Cabin (Male)(4) & Bath GrpA SPACE 64: PO Cabin (Male)(4) & Bath GrpA SPACE 65: PO Cabin (Male)(4) & Bath GrpA SPACE 74: SD Storerom SPACE 79: Specialist Cabin (Male)(6) GrpA SPACE 79: Specialist Cabin (Male)(6) GrpA SPACE 80: Specialist Cabin (Male)(6) GrpA</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 10: zoneDec0010: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 81: Specialist Cabin (Male)(6) GrpB SPACE 84: Specialist Cabin (Female)(6) SPACE 85: Specialist Cabin (Female)(6)</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 6: zoneDec0006: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 5: Battery Locker and Charging SPACE 13: Chain Locker</p>		<p>SUBZONEDECK 2: zoneDec0002: RESIDENT SPACES:</p>
Deck 2	<p>SUBZONEDECK 37: zoneDec0029: RESIDENT SPACES:</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 23: zoneDec0019: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 0: Air Pump Room SPACE 83: Specialist Cabin (Male)(6) GrpB SPACE 101: Mechanical Workshop (General)</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 15: zoneDec0013: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 75: Sewage Treatment Machinery Room SPACE 82: Specialist Cabin (Male)(6) GrpB SPACE 100: AMR</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 9: zoneDec0009: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 4: Auxiliary Propulsion Room SPACE 82: Specialist Cabin (Male)(6) GrpB</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 5: zoneDec0005: RESIDENT SPACES: SPACE 14: Chain Locker Sump SPACE 39: Fwd Pump Room</p>		<p>SUBZONEDECK 1: zoneDec0001: RESIDENT SPACES:</p>
Deck 1		<p>SUBZONEDECK 30: zoneDec0024: RESIDENT SPACES:</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 14: zoneDec0012: RESIDENT SPACES:</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 8: zoneDec0008: RESIDENT SPACES:</p>	<p>SUBZONEDECK 4: zoneDec0004: RESIDENT SPACES:</p>		<p>SUBZONEDECK 0: zoneDec0000: RESIDENT SPACES:</p>

RUN	Fitness	Min ZD	Avg ZD	Min SP	Avg SP
Run 03	0.681046	0.957526	0.994839	0.036667	0.714946
Without Uncertainty	0.746142	0.957526	0.994839	5.00E-02	0.783282

Fig. 13: Sigma 0.1 Long Term Run Elite

6. Conclusions

The methods of simulating uncertainty in the utility functions have proven to be a useful tool in addressing the robustness of the arrangements being analyzed. In particular, the inboard profile mapping of space allocations gives good insight to candidate general arrangements. It also gives the designer a qualitative grasp of how the model will behave as uncertainty increases within reasonable limits. The analysis done showed that for the habitability ship tested, the general arrangement trends and solutions were stable up through sigma 0.1. When one considers that the first sigma covers approximately 68% of the distribution of points around the given utility value, that 68% of the distribution covers 20% of the available utility values (recall that U is bounded $[0, 1]$). This is considered to be a relatively large amount of uncertainty in the utility values. Most of the stochastic runs were conducted on a 16 Core Desktop with 3 GHz processors. This number of cores made doing stochastic robustness studies of the arrangements a reasonable task. Furthermore, using this type of High Performance Computing (HPC) resource will allow the designer to perform larger designs of experiments to ensure that robust general arrangements are generated by the application.

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The Challenge in Hull Structure Basic Design: From Traditional 2D Drawings to 3D Early Product Model

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Abstract

Ship model definition is usually developed in three stages: concept, initial/basic and detail design. Correct integration of the stages is fundamental for the effectiveness of any shipyard or design office. 3D approaches are widely used in detail design while basic design is still mainly based on 2D drawings, leading to long design periods and cost increases due to re-work and inconsistencies. The main challenges refer to the integration of all stages and disciplines and to the use of a single software tool that must be effective in the generation of class drawings for approval as well as in the transfer of a simplified 3D Model to the analysis and calculation tools. The crucial concept is the reuse of the information. With more than 50 years experience as ship designers, SENER has been able to use this knowledge to develop the proposed approach, using an advanced CAD System, which incorporates the 3D model definition in all stages, thus leading to a design with better quality. The integration is achieved by the use of a single database for all stages and disciplines allowing collaborative design and providing full control of the integrity of the information. The intensive use of topology for the definition of the 3D model allows an efficient management of the modifications as well as an easy evaluation of design alternatives. The solution incorporates tools to facilitate seamless transition to detail design, including block splitting and completion of the model by including attributes for manufacturing stage.

1. Introduction

The definition of a ship project in shipbuilding usually comprises three stages, conceptual, initial/basic and detail design. During the detail design stage the use of a ship 3D model is very common, while the basic design is still based on 2D drawings in many companies, although it is the stage where most of the costs are compromised which implies long design periods, repetition of relevant parts of the work in subsequent stages and a potential for multiple design inconsistencies. This all leads to a major increase in costs and a low production performance. Being aware of this situation and also due to marketing and commercial reasons 3D tools have been introduced recently in the initial design stage. In some way, the problem could be understood as another episode of the traditional debate between the 2D and 3D approaches.

The ship design process is often shared between several design actors that develop different aspects of the engineering. The process is rather sequential as the input for some stages is the output from previous ones. A non exhaustive list of tasks normally includes:

- Development of the main hull structure based in 2D drawings;
- These drawings are sent to Classification Societies (CS) for further analysis and subsequent approval;
- In order to check the structure, CS often develop a 3D Model of the structure, based in the 2D drawings received;
- Indeterminate iterations of the process usually arise, due to the implementation of the comments from the CS into the 2D drawings;
- Detail design activities start once the structure has been approved, taking as starting point the 2D drawings to generate a 3D model that will be used for the early activities in machinery and outfitting;
- Additionally, there are other reasons to generate different 3D models like the needs for special calculations (finite elements analysis, noise, vibrations, etc) as well as the requirements for more realistic (rendered) views of the accommodation spaces.

Fig. 1: Design stages

As an alternative to the traditional method, a new approach is emerging in shipbuilding. It is based on the generation of an early ship 3D model during the basic design stage, by using the same tool as in the detail and production phases. Although at first sight the detail design process might seem more complicated, in the long run the advantages are huge mainly derived from the reuse of information. As a fundamental requirement for the solution to be efficient, the generation of the classification drawings for approval should be simple, as well as the transference of the model to the analysis tools.

2. Philosophy and principles of the FORAN solution

This paper focuses on the approach based in FORAN System and describes the experience of SENER, a company that plays the double role of software developer and ship design agent, in the development of tools for the definition of a ship 3D model in the early design stages, to be used during basic and detail design and production phases too.

The proposed solution is based on a 3D ship product model in which the geometry and the attributes of the elements of the ship are stored. The model is built as an essential part of the engineering work, can be visualized at all stages and can be exploited to obtain information for material procurement and for production. The main characteristics of the ship product model are discussed in the following paragraphs.

Building an early 3D model in FORAN allows to improve the design process of the ship and to study different design alternatives in shorter periods of time, which reduces both delivery schedule and cost. As a result, it is possible to reach a better performance when developing the design and, at the same time, to obtain a product of high quality in a very competitive way. The FORAN solution is based on the integration of all the design stages and disciplines, thanks to a single database, which moreover permits the implementation of collaborative engineering and guarantees the information integrity.

The definition of the model is easy, thanks to the advanced functions implemented in FORAN. The use of a topological model instead of a geometrical model, facilitates its definition, allows the quick study of different design alternatives and simplifies the modifications, which are very common in the

early design stages. The main advantage of the topological definition, where geometrical data are not stored but calculated on-line, is that changes in the main hull surfaces are automatically incorporated in the modified elements, just by reprocessing them. In addition, the topological definition allows the existence of powerful copy commands making thus the definition far more efficient than working only with geometry. Another benefit of the topological model is the size of information stored in the database, much less than for geometrical models.

The key aspect of the design process is the definition of a single ship 3D model, accessible for several designers working concurrently, to be used in all stages of the design. While the project is progressing, the level of detail is increasing and the different parts of the model are subdivided by means of a progressive top-down definition. The solution delivered by FORAN includes tools that facilitate the direct transition from basic to detail design, by means of simple operations that include blocks splitting, the assignment of parts to blocks and the completion of the model with attributes for the manufacturing phase.

3. Modelling sequence

The modelling sequence in FORAN begins with the definition of the material catalogues describing plates and profiles to be used in the design. Once the hull forms, decks, bulkheads and other surfaces are created, the hull structure module is used to create the major openings in all surfaces, the scantling of the main surfaces for plates and profiles as well as the main structural elements (floors, web frames, girders, stringers, etc.). The definition is usually based in the frame and longitudinal systems which allows a full recalculation of the model in case of changes in the spacing between elements.

In early stages, plates and profiles are created as objects representing zones of a surface with common scantling properties. Therefore, the size of the objects is not consistent with the manufacturability, which will be considered in later stages of the design. Other properties like the continuity and watertightness attributes of surfaces or parts of them can be defined at any time.

The sequence of the definition of the model in FORAN has a high degree of flexibility being possible to create both plates and profiles at any time. However, designers would normally follow the same rules as when working in 2D, i.e. to start with the definition of the continuous elements because this will allow the automatic splitting of the non-continuous elements.

The assembly break down to unit or block is optional at this stage, and the level of detail of the 3D model is the one required by the classification drawings, with respect to the type of parts included (brackets, face bars, clips, collars, etc.) as well as to other characteristics (profile end cuts, scallops, notches, etc).

4. Surfaces

Ship moulded surfaces model includes the external hull form, decks, bulkheads, appendages and superstructures. Under FORAN, the geometrical representation for all the surfaces is a collection of trimmed Nurbs patches, Bezier patches, ruled surfaces and implicit surfaces (planes, cylinders, spheres and cones). The surfaces can be imported from files using different generic formats, such as IGES and the AP-216 of the step format.

FORAN has two complementary tools for surface definition. The traditional tool permits the definition of the hull surface, either conventional or special forms, such as non-symmetrical ones, multi-hull and offshore platforms. This tool includes advanced fitting and fairing options and allows several transformations of the hull forms (based in block coefficient, longitudinal position of the center of buoyancy or quadratic) and other operations like lengthening or shortening of a ship that can be easily performed.

FORAN has incorporated recently an additional tool based in the latest-generation of mechanical design that can be used for improving hull forms. A target driven deformation improves the design creativity and the final shape quality, by means of parametric design and global surface modelling.

Fig.4: Different views of the external surface of a ship

5. Hull structure 3D model capabilities

The intensive use of topology makes possible the automatic recalculation of all elements when a modification is performed in upper level concepts (hull and decks surfaces or material standards). This type of topological definition produces important time savings during the development of the basic design, where the modifications are frequent.

5.1 Shell and decks

This 3D curved surfaces context allows the definition of plates, profiles and holes. Work division is made by using the surface and zone concepts, which allows the multi-user access to any surface. A general zone may be used to contain the entities common to several zones.

The following type of profiles can be defined:

- Shell and deck longitudinals
- Frames and deck beams
- General profiles

Profile definition is mainly based on topological references to already existing structural elements, as well as to auxiliary concepts used in the early stage of the design (longitudinal spacing, frame system, other profiles, etc.). The user can easily assign different attributes such as material, scantling and web and thickness orientation. These basic attributes can be completed by adding constructive attributes (parametric web, flange end cuts, etc) at any time of the design process. The profiles can be split up in profile parts later, when the transition from basic to detailed design is performed. Profiles crossing other profiles will automatically generate the necessary cut-outs and scallops.

All types of profiles including flat, curved and twisted are represented as solids. Web, flange and the corresponding end cuts are displayed with a user configurable degree of accuracy

Fig. 5: Shell and decks environment

Due to the intensive use of topology, the definition of the shell and deck plating can start in the early stages of the design, even with a preliminary definition of the hull and decks. In this regard, the basic concepts are:

- Butts: Lines lying on a surface used as aft and fore limits for the plates. Butts can have any shape or be located in transverse planes at any abscissa;
- Seams: Lines lying on a surface used as lower and upper limits for plates, with any geometric shape. Seams are usually defined by means of a set of points on the surface and some additional rules to define the layout;
- Plates: zones of the surface defined by aft and fore butts, and lower and upper seams, with attributes such as gross material, thickness and, optionally, beveling/edge preparation, construction margins and shrinkage factors. Plates can also be the result of breaking down an existing plate in two smaller plates.

Flat and curved plates are represented as solids (including thickness) and the information for plate pre-development is automatically generated allowing thus an early material take-off list.

5.2 Internal structure

The internal structure context is based on the same high performance topological and visualization environment of the curved surfaces, but applied to a section lying on a plane. This environment provides a set of advanced functions for the easy definition and modification of plates (flat, flanged and corrugated), straight and curved stiffeners, holes, face bars, standard plates, on and off plane brackets, collars and others.

Fig. 6: Internal structure environment

It is possible to have several sections in memory making easy operations, like copy or multiple editions of elements in different sections. The work division is made by using the section, structural element and zone concepts, which allows multi-user access to any section. The main features are:

- Predefined best practices support through the use of structural element concept, defining default constructive values and parameters for plates, profiles and face bars;
- Automatic part splitting, using the crossing/not crossing structural element attribute;
- High productivity tools, like one click plate definition, reduction to the minimum of the auxiliary geometry and join and split functions for plates and profiles;
- XML based high performance topological definition language for the definition of plates, profiles and face bars;
- Profile and face bars definition using standard profile cross-sections, parametric cut-outs and parametric web and flange end cuts;
- Automatic cut-outs insertion for both plates and profiles;
- Standard or free shape hole definition and automatic application to the affected plates;
- High productivity commands including split, multi-edit and multi-copy for both plates and profiles in the same or in different sections and structural elements.

6. Output from the 3D model

The next paragraphs describe the tangible outputs derived from an early hull structure 3D model like drawings, reports and models to be used in the analysis and calculation tools. In addition, there is other important output. The existence of a 3D model makes the tasks related to the outfitting basic design more efficient.

6.1 Main output: Classification drawings for approval

Although the approach described in this paper is more general, any improvement in the process of basic design must consider the fact that the main output during the hull structure basic design stage is to obtain the classification drawings for approval. Classification drawings are symbolic drawings of different types, like:

- Shell and deck drawings (different views, including expansion)
- Typical planar sections
- Other detail drawings

Fig. 7: Example of an automatically generated classification drawing

The drawing generation in FORAN is managed by a single module, which covers the output drawings of all design disciplines (general, hull structure, outfitting, electrical and accommodation). The drawing generation is completely user configurable, as the final aspect of the drawings depends on the user requirements. Drawings are generated directly from the 3D product model, and the 2D entities that represent the product model are linked to the 3D elements, and are always updated with the latest version of the product model. A symbolic representation for modelled elements is possible and different visualization methods are available.

The drawing generation module includes also a function to reprocess the drawing after changes in the model, and at the same time keeping any manual modifications introduced by the user in the drawing. There are also options for automatic dimensioning and labelling by means of user-configurable formats and templates representing different attributes of the selected elements (identification, scantling, profile cross sections, end-cuts and others). These entities are also linked to the product model elements. The drawings generated are compatible with most of the standard drawing formats too.

6.2 Link with finite element tools

One of the most relevant aspects during the basic engineering of a ship is the structural analysis by means of the application of the finite elements method (FEM), which makes possible to improve and validate the feasibility of the design. In practice, it is a laborious task that requires the preparation of a suitable model for calculation, meshing, the application of loads and constraints, processing, post-processing and analysis of the results.

Most of the finite element tools include standard formats for the direct import of 3D CAD models, but they fail when these models come from the shipbuilding industry due to the complexity of the ship models. The effort required in the manual simplification of the model (model cleaning process in the Fig. 8) is such that it is more efficient to repeat the model with a calculation-oriented approach, which slows down the analysis process dramatically.

Fig. 8: Meshing workflow

The use of a ship model already created in a 3D CAD for FEM analysis would optimise the design performance in the early stages. For this, there must be an efficient link between both tools so that a simplified ship model adapted to each type of calculation can be exported directly from CAD.

SENER's approach to this problem combines its broad experience in the development of a CAD/CAM shipbuilding tool with innovative solutions to obtain the expected results: a link that makes possible to export a simplified ship model, leveraging its topological characteristics. Functional algorithms in FORAN allow the creation of an intelligent model, simplifying, filtering and deleting unnecessary data to guarantee the quality of the model transferred.

Among other functionalities, the user can decide in FORAN:

- Whether the plates are translated as surfaces by the neutral axis or the moulded line;
- The automatic assignment of colors to every material and profile scantling;
- Whether the profiles will be translated as surfaces or as curves;
- The minimum area to discard the transfer of holes and brackets.

All structure entities will be subject to an “idealization” process aiming to simplify the 3D model by using the following criteria:

- For plates, notches, scallops, fillets and chamfers will be removed from the outer contour;
- For profiles (either via surfaces or curves), notches, scallops, macro-holes, end-cuts and profile extensions will be removed;
- Surfaces created as plate or profiles are extended topologically to the moulded line/neutral axis of the surface used in its definition. This simplification is applied on every intersection line with other surfaces used in the plate or profile definition;
- Plates are splitted in different surfaces using the profile layout and any other marking line;
- Corrugated and flanged plates are splitted in planar faces;
- Surfaces sewing, every two surfaces created by a previous one split will be sewn on the join line;
- Profiles sewing: If the profile is translated as a surface, flange and web will be sewn. Translated profile web surface will be sewn to its underlying plate surface too;
- Plate limits are extended to the surfaces used in its definition;

Fig.9: FORAN FEM-Link Overview

6.3 Other output

One of the advantages inherent to integrated 3D applications refers to the easiness of data extraction as the whole product model is stored on a single source of information. With FORAN, different types of reports that can be generated are configurable and can be exported to most of the standard formats like Excel, HTML and ASCII. Fixed contents reports like steel order (plates and profiles) and configurable bill of materials can be obtained based on query conditions decided by the user. Report contents will depend on the degree of definition of the project.

Among others, the following reports can be obtained in FORAN:

- Weight and center of gravity
- Painted areas
- Material take off
- Bill of materials
- Welding lengths

BILL OF MATERIALS SUMMARY												
UNIT No: 22												
REVISION: A												
DATE: 24-04-2006												
NEST TYPE	FORMAT NUMBER	MATERIAL QUALITY	RAW MATERIAL DESCRIPTION	NO OF PLATES/PROFILES	NO OF PARTS	GROSS WEIGHT [kg]	NET WEIGHT [kg]	SCRAP	LEFTOVERS WEIGHT [kg]	REAL GROSS WEIGHT [kg]	REAL SCRAP	
PLATES	1	A	12000 x 3000 x 6,0	1	4	1695,6	1470,5	13,28%	0,0	1695,6	13,28%	
PLATES	2	A	8000 x 3000 x 6,0	2	21	2260,8	1845,3	18,38%	223,3	2037,5	9,43%	
PLATES	11	A	12000 x 3000 x 6,5	5	15	9184,5	7976,5	13,15%	829,7	8354,8	4,53%	
PLATES	21	A	12000 x 3000 x 7,0	2	2	3956,4	2248,3	43,17%	1249,6	2706,8	16,94%	
PLATES	41	A	12000 x 2600 x 8,0	2	19	3918,7	1943,8	50,40%	791,9	3126,8	37,83%	
PLATES	42	A	8000 x 2600 x 8,0	3	127	3918,7	2806,3	28,39%	155,1	3763,6	25,44%	
PLATES	53	A	12000 x 2000 x 8,5	2	5	3202,8	1909,2	40,39%	1101,0	2101,8	9,16%	
PLATES	62	A	8000 x 2600 x 9,0	3	151	4408,6	3393,8	23,02%	0,0	4408,6	23,02%	
PLATES	72	A	8000 x 2600 x 9,5	4	8	6204,6	3137,4	49,43%	1454,2	4750,4	33,96%	
PLATES	81	A	12000 x 2600 x 10,0	5	191	12246,0	10378,1	15,25%	702,1	11543,9	10,10%	
PLATES	82	A	8000 x 2600 x 10,0	1	27	1632,8	1413,0	13,46%	0,0	1632,8	13,46%	
PLATES	121	A	12000 x 2600 x 12,0	1	2	2939,0	1916,3	34,80%	347,8	2591,3	26,05%	
PLATES	122	A	12000 x 2400 x 12,0	6	65	16277,8	12187,7	25,13%	2652,8	13625,0	10,55%	
PLATES	123	A	8000 x 2600 x 12,0	5	27	9796,8	6763,7	30,96%	1622,9	8173,9	17,25%	
PLATES	143	A	8000 x 2600 x 13,0	1	11	2122,6	1502,8	29,20%	0,0	2122,6	29,20%	
PLATES	144	A	8000 x 2400 x 13,0	4	4	7837,4	4654,0	40,62%	1993,0	5838,4	20,29%	
PLATES	163	A	8000 x 2600 x 15,0	1	9	2449,2	1922,3	21,51%	0,0	2449,2	21,51%	
PLATES	184	A	8000 x 2400 x 15,0	8	104	18086,4	14720,7	18,61%	0,0	18086,4	18,61%	
PLATES	500	A	1680 x 1540 x 7,5	1	4	152,3	89,5	41,26%	0,0	152,3	41,26%	
PLATES	503	A	1120 x 1100 x 9,0	1	5	87,0	14,0	83,90%	61,4	25,6	45,34%	
PLATES	565	A	4200 x 1090 x 9,5	1	1	341,4	166,1	51,36%	56,1	285,3	41,80%	
PLATES	2026	D	4300 x 2400 x 60,0	1	2	4860,7	3880,3	19,99%	0,0	4860,7	19,99%	
PLATES	2071	A	8000 x 840 x 13,0	1	4	685,8	347,6	49,31%	0,0	685,8	49,31%	
PLATES	2127	A	2600 x 990 x 11,0	1	2	222,3	143,0	35,67%	0,0	222,3	35,67%	
PLATES	2173	A	2700 x 2400 x 30,0	1	6	1526,0	646,7	57,63%	0,0	1526,0	57,63%	
PLATES	2174	A	3860 x 2400 x 30,0	1	7	2181,7	1647,8	24,47%	0,0	2181,7	24,47%	

Fig. 10: Example of a bill of materials

7. Transition to detail design through the reuse of the information

The key point to for any software solution aiming to provide a complete solution for ship design and manufacturing is the capability to provide smooth transition between the stages of the design avoiding rework and delays. Thus, as a logical continuation of the basic design, FORAN provides tools for subdividing and joining plates and profiles, and also features additional attributes for detail design such as bevelling, construction margins and shrinkage factors, and also for defining parts that are not relevant during the basic design stages.

The way from the initial to the basic and the detailed design is also the way from the conceptual and abstract to the concrete and manufacturable. Large conceptual parts useful to analyze for instance weight and structural behavior must be converted in manufacturable parts reusing all the information provided in the conceptual stages and detailing when necessary. The split concept is basic in this transition, for example large longitudinal layouts are splitted into manufacturable profile parts inheriting layout attributes and with the appropriated split properties according to end-cuts, margins, etc. The split concept is applied to any kind of part, from bulkhead profiles to curved hull plates.

The level of detail not only concerns geometry but also attributes. Part attributes irrelevant in conceptual stages become critical in detailed design. In order to provide a smooth transition, tools to modify, check and copy attributes of large groups of pieces are provided.

The block subdivision is perhaps one of the most critical points in ship design regarding the transition between design stages. Although split and refinement tools can be used for block subdivision, some specific tools are provided in order to perform automatic recalculation of parts when the block butts are modified. Assignment of parts to units can be done at any time by means of a powerful graphical selection tool.

Finally, in this stage it is the right time to complete the detail design by defining those parts which are not relevant for the basic design stage.

8. Advantages of an early 3D model

It is well known that most of the costs of a ship are compromised during the initial design stages. The proposed solution delivers tangible benefits as it optimizes the process by reducing the time dedicated to design and consequently the cost. Main advantages can be summarized as follows:

- Shorter evaluation of different design alternatives due to the high level of topology that allows an automatic recalculation in case of upper level modifications;
- More accurate design due to the use of a 3D tool;
- Less risk of inconsistencies comparing to the 2D approach in which every view is independent and has no relation with the others. Instead, the 3D approach, combines the implicit intelligence associated to the model by means of certain attributes (continuity, watertightness) with the graphical checking performed by the user leading to a design with better quality;
- Easier link with analysis and calculation tools based in the existence of a single 3D model that, for the purpose of other calculations, is subject to an idealization process for easier management in the FEM/FEA tools;
- Early estimation of materials and weights, including welding and painting;
- Easier co-ordination among disciplines as hull structure and various disciplines of outfitting are represented in the same underlying product model. This has obvious advantages in terms of interference or collision checks and leads to a better outfitting design regarding the general arrangement definition and critical compartments layout;
- Due to the incremental development of the model as the design evolves, there is a seamless transition to detail design based in the reuse of data

9. Possible drawbacks and potential for improvements

In general, designers are more familiar with the 2D based approach and therefore in certain organisations may be difficult the implementation of the 3D approach at this stage. Obviously, the starting point for a 3D approach cannot be an empty sheet as certain key documents like schematic general arrangement and midship section are available prior to the starting of 3D activities.

The discussion at this point would be formulated as “Model efficiency versus drawing efficiency”. The procedure described in this paper is absolutely focused on the use of a 3D tool and drawings must be understood as a consequence (sub-product) of the existence of the 3D model.

10. Summary and conclusions

FORAN improves design quality, provides higher precision and reduces the risk of inconsistencies. The rapid evaluation of several design alternatives and the early estimation of materials, weights,

welding and painting are additional advantages, in addition with the efficient link with finite element analysis tools. Finally, it also facilitates the definition of the outfitting (general layout and layout of critical compartments) and improves the coordination between disciplines. In conclusion, the key points are the simple transition to detail design and the reuse of information.

This substantial change in the development of the basic design stage, which is now being required and implemented, is expected to become the routine way of working in the future, particularly when the continuation with the detail design is considered and/or outfitting design is part of the scope of work.

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“The Virtual Fleet” – Use of Extended Conceptual Design Data for Trend Analysis of Inland Ship Characteristics

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Abstract

This paper discusses the creation of a virtual fleet of inland ships, featuring a large number of systematically varied vessel pre-designs, including a 3D general arrangement and steel plan. These serve as the required reference data on which to base predictions of vessel characteristics, even for vessels that are proportioned substantially different from those sailing around today. The paper starts out with a description of the design model developed in order to enable the rapid creation of inland vessel designs, continues with a description of the virtual fleet and concludes with a first set of trend-lines derived from the data of that virtual fleet.

1. Introduction

When starting the conceptual design of a new ship, it is an age-old custom to use reference data from other ships. In fact many preliminary estimation methods in the maritime industry, such as those for steel weight and powering are based on regression analysis of existing designs. In the inland ship building industry, such an approach runs into problems for two main reasons. The first is that little research has been carried out to arrive at such estimation methods, while methods from seagoing shipping can not be adopted due to the different requirements on the steel structure and hull form, resulting in a lack of suitable estimation methods, even for more or less standard vessels. The second reason is that the inland navigation community is increasingly exploring the use of differently sized vessels, such as very wide and low-draught vessels for use on the Danube and/or to deal with low water levels on the Rhine, as a result of which reference data from existing vessels can not be extrapolated to the new vessel's dimensions, as becomes apparent from Fig. 1, which displays results from a database of over 800 vessels built since 1996. Horizontal lines 1 and 2 represent lock width restrictions at 9.6 and 11.45 m beam, while Lines A and C represent the lengths at which an increase in crew is required according to ROS-R regulations as set forward by the Central Commission for Navigation on the Rhine, at 70 and 87 meters length. Line B and D present lock length limitations (85 and 110 m) and line D represents the maximum allowable length of an ‘indivisible’ ship on the largest inland waterways. Vessels that can be broken up (coupled units and pushtows) are allowed to have a larger length. Fig. 1 also reveals that there are no (modern) reference vessels for a very wide, shallow draught vessel.

Fig.1: Length and beam of existing inland vessels.

To overcome these issues, a model was developed with which it is possible to create conceptual designs of inland ships in a matter of minutes. In this model, weight of the steel structure is determined based on Germanischer Lloyd-prescribed scantlings (*Germanischer Lloyd, 2006*) and geometric data from the CAD model of the design, while weight of equipment is based on estimates that start from actual weights and sizes as specified by suppliers and/or actual vessel data. This way the lack of available estimation methods is circumvented. Due to the ability to generate such a design in a matter of minutes it becomes possible to design a large number of vessels, which systematically cover a design space that may extend well beyond the design space of existing vessels. Finally, using this newly created design data from a virtual fleet of ships, it becomes possible to derive new design trendlines for inland ships.

In this paper, the tool developed for the creation of the virtual fleet is discussed, as are the first results from that virtual fleet, valid for general cargo/container ships.

2. The developed design model

When making a preliminary design of a ship, manual input from the designer usually forms a major cost and time component in the design process. Therefore, if the input of the designer can be limited to making the most important choices and the more menial work can be delegated to the computer, the design process can be sped up dramatically, thereby creating the ability to make more designs in the same amount of time. The fact that for the issue under consideration in this paper, we are looking at 'simple' ships in the design stage where no interaction with specialists from other disciplines is necessary yet greatly eases the shift from manual to automated actions.

Over the last few years, several institutes have worked on automation of early stage ship design. To name but a few, *Nick Kirtley (2009)* of the University of Michigan presents a genetic-algorithm-based approach to automatic generation of warship lay-outs. Van Oers of Delft University of Technology has simultaneously developed an approach that goes several steps further, resulting in large numbers of physically feasible computer-generated (war) ship designs, which he elaborates in several papers, among which *Van Oers et al. (2009)*, which elaborately describes the approach followed. Both Nick Kirtley and Van Oers focus on complex ship types, in which space allocation is a crucial design aspect. For simpler ships the models developed for seagoing tugs by *Stroo (2009)* and for inland push convoys by *Van Hassel (2009)* show the potential of linking a CAD program (in both cases Rhinoceros 3D) to an external system (in both cases Quaestor) to find the most suitable ship for a specific task.

In this case, the solution to the challenge of speeding up conceptual design of inland ships was found in the ability to script commercial general purpose CAD package Rhinoceros 3D (Rhino) and to interface it with other software such as MS Excel in order to incorporate non-geometry-related calculations. This way the input values for the CAD program can be calculated externally and directly transmitted to it. Rhino can then do what it is good at (draw objects, perform Boolean operations, calculate volumes, surface areas, centers of gravity,...) and feed this data back to a non-geometry-related calculation program.

The work was inspired earlier work by *Van Oers and van Hees (2006)*, who linked Rhino to knowledge system Quaestor to allow rapid generation of conceptual designs for naval vessels. It shows some parallels with the work of Stroo and Van Hassel discussed above.

At the core of the developed solution is Rhino's ability to be scripted from an external source. For the purpose of the work done here, RhinoScript code was incorporated in Visual Basic for Application (VBA) code, which is an integral part of MS Excel. As an example, powering calculations following the method described by *Holtrop, Mennen and van Terwisga (1990)* together with propeller data as described by *Oosterveld and Van Oossanen (1975)*, could be used to determine required power to be delivered by the main machinery for propulsion purposes, based on which in turn weight and dimensions can be derived. Through the link with Rhino, these elements can then directly be imported and

fitted into the vessel design. In a similar way, Excel can be used to calculate structural scantlings based on Germanischer Lloyd's rules for inland ships, which can then be fed into RhinoScript to develop a 3D steel plan, the geometric data of which can in turn be fed right back into excel to make estimates of the ship's steel weight and center of gravity. The approach chosen also allows creation of easy-to-use VBA menus from which to drive the program.

All in all, the program developed by this method allows a user to make major design choices himself and allow the computer to do the rest of the work, resulting in a 3D arrangement, weight estimate, cost estimate and starting data for stability and loading condition calculations in 5 to 10 minutes, resulting in a first feasibility study that can be done in under half an hour. As a first indication of the variety of ships that can be designed with the model, Fig. 2 displays selected results.

Fig.2: Selected designs created with the model

3. Program flow

In this chapter the basic workings of the program will be elaborated. Fig. 3 presents a flowchart of the design model, with the following colour coding:

- Blue boxes represent user input
- Orange boxes represent pure Excel-based operations
- Yellow boxes represent operations where VBA-code, sometimes in conjunction with Excel, is used to operate Rhino
- Light green boxes represent (intermediate) results

What becomes apparent from the flow chart below, is that the user has substantial freedom to choose the ship features he/she wants: Hull form can be manipulated by selection of a number of different basic bow and stern forms from a database and scale these to the desired length. The user can also define power plant lay-out in terms of number, power and location (fore or aft) of main engines and/or generator sets, but is assisted in this by Excel-based powering predictions and estimates of the power use of other consumers. This, combined with the choice for steering devices (conventional rudders or steerable thrusters) and bow steering devices (tunnel thruster, 2-, 3- or 4-duct pumpjet), the ability to choose a raisable or-non-raisable wheelhouse and to select floor area and number of tiers for accommodations fore and aft, results in a high level of freedom to arrange bow and stern sections but at the same time limits user inputs to entry of a limited set of values and selection of a number of items from drop-down menus. In the second part of the work, further user input is possible in the selection of lay-out of holds, arrangement of double hull, main frame cross-section, framing system(s) and spacing of structural elements.

Based on the various user inputs related to the fore and aft part of the ship, the program will first create a hull form and table of offsets, fit selected equipment in it and define the spaces in these parts of the ship. Whatever space is left between fore and aft part may be filled with holds and double hull, based on user requirements. Once this is done, the structure will be added to the spaces and a steel weight and center of gravity is derived from that. Once combined with weights of the various pieces of equipment, a lightweight can be arrived at. At the end of the design process, the combination of

lightweight, hydrostatic data and the ability to add (cargo) weights and fill tanks allows the user to quickly determine the vessel's ability to safely carry a certain amount of cargo.

Fig.3: Program flow chart

4. The virtual fleet

With the newly achieved ability to generate an elaborate conceptual design of inland ship in minutes, it is now possible to generate a large number of ship designs, covering a desired design space. In the first version of the virtual fleet, The design space extends from a kempenaar-sized ship of 63* 7 *2 m LBT to a non-existent ship design of 150*17*4 m LBT. For the analysis at hand, the simplest type of inland ship is reviewed: Dry cargo vessels with diesel-direct drives and no major ballast system. This ship type is the most common type among inland vessels. Of this vessel type, 27 designs are made, with lengths of 63, 110 and 150 m., beams of 7, 11 and 17 m. and draughts of 2, 3 and 4 m. Through this systematic variation of vessel dimensions, a matrix of datapoints is created on which to base design trendlines. Of course the vessels' propulsion system and equipment are scaled too, so they still meet the required design speed and comply with rules and regulations.

Fig.4: The virtual fleet

5. First results from the virtual fleet

A major aspect of inland vessel designs is lightweight of the ship, both due to the fact that every kilo of vessel weight is a kilo less cargo carrying capacity and due to the fact that steel hulls for inland ships are commonly priced at X euro per kg, implying that the lower the weight, the lower the capital cost of the ship. Fig. 5 displays the results of lightweights for the 63 m vessel (continuous line), 110 m vessel (long dashes) and 150 m vessel (short dashes) at their respective draughts of 2, 3 and 4 m.

Fig.5: Lightweight vs vessel main dimensions

This graph yields the expected result that as size increases, so does weight, but it also reveals that the narrower the vessel becomes, the closer together the weights for vessels of different lengths lie. This is due to the smaller weight contribution of the midship, compared to less beam-dependent variables such as accommodation, rudders, generator sets, wheelhouses, masts etc. etc.

What is more interesting however is to display this weight as a fraction of LBT: What we can see from the graph below is that grouping is now different, based on draught rather than size: The highest cluster of lines represents a draught of 2 m, followed by that at 3 and 4 m. This can be explained by the fact that a double bottom is relatively heavy compared to the sides. As vessel draught (and depth) increase, the relative contribution of the double bottom to the total weight decreases. What the graph also reveals is that as the vessel gets longer, its becomes relatively heavier, which can be explained by increasing bending moments, requiring a stronger structure, but also by heavier equipment due to the increased equipment requirements to reach the same speed, maneuver the vessel and moor it. Finally the graph reveals the effect of widening the vessel: the wider the vessel the smaller the light-weight/LBT fraction becomes, as a result of the fact that relatively little material needs to be added compared to the gain in displacement.

Fig.6: Lightweight/LBT vs vessel main dimensions

When reviewing the subdivision of lightweight into hull steel weight and weight of all other parts (machinery, propellers, rudders, piping, ducting cabling, mooring gear, accommodation,.....) , we can see that its share ranges from 15 to 30% of the total weight. Fig. 7 shows results for the vessels discussed grouped by vessel size (so first 3 groups represent the 63 m vessel, groups 4 to 6 represent 110 m vessel and groups 7 to 9 represent the 150 m vessel), draught (first group of each set of 3 groups represents 2 m, second represents 3 m and third represents 4 m draught) and beam (first column of each group represents 7 m beam, second represents 11 m and the third represents a beam of 17 m.

Fig.7: Subdivision of lightweight into steel and miscellaneous items

Here it is necessary to remark that for the designs from which the data are derived, some vessel parameters are adapted to the type of vessel: the narrow vessels have been assigned smaller accommodation than the wide vessels (60 m² instead of 100 m²) and the 63 m. vessel was given a lower design speed of 18 km/h instead of 19 km/h since it is intended for canals rather than the main rivers. Finally, in some cases concessions had to be made to the design speed due to the fact that the limited propeller diameter did not allow the generation of sufficient thrust, without changing parameters like the propeller diameter to draught ratio, which would make a fair comparison impossible.

6. Outlook for the future

The virtual fleet described in this paper is only one of many that can be conceived. Work continues to arrive at more discriminating estimations and to include other ship types than just dry cargo/container vessels. In early 2010, the finishing touches are made to the model extension that allows proper modeling of tank vessels, including semi-automatic creation of a deck piping system and proper ballast system. Later in the year more elaborate virtual fleets will be developed.

Fig.8: Conceptual design of a tank vessel

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A Concept of Topological Optimization for Bow Structures

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Abstract

Nowadays, Finite Element Analyses are state-of-the-art in assessing the mechanical behavior of structures. They are employed even at very different levels of structural design – from first concepts to final details. However, they are generally used to verify structures that have already been designed based on rules and experience or to give indications of design changes. In this paper, a concept for novel stress related design proposals is shown. This approach is based on applying optimization techniques in direct combination with Finite Element Analyses already in the very first stages of structural design. A brief general introduction to the optimization problem is given, and the basic theory of topological optimization is outlined. After showing the applicability of the proposed concept to optimization at the level of detail design with the example of a floor, it is applied to the preliminary structural design of a bow. The results give indications for new design proposals. Using such an approach, the number of iterations within the classical design spiral may decrease and novel specific steel structures become possible.

1. Introduction

In the past, structural ship design was mainly experience and rule based. Today, the increasing use of first principle design methods such as FEM (Finite Element Method) allows a faster and more accurate evaluation of structures. With ever higher computer performance, numerical optimization has recently been brought into focus. By now several optimization methodologies have been applied to improve structural design in the maritime industry, e.g. *Riedel (2000)*, *Rahman (1998)*. Although topology optimization is widely spread in other branches of industry, as in the automotive and aircraft sector, it is hardly used to optimize ship structures.

Nevertheless, using topology optimization in the early design phase can reduce the overall time in development. With this optimization tool, rapid creation of design concepts is possible. Since these design concepts basically fulfill the general product requirements, the number of design iterations and thus time to market are decreased, *Schramm (2005)*.

The purpose of this paper is to show the influence of topology optimization on the ship design process. Moreover, the objective is to develop an optimization driven design process based on topology optimization and first principle methods. Firstly, the proposed approach of topology optimization is applied to a floor – showing its potential even for the phase of detail design. In the next step, a first concept for novel bow structures is created by this approach to demonstrate its applicability in the phase of concept design.

2. Structural Optimization

2.1. Optimization Methodologies

Following the design spiral, *Evans (1959)*, structural optimization is divided into “concept design” and “detail design”. Furthermore, concept design can be subdivided into topology and topography optimization. In case of optimizing a structure’s topology, just the design space is set as boundary. The arrangement of structural elements and cut-outs is completely left to the optimization algorithm. Topography optimization is limited to plate or sheet structures. The result leads to a pattern of different beads and can influence the structural properties of a component without changing weight.

Size optimization changes only explicit values, e.g. sheet-thickness, diameter or cross-sectional area. Changing the shape or profile of a component is called shape optimization. Fig. 1 gives an overview of this classification of structural optimization.

Fig. 1: Classification of structural optimization

For a general optimization problem with n design variables x , m inequality constraints and q equality constraints the mathematical optimization problem is given by:

$$\min f(\vec{x}) \quad (1)$$

$$g_j(\vec{x}) \leq 0 \quad j = 1, \dots, m \quad (2)$$

$$h_k(\vec{x}) = 0 \quad k = 1, \dots, q$$

Minimizing the objective function f leads to the solution of the optimization problem if the constraints are fulfilled. Typical objective functions of an optimization problem are to minimize volume, mass, stress, displacement or to maximize stiffness or the first eigenfrequencies. However, these objective functions are mostly accompanied by constraints. For instance, minimizing a component's mass without any restriction would lead to a design with zero mass. Maximizing the stiffness of a structure with a given mass, volume or stress constraint is a common topology optimization problem.

2.2. Topology Optimization

To use topology optimization in combination with FEM, it is necessary to define a design space that is filled with solid elements. It has to be emphasized that during the optimization it is not possible to delete elements to create holes and cut-outs. Therefore, the component is approximated by a density distribution. Thus, the normalized density of each element is a design variable and is allowed to change between the values of 0 and 1.

To define such a density approach, two methods are generally used in the context of mathematical topology optimization. The homogenization method, *Bendsøe and Kikuchi (1988)*, fills the design space with orthotropic material. Homogenization leads to a microstructure that allows relating the element's density and Young's modulus.

The basic idea of the second method, SIMP (Solid Isotropic Material with Penalization), which is used in this paper, is to set up a relationship between the normalized density as design variable x and the normalized E -modulus of a finite element, Eq. (3) and Fig. 2.

$$\frac{\rho_i}{\rho_0} = x_i \quad x_i^p = \frac{E_i}{E_0}; \quad p > 1 \tag{3}$$

Fig. 2: Elastic modulus, density relation

The parameter p is a penalty factor which penalizes densities between 0 and 1.

3. Application to Ship Structures

3.1. Topology Optimization for Detail Design

Proving the potential of topology optimization, a floor of a 2500 TEU container vessel was analysed. Using the structural symmetry, only half of a floor, Fig. 3, has to be considered. The component is subjected to container stack loads and water pressure on the hull. The objective of the optimization is to maximize the stiffness of the floor under a given mass constraint. The optimization result is the density distribution shown in Fig. 4. In a second step, elements with small density values are eliminated and the resulting design proposal has to be remeshed for further stress analyses. In contrast to the basic design of the floor, the von Mises Stress decreases by 27% and the mass by 40%.

Fig. 3: Original floor design

Fig. 4: Density distribution of optimized floor

3.2. Topology Optimization for Concept Design

The geometry of the considered bow structure is based on a CNG (Compressed Natural Gas) tanker in an early design stage. The principle dimensions are given in Table I.

Table I: Principle Dimensions

L_{oa}	294,54 m
L_{wl}	286,62 m
B_{wl}	50,00 m
T_{dwl}	12,20 m
Δ	151293 t
C_b	0.86

Fig. 5: Fixed structural elements

Fig. 6: Design proposal based on optimized density distribution

Fig. 7: Design proposal – longitudinal section off centerline

Starting point for the numerical model is an IGES-file containing only the tanker's hull. A couple of structural elements (decks, shell, bulkhead etc), which are expected to be essential regarding the global structural strength and ship's functionality, are set to be fixed, Fig. 5. These structural elements are

meshed with shell elements and remain unchanged by the optimization. The design space, in which optimization is performed, is filled with solid elements. The bow is then subjected to lateral pressure on decks and hull according to the rules of Germanischer Lloyd. The optimization problem is again set up to maximize stiffness under a given mass constraint.

Based on the resulting density distribution, Figs. 6 and 7 illustrate the design proposal where “unused” elements, i.e. elements with low density, are not depicted. The bottom of the ship’s bow contains a rather high amount of material, which arises from the high slamming load on the bottom. Fig. 7 shows a longitudinal section of the design proposal, which is located off centerline. Above the waterline, large regions of void space are seen, which are available for mechanical components to be installed.

In a first step, the density distribution resulting from topology optimization can be just a basis for new dimensions of plate thickness and stiffener cross sections. In a second step, however, further interpretation of the density distribution can lead to a radical new design: Following the orientation of the remaining material as seen in Figs. 6 and 7, “new” stiffeners at the bow have to be installed mainly diagonally.

4. Topology Optimization within the Design Process

In this paper, it has been shown that topology optimization is suitable for both detail design and concept design. Examples from other industries, *Raasch (1998)*, *Amorosi (2006)*, indicate that especially in the early design step, topology optimization gives the largest benefit to a design process. Therefore, the example of optimizing a bow structure in the context of concept design has been shown above. The design proposal for the bow leads to a novel structural concept. On first sight, arriving at a detail design starting with this novel concept seems rather impractical for a typical ship steel structure. However, bow structures are anyway very complex with a large number of curved panels. This leads – in a sense – to a high degree of freedom for the detail design. Therefore, bow structures are a perfect topic to prove practicality of topology optimization in shipbuilding.

Substitution of a single design step by optimization methods is not achievable as optimization is just an extension to the present design process. However, if topology optimization could be integrated into the design process at the stage of structural design, Fig. 8, it will decrease the number of iterations within the design spiral and therefore lead to faster developments with lower costs. Furthermore, topology optimization could be implemented at the stage of structural analysis besides size and shape optimization.

5. Conclusion

In the present study, topology optimization has been applied to the detail design of a floor and the concept design of a bow structure. It has been shown that topology optimization is suitable for both with encouraging results. However, the largest possibilities are expected to lie in the early stages of design. For the concept design of the bow structure, a design proposal has been presented. In a next step, a steel plan has to be derived from this proposal. Although the results are promising, the boundary conditions and loads have to be discussed. The result of the optimization will definitely be sensitive to the loads applied. Further work will concentrate on structural optimization under different loadcases. Another aspect that has to be pointed out is that new designs and in particular designs with a new topology become more important to a growing market of special purpose ships.

Fig. 8: Integration of topology optimization into the design process

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Trajectory Design for Autonomous Underwater Vehicles for Basin Exploration

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Abstract

This paper focuses on the design of efficient trajectories for an autonomous underwater vehicle descending into a basin. The vehicle is assumed to be an oblate spheroid with its actuation generated by a set of thrusters. We will consider several thrusters configuration, both fully actuated and under-actuated. These assumptions are based on two existing vehicles, the Omni Directional Intelligent Navigator, and the Deep Phreatic Thermal Explorer. In this paper we develop control schemes guiding the dive of the vehicle in some of the most common scenarios found in underwater sink holes. We assume a rough knowledge of the environment, thereby focusing the design of our trajectories on exploiting the capabilities of the autonomous underwater vehicles in an effort to map its environment efficiently to the required degree of resolution.

1. Introduction

Since the discovery of extremophiles in the 1970s, the plausibility that life originated from these microorganisms capable of surviving in the most remarkable circumstances has become a frequent interest in the search of life's origins. Extremophiles are not found only in places of intense cold, dryness, or immense pressure and heat, totally unsuitable for more complex life, but also in moderate environments of these sorts as well. It can be asserted that because of these organisms, researchers and scientists of ocean and space exploration are collaborating, significantly more than previously, to assess Earth's origin of life in the pursuit of extraterrestrial life. Access to these organisms is extremely challenging, but with the recent advances in the development of autonomous underwater vehicles (AUVs), researchers and scientists now have the capability to design missions intent on targeting and acquiring these hard to reach microorganisms.

Projects as the NASA funded Deep Phreatic Thermal Explorer (DEPTHX), engineered by Stone Aerospace, and its evolution Environmentally Non-Disturbing Under-ice Robotic Antarctic Explorer (ENDURANCE) give heed to such a claim. Both projects involve deploying an AUV to survey, exploiting simultaneous localization and mapping techniques (SLAM), the underwater environment of Lake Bonney in Antarctica (ENDURANCE) and a group of five sinkholes of Sistema Zacatón (DEPTHX) in preparation and anticipation for an opportunity to explore a moon of Jupiter, Europa, searching for life in its icy oceans (*Fairfield et al. 2008*). Moreover, the development of tools, such as the suspended-particle rosette SUPR (*Breier et al. 2009*) and the autonomous microbial sampler (AMS) for biological sampling on remote operated vehicles (ROVs) (*Taylor et al. 2006*) and AUVs, has paved the path for sophisticated means of properly collecting samples for examination. Currently, strategies involving AUVs used in teams to survey hydrothermal vents, environments where extremophiles dwell, by cooperating and localizing collectively (*Caiti et al. 2007*) as well as other strategies utilizing sonar sensors to create maps and eventually photograph hydrothermal vent sites (*German et al. 2008*) and predetermining of trajectories for the AUV to follow while sampling in order to decide on a site to study (*Ferri et al. 2008*) have been proposed.

However, little attention has been given to the reality of such exploration. Typically, the investigation of habitats of extremophiles tends to lead researchers and their underwater vehicles into hostile and dangerous environments, potentially hazardous to the vehicle. Survey of active submarine volcanoes, such as Loihi, located 35 kilometers southeast of the island of Hawai'i in the Hawaiian Island chain, as well as sinkholes are examples of environments where, outside of typical equipment malfunction such as short circuiting of electronics, the vehicle can easily become damaged and under-actuated.

Motivated by these remarks, the focus of this paper is on designing efficient trajectories for the descent of the AUV into a basin. Basins are found to be very frequent pathways when exploring volcanoes as well as icy environment. A major focus of our work will be the ability of the AUV to map the environment as efficiently as possible during the descent to gain as much knowledge as possible for the environment for future descents as well as to help the AUV while ascending after the exploration took place. Notice that a precise mapping is also critical when deciding which locations are best for sampling. Because of the feature of such mission we assume a vehicle shaped differently from the traditional torpedo shaped AUV. Indeed due to the environment in which it will evolve it is very important that the vehicle possesses the ability to create motion in a cluttered space. To be as general as possible we will assume the vehicle to be ellipsoidal. This is the form of two vehicles that have already been developed, one is the Omni-Directional-Intelligent-Navigator (ODIN) from the Autonomous System Laboratory, College of Engineering, University of Hawaii and the second is the DEPTHX mentioned previously. For both AUVs the actuation is made through a set of thrusters located at various positions on the vehicle. To validate our research we will consider different configurations of actuation based on the thrusters configuration of ODIN and DEPTHX. The trajectories considered in this paper will be designed using methods based on geometric control that have been developed previously, *Smith et al. (2008a, 2008b, 2009)*. The main idea is to provide the AUV with an ideal trajectory to track rather than navigating by relying solely on its sensor system. The combination of a pre-computed trajectory and a feedback controller is getting more and more popular among the AUV community as it provides a very efficient guidance scheme for the vehicle.

The goal of this paper is to present trajectory simulations for different missions and discuss the impact that the location of the various thrusters have on the structure of those trajectories. For this reason and because of limited space, the techniques used to compute the control strategies will be omitted here. Let us just briefly mention that their are based on kinematic reductions of rank one. The main advantage of our procedure is that the control strategy is obtained using an inverse-kinematic procedure applied to a reparametrisation of a trajectory designed in the configuration space only. It is especially efficient in under-actuated cases. Roughly speaking, our trajectories are composed by concatenation of motions, each motion being the integral curve of a special vector field, called decoupling vector field, defined on the configuration space of the submerged rigid body. More details on such approach for a general class of controlled mechanical systems can be found in *Bullo and Lynch (2001)*, *Bullo and Lewis (2004)*. The theory has been adapted to the submerged rigid body (to include dissipative forces) in *Smith et al. (2008a, 2008b, 2009)*. In these references the reader can find the calculation of the vector fields for which the inverse-kinematic procedure can be applied, and therefore the corresponding control in terms of the actuators determined.

2. Model of the Vehicle and Equations of Motion

To design efficient trajectories that take into account the capability as well as all geometric features of the vehicle, an accurate model is essential. AUVs come in a variety of shapes depending on the mission they are designed for. Clearly, the choice of the vehicle's shape impacts the mission

drastically since it determines a lot of characteristics of the vehicle like its maneuverability and stability.

Many AUVs have a torpedo-like shape which gives them a preferred direction of motion (*Smith, R. (2008a)*). Following that direction, they have small added masses and small drag forces even at a high speed. These vehicles are very efficient for large transects and are used, for instance, to map large areas of the ocean floor. A subsequent drawback of these particular vehicles is the necessity for a large turn radius which induces the inability to change direction rapidly. When considering missions in a cluttered environment the vehicle is usually not required to move fast but must be capable of executing complex maneuvers in several degrees of freedom, making torpedo shaped vehicles less preferable. For instance, in a basin exploration scenario, the emphasis is placed on obtaining a quality map of the basin, which is dependent on the maneuverability of the vehicle, rather than on the speed at which the vehicle maneuvers. Furthermore, exceptional maneuverability is crucial for the vehicle to avoid obstacles and to be able to dive into narrow tunnels. Based on these considerations, our simulations used theoretical vehicle model where the vehicle itself is assumed to be an ellipsoid. We will consider different actuation configurations to account for several stability/maneuverability ratios and compare the results. The distance between the center of gravity and center of buoyancy will be varied to study the effect it has on the trajectories given a configuration for the thrusters.

Fig.1: Earth-fixed and body-fixed coordinate reference frames

2.1. Equations of motion

The equations of motion are standard and we will not repeat their derivation in this paper. The reader is instead referred to *Fossen (1994)* for the classical formulation, and to *Smith, R. (2008a, 2009)* for the geometrical formulation. However, we will describe in details the features of the vehicle and the parameters used for our simulations.

To set up our notation, consider two coordinate frames: a moving frame and an inertial frame, Fig.1. The inertial frame is chosen to be fixed with the Earth since, for a low speed AUV, the acceleration of a point with respect to the surface of the Earth can be neglected. This coordinate system is defined in the sequel with the x and y axes lying in the horizontal plane orthogonal to axis z taken positive in the direction of gravity. The origin of the moving reference frame is fixed on the vehicle at its geometric center, and we denote by B₁ the longitudinal axis, B₂ the transverse axis and B₃ the normal axis. The configuration of a vehicle in six degrees of freedom can then be described by η , the position and orientation vector with coordinates in the inertial frame, and by v , the linear and angular velocity

vector with coordinates in the body-fixed frame. The dynamic equations of motion of a rigid body moving in six degrees of freedom submerged in a viscous fluid are given by, *Fossen (1994)*:

$$M\dot{v} + C(v)v + D(v)v + g(\eta) = \tau$$

$$\dot{\eta} = J(\eta)v$$

M is the inertia matrix, $D(v)$ is a matrix representing the hydrodynamic drag terms, $C(v)$ is a matrix accounting for the Coriolis and centripetal forces, $g(\eta)$ represents the restoring forces and moments, and τ accounts for the external forces and moments. In the sequel we will refer to τ as the six degrees of freedom control. From a practical point of view our model needs to include the transformation between the six DOF control and the actual thrusters, called the thrusters control, this is discussed further in the text. Finally, the rotation matrix $J(\eta)$ provides the transformation between the linear and rotational velocities in the body-fixed frame and the inertial one.

A geometric formulation of those equations can be found in *Smith (2008b, 2009)* for instance. While we do not repeat them here it plays a critical role in our study. Indeed, our control design is based on methods developed in *Bullo and Lewis (2004)* and uses the intrinsic geometric properties related to the equation of motion for a submerged rigid body.

2.2. Vehicle

To determine the values of the various parameters for our vehicle, we base our estimations on two existing vehicles presenting features comparable to the one we consider. The first vehicle, the Omni-Directional-Intelligent-Navigator (ODIN) from the Autonomous System Laboratory at the University of Hawaii at Manoa, is spherical and is fully actuated. In Table I we display the physical parameters for this vehicle. The second vehicle on which we base our work is the NASA funded ellipsoidal DEPTHX as described in the introduction, Table I.

Table I: Physical parameters comparison between different AUVs

	ODIN	ENDURANCE	MODEL
Vehicle Mass (Kg)	123.8	1360	1360
Diameters (m)	(0.64, 0.64, 0.64)	(1.9, 1.9, 1.5)	(1.9, 1.9, 1.5)
Displacement (m^3)	0.124	1.5	1.5
C_G (m)	(0, 0, 0)	(0, 0, -0.04)	(0, 0, 0)
C_B (m)	(0, 0, -0.007)	(0, 0, -0.66)	(0, 0, -0.66)
Effective masses (Kg)	(193.8, 193.8, 193.8)	(3750, 3750, 6222)	(3750, 3750, 6222)
Effective moments of inertia ($Kg m^2$)	(5.46, 5.29, 5.72)	(1008, 1008, 1114)	(1008, 1008, 1114)

While ODIN has been designed with maximum maneuverability in all six-degrees of freedom, DEPTHX is oriented more toward maximum stability in pitch and roll and therefore will be considered as an under-actuated vehicle. Based on these two vehicles, throughout this paper we will assume that the hull of our theoretical vehicle is an oblate spheroid (an ellipsoid with two equal diameters). The origin of the body-fixed frame is fixed at the geometric center of the vehicle and the body axes coincide with the principal inertia axes. Moreover, due to the shape of the vehicle we have three orthogonal planes of symmetry. Additional assumptions include the center of gravity is at the geometric center of the ellipsoid, and that the vehicle is neutrally buoyant. Based on those

assumptions, the inertia matrix (including the added mass matrix) and hydrodynamic drag matrix are diagonal, simplifying the equations of motion. This last property is common amongst many AUVs. As it can be seen in Table I, the center of gravity for DEPTHX does not coincide with the geometric center but from a practical point of view the small distance between both has been neglected during their trials (*Fairfield et al. 2008*). An important difference between these two vehicles is related to the restoring moment generated by the distance between the the center of gravity and the center of buoyancy. It can be observed that this distance is kept to a minimum on ODIN while it is much more significant for the DEPTHX vehicle. From a practical point of view, this distance determines the stability of the vehicle motion in pitch and roll *Leonard (1997)*.

2.3. Thrusters configuration

Throughout this paper we will consider three different configurations of actuation typically found in AUVs.

Configuration 1: Eight thrusters - Six DOF

This model is based on the thruster configuration found on the vehicle ODIN. We assume eight thrusters located on the horizontal B1-B2 plane, Fig.1. Four of them are aligned with the B3-axis to contribute to the heave, pitch and roll. The other four are aligned with the B1-B2 plane to contribute to surge, sway and yaw, Fig.2. With this thruster configuration, the vehicle is fully actuated. In other words, the vehicle can follow any prescribed trajectory in the configuration space provided that the desired motion is in the range of the thruster limitations. It is however not trivial to determine the control strategy to produce the desired motion.

Fig.2: Thrusters configuration 1

From our assumptions, the transformation between the actual thrusters and the six degrees of freedom controls can be decoupled into one horizontal and one vertical four by three matrix. These linear transformation matrix can easily be computed from the geometry and dimensions of the vehicle.

Configuration 2: Six thrusters - Five DOF

The second configuration is based on the thruster configuration implemented on the DEPTHX AUV, which only provides forces in five DOF, having no actuation for the pitch motion. In this model there are six thrusters, two of them are in a vertical position and the other four located on the horizontal B1-B2 plane. The vertical thrusters are aligned with the B2 axis such that they cannot produce a pitching motion, but just heave and roll, Fig.3. Under such a configuration the vehicle is under-actuated, due to the inability to produce a rotation along its transverse axis. For this scenario, there exist trajectories in

the configuration space that cannot be realized by the vehicle. This increase the difficulty of the motion planning problem associated to this vehicle.

Fig.3: Thrusters configuration 2

Configuration 3: Six thrusters – Four DOF

The third scenario is based on the same set of thrusters seen in configuration 2, but now the two vertical thrusters are restricted to produce equal thrust. As a consequence, a rolling motion is not possible. It will consume more energy than other motions because the restoring moment will try to align the center of mass and the center of buoyancy on a vertical axis. The set of the possible motions for this configuration will be even more restricted than in the scenario of configuration 2. One more degree of freedom has been lost in terms of the actuation. This is actually the mode of actuation under which the DEPTHX vehicle functions.

3. Missions

To showcase the mathematical framework, we will now present some trajectories that can be used to safely navigate our vehicle through some of the most common scenarios found in underwater sink holes. We assume that a rough knowledge of the environment is known, but the vehicle has yet to map the area to the required degree of resolution. If the environment has never been explored before, we can still plan a trajectory steering the vehicle inside its sensor range.

Fig.4: Map of Church Sink (Leon County - vertical section), with the three missions locations

In the first scenario, we will descend into a cylindrical sink hole (labeled as box 1 in Fig.4). Then, we will explore the conical opening of a more ample cavern (labeled as box 2 in the same picture). Finally, we will focus on how to get through a U-shaped tunnel.

For each of these missions, we will evaluate the performances of the three aforementioned actuator configurations in terms of maximum thrust needed and energy consumption, having fixed the time given to the vehicle to complete the assigned trajectory.

Mission 1

In this mission, the vehicle is required to descend into a cylindrical sink hole while mapping its walls. The dimensions of the cylinder are 40 m radius and 150 m length. The mission time is set to three hours. Below we will provide information about the needed power of the thrusters necessary to realize the descent in the prescribed time. As expected the thruster capacity will be related to the configuration setting of the vehicle.

To perform an accurate mapping, we chose to follow an helical trajectory. This particular choice of trajectory allows the vehicle to both inspect closely and extensively the surface of the wall and perceive in details the features of the wall from a high range of angles. This, in conjunction with a SLAM algorithm as implemented on DEPTHX, allows the vehicle to generate detailed three dimensional maps of the basin to be used for further navigation or sampling purpose. During the descent, we force the vehicle to be constantly facing outwards, keeping what is considered to be the "front" on the rocky wall. This allows the vehicle to accurately map the environment and optionally stop and collect samples whenever it reaches an area of interest. If a feedback control system is used to track the path and the vehicle is equipped with a forward facing Doppler Velocity Logger (DVL), the latter will be kept pointed toward the wall, ensuring the maximum probability it can achieve and maintain a lock.

The trajectory design will depend on the actuation of the vehicle. As stated previously, for the fully actuated vehicle we can determine a control strategy associated to any path described in the configuration space. In other word the vehicle can realized a pure helix to descent. To realize this trajectory, the vehicle needs to activate its actuation in sway, heave and yaw. More precisely, the trajectory is computed as follows. Starting from a stationary position at the top of the basin, the vehicle will accelerate toward the bottom while moving in a circular fashion on the horizontal plane. Toward the end of its path it will decelerate, until coming to a complete stop. We parametrize the trajectory to be at rest at the initial and final configuration in order to allow an easy concatenation of trajectories (that can generate complex paths starting from a few simple ones). This restriction can easily be removed if it is necessary and other parametrization can be considered.

The geometric method used to compute the control strategies is based on the existence of decoupling vector fields, *Smith et al. (2008a, 2008b, 2009)*. Those vector fields are such that their integral curves in the configuration space produce a kinematic motion that can be lifted into the tangent space of the configuration manifold. In other words it provides us trajectories in the configuration space for which we can determine the control that produce the desired trajectory (in other words the motion can be realized by the vehicle). For the mission considered here it can be proved that the six degrees of freedom control does not require the use of the pitch, therefore the same strategy can be used in thruster configuration 1 and 2. The vehicle's motion is displayed in Fig.5, along the values of the thrusters, associated to both cases, to realize this trajectory.

Fig.5: Trajectories and thrust plots for the first and second configurations (mission 1)

Fig.6: Trajectories and thrust plots for the third configuration (mission 1)

For the third configuration, a different approach has to be followed, due to the loss of roll actuation. Indeed, the previous integral curve used in configuration scenario 1 and 2 cannot be realized by a vehicle under-actuated as the DEPTHX vehicle is. To remedy this complication, a more in depth geometric has to be conducted. A result of this geometric study shows that the vehicle with thrusters configured as in scenario 3 is capable of motion to follow integral curve obtained from vector fields that are composed by either surge, sway and yaw or heave and yaw. To produce a trajectory that provides a coverage similar to the helix, the chosen trajectory for the vehicle is composed by linear descents (actuating the heave and the sway simultaneously) and circumferences in the horizontal plane (actuating the surge, sway and yaw simultaneously). The result is represented in Fig.6 as well as the corresponding thruster control. It can be observed that this scenario requires thrusters three times

more powerful than for the first two thrusters configurations and, therefore probably of larger dimension and weight. This is due to the frequent switching between the vertical and horizontal movement, which requires the vehicle to stop and accelerate each time. Therefore, it implies a higher acceleration component than for the other two configurations.

Of most interest in designing control strategies for autonomous underwater vehicles is the desire to minimize energy consumption. Defining the energy as the integral over the duration of the trajectory of the voltage needed for each thruster we can calculate and compare this cost for our trajectories. Here we assume a linear relationship between the thrust and the amperes needed for each thruster. Based on those assumptions, the three previously presented trajectories for the descent into the vertical cylinder (one for each thruster set up configuration) present similar energy consumption. This might be surprising given the fact that the thrusters require three times more power. However, the energy consumption is calculated over the whole trajectory and in the third scenario the vehicle compensates its higher thrust requirements by having less thrusters and using each at their maximum power for only brief periods. Actually, the second thruster configuration under-actuated in pitch only is the most energy consuming (notice that here we have not included in the model the weight of the thruster which would play a critical role in determining which configuration would be more efficient). A simple spectral analysis of the thrust provides the minimum cutoff frequency of the path-tracking subsystem and thrusters combined. If the vehicle does not meet the requirements in thrust or bandwidth, a new trajectory with a relaxed time limit has to be calculated.

Mission 2

In the second mission, we consider a scenario of a widening sink, possibly a cave entrance. Here, a cylindrical helix would not keep the vehicle close to the walls for the whole mission. Instead, we have opted for a conical helix, which has coverage features similar to the helical pattern listed in the previous mission. In our scenario, the radius of the cave section increases linearly with depth, ranging from 20 to 60 m. The vehicle descends for 100 m, following the conical helix with 10 m pitch. The mission time is set to two hours.

Fig.7: Trajectories for the three configurations (mission 2)

This mission is very similar to the first one and the qualitative results are comparable. We display the trajectories in Fig.7. As it was the case for mission 1, a vehicle equipped with the third configuration

scenario for its thrusters is unable to follow that path. Therefore, using the aforementioned vector fields we have designed a similar trajectory, composed of widening circles and vertical transects.

In this scenario, we have that the first and second configuration present similar energy consumption. The third requires twice the energy and maximum thrust in comparison to the other two, due to the frequent stops it is required to make.

Mission 3

In the third mission, we suppose that our vehicle is moving horizontally in a tunnel. A group of stalactites or boulders is partly blocking the way, therefore the vehicle has to pass under them to avoid collision. The environment is presented in Fig.8. The mission time is set to five minutes (it is just a local collision avoidance).

Fig.8: Scenario of mission 3

The goal is to produce a trajectory that is simple in its design and that at the same time uses minimal consumption. In cluttered environment the actuation of the vehicle plays a critical role as it will be seen here. This suggests that it might be interesting to construct a hybrid autonomous vehicle for which some thrusters are activated only in very specific scenario. The vehicle could function under-actuated most of the time to improve its stability as it is done for the DEPTHX vehicle for instance, but would have the capability to become fully actuated and therefore produce pitch and roll in cluttered environment.

Fig.9: Trajectory and thrust plots for configuration 1, mission 3. Dashed lines: vertical thrusters.

For mission 3, using the first thruster configuration, it is possible to follow an arc of a circle, since the vehicle is fully actuated, by simply moving forward while varying the angle of pitch. This path is presented in Fig.9 with the thrust required along this trajectory.

For the remaining two thruster configurations the pitching motion is prevented, so a different path must be followed. A trajectory that is actually implementable is depicted in Fig.10 along side with the thruster's values. This trajectory is simply composed of the concatenation a pure heave, a pure surge and another pure heave motion.

Fig.10: Trajectories and thrust plots for configurations 2 & 3, mission 3. Dashed lines: vertical thrusters.

To compare this path with the arc of a circle we fixed the endpoints and the maximum depth, the time being fixed for both at the same value. With these conditions, the energy required to follow a rectangular path is almost twice as much as the energy needed by a fully actuated vehicle. Therefore if the underwater vehicle ends up in a cluttered region where much obstacle avoidance is necessary, it can be very efficient to be able to switch from an under-actuated mode to a fully actuated one.

4. Conclusions

All the above missions can be implemented on an AUV with the same features of the model, in particular, the DEPTHX vehicle. As it is, the DEPTHX vehicle does not fully exploit its capabilities. As seen in the DEPTHX project, the mapping of the Sistema Zacaton, missions were accomplished through a process the developers have referred to as *iterative exploration*, which primarily uses the vehicles sonar array to map the environment and a robust localization method. During iterative exploration, DEPTHX descends and ascends vertically while rotating, using its sonar array to develop a rough map of the environment. After resurfacing from the initial drop and evaluation of its map, DEPTHX then completes the map to a desired quality by guiding to incomplete or low quality areas. With adequate knowledge prior to the mission, an implementation of the design of mission 1 can aid a vehicle like DEPTHX in two crucial ways. First, it allows the sonars to remain close to the walls of

the underwater cave, yielding high quality sonar data on the initial descent. For the DEPTHX, this would minimize the necessity to resurface, while a map of higher quality would allow DEPTHX to localize with even more accuracy, based on the methods used to localize. Second, the geometric planning minimizes the attempts to complete a satisfactory map of the environment, thereby minimizing energy consumption. For organizations unable to afford the technology and software used on the DEPTHX, the theory presented in this paper is still relevant. In general, since mechanical, electrical, or instrumental failures are important issues to consider, these scenarios become relevant when deciding if a mission can still be completed or if the vehicle will return, as the vehicle will know whether or not it can accomplish prescribed maneuvers. Specifically, DEPTHX employs what is referred to as 'Reactive abort' in the event of any general loss of control or localization. In this mode, the vehicle moves away from any object determined by the return of the sonar pulses with an inverse square law. Since this is only an obstacle avoidance, the vehicle acknowledges the wrong direction to the surface when the exit is smaller than the vehicles local surroundings. Moreover, the vehicle will be trapped in local depth minima, for example, enclosed domes. Implementation of these scenarios, in particular mission 3, can alleviate such issues, as they are global path planners. The trajectories calculated in this paper are model based, this means that even though the vehicle will face uncertainties (and therefore a trajectory tracking scheme is necessary) the trajectories that we produce can be closely followed by the vehicle. By keeping the vehicle at a security distance from the wall in our simulation, we can guarantee that the vehicle will be able to follow closely the chosen path and return to the surface safely during the experimental mission. Coupling our trajectory design with a tracking scheme can improve the overall robustness of the system, in particular it can be activated when the sensors receive high noise data or worst in case of a sensor failure. A feed-forward guidance is superior to a tracking one in case of complex maneuvers in tight spaces (as it can guarantee that the path is feasible a-priori, the vehicle should not get trapped) and when the vehicle is surrounded by hazy water, which create confusion for the sensors and thus to the localization subsystem. While a feed-forward control will be less precise than a feedback one, due to error accumulation, the former cannot be influenced by spurious sensor data.

Another advantage for the vehicle to have the capability to plan its trajectory using our techniques is that it can also be driven for short intervals in a dead reckoning fashion, or even without any form of sensorial input, which helps in decreasing the energy consumption, as the sensors can be temporary shut off. Our trajectory design will also play a major role in case of thruster failure. The techniques presented in this paper can be used to analyze which motion can be executed under the new under-actuated configuration and the vehicle will have the capability to exploit the remaining thrusters (for instance the vehicle may be forced to run backwards) to either pursue the mission or bring back the vehicle safely to the surface.

Finally, one aspect that can be associated to our control design techniques is the information gained through those simulations when developing the AUV. Indeed, it allows us to evaluate the costs and benefits of different thruster configurations and provide a lower bound for the thruster in both strength and bandwidth requirements. Therefore this information can be used to optimize the design of the vehicle to respond the most efficiently to a given mission.

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Robotic Tools to Assist Marine Inspection: The MINOAS Approach

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Abstract

This paper will introduce MINOAS, a marine inspection robotic assistant system, under development in the framework of an EC funded project SCP8-GA-2009-233715 under the topic SST.2008.5.2.1 Innovative product concepts. The project proposes the re-engineering of the overall vessel inspection methodology, by introducing an innovative system concept that incorporates state of the art technologies, but at the same time formulates a new standardization of the overall inspection process. MINOAS proposes the development of a new infrastructure that complements human personnel by high locomotion enabled robots and 'teleports' the human inspector from the vessel's hold to a control room with virtual reality properties. The proposed innovative system concept considers the assembly of a robot fleet with advanced locomotion abilities and sets of tools that are dedicated to the tasks attached to the inspection process, the development of control techniques and algorithms that provide a semiautonomous nature to the operation of the robot fleet and a hierarchical controller that enables online processing of the harvested data and operate as a Decision Support System in the aid of the inspector. In particular, the paper, in addition to provide an overview of the project motivations, concept and goals, will discuss the specifications of the MINOAS system, in particular with respect to an accurate analysis of the tasks executed during vessel inspections, the proposed overall architecture and the classes of robots that will be considered as a possible help to the human inspector.

1. Introduction

Humans and goods transportation by mean of ships and vessels is, so far and without any doubts, one of the most time and cost efficient method. In order to improve the transportation service quality, an always increasing safety standard level has to be achieved. As a direct consequence of the vast vessel-integration effort, occurred in the last 30 years, that enables the combined monitoring and control of engines and navigational means from a central point (e.g. the bridge and the engine-room), there has been a valuable reduction in maritime accidents. However many accidents still occur, with consequences for the environment and international economy. Even if many of these accidents have been attributed to structural failure of the ship, a continuous monitoring of failsafe conditions through technological means has not been extensively applied yet.

The surveying and subsequent repairs require many of the tanks (cargo, fuel, ballast, etc) to be cleaned and ventilated, and for suitable access to be arranged - usually using scaffolding. In the case of older ships, this preparation of each tank is necessary to allow the repair crew to enter and access the element that has failed. Thus a surveyor can also use the same facilities. However, in a younger ship, the number of required repairs is small (see Table I), so the bulk of these arrangements are only required for the survey itself. As a result a greater proportion of the preparation cost is entirely due to the survey, which for many well run ships is likely to reveal no defects in the early years.

Traditionally the upper structure has been a region that ship surveyors check most for defects due to

wastage from the presence of corrosive gases that boil off from the oil cargo. However, an analysis of defects across a number of double hull tanker over the last 20 years, reveals that the majority of

Table I: Occurrence of defects and failures by ship age for tankers

Age	Defect per ship
0 – 5 years	3.9
5 – 10 years	5.2
10 – 15 years	8.8
15 – 20 years	16.9

failures occurs within bottom third of cargo tanks (see Table II). This may be a reflection of the investment in high quality paint coatings that owners now apply to the upper structure (typically 3m). Nowadays, assessment of the structural integrity is made through periodical inspections, carried out by surveyors who operate using well established methodologies and techniques. However, despite the standardized methodologies and qualification criteria, the objectivity of the result cannot be guaranteed. The effort in the inspection tasks is huge (600,000 m² of steel require detailed inspection for a medium size cargo vessel) and this often has to be carried out by a single surveyor within a short amount of time (generally a few days) in order to return the vessel to service. The quality of the inspection results is also affected by both exogenous (exhaustion, stress, inaccurate judgment) and endogenous factors (different cultures, educational background, skills) whenever human intervention is used.

These above mentioned tasks have dramatic impact on the profit optimization of the ship owners and international trade; with less available vessel transporting the goods, transportation takes longer, consequently increasing the price of the goods. From a ship operator perspective, there are two main topics, regarding the costs, that have to be taken into account: *i*) the vessels are required to remain stationary for periodic time intervals in order to sustain the inspection procedures, which will not allow the ship to sail unless the inspection is concluded to specific accuracy criteria (the maximum achievable accuracy is the first priority); *ii*) the inspection related expenses increase as specific arrangements are required, for instance as in Fig. 1, making the structure available for close-up inspection (temporary and permanent staging, lift, movable platforms, rafts and other means). In particular, this second kind of survey is performed under the responsibility of the owner and aims to identify necessary repair works and estimate costs. These costs are frequently poorly estimated, due to the inaccessibility of the hull (the vessel might still be in normal operation conditions) or due to time restrictions. It is therefore evident that there is a need for a standardization of close-up inspections procedures through the incorporation of new means.

The maritime industry is forced to follow the general trend of rationalization so as to reach a higher level of standardization of the procedures related to marine transportation, that will enable higher performances according to safety and financial criteria. One way to achieve this is through the incorporation of more technological means that increase the level of automation.

The MINOAS project (Marine INspection rObotic Assistant System) proposes the re-engineering of the overall vessel inspection methodology, by introducing an innovative system concept that integrates human personnel with high locomotion-enabled robots, effectively “tele-porting” the human inspector from the vessel's hold to a control room with virtual reality properties.

The proposed innovative system concept considers the assembly of a robot fleet with advanced locomotion capabilities and sets of tools that are dedicated to the tasks attached to the inspection process, the development of control techniques and algorithms that provide a semi-autonomous nature

Table II: Occurrence of defects and failures by ship age for tankers

Age	Upper third	Middle third	Lower third
0 – 5 years	19.0 %	23.0 %	58.3 %
5 – 10 years	19.4 %	21.5 %	59.1 %
10 – 15 years	45.0 %	25.6 %	29.3 %
15 – 20 years	55.0 %	20.1 %	25.2 %

Fig. 1: Staging required during a vessel inspection

to the operation of the robot fleet and a hierarchical controller that enables online processing of the harvested data and operate as a Decision Support System in the aid of the inspector.

The expected immediate results of the MINOAS project implementation with respect to the traditional inspection procedures are:

- Minimization of the downtime related to the preparation of the inspection procedures due to the parallel deployment of the robotic platforms utilized.
- Utilization of robots to “environment set-up”, obtaining measurements in form of images and videos, thus producing a faster inspection procedure; human intervention will be required only for isolated or difficult situations.
- The withdrawal of human personnel from hazardous areas, avoiding the surveyor to enter the hold or climb on staging; these tasks will be mostly performed (except for those cases where human presence is absolutely required) by fleet of robots.
- A more systematic inspection methodology that will lead to minimization of the inspection time with enhanced quality.
- The use of advanced technological tools will abolish the need for extensive staging and other temporary arrangement traditionally required, thus minimizing the costs of the overall inspection procedure.
- The modularity of the inspection platform proposed by the MINOAS project will reduce the overall inspection cost for a specific vessel as it provides a repeatability property to the inspection.
- The increase of the inspection quality, that consequently will increase the safe operating conditions of the vessels and prolong their life-cycle.
- The minimization of trade costs due to the vessel’s increased lifecycle and operational time.
- The increase of the environmental protection through the elevation of the inspection quality.

The MINOAS system integrates a set of cooperative agents for vessel inspection. The agents are heterogeneous from the point of view of operating environment (air, underwater or ground), motion capabilities, instrument suite (sensors and task-oriented devices), power supply (batteries and/or tether), communications, positioning system and degree of autonomy. It is worth noting that the human being itself is considered as a particular agent able to co-operate with the robotic ones according to suitable procedures.

The agents have to act under human supervision and, in many cases, tele-operation, although at different degrees of autonomy, in a working area corresponding to the vessel to be inspected. The working area is characterized by geometric properties, propagation of communication/positioning signals, materials of the objects and inspection tasks to be performed inside. The inspection related tasks include visual monitoring, ultrasound monitoring, marking, and so on. As far as the definition of suitable strategies for robot task allocation and navigation is concerned, RTD activities carried out in the MINOAS project will pursue two main objectives:

- developing a general framework (task allocation, planning and supervision system) for the dynamic allocation of heterogeneous resources (i.e. agents) and corresponding tasks (i.e. inspection tasks) for executing a mission in a pre-defined operating environment (i.e. working area);
- experimentally validating the task allocation, planning and supervision system using a limited set of actual agents, with their particular capabilities, in a sub-set of the generic vessel inspection area.

2. System Architecture

The MINOAS architecture, Fig. 2, consists of a hierarchical controller handling the dynamic task allocation among a team of heterogeneous robots as well as the post-processing of the acquired data, and of a fleet of robotic vehicles, with different motion capabilities, in charge of executing the required inspection and marking activities. Each robot will be equipped with suitable localisation and path planning modules in order to navigate to and in its assigned working area.

Fig. 2: MINOAS project architecture

2.1. Task Allocation and Planning

One of the main MINOAS project goals is the usage optimization of a heterogeneous robotic team, to perform inspection mission of ships' areas, like hull, ballast rooms, etc. The achievement of this goal requires the definition of a procedure to classify the ship's areas, starting from the architectural drawings, and thus creating a table of the surfaces to be inspected, detailed by the characteristics of each area of interests: internal/external, underwater/in-air, ground/wall, etc. A complementary classification has to be done for the vehicle classes applied for the inspection: underwater vehicles, ground robot, climbing platforms, etc.

Depending on the capabilities (speed, type of inspection, operative constraints, etc.) of each class of vehicles and the number of available robots for each class, a procedure to optimally associate and share the robotic platforms among the different zones to be inspected has to be developed. This topic, referred as *task allocation* problem, has the aim of associating each vehicle, in space and time, to every interested area to be inspected.

The next step is to design, for each vehicle, the reference path in order to cover the assigned area to be inspected, keeping into account the geometry of the area, obstacles, motion constraints of the vehicle. The result is a complete association and scheduling of all the inspection resources to all the interested areas; in this context, the human operator can be also "scheduled", for instance in those cases where no robotic platforms have the compliant characteristics to perform the inspection. Thus, the user can decide to perform a human inspection, or discard the inspection if it represents a too risky operation.

2.1.2. Existing Methodologies

Due to the increasing interests in the multi-robot frameworks applied to cooperative explorations and sampling, inspections, area observation and protections, vehicle formations, search and rescue operations, a number of works have been proposed to face the problems of task allocation and path planning.

A description of an empirical guideline for task allocation strategies in multi-robot systems, identifying four distinct task allocation approaches is proposed in work *Østergaard et al. (2002)*. The idea is to perform an action selection for multi-robot coordination, generating a mapping from the combined robot state space to the combined robot action space. Even with a small number of robots, the task is an extremely high-dimensional mapping, thus a decomposed and distributed control is necessary. The proposed approach reduces the dimensionality of the coordination problem and the amount of inter-robot communication required.

Meuth et al. (2009) explore the problem of optimizing the behavior of a swarm of heterogeneous robotic vehicles executing a search area coverage task; the problem is further complicated with the introduction of dynamic vehicles and environmental properties making adaptability a necessary requirement in order to achieve a high level of mission assurance using unmanned vehicles. The search coverage problem for multiple heterogeneous vehicles is unique in that the task is defined in a general way, and must be divided into sub-tasks which are then allocated to each vehicle. This work addresses the task decomposition and allocation problems by first using a method for search area decomposition based on probabilistic occlusion maps and utilizing Voronoi diagrams to construct a set of points that provide complete coverage of the search space for a given vehicle sensing characteristic.

Bellingham et al. (2002) and *Bellingham et al. (2003)* address the problem of cooperative path planning for a fleet of UAVs (Unmanned Aerial Vehicles). The paths are optimized to account for uncertainty/adversaries in the environment by modelling the probability of UAV loss. In order to maximize the expected mission score, this stochastic formulation designs coordination plans that optimally exploit the coupling effects of cooperation between UAVs to improve survival probabilities. This allocation is shown to recover real-world air operations planning strategies, and to provide

significant improvements over approaches that do not correctly account for UAV attrition. The algorithm is implemented in an approximate decomposition approach that uses straight-line paths to estimate the time-of-flight and risk for each mission. The task allocation for the UAVs is then posed as a mixed-integer linear program (MILP).

2.1.2. Application To The MINOAS Project

The application of the approaches proposed in literature, to the case of the MINOAS project, requires, first of all, a rigorous procedure to classify both the vehicles and the areas to be inspected, on the basis of a set of main characteristics. This is necessary in order to develop a resolution method to allocate the robots to one or more areas that have to be inspected. After that all the robots have been assigned to one or more specific areas through a suitable task allocation algorithm, then the path-planning procedure can be run to design suitable inspection paths, that all the robots will have to follow.

To make more general the initial approach to the task allocation, the concept of *task* can be associated to a generic allocation, in space and time, of a so called *resource*; a *resource* is a generic agent, whose characteristics fit with the assigned task. To make the approach as general as possible, and also to make the application as feasible as possible, it can be imagined a framework where both inspection robots and human operator cooperate to fulfill the inspection objectives. Treating both robots and users as agents of the framework, also humans task can be assigned to cooperate with, assist, transport, if necessary, the robots.

The task allocation and path planning procedures have to be also constrained by logistic characteristics of the environment; for instance the availability of free passages between the areas to be inspected has to be taken into account, as well as the communication issues both with tethered and wireless connections. Tethered vehicles have, naturally, a reduced operative space given by the cable length and motion constraints to overcome possible cable bound or stuck. On the other side, wireless communication reliability can be affected by the closed areas, moreover metal walls, floors and ceilings can degrade more the functionality of the system. To face this problem, during task allocation phase, one or more vehicle can be assigned to serve as communication relay, on the basis of the geometry of the areas to be inspected.

To reach the optimal or quasi-optimal task assignment to every agent of the framework, a rigorous definition of the main capabilities of each class or robots has to be set.

A first rough classification can be based on the operative environment:

- water vehicles;
- ground vehicles;
- aerial vehicles.

The definition of the classes of primitive motions or motion characteristics can be a further step to understand the inspection capabilities of each robot class.

Water vehicles can be: *i) underwater* and capable of moving in all the 3D (underwater) area; *ii) surface* robots able to inspect the 2D surface at water level.

Ground vehicles, used for floors inspections and capable to overcome little obstacles (with respect to the dimensions of vehicle and obstacle) and slopes, can be divided in classes on the basis of the locomotion typology: *i) wheeled*; *ii) caterpillars*; *iii) legged*; *iv) hybrid* (merging different motion capabilities). Wheeled and caterpillars robots are surely faster and robust, but may have difficulties overcoming obstacles, while legged and hybrid vehicles can achieve more complex tasks, but the synthesis of the control algorithm is difficult.

Climbing robots can be: *i) roped*; *ii) equipped with magnets and wheels*; *iii) equipped with magnets*

and legs; these vehicles require a balancing between weight, payload, climbing capability, in order to make the robot reliable for its task.

Aerial vehicles have to be helicopter-like, or however with hovering capabilities in order to perform fine inspection operations; for their intrinsic nature, aerial robots are dangerous, thus requiring robust controller and strict operative procedures to guarantee safety during operations.

Further sub-classifications of the vehicle typologies can be done, on the basis of speed, dimensions, weight, payload, etc.; defining in the same way the area classes to be inspected, i.e. identifying submersed areas, floors, walls and other particular zones of the rooms to be inspected. Again further class specifications can be done, indicating narrow spaces, presence of obstacles (also classifying obstacles on the basis of the dimensions), visibility, communication constraints, etc.

On the basis of the vehicle and area classifications, a task allocation algorithm, performing an optimal mapping search can be developed in order to assign each vehicle to the area that most fit with its characteristics and capabilities. The assignment of more vehicles to a specific area requires the further vehicle allocation in space and/or time; for instance, two observing vehicles can inspect a floor at the same time, observing half the floor each one. But one observing vehicle and one marking vehicle may be scheduled in time, i.e. the observing robot will start the task looking for damages, and then, delayed in time, the marking robot will mark the damaged zones indicated by the other vehicle.

2.2. Communications

A bidirectional communication is allowed between the upper levels of the hierarchical controller and the on-site agents. The networking means required for this type of application are not restricted to wireless (ad-hoc) networks, but can also be stretched out in adopting wired communication, when the amount of transmitted data require large bandwidth, such as live video, or where the intervening physical mean does not allow for acceptable baud rates (underwater communication). In particular, a network monitoring system will be developed for the on-line health monitoring of the network. This module will extract the coverage of the overall network and will locate *blindfold* regions, which should be avoided during the robot movements, or bridged to the network infrastructure in order to ensure accessibility. Widely acceptable metrics will be used to evaluate the status of the ad-hoc networks (UDP based networks are susceptible to packet losses) and counter-measures will be taken to improve the network functionality (replacement of a malfunctioning stationary node with a mobile one).

2.3. Mission sensors and actuators

2.3.1. General approach

The sensing infrastructure in the MINOAS project is intended to allow the surveyors to be tele-ported to the hull parts that require inspection. To this end, the surveyor must be provided with mainly:

- thickness measurements at specific points of the hull, so as to be able to determine whether the structural integrity of the vessel is compromised; and
- detailed enough imagery (by means of the use of high-resolution cameras or the camera optics zooming capabilities) so as to remotely enable not only the visual assessment of the state of the area under inspection, but also the successful application of image processing techniques that autonomously or semi-autonomously can detect relevant hull defects and assist the surveyor with quantitative data, rather than estimations, before taking a “repair/no repair needed” decision.

Besides, the gathered information is continuously transmitted to the central controller to visualize it within an appropriate Human-Machine Interface (HMI), in which the available data is represented

over the 3D CAD model of the area under inspection. Finally, both raw data and processed results are to be logged for future reference and comparison in later surveys. The digital recording, together with the computation of quantitative data from the images, will result particularly useful for diminishing the effects of the always subjective interpretation of surveyors, which, moreover, can vary depending on the country where the inspection is performed. Additional measurements can be incorporated with samples from ambient sensors providing information about e.g. moisture and/or temperature.

Regarding actuators, the robots actuating infrastructure houses mainly the actuators required for preparing the surface before taking a thickness measurement (see next section) or before close-up inspection, e.g. hammer-like devices for tapping the surface and cleaners for detaching the remaining scales, as well as markers for distinguishing which areas need human intervention for repair.

Depending on the particular task to be undertaken, each kind of robot is to be fitted with the proper suite of sensors and actuators. Nevertheless, each robot is intended to be equipped with a camera to provide visual feedback of the area under inspection, and also to fulfill its localization needs.

2.3.2. Non-destructive thickness measurement

Non-destructive testing (NDT) is a broad interdisciplinary field that plays a critical role in assuring that structural components and systems perform their function reliably and cost effectively, and in such a manner that their future functionality is not impaired (see *Prakash (2009)*). The number of NDT methods that can be used to inspect components and make measurements is large and continues to grow. For the particular case of non-destructive thickness measurement, ultrasonic testing is among the most often used methods. In this case, thickness is determined from the time between the emission of a high-frequency acoustic signal, that is induced within the material by means of mechanical coupling, and the echo received from the part geometrical surfaces.

Fig. 3: UTM transmitter (top) and receiver (bottom) waveforms

Among other devices, piezoelectric transducers are widely used because they provide quick and reliable results. Besides, they can work either as ultrasound source or detector thanks to the reversibility of the piezoelectric effect, what allows encapsulating the whole function in a single transducer (*pulse-echo* method). Despite its many advantages, the main inconvenient of these transducers is the requirement, for an accurate and reliable measurement, of a good contact between the probe and the part under test, so that the waves go through the interface between the probe and the material without great loss nor reflections. This requirement is particularly important when the material is covered with paint, and also if it is corroded, as is the usual case in the maritime industry.

In order to improve the accuracy of the measurement: (1) the material surface is prepared by cleaning the spot from paint or rust, and next applying a layer of couplant (grease, water, etc.) to match the acoustic impedance between the probe and the material; (2) the time between the second and third echoes is measured, instead of the time between the transmitted tone burst and the first echo, for cancelling the effect of the additional delay caused by paint or other layers between the active element and the material (*multi-echo* method, Fig. 3).

2.3.3. Image processing requirements and first results

Apart from supplying inspectors with remote thickness measurements, MINOAS is to provide assistance during the (remote) visual inspection and documentation of surveyed surfaces. In this regard, two main defective situations on the hull structure that are of interest for the surveyor, cracks and corrosion, are to be autonomously or semi-autonomously detected.

On the one hand, cracks generally develop at intersections of structural items or discontinuities due to stress concentration, although they also may be related to material or welding defects (see Fig. 5). If the crack remains undetected and unrepaired, it can grow to a size where it can cause sudden fracture. Therefore, care is needed to visually discover fissure occurrences in areas prone to high stress concentration.

On the other hand, the different kinds of corrosion that may arise are to be identified: *general corrosion*, that appears as non-protective friable rust which can occur uniformly on uncoated surfaces; *pitting*, a localized process that is normally initiated due to local breakdown of coating and that derives, through corrosive attack, in deep and relatively small diameter pits that can in turn lead to hull penetration in isolated random places; *grooving*, again a localized process, but this time characterized by linear shaped corrosion which occurs at structural intersections where water collects and flows; and *weld metal corrosion*, which affects the weld deposits, mostly due to galvanic action with the base metal and more likely in manual welds than in machine welds.

To determine the state of a corroded structure it is common to estimate the corrosion level as percentage of affected area. Traditional methods quantify corrosion by visual comparison of the area under study with dot patterned charts, Fig. 4.

Fig. 4: Corrosion level identified as percentage of affected area

To finish with this section, first results regarding fracture and corrosion detection are shown in, respectively, Figs. 5 and 7. On the one hand, the crack detector is the result of the adaptation and posterior optimization of the crack detection method for concrete structures described in *Yamaguchi (2010)*. This method takes into account the particular geometry of cracks as they appear in digital images, i.e. elongated, narrow and connected sets of dark pixels, and, to this end, makes use of a region-growing technique based on a percolation model, a physical model for liquid permeation

through porous materials (see *Stauffer (1994)*). The method has proved to be tolerant to stains and shadows.

On the other hand, the results shown in Figure 7 correspond to a corrosion detector addressing this vision task from a machine-learning approach. To this end, RGB histograms for $m \times m$ pixel image patches comprising corroded scene points were learnt in the form of a 10-model/2-class dictionary resulting from a clustering procedure. A nearest neighbor classifier is then applied for classifying image patches as either not affected by corrosion or affected by pitting/general corrosion, Fig. 7[left]). This is a fast procedure that, despite producing a coarse-level corrosion identification, can be performed on-line onboard the robotic platforms for fast identification of corroded areas. Next, if needed (e.g. to improve the calculation of the percentage of surface affected by corrosion), the classification result can be refined off-line using a percolation-based procedure again, Fig. 7[right]).

Fig. 5: First classification results for a percolation-based crack detector: (left) original image, (right) crack detection, indicated as white pixels

3. Mobile Robots for the MINOAS Framework

In order to satisfy operating requirements, the MINOAS project will investigate and evaluate, also through prototyping, the possibility of using different robotic platforms. Due to the different and particular project specifics above mentioned, some of the cutting edge technologies have been reviewed in the following.

3.1. Magnetic Wheeled Climbing Robots

The idea of using magnetic elements or wheels on mobile robots dates back to 1972, when William Guy patented concepts for magnetic wheels systems *Guy (1972)*. From then, a number of robots, taking advantage of the magnetic force in order to travel on surfaces with any inclination regarding the gravity vector, have been developed, mainly for inspection of metal tanks, oil containers, pipe constructions such as sewers, gas/oil transmission pipelines, gas/oil distribution pipes. Anyway, their mobility is usually limited to smooth, i.e. with high radius of curvature, obstacle-free surfaces. The

introduction of a mechanism based on dual magnetic wheels, resembling a crawler, not only overcame limitations in negotiating pipe bends but enables robots to climb over sharp obstacles like sleeve and dresser joints *Kawaguchi et al. (1995)*. This concept has been exploited in *Tache et al. (2007)*, where magnetic wheel units incorporating active lifter-stabilizer mechanisms demonstrated their effectiveness in negotiating complex shaped structures. The proposed system is based on a lever arm mechanism, which can slightly lift off the wheel, decreasing the magnetic force at a suitable contact point. An adaptation of this locomotion concept to four legs wheeled robots working in a ferromagnetic environment characterised by abrupt changes of slope of the walking surface and vertical climbing is being evaluated.

For some inspection tasks on a ship, it is mandatory that the surveyor can reach a steel frame of the ship for visual inspection, often in places high above ground level of the ship. The current procedure is that the surveyor needs scaffolding or a raft for proper inspection. Even from a raft, it is often not possible the inspection of the upper part of the vessel tanks. A magnetic crawler is proposed as a first physical implementation for the MINOAS system. Most magnetic climbing robots are designed using a tracked or wheeled system and one large magnet in the body. Those systems are often heavy and dangerous if they fall off the wall, which could be the case in dirty and unstructured (uneven) environments.

An innovative design using magnetic feet is proposed for the robot platform. A hybrid legged-wheel approach is adopted too. As shown in Fig. 6(a), each wheel of the system contains five legs, ending in one foot. Each foot has a rubber base including 8 strong Neodymium magnets hidden within the feet. Two prototypes in order to test the feed were designed and tested in a vertical steel frame at the DFKI (RIC). The advantage of this hybrid legged wheel approach is that it can also overcome small obstacles and also perform a positive 90° transition (e.g. moving from the horizontal plane to a vertical plane without direct user interaction). Another advantage is the high clearance between the body and the wall, leaving room for additional sensors for inspection. The systems are both externally powered and remote controlled using 27MHz Radio transmission. The main advantage of the proposed lightweight climber is that the overall system weights only 605 g for the 2 wheeled version and 1050 g for the four-wheel system, Fig. 6(b). The current payload of the system is rather limited to around 250 g. This payload is sufficient to carry at least one camera for visual inspection plus a LED based light source. A stronger version is current under development which is able to carry more equipment.

Fig. 6: Wheels of system

3.2. VTOL Aerial Vehicles

With regard to other robotic platforms, *Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV)* are characterized by fast deployment times and larger flexibility when remote areas have to be reached. Besides, current advances in sensor technology and computational power availability are steadily increasing their

robustness and reliability in challenging scenarios. In the particular case of a vessel's hull, those features are to derive in non-negligible benefits towards optimizing the inspection time.

Unlike fixed-wing aircrafts, helicopter-type UAVs allow vertical flight manoeuvres, including hovering and *vertical take-off and landing* (VTOL). It is because of this superiority regarding vertical, stationary and low speed flights, that this kind of UAV is specially suited for detailed surveys of vertical structures such as the ones found in vessel holds. Among the different kinds of helicopter designs that have been proposed, multi-rotor configurations present several advantages over comparably scale helicopters (see *Castillo (2005)*, *Pounds (2006)*, *Hoffman (2007)*):

- They do not require mechanical linkages to vary rotor angle of attack as they spin, what simplifies the design of the vehicle and reduces maintenance time and cost.
- The use of several rotors allows each individual rotor to have a smaller diameter than the equivalent helicopter rotor, for a given vehicle size. Furthermore, if required, heavier weights can be carried, since they can have more lift, and the payload capacity can thus be larger.
- Flight is safer than for other helicopters because the small rotor size makes them store less kinetic energy during flight, what reduces the damage in case the rotors hit any object. Besides, rotors can be protected against collisions by enclosing them within a frame.

Fig. 7: First classification results for the corrosion detector: (a) coarse classification results, (b) fine classification results (general corrosion is indicated in green and pitting is indicated in blue)

This kind of AUV presents also some disadvantages deriving from the multi-rotor configuration, namely a larger weight and larger energy consumption due to the extra motors. However, all in all, their particular suitability for indoor flights and interaction in close proximity to other objects (and also in obstacle-dense environments), with low risk of damaging the vehicle, its operators, or its surroundings, overcome the aforementioned disadvantages when considered from the MINOAS viewpoint.

Among other multi-rotor UAVs, the four-rotor, or *quad-rotor*, is emerging as the most popular multi-rotor configuration. This kind of vehicle consists of four rotors in total, with two pairs of counter-rotating, fixed-pitch blades located at the four corners of the aircraft. In this platform, the control of

the vehicle motion is achieved by varying the relative speed of each rotor (see Figure 8). Moreover, because each pair of rotor blades spin in opposite directions, they cancel out any torque, keeping the helicopter flying straight. As a result, precise flight and stable hovering can be achieved. Finally, counter rotating propellers increase efficiency and flight times, as no extra thrust is needed to compensate for unwanted rotation.

Fig. 8: Quad-rotor motion control (Ω_H is the hovering speed, to counterbalance gravity): (a) vertical motion, (b) roll motion and lateral displacement, (c) pitch motion and forward/backward displacement, (d) yaw motion, clockwise for $(-\Delta)$ and counterclockwise for $(+\Delta)$

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A Digital Planning Tool for Outfitting: “DigiMAus”

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Abstract

In the business organization of FLENSBURGER the planning department is placed as a link between the design departments, the materials logistics and production. Planning engineers apply different IT-tools, design and construction application: Aveva Marine Outfitting (CAD), (enterprise resource planning system) material control system (MARS), project management software ACOS, Visualization System Navisworks and MS Office applications. To integrate all these applications in one platform we developed an application called “DigiMAus”. This is a shortcut for Digitale Methodenarbeit Ausrüstung (Digital Methods in Outfitting) and is based on the Eclipse RCP (Rich Client Platform). Aim is to reduce man-hours for prototypes or the first vessel in a series.

1 Introduction

FLENSBURGER has started the project “DigiMAus” in January 2007, a According to the steel planning project “DigiMeth”. All planning information produced from DigiMeth is also used with DigiMAus, how the steel structure is composed. For an outfitting object the planning information is for example an activity, which describes where and when this object is being built. Activities are created and controlled by Project Management Tool ACOS. All data which is necessary, except geometrical, for an object is stored in the PPS System, the main Oracle database. CAD System manages geometry data for each single ship project. DigiMAus is the interface, connects data from the several systems, and makes it available to users, Fig.1.

Fig. 1 : Relationships between databases and DigiMAus

Therefore an important point is the usability, which has highest priority, because of the variety of users working with DigiMAus. Eclipse RCP makes it easy to achieve this aim. Eclipse provides among other things a wide range of user interface components, starting from simple text fields based on SWT (Standard Widget Toolkit) over JFace as a toolkit that brings helper classes for developing UI features (for example : model view controller) to complex framework (workbench manager, views, editors, etc.). The large goal is the visualization of graphical data from CAD system with this very large amount of objects. Visualization performance and easy to use handling is the main requirement. DigiMAus uses a third-party application called Navisworks.

2 Tool integration

DigiMAus integrates miscellaneous third party tools into one user interface. The goal is for the user to have one application where he can manage and see all relevant data. In history he had these tools separate and was accountable for the data conversions between the tools. All users working with DigiMAus accesses the same data.

2.1 Navisworks

Navisworks is used for easily visualization of complex shipbuilding projects for real-time review. It can handle extremely large data sets, so it is optimal for DigiMAus. For one vessel for example Navisworks can handles over 30 Mio. Triangles and guarantees smooth rotations (minimal 6 Frames) depending on hardware conditions. Data sets are stored in Navisworks Document Files (*.nwd) and are very small, as they compress the CAD data by up to 80% of the original size. For example the file size for this ship is about 65MB. Navisworks provides a COM (Common Object Model) interface and allows a range of possibilities for customizing and extending its functionality. This methodology allows you to connect two pieces of software and they can communicate via an API (application programming interface). Components can be written in programming languages that supports COM (e.g. C, C++, C#, Visual Basic, Java). All functions you can do with the standalone Application are also accessible via API (Application Programming Interface).

Fig. 2 : Detail dataflow to and from DigiMAus

The NWD file is generated automatically every night by rvm2nwd converter. The converter is a console program that controls Navisworks without seeing the Navisworks GUI. Every night Aveva Outfitting exports ship data as review files (*.rvm) and after that executes the converter. The converter imports these files. Navisworks is possible to read a wide range of CAD fileformats. It is also possible to mix several fileformats into one Navisworks document file. The advantage in using review files is that the data structure as in Aveva Outfitting is the same after conversion process. After importing files the converter needs to read additional information, information about minimal-maximal dimension of the planning areas or steel assembly groups (e.g. Module, Whole section, Subgroup, etc.). The converter assigns all objects located in these bounding boxes to a Navisworks Selection Group, for performance reason during DigiMAus session. If the user is working in DigiMAus and selecting a selection group, all objects contained in this selection group are selected in Navisworks and are accessible nearly simultaneous. Selection groups are similar to collections of values which are used in programming languages. It is possible to change color, transparency, hide or

unhide selected Navisworks objects. The name of an object is the most important relationship between object in the Navisworksmodel and objects in the Oracle database. The construction engineer who works with CAD system is accountable of the name. At the end, the converter creates miscellaneous selection groups with several names:

- For zones (e.g. /D000/D100/D110)
- For steel assembly groups (e.g. /B11/1 → Module B11 with wholesection 1)
- Pipeparts (e.g. pipepart 8211-4044)
- Cabletrays
- Objects without standard names respectively undefined objects

Only pipeparts are handled in an other way. In Aveva Outfitting pipeparts are elements of pipebranches and single geometrical elements composes a pipepart. These elements are summarized to a selection group and the selection group with name of pipepart. Fig. 3 shows a pipepart as a selection group.

Fig. 3 : Selection group of pipe part 8211-4208

The assigning of objects to selection groups takes the most time of conversion (approx. 9 h). Each conversion process is executed on separate server machines. The final model contains over 100,000 objects with more than 13000 selection groups. Normally four shipbuilding projects will be converted per night.

The next step is to integrate Navisworks Visualization view in DigiMAus by using Navisworks COM interface and ActiveX control. With SWT you have the possibility to create a OLE/COM bridge between SWT Widget and the ActiveX control. OLE stands for Object Linking and Embedding. The embedded application must provide a COM interface and finally a PROGID that is needed to create the bridge between Java/SWT and Navisworks, Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 : Navisworks visualization in DigiMAus

```

...
try {
    oleFrame = new OleFrame(parent, SWT.NONE);
    oleFrame.setBackgroundMode(SWT.INHERIT_FORCE);
    oleControlSite = new OleControlSite(
        oleFrame,
        SWT.NONE,
        "NavisWorksAPI.nwControl.7"); // PROGID
} catch (Exception e) {
    dispose();
}
...

```

Fig. 5 : Code snippet that creates OLE/COM Bridge between Navisworks and SWT

The API provides a large number of classes. Based on first top-level object `nwControl` where you can load and save models and second 'state' top-level object `nwOpState` which is a hierarchy of objects exposed via properties, method and collections. The state object provides COM events when various things happen in the GUI (Graphical User Interface).

2.2 Aveva Marine Outfitting

AVEVA Marine is a set of integrated marine design and production applications. Hence FLENSBURGER uses the Outfitting Module with the equipment, steel structures, cable tray, HVAC and pipe work application for the detail design and the creation of production information.

All model data is stored in AVEVA's DABACON databases. A new building project at FLENSBURGER consists of a set of databases, catalogues are linked from a catalogue project. For each project all users have access to the same set of databases, so everybody is working with the same model. A claim management is provided by the DABACON databases to prevent two users modifying the same data at the same time.

Fig. 6 : AVEVA Marine Outfitting

Modelling is carried out using a customer-defined catalogue and specification, in a full 3D environment. This environment is customisable so FLENSBURGER has set up additional functionality to suit our design processes and speed up the design work. Creation and editing of the model can be done using graphical tools or a command line input. 3D Model data is exchanged with sub suppliers using the STEP format which is known to most mechanical CAD systems. The Hull part designed in NUPAS at FLENSBURGER is transferred by an interface to an outfitting database in AVEVA. Changes are updated daily with a batch job, so in the morning all users have the same information available. Drawings are produced from the model database. Their views with annotation and dimensions reference to the design model, so all changes in the design are included automatically in the drawing when doing an update.

2.3 MARS

MARS is a shipbuilding process management system that handles logistics, materials, resource and production planning information. It is the front-end of the Oracle Database. MARS is originally developed by Logimatic Denmark and over the years adjusted by FLENSBURGER. In history MARS contains a very large amount of screens (Fig.7 shows a screen example) and produces many reports. The difficulty is that there is no connection to the CAD system out of a screen. The user needs to look manually for the right object.

Fig. 7 : Object parts in MARS

2.4 Office and other Visualization Tools

In other cases where the user wants to view documents, like Word, Excel or PDF files, it is possible to open such in DigiMAus as part of the application. It is also possible to view 2D CAD drawings, work with it or print it out. All documents are stored as BLOB (Binary Large Object) in the database, so all users have access to the same data and only to this data that is approved. DigiMAus uses COM to integrate applications linked with type of file. For displaying graphical data which is generated at runtime, DigiMAus uses the VTK (Visualization Toolkit), an open source, freely available software library for 3D computer graphics, image processing and visualization. VTK is written in C++ but there exist various wrappers for other languages such as Java.

2.5 Perspectives of Data

RCP provides the concept of perspectives. A perspective is a visual container for a set of views. A view is typically used to navigate a hierarchy of information (e.g. the zone plan data or assembly construction steel diagrams are special views). The concepts of perspectives are filtering information and task oriented interaction with information. The active perspective controls the layout of views and actions. In DigiMAus there exist six different perspectives. This allows increasing usability. Depending on users workspace the user can choose his right perspective by switching between perspectives via menu or perspective bar switcher. DigiMAus provides a permission management depending on each perspective and user for read-write or read-only access.

Fig. 8 : Available perspectives

2.6 Zone plan

The Zone plan editor makes it possible to generate and edit geometrical boxes. For each box 6 planes are needed which describes minimal and maximal dimensions. A plane holds unique id and description information, for example frame or deck name.

The arrangement is under the directive of FLENSBURGER standard. The standard defines naming and hierarchical conventions. In history the zone did not contain any geometrical information. The user had to look at the master plan.

Project as root element

- Main planning area (e.g. M000)
- Planning area (e.g. M100)
- Zone (e.g. M110)
- Rooms (e.g. 13+ Seawater Filter Room)

Fig. 10 shows a VTK visualization of Zone 'M000' and its hierarchical zones and rooms. The data defined in this perspective is the basis of visualization of all other perspectives. Navisworks allows to define clipping planes (maximal six planes). The visualization of zones exercises this functionality. The limitation of six planes is exactly enough. Steel modules and underlying assembly groups uses hiding functionality of Navisworks elements.

Zone/Room	Description
M000	Activities Engineer Area
19	FR_-5
92	FR_68
17	SB_-20000.0
18	BB_20000.0
13	Bottom_0.0
300	D300_18150.0
M100	Engineroom Tank Top
19	FR_-5
74	FR_50
17	SB_-20000.0
18	BB_20000.0
4	Platformdeck_6000.0
5	L100_1650.0
M110	Engineroom Tanktop fr. 17- 50
41	FR_17
74	FR_50
17	SB_-20000.0
18	BB_20000.0
4	Platformdeck_6000.0
5	L100_1650.0
10+	Engineroom Tank Top
10A	Engineroom Tank Top SB
10B	Engineroom Tank Top BB
12+	HFO Purifier Room
13+	Seawater Filter Room
M120	Engine Room / Aggregate Room

Fig. 9 : Example of a zoneplan

Fig. 10 : Visualization of "M000" main planning area

Fig. 11 : Object list of seawater filter room

2.7 Control in 3D

In this perspective the planner gets the possibility to assign material respectively objects to an assembly activity in the three dimensional model. Fig. 11 shows the basic proceeding. The first (1) step is to visualize a zone or steel module, then the selection group (2) that creates a table-view of this area. Now DigiMAus queries data from database for each element and presents the result as an objectlist view and pipartlist view under the visualization. Now it is possible to show (3) detailed information and location in 3D model for each selected object. The planner is able to select an activity (4) and assign it to a selected object.

2.8 Production control

Aim of this perspective is to show all material assigned to selected activity. With this feature it is possible to check the current assembly state of the visualized area. After visualization (1) and selecting activities (2), an objectlist-view for each activity is created (3). Material that is built in before selected activities is also displayed (in grey), all other material is hidden. Created list-views have the same functionality as objectlist in “Control in 3D” perspective. Extended functions are:

- showing delivery state
- creating delivery requirement lists
- showing assembly order
- showing bundle order for the storage

Production control shows any controlling error done by the work in “Control in 3D”.

Fig. 12 : Visualization of several activities

2.9 Part search

Another perspective is the “Part search” perspective, an easy to use and fast search function. The search function relates to all material containing in the whole model. The searching condition can be any text, wildcards are allowed. This function uses Navisworks internal powerful finding function, it can fully be accessed via API. Found objects matching with searching condition are displayed as a

list. Now it is possible to select one or more objects and visualize it but hide all other objects around selection. Axes of coordinates is added with axis length of one meter, it is useful to see dimensions of objects. The worker in the storage who bundle pipeparts receives a right impression of the real object.

Fig. 13 : Part search of a pipepart

Fig. 14 : Meeting documentation and Methods

2.10 Method documentation

The method system is based on method-record-cards. It is allowed to link any information to these record-cards as textual notes, responsible person, date and remarks. Any zone, module, system, activity and protocol can be linked with method-record-card. Method-record-cards are summarized to a meeting-record with an attendee-list. Only in this perspective there exists another tabbed view, the system view. The shipbuilding project is separated into several subsystems and is shown in this view. During shipbuilding process the documentation of methods become more and more manifold.

2.11 Weights & Centre of Gravities

This perspective is for the steelplanning to control moduleweights and planning transportation procedures with using centre of gravities. This perspective is the newest feature and still under development.

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Reducing Management Software Costs

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Abstract

Shipyards often seek to improve operations through adoption of management information systems. The envisaged benefits include time savings, cost reductions and better strategic information. However when they go to market they are offered a difficult choice - either buy a commoditised 'shrink-wrapped' product or a heavy-weight ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning) suite. The former are cheap but generic, the latter powerful but expensive. Neither can satisfy both the requirements and budgets of many yards. This paper offers an alternative, to use the increasing ability of agile software development to rapidly and cheaply produce software, combined with the growing range of ever-more powerful open source technologies, can bridge this gap. We will show how not only initial development but crucially on-going support benefit from these innovations, and how every yard can now afford its own uniquely customised management information system.

1. Introduction

Computer applications for the marine industry come in two broad categories – functional software and procedural software.

Functional software is usually targeted at specific technical tasks that are required throughout the industry. Computer Aided Design and Hydrodynamic Analysis are good examples. Such functional software is essentially used as offered by vendors, and is chosen for the capabilities and cost-effectiveness of the product. It is installed then operated as sold, with usually periodic updates.

Procedural software also seeks to solve problems encountered throughout the industry, but these are usually company-specific. Examples are estimating and planned maintenance systems Procedural software such as accounting packages which have to satisfy legal requirements, can be considered “functional”, and used as sold. For most procedural software after initial selection customers expect to tailor the software to specific requirements. This paper discusses the implications of this customisation process, with an emphasis on how technical innovation can bring down costs.

2. Management Information Systems

Management information systems (MIS) are used as an example procedural computer application, because their functionality and application offer an ideal means to illustrate the ideas presented in this paper. MIS cover a wide range of activities designed to support planning, monitoring and control of operations within shipyards. Given this wide definition, we would expect the market to provide an equally wide range of software products. Instead we find either commoditised products such as Microsoft Project or heavy-weight ERP suites from companies such as Oracle and SAP. The commoditised products are relatively cheap (\$100's - \$1000's) but offer only generic functionality that cannot be tailored to yards' specific business. They can be considered functional software by our definition. The alternatives can be integrated with a yard's business processes., but the purchase customization costs of these procedural systems are in the \$10,000's-\$100,000's.

3. Lifetime Costs

The reason for this difference is that pricing reflects the lifetime cost per deployment for the software supplier. This can straight-forwardly be calculated as:

Clifetime = (Cdevelopment + Csupport) / n where:

Clifetime	: lifetime cost per deployment
Cdevelopment	: total development cost
Csupport	: total support cost
n	: number of deployments

There should be no significant difference between the development costs of functional and procedural software. Moreover any improvements in software development practices equally benefit any development effort. Thus 'Cdevelopment' is not a differentiator. What makes the difference is the customisation inherent in procedural software deployments and its effect on 'n' and 'Csupport'.

4. The Cost of Customisation

Compared to functional software, the customisation of procedural software inflicts two cost penalties; The first is the effect on the divisor 'n' - the number of deployments. The second is its direct impact on Csupport.

Bespoke developments where 'n' equals one inevitably cost more than functional software where 'n' can run into thousands. Cost-effective customisation has to increase the value of 'n' whilst still offering the unique functionality required by each customer. This feat requires an enhancement to the formula given previously:

$$\text{Clifetime} = \Sigma (\text{Cdevelopment} + \text{Csupport}) / n$$

If the software is viewed not as a single entity but as a system made up of multiple components, the cost calculation is similar but now the variables can be different for each component. The total cost is the sum of costs for all the components. The aim is to increase the proportion of components where 'n' is high (and conversely decrease the number where 'n' is low or one) and also reduce 'Csupport' for the components. This merits further investigation, as this is not a simple argument for code re-use.

5. Encapsulation

The support cost 'Csupport' of a specific component is a function of its quality and its complexity. Code complexity is whole field in itself, but in most modern development methodologies and technologies, a good proxy for code complexity is encapsulation. This hides internal representation and implementation details, thereby protecting parts of a system and its data from inappropriate access or alteration. [Kiczales, et al. \(1997\)](#) Encapsulation enables change in components without compromising the stability or functionality of other components.

An important overall trend in the evolution of software engineering is towards greater encapsulation at the finer and the broader scale. Examples range from the macro concerns of Service Orientated Architectures (SOA) to the intricacies of join points for orthogonal concerns in Aspect Orientated Programming (AOP). For this paper, the effect of encapsulation on support costs can be explained by stereotyping the architectures of customisable, procedural systems into one of :

- Big Ball of Mud;
- Hub and Spoke;
- Lego Brick.

The Big Ball of Mud architecture can be described as "... a haphazardly structured, sprawling, sloppy, duct-tape-and-baling-wire, spaghetti-code jungle. These systems show unmistakable signs of unregulated growth, and repeated, expedient repair. Information is shared promiscuously among distant elements of the system, often to the point where nearly all the important information becomes global or duplicated," *Brian and Yoder (1999)*.

Big Ball of Mud

Big Ball of Mud

This is the default architecture for complex, procedural software systems, particularly those with an extended life. Such systems have high 'Csupport' and low 'n' (often 1 as they become, in effect, bespoke systems for each customer). It is difficult to customise them beyond pre-planned limits, and the process of customisation may include obscure configuration & undocumented procedures.

Hub and Spoke architectures have a common core into which optional spokes of functionality can be plugged. Customisation is a matter of selecting the required spokes and then tailoring these. A Hub and Spoke architecture offers a coarse grained component model. The risk is that the spokes become interdependent Small Balls of Mud. Alternatively the hub may well expand over time at the expense of the spokes, becoming itself a Big Ball of Mud.

Hub and Spoke

Hub and Spoke

Lego Brick

Lego Brick

Lego Brick is the finest grain component model. Functionality is broken down to as low a level as possible. Each component is linked only to its direct dependencies. Lego Bricks offer the lowest 'Csupport' and highest 'n' of these architectures.

This terminology should be used very strictly in the context of this paper and not confused with similar terms used elsewhere. The architectural category of procedural software is often revealed by the terminology used and procedures necessary to customise it. If features can be 'unlocked' or 'configured' then we are probably looking at a Big Ball of Mud. If there are 'modules' that can be incorporated in a one-off manner by the supplier's technical staff there is probably a Hub and Spoke. If the required functionality can be selected, and applied on a per-user, per-machine, per-day basis then there are true Lego Bricks.

6. Why Lego Bricks?

The three architectures might be described as a continuum, describing in reverse order the evolution of many computer products. They start out as cleanly designed Lego Brick version 1's. Then the contingencies of production life, working to customers' timescales, gradually erode the initial design principles and structure. Customisation upon customisation causes components to bloat and merge. Coupling makes Lego bricks into spokes, and eventually a Big Ball of Mud emerges.

However this view does deal with the fundamental differences between Hub and Spoke, and Lego Brick architectures. These can be listed as:

- non arbitrary granularity;
- functional specialisation;
- general applicability;
- minimal state;
- additive, not just complementary;
- active dependency management;
- refactorable code.

The granularity of Hub and Spoke architectures is often defined by the product's marketing, which targets customers' business concerns; e.g. an MIS product may offer separate payroll and cost monitoring modules. These modules may integrate but are kept as discrete components. In fact the processing is effectively the same so the code is either moved into the Hub or duplicated across the Spokes. Reflecting the division of responsibilities within a specific shipyard organization structure does not lead to good technical design.

In contrast Lego Brick architectures offers a much finer level of granularity where the components can be scoped on purely technical merits, and then grouped as necessary to provide the business functionality. Using the same bricks can generate very different end results.

Finer granularity makes for simpler components, specialised for their particular functionality, but generalised in their applicability. Continuing the payroll/cost monitoring example, both functions may use a common component that collects job card data and aggregates it. The component need know about payroll or cost matters, only how to aggregate the data. Moreover if a new requirement appears, for example to monitor exposure to VOC emissions, the component is immediately reusable.

A particularly powerful technique is to abstract the business domain model as much as possible, so if a cost monitoring component deals with 'cost centres' rather than 'projects', then it can easily be used re-used in a planned maintenance function.

Generalisation also allows for extensibility. It removes constraints on how systems can be customised. It changes conversations with customers from 'here is the list of options available' to 'what do you want?'

Finer grained, simpler components also have less internal state. This makes them more testable, which increases confidence when introducing changes.

These arguments point to an ever-finer degree of componentisation. This will almost inevitably degrade unless rigorous engineering discipline is applied throughout the system's production life. Two fundamental disciplines must be followed if this is not to happen. Both are to do with the relationships between components.

The first is that functionality must always be added as components are built on top of one another. If component A depends on component B, A must not change B's behaviour. In the object orientated

world, it is acceptable for subclasses to override super class behaviour. For customising a system of inter-related components, this is almost invariably a bad idea. It introduces dependencies, risks unintended consequences and drives up ‘Csupport’.

The second concept is that component dependencies must be explicitly declared and managed. The Lego Bricks must be bound by a framework that accommodates changes to individual components and can deal with any mismatches or inconsistencies. Most importantly, it must be able to manage new versions and also be capable of backing-out changes.

If these disciplines are followed, a Lego Brick architecture produces refactorable code which can be modified, customised and extended beyond its initial scope. Maintenance and customisation work can be focussed and safe. In the proposed cost equation, ‘n’ remains high and ‘Csupport’ low.

7. The Effect of Open Source

The Lego Brick architecture requires both suitable technologies and suitable development methodologies. Both are now available and both have been heavily influenced by the Open Source movement. This involves disparate groups of developers remotely co-operating, sharing ideas and code. This style of development more or less mandates a Lego brick architecture where the patterns involved are repeatedly exercised and improved in an open forum. An example of the shift from Big Balls of Mud to Lego Bricks is the move away from the heavyweight, monolithic application servers to lightweight inversion-of-control frameworks.

Open source has heavily influenced the growth of ‘agile’ development methodologies. These demand an iterative development approach with many and frequent releases. Effectively they are customising their products every day. As a result, open source provides much technology that can be used within Lego Brick architectures. Third party code can be wrapped as a component and immediately used. Open source offers a selection of frameworks to manage the Lego Bricks. This reduces the absolute scope of work, and permits the inverted efficiencies of scale encountered in software development (a 30 person development team does not produce 6 times the output of a 5 person development team). Open source also provides the technologies to support Lego Brick development, such as source code repositories for complex version control, and continuous integration tools with automated regression testing. Thus open source provides and proves the tools necessary to develop systems using the Lego Brick architecture. It is now useful to consider an example of such a system

8. An Example; Incremental “EPIC”

Incremental Epic is a management information system for ship repair and small-scale ship building. It uses an archetypal “Lego Brick” architecture based on the open source Eclipse RCP project. The Lego Bricks in this case are OSGi bundles - within Eclipse these are called plug-ins.

Specific own platform plug-ins are added to the base RCP platform to provide abstract implementations of common elements, a security model, and importantly a generic business entity model.

Above this there are functional plug-ins, each representing a particular area within contract control, for example estimating, planning, purchasing or personnel. Some, as an example invoicing, rely on other functional plug-ins, whereas others require only the platform.

The functional plug-ins are then tailored through a combination of enhancement and specialisation plug-ins. Enhancement plug-ins host functionality orthogonal to primary business logic such as reporting and Microsoft Office™ integration. The specialisation plug-ins are at domain, or industry, and customer level. Although Incremental Epic was written specifically for the ship repair business, marine specific specialisation is only introduced via one of these top-level plug-ins.

Customisation can be introduced through more than 30 ‘extension points’. Through careful use of type and defensive programming, the business model, and its presentation, can be specialised without compromising the stability or processing of the core functionality. Customisation need not be a one-off process. Incremental Epic is designed to be continually customised, with each individual installation running its own set of plug-ins. These can be added and removed at any time. The system can even self test itself for any particular upgrade, customisation, or change of plug-ins.

Incremental Epic leverages all the advantages of its architecture. It is developed and maintained by a small team, yet is customised for each customer. The plug-in model permits a large number of variations in the core offering whilst preventing an explosion in the number of development streams.

9. Conclusions

The cost of customizing procedural management systems is directly related to the way different deployments work. To reduce lifetime costs, differences must be reduced, by using encapsulation and a fine grained component model. Modern technologies and methodologies, influenced and supplied by the open source movement, permit development of reasonably inexpensive customised systems. Affordable, company-specific management systems are now accessible to all shipyards.

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Validation and Quality Control of Design and Production Information - Applying Rule Based Data Mining and Business Intelligence Concepts to Engineering

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Abstract

Design and production preparation tasks for ships and offshore structures generate large sets of data providing every detail needed for planning, procurement, and production. Many different participants and systems are involved in this very dynamic process with high modification rates. There is a constant risk of errors being introduced. We describe how a combination of state-of-the-art data retrieval and rule-based analysis techniques to validate engineering design and production data has been employed to reduce the risk of costly errors often uncovered very late in the production process. A rule based approach helps to protect customer know-how and provides a high degree of flexibility and sophistication.

1. Introduction

The design and production of ships and offshore structures requires creation of large amounts of data which are used to define the engineering design and eventually help generate production data. The cost of recovering from errors introduced early in the design process grows non-linear as production progresses. It is therefore quite useful to try to detect such errors as early as possible. The widespread use of software applications in design clearly has helped to reduce the frequency and mitigate the effects of traditional “human” error introduced during design. Nevertheless, some categories of errors still remain, and, unavoidably, additional possible sources of errors have been added. These are commonly encountered typical errors:

- software induced errors (e.g. failure to update values after changes, failure to save modifications)
- data transfer errors
- numerical precision issues
- incomplete data
- non-compliant design decisions (intentional or unintentional)
- wrong input or configuration
- missing or late information

An analysis of commonly encountered errors in different shipbuilding environments has shown that a major part of all errors remains undiscovered until production, tests, or even sea trials mainly because of the un-validated transition of data through departments, sub-contractors and other partners involved. Explicit validation however is very time-consuming and usually quite costly. Therefore, validation is only performed when absolutely required or when quality issues are already known.

The research work described in this paper is based on the assumption that it should be possible to reduce the frequency of errors due to constantly applied quality validation procedures and by shortening the feedback distance (between discovery and origin of an error). To reduce the cost and time needed, these validation procedures should be automated as much as possible. At the same time it should be practicable to apply validation after any process step as required.

2. Sample Scenarios

The typical product development process for ships can be depicted in a simplified form, Fig. 1. It shows the principal flow of information between stages like early design and detailed design. In addition to the pure data flow perspective there is the increased partitioning of the design tasks as the

process moves from global design activities to more and more refined tasks. So, as a side effect, more and more parallel “threads” of activities are created, which are performed in a quasi-concurrent mode (i.e. a mixture of sequential and parallel tasks). This also increases the potential for change requests being exchanged between those tasks, which always bear the risk of some part of the data becoming de-synchronized.

Fig.1: Common design/production data flow in shipbuilding projects

The easiest way to create a quality control structure is to install hand-over milestones. This is what traditionally is being done in the form of some internal/external approval process, e.g. by signing of a set of drawings or by receiving some sort of more or less formalized statement of approval, e.g. from an owner or a classification society. It seems plausible to use exactly these milestones as initial QC checkpoints. Therefore the goal is to inject a computerized QC step just ahead of the regular approval processes as well as to inject additional QC steps around every data hand-over. In the case of subcontracted design, the QC step may occur before delivery (performed by the subcontractor) as well as after receipt (performed by the customer).

In the longer run, the execution of QC steps should also be possible at any point during the execution of a design task up to the point where a designer may use this as a regular checking tool. Again, by detecting errors at the earliest point in time leads to reduced rework within a single design task. Compared to system-embedded QC functions, this external review procedure will provide the possibility of checking against other external data e.g. to verify correct interfaces. Based on investigation of some real-world problems at shipyards, we have selected two scenarios that exemplify the quality control problem quite well.

2.1. Design data transfer from subcontractor to shipyard

Subcontracting of engineering work has been in widespread use in shipbuilding for many years. Subcontracted work is a clearly identifiable point of data handover. It often results in CAD models, CAM data, drawings, part lists etc. Subcontractors will usually be required to perform some pre-delivery checking. Similarly, shipyard customers will perform some sort of checking after receiving the data from subcontractors. Due to the potentially complex mixture of data, this checking process can be very costly and may only be based on random samples.

2.2. Release of production data to production

This scenario is part of the mainstream shipyard data flow. Once design data (incl. production specific information) has been released to production, any further change or correction will be potentially very costly. This is another critical data handover as the next stages of processing will produce large amount of derived information, creating a lot of dependencies on the original design data.

3. Validation Processes

All design processes include some sort of validation activity. Regularly, the current state of detail is communicated to project participants like owners, authorities, suppliers etc. In engineering projects validation will occur in many ways, but most of these activities are traditionally driven by high level considerations like acceptance of product layout, features, and performance, compliance with rules and regulations, or to provide technical conditions and constraints to suppliers. In addition there has, however, always been a fairly substantial degree of process-internal checking, e.g. like reviewing, signing off, and publishing of drawings for design units like steel blocks, piping systems etc.

To check the correctness and validate design or production data, it is necessary to have full access to the detailed data resulting from the design activities. Usually early and detailed design data is produced in CAD systems. It is quite possible that a single design involves multiple design software systems, either to cover different phases of the design activities (like during early vs. detailed design) or due to organizational constraints, e.g. different systems being used by different departments or subcontractors. For production preparation tasks, a wide range of CAM systems may be applied covering tasks like NC data generation, detailed scheduling, and work content estimation. Closely linked to this phase are production planning activities ranging from pure scheduling and resource planning to detailed production control tasks.

Usually, the execution of the validation process will occur by means of manual/interactive checking done by design staff/management or reviewers, either using the originating design system or working with derived information like drawings, lists, spreadsheets, and the like. This way of checking addresses high level aspects like fulfilment of the requirements and specifications, compliance with approval, corporate, or project-specific rules, or application of best practice. At the same time, reviews will be used to detect lower levels like modelling or drawing errors, but based mostly on random samples, experience, or by coincidence.

Increasingly, some of the more sophisticated applications like CAD systems are offering additional modules or functions to perform validation tasks within these systems. This helps to detect system-specific design errors, once validation constraints or rules have been defined. It makes it possible to perform regular QC validation tasks in the current design context. However, the application of these validation tasks is limited to the specific system. This results in major limitations both regarding the scope of validation (no possibility to check data combinations from different systems) as well as detecting data handover problems of any type.

Hence it is desirable to utilize automated methods to provide a better coverage of checking. For this type of automated validation it is a requirement to have access to all the data needed (which would in most cases originate from different data sources) and to find a means to formulate validation conditions/rules on a broad scale.

Automated validation may occur on many different levels:

- data correctness and consistency
 - data formatting/validity
 - data sufficiency or completeness
 - data consistency/inconsistency resolution
- design rules
 - fundamental design rules (to ensure compliance with fundamental principles, e.g. no free-floating parts, no collisions/intersections of rigid bodies)
 - classification and statutory design rules (to avoid trivial/obvious deviation from regulations)
 - corporate design rules
 - project-specific design rules

Data correctness and consistency checks are used to detect data corruption, unintended or unauthorized manipulation, or low level software errors. Checking design rules encompasses the major bulk of validation tasks. Such rules require higher semantic expressivity than data correctness conditions. In such a QC setting it should also be possible to work with different versions of data. This will help identify revision issues, allows discovering unexpected changes, and will provide historic information to track down the cause of such issues. As the automated QC process can be rerun at any time, complete validation can be (re-)done many times, therefore guaranteeing complete checking against all defined rules.

4. A System Architecture for Automated Quality Control

To describe the system architecture of our QC system, we first consider the QC process before discussing the system components and their relationships to the system environment. The process can be structured into four major steps, as shown in Fig. 2.

The first step is **data validation**: to perform quality control of engineering data, it is key to work with data taken straight from the current revision of data intended to be used in further processing. For example, before handing over design data to production planning, a QC check would prevent errors from migrating into production or planning data. To accomplish this, close integration is needed with those systems that are used to generate and/or maintain such design data. Integration in this context means that a most complete collection of the data should be accessible during the checking process.

In the majority of cases it will be necessary to collect data from different data sources which can use quite diverse data structures to represent partially similar or overlapping information, creating a data structure set combination as depicted in Fig. 3.

The data validation process step will include actions to remove duplicate information, to consolidate overlapping information from different sources, and elimination of obsolete or invalid data. Data sanity checking at this level may lead to a premature finalization of the whole quality control process, e.g. if some data file has been substantially corrupted.

Fig.2: QC Process Flow

Fig.3: Overlapping data from different systems vs. interesting subset

The key task for the next step *data integration* is the merging of different data sets into a single normalized data representation. Most importantly, it will also normalize the data structures such that following steps will be able to work with a single set of meta data, i.e. a single data model.

Once the data has been integrated into a single data representation, the *data analysis* activities can be applied as the next step. These activities will primarily aim at (re-)constructing a *fact base* from the data available. Constructing a fact base can mean simple actions like *selecting* objects of interest from the integrated data set. For example, if a CAD structure with assemblies and parts has been provided, depending on the objective of the checking activity, only parts may be considered for checking. More complex activities would try to *derive* additional facts from existing data. A simple example would be to calculate the weight of a part based on the geometry and material properties provided. However, far more complex operations may be performed at this stage. This can include the creation of new individual data items representing their own set of properties. For example, welding information may be inferred from part connectivity and edge preparation details. Derivation may actually be deferred in some cases, where the need to have this information available cannot be determined in advance and the computational effort is high.

Once the data preparation activity has been completed, a *rule evaluation* activity will be performed, to perform the full-scope quality validation. Rule based systems like *JBOSS (2009)* or *FRIEDMAN-HILL (2003)* provide a number of capabilities that seem an excellent fit for the quality checking problem: they use declarative rule formulations which do not require the user to pre-determine some flow of execution. Instead the user can focus on describing which conditions need to be matched in order to fulfil a certain rule. Rule definitions can be expanded over time by end users as needed, thereby allowing large systems to be built and maintained over time. This effectively means that a quality knowledge base can be established in an organization at a convenient pace. The result of the rule evaluations will be collected and processed to provide a report about the checking process result.

This process has been implemented in a system as shown in Fig. 4. The sample CAD and CAM applications are representing an existing design and planning environment. These systems are used without any modification.

To execute a QC process, only a few parameters need to be defined by the user:

- the set of original data sources and optional sub-selection filters (e.g. the steel block(s) or a outfitting module(s) to be checked), and
- a collection of rules and/or rule sets to be used for checking needs to be selected to define the extent of checking (called a rule/rule set configuration).

The data validation and data integration steps are performed by different *publisher* modules, which provide the capability to retrieve data from the specific target system (CAD 1, CAD2, CAM ...). All these modules are implemented using the Topgallant[®] Adapter Framework, and convert the incoming data according to a single normalized data model, the Topgallant[®] Enterprise Reference Model (ERM), *AES (2009)*. This data model is built on international and industry standards and forms a superset of the typical data models found in CAD, CAM, and planning systems, thereby capturing all available information, *ISO 214 (2004)*, *ISO 215 (2004)*, *ISO 216 (2004)*, *ISO 218 (2004)*, *ISO 227 (2005)*. All further processing in the system will occur using this data model.

The normalized data representation is next processed in the data analysis step. To generate additional fact data, this step is directed by the requirements of the selected rule set(s). Every rule defines dependencies on specific types of facts exclusively via its condition clause, see Sec. 7). It is therefore possible to activate any matching fact-finding algorithms (i.e. algorithms which will potentially produce facts of the required type) based on these requirements. For example, a rule to check the compatibility of edge preparations on parts to be welded together will look for specific edge feature objects in the fact base. These edge feature objects may be constructed from geometrical properties of a part's geometry.

Fig.4: System Architecture

Once the fact base has been established, the main rule evaluation will take place. It needs to be supported by a library of methods and algorithms, some of which may be computationally complex. These methods are collected in a toolbox library, which makes them available to rule definitions. For example, geometry algorithms like area or volume calculation, transformations, centre-of-gravity, shape comparison etc. are provided in a geometry toolbox. The toolbox mechanism needs to be extensible to add more methods as needed. This provides the flexibility necessary to cover more and more topics with rules.

A central foundation of the QC application will be a rule base, which can be created and/or expanded by the user/organization. Is essentially a database of rules organized into a hierarchy of rule sets.

5. Data Integration and Data Fusion

During the data integration phase, a data warehouse approach is used to combine data from different sources into a single, normalized representation, thereby eliminating duplication and identifying conflicting data. This is accomplished by an ETL process (extract, transform, load) provided by the Topgallant[®] adapter framework. The integration step includes data quality checks and can therefore already lead to QC error reports, which will help to identify inconsistent data items that are required to be in sync.

The storage mechanism used provides full support for versions of data items. It helps to identify data modification during all stages of the QC process and to include history records in the fact base and thus in the rule evaluation strategy. For example, unchanged, approved data may be exempted from some rules during future checking stages. The details depend, of course, on the actual dependencies of the rules.

The specific challenge during the data integration is the requirement to deal with “fuzzy” data. This effect can occur on all levels, the simpler examples being numerical round-off deviations. Therefore,

for example, geometric analysis methods have been equipped with numerical tolerance parameters that can be modified dynamically during execution. This way it is possible to take into account the reduced numerical resolution of some data sources, without generating a large number of error reports due to more or less trivial numerical differences, which are generally acceptable. This approach can be further extended to deal with unavoidably deviating data items by employing data fusion techniques like probabilistic indicators. In the system discussed here, resolution policies similar to the approach described in *ANOKHIN and MOHTO (2006)* have been implemented. All data flagged as conflicting is sent through a fusion pipeline, in which a series of *elimination* steps is followed by a *fusion* step. The elimination steps will be used to remove duplicates or contradictory values based on a selected resolution policy like selection of attribute properties like version, availability, or minimum, maximum, average value. Since this will potentially still leave multiple values to select from (particularly if multiple attributes of a single data item are conflicting) the fusion step will then pick the final resolution value based on distribution parameters or selection patterns.

6. Data Mining Techniques

Data mining techniques have been developed over many years, primarily to “discover” implicit facts in large, fragmented data collections. The main application domain has been for systems used for administration, finance, or sales and marketing, *HAN and KAMBER (2006)*. Data mining is used to discover relationships and structures between data items that are not known in advance and are not expressed explicitly in the data model(s) being used in the target data store(s). Data mining thus has a close relationship to knowledge discovery or machine learning. It seems useful to apply techniques developed in this field to other areas like engineering data analysis.

In the context of a QC application, data mining is particularly useful to support the attempt to *re-establish* links and relations in data sets that are expected to exist (e.g. due to technical requirements) but are not explicitly modelled anywhere in the available data. For example, a designer will have various design intent aspects in mind when defining a steel structure. While creating a CAD model of such a structure, a lot of that high level information will be lost and may not be documented in the stored data set but result in data elements like the actual geometric shape of parts that reflect a rather implicit representation of the original intent. Therefore data mining techniques may help to re-establish or derive facts from existing data that can be critical to validate the expected quality conditions.

Data Mining involves a wide range of analysis methods with different degree of complexity. The key method areas commonly used are various statistical analysis algorithms and pattern matching. Pattern matching is a very powerful mechanism particularly for discovery of associations between data items. For example, based on a certain feature tree linked to a part, it is possible to assess facts about the connectivity between different parts. Similarly, geometry relationships will allow deriving spatial or topological associations, e.g. a part being located in a compartment, being attached to a wall etc. In the QC application we have also implemented a number of classification algorithms to determine specific assembly types like T-beam or Micro-panel based on associations. The system is therefore able to discover specific configurations which can then trigger suitable rule evaluations. Along the same lines, failure to discover such associations may also be a relevant input to rule evaluations.

Another interesting result of data analysis is the identification of *outliers*, which represent untypical data items. Outliers can be submitted to additional checking, as their occurrence frequency is expected to be low. Therefore the likelihood to detect a design error will be higher but it may be that the special properties are fully justifiable, which can be proven by additional rule checks.

Outliers detection is a result of cluster analysis applied to the data set. Discovery of clusters in data attribute distribution can provide a lot of additional insights – from the quite obvious geometrical interpretation (e.g. all parts of a bulkhead form a geometric cluster) to the more advanced uses like welding dimension control, where material thickness would be related to welding dimensions by a weighting function.

7. Rule Based Processing

Rule based systems are another technology commonly used for knowledge processing. The traditional architecture of a rule processing system involved the *fact base* (also called working memory), the *rule base* (also called production memory), and an *inference engine* (also called rule engine). The system is configured by defining rules in the rule base, e.g. by using a rule editor application. To process concrete data the fact base needs to be initialized by inserting data items e.g. from external systems like databases or modelling systems. While the engine is executing, new facts may be derived and inserted into the working memory.

Rule processing systems differ from conventional programming logic as they are working based on declarative rules. This means that there is no fixed flow of processing (like: check this first, then do this, then do ...). Instead, rules define conditions that are evaluated based on a scheduling algorithm implemented in the inference engine, which will act upon fulfilment of conditions.

Fig.5: Rule Engine components

A *rule* is a relatively simple construct to describe a set of *actions* that should be applied if a specified set of *conditions* is matched by the facts found in the working memory. The basic structure of a rule looks like this:

```

rule "title" [<options>]
  when <conditions>
  then <actions>
end
  
```

The **when** clause states conditions that need to be satisfied in order to *fire* the rule. Firing a rule will result in its actions list described in the **then** clause to be carried out. Actions can be anything, but typically they will either establish new facts or revoke invalidated facts, or record some state, or send some message. As part of actions, any kind of computation may be performed.

Fig.6: Rule base structure

Rules can be grouped in *rule sets*, which will provide a logical collection of rules. E.g., some rules might be used to assert certain facts (thereby inserting newly constructed data items as derived facts in the working memory), which will then in turn be subject to further rule evaluation. Rule sets can again be included in other rule sets, which subsequently build up complete rule set libraries, Fig. 6.

It is also possible that rules within a rule set share common resources like parameter settings among all rules in a rule set. Rule sets also provide a convenient means of grouping or classifying rules by topic. Rule sets can be nested to any depth, which provides a flexible way of organizing a large collection of rules.

Having stated that rule systems are declarative, there are still situations where rule evaluation should follow some sort of sequence pattern. For example, it may be desirable to evaluate light-weight checks first to improve overall performance. Or, it may be useful to define several processing stages that should not necessary overlap, as each stage may produce new findings (ending up as new facts in the fact base), which in turn would trigger re-evaluation of other rules, that may have been evaluated before. The solution to this is to assign a rule priority, which tells the system to prioritize rules with a higher setting. It should be noted, though, that the priority mechanism is particularly useful for optimization, rather than bringing in procedural flow logic “through the back-door”.

8. Prototype Implementation

The QC application has been implemented as an interactive system that provides all functions to establish a rule base, load a fact base from different connected data sources like CAD or CAM systems, and to perform data analysis and evaluation of a selected rule configuration.

As described above, quality control rules fall into different categories. Whilst the lower level conditions are concerned with data integrity and transmission fault detection, and are therefore somewhat static, the higher level design rules involve a great deal of engineering knowledge. Following the architecture described above a rule base needs to be built that reflects the different types engineering rules and constraints to be checked. Most important is the fact that these rules often must take into account corporate or project-specific rules that must be enforced. Therefore, a QC environment has to provide users with the possibility to establish (i.e. define/write) such rules. Fig. 7 shows the rule editing view of the application. The tree display shows the structure of the rule set hierarchy and any rules contained in it. The form on the right hand side shows a sample rule as it is displayed during rule definition.

Fig. 7: Rule Editor

The editor component is required only when creating new rules or modifying existing ones. It can be disabled for workplaces that require quality checking but no rule development.

The data retrieval sub-system consists of dynamically pluggable adapters. For the test environment, publishers for the Tribon® M3 Hull system, the Unigraphics® NX system, and AutoCAD® DXF have been used. In addition, output from the Alma act/cut automatic nesting system has been connected as a sample CAM application data source. To access CAD data from a sample project, the system specific publisher view will provide access to the CAD data store, providing navigation through the design structure. By selecting parts of the structure (e.g. a block), all CAD data items in that structure will be included as input data.

Fig.8: Loading fact base from CAD data

Fig.9: Rule Evaluation

Once the fact base has been loaded, rule configurations can be selected and the checking procedure is performed using the “Check” function. Validation errors or warnings will be indicated in the tree, a summary of detected problems can be searched, and a more detailed report can be saved as a PDF or spreadsheet document.

9. Summary and Conclusion

The approach to validation and quality control for engineering and production data described in this paper has proven to be effective and useful. The goals defined for this development have been reached. The mechanism chosen for formulating rules for engineering data validation has a large potential. The brevity and conciseness of rule formulations is quite promising and can be even further developed to be highly domain oriented. The combination of computer science tools such as geometry processing or numerical analysis techniques applied to engineering with combined with data mining and business analytics tools on the business side will provide a platform for powerful validation tools.

The essential prerequisites for applying such a technology are a well-established method of accessing a wide variety of data sources combined with the data integration and data mining/analysis capabilities as described above. Only the fully attributed set of data items provides the platform for non-trivial checking tasks.

Further work is, of course, desirable. For example, the data analysis tasks can be further extended in deal better with uncertainty. The whole area of fact/knowledge discovery algorithms holds many more options for sophisticated processing of fuzzy data. Advanced user support for formulation of rule definitions is needed to lower the entry barrier and training effort needed.

The integration of external validation actions seems to be another route to expansion. Using the toolbox mechanism described, external heavy-weight verification tools like numerically more intense strength analysis, production simulation, or NC data processing simulation could provide powerful tools to verify produce-ability of designs.

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Extended usage of a Modern Product Model in Finite Element Analysis

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Abstract

Finite element method (FEM) has been an engineering tool for decades, and is beginning to replace also the more simple methods used traditionally for structural analysis in the initial phases of a ship design process. However, naval designers still seem to be lacking a practical tool for seamlessly integrating this sophisticated technique with other aspects related to iterative design cycles and the 3-D models applied. This paper will present the approach currently used in SURMA (Survivability Manager Application). The general principle behind the ideas described here lays in establishing a real two way communication between a modern ship product model and a full 3D finite element analysis software. The product model acts as a backbone for the structural analysis purposes, offering a highly detailed basis for the FE analysis, in terms of both the structures as well as the loads. The presented approach enables the full utilization of both tools when conducting structural analysis using finite element method.

1. Finite element analysis in a ship design project

As mentioned above, the finite element method has become a standard engineering tool for various calculation purposes, and is beginning to replace the more simple methods used traditionally for structural analysis. However, in the beginning of a new ship project, the designers usually have to consider various other naval architectural aspects such as the main particulars, capacities, the hull form, stability, etc., before the design takes shape enough for the structural details to enter the process. When the structural concept of the ship at hand is decided, the finite element analysis could for example proceed as showed in Fig. 1, IACS (2006).

In practice today, totally separate models are required to achieve this. In a typical procedure, the naval architectural calculations are done with some suitable software able to handle the surfaces and enclosed volumes, the structures are constructed in a software intended for structural engineering and the FE model is normally created within a third software, dedicated to the sole purpose of finite element analysis. At best, these software can make some use of the existing geometries in other systems. In most cases however, quite a lot of additional work is still needed to prepare the FE models in terms of idealization, mesh creation and especially definition of the loads and constraints.

A modern product model, such as NAPA in the current case, supports direct creation of finite element meshes which are based on the structural arrangement of the observed vessel. In addition to this, NAPA model also contains all relevant data for defining the most generally used loads and constraints needed in every basic FEA, in as well the intact, as in the damaged condition. This means that also the changes in the hydrostatic loads, e.g. due to holing and flooding or the reduction of structural strength could be taken into account.

In the following, first the current possibilities for FE model creation offered by NAPA are presented. Then SURMA (Survivability Manager Application) is given a short introduction, followed by a description of how and why SURMA is currently employing FEA. The main principles of utilizing the NAPA model for defining the loads and constraints used in an FE-analysis are presented with some examples. The benefits and the open issues are discussed, highlighting also some development plans for the future. Finally the paper is summed up with a few concluding remarks.

Fig. 1: An example of FEA work flow in a ship project

2. Modern product model – Solid basis for FEA

2.1. Structural model

In practice, every finite element analysis begins from the definition of the geometry model that describes the structures subject to the analysis. The level of details in this model is dictated by the purposes of the intended analysis, and varies greatly. For a global strength analysis for example, a relatively coarse model with only the main structural members i.e. shell plating, decks, bulkheads, girders and stringers may be sufficient. On the other hand, a hot spot analysis for fatigue prediction can require a very detailed model including the bracket toes or even seams.

NAPA product model offers a flexible platform for the structural modeling, enabling the designer to select the desired level of detail almost at will. The basic structural model can be consistently created from the compartment model, containing arrangement of compartments, thus their bounding surfaces. The amount of details can be increased as the design process evolves, and can virtually be taken to an arbitrary level in accuracy, if need be. A fairly detailed structural model created in NAPA is illustrated in Fig. 2, accompanied with a photograph taken from the corresponding vessel.

2.2. FE models

Currently NAPA model supports three different FE meshing policies and an arbitrary number of actual FE models within a single ship project. The predefined meshing policies are named 'Global', 'Local' and 'Fine', every policy defining an independent set of parameters controlling various aspects of meshing, thus the resulting mesh quality and accuracy. Although the number of different FE models is not limited, all FE models must be created within a single meshing policy, *NAPA (2006)*.

Fig. 2: Detailed structural NAPA model

The parameters controlled by a meshing policy affect for example which structures and structural details, e.g. stiffeners, brackets, openings and seams are included in the FE model. Also certain aspects of idealization and priorities of topological features can be controlled within a single policy. The option of selecting the parameters of each policy freely makes the organizing of models for different purposes quite simple and straightforward.

2.3. Meshing – controls and output

Besides having the possibility to select which of the structures and details of the structural model are included in the FE model, NAPA provides the user with various controls over the actual meshing. The parameters affecting the surface meshing which the user can manipulate include the upper and lower limit for desired mesh size, the tolerance for point detection, the weight factor of quadrangles and an exhaustive list of others. These controls can also be selected individually for single objects if necessary. When a complex enough geometry is encountered, where the meshing parameters alone do not lead to a satisfactory outcome, there is the possibility to control the meshing manually by locating suitable auxiliary traces on the surface objects, *NAPA (2006)*.

Regarding other preprocessing facilities, NAPA includes an FE model check tool, which enables the user to see the quality of the resulting FE mesh instantly when the mesh is created. The tool includes various check criteria, and a plotting functionality which makes the spotting of the problematic elements fairly simple, thus giving the user the proper means to further adjust the meshing.

When the user is satisfied with the particular FE model at hand, it needs to be output in suitable format in order to be analyzed. Sometimes only the geometry of the mesh is required, but a more useful output can be achieved by utilizing also the material data available in the product model. FE models in NAPA contain material data for all elements, plate thickness for shell elements and geometric data, i.e. cross section properties and beam orientation, for beam elements.

The built-in output formats include Patran Neutral File, Nastran Bulk Data and Element Node Point and Area Key Point formats for Ansys. However, the most powerful output utility in NAPA system is the macro language. By macros the user is able to modify the FE output to fulfill any specific needs and to create links to also other FE formats than those currently existing. One example of this is an in-house link to Abaqus FE software, written at Surma Ltd as NAPA macros, which among other things export the beam elements as geometrically defined objects, hence not only the section properties, and supports element sets defined for example by the structure type. An FE model exported to Abaqus for eigen mode analysis is showed in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: FE model for eigenmode analysis

3. SURMA – Extending usage of product model in FEA

3.1. Survivability Manager Application

SURMA, Survivability Manager Application, is a practical design and analysis aid for the concept and the basic design phases of vessels required to withstand the hazards presented by conventional weapons. The main aim is to assess the survivability of a vessel against given weapon threats by the applied vulnerability analysis. The current version of SURMA is based on the NAPA product model, and uses extensively the features and calculation possibilities offered by this model. Although the development of SURMA is driven by the needs of a military solution for combat survivability assessment, most of the features offered by this application can be used in any ship design project.

In the current version of SURMA the susceptibility and the recoverability are neglected, and the vessels survivability is assessed by means of damage stability, longitudinal strength and functionality of vital systems including operation capability of personnel.

SURMA is intended to be a fast and robust tool, that enables changes that are based on the analysis results provided by it during the iterative design cycles. Considering this statement with the characteristics of the FEA mentioned above, there seems to be a contradiction. However, one of the ideas behind SURMA is to find a practical balance between the current state of the art methods and the feasible procedures that are used in everyday engineering work. In the following is explained how this challenge is currently handled in SURMA.

3.2. Current FEA usage in SURMA - The aim for balanced analysis

The use cases to be considered regarding a naval vessel's survivability assessment vary on a wide range from small local models, observing for example a new bulkhead configuration, to huge global models assessing e.g. the whipping modes of the hull girder. In most of these cases the latest available techniques facilitate the analysis, including full 3D approach combined with the theory of large deformations and non-linear material behavior, *Kurki (2007), T., Shin and Schneider (2003), McShane et al. (2007)*. For the sake of performance and robustness, SURMA uses currently an equivalent single degree of freedom system (SDOF) to perform dynamic analysis for the local structural elements to define the effects of a warhead detonation. The resulting damage is then incorporated into damage stability and longitudinal strength calculations, which yield the traditional GZ and longitudinal strength curves.

To maintain the speed and robustness of this kind of approach, the first implementation of a full 3D finite element analysis in SURMA is not directly involved with the structural damage, but is meant to make this more reliable and accurate by supporting the generation of the SDOF systems. The idea is to create one global model of the whole vessel including the designed normal operating conditions. From this model the initially existing stress levels in different structural members can be calculated, and the initial dead loads affecting the SDOF system properties determined. Depending on the case, the effect of the dead loads on the deformation capacity of the structural element might become significant, thus influencing the total outcome of the structural analysis.

Holding with other assumptions, the presented approach requires only one reasonably rough global FE model of each vessel configuration without the need for smaller details to be considered. This means that even as the design of the vessel is altered, only major modifications call for a new FE analysis, thus the basic procedure remains fast.

Fig. 4: SURMA FEA work flow

SURMA uses currently an external non-commercial FE solver, which is needed only as for solving the FE analysis. However, this general approach can be utilized also for other purposes of numerical analysis and used in conjunction with other FE tools as well. The FE work flow implemented in SURMA is illustrated in Fig. 4 and some of the future development plans are discussed later on.

Although still in testing phase, this implementation shows remarkable promise regarding the potential this kind of approach gives with respect to utilizing FE analysis in vulnerability and survivability assessment.

3.3. Global loads

For the purposes of a global strength assessment, the fundamental loads to be considered are those resulting from the weight of the vessel and the buoyancy forces originating from the external pressure of seawater acting on the shell plating.

The weight of the vessel includes its lightweight and deadweight. Usually the part of the lightweight composed of the structural weight is automatically included in the FE analysis, as the vector defining the gravity is given and the mass of the elements is calculated from their volume and material data. The other part composed mainly of equipment, outfitting and furnishing can normally be fetched e.g. from statistics as curves giving the mass distributions with respect to main axes. With fairly simple means, this kind of distributions can be converted to proper nodal or element loads.

NAPA provides the longitudinal curves of strength automatically when the loading conditions are defined. The weight resulting from the deadweight can be handled in the manner mentioned above as the distributions derived from the loading condition. The other option is to calculate the actual local loads where applicable and add these to the other loads in the FE model as such. This option is more discussed in the following section.

The buoyancy forces depend on the floating position of the vessel, thus the observed loading condition. NAPA calculates automatically the floating position corresponding to any given loading condition. In an even keel situation it's trivial to find the elements of the shell plating which are below the water plane. When considerable trim or heel takes place, the task of finding these elements becomes somewhat more tedious, yet manageable. When the elements subject to external pressure are collected, the pressure acting on each element can be calculated with sufficient accuracy from the draught of the element and the seawater density, thus applied to the FE model.

3.4. Local loads

NAPA offers a possibility to calculate the local loads resulting from aspects such as the lateral pressure in tanks, the weight of cargo other than liquid as well, the weight of main equipment components and the weight of the outfitting. What makes this feasible is the fact that within NAPA system there usually exists some kind of geometric or topological connection between different objects and this way also between different definitions related to these. The noteworthy thing is that these objects and definitions are either having or can be given also physical properties.

When the bounding bulkheads of a tank are known, or the location on the deck where some heavy apparatus will be mounted, the elements and the nodes subject to the resulting load can be defined from the geometric or the topological connections. When this is combined with the data provided by the compartment arrangement, the loading condition and the equipment properties, basically all information exists to determine the actual loads, which can then be inserted into the FE model.

3.5. Special loads

As stated earlier, SURMA is primarily a tool for the combat survivability assessment of naval vessels. This means that most of the analysis include military loads, e.g. loads originating from warhead explosions etc. Currently SURMA is able to provide the time-pressure histories related to conventional warhead detonations in air, either inside or outside the vessel. Also the mass and the velocity of the fragments from the casing are calculated. These loads are already used in structural damage calculation in SURMA, and can be incorporated into an FE model as local loads in the manner described above. An example of an air blast related FE analysis conducted using this approach is illustrated in Fig. 5.

LC1:DISP
 Tim:0.001166
 entity:ALL
 max: 5.38e-002
 min: 0.00e+000

C:\temp\koelaatikko3.frd

Fig. 5: FE calculation of air blast response using SURMA

3.6. Other constraints

Beside the loads described earlier, NAPA model can be used to generate other constraints as well. One example is the 'spring constant' associated with the change of buoyancy in dynamic situations.

SURMA currently uses this kind of constraint in the simplified eigen mode analysis, which is based on beam elements. In this approach, the hull girder is presented as a set of beam elements, and the cross section properties are calculated from the structural NAPA model. The residual weight of the vessel itself is fetched from the compartment and the equipment arrangements and the added mass of the surrounding water from an empirical formula. These are then added onto the beam elements.

The constraints related to the surrounding water in this model are imposed in the form of spring elements, and the properties of these spring elements are derived from the hydrostatic data of the NAPA model. In the current implementation spring elements with non-linear force-elongation relationship are used. Three first eigen modes calculated for a 250 m long crude carrier using this method are illustrated in Fig 6.

Fig. 6: First eigen modes of a crude carrier's hull girder

3.7. Benefits of the presented approach

The benefits of the presented extension of a modern product model usage in FEA are apparent:

- The analyzed FE model is always consistent with the product model presenting the current design of the vessel, thus minimizing the potential of differences and errors.
- The additional work and time consumption for creating the FE model can be minimized.
- This kind of approach is fairly straightforward in terms of widening the scope and extending the usage to other areas of application of FEA.

4. Development - current issues and beyond

Currently the development concerning the integration of FEA is focused on making the herein described first implementation work seamlessly with the already existing SURMA machinery. The next natural step will be the damaged longitudinal strength analysis with the global model. The recent advancements to include also fire simulations in SURMA make this an interesting prospect for taking the secondary damage effects such as the effect of heat on materials into account also structural wise.

Although the replacement of the SDOF systems to corresponding FE models as a basis for the local structural damage analysis doesn't currently seem practical, the presented approach gives a possibility to create local FE models of the selected structural members if these are considered critical in further design stages. Also the system functionality analysis can be enhanced to gain better resolution regarding the damage with the assistance of the FE calculations. Global FEA is also required when the whipping effects of a shock impact of a near field under water explosions are assessed.

Some attention is going to be paid also to the utilization of the finite element method for other fields of application beside the structural analysis, such as the signature reduction. However, these are only issues subject to further consideration in the future.

5. Conclusions

The herein presented approach shows the remarkable potential that a modern product model offers when used in conjunction with modern analysis tools, such as the finite element method. The described procedure for extending the usage of data provided by the product model in FE calculations is straightforward and relatively simple to adopt for use in almost any environment meant for numerical analysis. The mentioned FE tools and features of herein utilized product model enable the user also to perform finite element analysis in some cases even without external pre- or post-processors, requiring only the solver.

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Rule-Based Resource Allocation – An Approach to Integrate Different Levels of Planning Detail in Production Simulation

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Abstract

The production simulation has been proven to be an effective tool for handling the complexity of shipbuilding. To deal with the planning processes varying from detailed planning to on-site decision, simulation models have to be reprogrammed by simulation experts who are scarce resources on shipyards. Therefore the IPMT developed a rule-based decision module for simulation tasks, which supports the simulation user to model the decision-making process with the help of predefined conditions and actions. This module decreases the simulation experts' efforts and gives planners a flexible and easy modeling tool for the simulation.

1 Situation

The European shipbuilding industry is challenged in the global market by the Asian yards, which benefit from the site-specific advantages in case of low labor costs. In contrast to this advantage the German shipyards try to be distinguished by the quality in the products and in the production process, *Krüger (2003)*. Regarding the production processes the key performance indicators are efficiency and reliability, expressed through lead times and adherence to schedules.

In general, each ship is unique and there is a high variety of ship types. Hence the product imposes a great dynamic influence on the production processes. Quantifying and controlling these influences has to be the primary objective of the production planning to achieve a reliable workflow with minimal resource usage.

Simulation is a proven tool to measure and quantify production workflows. The reliability of a plan can nowadays be ensured through simulation because different influences on the production processes can be modeled and quantified. In recent years, shipbuilding industry specific toolkits have been developed for different simulation tools to provide a simplified representation form of the simulation models. The simulation toolkit in Fig. 1 named „Simulation Toolkit Shipbuilding (STS)”, *Steinhauer (2003)*, was developed by the international research cooperation „Simulation Cooperation of Maritime Industries“, which consists of several shipyards and universities. The toolkit is consistently developed further to adapt to current challenges. The toolkit supports the modeling of shipbuilding specific material flows by providing a set of modules, which represent complex functions within the model. An example is the assembly order control in block building or the administration of resources on the building sites, *Steinhauer et al. (2005)*. The simulation of the building site capacity within the shipyards is an example of area capacity planning. The user is enabled to calculate the area demand and the missing building site capacity as well as the necessary transport capacity with the support of predefined area assignment rules, *Nedess et al. (2007)*.

To further decrease the effort in simulation projects, TUHH developed in cooperation with Flensburger Schiffbaugesellschaft a tool to automatically parameterize simulation experiments in the shipbuilding planning, *Nedess et al. (2008)*. This tool leads to an improvement of the sequence planning e.g. within the single part production or panel assembly, by decreasing the necessary production capacity up to 10% compared to common planning methods, *Steinhauer (2008)*. Despite the realized potentials, the use of simulation as a planning tool is limited to selected areas within shipbuilding companies. This is mainly caused by the need for intensive support from simulation experts for the planning staff, production engineers and foremen.

The optimization of the simulation by heuristic search methods for the optimization of alternative plans leads to a workload relief for the simulation user by automatically carrying out the simulation and looking for adequate alternative simulations. If however the boundary conditions of the system change, the simulation model has to be adapted as well. The simulation expert has to modify the controlling and planning rules of the model.

The STS provides adapted modules for the model development e.g. the construction area and it also allows the adaption of common simulation modules through parameterization so the model can respond to each new situation. The simulation model is however linked to a predefined workflow order, which cannot be changed, in order to reduce the complexity and to simplify the verification of the model.

If variant plans are needed or the workflow order changes, e.g. caused by a delayed delivery of components like the main engine, the simulation expert has to adapt the process logic of the model accordingly.

Fig. 1: Simulation toolkit for the shipbuilding industry and model examples

Nedess et al. (2004) found that one of the major hindrances against the use of simulation in the shipbuilding industry is the low availability of simulation experts. Looking for ways to overcome this shortage, the following concept of scenario based simulation has been developed.

2 Scenario-based simulation

The basis of this concept is the profile of requirements or competences for the different tasks and responsibilities in the production simulation, which leads to the classification into the two user groups of the simulation operators and the simulation experts. The group of the simulation operators consists of the planners and the technical staff, like foremen or engineers in the production. Those simulation operators have the detailed knowledge about the systems or processes to be modeled, but have only a basic understanding of the modeling and simulation methods. They do not have the specific knowledge about the simulation models as the simulation experts own. Based on the user classification the responsibility assignment shown in Fig. 2 was developed. The simulation operator as the user of the simulation tool for robust production planning and control and the simulation expert can be characterized by their different tasks.

Fig.2: User groups in the production simulation

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The simulation operator specifies the simulation task according to the planning problem. It is defined in a similar manner like the functional specifications from IT-projects (main questions are: What? Wherefore?). The data and information for the implementation of the simulation model is defined by these functional specifications so that the simulation model can be build. Additionally the requested parameters for the experimentation have to be derived from the particular problem resp. simulation task.

In order to evaluate planning alternatives and possible data scenarios with the simulation the simulation operator has to be enabled to use the parameters according to his in-house knowledge about the production processes. After the experimentation, the simulation runs, the simulation operator is supposed to interpret the simulation results and has to develop the measurements or consequences for the production planning and control. But he has to be supported in the interpretation of the results. The support of the simulation operator requires specific knowledge about the simulation models and the validity of the data to avoid the problems in case of the in-house acceptability of the simulation-based decisions.

The simulation expert shall prepare the simulation scenarios for the simulation operators. Therefore the experts' tasks are divided into the preparation of the data retrieval, the modeling or implementation of the executable simulation model and the design of experiments resp. the parameterization of the simulation scenarios. The simulation models and the simulation data has to be validated and verified over the whole process, *Rabe et al. (2008)*, so that the simulation expert has to assure the accompanying validation and verification of the simulation tools.

The objective of this concept is to disburden the simulation experts in case of the direct use of the simulation tools in the production planning and control. Nevertheless the simulation operators have to be supported as good as possible in case of simulation use. In order to achieve these goals the problems for the simulation tasks are surveyed, whether there are different categories of customizable simulation scenarios to develop a step-by-step customization of the used simulation toolkit. Thereby the effort for the customization of the simulation toolkit should be reduced.

3 Elements of simulation scenarios and the requirements for the modification

Studying the basic elements of a simulation scenario (simulation data, results and model, Fig. 3) with a view to the requirements from user specified modifications, the evaluations as well as the simulation models can be pointed out. While the evaluations can be generally classified by the different types of representations (such as capacity or due date oriented diagrams) and therefore the evaluations can be defined in advance of the specific simulation experiments, the simulation models have to be implemented according to the specific problem. The implementation of the models cannot be fulfilled by the simulation operators, because they do not have the adequate knowledge in case of the modeling requirements and the consistency of the models.

Fig.3: Elements of a simulation scenario

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The consistencies are required for the data validation in terms of plausibility, integrity and correctness of the simulation scenarios. The specific lack of experience in this area can be handled by different approaches. Basically adaptive solutions for this problem are on the one hand the availability of numerous standard simulation models (with corresponding descriptions like characteristics for the simplification of the model selection) or modifiable simulation models that are restricted to an approved number of variants by the simulation experts. In both approaches the development or implementation of the models has to be based on the vocabulary of concepts from the simulation operators, because the simulation model is not used on basis of a black-box-concept anymore but rather modified by an intervention of the operator.

As a result of the various effect parameters, the use of the numerous standard simulation models requires a powerful model management system including the components for the description and the selection of each model. For this reason completely new elements or modules for the simulation toolkit would have to be developed. This development takes a lot more efforts and time to develop properly.

A modifiable simulation model requires on the other hand only a conventional enhancement of the available simulation models in terms of the alternative simulation model components and the processing logic for the internal model linkage. If there is only a limited need for modification resp. variation of the simulation models, the adequate solution for this problem is an approach based on the configuration of the model. The simulation operator has to be enabled with the help of a graphical user interface to configure the processing logic of the simulation model. This is implemented by means of a rule-based methodology that is defined in the vocabulary of concepts from the simulation operators, such as the planners or the technical staff.

4 Rule-based approach

4.1 Rule definition concepts

Puppe (2003) implements the configuration process over different basic functionalities for a rule-based configuration system. The first approach is based on defined meshes of rules, which are used to select the different modules and combine them to a complete system. Thereby it is possible to modularize the meshes of rules in order to use them in different configuration systems such as different simulation scenarios.

The second approach starts with the definition of a particular configuration variant that has to be customized step-by-step by the user till a given criterion is fulfilled. With the third approach the problem is segmented in differenced partial problems or tasks so that the partial tasks can be easier fulfilled. The last-mentioned approaches are not adequate for the design of the rule based system, because the simulation operators do not have the competencies in terms of the simulation experts. That means on the one hand they do not have the model-specific knowledge to implement a simulation model and on the other hand the operators cannot segment the problem into partial tasks for the simulation implementation. The first approach is the best solution for the development of a configuration system in terms of simulation models, because the user does not need the model-specific knowledge for the simulation. Additionally the modularization of the meshes of rules provides an easier modularization of the simulation scenarios. Therefore a method based on a generative modeling concept has to be developed that can be used to build a mesh of rules for the configuration of simulation scenarios. The Feature-Diagrams from the generative programming concept, *Czarnecki (2005)*, can facilitate the development of the meshes of rules. Those diagrams provide the possibility for a hierarchical representation of the obligatory, optional or alternative configuration rules. The basic principle of the rule-based systems consists of an If-Then-logic for the rules. Therefore the rules have to be assembled from a preconditional and an action part. The preconditional part is applied on the to-be checked facts. The action part is triggered by a fulfilled precondition that is to say the rule fires, *Puppe (1993)*. A configuration rule states for a particular precondition (scenario specification or simulation modeling) the to-be conducted action in the compilation of the simulation scenario. Regarding the different configuration requirements the methods for the Feature-Diagrams has to be adapted to the scenario specification and the implementation of the simulation models. Indeed the check of consistency for the rule-based system is supported by the clear arrangement of the Feature-Diagrams. But the modularization of the meshes of rules inhibits an integrated checking of integrity, redundancy and contradictions in the complete rule system. Therefore a check for consistency should be conducted during the configuration of the particular simulation scenarios. In case of inconsistencies the scenario configuration should be halted and a report has to be send to the simulation expert. For the scenario specification the configurational aspects have to be defined according to the simulation scenarios. The rules have to be derived from the defined configurational aspects and have to be defined with the help of a descriptors' hierarchy, like in a database system. The configurational aspects are the possibilities of the simulation operator for a scenario build. The requirements for the simulation scenarios should therefore implemented as optional or alternative rules in the configuration. With the aid of the operators the simulation experts defines the configurational aspects in the notation of the Feature-Diagrams in order to reach nearly completeness of the possible scenario builds by the operator.

The building site allocation for example is one major configurational aspect for the simulation module „Production Space“. It is defined by different allocation strategies like locally fixed or object related strategies. The implementation of the Feature-Diagrams is the task of the simulation experts who develop from out of the diagrams the specific model structure for the simulation scenario. The Feature-Diagrams can be interpreted differently.

4.2 Rule Application

The application of rules influences three actuation variables of the production planning and control: resources, resource demand and sequencing of the resource demand.

The resource “staff” has a variable accuracy depending on the planning horizon. Within the rough planning, staff capacity is assumed to be inexhaustible. With a shortening planning horizon, qualification of employees and shift plans come into consideration. This has to be recognized by a planning horizon dependent rule. The transport resources, especially shipyard internal transportation means like heavy haulage or stationary cranes but also transportation routes are generally integrated into the simulation as transport control in the form of a simulation algorithm. This makes the consideration of transportation capacity bottlenecks in the simulation possible. This happens without user interaction, thus without the “firing” of a transportation rule. The user defines the selection of the transportation means and by doing so, determines the transportation requirements. These conditions are programmed within the method. In contrast to that, the resource „area“ (referring to storage and production areas) is predetermined through allocation decisions by the user. These decisions have to be considered within the simulation and they require an accompanying rule formulation. The manufacturing equipment resources, thus machines, production systems and workplaces may require alternative planning in bottleneck situations. The variation can be fulfilled through a rule based selection.

Resource demands can be derived as units demand from assembly oriented bills of materials, which lead to the capacity demand by the operation times documented in the work plan. The connection is implemented with the use of control algorithms into the simulation model. Different planning horizons and with that more detailed accuracy of the data, where calculated data replaces estimations, call for a variation of the model. Possible failures or changed working conditions which can be selected by the user need to be predefined to enable a robust planning.

Finally the sequencing of resource demands has to be implemented to the set of rules. On the one hand, the resource demand is influenced by the order sequence, and on the other, the workflow order is not always strictly predefined due to the one of a kind character of the product. The workflow order may vary within certain boundaries. The technological order sequencing requirements are predefined through assembly constraints. The adaptation or sequencing based on capacity conditions like e.g. blocked rooms due to high temperature operations, have to be defined accordingly within sequencing rules which block or release depending on the “firing” of the linked working operation. Therefore, the working operations to be executed have to be selected through a rule based system.

5 Application example

To evaluate the rule based simulation, the block assembly, Fig. 4, which plays the key role in time and capacity planning, is used as application example. All steel based structures of a ship are produced and assembled in the block assembly. In addition to the production and assembly of steel based structures, machinery and equipment is installed. The time frame in the section assembly is defined by previous and afterwards processes. Previous processes are panel and sub assembly production and the pipe and machinery shop floors. The afterwards process is the moth-balling of the sections.

Workers with different professions are working in the block assembly. These workers have to be coordinated. In addition the transport resources have to be planned with respect to the size and the weight of the sections because hall crane and heavy haulage may be a bottleneck. The most important resource in the section assembly is the building site. The use of the building site is planned during the early phase of scheduling sequence. The building site capacity is a narrow resource for building the big parts. That causes the high interest in an efficient use of this resource. This is realized by different allocation rules for the sections. For example building sites outside the halls are only used in case of

necessity in the winter. These outdoor building sites are only used for steel sections as other materials become too brittle to be processed.

Fig.4: Site allocation problem in the simulation

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In this way different rules could be implemented by the rule based simulation. The rules are able to realize the typical decision process of planning on the basis of prioritized criteria as in the utilization of the building site. The prioritization of the decision criteria is realized by the nesting of the rules. The implementation in a simulation model is transformed in two steps. In the first step a simulation user with operational experience defines the rules and the different configurations in a Feature-Diagram. The Feature-Diagram is implemented into the model by the simulation expert. In the second step the model is configured by the simulation user.

5.1 Implementation of the processing logic

The simulation operator has to define the Feature-Diagram for the building site allocation in the described way so that the simulation expert is able to configure the processing logic, Fig. 5. With the Feature-Diagram the simulation expert is able to define the rule terms. Afterwards he defines actions and programs the consistency check for the configured decision rules and the processing logic.

For the rule condition different control attributes, which have to fit the real conditions, have to be selected. The simulation operator is not able to define the rule condition or to select the control attributes. Hence the simulation operator uses descriptors to describe the real conditions. Afterwards the simulation expert implements the rules and realizes the model based on the descriptors. The control attributes could be elements of the model structure or attributes of the experiment environment, e.g. the simulation time or the dimensions of the part. From the control attribute the control value of the operator is conducted, e.g. “is bigger than” or “same as”. In this way the conditions are composed. By this preparation of the conditions it can be ensured that the rules work properly in the simulation model.

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Fig.5: Model of the decision process for the site allocation

The actions of the rules could activate the monitoring of nested rules or activate algorithms in the simulation model. The activation of simulation algorithms could change the model structure, the sequence logic or parameters which change the simulation sequence. E.g. an algorithm could change the type of selection of the building side. For the definition of the conditions and actions a graphic user interface was created. The interface supports the user by defining the rules and checks the submissions for completeness.

To ensure the consistency of the rule system, the rules have to be checked in terms of correctness, completeness and redundancies. The consistency check is based on the simulation model and has to be designed by the simulation expert. For the correctness of the rule system the attributes and action algorithms have to be checked with respect to existence and declaration. Regarding to completeness of the rule system the uncovered cases have to be identified. To check for redundancies the nested rules have to be reviewed for circular arguments. If one of these criteria is not fulfilled, an error report has to be written. With this error report the simulation expert should fix the problem as fast as possible.

5.2 Utilization of a configurable simulation model for the building side

To adapt the decision rules of the building side utilization planning in the simulation model, the simulation operator is able to select and prioritize the decision rules, Fig. 6. During this process the simulation user is supported by a graphical user interface. The interface shows the whole decision tree.

To select the rules the simulation operator utilizes the descriptors of the feature diagram. The simulation user is supported in changing the sequence logic by the selectable building side decision rules. This also changes the shown material flow and the given boundary conditions. On the one hand the user gets a deeper understanding of the modeled system and is able to create easy solutions for identified bottlenecks. On the other hand the user can operate the system correctly without the simulation expert.

Fig.6: Decision tree for the space allocation

6 Conclusions

The described rule-based approach is one step towards an easier usability of the production simulation as core objective of the GENESIM project funded by the German Ministry of Economics and Technology. The implemented toolset is used in the building site allocation of a German medium-sized shipyard in order to estimate a rough plan for the building site utilization in the block assembly. An efficient use of the resources and a comprehensible documentation of the planning decisions based on the simulation results were achieved. The production planner now operates the simulation. He is enabled to model, simulate and evaluate different allocation strategies based on defined allocation criterions. Additionally the processing logic of the simulation model is clearly arranged and can be easier compared with other scenarios in this simulation than in case of the conventional simulation modeling by the programming of simulation algorithms in the programming code of the simulation software.

The description of the decision rules in terms of the descriptors simplifies the comprehensibility for the simulation beginner. The communication between the simulation operators and the simulation experts is improved via the Feature-Diagrams so that a more complex processing or decision logic can be defined for the simulation scenarios as well. Overall the full potential of the use of simulation can be tapped by the rule-based modeling concept that was developed. The reason for this is that the simulation operators can be involved more into the modeling process. And the simulations experts benefit from this concept via an easier comprehensibility of the modeled systems and the systematic approach in the simulation modeling.

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Combining Artificial Neural Networks and Simulated Annealing Algorithm for Increasing Ship Transport Efficiency

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Abstract

The paper presents research results for application of artificial intelligence to the optimization of main ship design parameters and hull shape coefficients reducing ship effective power and thus increasing the ship transport efficiency. Basics of ship transport efficiency formulation were concisely discussed, together with examples for different approaches to optimization. An example of neural network use for determination of ship effective power is given. Furthermore, the constructed network was used in the optimization algorithm employing simulated annealing technique. A short computational example how the presented method can be used in the ship design is given and results of computations are presented.

1. Introduction

Due to increasing prices of oil every user of a transport mean is interested in saving fuel and this objective can be achieved with different approaches. Fuel consumption is less when ship's resistance is decreased, e.g. by forming a hull shape more slender. However, then the ship has less cargo capacity. A sensible compromise is needed. A measure for designing a ship which is economical from the fuel costs point of view and has sufficient cargo capacity at the same time can be formulated as transport factor or transport efficiency. The factor can be written as:

$$TE = \frac{W_P \cdot V}{P_B} \quad (1)$$

V denotes ship's speed, P_B is total installed propulsion power and W_P represents design payload. Design payload may be considered different for various types of cargo ships. E.g. for container ships design payload can be defined as the TEU number and then the transport factor can be written as:

$$TE = \frac{TEU \cdot V}{P_B} \quad (2)$$

For ro-ro ships a loading lane length given in meters might be applied:

$$TE = \frac{Lane_meters \cdot V}{P_B} \quad (3)$$

All variables in the presented above formulae depend on main ship dimensions and ratios such as: ship length L , breadth B , draft T , height H , block coefficient C_B , midship coefficient C_M , waterplane area coefficient C_W and many others. Usually, when a traditional design approach is considered the following problem is given:

- find a vector of independent variables (main ship dimensions and ratios):

$$x = x(x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_m) \quad (4)$$

which minimize or maximize a target or fitness function subject to equality constraints:

$$f_i(x) = 0, \quad i = 1 \dots j \quad (5)$$

or inequality constraints:

$$f_i(x) \leq 0, \quad i = j + 1 \dots k. \quad (6)$$

Constraints determine the space of design solution variation. In the ship design problem, an optimization task may be formulated as: for given deadweight DWT , speed v , and/or range R ; find a set of ship dimensions L, B, T, H, C_B for which a product:

$$L \cdot B \cdot T \cdot C_B = D \quad (7)$$

reaches a minimum, when the following constraints are fulfilled:

$$\overline{GM} = f(L, B, H, T, C_B) \geq \overline{GM}_{\min} \quad (8)$$

$$DWT = f(L, B, H, T, C_B) \geq P_L + P_S + P_R \quad (9)$$

P_L is a weight of cargo, P_S a weight of stocks and P_R a weight of reserve. GM is a metacentric height.

Other constraints may be applied if necessary. Frequently relationships for GM or DWT are empirical and come from statistics of the new-built ships. The neural networks can be applied for better performance of algorithms and this will be shown farther in the paper. The presented approach can be easily upgraded to multicriteria optimization.

Considering Eqs.(1) - (3) the propulsion power P_B can be written as:

$$P_B = \frac{P_E}{\eta_T}, \quad (10)$$

P_E is the ship effective power, a product of ship's total resistance and the speed: $P_E = R_T \cdot V$. η_T is the total efficiency:

$$\eta_T = \eta_H \cdot \eta_0 \cdot \eta_R \cdot \eta_S, \quad (11)$$

η_H is the hull efficiency, η_0 the open-water efficiency, η_R the relative rotative efficiency and η_S the shaft efficiency.

The process of optimization of ship transport factor TE may be thus formulated in many ways depending on global constraints and assumptions from a ship owner. E.g. in this paper the example of optimization of P_E (minimization) for the constant displacement target function is formulated as $P_E = P_E(L, B, T, C_B, \dots)$. The displacement becomes an equality constraint. The results are ship dimensions and ratios giving the less value of P_E for assumed speed or the speed range.

2. Objective function - neural network application

For the purpose of objective function formulation a neural network was developed. The network is a standard feed forward structure with back-propagation Levenberg-Marquardt training algorithm applied. The network was designed using Neural Network Toolbox, a part of MATLAB software. Log-sigmoid transfer function was selected for all neurons:

$$\log \text{sig}(x) = \frac{x}{1 - e^{-x}}, \quad (12)$$

where x is the input signal. The function generates outputs between 0 and 1 and requires inputs to be normalized to the given range. The learning set consisted of 171 cases of ships. Results for effective power partially come from experiments and partially from empirical algorithm developed by *Holtrop and Mennen (1984)*.

Initially, the ship length L , breadth B , draft T , block coefficient C_B and speed v were chosen as input values - the vector of solution which is the subject of optimization. Obviously, the effective power depends upon more parameters but they are less important and can be omitted during the selection of main ship data. The network has one input layer, one hidden layer with 9 neurons and output layer producing the result. The simplified structure of the network is given in Fig. 1.

Fig.1: Simplified network structure designed for the purpose of optimization objective function

The data set was divided up between learning set for determination of network weights and validation and testing data sets which give the independent measure for ability to generalize and the network performance. The process of network learning is presented in Fig.2, the regression analysis giving the information on network performance is presented in Fig.3.

Fig.2: Network error during learning process

The network performance seems to have good accuracy. This is due large size of learning set and the preparation of data with systematic changes of parameters which are subject of optimization. Data were prepared mainly basing on empirical algorithm. The designed network represents its simplified form.

Fig.3: Regression analysis of outputs and targets for three sets (learning, validation and testing).

For the purpose of further investigation of network ability to producing results with accurate trend, the network was checked against the data set containing values of propulsion engine power P_B for real ships. There is difference between effective power P_E and installed power P_B and it is the overall propulsion efficiency η , defined as it has been given in Eq.(10). The overall efficiency η represents energy losses in transmission system and propeller-hull interaction effects. For standard solution of propulsion system which is a system with one propeller in the aft and transmission without gearbox, the overall efficiency can be considered almost constant or changing at limited extent. The results of testing are presented in Fig.4. The network has sufficient ability to generalize data and may be used in optimization algorithm as the objective function.

Fig.4: Effective power P_E computed by neural network for real ship cases data, compared with engine power P_B for those ships.

3. Optimisation algorithm

For minimization of function represented by the neural network a simulated annealing algorithm has been applied. Simulated annealing is a method for solving unconstrained and bound-constrained optimization problems. The method models the physical process of heating a material and then slowly lowering the temperature to decrease defects, thus minimizing the system energy. At each iteration of

the simulated annealing algorithm, a new point is randomly generated. The distance of the new point from the current point, or the extent of the search, is based on a probability distribution with a scale proportional to the temperature. The algorithm accepts all new points that lower the objective, but also, with a certain probability, points that raise the objective. By accepting points that raise the objective, the algorithm avoids being trapped in local minima, and is able to explore globally for more possible solutions. An annealing schedule is selected to systematically decrease the temperature as the algorithm proceeds. As the temperature decreases, the algorithm reduces the extent of its search to converge to a minimum.

In general the following elements of simulated annealing algorithm can be distinguished:

- the representation of possible solutions,
- the generator of random values in the solution,
- solution assessment function - target function,
- cooling or annealing method - the starting temperature and the rules of its lowering in the process of target function minimum searching.

When the annealing algorithm is working it is necessary to adopt a method reducing the probability of transition to the state of worse parameters. Such a rule is called the cooling schedule. For the definition of the cooling schedule the following must be given:

- starting temperature T_0 ,
- final temperature or the alloy criteria,
- the length of the Markov's chain (depending on the number of variables),
- rule for the temperature decreasing.

In the basic version of the method the temperature is lowered proportionally - for each step the value is divided by the number from the range of $(1, \infty)$. The application of more complicated method is possible, which allows for the regulation of lowering speed during different phases of the working algorithm. The first method is:

$$T_{k-1} = \alpha \cdot T_k, \quad 0 < \alpha < 1 \quad (13)$$

and the second:

$$T_{k+1} = T_k e^{-\left(\frac{T_k \Delta(E)}{\sigma_{T_k}^2}\right)} \quad (14)$$

$$\Delta(E) = E_{T_k} - e_{T_{k-1}} \quad (15)$$

When $\sigma_{T_k}^2$ can be considered large, which usually has place during algorithm starting, the algorithm behaves like in random searching - the changes of temperature are very small. The opposite situation is when $\sigma_{T_k}^2$ is small and this usually means the algorithm is close to minimum. The probability of the transition to the higher energy state is given by the following formula:

$$p = e^{\frac{\Delta E}{kT}} \quad (16)$$

ΔE is a value of energy increasing, T the temperature at which transition to higher energy takes place, k the Boltzmann's constant.

Like genetic algorithms, simulated annealing models a natural process, which is the recrystallization of a liquid metal during annealing. The simple draft of the simulated annealing algorithm may be arranged as follows:

```

Initialize the temperature to T
initialize the chain length to L
initialize the neighborhood length to  $\zeta$ 
 $x_0 \in \Theta(x)$ ,  $f_0(x_0)$ 
initialize optimal solution  $x_{opt}$  to be  $x_0$  and its objective value
 $f_{opt} = f_0$ 
initialize current solution  $x$  to be  $x_0$  and its objective value
 $f' = f_0$ 
repeat
  for j = 0 to L
    i = i + 1
     $x_i \in \text{neighbourhood}(x, \zeta)$ ,  $f_i = f(x_i)$ 
     $\Delta(f) = f_i - f'$ 
    if  $f_i < f_{opt}$  then ,  $x_{opt} = x_i$ ,  $f_{opt} = f_i$ 
    if  $f_i < f'$  then ,  $x = x_i$ ,  $f' = f_i$ 
    else if  $\exp(-\Delta(f)/T) \cdot \text{random}(0,1)$ 
      then  $x = x_i$ ,  $f' = f_i$ 
  update L and T
until loop condition is satisfied
return  $x_{opt}$  and  $f_{opt}$ 

```

4. Example of application

For the purpose of optimization giving reasonable results constraints must be adopted. Unconstrained optimization yields usually results which are unacceptable from various reasons which must be taken into account during the design. These reasons in ship design can be for example a minimum cargo load required by an owner or safety issues. In the presented research the adopted constraints are ship displacement (Eq. 7) and the metacentric height of a ship, a measure of safety from stability point of view. The metacentric height GM is the distance from the gravity centre of a ship to its metacentre. The GM is used to calculate the stability of a ship and must be positive for existing of righting arm when the ships is heeling. The GM changes for different load condition but in the design process it is assumed that ship is fully loaded. The constraint on GM is: $GM > x$, where x is an adopted criteria, usually not less than 0,2m. The location of gravity centre must be known for the determination of GM . At the initial design process it can be estimated only using empirical formulas relating dimensions of the hull (mostly height of a ship H and draft T). One of such formulas given by *Schneekluth and Bertram (1998)* has been applied.

The developed optimization technique has been tested for a virtual ship for which the design task was assumed. The task was to determine the main dimensions and block coefficient of a ship hull giving the lowest effective power PE. The constraints were:

- Displacement of a ship should satisfy: $D \in (16100, 16500), [T]$,
- Speed of a ship should satisfy: $v \in (12.5, 13), [kts]$
- Metacentric height: $GM > 1.2, [m]$

The constraints were also specified for the determination of upper and lower bounds of design solution vector, $X = [L, B, T, C_B, v]$. It was assumed that the ship length will vary during the optimization process from 125 to 135 m and other vector components will be bounded to ratios: $L/B = 6 - 8$, $B/T = 2.4 - 3.6$. Block coefficient C_B will vary from 0.7 to 0.8. The process of optimization – values of objective function during iterations - is given in Fig.5. Penalty function was set to the algorithm that if a solution does not fulfill the criteria, the objective function receives very high value. The optimization process has been stopped after about 850 iterations. The minimum objective function value was 1486 kW, and the vector of design solution is: [127.3, 22.5, 7.1, 0.79, 12.5]. The selected value for the ship speed (12.5 knots) is at the lowest bound of the assumed vector. This is

because the relation between speed and propulsion power of a ship (or any other transport mean) is in third order power, so that it is the strongest relation in the objective function. When considering the design problem of minimization of ship effective power upper and lower bounds on the speed should be set very close.

The method was also applied for optimization of dimensions a tanker built in Szczecin Shipyard. The ship ship has displacement of 46542 m^3 and this value was selected as minimum criteria. Ship has following dimensions; $L = 176 \text{ m}$, $B = 32.2 \text{ m}$, $T = 10.5 \text{ m}$, $C_B = 0.8$. The hull of a ship model was tested in towing tank and for the speed of 15 knots effective power is 4818 kW. It was decided that the speed of ship equal to 15 knots should be kept at the same level due to the strong relation with effective power. Since the ship has breadth $B = 32.2 \text{ m}$, it is known that this a Panamax vessel and upper bound for this value should not exceed 32.2m. The results of optimization are given in Fig.6. Optimization process has been stopped after 300 iterations.

Fig.5: Optimization process for the virtual ship.

Fig.6: Optimization process for the tanker.

The solution vector of best value function is: $[177.8 \ 30.08 \ 12.08 \ 0.72 \ 15]$. Now the ship is longer but breadth and block coefficient were decreased and draft is bigger. The optimized ship has exactly the displacement of 46542 m^3 so that the optimized ship should be capable of carrying the same amount of cargo as before optimization and the resulting effective power is 4192 kW. This seems to be very promising because reduction was 626 kW with the same displacement and the speed. Nevertheless, as the objective function is the simplified form of empirical method more tests should be carried out for

the proper verification of presented approach.

5. Final Remarks

This simple example given above presents an attempt at optimization of main ship dimensions. The results of the method can be considered encouraging for further research. The reduction of effective power of the ship being the subject of investigation is significant and if achievable in the real design must give substantial reduction of fuel consumption.

Formulation of the target function as a neural network seems to be reasonable for the optimization algorithms of the direct search type. Design criteria can be applied and their use does not perturb the optimization process and the results are feasible. If there are any constraints being the subject of the service or navigational matters (such as dimensions limitations for channels or locks), they can be introduced to the algorithm. Subsequent research will be devoted to the development of methods taking into account more dimensions and hull shape coefficients and models will be compared systematically against built ships.

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Developing of a Computer System Aiding the Determination of Mean Long-Term Service Speed

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Abstract

Service speed obtainable by a ship in real weather conditions when sailing on a given shipping route, is one of the major parameters which have great impact on ship operation costs. The so far used, very approximate method of service speed prediction based on “service margin”, is very little exact. In this paper a new method based on additional ship resistance dependent on mean statistical parameters of wave and wind occurring on a given shipping route, is presented. The mean long-term service speed is calculated on the basis of the calculated additional resistance and the screw propeller and propulsion engine parameters. Also, a new definition of service margin and a way of its calculation is presented apart from the results of the mean service speed calculation depending on ship’s type and size and shipping route.

1. Introduction

The ship owner, when planning building a new ship, on the basis of his experience and knowledge of shipping market, determines the ship’s deadweight and predicts its service speed to be reached by the ship on a given shipping route. The service speed obtainable by a ship in real weather conditions (mainly wind and waves) is one of the most important parameters greatly influencing ship’s profitability on a given shipping route. In the design algorithms used today in ship design offices, ship’s deadweight is determined with a satisfactory exactness, but calculation of ship’s service speed is rather inexact and practically known already after ship’s delivery and some time of its service. Hence in the ship building contract, is given another speed, so called contract speed which the ship has to achieve in still-water conditions. On the basis of still-water resistance characteristics and rated output of propulsion engine, the obtainable ship service speed is predicted by accounting for relevant coefficients, Fig.1.

In that prediction an increase of ship resistance in service conditions in relation to that in still water conditions (represented by the service margin SM in Fig.1) is not exactly determined as it depends on real weather conditions occurring on a given shipping route.

Basing on known statistical data on winds and waves possible to occur on a given shipping route, one is capable in determining a long-term distribution function of additional resistance, and next, for an assumed main engine output, a long-term distribution function of ship’s speed possible to be obtained on a given shipping route. Such approach makes it possible not only to exactly determine the mean statistical service speed of the ship, but also to investigate the influence of power output of a selected main engine on the ship’s service parameters including its long-term service costs.

Attempts to determine the service speed of ship in real weather conditions have been already reported in, Buxton (1995), Zdybek (1985,1990), however there were not accounted for statistical distributions of wind and wave parameters met on a given shipping route.

Fig. 1: Predicted service speed of a ship. Notation : N_n – rated output of engine, PS – shaft power, PD – power at propeller’s cone, OM – operational margin, SM – sea margin, V_K – contract speed, V_E – predicted service speed, 1 – propeller curve for still-water conditions, for non-fouled hull, 2 – predicted propeller curve with service margin, for real conditions

2. Statistical long-term parameters of winds and waves on shipping routes

In order to determine the mean long-term ship service speed the ship’s resistance in real weather conditions should be determined in advance. The statistical long-term wave parameters, namely: H_S - the significant wave height, T_1 – the mean characteristic period, μ - the mean geographical direction, were determined on the basis of multi-year measurements. Results of the measurements are contained in the atlas of wave parameters, *Hogben et al. (1986)*, and in extended form in *Hogben and Lumb (1967)*, in which seas and oceans have been divided additionally into the set of sea areas shown in Fig.2 (where each sea area is characterized by its own statistical wave parameters).

The atlases, *Hogben et al. (1986)*, and *Hogben and Lumb (1967)*, contain sample size of waves characterized by H_S and T_1 parameters and recorded in a given area for a given season and wave direction μ , as exemplified in Table I. Based on these data, was elaborated a computer database on the waves met on seas and oceans, which contains the occurrence probabilities of waves with H_S , T_1 parameters, f_{HT} , and the occurrence probabilities of μ directions, f_μ , for all the sea areas (split into seasonal data).

The statistical wave parameters used for calculation of ship resistance due to wind and waves should be correlated with the wind parameters: V_A - mean wind speed, γ_A - mean statistical geographical direction of wind. As such atlases for wind do not exist the appropriate relations between wind and wave parameters were elaborated on the basis of measurements, *Szlangiewicz and Zelazny (2006)*, based on literature sources, one elaborated the relations $V_A = V_A(H_S, T_1)$ for the purposes of this work, assuming that :

- Wind direction coincides with wave direction:

$$\gamma_A = \mu, \tag{1}$$

- The occurrence probability of wind direction, f_{γ_A} , is the same as that of wave direction, f_μ :

$$f_{\gamma A} = f_{\mu}, \quad (2)$$

Fig. 2: Oceans divided into set of sea areas, acc., *Hogben et al. (1986)*

Table I: Sample size of waves of H_S height and T_1 period for a given μ direction and sea area, *Hogben et al. (1986)*

Sea area: 1											
Season of the year: December – February (winter)											
Wave direction: $\mu = 000$ deg											
$T_1[s]$ \ $H_S[m]$	calm	<5	6-7	8-9	10-11	12-13	14-15	16-17	18-19	20-21	>21
0,25		2									
0,5		1	1	1							
1,0		8	2	1	1						
1,5		2	4	5		2					
2,0			5		3						
2,5		1	5	4	3						
3,0			1	3	2	1					
3,5			1	4	5						
4,0				1	1	4	1	1			
4,5				4	2		1	1			
5,0					1						
6,0				1							
6,5				1	2						
7,5					1						

- The occurrence probability of mean wind speed, f_{VA} , is the same as that of wave of H_S , T_1 parameters, f_{HT} :

$$f_{VA} = f_{HT}. \quad (3)$$

Results of calculations of the relations $V_A = V_A(H_S, T_1)$ for the wave parameters contained in, atlases, were published in, *Szelangiewicz and Żelazny (2006)*.

3. Ship resistance in real weather conditions

In real weather conditions during sea voyage of a ship on a given shipping route, its total resistance consists of still-water resistance and additional components :

$$R_C = R + \Delta R, \quad (4)$$

R - still-water resistance of ship (accounting for the drift angle and possible surface sea current)
 ΔR - additional ship resistance resulting from real sailing conditions :

$$\Delta R = R_{xA} + R_{xW} + R_{xR}, \quad (5)$$

R_{xA} - additional wind-generated resistance

R_{xW} - additional wave-generated resistance

R_{xR} - additional resistance resulting from e.g. rudder action to keep a given ship course.

Method of calculating the additional resistance is presented in, *Szelangiewicz and Żelazny (2006)*.

4. Intentional reduction of ship speed in view of hazardous wave-generated phenomena

During ship sailing in rough water ship's oscillating motions and their derivatives i.e. velocities and accelerations are the direct effect of waves. The secondary phenomena which accompany the oscillating motions are : shipping of water on deck, propeller emerging, pounding of wave to ship bottom and sides (slamming), worsening of ship stability and manoeuvrability, additional dynamic loads on hull structure. The oscillating motions and accompanying phenomena depend on parameters of ship hull and waves as well as the ship speed V and course relative to waves (the angle β_w). The phenomena, especially if very intensive, may lead directly to averages and disasters at sea. It is possible to mitigate the phenomena, e.g. ship rolling - by changing ship's course relative to waves (the angle β_w), reducing ship's speed V, or simultaneous changing ship's course and speed. In predicting the mean service speed was made the assumption that ship's speed reduction will be performed if :

$$\bar{U}_Z > \bar{U}_{Zdop} \quad (6)$$

\bar{U}_Z - mean statistical value of the wave-generated phenomenon Z considered hazardous to ship

\bar{U}_{Zdop} - permissible value of the wave-generated phenomenon Z, at which the sailing ship is still safe.

In the performed calculations the ship course relative to waves was kept unchanged (though its changing is always possible), since in predicting the mean long-term ship service speed it was assumed that the ship heads the course resulting from the selected shipping route.

Fig. 3: Points at which ship sea-keeping parameters were calculated: 1 – for slamming, 2 – for water shipping onto deck, and bow accelerations, 3 – for propeller emerging, 4 – for accelerations at wheelhouse.

In assessing ship performance in waves and making decision on possible reduction of its speed, the following phenomena were taken into consideration: rolling, pitching, vertical accelerations, horizontal transverse accelerations, shipping of water on deck, slamming, propeller emerging. The

calculation methods of the phenomena and the assumed acceptance criteria are presented by *Dudziak (1988)*, *Karppinen (1987)*, *Szelangiewicz (2000)*.

The points at which values of the parameters of ship seakeeping qualities were calculated, are presented in Fig. 3.

5. Prediction method for mean statistical service speed for given shipping route

5.1. Instantaneous service speed of ship

During ship motion in rough water, apart from still-water resistance also additional forces due to wind, waves and possible surface sea current act on the ship. These actions generate, apart from an additional resistance, a transverse force and a moment tending to rotate the ship around its vertical axis.

The transverse force results in ship drifting, and the moment – in ship course changing. Ship's passive rudder is to be laid appropriately to keep ship course constant under action of the external rotating moment. Under the assumption that the ship course has to be maintained, from the solution of the following non-linear equations :

$$\begin{aligned} R_{yA}(V) + R_{yW}(V) + R_y(V, \beta) + R_{yR}(V, \beta, \delta_R) &= 0, \\ M_{zA}(V) + M_{zW}(V) + M_z(V, \beta) + M_{zR}(V, \beta, \delta_R) &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

together with the relevant equations describing additional resistance forces, (presented below), for given values of the ship speed V , course angle ψ , wind parameters (V_A, γ_A), wave parameters (H_s, T_1, μ) and possible sea current parameters (V_C, γ_C), the following quantities can be obtained :

- β - ship drift angle
- δ_R - ship passive rudder angle
- ΔR - additional ship resistance due to wind, waves, current and passive rudder
- R_C - total ship resistance to motion.

Schematic diagram of the complete calculation algorithm of β , δ_R and R_C for given values of the ship motion parameters (V, ψ), wind parameters (V_A, γ_A), wave parameters and current parameters (V_C, γ_C), was presented in, *Szelangiewicz and Żelazny (2007)*.

The instantaneous ship service speed on a given wave with parameters H_s, T_1 and μ is obtained by the ship when the total ship resistance is balanced by the propeller thrust, taking into account its potential drop caused by the emergence. and the moment on the propeller will be equal to the propulsion engine moment. These conditions are written as a set of two nonlinear equations:

$$\begin{aligned} T \cdot \beta_T - \frac{R_C}{1-t} &= 0, \\ Q - \frac{N \cdot \eta_S \cdot \eta_R \cdot \eta_G}{2\pi n} &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

- T – the separated propeller thrust
- β_T – the ship thrust drop coefficient as a result of the propeller emergence during ship navigation on waves (the method of the coefficient calculation is presented in, *Szelangiewicz and Żelazny (2007)*).
- R_C – the total ship resistance is dependent on the ship speed V , ship course Ψ , waves parameters H_s, T_1, μ and wind parameters V_A, γ_A

- t – thrust deduction factor
- Q – torque on the separated propeller
- N – power of the propulsion engine (resulting from the motor/engine operation area)
- η_s – shaftline efficiency
- η_G – efficiency of gear (if it is applied on board. when it is missing then $\eta_G = 1$)
- η_R – rotational “efficiency”
- n – nominal r.p.m. of the propulsion motor.

Method of calculating the total ship resistance on waves R_C thrust T and the moment (torque) on the propeller Q as well as the driving engine capacity N from the motor/engine N operation area are presented in, *Szelangiewicz and Żelazny (2007)*.

The solution of the non-linear Eqs.(8) for each set of data concerning:

- ship movement. V, ψ ,
- waves: H_S, T_1, μ ,
- wind: V_A, γ_A ,

gives the instantaneous ship speed V_i .

5.2. Mean statistical service speed of ship sailing on a given shipping route

During the long-term sailing of ship on an assumed shipping route the additional resistance due to wave action will depend not only on a wave height (and period) but also on geographical directions: of wave, μ , and ship course, ψ . Also the additional resistance due to wind will depend, apart from the wind speed V_A , on the directions γ_A and ψ . It means that the additional resistance and also ship speed will depend on the values of the parameters of waves (H_S, T_1, μ), wind (V_A, γ_A) and ship motion (V, ψ), which may occur on a given shipping route within a long period of time.

In the case in question the surface sea current is considered to be a determinate phenomenon of the mean speed V_C and direction angle γ_C . If a ship is assumed to enter a region of large-scale surface currents then the current action will be included into ship still-water resistance.

Therefore the occurrence probability of the additional resistance ΔR of a given value, as well as the speed V which can be reached at occurrence of that additional resistance, depends on :

(V, ψ).

- shipping route and probability of staying the ship in particular sea areas
- the statistical parameters of waves, (H_S, T_1, μ), and wind, (V_A, γ_A), and probability of occurrence of the parameters in given sea areas
- probability of occurrence of the ship motion parameters (V, ψ)

The probability of being the ship in a given situation when sailing in waves on a given route, is as follows:

$$p_w = f_A \cdot f_S \cdot f_\mu \cdot f_{HT} \cdot f_V \cdot f_\psi, \quad (9)$$

f_A - probability of staying the ship in the sea area A

f_S - probability of staying the ship in the sea area A during the season S

f_μ - probability of occurrence of the wave direction μ in the sea area A during the season S

f_{HT} - probability of occurrence of the wave of the parameters (H_S, T_1), propagating from the direction μ

f_V, f_ψ - probability of the event that the ship moves with the speed V and heads the course ψ , respectively.

In a similar way can be expressed the probability p_A of being the ship in a given situation associated with wind state. In the calculations of additional resistance due to wind and waves it was assumed that wind speed and wave height are mutually correlated, hence $p_w = p_A$. As the event of being the ship in a given situation described by (9) will result in generating an additional resistance and achieving a determined speed, hence:

$$p_w = p_R = p_V \quad (10)$$

p_R - partial occurrence probability (in given conditions) of additional resistance

p_V - partial occurrence probability (in given conditions) of instantaneous ship service speed.

Values of the additional resistance due to wind, and that due to waves, depend on random parameters of wind and waves. Therefore the same values of resistance due to wind and waves can occur for different values of the parameters V_A , γ_A , H_S , T_1 , μ , V , ψ . For each of the values of this way calculated additional resistance, a value of ship speed is calculated (the criteria concerning sea-keeping qualities are simultaneously examined to execute possible speed reduction in order not to violate them at given wave and wind conditions).

The total probability P_{TV} of achieving the ship speed V at a given value of the additional resistance ΔR , is as follows:

$$P_{TV} = \sum_{A=1}^{n_A} \sum_{S=1}^{n_S} \sum_{\mu=1}^{n_\mu} \sum_{H,T=1}^{n_{HT}} \sum_{V=1}^{n_V} \sum_{\psi=1}^{n_\Psi} p_{V_i} [V_i(\Delta R_i)] \quad (11)$$

$V_i(\Delta R_i)$ - instantaneous ship service speed in function of instantaneous additional ship resistance

n_A , n_S , n_μ , n_{HT} , n_V , n_Ψ - numbers of sea areas (crossed by a given ship), seasons, wave directions, wave parameters, ship speeds and courses, respectively.

By calculating the distribution function of occurrence probability, $f(V_i)$, of the instantaneous ship speed V_i the mean long-term ship service speed for a given shipping route, can be determined as follows:

$$\overline{V_E} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n_V} P_{TV_i} \cdot V_i(\Delta R_i = const)}{\sum_{i=1}^{n_V} P_{TV_i}} \quad (12)$$

n_V - number of intervals containing similar values of the instantaneous ship service speeds.

6. Parameters of the ship for which calculations were performed

Calculations of the mean additional resistance and mean long-term service speed were performed for container ship of determined propulsion systems and 15% service margin, Table II. All calculations for ship were performed for constant ship's draught and constant state of hull and propeller surface, that made it possible to more accurately compare the ship sailing on a given shipping route, by taking into account ship's type and size. The used computer software has been so designed as to make it possible to perform calculations at variable draught (considered as a random variable of a given occurrence probability) and for changeable state of hull and propeller surface.

7. Shipping routes

For the calculations of the mean additional resistance and mean long-term service speed the most representative shipping routes were selected based on *NN (1989)*. They are specified in Table III. All additional data which describe ship's voyage on a given shipping route (i.e. specification of sea areas crossed by the route, probability of ship's staying in a given sea area, f_A , ship's course angle ψ and

probabilities of ship's courses in a given sea area, f_{ψ}) can be found in, *Szelangiewicz and Żelazny (2007)*.

Table II: Parameters of container ship

Length between perpendiculars	L [m]	140.14
Breadth	B [m]	22.30
Draught	T [m]	8.25
Displacement for T	∇ [m ³]	17300
Contractual speed	V_K [m/s]	8.44
Propeller diameter	D_P [m]	5.2
Propeller pitch	P [m]	3.9
Nominal power of the propulsion motor	N_n [kW]	6930
Nominal r.p.m. of the propulsion motor	n_n [1/s]	2.33
Ship resistance on calm water for T and V_K	R [kN]	461.3
The sea margin assumed in the ship propulsion	K_z [%]	15

Table III: Specification of shipping routes used to calculate added resistance and service speed of ship

Nr	Name
1	Sout America – West Europe
2	US East coast – West Europe
3	US East coast Gulf Mexico – West Europe
4	US East coast – Mediterranean – West Europe
5	Indonesia - Japan
6	Persian Gulf - Japan
7	North Africa – West Europe
8	North Africa – US East coast
9	Persian Gulf – Africa – West Europe
10	West Europe – Mediterranean – Persian Gulf - Japan
11	West Europe – Panama Canal – US West coast
12	West Europe – South and Central America

8. Calculation results

The calculation results for ship and shipping route are presented in the form of bar charts for the additional resistance ΔR and service speed V_E . The speed the ship is able to achieve, was calculated under the assumption that its set value has to be maintained or its maximum value achievable in a given weather conditions at simultaneous keeping the set ship course, has to be determined. The obtained bar charts were also approximated by using the distribution functions : that of the additional resistance $f(\Delta R)$, and that of service speed $f(V_E)$, with the determined R_2 (share of the “resolved” variance).

Under the bar charts for a given ship and shipping route the following data are tabularized:

- the maximum value of additional resistance, ΔR_{\max} , which occurred for a given ship on a given shipping route
- the mean value of additional resistance, ΔR , calculated from the formula :

$$\overline{\Delta R} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n_R} P_{TR_i} \cdot (\Delta R_i = const)}{\sum_{i=1}^{n_R} P_{TR_i}} \quad (13)$$

- the relative resistance increase, PR, calculated from the formula:

$$PR = \frac{\overline{\Delta R}}{R} \cdot 100\% \quad (14)$$

- the set value of ship service speed, V_{ZE} the minimum value of ship speed, V_{min} , which occurred on a given shipping route at keeping a set course
- the mean long-term value of ship speed, V_E , on a given shipping route, calculated from the formula:

$$\overline{V_E} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n_v} P_{TV_i} \cdot V_i (\Delta R_i = const)}{\sum_{i=1}^{n_v} P_{TV_i}} \quad (15)$$

- the probability, P_{VE} , of maintaining the service speed, V_{ZE} , on a given shipping route at keeping a set course
- percentage of the events in which ship speed has been reduced for the reason of exceeded ship's sea-keeping criteria
- percentage of the events in which no result of calculations, i.e. no value of ship speed, has been found. The lack of solution resulted from the fact that it was assumed to keep a set course, that was not possible in very high and oblique waves - the ship course should be changed in such situations.

The calculated bar charts for the ship (Table II) and all the shipping routes (Table III) together with the remaining results can be found in, *Szelangiewicz and Żelazny (2007)*. Fig. 4 shows example bar charts for the ship in Table II, sailing back and forth on the chosen route (South America – West Europe).

9. Analysis of the achieved results

The presented calculation results clearly show which value of the mean long-term service speed can be achieved by the ship or which value of probability of maintaining a given service speed on a given shipping route can be achieved at a service margin value assumed in design process of ship propulsion system (e.g. 15 %). Both the quantities for container ship on different shipping routes are shown in Fig.5.

In Fig.6 are shown the values of additional resistance index for the same ship, defined by means of the Eq. (14) depending on a shipping route. The index should not be identified, as for its value, with the service margin because it constitutes a definite long-term statistical quantity tightly connected with parameters of weather conditions occurring on a given shipping route, hence value of the index is changeable whereas value of the service margin assumed in design process is of a constant value. However, value of the index may suggest how large service margin for a given shipping route should be to maintain the set service speed at a given probability of its exceeding; it can be clearly observed when comparing the diagrams in Fig. 5 and Fig.6. It means that in the case of applying the traditional method of determining the propulsion engine output power, with the use of service margin, percentage value of service margin for a given ship should be tightly correlated with statistical parameters of weather conditions on a given shipping route, and with an assumed probability of maintaining an assumed long-term service speed of ship.

Container ship
Shipping route no. 1a

Histogram and distribution function of additional resistance

Histogram and distribution function of service speed

Still-water resistance at the speed V_K [kN]	R	461,26
Max. additional resistance [kN]	ΔR_{\max}	367,70
Mean additional resistance [kN]	$\Delta \bar{R}$	35,77
Resistance increase [%]		7,8
Percentage of no-solution events [%]		0,11

Set service speed [m/s]	V_{ZE}	8,44
Minimum speed [m/s]	V_{\min}	1,88
Mean speed [m/s]	\bar{V}_E	8,38
Prawdopodobieństwo V_{ZE}	P_{V_E}	0,90
Percentage of speed-reduction events [%]		0,11

Shipping route no. 1b

Still-water resistance at the speed V_K [kN]	R	461,26
Max. additional resistance [kN]	ΔR_{\max}	365,74
Mean additional resistance [kN]	$\Delta \bar{R}$	28,02
Resistance increase [%]		6,1
Percentage of no-solution events [%]		0,22

Set service speed [m/s]	V_{ZE}	8,44
Minimum speed [m/s]	V_{\min}	1,88
Mean speed [m/s]	\bar{V}_E	8,37
Probability V_{ZE}	P_{V_E}	0,92
Percentage of speed-reduction events [%]		0,07

Fig. 4: Bar charts and distribution functions of additional resistance and service speed for container ship

Fig. 5: Ship Container ship a) probability of maintaining the set service speed V_{ZE} b) mean long-term service speed

Fig. 6: Index of additional resistance increase for container ship depending on shipping route

Fig. 5 and 6 show the influence of shipping routes on the parameters associated with speed of container ship. The same relations for the remaining ships can be found in *Szlangiewicz and Żelazny*

(2007). In the next figures an influence of type and size of ship on the parameters associated with its speed on a given shipping route, is presented. As the considered ships differed to each other with regard to the contract speed V_K the following index of maintaining the set speed was introduced. The index makes it possible to more accurately compare performance of particular ships on a given shipping route.

10. A proposal of definition of service margin

On the basis of the performed calculations and conclusions resulting from the diagrams in Fig.5 and 6 was elaborated a proposal of definition of the service margin which associates a set service speed with probability of its maintaining on a given shipping route during a long time period.

Proposed definition of the service margin (which determines surplus of engine output power): For a given ship sailing on a given shipping route, the service margin k_z should have such percentage value as the ship in assumed loading conditions and assumed state of its hull and propeller surface, would be able to maintain the service speed, V_{ZE} , assumed in the frame of long-term prediction, at the assumed exceeding probability P_{VE} .

The definition concerns a designed ship intended for sailing on a given shipping route, however it can be also generalized to cover an arbitrary sailing region.

It should be observed that :

- too large value of V_{ZE} relative to V_K (contract speed) or too large value of the probability P_{VE} may cause that k_z would take large values and such ship would appear operationally unprofitable for its owner
- a reasonable (smaller) value of V_{ZE} may cause that at a reasonable value of k_z , the probability P_{VE} would reach the value of one ($P_{VE} = 1$).

The above given comments mean that ship owner, when ordering a ship, should be aware of :

- a value of the long-term service speed he expects to be reached and
- at which level of its maintaining probability the designed ship would appear operationally profitable for him.

Fig. 7. The service margin k_z calculated for container ship in function of shipping route, or $V_{ZE} = V_K$ and $P_{VE} = 0.95$; blue - service margin for one-leg voyage of the ship; red - mean service margin for a shipping route

For the so defined service margin were performed calculations aimed at determination of its percentage value depending on shipping route under assumption that the set service speed V_{ZE} , maintained during long time period, will be equal to V_K ($V_{ZE} = V_K$) with the probability $PVE = 0.95$.

The results of service margin calculations for container ship in function of shipping route are presented in Fig.7.

11. Conclusions

From the performed calculations the following conclusions can be drawn :

- Additional resistance of ship and its mean service speed depend on statistical weather parameters of shipping routes, hence ship service parameters depend on a kind of shipping route hence full utilization of statistical long-term parameters of waves and winds makes more accurate predicting ship service speed on a given route, possible.
- Influence of ship's type and size on its service parameters (resistance, speed) is observable but not so great as that of shipping route, but definite differences in effectiveness of the same ship on a given shipping route can be observed, that speaks for different quality (perfection) of designed propulsion systems.
- Service margin's value can be determined on the basis of ship service speed assumed by ship owner and probability of its maintaining on a given shipping route, hence it is not to have a constant value for a given shipping route, but it may result from targets and strategy which ship owner would apply to a given ship.

On the basis of the presented method was elaborated a computer software which may be also used for the following purposes :

- Comparison and assessment of ship designs as well as existing ships from the point of view of their service costs
- Optimization of a shipping route for a ship, especially in rough weather conditions
- Investigation of many other service parameters of ship and its equipment, e.g. frequency of using ship's steering gear on a given shipping route.

Calculation results obtained in the frame of long-term prediction of ship service parameters will be presented in separate papers.

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Data Mining to Enhance the Throughput of Container Ports

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Abstract

In this paper, we describe our hybrid data mining system, which provides insights for improving the throughput of container-based port. Operation of the system has three phases. First, instances are classified into two classes, acceptable and unacceptable, based on waiting time, then using decision tree method. The second phase tries to improve the classification and achieve a more accurate class boundary via an aggregate norm obtained from consultations with experts and statistical concepts. In the final phase association rule mining is used to find relationships that may exist among unacceptable instances thus identifying the most problematic instances. Our proposed system has been tested with a database containing the transactions of a real container port.

1. Introduction

There are different applications of data mining methods in maritime industries and port scopes. Two first steps of the proposed system in this paper are a kind of coarse to fine classification which is an approach that first classifies the instances into large classes then in the second step does a bit more exact classification to determine class boundaries more precisely, *Osareh (2004)*. Another example of Coarse to Fine Classification has been introduced in *Geman (2003)*. In this application, Coarse to Fine classification has been used for image segmentation as the segmentation phase has been divided into two parts. The class labels in the first phase are crude and not so precise, but in the second phase in addition to revise the kind of representation of image, labels has been more sound and precise than the first phase. In fact, at the first phase that is called Non-Contextual, the components which are easy to detect and segment, are separated and in the next phase that is called Contextual, elements which are not classified properly and segmentation of them is more complicated, are going to be separated.

Data mining algorithms have had different applications in maritime transportation. *Bilegan et al (2007)* proposed a methodology based on neural networks to forecast freight demand at multimodal container terminals. *Nathan (2008)* presented a methodology to investigate the source of dray trucks delay, to reduce the turnaround time and finally to discover the effective factors in port throughput, using decision trees.

Improving the throughput in multimodal freight transportation as another scope of data mining has been introduced in *Yahalom (2001)*. *Yahalom (2001)* tried to plan and implement a technique to analyze data and managing information. To achieve the goal of enabling ports to service her customers in a reasonable amount of cost and time, they have used data mining to study and discover the patterns which exist in port operations.

Ng et al. (1998) integrated various techniques of data-mining (such as decision tree induction, deviation analysis and multiple concept-level association rules) to form an approach to gauge customer loyalty.

Faster turn-around time of vessels and high berth productivity are important factors of container terminals for competitiveness. *Lokuge (2004)* proposed a hybrid BDI agent model with Neural Networks and Adaptive Neurofuzzy Inference system (ANFIS) in dealing with complex environments such as operations in container terminal in the shipping industry. This hybrid model is emphasized to improve the learning capabilities of the generic BDI agents.

2. Data set description

The data set which was used in this paper, contains more than 8000 transactions of a container port in south of Iran during 10 years. Instances in data set have 17 features.

3. Proposed System

The operation of the proposed system has three phases. First, instances are classified into two classes, acceptable and unacceptable, based on waiting time and using decision tree method. The second phase tries to improve the classification and achieve a more accurate class boundary via an aggregate norm obtained from consultations with experts and statistical concepts. In the final phase association rule mining is used to find relationships that may exist among unacceptable instances thus identifying the most problematic instances.

But before starting the first phase, some preprocessing activities is inevitable. Since most of the systems which we gather our datasets from, are not specially designed for data mining purposes, their datasets need to be preprocessed and ready for any kind of mining processes, in advance. So, we had to revised our real data, before entering the mining process. The most important preprocessing activities which has been applied on the data set are as follows:

- Filling missing values:
In some cases to reach the most accurate analyses during the mining process, some fields has been initiated manually, for example in some records, length and width fields of a ship have no value but according to other transactions of that ship which had a complete data, these two fields have been filled.
- Removing noisy data:
Some fields such as source and destination of a vessel, are wrong and meaningless, so we have removed these instances from data set.
- Decomposing mixed features:
To achieve more precise results, fields such as arrival vessel date, has been splitted into three separate field each on containing year, month and day respectively. This may result in more detailed data for mining process.
- Categorization:
In arrival vessel time field, we have mapped the arrival time to 3 different indicating three different working shift.
- Adding new features:
Like any other simillar data mining projects, the dataset which has been used for this application, does not have some required information to reach the greater accuracy, for example knowing the number of vessels that has arrived to the port before the current one and has not been departed yet, would be usefull.
- Removing additional fields:
There are high dependancy between some features for instance, attendance time, has been removed from the dataset, because it is the sum of waiting time and service time, so it has very high dependancy with both of them.

3.1. First Phase

After the original data set has been preprocessed, the data is ready to use. As the first step in this phase we have to set out the appropriate labels for the instances. According to maneuvering and waiting time, the class of every instance has been determined. To do so, while considering

maneuvering time and according to waiting time, the class of every instance has been determined. In fact, transactions with waiting time greater than zero, belong to unacceptable class while the others belong to acceptable class. it is worthy to note that manovering time for each vessel has been extracted according to domain experts consultation as mentioned in Table I.

Table I: Maneuvering time

Group of vessel	Maneuvering time
25,000 < GRT	5 hours
10,000 < GRT ≤ 25,000	3 hours
GRT ≤ 10,000	2 hours

New waiting time is obtained through eliminating maneuvering time from waiting time. Using this new value for waiting time, each vessel which has a waiting time greather than zero, is assigned to unacceptable class and the others are assigned to acceptable class.

After class determination, the dataset is ready for feature selection. Feature selection is one important means to attack problems with various aspects of data, and to enable existing tools to apply, otherwise not possible. Feature selection result in a reduced subset of features and we need it because of various purposes such as to improve performance (speed of learning, predictive accuracy, or simplicity of rules) or to reduce dimentionality and removing noise. Feature selection is defined as follows:

Feature Selection is a process that chooses an optimal subset of features according to a certain criteria *Liu and Motoda (1998)*. There are various methods of feature selection, that may be chosen according to different criteria. In this application we have used both ranking and selection methods. The result of the former is a ranked list of the features of dataset and the latter would result in an optimal subset of the original set. To gain a better and much more detailed result, first we have used two ranking method with two evaluation measures (Gain Ratio and Information Gain).

Table II: Result of ranking methods.

	Features	InfoGainAttribute Eval	Accuracy C4.5	GainRatioAttribute Eval	Accuracy C4.5
1	F1	6	64.9801	11	64.6350
2	F2	3	64.8356	9	64.7579
3	F3	7	65.5945	4	66.4414
4	F4	1	62.4601	1	63.1731
5	F5	2	64.2935	3	65.7901
6	F6	9	65.3054	10	64.6473
7	F7	15	64.9422	15	64.9422
8	F8	16	64.9545	16	64.9545
9	F9	12	65.1880	8	56.3109
10	F10	11	64.9914	12	65.1880
11	F11	13	65.1757	13	65.1757
12	F12	10	64.7948	6	64.9087
13	F13	14	65.0406	14	65.0406
14	F14	5	65.1634	5	65.0524
15	F15	8	65.1247	7	65.3355
16	F16	4	64.2787	2	64.7271

After that, we have presented the features according to their priority that has been obtained from the ranked list, to the decision tree and have registered the accuracy of the tree. When we have obtained the highest accuracy, the number of features which has been included, are the members of optimal subset. These result is illustrated in Table II.

As illustrated in Table I by gray color, the best result has been gained with the Gain Ratio evaluation measure. Its subset have 4 features, F4, F26, F5 and F3, and the accuracy with this subset equals 66.4414 %. To complete our research in this step, we have used some subset selection methods and represented the results in Table III.

Table III: Result of Ranking Methods.

Evaluation Function	Search Strategy	Number of members in subset	Accuracy of decision tree(C4.5)
Correlation	Best First	3	65.1880
	Greedy	3	65.1880
	Exhaustive	3	65.1880
Consistency	Best First	12	65.1880
	Greedy	12	65.1880
Classifier(C4.5)	Best First	14	64.2787
	Greedy	12	64.2173

As shown in Table II, the best accuracy is 65.1880%. This is less than the best result of ranking method (66.4414%), so the best subset with the highest accuracy is set of 4 features include F4, F26, F5 and F3.

3.2. Second Phase

By the end of the first phase, we have labled instances according to their waiting time, so classified them into two classes, acceptable and unacceptable. After that, using different feature selection methods and compare the result of them with eachother, we have choosed the best features that are relevant and influential in waiting time.

Now we omit the instances that are assigned to acceptable class from dataset to more concentrate on instances of unacceptable waiting time class. Now we are going to study the result subset more precisely.

In fact, may be there exist a number of instances that are dedicated to unacceptable class in the previous phase but they are not a problematic instance, at all. In fact we are going to investigate weather all of the vessels which are dedicated to the unacceptable class,are really problematic from waiting time point of view.It means we are interested in fing out if there are any other factors that are influential in waiting time.Therefore, in this step of the proposed system, we are going to set up an aggregate norm for waiting time in the port. In this way, after setting up the aggregate norm for waiting time by means of consulting ports experts, we specify the real class of every instances according to this norm using some statistical methods.

As mentioned above, we are going to establish an aggregate norm. an example of using aggregate norm has been described in *USSR (1990)* simply. In this application, with the aim of creating economic conditions for the efficient replacement of fixed assets and in order to reduce expenditures on carrying out major repairs of physically machinery, the authors have determined an aggregate norm in accordance with different factors.

Preferences of adhere to aggregate norm instead of simple norm, has described in different references. *Burdenski (2000)* reviews graphical and statistical procedures for evaluating multivariate normality.

The author emphasize that reality is complex. Over time, researchers have become increasingly aware that simple univariate methods are inadequate to meet the needs of the complex world. In most of the real problems, two or more dependent variables are necessary, because nearly every effect has multiple causes and nearly every cause has multiple effects.

Daniel (1990) noted that multivariate methods usually best honor the reality about which the researcher wishes to generalize. *McMillan and Schumacher (1984)* compellingly argued against the limitations of viewing the world through an overly simplified univariate lens. *Thompson (1986)* stated that the reality about which most researchers strive to generalize is usually one “in which the researcher cares about multiple outcomes, in which most outcomes have multiple causes, and in which most causes have multiple effects”. Given this conception of reality, only multivariate methods honor the full constellation of inter-relating variables simultaneously. *Grimm and Yarnold (1995)*, *Fish (1988)* and *Maxwell (1992)* used multivariate methods rather than univariate methods.

In addition to the above information about the advantages of using multivariate methods, as has been mentioned in *Tower (2002)* it is necessary to say that, a problem with some of the multivariate techniques is that it is usually quite easy to include many variables in an analysis, but taking into account the nonlinear correlation between more than two or three variables is prohibitively complicated.

Obviously, using many variables in an analysis makes it quite difficult to determine if the model is accurately describing the data in the multidimensional parameter space. In addition to this problem, however, adding too many variables to the multivariate analysis will actually degrade, rather than enhance the results *Tower (2002)*.

According to the above introduction and port experts consultation, we have considered three indicators below, to define the aggregate norm. the indicators are:

- Amount of Discharged TEU
- waiting time to service time ratio
- Gross Register Tonnage

Hence there are three factors with different scales, to be able to calculate the aggregate norm, we have to map them into a unique scale. First of all, as illustrated in first column of table 1, three groups of vessels have been considered and the aggregate norm for each group has been computed, individually.

The approach that has been considered to map the TEU to a unique scale is illustrated in Table IV. The average of discharged TEU has been calculated for each group of vessels.

Table IV: Discharged TEU average

Discharged TEU	Group of vessel	
DT1	$25000 \leq GRT$	1
DT2	$10000 \leq GRT < 25000$	2
DT3	$GRT < 10000$	3

In this step, a heuristic function was used for mapping each of three factors to a unique scale, Fig. 1. In this approach we have a kind of mapping procedure: every instance whose discharged TEU is greater than or equal to the average, the instances which their discharged TEU is less than average but not less than 10% of it, and the rest of instances are mapped to 1, 2 and 3 respectively.

Similar approaches are used for two other factors, waiting time to service time ratio and Gross Register Tonnage (GRT). After the procedure of mapping, each instance has 3 additional features corresponding to, three mapped values. To obtain the value of aggregate norm for each instance, we have calculated the average of three mapped values. We have plotted the distribution of the aggregate

norm values, then utilizing curve fitting method, its mean has been acquired. The result of curve fitting on distribution of aggregate norm values, is depicted in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1: Heuristic function for mapping

Fig. 2: Curve fitting on values of aggregate norm

A confidence interval of 95% is taken into account to calculate the mean of the mentioned distribution. After that, using the aggregate norm, we revise the labels of instances and reassign them into one of the two predefined classes. In this procedure all of the instances which have an aggregate norm value less than or equal to average, are assigned to acceptable and the rest of them, to the unacceptable class.

3.3. Third Phase

Until now, we have distinguished the instances of two classes precisely, at this time we aim to discover the refusal effect of one vessel in unacceptable class on the others using association rule mining. Hence, we have to convert the second phase output of the proposed system, to the format that is admissible by Apriori algorithm.

In our problem, we are interested in discovering such relationships that may exist between refusal of one vessel, and the other vessels of this class. So in the appropriate dataset for Apriori, we have modelled the problem, reversely. It means that in the dataset, if a ship doesn't select the port, we have labelled it by '1' and if the vessel selected the port, we have mentioned it by '0'. Using days for the

time intervals was not appropriate and didn't result in a proper rules, so we have changed the time intervals to year instead of days, therefore achieving the dataset with only 10 rows.

Table V: The structure of dataset to explore the relationship that may exist between vessels.

9149873	9148518	93991	93990	93976	93965	Ship Code date
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	Date-1
1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	Date-2
0									...
1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	Date-n

One result of the third phase is shown in Fig. 3. The set of rules in this figure describes vessels number 96070 and 96060, have bidirectional effect on each other. It indicates that refusal of each one, would cause the same behavior for the other one. So in this case, both of these vessels would be paid more attention by the port.

1. 96070=TRUE 10 ==> 96060=TRUE 10 conf:(1)
2. 96060=TRUE 10 ==> 96070=TRUE 10 conf:(1)
3. 96090=TRUE 10 ==> 96060=TRUE 10 conf:(1)
4. 96060=TRUE 10 ==> 96090=TRUE 10 conf:(1)

Fig. 3: Sample output of Apriori algorithm

4. Conclusions

We proposed a novel system to enhance the throughput of container ports utilizing variety of data mining methods. In the first step, after labeling the instances, we have used a number of feature selection methods to discover the most important and influential features on waiting time. At this step by representing the dataset to the decision tree method, the accuracy of 66.4414% has been reached, whereas after relabeling the instances at the end of second phase, accuracy was 99.71%, so the this factor has been improved, significantly. The standard error rates *Nakhaeizade (2009)* are 40.6548, 41.4, at the first and second steps, respectively.

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The Role of IT in Revitalizing Brazil's Shipbuilding Industry - A Case Study

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Abstract

This paper examines Estaliero Atlântico Sul (EAS), a shipyard which illustrates how rapidly-learned CAD/CAM/CAE 3D modeling software is playing an integral role in Brazil's shipbuilding revival.

1. Introduction

According to Lloyd's Register, in 1980 Brazil was the world's 2nd largest shipbuilding nation behind Japan. However, the industry collapsed in the following decades due to local economic factors such as hyperinflation, high interest rates and the ending of state subsidies. By 1999, no ships over 100 tons were being built and the industry had shrunk to only 2000 workers nationwide, *Paschoa (2010)*.

However, an amazing revival has occurred in the last decade in response to large deepwater offshore oil and gas discoveries. For political reasons, the Brazilian Government through its state-sponsored oil company Petrobras and its shipping subsidiary Transpetro have used these oil discoveries as a vehicle for job creation. Wherever possible the Brazilian government has required as many of the requisite vessels and oil rigs to be built within the country. This has resulted in a shipbuilding boom. Today, the industry has a national workforce of over 45,000 with approximately 80 booked orders for a variety of ships and rigs, *França (2009)* and *Paschoa (2010)*.

One of the most interesting stories involved in this revitalization is the meteoric rise of Estaliero Atlântico Sul (EAS), a new Brazilian shipyard which has received a substantial share of the new orders. This shipyard, with an order book of over \$3.4 billion USD, has been purpose-built to address the lack of modern shipbuilding capability within Brazil.

In order to capitalize on current opportunities, EAS has pursued an aggressive strategy of building the ships while the shipyard was still being built, *França (2009)*. This is all the more surprising since the shipyard is now the largest in Latin America with a total area of 1.65 million sq. m. *Paschoa (2010)*.

However, quickly constructing a shipyard of such size has not been the largest difficulty the company has faced. At a recent conference, Ângelo Bellelis, President of EAS, noted that his company has had challenges finding qualified labour. At full capacity, the shipyard will employ over 5000 workers, the majority of whom are locally trained and who lack any shipbuilding experience. The challenge of finding engineering staff has been even more acute. EAS has had to scour the country to find their team of 194 engineers, designers and draftsmen, *Bellelis (2009)*.

Based on this factor, EAS determined that its choice of CAD/CAM/CAE software would be critical to the success of its shipbuilding program. In order to ensure that the production design could be completed on schedule by a largely inexperienced workforce it was determined that a stringent process was required to choose an appropriate 3D product modeling toolset. The ShipConstructor software suite was selected as the center of a best-of-breed solution, largely due to the ease with which new users can become proficient in its use. As a result of the diligence applied in the selection process, EAS is already ahead of schedule on orders from Petrobras with good prospects for winning several more contracts.

2. Brazil's Shipbuilding Industry

The recent growth of the Brazilian marine industry is astounding. The revival started in approximately 2000 with offshore platform construction for Petrobras and then continued at an accelerated pace in

the second half of the decade in the wake of more oil discoveries in the Campos, Santos and Espirito Santo Basins.

Estimates vary widely regarding the ultimate size of Brazil’s petroleum resources but the proven reserves of oil are 12.8 billion barrels and the proven gas reserves are 365 billion cu. m. There are 29 sedimentary basins with oil and gas potential, comprising 7.5 million sq. km, with 2.4 million sq. km being offshore, *Paschoa (2010)*.

In order to develop and supply the petroleum industry, in 2006 Transpetro, the shipping subsidiary of Petrobras, selected shipyards to construct the first 26 ships in order to modernize and expand its fleet. In 2008, the Brazilian government launched the Petrobras Fleet and Support Vessel Modernization and Expansion Program which included orders for 146 support vessels, 40 survey/drill ships (12 already in construction by international shipyards and 28 to be constructed in Brazil), 23 tankers, and eight offshore rigs, *Paschoa (2010)*.

The need for more ships and rigs has led to a dramatic growth in employment as evidenced in the statistics provided by Brazil’s shipbuilding association (SINAVAL), Table I.

Table I: Workers Employed in Brazilian Shipbuilding Industry, *França (2009)*.

Year	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009
Workers	1910	3976	6493	7465	12651	14442	19600	39000	40277	45470

3. Overview of EAS

In accordance with the Brazilian Government’s policy of supporting domestic control of the country’s shipbuilding industry, Estaliero Atlântico Sul is 80% owned by corporate Brazilian industrial groups (Camargo Correa and Queiroz Galvão) and 10% PJMR local shipbuilding specialists. However, 10% of the ownership (worth \$22 M) is held by Korea’s Samsung Heavy Industries (SHI) who is hoping to gain a share of the growing and lucrative Brazilian market, *França (2009)*.

Fig.1: Rendering of EAS Shipyard which is the largest in Latin America

The EAS strategy is to use the Petrobras/Transpetro orders as a launching pad to developing international competitiveness and to be productive within five years. To meet this challenging goal they began simultaneous steel processing and yard construction during the start-up phase of their projects.

The EAS shipyard was designed for a processing capability of 160 000 tons of steel per year with facilities to build ships up to 400 thousand tons and various types of offshore rigs, *França (2009)*. The shipyard has a drydock measuring 400 m in length and 73 m wide, a 400 m dock for construction and repair of ships and offshore rigs, with two 1,500-ton cranes and two 300-ton horizontal transport cranes. The property covers a total area of 1.65 million sq. m with a covered building area of 110, 000 sq. m, *Paschoa (2009)*. The shipyard currently has an order book of \$3.4 billion USD for 14 Suezmax tankers, 8 Aframax tankers as well as the hull of a P55 semi-submersible platform, *França (2009)*.

4. Software Evaluation Criteria

The requirement for quickly training a new engineering team led EAS to create a specific set of criteria for the purchase of its 3D product modeling Computer Aided Design, Manufacturing and Engineering (CAD/CAM/CAE) toolset. At a conference in 2009, Ricardo Barcellos, Coordinator of Modeling for EAS, listed and explained criteria EAS used in their evaluation, *Barcellos (2009)*. To meet their needs, EAS believed the software had to:

1. Be shipbuilding-specific
2. Have seamless engineering to production integration
3. Be easily learned and used
4. Allow for working on the model in different offices at the same time

5. Shipbuilding-Specific Software

EAS wanted a CAD/CAM/CAE software package that was specifically designed to fit the needs of shipbuilders. They saw that while some software packages were ideal for projects involving industrial plants or general 3D modeling tasks, they were actually weak when it came to modeling the complex structure of a ship.

EAS also realized that many different groups must interact during the design and construction of a vessel so it was important that they all be able to communicate using common terminology—the terminology of shipbuilding. This principle applied directly to how information was stored and displayed in the ship's 3D product model since the model is utilized throughout the shipbuilding process by various groups using different pieces of software for production automation and planning.

Unfortunately, some CAD/CAM/CAE programs define the product model's geometry and relationships in terms of parametric geometric elements rather than common marine-specific terms. This can confuse end-users who have little understanding of concepts having no real-world counterparts and that do not easily map onto the processes used in a shipyard.

Since EAS was building a modern shipyard designed to facilitate modern shipbuilding practices such as extensive pre-outfitting and design for production principles, they required a software capability that incorporated these principles directly into the 3D product model and facilitated the production of a vessel using these techniques. In addition they needed a software package that would allow seamless integration with shipbuilding production methods without requiring a high degree of production knowledge in the majority of their engineering staff. Only a shipbuilding-specific software package could fulfill all of these requirements.

Fig.2: ShipConstructor Structure Module with AutoCAD interface and ribbon with shipbuilding-specific menus and tools.

6. Integration with Production

Due to the fact that EAS was working with an inexperienced staff, the company determined it was critical for the engineering information from the 3D model to be able to be easily transferred to production. Drawings had to be easily created and information for NC machine-cutting had to be accurately extracted.

This meant that the model had to be more than just a picture. Large amounts of detailed, shipbuilding-specific production output had to be able to be generated semi-automatically. With some software, especially those focused mainly on the 3D modeling tasks or those that are not dedicated to the shipbuilding industry, this is not possible so a significant amount of information for production must be created manually. This requires a high degree of expert knowledge and skill in the entire engineering department—things that were in relatively short supply in Brazil. Manual creation of production documentation would also have been costly, more prone to errors and much more time-consuming. This could have jeopardized the tight schedule EAS was facing in order to complete their first project.

By contrast, EAS saw that the ShipConstructor application allowed for the semi-automatic creation of accurate production output such as assembly drawings, arrangement drawings, spool drawings, plate nests and profile plots etc. because all relevant information is contained within a relational database.

The relational nature of the data also made possible interference checking, clash detection and other error-reduction features which helped speed up the process and improve the quality of work. These were especially important to EAS.

7. Speed to Proficiency

In order to be able to start work as soon as possible, EAS believed it was critical to be able to quickly train new workers on the CAD/CAM/CAE toolset. EAS could not afford to delay the engineering schedule while users gained a sufficient level of proficiency. The software had to be relatively intuitive so that work could start almost immediately.

EAS learned that with ShipConstructor this would be possible due to the way ShipConstructor is designed. ShipConstructor uses the widely-known AutoCAD software as a viewport into its SQL database. Users open AutoCAD directly and ShipConstructor provides a set of shipbuilding-specific menus and tools within the familiar AutoCAD interface. A consistent UI is maintained across several disciplines such as Structure, Piping and HVAC. All disciplines utilize AutoCAD as a viewport and workspace for interacting with the 3D model.

ShipConstructor works in the background via its patent-pending method for storing three dimensional geometry and attribute information within a Database Driven Relational Object Model. The database which stores the ship's 3D model is easily accessible for both importing and exporting to and from other best-of-breed programs which specialize in different aspects of the ship design and production process such as initial design, virtual reality visualization, document management and ERP.

EAS was able to find staff who already knew AutoCAD since it is a widely known design program used in most industries. These AutoCAD users were able to become productive in ShipConstructor after only a few weeks of training. The fact that new employees could quickly become proficient in the software was critical in a country where the industry was being built from the ground up and growing at a rapid rate.

Fig.3: Completed Suezmax ShipConstructor 3D Model

8. Sharing the Model amongst Multiple Offices

EAS had a requirement that is becoming more and more prevalent in the global shipbuilding industry. EAS wished to split some of the production design and engineering work with another company. EAS had arranged for engineering firm CONSUNAV to handle the production engineering of distributed systems such as HVAC, Piping and Equipment while EAS was to be responsible for the structural detail design. That meant that both companies had to have access to the 3D model at the same time while separated by a distance of over 2000 kilometers.

Working on the model over a real time network or internet connection was not a viable option due to the vast distances involved as well as the lack of sufficiently robust and reliable infrastructure. However, trying to work on two different versions of the 3D product model would have resulted in an error-prone project management nightmare.

ShipConstructor fortunately provided a lightweight technological solution. ShipConstructor allows parts of the model to be “split off” and “sealed”. In other words CONSUNAV could work on some parts of the model, safe in the knowledge that EAS would not have the ability to overwrite those areas and vice versa. The split model could then be merged back together when required. This solution was critical in giving EAS staff in Recife the ability to work on the model simultaneously with the CONSUNAV staff in Rio de Janeiro.

9. Conclusion

Brazil is showing the world that a country’s shipbuilding industry can be brought back from the dead in a short period of time. However, the largest problem Brazil faces is the need to quickly train workers. The success of Estaliero Atlântico Sul has proven that a careful selection of technology can help address this challenge.

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Practical Applications of Design for Production

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Abstract

This paper is an overview of Design for Production principles, how they have been applied in practice in several US shipyards, and how technology is being used to make these principles accessible to designers.

1. Introduction

Recently the U.S. Office of the Deputy Under Secretary of Defense (Industrial Policy) commissioned a study, *NN (2007)*, which concluded that engineering departments within US shipyards created a level of design and engineering information that was at least equal to that of major international yards. Despite this apparent equality the study found that average man-hours and cycle times of the US yards remains substantially higher than their international counterparts. Processes and practices employed “pre-production” were identified as having the largest impact on these hours, and it was observed that US shipyards put less emphasis on design for production (DFP) principles. The absence of DFP principles in engineering results in a significantly higher man-hour per Compensated Gross Tonnage (CGT) ratio for US shipyards. The study included an analysis of major European, Korean, and Japanese shipyards for comparison purposes. While the average shipbuilder in each of these regions was ahead of the average US shipbuilder, this was not true in all cases. In addition equality does not exist across these regions with Japan being significantly ahead of Korean and European shipbuilders. This implies that many shipbuilders outside the US could benefit significantly from a greater application of these principles. Through the US Navy-funded National Shipbuilding Research Program (NSRP), US shipyards, led by Bollinger Shipyards, undertook several projects to apply DFP principles to their shipbuilding processes and technologies. These projects involve the introduction of DFP principles into the shipyards processes and engineering tools.

2. Design for Production in Shipbuilding

Design for Production principles have been used successfully in many industries for decades, and are employed to various degrees by shipyards. Some shipyards intuitively apply these principles; however the application is not as effective as an intentional effort would be. A formal definition of DFP can be stated as, *Lamb(1986)*: “... the deliberate act of designing a product to meet its specified technical and operational requirements and quality so that the production costs will be minimal through low work content and ease of fabrication.” One of the more significant challenges shipbuilders face in implementing DFP principles is caused by a lack of understanding of facility constraints and production techniques in junior designers. Many inexperienced designers do not have the skills or knowledge required to know how these constraints and techniques are applied, nor how to apply changes to a production design to mitigate the costs associated with them. This challenge can be overcome by building DFP principles into shipyard manuals, processes, and software tools.

3. Project - Design for Producibility (DFP) for Mid-Tiered Shipyards

The first of two recent NSRP projects looking into the application of DFP principles involved Bollinger Shipyards, Atlantic Marine, and Todd Pacific Shipyards. This project was focused on analyzing and implementing DFP principles into the processes of the member shipyards.

In defining what DFP means in a shipbuilding context the project participants identified 12 DFP guiding principles. These principles are enumerated in *Fanguy et al. (2008)* and reprinted here:

Principle	Description
Design for Facility, Workstation, and Equipment Capabilities	Complex production and costly rework occurs in the ship construction process when the ship has been designed outside the ship builder's infrastructure parameters. The design should be optimized for the shipyard's capabilities and constrained to accommodate the shipyard's limitations. The design should also be optimized for the shipyard's typical build strategy, which should reflect the facility capabilities and constraints. The shipyard's facility, workstation, and equipment information should be documented in a user-friendly format, and maintained in a central repository that is made accessible to the designer.
Minimize Number of Parts	DFP is often understated as simply, minimizing the number of parts, whether it is number of unique parts or total number of parts in a product. This oversimplification emphasizes the correlation of part minimization to many of the other core DFP principles. If parts can be eliminated through the design process, then handling and lifting will be minimized, the amount of welding will decrease, and overproduction will be minimized.
Standardize Parts	Similar to part minimization, standardizing the parts to minimize the number of unique parts that have to be researched, designed, purchased, stored, handled, and processed should lead to dramatic cost and cycle time reduction. Standardized parts enable the shipyard to develop and streamline construction processes and to make the processes repeatable and predictable. A lower skilled work-force can be trained to perform the standard work associated with these parts, and reduce the overall risk of poor quality. With an increased utilization of standard parts, the shipyard can also set up manufacturing work cells to process these parts efficiently through the ship building factory.
Standardize Material Types	The traditional ship design process becomes fragmented through the efforts of multiple designers without tight set-based design criteria established to provide continuity. Left to their own accord, each designer will make material selections that tend to sub-optimize the overall design. These selections are typically based on the designers past experience and their individual preferences. While unintentional, the project becomes overburdened by an increased supply chain complexity, along with an increased purchasing and accounting activity. It minimizes the potential for volume-based discounts, and adds complexity to material handling and warehousing. Multiple material types also causes inefficiencies in production, as production becomes overburdened by the increased skill-set that must be maintained to process the various material types through the ship building factory. With multiple material types to handle, production also loses the ability to realize a learning curve associated with processing standard material through the system.
Minimize Lifting and Handling of Parts	Lifting and handling of parts is labor intensive and non-value added. Therefore attempts to minimize the lifting and handling of parts should be carefully considered during the design process. The transportation activity detracts from flow. Designing the parts so that they can be easily transported through the facility should positively impact the overall flow speed of the facility. When a part is too heavy to lift through the normal lifting and transporting process or its shape invokes extra handling requirements, an overburden is placed on production to accommodate the excess lifting and handling requirement.
Minimize / Optimize Welding	The welding activity is one of the largest contributors to total labor cost, therefore the ability to minimize welding and increase weld efficiency should lead to a reduction in the labor component associated with both structural steel and outfitting work. The design should reflect a build strategy that has minimized the use of "out-of-position" welding. Efforts to eliminate weld sequence variation should be made in the design process, while maintaining compliance with the regulatory requirements. Standardization of weld requirements over multiple parts will enable the shipyard to realize improvement through an increased utilization of semi-automatic and automated welding equipment. Minimization of manual welding can be achieved through consideration of semi-automatic welders, pipe benders, automated flange welding machines, welding positioners, etc.
Simplify Layout and Measuring	Any activity that doesn't change the form, fit, or function of the product is considered non-value added. Layout and measuring activities are often necessary to compensate for variation inherent in the labor-intensive ship building process. The ship design can simplify the layout and measuring activity, by minimizing

	<p>component and part size variation. This will enable manufacturing aids to be customized to “mistake-proof the process so that inspections can be eliminated and measurements be made “at a glance”. Master control lines and reference lines that are marked during the plate cutting process are good examples of how to simplify layout and measuring.</p>
<p>Minimize Fabrication / Assembly Complexity</p>	<p>The design and build strategy should be formulated to minimize the complexity of the fabrication and assembly process. This is accomplished through an overt attempt during design to limit variation in the fabrication and assembly process. For the hull steel process this could mean limiting the variation of plate thicknesses, which minimizes the need to chamfer the plate. In addition, similar size panels being processed through the panel line contributes to smooth work flow. The design should also minimize the number of jigs and fixtures needed to fabricate hull units. On the outfitting side, this could mean limiting the number of fittings per pipe spool to reduce the number of pipe spools with complex shape which requires strict accuracy control for both fabrication and installation. The design build team should assess current steel and outfitting fabrication and assembly processes with an eye towards simplification that can be institutionalized through the design. A “Design for Ergonomics” philosophy should be applied to minimize the level of work effort required to perform the fabrication and assembly processes.</p>
<p>Optimize for Outfitting and Assembly</p>	<p>Outfitting and assembly should occur as early in the process as possible, to allow outfitting to be accomplished when the unit is accessible. To support this goal, the structural and outfitting design processes need to be closely synchronized for each unit, so that the design drawings can be delivered to support the early accomplishment of outfitting. For example, the design group and production group should collaboratively plan for machinery and pipe sub-assemblies so that the appropriate production information can be generated. The ability to preoutfit units can also make a substantial impact on construction schedule, reducing construction cycletime.</p>
<p>Apply Shipyard Standards</p>	<p>Each shipyard has preferred processes, methods, and techniques associated with their view of shipbuilding. Many of the shipyards have codified these preferences through shipyard standards. Typical shipyard standards for steel include standard profile end cuts, structural brackets, collars, etc. Typical shipyard standards for outfitting could include standard vertical ladders, inclined ladders, louvers, gratings, hatches, manholes, doors, electrical control cables, pipe hangers, HVAC duct hangers, etc. The design should incorporate the shipbuilder’s standards as much as possible, while maintaining regulatory compliance and customer performance and operation requirements. The designer should apply the shipyard drawing standard that defines the shipyard’s expectation of what needs to be included on the drawings, specifies the format, naming conventions, Bills of Material, etc to minimize the complexity for the production worker.</p>
<p>Simplify Engineering and Design Process</p>	<p>The constraint of shipbuilding is often found to be receiving on-time, quality drawings. Therefore, the need to simplify and accelerate the engineering and design process has become critical for the U.S. Shipbuilding Industry. Lean Design techniques should be applied to eliminate wastes inherent to the traditional ship design process. Typical wastes include delays resulting from downtime searching for information or waiting on analysis results. Features are added to the design that customers don’t need or haven’t specified, resulting in over-design. Poor quality designs due to process churn, result in producing product defects. Lean Design reduces delays through fully integrated, synchronized management of all product data and process knowledge. A key component to simplifying the engineering and design process is to have standard engineering processes and a structured repository for all product and process data required in product development, including the wealth of related information needed to execute the standard product development processes.</p>
<p>Optimize for Inspection and Test</p>	<p>When designing systems, the designer should be knowledgeable of the inspection and test requirements and how system segmentation impacts the ability to optimize tests. The design methodology for systems should include a combination of “in-line” component tests and system tests to enable testing to be performed as early as possible within the build process, even in the shop fabrication or unit assembly stages, to mitigate risks associated with system performance and schedule delay.</p>

3.1 Implementation Examples

As part of this project the shipyards implemented a few DFP principles into existing shipbuilding programs. These examples show the efficacy of DFP principles applied in engineering at the participating shipyards. Each of these examples and the results of implementation were summarized in *Fanguy et al. (2008)* after the project was completed and are shared here.

Grid-Cooler Arrangement and Build Strategy

Before: In their initial arrangement, grid cooler location was such that the coolers crossed a master erection butt. Therefore, the grid coolers could not be installed until after the two adjacent units were erected. Because the grid coolers are generally situated on the bottom shell, this meant that the coolers had to be installed in an overhead position, using pad-eyes and chain-falls for the lifting arrangement. In addition, because the shipyard uses stock at the ends of units, and trims to suit during final fit-up of the units, the piping penetration locations for the grid coolers could not be finalized until after the two blocks were joined. The penetrations then had to be manually cut.

After: Implementing DFP methodologies, the arrangement was optimized for build strategy considerations. The grid cooler location was revised so that it only spanned one unit. The result was that the grid coolers could be installed at the subassembly stage of construction, while the unit was in the shop, and was accessible by an overhead crane. In addition, because the piping penetration locations were firm, the penetrations could be cut with the plate, using the CNC plate cutting machine.

Fig. 1: Before: Grid cooler crossed master butt

Fig. 2: After: Grid cooler included on one module

Cost Avoidance: There were two of these grid coolers per boat, and the shipyard estimated a projected savings of approximately 1,050 man hours per boat. There was a minimal cost for engineering and drawing changes required to implement this change.

Minimizing Total Piece Parts and Welding

Before: The steel functional design of the deckhouse structure had already included some instances of using flanged plate parts for some minor bulkheads in lieu of welding plate parts to create small subassemblies. For example, as shown in Fig. 3, the design shows the three minor bulkheads around an outfitting trunk being created from one flanged plate part. This type of arrangement, while viewed as a cost saving opportunity, was not fully implemented in the existing functional design.

Fig. 3: Example of Minor Bulkhead using Flanged Plate

After: Lessons-learned held with production and engineering personnel after construction of the first in a series of vessels, indicated that there were numerous other instances in the deckhouse design where they could take advantage of using flanged parts in lieu of welding for minor bulkhead subassemblies. One example is shown below. It shows a recessed bulkhead with a door opening. The first boat sub-assembly had four plate parts that were welded together, with an angle backing bar used to facilitate welding of the part in place. Subsequent vessels used a flanged part in lieu of 3 of the 4 parts, and simplified the backing bar arrangement. Cost Avoidance: A total of 12 sub-assemblies were eliminated in the deckhouse design. It is estimated that a savings of 120 man-hours per boat was achieved, with a minimal design change cost.

Fig. 4: Before: 5 parts total, welded

Fig. 5: After: 3 parts total, flanged

5. Project - Practical Applications of Design for Production

The first NSRP project established the value of introducing DFP principles into the engineering process via DFP guidelines, shipyard standards, and DFP manuals. The introduction of documented shipyard standards and preferences, along with a set of DFP manuals, was intended to provide a set of tools which allows junior or inexperienced designers to apply DFP principles to their work. As the

workforce available in the US, as in many regions, is an aging workforce these tools were essential to ensure correct implementation of the guidelines.

Following the successful completion of the first project it was noted that the tools created still require designers to interpret and apply these principles manually. Leveraging the success of several past NSRP projects, the shipyards involved proposed a following project that would strengthen the DFP specific capabilities of ShipConstructor, the detail design and production software that they use. The team members on the project included Bollinger Shipyards, Inc., VT Halter Marine, Marinette Marine Corporation, Northrop Grumman Ship Systems, ShipConstructor Software USA Inc., ShipConstructor Software Inc., and Genoa Design International Ltd.

5.1 State of Practice

To determine the areas of ShipConstructor that could benefit the most from the work done in the first DFP project, a review of the capabilities already available in the software was necessary. The review found that ShipConstructor already offered a degree of capability in many areas that allowed DFP principles to be implemented. Specifically, the principles around *Standardization of Material Types*, *Application of Shipyard Standards*, and *Optimization for Outfitting and Assembly* were well covered by ShipConstructor's flexible stock libraries, ability to limit standard's based on situational usage (for example endcut standards and stiffener cutouts associatively applied to only specific stiffener stocks), and focus on product driven pre-outfitting within the build strategy respectively.

5.1.1 Simplify Layout and Measuring

This is an area where it was determined that improvements to ShipConstructor *could* see marked decreases in production hours. While ShipConstructor does have many existing features to allow for automatic marking of plates (many of which are shown in Figure X), including associative stiffener marking, bevel marking, marking of the angle between two plates (referred to as the dihedral angle), marking of datum and reference lines, there are additional features that could be added that would extend these capabilities.

Fig. 6: Minor assembly with marking

These additional capabilities include features commonly used in Japanese shipyards where DFP principles are applied more generously, and effectively, than anywhere else in the world. An example of this type of feature, called Accuracy Control Marks, allows for accurate fit-up between plates, and stiffeners, during assembly. A mark is made on each plate at a set distance from the mark on the other plate. Without referring to any documentation the shipyard worker can make a single measurement that includes the gap between plates and ensure a high degree of dimensional accuracy. Although there was significant benefit to be gained here, many of the enhancements of this type would require changes to the member shipyards current processes which were outside of the scope of this project.

Fig. 7: Accuracy control marks used for accurate fit-up

5.2 Improved Practice

The areas where the shipyards felt that they could benefit the most from DFP principles in the software involved three of the previously identified guiding principles: *Minimization of Total Piece Parts and Welding*, *Minimization of Fabrication/Assembly Complexity*, and the *Standardization of Parts*. The identified areas were related to the areas in which the shipyards had showcased the application of DFP principles towards the end of the first DFP project.

The most significant challenge these shipyards face when trying to implement this type of cost saving measure is in ensuring that less-experienced designers can identify these opportunities and create solutions that take advantage of them. As a result two new modules were identified that, when added to the ShipConstructor software, would provide the largest return.

5.2.1 Standard Assemblies

During the first NSRP project on DFP a practical example of applying these guidelines minimized the overall complexity and number of parts in a *single* commonly used subassembly and saved over 120 man-hours per vessel as a result. Many similar types of sub-assemblies were identified that represent similar cost savings.

Fig. 8: Inner bottom panel defined as a standard assembly

The first deliverable proposed as part of this project was a new software module called 'Standard Assemblies'. A Standard Assembly is defined as a part, or set of parts, including Structure, Pipe, HVAC and Equipment components defined once and used repeatedly throughout the detail design of a vessel. The definition of a Standard Assembly includes both the 3D model of the assembly as well as the specific assembly sequence to be used each time the assembly is used in the 3D product model.

This module allowed experienced designers to build a library of commonly used parts, assemblies, and components that can be consumed by less experience designers. These assemblies can be moved between one vessel and the next, allowing for significant reuse of this captured knowledge. Reusing portions of the detail design across shipbuilding programs increases the degree of repeatability during the build process of vessels. Increased repeatability reduces the amount of training required across vessels and once again reduces the number of hours spent in production.

The effort by experienced designers to introduce DFP principles into a detail design, thereby reducing the number of parts or complexity of a given assembly, can be used over and over by less experienced designers. When used correctly this process creates significant cost savings due to reduced production labor, but also significantly reduces the time required to model the portions of the vessel where these Standard Assemblies are used. In addition, a Standard Assembly does not only consist of the 3D product model for the assembly. The assembly sequence required to correctly fabricate the assembly is maintained along with the 3D model information. This ensures that the knowledge capture from the experienced designer, when utilized by a less experienced designer in a vessel, includes both the model and the *intended* assembly sequence for the piece parts.

A key requirement of the Standard Assemblies module, and all ShipConstructor software, is the ability to associatively update all instances of the Standard Assembly when the standard itself changes. This requirement was set to allow the shipyards to respond to changes in applied DFP principles, in shipyard constraints and capabilities, and as the designers improve on the overall design of the vessels.

5.2.2 Improved Pipe Supports

Another area was identified where an extremely low degree of standardization, little use of documented shipyard preferences, and a high degree of assembly complexity was causing a significantly higher than necessary amount of production work. The culprit was complex supports for piping systems throughout the vessel.

Each situation where a support is required, for one or many pipes, is slightly different. This often results in a completely different support arrangement for each situation. Different material types are used for the doublers, legs and cross tiers for each support. Different endcut and cutout standards are applied to each of the elements in the support depending on the preferences of the designer. A different configuration is created for each support with insufficient thought to the variety that production will see.

Fig. 9: Improved pipe supports in a ShipConstructor model

However, because every situation *is different*, a system was required that would allow for standardization on configurations, material types, and production standards without imposing too

many constraints on the resulting supports. As a result the project team proposed the creation of a DFP-based Pipe Supports module.

The requirement to improve the use of shipyard standards, and material types across various situations where pipe supports are required led to the creation of Pipe Support Templates. A Pipe Support Template is the definition of the required elements, including endcuts, doubler plates, and material types to be used, to build a support when it is applied in a specific situation. Five different categories of templates were identified to ensure that the software being developed handled the majority of cases required by the shipyards.

Upon insertion into the 3D model the pipe support, derived from the selected template, has the required cutouts, endcuts, trims and materials required to produce each one of the components required. In addition each of the components can be included in ShipConstructor's usual array of production output including plate and profile nesting, profile plots, assembly drawings and more.

Fig. 10: Several Pipe Supports derived from the same support template

Fig. 11: Generated pipe support construction drawing

To ensure that the standardization added to the design of pipe supports was correctly leveraged by the shipyard, a final requirement of the new software was the addition of functionality to generate template driven, construction drawings for the supports. The drawings needed to be automatically

dimensioned, and annotated based on the shipyards requirements. Complete bills of materials on each drawing were required that would facilitate the fabrication of the support.

6. Conclusions

Based on a study comparing the capabilities of US shipyards to those abroad, it was found that the lack of DFP principles applied in engineering was a significant factor in the higher cost of building a vessel in the US. A series of projects was proposed that would allow US shipyards to investigate and implement DFP principles, both into existing practices and into the software tools they use for detail design. These projects, now successfully completed will help US shipyards to product vessels at lower cost for domestic commercial and naval markets and is a step towards international competitiveness.

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Modeling Complex Vessels for Use in a 3D Packing Approach: An Application to Deepwater Drilling Vessel Design

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Abstract

The recently developed 3D packing routine for the early stage configuration design of ships (v. Oers, 2010) offers an approach to maintain flexibility in the arrangement of designs at a higher level of detail, allowing for a speedier and more thorough consideration of concept alternatives. Application of the packing routine requires definition of configurable parts and corresponding interactions as well as an approach to direct the search to interesting designs. This paper presents the first application of the packing approach in a test case on deepwater drilling vessels and illustrates how a large and diverse set of compact and coherent design configurations are obtained on the basis of one single input model.

1. Introduction

Efforts at Delft University of Technology, *Oers and Stapersma (2006)*, *Oers et al. (2007,2010)*, have led to the development of a packing approach¹ that enables the rapid generation of a large and diverse set of feasible three-dimensional ship configurations. Key feature is its ability to generate ship configurations by arranging parts of the ship (e.g. systems) inside a changeable envelope, without relying on a pre-defined layout. This results in a vast increase in the range of ship configurations that can be generated and evaluated.

The packing approach is developed into a MATLAB based routine which is capable of finding feasible designs, which all meet a set of non-negotiable, user-defined criteria, *Oers et al. (2007,2009)*. Examples of such criteria are requirements on minimum levels of intact stability, freeboard and station keeping capability. The routine uses a genetic algorithm in order to direct the search for designs of increasing quality. In combination with a space allocation routine the solution space of possible configurations is searched extensively supplying the user with a diverse set of coherent ship configurations, i.e. alternative design solutions.

The approach is envisioned to have two main qualities, *Oers et al. (2007)*:

- Human decisions can be restricted to feasible designs. A significant reduction of user effort can be achieved by omitting the need to manually generate balanced design solutions, especially when one wants to consider multiple design solutions that satisfy similar requirements.
- Compromise decisions can be taken with instant feedback on the impact of such a decision. This replaces the slow feedback designers experience today when working out the impact of compromise decisions or large design changes on the configuration of a design.

In summary the 3D packing approach offers an approach to maintain flexibility in the arrangement of designs at a higher level of detail, allowing for a speedier and more thorough consideration of concept alternatives in early stage design. The development of this approach has always focused on practical

¹ The term packing approach relates to the research field of packing problems which studies the optimization of packing objects into a container.

use in early stage design but was up to now never applied. This paper, therefore, presents the first application of the developed packing approach in a test case on concept alternatives for deepwater drilling vessels.

A drilling vessel can be characterized as a complex and highly integrated ship type. The configuration of drilling vessel arrangements is not straightforward but nonetheless vital to the development of a concept design. This makes the early stage design of a drilling vessel a perfect test case for the 3D packing approach.

Application of the approach in a test case is, however, far from trivial. First, one must define both the parts of the ship that will be configured and the interactions that occur between those parts or systems. Second, the freedom to generate a wide range of configurations comes at a cost: not all configurations will be of interest. One must therefore have the means to control the packing process such that it generates suitable ship configurations. This paper presents the development of a practical and efficient ship architectural model for use in the 3D packing approach and discusses the results and experiences obtained from the test case.

Section 2 starts with a brief description of the used packing routine. For a more complete description of the packing approach reference is made to *Oers et al. (2010)*. In section 3 the implementation of a suitable model is discussed. In section 4 the model is applied and the test case results are discussed. In the final section conclusions are presented.

2. Introduction into the 3D Packing Routine

The 3D packing routine comprises of two core modules; the (1) packing routine and the (2) genetic search algorithm. The packing routine configures a single design based on configurable components or system input, *Nat (1999)*. The genetic search algorithm directs the repetitive process in order to steer convergence to increasingly improving design alternatives, Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Overview of the 3D packing routine

The packing routine places systems in the hull envelope one after the other on the basis of initial position values. The routine searches for the closest suitable location satisfying the system requirements. Systems are defined with properties, such as; shape, weight, required area, volume, overlap, connections to other systems, or required surrounding free space. These attributes can be combined in order to represent all the functional requirements for a system. Systems are placed within a matrix which administrates the remaining available space and includes the objects already placed in the hull envelope.

The initial position values for the systems are used by the genetic algorithm as the main decision variables required to uniquely describe a design. The strings with decision variables are manipulated by the genetic algorithm mechanisms of selection, crossover and mutation in order to create new populations of design alternatives.

Further inputs to the genetic algorithm are constraint and objective values which serve to evaluate the ‘quality’ of a design. Design alternatives which satisfy the constraint requirements and better satisfy objectives have a higher probability of being selected for reproduction by the genetic algorithm and are therefore more likely to hand over their traits to the following designs. In this manner convergence to increasingly improving designs is achieved.

The genetic algorithm used is the NSGAI which is a well established genetic algorithm capable of dealing with multiple constraint and objective functions, *Deb et al. (2002)*.

3. Development of an Input Model for Deepwater Drilling Vessels

After a brief introduction into deepwater drilling vessels the approach to the modeling of a deepwater drilling vessel for application in the 3D packing routine is presented in a step-wise manner.

3.1. Introduction into Deepwater Drilling Vessels

Drilling vessels are designed to execute drilling activities at sea in the search for hydrocarbon deposits below the seabed. Drilling vessels find their application particularly in deep waters due to their supreme station keeping capability. In the case of the P10,000NG, Fig. 2, which is used as the parent vessel for this test case, the activities can be refined to exploration and development drilling, well testing and well completion. In order to perform these activities numerous support functions are required. These functions can be investigated and visualized by means of a functional breakdown, *Klein Woud and Stapersma (2002)*. Fig. 3 illustrates such a breakdown for a drilling vessel.

Fig. 2: Drilling vessel overview (GustoMSC's P10,000NG)

A parent design (P10,000NG) has been chosen as a basis for the test case for two main reasons. The first is practical, weight and dimension input required for the system model can be based on the parent design instead of having to derive the weight and dimension input generically. As such the focus can be placed on the modeling of the system interactions or constraints. The second motivation is that the parent design offers a basis for comparison of the test case results.

Fig. 3: Functional decomposition for deepwater drilling vessel (drilling, well testing & completion)

The functions of a drilling vessel can be broken down and allocated to the systems required to perform these functions. In turn, systems can be combined into configurable objects which are required as the main input for the model. From the functional decomposition six key functionalities can be distilled, namely:

1. **Riser, Pipe and Casing Supply** – Storage and handling of tubulars required for the drilling operation. Efficient transport routes are required to and from the drilling assembly.
2. **Mud Circulation** – Storage, processing and supply of pressurized mud (and cement) required to control the drilling operations.
3. **Drilling Capability** – Hoisting and rotation, heave compensation, tubular and manifold handling required to perform the drilling operations.
4. **Electrical Power Supply** – Power supply for drilling, vessel systems and station keeping.
5. **Hotel Functionality** – Accommodation and supporting systems for the crew.
6. **Platform Functionality** – Buoyancy, stability and station keeping capability to provide a suitable platform for the operational functions.

The first five functionalities are the key to identifying a system decomposition relevant to a suitable drilling vessel model and the interactions that need to be attached to these systems. Process diagrams have been used to identify system decompositions and system interactions schematically, Fig. 4. These insights form the basis for the system input required for the model. The interactions between the systems are discussed in the section on system constraints (section 3.3). The sixth functionality (platform functionality) is relevant to the vessel as a whole and is therefore discussed in the section on constraint functions (section 3.4). First, however, the breakdown of the vessel into systems is discussed in the next section.

3.2. Selection of Systems

The principal step towards deriving a model is the selection of the systems to be modeled. In the preceding section a functional breakdown, Fig. 3, and process diagrams, Fig. 4, were discussed as

means to get an insight into the systems and relationships relevant to a drilling vessel. Furthermore the selection of a proper system subdivision is based on the following criteria;

1. **Demarcation and clustering of systems** – Demarcation of systems and their boundaries is to be clear and intuitive so that analysis of the results is understandable.
2. **System size** – Systems are selected on the basis of their size, i.e. the size of the system is to be relevant to the packing problem.
3. **Spatial subdivision** – Decomposition is mainly based on spaces, rooms or areas rather than pieces of equipment.

Fig. 4: Process Diagram - Riser, pipe & casing supply

Fig. 5: Subdivision into systems

Fig. 6: Overview of modeled systems

Fig. 5 illustrates the subdivision of the vessel into systems on the basis of the general arrangement of the P10,000NG. Separate configurable systems are identified with a number. Systems 1-7 all relate to the hoisting and rotation functionality. Each system has a separate sub-function and can be identified by clear boundaries. In the case of systems 1-7 the choice has been made to group them into one single system, namely the drilling assembly. A subdivision is made for the complete drilling vessel; Fig. 6 gives an overview of the systems used in the model.

3.3. System Constraints

Given the subdivision into systems, the system input has to be determined consisting of dimensions, shapes, weights and, most importantly, a set of positioning requirements or so called system constraints. System constraints are the prerequisites for the proper positioning of a system, or the functionality of a system, and thereby constitute the main logic of the model.

Four main cornerstones have been used for the modeling of the system constraints; the (1) generalization and clustering of systems, the use of (2) discrete alternatives, (3) reduction of the degrees of freedom, and the use of (4) initial position boundaries, *Wagner (2009)*.

A generalization and clustering of systems has been used in order to limit the number of systems used. Systems which predominantly interact with a specific group of systems and little with other systems, and which are typically placed in a consolidated configuration have been grouped as a single system. An example is the drilling assembly including the derrick, drill floor, substructure, BOP and X-mas tree storage locations (numbers 1-7 in Fig. 5). This generalization and clustering reduces the complexity of the system constraints and positioning complexity of the system group and thus speeds up the positioning process considerably. The downside is that the system group is limited to a specific configuration. In order to be able to distinguish multiple configuration alternatives for such a system group discrete alternatives have been used.

Discrete alternatives distinguish between a collection of predefined configuration alternatives for a system or system group. An example is an engine room arrangement comprising of either three or four separate engine rooms.

Symmetry and limitation of degrees of freedom in positioning are used as means to make the search for suitable locations more efficient. Symmetry of systems is used to allow for positioning of systems on the centerline of the vessel irrespective of their shape and form. Consequentially the y-degree of freedom can be discarded reducing the number of decision variables from three (x,y,z) to two (x,z). Further degrees of freedom can be discarded for specific systems such as the z-position for a crane and the z-position for the moonpool.

Initial position boundaries are implemented in order to steer placement to configurations which reflect the logic of a drilling vessel. Fundamentally the drilling assembly is placed in the midship area of the vessel for motion and weight distribution reasons but also so that supporting systems can be placed in its vicinity and so that tubulars can be supplied from either side of the drilling assembly. This leaves the fore and aft end of the vessel available for the other, platform related systems. The range of initial position values has been limited for specific groups of systems in order to reflect these virtual boundaries typical to a drilling vessel. Note that these boundaries only apply to the initial position, and not to the final position of a system. Therefore the range of possible positions for systems is not limited in a strict manner, but the search for suitable arrangements is supported.

Finally it is important to address the relevance of the positioning order of the systems to the efficiency of the packing process. The taken approach is to place the large objects first in order to have the largest likelihood of obtaining an arrangement in which all systems can be fitted.

Aside of the system modeling an approach is required to the modeling of the hull, decks and bulkheads. The hull is scaled on the basis of the main dimensions, which are implemented as decision

variables. The shape of the hull is manipulated by extending or shortening the length of the midship section, which is implemented as a further decision variable.

Longitudinal bulkheads are included to model the wing tanks. Five transverse bulkheads are taken into account of which two are the fore and aft peak bulkheads and three bulkheads are directly placed in connection to three of the largest systems. As such the positioning of bulkheads is linked to logical locations and does not require additional positioning algorithms. Although the number of transverse bulkheads may be insufficient the main importance of their impact on the arrangement is considered to be covered.

Decks are not physically included in the model but are used as positioning heights for the systems. The deck height is fixed to four meters and the tank top height is variable. In this manner it is secured that all systems are placed level to each other. Systems can however take up multiple deck levels.

3.4. Constraint Functions

Constraint functions are required by the search algorithm in order to evaluate the overall feasibility of the design solution, i.e. aspects critical to the feasibility of the design which cannot be covered in the system constraints. Certain aspects, such as the floating position and stability of the design (i.e. platform functionality as discussed in section 3.1), are relevant to the design as a whole and can only be evaluated when all systems are configured. As such they are implemented as separate constraint functions and are evaluated at the end of the packing sequence.

Two key constraint functions are identified as important for the model to function properly; a freeboard, trim and stability constraint and a constraint that secures that all systems are actually placed.

The latter is merely a formality required to distil incomplete designs from the results. The freeboard, trim and stability constraint function secures that a proper weight balance is established aside of the spatial balance which is already established by means of the system constraints.

The freeboard, trim and stability constraint is implemented as a separate routine in which a ballast calculation is performed in order to satisfy a condition of zero trim, zero heel and a minimum required Metacentric value (GM) for all defined loading conditions. Finally the remaining freeboard is evaluated.

The implemented constraint functions are considered to constitute the minimum evaluation required in order to generate coherent design solutions which satisfy a basic level of feasibility.

3.5. Objective Functions

Objective functions are required by the NSGA-II in order to direct the search to increasingly improving design solutions, i.e. to obtain the set of design solutions of interest.

It is important to minimize the number of objective functions used, since this determines the calculation complexity of the convergence process, *Deb et al.(2002)*, i.e. the number of generations and according time to reach a proper level of convergence. In principal two objective functions have been used. The result is a two-dimensional optimization problem resulting in a two-dimensional Pareto front.

The first objective is the minimization of void space, i.e. the minimization of empty cells within the hull envelope. This fundamental objective is required in order to direct convergence to compact design solutions which are more difficult to configure than spacious arrangements. Moreover the pursuit of reasonably compact design configurations is a principal goal in naval architecture in order to minimize cost of a vessel.

Fig. 7: Objective functions and Pareto front (green)

The second objective is to minimize the logistical effort in the design, i.e. to minimize distances between related systems or building blocks. This incorporates aspects such as piping, cabling and transport routes for materials such as risers, pipes and casings.

4. Results and Discussion

The foregoing completes the required input model comprising of (1) a set of systems constraints in order to secure the feasible configuration of systems, (2) constraint functions in order to secure overall or platform functionality and (3) objective functions in order to steer the convergence process to interesting configuration alternatives. This section describes the application of the model in the 3D packing routine and presents the obtained results. First the underlying test runs are described and discussed after which one example design solution is selected and discussed. Finally a number of remaining aspects are addressed in a discussion in section 4.3.

4.1. Test Case Results

Preliminary runs were executed in order to validate and improve the model until the quality of the obtained results was found to be acceptable. Thereafter five separate test cases were run in order to force the routine into different directions of the solution space. These five test cases form the data set of results presented in the following sections.

For the different test runs, discrete decision variables were fixed to specific values in order to force the routine to develop different types of overall configurations. The reasons for running five separate test runs instead of perfecting a single run is that the genetic algorithm tends to converge prematurely to a dominant configuration alternative. As a result insufficient diversity is obtained in a single run. The issue of premature convergence is addressed in more detail in section 4.3.

Fig. 8 illustrates the variety of design solutions obtained from the different test cases. The variety in configurations illustrates the diversity of the solutions which are obtained with the same architectural model. The obtained configurations are logical, i.e. the implemented system constraints and constraint functions effectively secure a basic level of feasibility of the design solutions. Visible examples are

the free space available above the thruster trunks, the connection between the riser catwalk and the drilling assembly and the free space above the pipe racks.

Fig. 8: Design Alternatives from the different test cases

From the obtained design solutions the effect of the objective functions is also evident. The obtained solutions are compact as a result of the compactness objective and systems which interact with each other are predominantly clustered together as a result of the vicinity objective. Note for example how in all configurations the riser hold is located directly adjacent to the drilling assembly. The objective functions effectively support the search for design solutions which are increasingly compact, and have increasingly efficient arrangements.

Fig. 9: Cloud of all generated design solutions

Fig. 9 gives an overview of the complete cloud of obtained design solutions. Solutions from different test runs are marked in different colors. Values on the horizontal axis indicate the compactness objective values and values on the y-axis mark the vicinity objective values. As such the Pareto front of best solutions runs along the lower left edge of the scatter.

Comparison of the objective values of the different test cases show that certain test cases supersede others and dominate the total Pareto front. On this basis it can however not be concluded that certain configurations (such as the riser hold aft and the engine rooms forward for test run 5) are better than others. Convergence for the different test cases is not necessary completed, and small updates and modifications of the model were implemented over the course of the test cases.

4.2. Design Selection

Successful application of the routine in the early stages of a design process requires that a designer can assume responsibility over the generated results and can support one or multiple dominant design solutions as his design(s). Therefore *Oers (2008,2009)* argues for an approach consisting of two phases, namely in the first phase the routine searches for a large and diverse set of feasible design alternatives after which the designer selects a best solution from the obtained design solutions. By running the five test runs the required set of feasible design alternatives has been obtained (step 1). In this section the second step of manual evaluation and selection of design solutions is discussed on the basis of an example.

The proposed approach to the evaluation and selection of configuration alternatives is to filter the cloud of obtained solutions by means of secondary constraints and objectives. Filtering of the cloud of solutions allows for the user to direct the search and look at the design solutions from different perspectives. This approach supports the goal of exploiting the available information and learning from the obtained solutions, *Wagner (2009)*.

Examples of secondary constraints and objectives are a maximum Metacentric value (GM), a maximum required ballast capacity or specific requirements for the location of systems. Secondary constraints and objectives can be based on post processing calculations such as resistance and powering estimates or for example a separation objective as used in the following example. This makes filtering of the cloud of solutions flexible, i.e. not all objectives need to be defined on beforehand.

The following example illustrates the selection approach at the hand of one of the obtained results. The cloud of obtained design solutions is filtered on the basis of the following set of secondary objectives and constraints.

Secondary Objectives:	Secondary Constraints:
1.Minimize Compactness (L x B x D x Cb*)	1.GM \leq 4 m
2.Minimize Vicinity	2.Total required ballast \leq 30.000 tons (all LC's)
3.Maximize Separation	3.ROV Moonpool – thrusterl \geq 4Dthruster
	4.Engine room placed aft (TC's 1,2,4)

Fig. 10 gives an overview of the selected design. The plots in the top of the figure represent the secondary objective (two leftmost plots) and constraint values (two rightmost plots). The pink dots mark the solutions which have been discarded because they do not satisfy the secondary constraints. This leaves the blue dots as the remaining solutions. Of the remaining solutions the green dots form the set of Pareto front solutions, i.e. solutions which best satisfy the three objective functions. The red dot marks the solution which is visualized in the bottom of the figure. Selection of a specific design from the obtained Pareto front is up to the user. The designer is able to look into the filtered configurations and the corresponding parameters and can chose to alter or refine his secondary objective and constraint functions until he is able to complete the selection process.

For the post processing of the results, and selection of this specific design alternative a third separation objective has been used. Recall that the runs were executed on the basis of two objective functions, and that the separation objective is used as a secondary objective for post processing purposes only. Similar to the vicinity objective, the separation objective contains a set of relations between systems which are to be separated. Separation of systems may be an objective for reasons of

noise or vibration, separation of hazardous areas and minimization of thruster interaction or thruster moonpool interaction.

Fig. 10: Selected design solution (Design 9230, Test Case 5)

Table I gives an overview of key particulars of the selected alternative configuration. The values are compared to those of the P10,000NG which formed the basis for the system input such as system dimensions and weights. Note how closely the main particulars correspond to that of the P10,000NG. In fact the selected design solution is also largely similar in configuration to that of the parent design. The example illustrates that the routine is capable of converging to solutions which are similar to existing designs. This validates to some extent the input model and shows that the obtained results are reasonably converged.

Table I: Particulars for selected design (Design 9230, Test Case 5)

	design name	Lx Bx Dx Cb*	viscosity objective	separation objective	Length	Breadth	Depth	Displacement (max LC)	Draft (max LC)	Tank top height	Long. bulkhead distance	Cb*	L/B	B/T	Total ballast (all LC \$)	min GM (LC)	max GM (LC)	min Freeboard (max LC)	Lightship weight	Required ballast tank capacity (max LC)
	[-]	[m³]	[m]	[m]	[m]	[m]	[m]	[t]	[m]	[m]	[m]	[-]	[-]	[-]	[t]	[m]	[m]	[m]	[t]	[t]
P10,000NG	1	102710	1300	-2310	230	36	18	60717	10,4	2	5	0,69	6,4	3,5	18453	1,00	2,52	7,6	30795	6872
Selected	9230	103359	957	-2339	230	36	18	63137	10,7	2	5	0,69	6,4	3,4	20790	1,00	3,15	7,3	30795	8092

4.3. Discussion

In the foregoing sections some of the obtained results have been presented. Application of the derived model in a test case has shown that a large and diverse set of logical design alternatives can be obtained. In this section a number of issues which were encountered during the test case are discussed in more detail.

4.3.1. Premature Convergence

Analysis of the preliminary test runs show that the genetic algorithm has the tendency to converge to one dominant configuration alternative during a single run. I.e. all solutions from a specific generation onward show similar configurations with for example the accommodation forward, the engine rooms aft and the riser hold forward. These results show that the genetic algorithm is incapable of maintaining sufficient diversity in configuration over the course of the convergence process. I.e. it is not secured that the complete solution space is scanned, nor the global optimum reached. Moreover the genetic algorithm is incapable of generating the diverse set of design solutions that are required, through one individual run.

This effect can be explained by the fact that the combination of two, widely different, parent designs has a large probability of resulting in infeasibility of the resulting child design. Because of the differences in the decision variable values of two widely different designs, combination or crossover of these values is likely to lead to an odd configuration in which some of the systems cannot be placed, i.e. an incomplete and therefore infeasible design. Crossover of similar configuration is much more likely to yield a complete and therefore feasible solution. The genetic algorithm NSGAIL, *Deb et al. (2002)*, prioritizes feasibility over diversity in the selection of solutions for the next generation. Therefore the emphasis of convergence of the genetic algorithm is on maintaining feasibility, which is more likely to be obtained from populations with similar configurations than from populations with very diverse configurations.

This issue is patched by manually forcing the routine into different directions by fixing the discrete decision variables of the key systems to specific values, as was done for the five test runs discussed in section 4.1. In this manner it is secured that the complete solution space is scanned. Key systems are typically the large and discrete systems which dominate the configuration such as the riser hold (either forward or aft of the drilling assembly), the engine rooms (in the stern or bow of the vessel) and the accommodation (forward or aft).

The implemented discrete decision variables can be identified as a potential source of the dominance of similar configuration alternatives. On the other hand it can be concluded that these alternatives are an inherent property of drilling vessels. The riser hold can either be located forward or aft of the drilling derrick; there are no alternatives, other than these two extremes. Therefore, the presence of discrete alternatives in a ship configuration, regardless of how they are modeled, is identified as an inherent challenge to the convergence of the genetic algorithm.

4.3.2. Constraining

From the test case results it can be concluded that the implemented system constraints and constraint functions effectively support the generation of feasible design configurations. The derivation of a suitable constraint model is however not an instantaneous process, the modeling is rather a process of trial and error and gradual improvement. This fact emphasizes that the taken approach is not the only possible solution but merely shows to fulfill its function. Cornerstones to the approach taken are the gradual refinement of system constraints and the limiting of constraint functions.

Critical to the system constraints is the balance between over- and under-constraining. On one hand it is necessary to be careful with constraints and not limit the possible variations excessively, on the other hand sufficient constraints are required in order to secure feasibility. An under constrained model is useless because it offers loopholes to infeasibility. I.e. the routine may converge to infeasible configurations with higher objective values because the positioning of systems is not sufficiently constrained. An over-constrained model is useful but may be limited in the obtained variations. Consequently it is more likely that a suitable model is over-constrained than under-constrained. During the modeling process the implemented system constraints have gradually been reduced in order to diversify the model. The priority remains however the robustness of the model, i.e. feasibility over diversity. The challenge therefore remains to balance the system constraints as much as possible.

Furthermore the approach to the implementation of constraint functions has been to limit them as far as possible. Only the minimum required constraint functions to secure a basic weight balance in the designs have been implemented. The approach on design selection has shown that secondary constraints can always be added in a later stage as a means to evaluate further aspects. Implementation of subsequent constraints can be expected to shift the Pareto front of solutions backward, to areas of the solution space which are likely to have been covered by the search algorithm. Furthermore the implementation of further evaluations which can be used either as primary or secondary constraint functions requires a large amount of programming effort. Moreover a tradeoff has to be made between the required level of detail of such evaluations and the required calculation time.

4.3.3. Practical Application

Application of the 3D packing approach has given rise to two main practical issues. First, the calculation time of the routine poses a large limitation to the practical applicability. Running of a single test run resulting in roughly 5000 designs requires around 24 hours. Substantial improvements can be expected by changing to a low level script and by rearranging the data structure. Second, implementation of a model requires experience with the routine. The required programming effort is however acceptable and alterations to the model are easily made. Implementation of a proper interface is however required to make the routine more accessible to users that lack programming and modeling experience.

5. Conclusions

The test case results have shown the ability of the routine to successfully model a complex vessel on the basis of a set of basic system constraints, objective and constraint functions. Results show that the routine is capable of generating alternative design solutions which are logical in configuration, satisfy a basic level of feasibility and are optimized to a reasonable extent. Both configurations which closely correspond to the P10,000NG parent design and which are radically different can be obtained.

Test runs on the other hand also show that the routine is incapable of preserving sufficient diversity in order to secure that the complete solution space is scanned. Therefore it is necessary to manually force the routine into different directions of the solution space in order to obtain a sufficiently diverse and complete set of alternative design solutions. Further research is required to find a more definite solution to this issue.

Experience obtained from working with the routine has shown that practical application of the routine is hampered by an excessively large calculation time and the lack of a proper interface. Improvement of both aspects is critical to the further development of the routine and to the practical implementation of this methodology as a design approach.

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Optimization-Based Approach to Rationale Capturing in Ship Design

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Abstract

Although reasoning by analogy is an important aspect of decision making in ship design, it limits the quality of rationale generated by designers. Practices such as the overemphasis of previously successful solutions and a predisposition toward favorite designs result in an immature and underdeveloped knowledge base. This is problematic because it prevents the application of design rationale to other ship-types. In this paper, a detailed description of a feedback mechanism for expanding the knowledge base is presented. An optimization-based approach is used to interactively steer a genetic algorithm to areas where design rationale is absent, masked or hidden. Test cases demonstrate the validity of this approach. Conclusions and areas of further research are also presented.

1. Introduction

Rationales play a crucial role in ship design and the selection process. Rationales not only advocate proper reasoning in design, they also enable naval architects to effectively communicate design decisions. Design rationales also contain a design argument, i.e., a history of the compromises and trade-offs at the core of design synthesis. In spite of their importance, they remain fiendishly hard to capture.

In a recent paper, the authors employed reactive knowledge capturing in a prototype tool, *DeNucci et al. (2009b)*. The premise of reactive knowledge capturing involves the reaction of a designer to a set of feasible ship configurations. Since a preponderance of knowledge in ship design is derived from practical experience, reactive knowledge capturing employs a series of design ‘experiences’ as an alternative to the common practice of ‘interrogating’ designers directly, e.g., surveys, questionnaires and interviews. From a set of designs, the naval architect identifies both the desirable and undesirable features present in one or more designs together with the underlying rationale, *DeNucci et al. (2009a)*. By choosing whether to accept or reject the design, the designer is triggered to express both the compromise itself and, implicitly, the design rationale.

Although preliminary testing of this approach demonstrated the successful capture of design rationale, the influence of designer experience in generating rationale was underestimated. Most importantly, it was observed that designers overemphasize the success and applicability of previous solutions. As a result, the design rationale lacks diversity, breadth and scope. This is problematic because it prevents the application of design rationale to other ship-types.

In this paper, a detailed description of a feedback mechanism for expanding the knowledge base is presented. The feedback mechanism complements the rationale capture tool by automatically generating designs most likely to ‘trigger’ design rationale. By interactively steering a genetic algorithm to areas where design rationale is absent, masked or hidden, non-existent rationale is generated. This is a preliminary step in developing a robust and mature rationale database for ship design.

2. The Influence of Designer Experience in Rationale Capturing

At the heart of design rationale is the ability to support and justify *decisions*. In practice, designers do not make decisions in isolation, i.e., they don’t view each decision as entirely new or novel. Instead, they rely upon prior knowledge, most commonly in the form of previously successful solutions and

favorite solutions, to pilot their reactions to an original design. While reasoning by analogy is an important aspect of real-world decision making, it can unfortunately limit the quality of rationale generated by reactive knowledge capturing.

2.1. Previously Successful Solutions

Designers often over-value previously successful solutions. While this can be a cost-effective approach to ship design, there are a number of practical limitations when considered in the context of rationale capturing. First, ‘one-off’ solutions absolve the designer from considering unconventional interactions, i.e., rationale, between objects in the design. As a result, the breadth of design rationale is limited. Second, designers may adopt successful solutions without knowledge of, or regard for, previous rationale. There are numerous risks associated with this approach, the most obvious being that the current circumstances and those of past events have changed. *Reinertsen (1997)* notes that instances such as these, best practice can quickly get disconnected from its intent and context. Without careful consideration of the design context, the already narrow breadth of design rationale can also have questionable value, i.e., it can be incomplete, misleading and inappropriate. This can especially be problematic when design teams have little or no experience with new a particular type or class of design and a ‘one size fits all’ mentality prevails. In both situations, the knowledge base is only supplied with limited ‘pockets’ of rationale and significant ‘gaps’ result.

2.2. Favoritism

Even when they have a large stock of experience, designers are likely to have a limited range of favorite classes that they rely on as a basis for new designs, *Gilovich (1981)*. The fundamental problem with ‘favorites’ is that designers keep going back to them, i.e., they focus on the same solutions in *every* design, while overlooking or discounting many other important features. Unfortunately, this results in the formulation of duplicate rationales for a variety of ship types, i.e., the diversity of design rationale is limited.

2.3 Impact & Implications

While the tendency to form associations with previous designs is an important aspect of decision-making, it prohibits the development of a robust and mature knowledge base, i.e., it perpetuates ‘pockets’ of incomplete and unbalanced rationales. The lack of a complete knowledge base is troublesome. At a minimum, it prevents the proper application of design rationale to other ship-types because information is missing, i.e., you are forgetting something. Relationships that have important consequences later in the design cycle are absent, resulting in large design changes, additional risk, and in some cases, system or concept failure. The solution to these problems concerns the ability to generate very specific ship configurations, which prompt the designer to fill in gaps in the rationale database.

3. Description of Feedback Mechanism

The role of designer experience described in section 2 results in a rationale database of limited utility, i.e., the database is missing information, contains many ‘gaps’ and has an over abundance of duplicate rationales. The feedback mechanism aims to solve this by generating designs that result in ‘usable’ information, i.e., the knowledge to further populate the rationale database.

3.1. Objectives of the Feedback Mechanism

The feedback mechanism controls the steering of designs to areas where design rationale is absent, masked or hidden by redefining the design, e.g., the envelope and objects of interest. The feedback mechanism supports the following objectives in the rationale capturing process:

- Generate non-existent rationales

- Refine or ‘fine-tune’ existing rationales
- Investigate targeted areas of the design and specific considerations, i.e., ‘zero’ in on specific rationales

If properly formulated, the feedback mechanism should support all three objectives without major changes to the approach. For example, generating non-existent rationale and refining existing rationale requires identical input – two objects of designer interest.

The approach taken in this research is to first address the generation of non-existent rationale. There are two reasons for this. First, the generation of non-existent rationale provides the database necessary to consider other feedback activities, e.g., it is difficult to properly refine rationale if the database is incomplete. Second, ‘triggering’ non-existent rationale is a more difficult problem because the relative positions describing the object interactions are not defined, i.e., absent.

3.2. Selecting Objects of Interest

All objects in a particular design are modelled using a three dimensional Design Structure Matrix (DSM), *DeNucci et al. (2009b)*. As illustrated in Fig.1, interactions between objects are identified in two dimensions, while the third dimension contains a data structure consisting of design rationale for the object pair. In addition to the rationale itself, the data structure also includes information regarding relevant design features, a subjective assessment of the rationale quality, e.g., truth, trend or opinion, classification of the rationale according to its type and a text-based description of preferred relative positions between the two objects of interest.

Fig.1: 3-D Design Structure Matrix

As described in the previous section, input to the feedback mechanism is a pair of objects. How are the objects selected? As the DSM is populated, the number of rationales for a pair of objects as well as an overall measure of rationale quality is calculated. To determine candidate object pairs for the feedback mechanism, the algorithm will first search for pairs of objects lacking interactions followed by object pairs with a ‘low quality’ rationale ranking. In cases where there are multiple objects lacking interactions or object pairs with similar quality rankings, larger objects (physical size) are given preference as these objects usually have the most ‘strings attached’.

3.3. ‘Triggering’ object interactions

Once an object pair is selected, a design must be generated which is likely to ‘trigger’ specific rationale. How can this be done? The authors argue that successful ‘triggering’ of object interactions, i.e., rationale, depends on the relative positions of the object pair. Therefore, the first requirement across a set of designs is to achieve a varying relative position between the two objects of interest. While relative position extremes, e.g., adjacency or maximum separation, are much more difficult to achieve in the design, they are also much more likely to trigger rationale. This is discussed in further

detail in section 4.2.1.

While the relative position of the object pair varies, what happens to everything else, i.e., all the other objects in the design? In order to keep rationale generation focused on the object pair, all other objects must remain in the same general position across all designs. If too many objects change position, interactions between these objects are identified instead of between the object pair. Therefore, the second requirement across a set of designs is to keep all other objects in nearly identical positions. This is discussed in further detail in section 4.2.2.

In summary our goal is to produce designs with a *diverse* set of relative positions for the objects of interest, but nearly *identical* relative positions for all other objects.

4. Interactive Redefinition of Designs

4.1. Approach

There are numerous ways to redefine computer-generated designs. Two approaches considered for this paper are sequencing and optimization. In sequencing, the order of object placement can be changed to achieve preferred object proximity. While this is an acceptable approach, it presents important drawbacks. First, the overall execution time of the sequencing approach is slower because the system definition file must be reformulated for every different object pair considered, i.e., objects must be reordered. Second, reformulation of the system definition file also influences topside shape. This could bear unintended consequences when trying to achieve identical relative positions for all other objects in the design. Last, development of sequencing code would require either adaptation of a sequenced-based allocation approach, e.g., kernels from *Nick (2008)*, or major revisions to the space allocation code currently employed at TU Delft, *Van Oers (2009)*. By way of comparison, optimization employs a fixed order of object placement but achieves desired relative positions by means of objective functions. Although optimization theoretically generates designs faster than sequencing, it may require a greater number of designs, i.e., more time, to achieve the desired object proximities. In spite of this, optimization was initially chosen over sequencing because of the low developmental costs and relatively quick speed at which designs can be generated. If it turns out to be too slow for rationale capturing purposes, other approaches such as sequencing must be considered further.

Using optimization, the relative positions of the object pair can be controlled using the methods listed below in Table I.

Table I: Comparison of Position Control Approaches

	Advantages	Disadvantages
Logical Operators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relatively quick 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Require system redefinition • Require additional user knowledge • Not transparent
Constraints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transparent • No system redefinition required 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not reusable • Contradictory • Require additional computing time • Discard useful design information
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transparent • No system redefinition required • Reusable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Never complete

While each method has advantages and disadvantages, Table I illustrates that the advantages of objective functions far outweigh their disadvantages. Their primary disadvantage, the fact that they are never complete, is mitigated by the fact that they are not used to evaluate the entire ship, but rather

relative positions between objects.

4.2. Objective Functions

In order to control changes in position, we must be able to measure changes in position. Therefore, the objectives developed in this section measure the change in position between two objects of interest and measure the changes in position of all other objects. Since positions are being evaluated across a range of designs, they must first be normalized to account for differences in hull length and the overall height of the ship.

4.2.1. Object Proximity

Object proximity refers to the relative distance between two objects of interest. It describes whether objects are adjacent, separate or located at some distance between these extreme values. To calculate the object proximity objective, object reference points and mathematical formulation for distance must be determined.

The reference point is the location from which distances are calculated. In this paper, the geometric center of an object is used as its reference point. Simpler definitions of the reference point, e.g., forward-most position, often discount the compartment geometry and result in inappropriate results. For example, since most objects are longer than they are tall, a forward-most reference position results in objects stacked on top of one another to minimize proximity between them. This is especially obvious in designs where objects are loosely packed and there are many opportunities for objects to be positioned on top of each other. Alternatively, a proximity measurement taking into account the closest points between objects could also be used.

The two most useful formulations for distance are the ‘Euclidean distance’ and ‘Manhattan distance.’ Shown in Eq.1, the Euclidean distance describes the absolute distance between two reference points and is useful for describing object interactions describing noise or vibrations. The Manhattan distance or ‘city block’ distance, Eq.2, takes the travel path into consideration. This is useful for problems such as logistics efforts or personnel movement. Note that there can be appreciable differences between these two values, especially in designs with unconventional topside shape or multiple-superstructures.

$$\text{Euclidean Distance} = \sqrt{\Delta x^2 + \Delta y^2} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Manhattan Distance} = \Delta x + \Delta y \quad (2)$$

Ultimately, the proper formulation of distance is dependent on the specific functionality of the objects being considered, e.g., interactions between accommodation spaces and an evacuation vehicle should likely be formulated as Manhattan distance. Unfortunately, this knowledge is not available up-front. Therefore, we assume the more applicable Euclidean distance formulation in this paper. In addition, since the model used in this paper also lacks passageways, the Manhattan distance would only be approximate at best.

There are numerous reasons for formulating the proximity objective as a minimization problem. First, achieving a minimum distance between a pair of objects is much more difficult than achieving some *other* distance, i.e., only four locations around a compartment can be achieve ‘adjacency’ while many others can be achieve ‘separation’. While this is true in a general sense, minimum distances are even more difficult to attain when objects have additional requirements, e.g., placement on the keel. Second, the formulation of object proximity as a minimization problem describes a greater number of object interactions, e.g., separation only pertains to a limited number of object interactions such as hazard areas, vibrations or transport effort. Third, although a minimum distance and a maximum distance are the inverse of each other, anecdotal evidence suggests it is much easier to identify and recognize interactions between objects in close proximity to one another.

4.2.2. Object Placement Similarity

To calculate changes in the positions of all other objects, a baseline design containing original positions is either selected by the designer, e.g., a previously saved design, or chosen by the genetic algorithm, e.g., first feasible design in the population. While the source of the baseline design is irrelevant, the amount of design data, e.g., coefficients describing relative positions, transferred to the genetic algorithm have an important impact on how quickly designs converge. This will be discussed further in section 5.

To properly ‘trigger’ the designer, designs with a preponderance of *identical* positions are preferred over a larger number of objects in *nearly similar* positions. Therefore, the average change in distance between all objects in a design and the original baseline positions is a far too simplistic approach. In this formulation, designs that do not achieve identical object placement are not penalized. For example, consider Table II which shows hypothetical position differences between 4 objects (A,B,C,D) across 5 different designs.

Table II: Merit Calculation using Averages

	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5
$\Delta A_{1,2}$	4	0	0	0	0
$\Delta B_{1,2}$	4	0	0	0	4
$\Delta C_{1,2}$	4	0	4	12	8
$\Delta D_{1,2}$	4	16	12	4	4
$\frac{\Sigma(\Delta pos)}{\# \text{ obj.}}$	4	4	4	4	4

In spite of the fact that some designs match the baseline design positions better than others, e.g., in design #2 three of the four objects are *identical* position matches, all the designs receive the same objective score. In addition, the sequence of object placement is also disregarded, e.g., design #3 and design #4 receive the same objective score even though the change in the position of the third object placed, object C, is different.

While a variety of other formulations were considered, e.g., penalty for designs based on the number of non-matching positions, the majority of them introduced additional issues. In the end, we decided on a weighted priority method. This methodology not only gives preference to identical position matches, but also places a emphasis on sequence, so that objects placed earlier in the space allocation routine (where a larger position space is available) have more weight than those placed later.

To do this, a distance-based model for horizontal and vertical changes in position is used to minimize the change in positions of all other objects. Eq.(3) to Eq.(5) show the model. Parameters Δd_H and Δd_V represent the horizontal and vertical changes in position between an object in the baseline design and the same object in a newly generated design. As mentioned previously, normalized relative positions are used. Note that the object pair is removed from the calculation (n-2).

$$\text{Change in Position} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (\Delta d_H + \Delta d_V)(n - i + 1)}{\sum i} \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta d_H = |b_{ix} - a_{ix}| \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta d_V = |b_{iy} - a_{iy}| \quad (5)$$

for $i = 1, \dots, n-2$

New objective scores for the designs considered in Table II are calculated in Table III using Eq.(3) through Eq.(5). Preference for identical matches and sequence are realized in this formulation.

Table III: Merit Calculation using Weight Priority Formulation

	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5	Priority
$\Delta A_{1,2}$	4	0	0	0	0	4
$\Delta B_{1,2}$	4	0	0	0	4	3
$\Delta C_{1,2}$	4	0	4	12	8	2
$\Delta D_{1,2}$	4	16	12	4	4	1
Eq.(3)	4	1.6	2	2.8	3.2	

4.3. Feasibility & the Issue of Constraints

While an optimization approach using objective functions is used to solve this problem, constraints are still required to generate ‘feasible’ designs – or are they? The answer to this question depends on the definition of a ‘feasible’ design for rationale capturing purposes. Unfortunately, this is most likely a matter of preference and will vary from designer to designer. While constraints such as freeboard or initial stability are not overtly required for rationale capturing, the fact that rationale was generated from ‘feasible’ designs might be useful and make acceptance of design rationale easier. In addition to a check that ensures all objects are successfully placed within the design, additional constraints such as minimum freeboard, center of gravity and packing density are used in this paper.

4.4. Validation Procedure

The space proximity objective function was checked using both visual and computational test cases. Object placement similarity between a baseline design and newly generated design was validated using a series of test cases that employed a limited number of objects. The nearly identical positioning of objects between two different designs is shown as Fig.2.

Fig.2: Simple test case validation of design similarity objective

Although these simple test cases validated the objective functions formulated in 4.2.1. and 4.2.2., they did not validate the overall approach as the reduced number of objects offered ample posing space to achieve minimum proximity and similar object placement. In cases such as these, i.e., low packing densities, the relationship between the objective functions is only weakly Pareto optimal, i.e., one objective remains constant while the other objective declines.

5. Results

5.1. Ship Model

The test cases described in this paper are based on a model of the U.S. Coast Guard National Security Cutter and use a 2.5-D version of the space allocation routine, *DeNucci et al. (2009b)*. In this

approach, a simple arrangement of objects in the transverse direction is assumed, thereby saving computational effort required for steering. A comprehensive overview of the space allocation routine appears in *Van Oers et al. (2009)*.

In this model, 130 objects are positioned, resulting in 262 independent variables. Of these objects, 8 tanks are constrained to positions near the keel of the ship. Other objects requiring constraints, e.g., aft slipway for a rigid hull inflatable boat and minor weapon systems, e.g., 12mm weapons have been excluded from this model. Fig.3 shows the model of the USCG National Security Cutter. As evident in Fig.3, objects have been collapsed along a centerline plane to eliminate the computational effort associated with transverse direction positioning. As mentioned previously, there are limited constraints on the placement of objects, as the overall goal remains to ‘trigger’ the likes and dislikes of the designer.

Fig.3: Model of USCG National Security Cutter

5.2. Full Case Test Results

As series of full ship test cases were performed. In these cases, a previously saved design was used as the baseline, i.e., the object positions in the baseline design were compared to those generated by the genetic algorithm to evaluate similarity. An example of one test case result is shown as Fig.4. While reasonably similar designs were achieved using the optimization approach, two practical problems surfaced.

First, it takes a substantial amount of time to achieve object placement similarity, e.g., upwards to 500 generations. Yet, after careful consideration, this should be expected. Since the genetic algorithm has no previous knowledge of the baseline design, e.g., object positions, many generations of designs are required to randomly match 262 variables. Unfortunately, the time required to generate this number of designs is unacceptable for rationale capturing, i.e., it takes too long! To solve this issue, two approaches could be employed. First, instead of reading in the baseline design from an external source, the first feasible design generated by the genetic algorithm could become the baseline design. In this way, the chromosome (262 variables) of a matching design can at least be passed to the child populations of design, thereby increasing the probability of similar designs. Second, the initial population could be ‘seeded’ or transplanted with position data from the original design. This not only achieves a greater probability of similar designs in the children populations, but also offers options to control the convergence speed by varying the amount of design data transferred to the child population.

Second, there is an imbalance in the objective functions. The first objective function consists of the relative positions of just two objects, while the second objective function contains the summation of over 250 object positions. This results in the genetic algorithm spending a majority of computational effort minimizing the first objective because it is far easier to achieve. The desired spread across relative positions of the object pair is missing. In simple designs, with a relatively balanced number of relative position considerations, e.g., Fig.2, a balanced and equally spaced Pareto front results, but for larger, i.e., realistic designs, it is much more difficult. One solution may be to reformulate this as single objective problem. Alternatively it could also be combined into a min-min/max-min optimization problem. Detailed solutions to both of these problems are presented next.

Fig.4: Results using previously saved baseline design

5.3 Baseline Design Selection

Although assigning the first ‘feasible’ design as the baseline design would achieve acceptable convergence speeds, a saved or external design is likely to produce more useful rationale. For example, if the baseline design is ‘random’ and ‘new’ it is likely that the designer will focus on other aspects of the design, e.g., favorites, not the object pair in question. One solution to this would be to use a design the user has already commented on, thereby minimizing the tendency to repeat already captured rationale. Another solution would be to present the designer with multiple competing designs of limited objects from which he or she can select a favorite design. In either case, an external design is used as the baseline design.

Therefore the code was modified to accept and seed the genetic algorithm with an external design. Fig.5 shows the results of the seeding process. In this case, a partial chromosome describing the initial position of each object in the design was seeded in the initial population. After only 20 generations, the Pareto plots converged and reasonably similar designs were achieved. A seeding approach also lays the foundation to explore additional designs along the Pareto front or allows for additional generation of new designs near a specified point in the design space.

During the analysis of test case designs, two other factors influencing the convergence rate of the Pareto plots were also observed.

- Location in Packing Sequence: Although a byproduct of the optimization approach, for tightly packed designs, objects that occur later in the packing sequence have fewer available positions for placement. Therefore, it can take longer to achieve the desired proximity between the object pair.
- Type of Object: Hard objects, e.g., propulsion objects, flight deck, cannot undergo shape changes during the packing process. Soft objects, e.g., accommodation spaces, are allowed to change shape in accordance with defined rules. When trying to minimize the distance

between objects, it is most difficult to minimize distances between hard/hard objects, followed by soft/hard objects, hard/soft objects, and finally soft/soft objects.

Fig.5: Seeding initial population with baseline design

5.4 Min-Min / Max-Min Problem

As described in section 5.2, the objective functions are imbalanced. When minimizing proximity distance between two objects and the change in all other object positions, the Pareto front collapses and single point minimums are obtained. Although these designs represent minimum proximity distances between object pairs, they don't achieve the desired diversity required in section 3.3. This could be solved in two ways.

First, the approach could be reformulated as a single objective problem. For example, the proximity objective for the object pair could be assigned a constant value and the change in all other object positions could be minimized. Unfortunately, this is rather difficult because one must ensure that the relative position for the object pair maintains a constant relative position. This not only requires the inverse scaling of normalized distance to initial position coefficients (variables), it also requires that the area is available in the positioning space for allocation. While sequencing would eliminate some of the problems with the latter issue, it would still suffer from the limitations identified in section 4.1.

Instead, the problem is reformulated as a combined min-min problem *and* a max-min problem. This approach not only explicitly supports 'triggering' of rationale by object separation, but also includes the ability to refine rationale based on separation distances. Although the code must be executed twice in order to achieve the proper Pareto plot, the overall computing time may be shorter as less time is spent minimizing areas of little interest. An additional Pareto front check is also required to ensure that the largest separation distance in the min-min problem is less than the smallest separation

distance in the max-min problem. If not, new Pareto fronts must be sorted out from the combined plots. Fig.6 shows an example of a combined min-min and max-min problem.

Fig.6: Combination of Min-Min and Max-Min Problem

The rightmost plot in Fig.6 illustrates the goal stated in section 3.3; to produce designs with a *diverse* set of relative positions for the objects of interest, but nearly *identical* relative positions for all other objects.

5.5 Performance

One of the practical requirements of a rationale capture tool is that it must quickly generate and steer designs – otherwise designers, whose time is already at premium, become disinterested and bored with the overall reactive capturing approach. The optimization-based feedback mechanism presented in this paper appears to satisfy these speed criteria. With the space allocation routine handled by a parallel processor, each four-constraint design described in section 4.3 takes approximately 0.55 seconds to generate. With this formulation, the average number of ‘feasible’ designs is approximately 26.5%. By reducing the number of constraints and limiting the amount of design visualization between generations, an additional 25% savings in computation time and can also be realized.

6. Conclusions & future research

6.1. Conclusions

A methodology for controlling object position changes in a design was presented. The approach was motivated by the observations that:

- Designers employ past experience in formulating design rationale
- Designers overuse and overemphasize reasoning by analogy and favorites
- An incomplete rationale database results

These problems were resolved by:

- Employing an optimization based approach to steer designs to areas where design rationale is absent, masked or hidden
- Seeding the genetic algorithm with external baseline designs to reduce computation time and design distractions
- Using a combined min-min and max-min approach to achieve object proximity diversity

The designs generated by this approach illustrate that diversity in the relative position of an object pair can be achieved while holding the position of all other objects nearly constant.

6.2. Future Research

- Continue researching the role of designer experience in rationale capturing. Develop additional steering routines and objective functions that mitigate designer bias in reactive knowledge capturing.
- Incorporate the approach presented in this paper in the prototype rationale capture tool.
- Use the prototype tool to collect design rationale from naval architects. Evaluate the effectiveness and usability of the tool.
- Develop an ontology for ship design rationale.

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Improvement of Interoperability between Yards and Equipment Suppliers

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Abstract

In accordance with the majority of the German shipyards and shipbuilding suppliers, FLENSBURGER and CADENAS during the last two years have been developing a 3D-equipment catalogue. This catalogue enables customers to integrate 3D-Models of equipment directly into almost all used 3D-CAD Systems, in native format. This way yards are able to speed up their design process in early design stages and to achieve secured results, which becomes especially important for building highly specialized ships.

1. Ship Design Today

For more than 15 years now, 3D-CAD systems are used in engineering offices for the design of ships, in the first time mainly for steel design but already for many years now to a high intense in the equipment and arrangement design, for pipe construction and mechanical engineering. In the meantime, a nearly entire 3D-model of the ship (Fig.1) is available for the coordination of all design departments of the shipyards. Also most of the shipbuilding suppliers work with 3D-CAD systems. While the supplying industry works almost exclusively with mechanical engineering CAD systems, most shipyards use design tools which have their roots in the plant industry.

On both sides there are very heterogeneous CAD environments, in particular on the yards there is a big variety of used CAD programs. For different reasons a standardization of these CAD systems is neither realistic nor in view or intended.

Fig.1: Fully equipped ROPAX-Ferry

2. CAD Catalogues and Modelling

Every shipyard and every CAD-system has a large catalogue of components, armatures and pipe components. Depending on the time, the respective programs have been in use, the catalogues are more or less complete. On a shipyard like Flensburger, approx. 50,000 components with a value of 100 million Euro are supplied per year and also integrated into the CAD programs. This corresponds in general to 72-85% of the ship costs. Even though on shipyards there already exist extensive catalogues in CAD programs, it is necessary for the yards to perform a considerable effort on modelling, e.g. if suppliers have to be changed, if components have to be modified or if project specific supply parts have to be verified. On a yard with one new design per year, some 2.000-3.000 components need to be modelled anew or to be modified. The average amount of 3-5 work hours per component adds up to 3-5 man years. These relate to a shipyard with a very complete and sophisticated catalogue; otherwise the amount of work can be considerably more, particularly if the yard changes to another ship type.

3. Significance of Early Modelling

In an early design phase, it is very important to reserve the space needed for the most important components in order to guarantee the function of the ship, e.g. the main machinery. Many 3D-models are already required in a very early design phase. Because of the world market situation all European shipyards are forced to build highly specialized ships and ships as one-offs or in very small series. It is decisive to be able to calculate the risks of the design for high specialized ships at a very early stage; otherwise the risks for the yards are too high. While a considerable amount of work for modelling in an early design phase cannot be done, as it is extremely time consuming, time for modelling is more acceptable at a later detailed design phase.

4. Data Exchange between Shipyards and Suppliers

Many suppliers are able to provide their customers with 3D-models of their products. Because of the variety of used CAD systems, often data exchange of components, between shipyards and suppliers is carried out with neutral interfaces and formats (STEP, Acis, Parasolid, 3D-DXF, JT). Nevertheless, the result is mostly not satisfying. The file size is usually far too huge, the models are often transferred with too many details, contours are mostly transferred tessellated and there might occur lots of quality problems. Important attributes and metadata are normally missing.

5. Data Exchange in proprietary Format

For quite some years now catalogues of the company CADENAS are used increasingly in machinery CAD-systems. With help of this catalogues it is possible to import norm parts and other small parts in proprietary formats of the respective systems. On account of many advantages electric catalogues have asserted themselves in mechanical engineering very fast and have become an important tool for all designers. Since we have noticed this development in mechanical systems, we met with CADENAS in 2007 and discussed how e-catalogues can be established also for components of the shipbuilding industry. As a result of this meeting, CADENAS and the involved CAD manufacturers have developed interfaces to be able to take over CADENAS catalogue parts in the propriety formats of the shipbuilding CAD systems. In the meantime it became possible to import CADENAS catalogue parts in AVEVA MARINE, NUPAS-CADMATIC, CATIA, Siemens / UG NX, TRIBON, PRO / E. Currently interfaces to INTERGRAPH and FORAN are also under development.

6. Pilot projects

In addition to the development of interfaces, there have been initiated pilot projects with three suppliers. These suppliers are very different. MAN Diesel, HATLAPA and SCHOENROCK cover a very wide range of different vendors and therefore have an extreme range of requirements to an e-catalogue as well. While MAN engine models (Fig.2) are very complex, detailed and large,

Fig. 2: Main engine as e-catalogue model

Fig.3: Compressor as early design product model

HATLAPA models (Fig.3) are more common as they are of a typical size. SCHOENROCK (Fig.4) represents smaller vendors with smaller requirements in CAD in-house design. Via an e-catalogue, companies like SCHOENROCK will be able to provide their customers with detailed information about their products and nice 3D product data models.

Fig.4: Detailed configurable watertight sliding door

7. Catalogue Details

The e-catalogue (Fig.5) does not work with fixed geometry of the models, but models are defined by a set of rules and parameters. The models are only defined by primitive bodies. These are the requirements to export the model in a lot of different native CAD formats without loss of data and "on the fly". These models are very small. Another advantage is that these models can be configured simply. Through simple variation of parameters it is easy to create whole product families of components and to simply transfer the models into native formats in different CAD systems. Besides, the so created and centrally held e-catalogue data bank models only exist of the wrapped geometry of the outer shell of the models. But they are added with useful information like connection points and other required attribute information. On this way it is possible to transfer useful information from suppliers to shipyards and the models are small and well manageable. The usual file size of a main engine in neutral STEP format is about > 20 MB, i.e. as AVEVA macro out of the CADENAS catalogue the file size of the main engine is only 2.5 MB, but with a lot of more useful information. Also the level of details can be changed, influenced by parameters before importing the model. The models are simplified and exist mainly of the outer contour, which is a big advantage for the suppliers, because their competitors get no detailed information and therefore no copies are possible for them. No additional data converters are necessary for the suppliers and many discussions and arrangements about data exchange can be cancelled. Additional data, technical data sheets, assembly information and documentation can also be handed over this way.

Fig.5: Selection and configuration of e-catalogue product data

8. Advantages for Suppliers

Through a well configured e-catalogue suppliers are able to give customers a good overview about their product range and allow them to get models which are technically useful and are deliverable. With help of a worldwide shipbuilding portal it opens new markets for the suppliers and they are able to get additional customers. It makes them able to increase their image and open new distribution channels. Furthermore suppliers can offer customers an own e-catalogue with multi CAD download functions (Fig.6), in the company's individual graphic layout, on their own website as a free after-sales service.

9. Advantages for Shipyards

For the shipyards the catalogue means an important improvement in the possibility to build individual ships because of earlier and more complete 3D models of the ship. At time being each component of a supplier is modelled several times at different yards with the risk of failures in the model. This problem can be solved by an e-catalogue and the possibility to get models in the proprietary format of the CAD systems.

Fig.6: Presentation of main engine

10. Support by VSM and VDMA (associations)

Along with the technical developments, the initiative was coordinated with most of the important German shipyards and the associations VSM and VDMA. The initiative is widely supported from all sides. At present the activities are continued to add suppliers to the e-catalogue, adding values for all participants.

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Combining the Design Building Block and Library Based Approaches to improve Exploration during Initial Design

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Abstract

University College London (UCL)'s Marine Research Group has proposed two approaches to ship concept design, the Design Building Block approach and the Library based approach. The Design Building Block approach provides an integrated model that allows the designer to explore both the configuration and numerical aspects of a design. This model allows the designer to explore innovative design solutions. In comparison, the Library based approach utilises a large library of options to provide the designer with information on acceptable alternatives given a set of requirements or constraints. This paper explore combining these two approaches to provide a tool that allows the designer to better address the import task of requirement elucidation, shaping both the customer's needs and the designer's initial solutions during the concept stage of the ship design process. The paper first introduces the Design Building Block and Library based approaches via one example showing an application of each approach. The paper then discusses the advantage arising from a combination of the approaches and shows how a combined tool could assist the designer in the initial exploratory stage of the ship design process. While the combination of these two approaches appears to be promising, further research is necessary to explore appropriate mechanisms for integration and applicability to wider design problems.

1. Introduction

The early stage of the ship design process presents the designer with an opportunity to explore radical alternatives that could satisfy the needs of the customer, the requirement owner and users. However, current design approaches and tools do not satisfy the range and depth of solution exploration in elucidating the true requirements (Andrews 2003a). This paper explores the potential for a synthesis between two alternative approaches, both develop at UCL.

2. The need for a wider exploration in initial ship design

The issue in the initial design of complex ships, such as naval combatants, is that the exploration should be as wide as possible, so that all conceivable options are explored and the emergent requirements are "elucidated" from this comprehensive exploration which, importantly, informs the dialogue between the requirements owner and the concept ship designer (Andrews, 2003a).

While there have been numerous design approaches proposed to address the initial design phases (e.g.. the twenty six approaches to modelling the ship design process identified by the first author in Andrews *et. al.* (2009)), these approaches often fail to provide a designer with the means to rapidly explore the consequences of emergent design issues or requirements. Broad investigations of alternative options are currently undertaken, at best, by a separate investigation or exploration through distinct synthesis modelling of each alternative. In initial design this is seen to be problematic in that, either, such a comprehensive exploration is rejected, as being inefficient in the timescale this demands, or, worse, is not even addressed. This then means that the initial concept exploration is restricted, with potential solutions unconsidered, and the elucidation of the requirements is narrow, leading to downstream vulnerabilities in requirement justification and project approval processes.

Current design methods restrict the designer's ability to conduct rapid and broad explorations in the early stages of the ship design process. However, the extent of this restriction varies between methods. Some, such as the traditional numerical ship synthesis and the UCL Design Building Block

(DBB) approach, are restricted by the inherent limits of human cognitive speed to consider more than one ship design type at a time. Whereas those relying on numeric selection processes (such as expert systems, neural networks and genetic algorithms, which use objectives and constraints to find a 'best' solution) are restricted by the simplistic manner in which they represent aspects where considerable human input is necessary to identify an acceptable solution (e.g. appreciation of variations in ship configuration). The first author has identified initial ship design methods as being in two categories – termed "glass and black box", respectively (*Andrews, 1994*). Thus glass box methods allow the designer to gain a detailed understanding of the driving factors in the design, highly desirable for requirement elucidation and in identifying design drivers early. However, glass box design methods are often not amenable to automation and hence cannot be used to rapidly assess a large number of options. This can curtail the designer's ability to explore a large number of solutions and to develop understanding, in contrast to finding a single 'best' solution or obtaining a high degree of insight regarding a single specific 'detailed' solution. A design method able to explore a large number of potential designs but which does not remove the designer from control over option choice is desirable.

Given the importance of the designer fully exploring potential options, as part of the concept phase of the ship design process, there remains a difficulty in that the number of options the designer can explore is always going to be limited by design imperatives (i.e. manpower, time and funds). The process of requirement elucidation, as the driving motivation in early ship design, adds a further complication. If, as a necessary part of a comprehensive early design process, the designer is also to consider different styles – with widely varying characteristics and performance – then the need to find a quicker manner to undertake a wide exploration of options becomes more challenging. Current ship design methods fail to provide a tool that adequately addresses this issue. This is due to the fundamentally solution centric approach that they adopt, typified by the following broad scheme: take inputs, develop a whole ship solution, evaluate performance, and then iterate by adjusting the inputs. This approach is not suited to the exploratory phase of the design process where designers wish to develop their understanding of the potential solution space. Furthermore, additional requirements are likely to radically change the solution space, so the wider the exploration the more robust the concept design process needs to be.

At this point it is useful to consider what features ship designers have previously requested in a concept design tool. *Betts (2000)* provides a useful checklist for potential warship design tools, while *Andrews (2003b)* considers there to be five features required to be exhibited in the outcome of any approach to preliminary ship design, if this is to meet the demands of requirement elucidation:-

1. "Believable solutions, meaning ones that are both technically balanced and descriptive;
2. Coherent solutions, meaning that the dialogue with the customer should be more than merely a focus on numerical measures of performance and cost, and should include visual representation;
3. Open methods, in that they are responsive to the issues that matter to the customer or are capable of being elucidated from the customer or from user teams;
4. Revelatory, so likely design drivers are identified early in the design process to aid effective design exploration;
5. Creative, in that options are not closed down by the design method and tool but rather alternatives are fostered."

This can be used as a benchmark in judging whether a proposed early design approach is attractive in meeting the designer's needs. An approach able to fully support the exploratory phase of the ship design process will assist the designer in understanding the customer's needs. It should capture the impact of emerging requirements on possible solutions and not unduly constrain the designer to a limited selection of alternatives. It must be sufficiently flexible to allow the addition of new information by the designer, as it becomes available. It should aim to fulfil the above list of creative ship design system features. Finally, the method should strive to support the full range of ship design from simple batch development through to radically new configurations and technologies (*Andrews, 1998*).

3.1.1. A process for employing the Design Building Block approach

A description of a process for utilising the Design Building Block approach in the preliminary design of ships is presented in (Pawling, 2007). This is derived from a variety of design studies conducted at UCL (Andrews, 1986; Dicks, 1999; Pawling, 2001). These studies extended across both a variety of ship roles and a wide range of hullforms (e.g. monohull, trimaran, SWATH). While the detail procedures used in each of the studies varied, given the nature of the design model and objectives for each of the studies were different, this meant that a common detailed procedure was found to be impractical. However, it was possible produce a generic illustrative sequence for progression of a design using the DBB approach, Fig. 2.

The early variants developed in the Major Features Design Stage (MFDS) represent significantly different overall layout configurations, which are not developed to a high level of detail and are, therefore, akin to rough sketches. One of these layouts is then taken forward to the Super Building Block Design Stage (SBBDS). However, as shown by the dotted arrows, it is also possible to develop several variants to a higher level of detail, (some UCL design studies have demonstrated this approach (Andrews and Pawling, 2004)). Given that the process of design is iterative, feedback mechanisms exist not only within the processes of comparison and selection, but also between the stages of design development, allowing information to be fed back into an earlier stage, as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig.2: Progress of a design using the Design Building Block approach (Pawling, 2007)

Pawling (2007) also highlights the perceived advantages that arise from integrating numerical models and methods able to explore a set of options. These tools could be employed to reveal the nature of the possible solution space, for each of the major options or variants. This would allow assessment of the design topology selected and reduce the pre-determination of the design form, identified as a potential problem with the application of the Design Building Block approach (*Dicks [1999]*). For example, if a large set of options were to be produced, for each variant the designer develops, then feedback could be improved. The DBB approach could be of great assistance in this respect, due to the enhanced understanding of the design provided by the interactive graphical display. This could then lead to a common environment for improved communication between all parties involved in the design evaluation process.

3.2 The Library based ship concept design approach

McDonald and Andrews (2009) presented the UCL Library Based approach to initial ship design. This approach is based upon a limited library of possible options describing a large number of ship designs, which the designer can rapidly filter to find options that satisfy the current design requirements. The initial library must be broad enough to contain an array of options that will be of interest to the designer. To prevent the number of options within the library growing to an unmanageable size, a process of decomposition and down selection is applied to reduce the number of options that must be stored within the library. If a ship option is decomposed into a number of sub-options then these can be stored in place of whole ship options. The Library based approach decomposes options into the same functional categories as used by the DBB approach: Float; Move; Fight (in the case of a naval combatant) or Operations (in the case of a commercial ship with a cargo or service function); and, Infrastructure. The sub-options have then to be combined to produce a larger set of possible whole ship options, which have been termed ‘combined options’ (*McDonald and Andrews, 2009*).

The options from the library could be filtered via a number of different search mechanisms, such as those employed within database tools (*Atzeni et al., 1999*). The power and speed of current search techniques should be familiar to any user of Internet search engines. By assessing the options pre-calculated characteristics and performance a rapid down selection process can be easily implemented. Furthermore, if part of this down selection process occurs at a sub-option level, by making use of an appropriate subset of the requirements, this will significantly reduce the number of combined options that need to be considered. The possible combinations of remaining sub-options could then be used to produce a set of combined options. Finally, the set of combined options, which meet the overall constraints and requirements, can be found.

Fig. 3 summarises the library based approach. Fig. 3(a) shows the sub-options for the three functional groups (S_F , S_M , S_I) that are stored within the library. These sub-options are assessed against appropriate subsets of the ship requirements (R_F for the Float options, R_M for the Move options and R_I for the Infrastructure options), with those that fail to meet given thresholds of performance being removed from consideration. The subsets of the requirements differ between the functional groups (e.g. Float sub-option removed by requirements such as upper deck length to accommodate the combat system equipment). Such a weeding out process would then result in three sets of acceptable sub-options S'_F , S'_M , S'_I (Fig. 3(b)). A suitable mapping (*McDonald and Andrews, 2009*) allows the three sets of sub-options to be combined into a new set of combined ship options that initially exclude the demands of the operational items, $S_{(S-O)}$ (Fig. 3(c)). The remaining requirements can then be used to delete the unacceptable options from the set of combined ship options excluding the $S_{(S-O)}$ demands. This would include both those requirements originating from the demands of the Operations functional group R_O (e.g. available internal volume for ‘payload’) and those ship requirements R_S that encompass other customer needs and span several functional groups (e.g. maximum speed requirement). To assess some of these requirements performance prediction methods may need to be employed to predict values not stored within the Library or account for major interactions between sub-options. These values could be found using a fast calculating method (*Maroju et al, 2007*). This will result in the final set of acceptable combined ship options that can accommodate the payload S'_S (Fig. 3(d)). This collection of options would then be presented to the designer.

Fig.3: Option Exploration Process Based on a Set of Functional Ship Sub-Options

3.2.1. Presentation of Library based Synthesis

This section briefly outlines a demonstration of the library based ship concept design approach. This employs a database backed object-oriented programming approach to rapidly explore options representing a range of alternatives stored in a library by using a set of requirements selected from a recent actual naval ship design programme. Adopting a database storage system enables the down selection process to make use of the database's rapid search and query capabilities. Items returned by the database can then be realised as instances of objects within the implementation. This specific implementation is built using a number of different objects that act together to create a data model able to perform the key tasks, which underlie the approach as outlined in the previous sub-section. The seven primary types of objects that make up the improved implementation are:

- Items;
- Characteristics;
- Values;
- Conditions;
- Functions;
- Styles;
- Characteristic Types.

Fig.4: Key Objects within the Library

These seven object types are illustrated in Fig. 4. This shows each object's attributes (the variables stored within the object) and the relationships the object has to other objects in the Library. A line terminating with two single arrows denotes a one-to-one relationship. A line terminating in one single arrow and one double arrow denotes a one-to-many relationship. Finally, a line terminating in two double arrows denotes a many-to-many relationship. For example, an Item object may contain relationships linking it to a number of Characteristic objects while each Characteristic object can only be related to a single Item object, this relationship can be defined as a one-to-many relationship. This

description of the objects with relationships allows the objects within the Library to be mapped to a relational database structure, which allows storage and rapid retrieval, for a given set of constraints.

The process of searching the Library for appropriate options and combining these to form new options, which are then presented to the designer, is performed by several actions. Actions are split into two types: Fetch Actions that retrieve Item objects from the library and Combine Actions that generate new options by combining sub-options belonging to a number of input actions. These two types can be combined into a hierarchical tree of Actions with Combine Actions as branches and Fetch Actions as leaves, Fig. 5. This differs from the iconic representation, Fig. 3, as a two stage combination process, is employed to develop combined Float-Move options and then combined Float-Move-Infrastructure options.

Fig.5: Hierarchical tree of fetch and combine actions for improved implementation of library method

3.2.2. An example method demonstrating the Library based approach

Before the Library based approach can be used to explore a set of options the library must be populated with data. In this case Float, Move and Infrastructure sub-options were developed then stored in the library. The tools used to synthesise the sub-options will not be described in detail here, however a brief description of aspects, identified as being key to each Float sub-option, is provided below showing the data incorporated into each sub-option:

- Generation of the hullform geometry;
- Resistance and propulsive power requirements;
- Weight and volume estimation of items within the Float functional group;
- Intact stability analysis for large angles against appropriate standards;
- Seakeeping performance in head seas.

Fig.6: The Three Styles Explored for the Float Sub-Options

Table I: Extract from the Set of Functions and Requirements from LCS Programme (*US Navy, 2003*)

Function	Threshold Requirement
Float	Draught < 6.10 meters
Infrastructure	Max Accommodation < 75
Combined Float–Move	Range > 1000 nautical miles at 40 Knots
Combined Float–Move	Range > 3500 nautical miles at 22 Knots
Combined Float–Move	Maximum Speed ≥ 40 Knots
Combined Float–Move–Infrastructure	Crew available ≥ Crew demand
Combined Float–Move–Infrastructure	Total cost (excluding payload) ≤ £66M

Fig.7: Max. length vs. total displacement for all float sub-options in the three example hullform styles

Sub-options were developed for monohull, catamaran and trimaran hullform styles, with representative image shown in Fig. 6. Using this tool 3787 sub-options were developed, comprising 1458 monohull, 1080 catamaran and 1249 trimaran sub-options, respectively. All 3787 Float sub-options are plotted in Fig. 7 to demonstrate the wide range of solutions that were generated.

The design study that occurred as part of the US Navy's LCS programme (*Long and Johnson, 2003*) was seen to provide a suitable test case. The set of requirements in Table I are based upon those defined at the start of the US Navy LCS design competition. Several of these requirements were not explicitly defined in the original LCS requirement (*US Navy, 2003*). Using the threshold requirements defined in Table I the following down selection and combination Actions were implemented (more extensive details of these steps is provided in (*McDonald and Andrews, 2010*)):

- **Action A - Float Sub-Options Down Selection:** The initial library contained 3787 Float sub-options. Requirements were applied to down select these sub-options until 2964 Float sub-options remained.
- **Action B - Move Sub-Options Down Selection:** As with Action A the 2560 Move sub-options stored in the Library were down selected to 585 acceptable Move sub-options;
- **Action C – Infrastructure Sub-Options Down Selection:** As with Actions A and B the 583 Infrastructure sub-options stored in the Library were down selected to 205 acceptable Infrastructure sub-options;
- **Action D - Float–Move Options Combination and Down Selection:** Combining the 2964 remaining Float sub-options and 585 remaining Move sub-options gives a possible 1,733,940 combined Float-Move options. However, both incompatibilities between the functional groups and design generated requirements were used to down select these combined options. In this case 51,450 possible combined options were rejected due to incompatibilities between

the functional groups (i.e. the Move sub-option was unsuitable for the Float sub-option). The remaining possible combined options were then assessed using the requirements to down select acceptable options. This down selection resulted in 136,749 combined Float-Move options remaining.

- **Action E - Float–Move–Infrastructure Options Combination and Down Selection:** Combining the 119,837 combined Float-Move options, from the previous step, with 205 Infrastructure sub-options gave 24,566,585 possible combined Float-Move-Infrastructure options. Once again requirements were used to down select these new combined options. This down selection resulted in 25,195 combined Float-Move-Infrastructure options remaining.

a) Remaining Combined Float-Move Options, at Conclusion of Action D

b) Remaining Float-Move-Infrastructure Options, at Conclusion of Action E

Fig.8: Available weight vs. procurement cost for all float sub-options in the three hullform styles

Fig. 8a shows the procurement cost vs. available weight for Combat Systems for Remaining Combined Float-Move Options, at conclusion of Actions D. This figure shows the remaining Float options separated into three plots by the options hullform styles. While a large number of combined Float-Move options of the trimaran and monohull styles are able to satisfy the requirements imposed up to this stage, a far smaller number of combined options with a catamaran hullform are acceptable. The results of Action E, the final combination and down selection, is shown in Fig. 8b. At this point these remaining 25,195 acceptable combined Float-Move-Infrastructure options fully satisfy the set of requirements that were applied. The grouping of acceptable options is plotted in terms of the weight available for the combat system and the ship solution procurement cost, (excluding the combat system equipment cost). Fig. 9 shows the number of remaining options. No Catamaran style solutions remain. A monohull or a trimaran option may provide an acceptable solution for the specified requirements.

Fig.9: Number of Combined Float-Move-Infrastructure Options Remaining for Varying Procurement Costs, at Conclusion of Action E, showing Three Hullform Styles

4. Combining the Design Building Block and Library based approaches

The aim of the Library based tool is to provide the designer with information on the range of options that are available to the designer. Fig. 10 shows how the output of a Library based ship design tool could be used to better inform a designer by being combined with the Design Building Block (DBB) approach, to indicate to the designer how the Library options relate to the architectural configuration of the component spaces in the ship.

Fig.10: Illustrative Example of Integration with Design Building Block Approach

The vessel chosen is the LCS derived DBB design whose detailed concept evolution is outlined by *Andrews and Pawling (2009)*. In this case a number of outlines have been indicated illustrating the gross geometry of the remaining Library derived options (i.e. those generated by the library based tool, which have not been removed by the requirements input by the designer). As the designer begins to define and develop the design (in this case using the configuration driven tool) additional constraints will emerge – e.g. positioning payload along an upper deck may define a minimum length or machinery layout may drive beam at certain longitudinal locations. These new constraints can be used to further refine those remaining options that ‘make physical sense’.

One substantial benefit of the library based approach is the rich variety of design data which it is able to store. For example, the current implementation stores sub-option information, such as ship motions and power-speed data, that can allow the designer to gain insights into the ship performance for a range of sub-options. As this data is pre-generated the designer is able to rapidly access information

normally not likely to be available until later in the design process, when a more detailed ship definition can be analysed. This has the potential to help guide the designers as they explore options at the outset of the design process.

Fig.11: RMS Velocity vs Distance from LCB for a specific Float sub-option

Alternatively, useful information could be extracted from other performance metrics within the library and used to guide the ship’s layout. For example, by examining the options or sub-options obtained using the Library based approach, an earlier assessment of performance measures should be possible,

rather than the normal approach in which investigations are undertaken after a detailed design has been developed. Fig. 11 shows how this information could be displayed to help guide the designer in positioning systems with motions limitations (such as those required for helicopter operations). In this case the magnitude of vertical motions (Root-Mean-Squared (RMS) velocity in Sea State 5 (SS5)), relative to the distance from the hullform's longitudinal centre of buoyancy (LCB), is used to identify locations that are unacceptable. Two alternative presentation formats are shown in Fig. 11. Fig. 11a shows the data points from the library, while Fig. 11b shows how processing this data, using a number of box plots, can provide improved guidance on the likely performance of the remaining options in the library. Finally, Fig. 11c shows the potential of incorporating this information in conjunction with a Design Building Block model of a remaining option.

5. Discussion

Referring back to *Andrews' (2003b)* list of features, necessary in a approach able to fully support the initial ship design process, allows an assessment of the utility of the Design Building Block approach combined with a Library based approach against the generic needs of preliminary ship design. The following responses are considered appropriate for the combined approach outlined in this paper:

1. Believable solutions: the options proposed by this approach satisfy a set of constraints defined by the designer. These constraints can be used to ensure that the developed solutions are technically balanced and the combine/discard mechanism eliminates unreasonable options;
2. Coherent solutions: Integrating the method presented here with an architectural model (as shown in Fig. 10 & Fig. 11c) allows a dialogue with the customer beyond simple numerical measures of performance and cost. The combined Library and DBB approach allows the designer to present the customer with an integrated configuration based design, but at the same time allows the rapid exploration of options using the library;
3. Open methods: The rapid manner in which the options are down selected is highly amenable to alteration, thus allowing the designer to respond quickly to issues raised by the customer/requirements owner. Coupling this method with an appropriate configurational and numeric design tool should allow rapid exploration of options, improving the design team's responsiveness to queries and hence communication with the customer/requirements owner;
4. Revelatory: The proposed method can be used to quickly identify numerical design drivers early in the design process. But to realise its full potential as an aid to effective design exploration, links to the DBB approach, as outlined above, need to be more fully realised;
5. Creative: Compared to other ship design methods, by allowing the designer to postpone the selection of style, this approach allows options to remain open until later in the design process, fostering the development of hullform style alternatives that usually are ignored due to the difficulty in assessing them alongside conventional (monohull) options.

The concept of linking the Library and DBB approaches to ship design raises several issues for future investigation in developing both a broad approach and a more detailed procedure for use in design:

- Should the Library based approach be used to define limits on the layout, or should a partial layout be used as a selection tool in the Library based approach? Both methods have potential application in the exploration of (and importantly, generation of) design options and variants as shown in Fig. 2. This also raises the issue of the degree of automation or parameterisation of ship design models that would be acceptable in the combined approach.
- Can the Library based approach be used as part of an iterative design process? Considering the partial layout shown in Fig. 10, new constraints could be created (or old ones modified) that imply a re-iteration of the Library selection process would be appropriate. Given the Library based approach is applicable over a wider range of problems than hullform selection (such as addressing certain aspects of internal arrangement), then the incorporation of emergent drivers and relationships in an iterative process would be important.
- How can graphical user interfaces be used to improve the effectiveness of designer investigation and understanding of the solution space. With the incorporation of layout

aspects, the design is no longer being compared against a simple performance metric, so research is needed into methods that make use of all aspects of 3D environment, to allow the designer to extract valuable information from the selected options.

6. Conclusions

This research has explored the potential utility of combining two alternative design methods, namely the DBB approach and the Library base approach. By combining these, an integrated approach has been developed able to rapidly tackle the requirement elucidation need for wide exploration of options, while retaining the DBB approach's key feature of allowing the designer to explore innovative configuration alternatives. This combination can provide a basis better able to assist the designer in addressing the problem of requirement elucidation.

The combined DBB and Library based approach outlined is considered to provide a first step towards a tool that could satisfy Betts' and Andrews' lists of features supporting the very early stages of the ship concept design process. However, further work is seen as necessary for it to be incorporated in the preliminary ship design process for real naval ships:

- Demonstration of the application of the tool to a problem with a wider range of styles (for the hullform, machinery and configuration) and differing ship roles. This would ultimately require a range of comparable designs to be developed;
- Exploration of alternative methods of presenting the designer with information on the hullform styles suggested by the Library based approach in the context of a configuration based design environment (i.e. the DBB approach);
- Testing of the combined approach against actual designs produced by conventional methods.

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GeneSim - Development of a Generic Data Model for Production Simulation in Shipbuilding

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Abstract

Today the lack of sufficient data is the biggest challenge for using simulation in order to support production planning in shipbuilding. Within a project called GeneSim three German shipyards and partners work on a generic model for simulation data. This data model shall cover the required data for production simulation in shipbuilding and it shall be usable for other companies from maritime industries or related branches. The goal is to increase efficiency at shipyards already using simulation and to help other shipyards introducing simulation technology even if the required data is not available completely.

1. Introduction

Simulation has been established as an effective tool to support facility layout planning and production planning on shipyards, *Steinhauer (2006)*. But even for the shipyards that integrated the simulation into their planning procedures, the full potential cannot be tapped because of the lack of sufficient data about products or production planning in the different phases of the planning and shipbuilding process. Shipyards being in the phase of implementing the simulation face the most difficult obstacles there. Even if available, data from CAD or network planning does often not contain the required information for planning or simulation not to mention that a sufficient format is rarely provided.

The experience gained by the shipyards using the production simulation show the limits of today's data and model management. First of all, the product data is often not or not yet completely available on shipyards not using IT tools for planning or on every shipyard in early planning phases. Data generators based on ship's key figures or experience are only available for special purposes. Some product attributes having a significant impact on the production flow and the production times can only be defined in a fuzzy way e.g. quality or accessibility. Methods to handle this data have not been established yet.

Data management solutions developed by simulation using shipyards are mostly grown based on concrete project requirements and therefore neither efficient nor transferable to other companies. For that reason some operative applications are still not implemented and the data management is very time-consuming.

The usage of simulation results is also not systematically applied. Efficient analysing tools or export functions are not available for shipbuilding purposes.

Another difficulty in using simulation data in existing applications is the assurance of validity and plausibility. Finding data errors only in the simulation run is time-consuming on the long run. Not detected data errors can result in wrong decisions. Systematic methods for verification and validation of data are not existing yet.

In October 2009 the **GeneSim** (**Generic Data and Model Management for Production Simulation in Shipbuilding**, www.genesim.de) project started funded by the German ministry of economy and technology (FKZ 03SX274) planned to expire in September 2011. In this project the data required for simulation of production processes in shipbuilding are to be defined and structured in a generic way by a consortium of partners from different shipyards supported by a university and a research institute.

2. Aspects of Production Simulation in Shipbuilding

Unlike most applications in industries with series production the main focus of using the simulation in shipbuilding is not on layout planning but on supporting the production planning and control. Therefore current data from the product and the production planning has to be used accompanying the production progress in the simulation.

The application of production simulation requires

- a verified and valid model,
- sufficient input data and
- analyzing functions for the results.

Building simulation models of production processes in shipbuilding is generally not a big challenge any more, Fig. 1. Simulation tool-sets containing simulation functionalities for shipbuilding support the modelling of production facilities or assembly procedures. One widely used tool-set in shipbuilding is the Simulation Toolkit Shipbuilding (STS) developed and used in the cooperation community **SimCoMar** (**Simulation Cooperation in the Maritime Industries**, www.simcomar.com).

Fig.1: Flensburger's complete shipyard simulation model

A challenging part of simulation is the verification and validation of simulation models though. The high amount of partly fuzzy influencing parameters on the shipbuilding process and the large variety of feasible process alternatives makes the comparison of model and reality very difficult. Planning support as the most interesting application field for simulation in shipbuilding requires a certain quality of data to be used. In order to use simulation for production planning and control the used data about the product, the schedule or the resource availability has to be up to date. The latest change in the design has to be considered in the simulation as well as the current number of convalescents suffering from swine flu or delayed material deliveries. Often these kind of changed conditions to the planned status are the objects of the analysis. Their impacts on production flow are to be evaluated and quantified in order to find a sufficient solution.

3. Goals and partners of the GeneSim project

The goal of the GeneSim project is to expand the usage of the production simulation technology in shipbuilding. New application fields in production planning and control are to be entered and the

efficiency in using simulation is to be increased. Existing obstacles for shipyards or suppliers to introduce this technology into their companies for the first time are to be removed by the development of a generic data and model management.

In GeneSim a data model is to be developed containing all the required data for production simulation in shipbuilding universally usable by companies from maritime industries. Interfaces to the existing data from CAD or planning are to be defined, as well as data generators for not or not yet completely existing data. To work on this task a consortium has been established by

- Flensburger Schiffbau-Gesellschaft mbH & Co. KG (FSG),
- Friedrich Lürssen Werft (FLW),
- Howaldtswerke Deutsche Werft (HDW),
- Technische Universität Hamburg-Harburg, Institute for Production Management and Technology (TUHH) and
- the Center of Maritime Technologies e.V. (CMT)

coordinated by FSG. This consortium covers a variety of shipyards working on completely different types of ships like freight ships, yachts or submarines. This group of shipyards is reasonably completed by a company very experienced in simulation consultancy and by a university for the scientific support. Therefore in the GeneSim project a wide range of application cases and requirements can be taken into consideration.

Another parallel strategy to be followed in GeneSim is the implementation of the scenario technique. This technique not only helps managing the analysis of different alternatives in planning but also enables the consideration of fuzzy product data. Scenarios combing different data sources or assumptions are to be defined, evaluated and compared by adapting and using the scenerio technique within GeneSim.

Preliminary studies about data structures for simulation cases have been carried out within the SimCoMar cooperation in 2006 and 2007. A first entity relationship model to describe the data structure was developed showing the general feasibility of defining a generic data model. The results from that preliminary studies are taken as the basis for the first data structures to be developed. Nevertheless, the modelling technique and the first assumptions from SimCoMar will have to be verified in GeneSim.

4. Content of the GeneSim project

The GeneSim project is structured in eight work packages as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig.2: Structure of the GeneSim project

4.1 Data structure

As the goal of the first work package a generic data structure is being developed by the project partners. The structure takes the requirements of simulation in shipbuilding and its application fields in planning and control into consideration. It will be documented by an entity relationship model (ERM) showing entities, relations and attributes. The data structure shall be universally usable by companies within the maritime industries and possibly in related branches.

4.2 Data and model management

A data administration concept is being developed both for simulation data and for simulation models. Therefore data is being classified by usage, extent of validity and source. The requirements for data and model management are being derived from the classification. Data management strategies are developed for the accompanying usage of simulation in planning and control as well as for the export of data to the ERP tools based on reference models.

4.3 Data collection

Strategies will be developed for the import of data from existing sources like CAD or project planning. Possible requirements for post processing due to format differences will be taken into consideration. One important task will be the definition of data generating methods. Fuzzy or incomplete simulation data is therefore being collected and classified. Dependencies of missing data to existing figures of the product or planning are to be analysed and formalized based on experience or examination of analogies. These methods will be transferred into data generating functions. Methods of fuzzy logic will be applied to the part of data which can not be defined exactly like quality or accessibility.

4.4 Output data and analysis

Standardized analysing functions and key figures for simulation output data are to be defined based on requirements from production planning and control. A modular structure for simulation analysis is to be developed in order to combine standard analysing function and shipyard specific requirements in a tool-set for simulation analysis. A revision monitor will be designed that helps to systematically manage and compare alternative planning scenarios by simulation.

4.5 Validation and verification

Methods for systematic data validation will be developed. Therefore criteria for data validity will be defined and methods for checking the data will be developed. For a systematic model verification possible model errors will be collected and classified. Based on these error classes procedures of model verification will be defined. In order to develop methods for model validation the criteria for model validity will be defined based on the requirements of the different planning applications.

4.6 Adaption of scenario technique

In the first phase of adapting the scenario technique relevant classes for scenarios and their systems and structure are defined. Criteria for comparing the scenarios are developed. Then templates and rules for easy and fast definition of consistent scenarios are to be set up. A description method for scenarios based on fuzzy-logic will be defined. For the management of simulation scenarios a meta model will be developed and integrated into the data model. For validating and verifying planning results so-called robust scenarios are designed based on evaluation criteria from planning requirements. The robustness of planning scenarios will be shown in a robustness monitor.

4.7. Verification of methods

To verify the developed methods reference scenarios from different areas of the production in shipbuilding (steel, outfitting, furnishing, supplier integration and logistics networks) will be developed and criteria for verification will be defined.

4.8 Validation of concepts in complex production areas (steel and outfitting)

In the last work package the developed concepts are to be validated by the partners on simulation models from different fields of application. Steel fabrication and assembly will be part of the validation as well as outfitting and furnishing.

5. Current results: structure of simulation data

In the first phase of the project a generic data model is being developed covering all the required data for production simulation. The requirements are generated and the structure is verified by a variety of different simulation scenarios contributed by the partners. Simulation applications at partner shipyards are discussed as well as experiences from consulting projects at various shipyards from all over the world. The simulated process is analysed with regard to the determining factors for the process flow and the process time. Parameters defining the sequence of process steps and their constraints are collected as well as the product characteristics influencing the process time.

One simulation scenario analysed is the manufacturing process for plate parts, Fig. 3. In this production process a raw material is transferred into parts by a cutting process. The process parameters and their determining product attributes have been collected and clustered. The data was generalized to cover all related processes on a shipyard e.g. profile cutting or bending.

Fig.3: Flensburger's simulation model of the plate part production

Another simulation scenario analysed is the assembly process for steel constructions like sections or blocks, Fig.4, *Steinhauer and Meyer-König (2006)*. Substructures, steel parts and outfitting are assembled by a complex process limited by a multitude of different constraints. In this application case for production simulation the relation between the sub-constructions and parts to the resulting construction of the assembly process is most important. Another focal point of interest was the definition of the required assembly process steps and their relations. The applied simulation models

and used engineering tools showed different possibilities for defining process steps respectively deriving them automatically from part attributes. But these different ways of process definition are not mutually exclusive so a data structure was defined covering both approaches.

Fig.4: Flensburger's simulation model of the block assembly station

The main backbone within the structure of system load data are the entities for the parallel hierarchies of the product data: steel structure, compartments and systems. A very important focus was also put on the relation between elements and its attributes forming e.g. the welding joints. Entities have been developed to flexibly take this important process information for production in shipbuilding into consideration. The challenge for the future work on the data structure will be to combine the different focuses and approaches of the different shipyard that were detected during the several workshops. Shipyards have different philosophies in material control, process and work plan definition or planning. These philosophies are impacting the data management significantly and have to be taken into consideration.

6. Outlook

The results achieved so far in the GeneSim project show that the chosen approach is very promising. A common basis for data structures was found usable for all the participating shipyards or consulting companies. In some areas of the data structure alternative data links may have to be provided to cover the different philosophies in data management of the shipyards. As one next step the intermediate results of GeneSim will be discussed with simulation users from related branches. Since 2006 FSG is working within the **SIMoFIT** cooperation (**Simulation of Outfitting** in Shipbuilding and Civil Engineering, www.simofit.de) with partners from Bauhaus-University in Weimar and from Ruhr-University in Bochum on simulation solutions for complex assembly procedures, König et al. (2007), Steinhauer (2007). In this cooperation community the first results will be verified on different simulation applications from building industries.

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Utilization of Integrated Design and Mesh Generation in Ship Design Process

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Abstract

Advantages within creating FE models from the design model have been confirmed earlier. Application of an integrated 3D product model as the source of information helps the FE analysis to follow the pace of the design evolvement. While the general geometry modelling and FE analysis proceed in parallel the overall design process gains speed. Development over the last few years has progressed towards the ideal where structural engineering more and more utilizes directly the information stored within the design models. This paper presents a process where integration is achieved and reviews the results that are available for FE analysis. Meshes for global strength, vibration, local stress, and fatigue analysis are presented and the prerequisites for creating these are discussed. Some instances of modifying the design and their implications for updating the FE analysis are shown.

1. Introduction

It is a time-consuming task to create finite element mesh for ship structures. During the past decades, several attempts and solutions have been made for integrating ship design and mesh generation, *Doig et al. (2009)*, *Dumez, et al. (2008)*. At the point of early design, it is profitable to have a global finite element model as early as possible. If structural concepts can be evaluated effectively with FEA, this yields an optimum where the results of the finite element study can be utilized during the design process, rather than only in the verification of the structural integrity of a ready design.

Currently, the common trend for shipyards and design offices is to develop the working methods away from the separate drafting and 3D design towards unified design process, where 3D product model is created in one system, and that information is used for several purposes, i.e. for analysis, classification drawings and production material, *Hughes (1988)*.

Fig. 1: 3D product model, primary source of information for design and analysis (by Napa Ltd).

In order to effectively manage design changes during the ship design process, it is advantageous to use a system, which allows intelligent modelling of ship structures. Thus, the design changes can be made with the minimum effort and up-to-date mesh is available for FEA at any time during the design process.

This paper shows the methods for parametric modelling and automatic mesh generation based on parametric 3D product model. Fig. 1 illustrates some fields which can utilize the information in a 3D product model. Herein the focus is on the mesh generation based on 3D product model. The following section describes the challenges in creating discrete geometry (mesh) based on as-built ship geometry. Also, it is shown what kind of information from the 3D model can be included in FE models automatically. Chapters 3 and 4 present the variety of finite element models needed.

2. Idealization of structures

The as-built ship geometry sets a challenge when the mesh is generated from that. The ship is a massive construction with an enormous number of structural details. The FEM analyses should take care of not only the global behaviour of the whole ship hull but also the smallest details at the size of fatigue cracks. Not even today do the computer resources allow modelling the whole ship construction at this fine mesh level. The structures must be idealized in a proper way in the FE models.

Not all the structural details are necessary from the global finite element point of view. The big challenge in automatic meshing is not to include realistic details into the model but to remove them by idealization from the model and still get realistic results. In several cases, it is also better to have slightly distorted geometry in the FE model in order to achieve better shaped elements for the analysis, and also to limit the number of created elements.

The following example in Fig. 2 illustrates how the as-built geometry of double bottom and hopper could be idealized for finite element purposes in a tanker model. Idealizations in Fig. 2 are:

1. Connected stiffeners: they are extended to the connection point.
2. Openings: in this case study, the openings are taken into account via effective plate thickness. Alternatively, they can be omitted from the model or idealized as square.
3. Unconnected stiffener: end is moved with a tolerance to adapt to the mesh better.
4. Hopper opening: exact curved geometry is discretized.
5. Corner notches: omitted from FEM.
6. Cut-outs and end-cuts: not included in the global level finite element model.
7. Plate thickness: structures are modelled at moulded surfaces with shell elements.

Fig. 2: Left: as-built structures. Right: shrink plot of elements. Lines represent beams. Grey fill colour indicates the elements with effective plate thickness (by Napa Ltd).

The right side in Fig. 2 illustrates the finite element mesh of the double bottom, hopper and side, generated automatically from the as-built 3D model. The target mesh size is approximately 0.85 m, which is the longitudinal stiffener spacing in the example.

3. Intelligent modelling enables effective handling of design changes

Ship structures change during the design process. As more information is available, the ship geometry varies and also the level of details increases. In practice a ship designer will find an optimum design in an iterative process. To gain the maximum benefit, the numerical optimising algorithms are used also for ship design, *Kuutti and Uppala (2005)*. In general, the usage of a numerical optimising algorithm with 3D product models needs topological and parameterized product models.

It is massively time-consuming to try to synchronize the finite element model with the classification drawings (or production material). Therefore, if the information is retrieved from one database, it is more likely to succeed in up-to-date geometry and the properties of a finite element model and the drawings, for example. The requirements from a large number of design iterations lead to fully automatic meshing algorithms.

Based on the initial scantling analysis, the strength assessment or perhaps a decision to change the general arrangement of a ship, the geometry and the properties evolve constantly and eventually several analyses are needed. Fig. 3 shows an example and the principles how the structures and compartments could be modelled in a way that the changes are controlled with minimum effort.

Fig. 3: Hull surface, two reference surfaces, five tanks, and steel structures within one tank are illustrated in a 3D product model (by Napa Ltd). (1) Hull surface; (2) Reference surfaces; (3) Compartment arrangement; (4) Steel structures

The compartment arrangement and the steel structures refer to the same reference surfaces and the hull, yielding unified changes during the entire design process. Also, the model is created with the references to the neighbouring structures and surfaces. These principles make the ship geometry fully topological. Topological geometry can be used in the optimization of structures, for instance. In Fig 4:

Another aspect from the finite element point of view is corrosion reduction: a compartment model can be used as a basis for the corrosion reduction. The corrosion reduction required in CSR (Common Structural Rules) should be applied automatically to surface elements (plate and shell) and line elements (rod and beam).

Fig. 4: Intelligent modeling using parametric web frame structures and topological compartment model (by Napa Ltd). (1) Reference surfaces for longitudinal bulkheads; (2) Parametric web frame structures; (3) Center Cargo Oil Tank No.4; (4) P-Wing Cargo Oil Tank No.4; (5) S-Wing Cargo Oil Tank No.4; (6) Water Ballast Tank No.4 (P-side); (7) Water Ballast Tank No.4 (S-side)

4. Design changes, case study

The purpose of the case study is to show the power in intelligent modelling and the product model based mesh generation. The examples show how big general arrangement level changes can be controlled with topology in product model and structural details with parametric modelling concept. These examples are prepared with NAPA software.

In the example, a reference surface is moved, first from #LONG14 to #LONG13, and further to #LONG12. As seen in the figure below, the model lives with the changed location of the reference surface. Therefore, the following structures move along the reference surface: the longitudinal bulkhead, the girder, the web frame, and the transversal bulkhead.

Fig. 5: Left: longitudinal bulkhead on long14. Centre: longitudinal bulkhead on long13, and right: longitudinal bulkhead on long12. Typical web frame, horizontal stringers etc., only port side shown in full-breadth model (by Napa Ltd).

Figs.6 to 8 show the possibilities to change hopper opening shape and location and how the automatic mesh generation treats different opening geometry and structures. The shown meshes have been coarse and uniform which is suitable for global strength studies. The following chapter shows the possibilities to generate non-uniform meshes and include more detailed geometry for the analysis.

Fig. 6: Initial design of hopper and generated mesh (by Napa Ltd).

Fig. 7: Modified hopper and updated mesh (by Napa Ltd).

Fig. 8: Further modified hopper and updated mesh (by Napa Ltd).

5. Structural details and fine mesh areas

As the design evolves, more detailed information on structural details is available for more detailed analysis. Detailed shapes e.g. end-cuts, cut-outs, corner notches, and bracket toes are typical structures that need to be investigated for fatigue analysis. Often the applied mesh size is smaller than 50 mm, or even thickness by thickness mesh is applied to achieve the most accurate estimate for stress results, Common structural rules for oil tankers (2006).

Fig. 9: Bracket toe and faceplate end-cut modelled in NAPA Steel.

The generation of fine mesh areas in NAPA is rather straightforward. In general, there are numerous meshing parameters to choose from and the user has full control of the mesh outcome. Fine mesh areas can be defined and used in several different ways and the system sets no limitations on the creation of fine mesh areas. In practice, the NAPA user has to define only the target mesh size for the refinement and the mesh is generated automatically. See Fig. 10 for JTP requirements for fine mesh areas.

Fig. 10: Fine mesh zones according to JTP requirements.

Fig. 11: Web frame mesh with local fine mesh areas (by Napa Ltd).

In most cases, it is desired to apply solely quadratic mesh at the free boundary for potentially high stress areas. See the following mesh example on a tanker model. The applied global mesh size is 0.425 mm, which in this case, results in two elements between the longitudinal stiffeners. The given element size for fine mesh areas is 40 mm. Also, the NAPA user can choose how smoothly the fine mesh area conjoins to the overall (global) mesh. Fig. 11 shows the mesh for the example case. Only the port side of full breadth model is shown. Fig. 12 shows the mesh for a bracket toe. Full-quad mesh is applied at the boundary.

Fig. 12: Bracket toe mesh (by Napa Ltd).

Fig. 13 and Fig. 14 show the meshes for a bracket toe, a faceplate end-cut and an opening. Also, full-quad mesh is applied to the opening boundary, which is a potential area to contain high stress levels, to ensure the best possible estimate for stress results.

Fig. 13: Bracket toe, innerskin, and faceplate end-cut (by Napa Ltd).

Fig. 14: Mesh refinements for an opening and a bracket (by Napa Ltd).

6. Conclusions

This paper illustrated some benefits in parametric modelling and automatic mesh generation based on 3D product model. The introduction stated that it is profitable to have a global finite element model as early as possible during the early design and if structural concepts can be evaluated effectively with FEA, these factors yield an optimum situation where the results of the finite element study can be utilized during the design process. This paper presented a method and a system, which help to reach the point where finite element models can be created with very fast pace and good quality up-to-date mesh is available for FEA at any point during the design process.

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Interactive Hull Form Transformations using Curve Network Deformation

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Abstract

All hull surface transformation techniques used today are applied to the space in which the surface definition resides, deforming it geometrically. This approach is usually successful for changes to large portions of the surface but often smaller features can be harder to change, becoming undesirably distorted in the process. If a transformation toolkit within a design tool is unable to accommodate a particular feature, the change must be made by hand and is likely to take significantly longer than if a transformation had functioned effectively. For a hull surface defined using a curve network, local features can be identified by reviewing the hull form topology. However, rather than invoke a spatial deformation specifically designed for each feature, the curve network can be used to transmit changes across edges and faces, adapting to any features that may be present. This paper presents an approach to hull surface transformation based on identifying features in the form topology and allows changes using both interactive mouse manipulation and numerical parameters. A rich transformation tool kit is created which allows the user to confidently make rapid hull changes in conjunction with existing surface definition techniques.

1. Introduction

The process of developing a new hull form can be costly and time consuming. The qualities of a hull form, developed without reference to a previous design are unknown. Designs with no heritage often require extensive analysis to verify that they perform as desired. The preferred alternative to this approach is to take an existing design and modify it to suit the new requirements of the project. The performance characteristics of a derived design should be similar to the original as long as the changes between the two hull forms remain conservative.

To change hull form shape many commercial hull form design software include the ability to transform the hull surface. The most prolific approach is based on the methods documented by *Lackenby (1950)* and allow the designer to adjust the hydrostatic characteristics of a hull form by either changing the length of the parallel middle body or distorting the entrance and run. Simpler changes using combinations of scaling and translation can be implemented providing geosim changes. In both cases, the changes made by these techniques cover significant areas of the hull surface. For minor changes, it's necessary for the surface to be changed by directly modifying the definition.

The nature of the changes to the hull form and any tidying up that must take place after the surface has been changed means that the activity can only be undertaken by the person in the organization responsible for the hull surface, having been trained in the skills required to make changes reliably. When a project is innovative or resources must be efficiently managed, other members of the project may need to use a representative hull surface to check design or production issues. However, often the project member responsible for hull surface modifications is unavailable or a design does not exist. In these cases, a user-friendly design tool is required to allow a range of changes to be made quickly and easily to a hull surface without requiring the full range of skills required for detailed hull surface design activities.

2. Some Notable Hull Transformation Techniques

Before computers were introduced into design offices, hull surfaces were manipulated on the drawing board by hand. This process was incredibly time consuming because the designer was responsible for ensuring that the 2D views would produce a viable 3D surface. Any hull transformation techniques used in the design process needed to avoid introducing unnecessary manipulation and complex

calculations. Lackenby documented two practical techniques generally known as “1-Cp” and “Lackenby” which change a hull form by longitudinally translating hull sections using calculations that could be made by hand. Both techniques use relatively simple scaling functions to deform forward and aft regions of the hull surface. In addition, Lackenby developed functions which would convert the desired hydrostatic changes into the amount of adjustment that should be applied to the hull form using the transformation functions. Lackenby’s methods are still used in modern hull design applications but it is necessary to extend the technique to deal with modern surface representations and distortion beyond the limits of the section area curve.

Once computers began to be used to manipulate hull surfaces richer techniques for transforming the hull form were developed. *Söding (1977)* aimed to provide a generic solution to hull form transformation. The transformation defines a mapping from the original to the derived surface, with the mapping consisting of a structure of functions in each coordinate component. The functions themselves may be stored in a library, accessed when a change is required or defined by the user. The solution was developed in association with design software because structure used to formulate and apply the change is an important aspect of this solution, using specific command syntaxes to invoke and specify mathematical changes. The approach provides a rich and open set of tools for changing hull shape and it seems possible for the user to develop their own custom transformation rules. However, this technique was developed prior to the introduction of standardised user interfaces, like Windows, and it would have been very difficult for practical designers, who often show impatience with complex tools, to get the best from the system.

Free form deformation (FFD) is a recent introduction that has its origins in the 3D graphical design software. The principle behind FFD is to enclose a complex geometric shape within a simpler shape which under goes distortion. The distortion of the simpler shape provides a mapping to change the coordinate positions of the more complex shape. A simplistic example is to use a cuboid that when distorted regularly can cause contained geometry to be translated and scaled. If individual corners of the cuboid are translated, the contained geometry can be twisted and sheared. In more complex examples, the enclosing volume may be represented by trivariate NURBS volumes allowing highly complex and non-linear distortions. As the enclosing volume is geometric, it is very easy to control using interactive or parametric means and is one of the reasons why it has become popular. However, while the technique is very successful at making informal changes to geometry, a requirement of hull design is the requirement to make precise changes to the surface. This can be achieved with the FFD technique but it is necessary to prepare the deforming volume so that its changes will be compatible with the structure of the hull surface and respect its features. This takes time and means that software implementations using this approach can only provide a limited range of hull form changes if customisation is to be avoided.

2.1. The Limitations of Geometric Hull Form Transformation

Hull forms, particular of commercial ships, have specific features which contribute to the performance of the vessel. These features have limitations on the way that they can be distorted otherwise they may have a detrimental effect on performance. Each of the techniques discussed here change the hull form by defining an explicit mathematical set of transformation rules which are applied to the geometric definition of the hull surface. In order to avoid undesirable distortion to hull surface features, the transformation must account for the features by coding into the technique. In the case of *Söding’s* approach, the transformation functions must be designed to fit to the features of a hull surface. In FFD, the initial distorting geometry may have to be tuned to fit the surface. Lackenby’s techniques requires the locations of the parallel middle body to be established prior to applying the transformation to the hull offsets and it does not make any specific allowance for the shape of the hull form beyond the limits of the section area curve. These limitations make it difficult to incorporate a wide range of efficient generic transformation tools into hull design software and it often results in the designer becoming frustrated when it does not work correctly or choosing to modify the surface by directly manipulating the definition.

3. Modern Hull Form Representation Techniques with Respect to Transformation

The offset data of Lackenby's era is rarely used in modern shipbuilding, with almost all tools using mathematical surfaces, particular NURBS, due to the wide number of applications these representations support. NURBS, in particular, have become ubiquitous because complex shapes can be accurately represented by a very small amount of structured definition data. Consequently, it's very easy to transfer surface representations between software tools and allows a single definition to be used for applications as far ranging as detailed hydrodynamic analysis to numerically controlled fabrication. Furthermore, the definition used to control NURBS surface is a grid of coordinate points, which when presented to the user within a design tool, can be manipulated to change shape with ease. The control points can also be manipulated using coordinate transformations without any significant complexity.

While the introduction of NURBS enabled sharing of the hull representation and made design of individual surfaces easier, it still requires a lot of skill to produce a surface of the quality required for efficient hydrodynamic and production performance. In particular, it is difficult to fit the rectangular shape of these surfaces to the varied shapes which can be found in hull forms. A natural extension is to allow the use a number of surface patches to represent the hull form but this introduces the problem of ensuring smooth continuity between surface patches. There are various techniques for achieving this, but the most appropriate for ship hull forms is to use a network of curves, from which a patchwork of surfaces is generated. This approach, arguably, requires more skill than individual patches to generate a good quality hull form but it does allow the designer to work with curves, which often offer a better technique for describing surface shapes than directly manipulating the surface itself. Consequently, this technique will often be used produce or change complex hull surface in a much shorter time than direct manipulation of the surface definition. As the curves are defined by coordinate points, they can be manipulated by coordinate transformations much like the surface definition. However, topology is often used in the curve definition to allow curves to reference others and non-uniform transformation techniques must take extra care to avoid changing the curve network in such a way that references become invalid preventing the hull surface from being generated.

4. IntelliHull and the Introduction of Form Topology

While in a role that involve the regular definition of hull surfaces, the author noted that almost every hull surface uses a similar structure of definition, yet it was necessary define a new definition structure each time a different surface was required. Furthermore, the structure could easily be sketched and annotated to describe how different shape characteristic would be distributed about the surface, Fig. 1.

Fig.1: An outline sketch of a hull form showing typical boundary and feature curves (Form Topology) (left), separating the regions of different shape characteristics (right).

IntelliHull, *Bole (2006)*, was an attempt to use this structure to generate a hull form surface producing a tool which combined the ideas of both parametric hull generation and traditional hull surface manipulation to allow the designer to manipulate shape interactively and control dimensions and

hydrostatic properties numerically. The concept of Form Topology was introduced to allow the software to understand the designer’s definition by representing the structure and relationships between the different features and shapes that can be found in a hull form surface definition. Graphically, Form Topology has the same shape as the sketch, Fig. 1, but may be represented using a topological graph data structure and curve geometry, Fig. 5. Using Form Topology, IntelliHull software can identify features such as the Parallel Middle Body or the ends of the ship, creating flat or curved surface definition in those locations respectively. Form Topology could also be used to expose form parameters measured from key features in the designer’s definition or the generated hull surface. Modification of these parameters invoked a specific transformation to change the feature guided by the Form Topology.

IntelliHull was limited to producing a single surface using a lofting technique across a transverse set of curves. As a design progressed, it became increasingly difficult to introduce smaller features because the surface definition was restricted to a maximum number of definition curves each with a consistent number of control points. Experience with commercial tools highlighted that the only way to extend the Form Topology concept beyond the generation of a single hull surface was to use a curve network to generate more flexible representations and that the technique would function better if focused on transforming the hull surface definition rather than on the hull form generation problem.

5. Hull Surface Definition Using Curve Network Topology and Hierarchy

A curve network allows the designer to build up a surface definition in stages, unlike direct surface manipulation where the designer starts with a complete surface and must deform it into the desired shape. In the initial stages of the process, Fig. 2, key shape curves, such as the midship section and the boundaries of the surface definition will be defined, such as the centreline and deck. Subsequently, curves will be added between key curves to refine the shape. Some surface design tools allow curves to be attached to previously defined curves, creating a hierarchy. Consequently, curves lower down the hierarchy will update as result of changes to curves higher up. This feature is useful in the early stages of defining a surface as it may only necessary to accurately position the initial key curves, as subsequent curves may reference them without the need to position control points explicitly.

Fig.2: Create a simple bow of hull, beginning with the boundaries, features followed by waterlines and sections. Curve created at each stage actively reference curves generated in previous stages.

In addition to control points, rules may be assigned to components in the curve network to control or constrain the shape of curves without the designer having to specifically position the control points. These attributes can be summarised as follows:

Fig.3: Point attributes, beginning with the raw B-Spline curve, with a straight, knuckle and blend applied respectively.

Point attributes: These attributes can be assigned to control points in the curve to change its shape as it passes through the point. Usually, this will involve constraining the tangent of the curve or

introducing a knuckle, Fig. 3. Rules assigned to point pairs can introduce straight segments or blends in the curve shape.

Curve Attributes: Curve attributes can be used to introduce the same constraints as point attributes, but assign the effect to the referencing points of any attached curves. The result is that the attribute affects all attached points without having to assign an attribute to each point individually. Shapes such as knuckles and surface angles can be generated in the surface using this method, Fig. 4. Curve attributes can generate tangents in referencing curves based on the definition of the surface attribute. In the area of the parallel middle body these attributes can be used to ensure that curves enter the flat of side, bilge radius and flat of bottom with the correct tangent.

Fig.4: Curve attributes, beginning with the raw curve network and then showing the effects of a knuckle attribute or the application of curve tangent constraints.

Surface Attributes: These attributes are used to simplify curve definition by locating it within a surface effectively making it two dimensional. This makes manipulation and management of certain key curves such as midship sections and flat of side/bottom curves easier. As mentioned above, surface attributes can be used in conjunction with curve attributes to constrain tangent shapes at points. The implementation used in this study restricts surface attributes to planar constraints, although more elaborate definitions are available in other design tools.

The ability to add attributes to control curves, and hence surface shape, is an advantage that other definition techniques which are purely geometrical do not have. However, care must be taken with attributes when it comes to transforming the surface. It is possible to introduce attributes which cannot be transformed geometrically. In particular, it is hard to transform an attribute which introduces a tangent angle into a curve using a non-uniform coordinate transformation. In the curve network implementation used in this study, the designer can only assign attributes that can be safely transformed. Furthermore, none of the attributes implemented have any extra parametric information beyond that of the curve control points because this could introduce the need for specific transformation rules to change the attribute as well as the curve geometry.

6. Identifying the Form Topology in the Curve Network

As mentioned in the previous chapter, the procedure used to create a curve network has a very natural feel with respect to the design process, with curves representing key features of the surface being defined before any free form surface shape is defined. The explicit relationships between curves for certain types of hull form allow properties which may be common to all surface definitions of that type to be identified. For example, for traditional monohull ship hull forms:

- The midship section curve will lie within the transverse plane and, in a hull form with parallel middle body, the hull surface will be normal to the plane in which the curve is defined. The midship section curve will lie approximately midway along the length of the hull form.
- Tangents of curves at points attached to Flat of side and Flat of bottom curves will be tangential to the parallel middle body.
- Within the parallel middle body region of the flat of side and flat of bottom, there will be no need for definition curves.

- Etc.

Furthermore, certain curve relationships will be known. For example, the flat of side and flat of bottom curves will attach to the midship section curves forming the extents of the parallel middle body. This relationship can be used to establish the portion of the midship section curve that defines the bilge radius. By continuing to extend these heuristic rules to the other key features of the hull form, the network of Form Topology curves may be established by checking the location, connections and attributes associated with each element within the wider curve network. Once the Form Topology curve network has been found, Fig. 5, form parameters in addition to the main dimensions and hydrostatic properties may be identified. The free form regions of the hull form, in the entrance and in the run, which would need to be adjusted to change the volumetric properties of the hull form, are also identified, highlighted later in Fig. 10. Consequently, the approach used in IntelliHull, to measure parameters from the surface definition and invoke a transformation when changed can be used as an additional tool alongside the manual manipulation of the curve network definition.

Fig.5: The Form Topology formally identified in the curve network (left). Design parameters can be identified in the Form Topology once the individual curves within the structure are identified (right).

7. Using Topology and Hierarchy to Transform a Hull Form

7.1. Transformation guided by the Curve Network Hierarchy

As the curves representing the key features of the hull form are usually designed first, appearing at the top of the curve network hierarchy, it is natural to assume that this structure can be used to deform the hull surface definition. By modifying key curves, any descendant curves, attached through referenced points will update to the changes. Such a technique, Sticky Splines, *van Overveld (1996)*, has been explored for use with 2D animation. Unlike the curve network used to define a hull form, it consists entirely of free form splines and doesn't necessarily use the additional attributes. The use of curve attributes makes the process of transforming the network a little easier. In the case of Sticky Splines, the technique has to identify any specific features from the arrangements of control points and introduce constraints to ensure that the correct transformation is applied. A process to identify special features and introduce particular transformations into the curve network is not necessary if attributes are present, and consequently, the attribute itself will take care of any specific updates. Consequently, all that is necessary is to find a method of transforming free control points that lie on curve segments between the constrained control points that are attached to other curves or control points representing discontinuities in the curve, defined using attributes. A simple transformation rule was developed, Fig. 6, inspired by the Elastic option available when modifying Spline curves in CorelDraw, a vector graphics drawing software application.

The simplicity of this approach was really attractive but it was found to have limitations because the order in which the transformation was applied was entirely governed by the user. In vessels, without flat of side/bottom, particularly small craft and yachts, the natural order in which the curve network hierarchy is composed, for the ease of design, is not necessarily appropriate for the best transformations, Fig. 7. Hence the designer is forced to use an undesirable hierarchy to utilise these transformations properly.

Where t is the normalised (chord) distance along the curve from P_0 to P_n .

Fig.6: Translations of curve end or attachment points need to be distributed to all internal free points on the curves to achieve the full transformation

Fig.7: Deformation of a yacht hull form using the curve network hierarchy. In this example, the transformation is successful (centre) if waterlines F, E, D are connected to sections A, B and C, but not if the relationships are reversed (right).

However, while this approach was found to be unsuitable for formal hull form transformation it was found to be very useful when creating the hull form because descendant curves update as a result of changes further up the hierarchy. This means that the surface definition subtly maintains its general style and fairness. In fact, the user is generally not aware of this process happening until the feature is switched off.

7.2. Transformation guided by Form Topology Curve Network

The approach explored in the previous section performed poorly because it relied on the user to provide the structure of the transformation. Yet, if the correct structure was provided, the transformations performed remarkably well. As the structure of the users curve network cannot be relied upon, a solution is to generate a separate hierarchy based on the users curve network and this can be found by extracting the Form Topology curve network from the hull form definition and treating it as a unidirectional graph. Consequently, the issue of the order in which curves are connected is avoided. Based on the elements of the Form Topology graph data structure, i.e. the vertices, edges and faces, a new transformation order can be devised as follows.

1. Translate selected vertices in the Form Topology.
2. Update any planar constraints associated with the selected vertices.
3. Distribute the transformation around the Form Topology graph using a Breadth First Search, as described in 7.2.1.
4. Deform the edges of the Form Topology graph by calculating new positions of free control points on curves associated with each edge, as described in 7.2.2.
5. Translate all curve control point positions associated with each face in the Form Topology using the difference between two multi-sided surfaces blended using the face edge geometry, as described in 7.2.3.
6. Assign each new position to the control points of the curves (in the order of the users curve network hierarchy).

It is not necessary to identify the role of each curve in the Form Topology curve network graph at this stage, it is only necessary to identify whether a curve forms part of the Form Topology. This can be achieved by selecting all the curves which either form the surface boundary or have curve attributes. It may be necessary to do a deeper investigation to identify cases where the user has used many individual point attributes instead of a single curve attribute or the Form Topology introduces a curve which is important to the design process but does not need use an attribute to generate a specific surface feature, such as a midship section on a hull form with no parallel middle body features.

7.2.1. Transformation of Form Topology Graph Vertices

The vertices of the Form Topology curve network occur at the intersections of key curves. In most cases, specific hull form design parameters can be associated with individual or pairs of these vertices. A transformation can be instigated by translating the vertex and subsequently distributing the change throughout the Form Topology curve network graph.

As the position of vertices corresponds to a control point on a curve in the Curve Network, it must respect any attributes which constrain its position. As vertices lie at the intersection of a number of curves, its position may be constrained by a number of planes as defined by any surface attributes. As planes can generate a significant amount of constraint, the Form Topology curve network is analysed to identify any plane attributes and any faces with planar geometry within the Form Topology graph. Planes associated with the initially translated vertices need to be repositioned first with respect to the applied change because the update of the remaining vertices will respect these planes when the transformation is distributed. Once any relevant planes have been updated, the remaining vertices respect planar constraints as follows:

- Vertices associated with a single plane can only be moved by the translation component parallel to the plane.
- Vertices associated with two planes are constrained to the line defined by the intersection of the two planes and can only be moved by the translation component parallel to the line.
- Vertices associated with three or more planes must lie at the intersection of the planes and cannot be moved.

Once an initial vertex has been selected for change, it must pass the translation on to neighbouring vertices through adjacent edges. The translation may be affected by any attributes the curve geometry associated with the edge. Three different types of edge geometry can be identified and a rule for each case can be defined controlling how a translation at a source vertex may affect a destination vertex at the other end of the edge:

- Free Form edges have one or more free control points associated with the curve geometry representing the edge. As this edge is free to move about under the user control, the translation applied to a vertex at one end of the edge is not transferred to the adjacent vertex.
- Edges representing straight lines have no free control points. Consequently, only the translation component normal to the line is passed on to the adjacent vertex allowing the edge to change length and position but not direction.
- Edges representing blends have no free control points but are shaped by attributes affecting the curve tangents present at the terminating vertices. A number of rules are possible, but to ensure the overall size is maintained, the translation is transferred along the edge without modification.

When a translation is being distributed around the Form Topology graph, a vertex could potentially receive a translation from a more than one neighbouring vertex. This means that the distribution must be carefully done to make sure the translation is passed around in a synchronised manner, this is achieved using a breadth first search. The following procedure is used.

1. The initial selected vertices are translated and are collected into an input array.
2. Each vertex in the input array passes its translation on associated edges which have adjacent vertices that have not been translated. The edge modifies the translation based on the edge geometry rules, stores the result and collects the adjacent vertex into an output array. The vertex is marked as transformed.
3. Each vertex in the output array checks its associated edges for translations, and calculates the average translation. The translation is constrained to any planes associated with the vertex.
4. The output array becomes the input array and the procedure returns to step 2 until all vertices have been processed.

Fig.8: Translation of vertex 'V' is distributed along the edges using a breadth first search. The translation is adjusted based on the geometrical definition of the underlying curve. In the case of freeform edges, further distribution of the translation is terminated.

7.2.2. Transformation of Free Control Points associated with Form Topology Graph Edges

After the vertices have been processed, the new position of free control points associated with each edge is calculated using the technique described in 7.1 for curve segments.

Fig.9: Vertex translation is subsequently transferred to the curve geometry associated with each adjacent edge.

7.2.3. Transformation of Free Control Points associated with Form Topology Graph Faces.

Although it would be possible to update each curve segment associated with a Form Topology graph face using the process described in 7.1, the curve itself would only change based on the translations occurring at the points where curve connects with the edges of the face. Consequently, it could only respond to changes face edges to which it is not directly attached by receiving changes from the curves it references. We have already established that this is not a reliable method of transformation. What is required is to extend the concept that updates curve geometry associated with an edge with respect to its bounding vertices, to updating curve geometry on a face with respect to its bounding edges. This can be achieved by using a surface defined across the face and generating two surfaces, one representing the initial state of the Form Topology and one the transformed Form Topology after vertices and edges have been updated. By projecting each free control point onto the surface and

subsequently identifying the parametric location the point, the translation applied to the free control point can be determined by the change of position of the projected pointed as it moves to the transformed surface at the same parametric location. As the free form faces of the Form Topology curve network are unlikely to be four sided, it's necessary to blend a multi-sided surface, in this case a Coons patch using Gregory's method, *Gregory (1982)*, across the face. This transformation may be extended by using an additional parameter to bulge or flatten the surface and can be used to control the volumetric properties of a hull form independently of changes experienced through the face edges. This is discussed more in 8.2.

Fig.10: Edge deformation is transferred into a multisided surface blended across the faces, (left). The difference in the surface in the pre- and post-transformed form topology curve network is used to deform curve geometry associated with the face (right).

7.2.4. Reconnection of Curves in the Curve Network

As the Form Topology curve network is deformed, it may not be possible for certain curves to continue to be connect to referenced curves, for example, if the curve plane no longer intersects with the referenced curve or the update causes curves to overlap, invalidating the curve network topology and preventing the surface patches from been generated correctly. Consequently, once the Form Topology curve network is deformed a reconnection process needs to be applied to validate correct connections. At the time of writing a process for achieving this has been proposed but not yet investigated.

7.2.5. Parametric Transformation of Linear Dimensions

Once curves in the Form Topology are tagged, vertices associated with specific parameters can be found by searching at the intersection of key curves. For example, the forward end of the deck may be found by looking for the intersection of the flat of side curve with deck boundary of the surface. The values of design parameter can be then be established by measuring the either the absolute position of Form Topology graph vertices or relative positions between a number of vertices. Changes to parametric values can then be applied as vertex translations. In some cases, it may be possible to directly assign the change in value to one of the coordinate components of the translation. For example, to increase the breadth of a vessel, the increase could be assigned as a transverse translation of all vertices associated with the parallel middle body, Fig. 11.

Fig.11: The curve network resulting from a change in breadth applied to vertices within the parallel middle body at the deck.

In other cases, it may be necessary to devise an algorithm to distribute the change across a number of vertices. For example, in changing the bilge radius, it will be necessary to calculate a variety of different translations to reposition the vertices terminating the bilge radius arc moving their position along the flat of side and flat of bottom planes, accounting for rise of floor etc, if present.

7.2.6. Interactive Transformation

The vertices of the Form Topology Curve Network may also be manipulated using the mouse providing another way of interacting with the definition in addition to directly manipulating the free control points on each curve. However, considering the amount of processing required to present the transformation interactively and the fact that the Form Topology Curve Network quickly becomes badly deformed when indiscriminate changes are made, its often better to restrict changes to the subtle transformations that can be achieved using parameters.

8. Using the Form Topology Curve Network to make Hydrostatic Transformations

The Form Topology curve network offers some advantages over the techniques discussed in the introduction. By breaking down the surface definition into several regions, we can identify the areas that can be deformed to change the volumetric properties, such as the free form faces in the entrance and the run and those that cannot be transformed, such as those in the parallel middle body. Furthermore, if the available adjustment within individual regions is not sufficient, we may look at more extensive deformation of the Form Topology curve network in order to achieve the hydrostatic parameters that the designer has in mind. The technique may also provide the designer with a number of different deformation options with which to achieve the change.

Fundamentally, the Form Topology curve network, with respect to ship hull forms, offers two main techniques for adjusting the hydrostatic properties of the hull form, similar to the approaches described by Lackenby:

- The extents of the parallel middle body may be adjusted in a manner similar to 1-Cp and may be achieved through the Form Topology curve network by moving the vertices on the midship section curves at either end of the parallel middle body (PMB) longitudinally. Unlike, the 1-Cp method, the deformation does not have to be applied uniformly across the entrance or run. If no further vertices are moved, the change is restricted to the movement of the midship section curves only and no deformation takes place at the ends of the vessel or to deck shape. Further rules may be introduced which translate the position where the flat of side meets the deck, either by the same amount that the midship section is displaced or by maintaining the ratio of the position of this point between the end of the vessel and the parallel middle body.
- The free form faces of the Form Topology curve network in the entrance and the run may be adjusted. The deformation only affects the curves crossing the free form face region so that, unlike the Lackenby method, there is no deformation in the deck, flat of side or flat of bottom. This approach offers a much more subtle change than Lackenby's method.

These two approaches may be combined together when making more extensive changes to the hull form.

8.1. The Architecture of Iterative Hydrostatic Transformations

The techniques documented by Lackenby are restricted to uniform longitudinal translations using simple functions without discontinuities and were designed to be applied to hull offsets. Consequently, it was possible to develop an analytical model to guide the magnitude of the deformation to achieve the desired set of volumetric properties without too much difficulty. However, when these transformations are applied to modern hull surface representations the analytical models of the transformations are not as accurate as it is necessary to use a number of iterations to achieve the

desired volumetric properties to a desirable degree of accuracy.

Care must be taken when using iterative techniques because each iteration is often expensive to compute. With respect to the Form Topology curve network, the computing expense associated with each iteration is significant as it is necessary to compute the surface resulting from the curve network, the Form Topology curve network and integrate over the surface to identify the volumetric properties. A significant amount of effort was given to optimising the processing that occurs during each update, although it was found that the surface integration was the most expensive element. As each iteration is expensive, the number of iterations must be minimised. This can be achieved by using the following recommendations:

8.1.1. Explore the limits of the Deformation prior to iterating

Bracketing is a very effecting way of controlling iterative techniques constraining an iterative search to a closed parameter space. As well as creating a very efficient way of managing the algorithm so that it arrives at a solution, it also allows the algorithm to identify if the requested solution is outside the parameter space and terminate further iterations. However, efficient search algorithms are often generic and it is often not possible to tailor them to the specific issues associated with the application. The process of identifying the brackets needs to both decide on the appropriate range of deformation and can check that the designer has requested a solution that can be found in the bracketed parameter space.

In order to identify the range of deformation associated with face in the Form Topology Graph, an iterative technique is used to deform curves to identify the point when undesirable shape begins to appear. This process itself must be bracketed. In this case, the brackets are set to be artificially large and the definition curve algorithms are robust enough to deal with significant deformation beyond what would be deemed suitable for a hull form. Subsequently, hydrostatics obtained when the hull surface is generated at the minimum and maximum range of deformation identify the range of change available in the displacement and longitudinal centre of buoyancy (LCB).

8.1.2. Develop a Model to Guide or Simplify Iterations

When controlling displacement and LCB, two control parameters are required in the entrance and run to change hull shape which suggests the use of multi-parameter iteration algorithms. However, this can be avoided by introducing an empirical model which translates displacement and LCB into two independent parameters. IntelliHull introduced a simple model which achieved this, although the approach used by Lackenby's is more advanced converting displacement and LCB into values of prismatic coefficient in the entrance and run. The introduction of this technique reduces the number of iterations required and simplifies the iteration algorithm implementation. It also means that numerical quantities used in the software remain meaningful to the problem. Before these models can be used, they often need to be initialised with hydrostatic properties from the hull form. The method introduced in IntelliHull is initialised using the information from the bracketing process described previously.

8.2. Extending the control of Surfaces blended across faces of the Form Topology Graph

The iterative process used to change the shape of the hull surface requires the use of two control parameters which will be adjusted, deforming the hull surface, to achieve a desired displacement and LCB. If the underlying geometry of the Form Topology curve network is to remain unchanged, two free form faces in the Form Topology Graph, from the entrance and the run respectively, are selected with which to modify the hydrostatic properties of the hull surface. Each face must expose a parameter with which the curves associated with the face may be deformed.

As the Form Topology curve network is to remain unchanged, the edges of the surface blended across the face will also remain unchanged. Consequently, the formulation of the surface blended across the

face must be extended to introduce a deformation parameter creating either a bulge or flattening of the curve geometry associated with the face.

Fig.12: By introducing a bulging parameter into the surfaces blending across the faces of the form topology curve network, hydrostatic changes of the hull form can be introduced.

Gregory's multi sided Coons Patch can be extending to introduce the deformation parameter using existing principles in the formulation. In the technique, a local surface is generated between each pair of edges. Using a parameterisation known as a "footprint", the concept of which is best described in *Gao (2005)*, a point is calculated on each local surface and combined using a weighted least squares to produce the final surface representation. Obviously, the surface can be linearly offset by adding a uniform vector to each point found local surface. However, a bulging effect can be achieved by using the weighted least squares combination and weighting parameterisation so that the offset applied in the centre of the surface is maximum and reduced to zero at the edges. The magnitude of this offset can be adjusted by the associated control parameter, with negative values causing the surface to flatten.

8.3 Providing the Designer with Hydrostatic Transformation Capability

In combination, the Form Topology curve network and the ability to modify the geometry of curves associated with freeform faces of the Form Topology graph provides the designer with a powerful capability for varying the hydrostatic properties of a hull form. However, it must be packaged in way which hides complexity and makes it accessible in during the design process. Reviewing the significant design parameters affecting hydrostatics, displacement (including C_p and C_b), LCB, Length of PMB and position of PMB appear to be the principle quantities. Various combinations of these parameters can be used to invoke the hydrostatic changes previously described. A transformation schedule was developed which favoured changed to the PMB over modifications wholly within the entrance and run unless PMB was constrained. Some combinations of parameters require the PMB to be changed prior to modifying the freeform faces in the entrance and run. In situations where the PMB is partially constrained, i.e. only the extent of the PMB or the location of the PMB is constrained, a further iterative procedure is used to ensure that the amount of change applied to the freeform faces is balanced between each end of the vessel after the PMB has been updated.

Finally, as only the extreme limits of Displacement and LCB are found when identifying the brackets, not all combinations of these values are possible resulting in a failure of the iteration process. Rather than flag an error to the designer, a process originally introduced into IntelliHull finds the closest solution to the desired hydrostatic properties. Consequently, the designer is able to understand more about the volumetric capabilities of the hull form.

9. Designing the Hull Transformation Software Experience

One of the striking observations about many commercial hull design tools, given the importance of

hull transformations in the ship design process, is the poor experience it provides the designer. In the best of cases, transformations tools are provided separately to the definition experience. In the worst of cases, the designer may not have any control over how the results of the transformation are applied to the overall design or the surface may require a significant amount of preparation before reliable changes can be made. If there is any question over the robustness of the transformation tool, with the possibility that the surface definition could be ruined, the designer is unlikely to choose to use it.

To address issues found in commercial systems, the hull transformation experience in which the methods described previously are implemented was designed to be closely integrated into the surface definition process. It is provided as an extra tool that can be accessed at any point and aims to minimise the chance of breaking the designer's thought process or 'flow'. To provide a quality transformation experience, two key processes must be provided by the software.

9.1. Management of the Surface Definition throughout the Transformation Process

The designer may have spent many hours manipulating a hull surface but may then be faced with making a major change using a transformation. There are several reasons why a transformation could fail. The applied transformation could be inaccurate, it did not achieve the designer's expectations, the requested deformation could have been beyond what the surface definition could support and has undesirable features or due to poor software robustness. Consequently, the designer will need to return to the original definition as start again. The implementation of an Undo/Redo facility could achieve this, but it is not possible to implement any reviewing capabilities of the design changes as only one view of the surface definition can be seen at any time. To support the review of design changes and to ensure that the original definition is isolated from changes, a copy of the original surface definition is taken and each change produces a further copy in a stack. Each copy is associated with a description of the change. The designer can select different transformations in the stack providing the ability to go back or compare the definition with respect to the original definition. Once the designer has explored the options, a range of choices can be made. The changes can be applied to the original definition, to accept the change as a new surface definition or to abandon the process all together. Throughout all of these activities the original surface definition remains untouched until the designer commits or rejects the changes.

9.2. Review of Transformation Changes

One feature which is seldom provided when transforming a hull surface is the ability to compare it with the original design. Within the design environment it is possible to review geometrical features, but also check the hydrostatic properties and section area curve. When different copies of the design are held, it is possible to overlay the changes with respect to the original design both graphically and numerically. This provides the designer with confidence that the transformed provides the expected capabilities prior to accepting the change. However, it should be noted that care must be taken with the amount of information displayed on screen that the designer is not overloaded with information. Consequently, it is necessary to provide with the option of turning on the additional review features and begin from a minimal display state.

10. Observations

Although development of this technique is incomplete it has shown itself to be robust from the beginning. Prior to the introduction of any parametric control, interactive manipulation was used to translate the position of vertices and, as this approach is often capable of making uncontrollably significant modifications, the method had to be robust enough to cope with this level of distortion. The main outstanding item of development remains to be the ability to reconnect curves when a change results in improper references in the main curve network. In isolation this would be a significant risk to the success of the work. However, techniques for automatic curve generation and connection are already available to the designer when creating a hull surface definition and the intention is to use a similar approach when transforming the curve definition.

Fig 13: A prototype of the intended user interface illustrating the ability to compare the original design with respect to the changed design, both graphically and numerically.

In the author's experience, complex hull surface design operations often result in poor performance and limited robustness. However, this approach seems to go against this trend. The use of topology in any process increases its complexity significantly, certainly when comparing this approach to those introduced by Lackenby. In this particular case, topology is used to capture the features of the hull form allowing the geometrical transformations to be localised to specific regions of the surface definition and, as a consequence, the geometric operations are kept simple.

Due to the level of complexity encountered when dealing with topology, the author perceived that there was a significant risk that the approach would not succeed. This was the first opportunity to use Form Topology explicitly in combination with a surface definition technique based on curve networks since this was identified as the only way of extending IntelliHull. In IntelliHull, it was necessary to encode the Form Topology into the technique itself and the reliance on producing a single B-Spline limited the range of shapes. In this development, the Form Topology is identified from the curve network definition itself and from this the parametric transformations that are appropriate to the hull form are identified. At present, if a hull surface that did not conform to the tradition prismatic shape of a commercial hull form was used in this transformation it is unlikely that there would be many useful parameters available to the designer. However, it would still be possible to deform the hull surface using this technique using interactive manipulation.

Although this approach departs significantly to those documented by Lackenby, his methods have proved invaluable when it came to devising routines to control the hydrostatic properties of the hull surface and in many ways could be described as a "first principles approach" to changing hydrostatic properties. It situations where it was possible transform the desired hydrostatic properties into prismatic coefficient for the entrance and run, it was possible to incorporate Lackenby's methods directly into the iteration routines. Consequently, Lackenby should be considered recommended reading for anyone attempting to develop routines to systematically change the hydrostatic properties of hull forms even if the techniques described do not apply directly.

11. Concluding Remarks

Although development on this hull transformation technique still continues, the following statements

can be made about the principles used to develop this unique approach.

- Topology is a valuable tool that can be used to introduce alternative ways of manipulating hull surfaces beyond the direct manipulation of the basic surface definition.
- Form Topology can be used to identify specific parts of the hull form and subdivides it into a number of different regions allowing specific operations to be applied to the associated surface definition.
- It continues to be good advice to keep hull surface generation or manipulation rules as simple as possible to ensure robust performance and a wide range of applicability.
- Although rarely used for hull surface representation, Multi-sided surfaces have proved to be invaluable when trying to control surface shapes over the arbitrarily shaped regions within the Form Topology.
- The principles described by Lackenby in 1950 are still applicable to modern hull surface definition and remain valuable when devising routines for transforming the hull with respect to the hydrostatics properties.

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Aerodynamic Optimization of Superstructures and Components

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Abstract

Ships feature superstructures and components with steps, recesses and styling surfaces that cause detached flow phenomena. A favorable air flow becomes a design criterion, particularly for mega-yachts and cruise ferries. For instance, exhaust gases should be kept from passengers and crew. Within this paper it is discussed how Computer Aided Design (CAD) and Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) are coupled for aerodynamic design. The FRIENDSHIP-Framework for parametric modeling and process control and ANSYS CFX for viscous flow simulations were combined. The aerodynamics of a mega-yacht was studied. Systematic refinements were undertaken to clarify the levels of detail for resolving geometry and fluid domain. Subsequently, the yacht's funnel was optimized to improve emissions.

1. Introduction

Functional surfaces such as ship hulls, propellers and appendages are increasingly described parametrically and formally optimized with regard to their hydrodynamic performance by tightly integrating Computer Aided Design (CAD) and Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), for example Brenner *et al.* (2009) and Harries *et al.* (2006). A similar process can be established for the aerodynamics optimization of superstructures and components (section 2). While energy efficiency is of paramount importance in hydrodynamic design, comfort, habitability and aesthetics are of higher significance in ship aerodynamics, particularly for cruise ferries and yachts. Consequently, most superstructures and components feature steps, recesses, styling surfaces etc. which, normally, are not favorable for a clean air flow.

In this paper the parametric modeling and aerodynamic optimization of superstructures and components are discussed. The *FRIENDSHIP-Framework* was applied for the geometric modeling of a contemporary mega-yacht. A parametric definition was established to allow the efficient variation of geometry with a low number of free variables yet surfaces of high quality (section 3). The geometric model was coupled to the viscous flow solver *ANSYS CFX* for flow field analyses in typical modes of operation, for instance the yacht at anchorage with winds straight from the bow or from smaller sideward angles. The hot exhaust from the funnel and its downwind dispersion were studied.

A systematic de-featuring was undertaken to clarify at which level of detail the superstructure needed to be resolved for meaningful flow simulation (section 4). Based on the insight found an aerodynamic optimization was undertaken for the funnel's pipes and spoilers to improve the emissions in regions where too high gas concentrations are usually rather unwelcome (section 5) – as they spoil fresh fruit cocktails.

2. Simulation-driven design

The traditional process in fluid dynamic design is, firstly, to develop a geometric model of the envisioned product and, secondly, to undertake a simulation of the flow field associated. While the product's performance remains unsatisfactory (and resources still permit) the geometry is iteratively changed, often intuitively by an experienced designer, and the new flow field is assessed once more. In this sense modeling is the driver of the process and, not atypically, up to ten variants are studied.

The design process is changed notably by making the simulation the governing driver of the process, *Harries (2008)*. In simulation-driven design as depicted in Fig.1 the most favorable geometry is derived from simulations and associated performance assessment. An initial model, be it a CAD representation or a suitable description of the fluid domain such as a volume grid, is still needed but changes are usually brought about from a controller other than a human being. Such controllers are (optimization) strategies that screen the design space in a meaningful way. Prominent strategies are designs-of-experiment such as SOBOL to explore and genetic algorithms like MOGA to exploit many design options. This then results in hundreds and even thousands of variants from which the best designs can be selected, *Abt et al. (2007)*.

Fig.1: Process of simulation-driven design

Naturally, the number of variants depends on both the response time of the individual simulation and the sheer computer power available to do the number-crunching. In ship hydrodynamics it is considered state-of-the-art to utilize potential flow codes for systematic studies, assuming inviscid and incompressible flow. This gives reasonable accuracy for low computational time before further experimental work commences. Unfortunately, potential flow codes cannot be employed to predict detached and re-circulating flows as found in ship aerodynamics. Therefore, a viscous flow simulation needs to be carried out. This leads to additional effort in geometric modeling, grid generation and flow simulation but yields physical quantities in the entire flow domain such as velocity, pressure and exhaust gas concentration. Viscous flow simulations on the basis of solving the Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations frequently require several hours (to several days) of CPU time on a single computer. Consequently, a large set of variants can best be investigated on a cluster of machines equipped with the necessary CFD licenses.

The design process of Fig.1 was set up within the *FRIENDSHIP-Framework* which served as (i) the geometric modeling engine, (ii) the controller for the external flow code and (iii) distributor for remote computing on an external cluster. The flow simulations were performed with *ANSYS CFX* on unstructured grids.

3. Modeling of geometry and flow simulation

While aerodynamic studies are not so common for merchant ships, the situation is different for research vessels and passenger ships, in particular cruise ferries and mega-yachts. Here, an important acceptance criterion is a nice flow field in regions where people spend their time. A nice flow field means, for instance, that the exhaust plume does not reach the sun deck or pool area and, furthermore, that there is neither strong nor alternating downwash.

For the study presented here a contemporary mega-yacht with L_{PP} of around 100 m was considered. The superstructure predominantly consists of curved surfaces and was modeled at a level of detail

commonly used in wind tunnel tests, including recesses, styling surfaces, railings, pipes, spoilers / winglets, masts, lights, antennas and radars as depicted in Fig.2, Fig.3 and Fig.5.

3.1. Parametric modeling

An important aspect for a competitive design process is to be able to quickly realize changes in order to deliver an excellent product. Parametric models allow capturing the essence of a product with as few descriptors as possible, thereby reducing the design space and guaranteeing a certain shape quality, *Abt et al. (2007)* and *Palluch et al. (2009)* for elaborations. Fig.2 illustrates the parameters used for the geometric model of the mega-yacht's funnel. Here the parameters define the exhaust pipes along with spoilers. Typical parameters describe positions, lengths, angles etc. which can be addressed within an optimization as free variables. Parameters change between meaningful bounds, i.e., their upper and lower permissible values. However, unlike in structural optimization no changes of topology are considered. In other words: During an optimization an element such as a spoiler may become larger or smaller but it cannot simply pop up without having been included in the model.

Fig.2: Parametric model of a mega-yacht's funnel
(left: important parameters defining geometry, right: use of selected parameters as free variables)

3.2. Grid generation

Taking into account a superstructure's geometry in detail leads to rather complex grids with a huge number of small cells. This decreases the acceptable time step for transient flow calculations and, thus, increases the computational time. In addition, the many components and their necessary levels of detail bring about an elaborate grid generation processes. An investigation performed by *Vesting (2009)* clearly demonstrated that a block-structured approach would be tedious and instable due to the necessary fragmentation of topology even for simplified decks. Therefore, unstructured grids were favored.

Fig.3 depicts the situation. The fluid domain was discretized with tetrahedrons and prisms on the basis of automated grid generation procedures. The boundary layer was refined by using prism cells. A reasonably coarse element size was chosen for the aerodynamic boundary layer according to *El Moctar (2001)*. The density of the grid points was increased at the leeward site of the funnel so as to better resolve the expected exhaust plume. The domain size was chosen according to *Schmode (2002)* with one times the characteristic length L_{PP} upwind and twice L_{PP} sideways and downwind behind the ship. In upward direction, the domain boundary was placed L_{PP} above the water plane. For symmetric inflow, the water plane, the top and the sides were taken as no slip boundaries. For asymmetric inflow, the portside face was included as an inlet while the starboard face was treated as an outlet.

Fig.3: Close up of unstructured grid for decks and components
(left: cells on center plane, right: surface mesh)

3.3. Flow analysis

The flow associated with the exhaust gases from a ship's funnel is influenced by a large number of factors, for instance (apparent) wind velocity and direction, exhaust gas velocity and temperature and the interaction of hot gases with ambient air. The flow is usually characterized as fully three-dimensional, highly turbulent, separated and sometimes unsteady.

Table I summarized the flow situation considered. It represents a common situation for a yacht at anchor or in dynamic-positioning mode. Mega-yachts in the range of 100 m often feature underwater outlets for exhaust gases. Nevertheless, at zero speed they are commonly not used. Instead, the whole exhaust of the auxiliaries and the main engine is led through the funnel. A rather typical situation is the yacht in calm weather with low wind speeds kept stationary in a bay.

Table I: Flow situation

Quantity	Value	
Exhaust flow rate	29200 m ³ /h	assumption (*)
Diameter of exhaust pipes	0.35 m	assumption (**)
Exhaust velocity	5.269 m/s	from (*) and (**)
Wind velocity	2.058 m/s	assumption 2 Bft, ship at anchor

The flow around the ships superstructure was modeled with a homogeneous two phase Eulerian-Eulerian model where a common flow field is shared by all phases with the same velocity and temperature field as well as the same turbulence properties. The air stream was modeled as a continuous phase with the exhaust as a dispersed one. The Eulerian-Eulerian model was utilized since it permits to model a larger number of small particles in the main flow as compared to Lagrangian particle tracing, keeping in mind limited computational resources.

Cengiz (2008) analyzed the exhaust of a four-stroke Diesel engine. At the engine's test bench 75% of the exhaust was nitrogen oxide when using common diesel fuel. Thus, in the CFD simulation the exhaust phase was idealized as a nitrogen oxide to consider buoyancy.

3.4. Validation

Kulkarni et al (2006) investigated the exhaust gas flow for a generic frigate with different superstructure configurations both numerically and experimentally. The CFD simulation was carried out on a tetrahedral grid of approximately 0.8 million cells. A k-ε model was applied for turbulence. It was observed that for headwinds with angles of attack between 17° and 30° the bow played an important role regarding the downwash in the funnel's lee.

Schmode (2002) applied a RNG k- ϵ model to capture the turbulence, using a tetrahedral grid, too. In this case the constant $C_{\epsilon 1}$ is replaced by a functional coefficient $C_{\epsilon 1RNG}$. *Schmode (2002)* showed the influence of baffle elements to account for turbulence stimulating elements like railings without the need to resolve them in detail. These elements are semi-permeable, and *Schmode* changed them systematically to examine their influence. It turned out that the baffles were able to reflect resistance forces well. Yet, the influence on turbulence did not show. As a consequence, and because of a full turbulent flow in original scale, baffle elements were omitted here.

Fig.4 shows the re-calculated flow field for *Kulkarni's* frigate model as a vector plot of velocity in the center plane. The best CFD results in comparison to the wind tunnel tests stem from a RNG k- ϵ model with the following values: $C_{RNG\epsilon 1} = 1.44 - f_{\eta}$, $C_{RNG\epsilon 2} = 1.9$ and $C_{\mu} = 0.09$. It can be nicely seen that the CFD captures the flow patterns found in the wind tunnel quite well, underlining the validity of the numerical approach.

Fig.4: Comparison of numerical and experimental exhaust investigation (left: simulation with *ANSYS CFX* from *Vesting (2009)*, right: photo from *Kulkarni et al (2006)*)

4. Resolution study

Aiming at fast turn-around time and high number of variants for optimization, a geometry resolution study was carried out to identify the lowest level of acceptable detail without losing accuracy of the results. A mega-yacht, resembling a contemporary design, was modeled with the *FRIENDSHIP-Framework* at three different levels of detail: *model A* of fine resolution, *model B* with intermediate definition and *model C* with an approximation of the actual shapes.

Fig.5 (top) shows *model A* with the highest level of detail. This geometry includes a certain number of curved surfaces with recesses in the front for sideways, nocks and sundecks and in the aft part for dining places and the swimming platform. However, the stairs in the aft part to the swimming platform are just adumbrated. In general, this model is close to a modern cruising yacht and the level of detail corresponds to that taken for wind tunnel test.

Fig.5 (center) shows *model B* with medium level of detail. Most of the curved surfaces are replaced by developable surfaces featuring straight lines in the vertical direction. Decks are reduced and some recesses are neglected. However, the contours and the radomes around the funnel are kept. Fig.5 (bottom) shows the geometry of deck C. This deck features the most simplified level of detail but, from an aerodynamics point of view, also the most radical form changes. The superstructure is built up from simple boxes in which just the global dimensions are maintained. Thus, the swimming

platform and the characteristic bend at the funnel deck disappear while the deck overhangs are kept.

A systematic series of CFD simulations was conducted for all three models with the flow situation summarized in Table I. Six different angles of attack φ , namely 0° , 10° , 15° , 20° , 25° and 30° , were considered, giving rise to 18 configurations. The CFD computations converged well with less than 100 iterations to hit the convergence criteria. Only one computation, namely deck C with $\varphi = 10^\circ$, could not be solved with a steady solution method.

Fig.5: Different resolutions of superstructure and components
(top: *model A* – detailed deck with fine resolution of geometry,
center: *model B* – deck with medium resolution, keeping deck characteristics in vertical projection,
bottom: *model C* – crude deck with low resolution, omitting various components)

Table II presents the properties of the different grids which were created for the three different deck models. Since the domain needed to be discretized for asymmetric computations, even at the lowest level of detail the grid already had more than 1.6 million cells. (No grid refinement was undertaken.)

Table II: Grid sizes of different decks

Deck	Number of cells	Cells on the surface
<i>model A</i>	2 857 035	6.36%
<i>model B</i>	2 065 313	6.08%
<i>model C</i>	1 608 374	4.37%

The numerical investigation showed amazing similarities for all three deck models far behind the ships both for the symmetrical and the asymmetrical inflow conditions. Fig.6 presents the superstructure from behind and the velocity vectors on a plane far behind the ship. Two contra rotating vortices can be observed for all models. Nevertheless, the flow field, turbulence and dispersion of exhaust gas near the superstructure varied considerably with deck resolution. Fig.7 gives a picture of the changes in the streamlines. For *model A* the streamlines nicely follow the curved surfaces while for models B and C the streamlines are more and more straightened out by the plane decks. The sharp edges of the decks B and C cause vortices which enlarge the concentration of exhaust gas on the lower decks. Fig.8 confirms that global similarities are found in the far field also for asymmetric inflow while the near field is heavily influenced by the resolution of geometry.

Fig.6: Flow patterns far downstream (left: *model A*, center: *model B*, right: *model C*)

Fig.7: Longitudinal flow patterns around decks and components (left: *model A*, center: *model B*, right: *model C*)

Fig.8: Streamlines from around the funnel for oblique (apparent) wind (left: *model A*, center: *model B*, right: *model C*)

Fig.9 gives a closer look on the flow around the superstructure. The velocities are plotted in a plane close to the funnel for *model A* and *model C*. Both models give rise to similar vortices beside the ship. However, *model A* shows an expanded field of higher velocities parallel to the ship's side, which redirects the flow from the funnel.

Fig.9: Transverse flow patterns around decks and components (left: *model A*, right: *model C*)

Finally, Fig.10 displays a diagram for the exhaust concentrations of models B and C in comparison to those of *model A* for symmetrical inflow. The values were taken on the lowest deck at several sideway positions (y-coordinate), the centre plane being denoted with "0". It can be seen that *model B* exhibits lower dispersion while deck C features a higher exhaust gas concentration than A. The same effect could be noted for different angles of attack. However, the differences decreased with height (increasing z-coordinate) which seems plausibly explained by the smaller distance to the funnel.

Concluding this investigation, it can be stated that a geometric resolution similar to a wind tunnel's model is advisable. Reducing details so as to speed up computations appears to be problematic as the flow's near field is tangibly affected which could then be misleading during an optimization. Positively seen, a ship's superstructure is influenced by all surface particulars, giving rise to optimization potential.

Fig.10: Comparison of exhaust concentration for different deck resolutions

5. Feasibility study for funnel optimization

An automated optimization was carried out to improve the dispersion of exhaust behind the funnel. Since the necessary resolution of geometry and a sufficient grid density seemed to be beyond the scope of a feasibility study, only the vicinity of the funnel was taken into account. Thus, a bare funnel tower was created with parameters according to Fig.2 and the necessary geometric resolution identified in section 4. A design-of-experiment (DoE) was performed to find the most favorable funnel with regard to gas concentration on the upper deck – where passengers and crew are not amused if they are to inhale unhealthy fumes.

5.1. Process details

The *FRIENDSHIP-Framework* was utilized to automatically generate the geometric variants, to exports these as IGES files for further processing and then, ultimately, to collect the data of interest from the CFD simulations, Fig.11 and Fig.12. The coupling between the modeling engine *FRIENDSHIP-Framework*, the grid generator *ICEM* and the flow solver *ANSYS CFX* was realized via the *FRIENDSHIP-Framework's* generic integration mechanism, see *Abt et al. (2009)*.

The ANSYS programs can be started in batch mode and run by ASCII type script files. Commands that are used, for instance, for grid generation and for CFD set up can be recorded in these scripts and then be run again and again without any manual interaction. In a generic integration any previously recorded script or input file can be treated as a template. Using these templates any change in geometry triggers an export and new input files are written to the actual design directory by the *FRIENDSHIP-Framework*. The script files are created by replacing values in the corresponding templates, for example to update the path to the current geometry. The output files that hold the CFD results of interest are then parsed by the *FRIENDSHIP-Framework*. To do so representative output files are taken as templates and anchors are set from which data are identified via their positions within the file, see *Abt et al. (2009)* for details. Importantly, whenever geometry is varied the number of surfaces and their names, i.e., the domain's topology, are maintained. In this way the grid generator is able to produce a new grid of similar size that fits the new shape.

If the calculations are done on a remote computer or cluster – as done in the present investigation for faster turn-around time – the *FRIENDSHIP-Framework* can be employed to distribute the computations. Here, the allocation and result management was handled through a secure shell protocol.

Fig.11: File and execution control for external tool, here ANSYS CFX, as applied by the FRIENDSHIP-Framework via Generic Integration

Fig.12: Process of simulation-driven design by coupling the FRIENDSHIP-Framework and ANSYS CFX

5.2. Selected results

In order to observe the influence of the geometric parameters on exhaust dispersion, a plane was created in the wake field of the funnel. Here the concentration of exhaust gas was averaged. This objective was selected from the results file as a quality criterion. It should be noted, however, that the size and the position of this plane were chosen as good guesses. Thus the results can just give qualitative assumption of the parameter influence and should not be considered as an ultimate measure of merit.

About 50 variants of the funnel geometry were created automatically by a SOBOL algorithm within the *FRIENDSHIP-Framework*. Six parameters describing geometries close to the initial exhaust outlet were varied. The overall calculation time took approximately 10 hours on a cluster with 12 processors, essentially making the work an overnight investigation.

Fig.13 shows the normalized parameter distribution for the six best variants along with corresponding exhaust gas concentration. The change of parameter l_{Pipe} is relatively small while the parameters $angle_{Winglet}$ and $angle_{Pipe}$ vary quite a bit without exciting a strong influence on the exhaust concentration. The result of the parameter $angle_{Spoiler}$ has to be treated with some caution. The parameter is naturally coupled to the length of the deflector and, hence, the influence of the angle is necessarily small if the deflector is short. Fig.14 shows the differences between the best variant Soboll29 (right side) and the worst variant Soboll14 (left side). For Soboll14 the exhaust gas is transported back to the funnel by a recirculation while the exhaust discharges directly for Soboll29. Major changes of geometry are the length and the angle of the deflector as well as the angle of the exhaust pipes. Fig.15 gives a photo-realistic impression of the aerodynamics of the mega-yacht at anchor.

Fig.13: Normalized distribution of free variables and objective

Fig.14: Comparison of designs and exhaust dispersion

Fig.15: Illustration of exhaust for a fine deck model

6. Conclusion

Parametric modeling, viscous flow simulation and aerodynamic optimization of superstructures and components were discussed. The optimization process follows the principles already established for the simulation-driven design of ship hulls, propellers and appendages. However, more care needs to be given to geometric resolution. While nearly all underwater shapes are rather smooth, most decks, deckhouses and equipment commonly feature a lot of minor entities such as openings, steps, recesses, handrails, wires, horns, lights etc. In order to keep the necessary volume grids moderate these details were neglected. A resolution similar to a typical scale model for experimental work was chosen, meaning that all major entities were taken into account with their actual shapes. A systematic study in which decks were replaced by approximating boxes showed a heavy shape-dependence of the local flow patterns. Therefore, a quick and rough layout cannot be utilized for a meaningful analysis. Rather, a finer resolution is needed similar to what is used in experiments. An automated optimization

of a zoomed in region, namely a mega-yacht's funnel, was undertaken. 50 different variants were created from a parametric model and analyzed with a coupled RANSE solver. The exhaust concentration behind the funnel could be tangibly reduced for a representative situation of the yacht at anchor encountering head-winds. The application nicely demonstrates the potential of simulation-driven design for superstructures and components.

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AUV Networks for Adaptive Area Coverage with Reliable Acoustic Communication Links

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Abstract

This paper presents a distributed cooperative algorithm for a team of autonomous underwater vehicles (AUVs). The overall mission goal for the AUV team is to defend an asset using detection sonars while maintaining the acoustic communication connectivity for the whole mission duration, even when environmental changes affect the vehicle devices. The performance of the algorithm is shown with respect to optimal geometric solutions and in scenarios characterized by long propagation delays in the acoustic communication.

1. Introduction

The increased reliability and efficiency of acoustic communication and the current technological development of Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs), is driving the development of Autonomous Ocean Sampling Networks (AOSN), and leading to an intense research in the field of distributed control and coordination of large set of underwater agents, *Akyildiz et al. (2005)*. However, the possibility of a coordinated control of a team of underwater vehicles still brings more challenges with respect to the terrestrial case, due to the remaining difficulties and constraints of the underwater scenario: acoustic communications cannot be always guaranteed and are strongly dependent on the environmental conditions of the mission area.

Within this paper we present a cooperative adaptive algorithm for the management of mobile nodes of an ad-hoc underwater network with the main objective of protecting an asset while maintaining reliable acoustic communication links among the team of agents. Each vehicle is considered to be equipped with a detection sonar for asset protection and with an acoustic modem for communication purposes. In addition, performance of the vehicles detection sonar and modem is time variant and depends on the spatial position in the covered area. The proposed approach makes the agents able to effectively protect the asset while adapting their position to changing environmental conditions. We describe the performance of the algorithm in terms of maximum area coverage guaranteed around the asset, by the team of agents, and we verify the behavior of the algorithm with respect to varying propagation delays and communication schemes adopted among the agents.

The paper is organized as follow: Section 2 describes the problem setting, in terms of mission goals and requirements and the proposed adaptive cooperative algorithm. In Section 3 we show through simulation the area coverage performance with respect to optimal geometric solutions and with varying propagation delays. Finally, conclusions are given in Section 4.

2. Problem setting and the distributed cooperative algorithm

Let us suppose that n autonomous vehicles are available, each of them equipped with an on board sonar for intrusion detection and with an acoustic modem for communication purposes. The overall mission goal is that of covering with the vehicle detection sonars the maximum possible area in the neighborhood of a given asset. Since the performance of both AUV devices depends on the local oceanographic conditions, we also suppose that each agent is equipped with a sensor able to measure the environment variability (e.g. Conductivity, Temperature, and Depth – CTD probe) and with an acoustic channel performance predictor to convert these measurements into communication

¹ ISME = Interuniversity Ctr. Integrated Systems for the Marine Environment

performance. The derivation of the sonar and communication range from environmental and geometric information on the channel is not treated here, but it can be pursued for instance with the approach described in *Caiti et al. (2009)*. In this regard, we consider these quantities as available information, and we assume that each agent is able to adapt its depth, when needed, to achieve the desired communication performance. We do not consider in what way this adaptation takes place, while, in the following, we restrict our analysis to a two-dimensional scenario. The area coverage problem is formalized as follows:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \min_{x_i} \sum_{i=1}^n \|x_a - x_i\|_2 \\ \|x_i - x_j\|_2 \geq R_D^i + R_D^j \\ \|x_i - x_j\|_2 \leq R_C^i \quad \text{for at least one } j \neq i \end{array} \right. \quad (1)$$

Solving (1) means to find the positions $x_i \in \mathfrak{R}^2$ of n agents that minimize the sum of the distance of the agents from the asset placed in $x_a \in \mathfrak{R}^2$, subjected to the constraints: (a) two vehicles, placed in x_i and x_j , cannot overlap their detection sonars ($R_D^i \geq 0$ is the maximum detection sonar range of vehicle i); (b) agent i has to move in order to keep at least one other agent within its communication range $R_C^i \geq 0$. We propose a distributed algorithm for a team of AUVs, able to solve (1), even when environmental variations change the sonar and the communication ranges during the evolution of the mission. In the algorithm the overall goal is not pre-programmed and it is obtained as the result of the emerging behavior of the team, defining simple rules to characterize the agents movements and actions.

2.1 Algorithm Description

Let us consider each vehicle dynamic represented by the simple discrete kinematic model:

$$x(t+1) = x(t) + u(t) \quad (2)$$

where $x(t) \in \mathfrak{R}^2$ is the robot position; $u(t) \in \mathfrak{R}^2$ is the control input to be defined such that, at each step, the vehicle maintains the communication connectivity with at least one other vehicle of the team, and ensures the best asset protection.

In the following we consider:

- $R_D^i(t)$ as the maximum detection sonar range for vehicle i at time t ;
- $R_C^i(t)$ as the maximum communication range achieved by vehicle i at time t ;
- $R_M^i(t) \geq R_D^i(t)$, as the maximum separation distance at which the i -th vehicle wants to keep its closest neighbor.

Having defined $R_C^i(t)$ as the maximum communication range of vehicle i , one vehicle has to be, at any time t , at a distance $d \leq R_C^i(t)$ in order to receive data from i . It is assumed that these quantities may be computed on-board the vehicle on the basis of the environmental measurements performed by the vehicle itself.

The proposed algorithm defines each vehicle behavior through simple rules, obtaining the overall

mission goal as the result of the emergent behavior of the team, *Caiti et al. (2007)*, *Martinez et al. (2007)*, *Tanner et al. (2003a)*. Specifically, each vehicle, at each given time frame moves in accordance to the following rules:

- rule #1. Move towards the critical asset
- rule #2. Move away from the closest neighbor.

The first rule assures the asset protection. The second rule modifies the behavior in order to let the AUVs cover the maximum area around the asset, with minimum overlaps of the on board sonar detection ranges, while guaranteeing the reliability of the communication links (see *Caiti and Munafo (2010)* for further details on the connectivity conditions). The vehicle interest for each rule is defined by a “function of interest” which determines in which way each agent enforces the specific rule, while a comparison among the functions of interest determines the priority of the rules followed at any time frame by each vehicle:

- the *Asset attraction function*, $h_A(r): \mathcal{R} \rightarrow \mathcal{R}$, as a function of the agent’s distance from the asset, is used to enforce rule #1: it is statically defined and equal for all the team members (see Fig. 1, left);
- the *Cooperation function*, $h_C(i, r, t): \mathcal{N} \times \mathcal{R} \times \mathcal{R} \rightarrow \mathcal{R}$, is used to enforce rule #2: it is computed online and modified by each vehicle on the basis of its detection sonar performance (defines the minimum distance between two vehicles) and its maximum communication range achieved at a given spatial and temporal location (defines the maximum separation between two vehicles), see Fig. 1, right. The cooperation function allows each agent to adapt its behavior to changing environmental conditions, minimizing the sonar overlap and maintaining the communication connectivity.

Fig. 1: *Left*: Function of interest for rule #1: move towards the asset. The higher the distance from the asset, the higher the interest in applying the rule. *Right*: Function of interest for rule #2: cohesiveness, as a function of range from the nearest neighbor (move away when sonar ranges overlap, move closer for values approaching the maximum communication range).

From the function of interests, the control input $u_i(t)$ for each vehicle is determined computing the gradient of the function of interest and adding up their contributions; the mathematical formulation of the algorithm is reported in Table 1. Note that the algorithm makes each vehicle able to move back to the asset it needs to protect even when it loses the communication with the other team members, since

each agent can always apply rule #1. In any case, the amount of information the vehicles need to exchange with the others is limited, as they only require communicating to their closest neighbor two data: position and maximum detection sonar range.

Table 1: Algorithm#1, area coverage with communication constraints.

ALGORITHM #1: AREA COVERAGE WITH VARYING DETECTION AND COMMUNICATION RANGES
<p>Vehicle i, placed in $x_i \in \mathfrak{R}^2$, at time instant t:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Computes all its neighbors in a range $R_C^i(t)$ and selects its closest neighbor N_k^i 2. Vehicle i receives from N_k^i: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the point $x_k \in \mathfrak{R}^2$ at which N_k^i is located • its maximum detection sonar range $R_D^k(t)$ and computes the point W_K as: $W_K(\bar{\vartheta}) = x_k + R_D^k(t) \bar{\vartheta}$ <p>where $\bar{\vartheta}$ is the direction of the segment connecting $x_i \in \mathfrak{R}^2$ and $x_k \in \mathfrak{R}^2$</p> 3. Computes the control input $u_A(t)$ applying rule 1: $u_A(t) = \nabla h_A(\ x_{asset} - x_i\ _2)$ 4. Computes the control input $u_C(t)$ applying rule 2: $u_C(t) = \nabla h_C(i, \ W_K - x_i\ _2, t)$ 5. Computes the overall control input $u(t) = u_A(t) + u_C(t)$

3. Area Coverage, Detection Performance and Propagation Delay

We now analyze the performance of the proposed algorithm in addressing the area coverage problem using three and four vehicles with the same detection capabilities, and finally we show, through simulations, the dependence of the algorithm on the propagation delay in the communication among the agents.

3.1 The Area Coverage Problem

The total sonar coverage depends on the sonar detection range R_D and on the maximum distance allowed R_M between two vehicles. These parameters can be thought respectively as the maximum detection range at which the detection performance is above a desired threshold \underline{DL} , and as the range above which the detection performance is below a minimum level \underline{DL} .

Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden. shows the result obtained applying the proposed method using three vehicles. The agents place themselves in order to position the asset at the center of the detection area. The final configuration reached allows the vehicles to completely protect a circle of radius R_M around the asset with a minimum overlap $(R_M - R_D)$ of the vehicle sonars, and with a detection level always greater than the minimum desired. The final agent positions coincide with the analytical solution of the area coverage problem of a circle of radius R_M , with the vehicles placed on the circumference, as vertices of the equilateral triangle inscribed in the circle itself. The

configuration reached has three axis of symmetry, one per each vehicle, and along these axes the detection coverage is more effective (detection directivity). It is interesting to note that once the final stable configuration has been reached, it may be possible to add a third behavior for the agents so to make them move on the circumference of the circle to periodically scan the whole area around the asset. This additional movement might even be stimulated using only ordered and sequential communication among the agents and exploiting the underneath rule #2: vehicle 1 communicate with vehicle 2, which moves, on the circumference, away from vehicle 1 (considered as its closest neighbor) and so on. Investigations are on going to further analyze this property.

Fig. 2: Solution obtained using the proposed approach: the optimal locations for the agents to obtain the total coverage of a circle of radius R_D are the vertices of the inscribed triangle.

Fig. 3: Final configuration reached using four agents. For symmetry reasons, the configurations with the asset placed at the center of mass of the team detection area are all optimal. For each agent, bold lines are used to depict both the maximum distance allowed R_M and the detection sonar maximum range R_D ($R_M > R_D$).

With four vehicles the area that can be protected becomes larger, and different solutions can be obtained depending on the weight given to the minimization of the sonar overlaps. The proposed approach aims at maximizing the total area coverage around the asset, while minimizing the detection sonar overlaps. The vehicles are hence taken to an asymmetric final configuration characterized by detection directivity along an axis difficult to be predicted a priori, and which depends on the agents' initial conditions. As shown in Fig. 3, the asset is always placed at the center of the sonar detection area, and the vehicle positions coincide with the vertices of a regular polygon around the asset to be defended. In Fig. 3, agents E1 and E4 are further away from the asset than vehicles E2 and E3 providing the increase in directivity. Note that a symmetric position of the vehicles around the asset (e.g. agents placed as vertices of a square) is *not* a solution of the optimal area coverage problem as stated in Eqs. (1): in fact, symmetric placement of the four vehicles would imply larger sonar overlaps and, as a consequence, a decrease in area coverage.

3.2 Propagation delay

When multiple vehicles cooperate to achieve a common goal the ability to exchange information during the mission represents a critical factor. This aspect assumes even a greater importance in underwater environments because of the limitation of the mean of communication, characterized by very limited bandwidth and very long propagation delays. In this regard, in this section we verify the cooperative behavior of the proposed approach in presence of communication schemes characterized by long latencies and long waiting period for transmission.

In the first simulation performed, the communication is discontinuous, and each vehicle can update its status and communicate with the rest of the team only every t seconds, which means, that only every t seconds each vehicle has an updated map of all the agents locations. In this scenario, a vehicle does not always know the actual position of the teammates, and it can only apply correctly *rule #1* (it always knows the position of the asset). *Rule #2* is applied using the last known position of its closest neighbor. Fig. 4 shows the behavior of the team.

Fig. 4: Behaviour of the team during the mission when communication delays are considered. Information is updated to all the vehicles every t seconds. It is possible to see the zig-zag movement due to not up-to-date information.

It is possible to note a zig-zag movement due to the discontinuous communication. However, the final optimal configuration can still be reached, since the importance of the propagation delay decreases as the mission goes on and the agents move towards the target: the closer the vehicles are to the final configuration the smaller is the distance between the actual and the last known position of the agents.

Note that the extent and the spatial frequency of the zig-zagging will depend on the vehicle speed and on the communication delay. In this paper we are focusing on the *behaviours* of the team more than specific dynamic performances at sea with a given set of vehicles. However, it is clear that in practical applications this issue must be further investigated at least on a case-by-case basis.

Finally, the algorithm has been tested with a round robin communication scheme. Following this method, vehicles take turns to communicate during a time window W_R : once a vehicle has finished its communication phase (of maximum length W_R), it has to wait $(n-1)W_R$ seconds to communicate again, where n is the number of agents composing the team. According with this paradigm, each vehicle has never an updated map of the positions of all its teammates.

Fig. 5 shows the behavior of a team composed by four agents with the same detection and communication capabilities. Note the circular trajectory (especially clear for vehicle 4) followed by the vehicles when rule #2 is used with not up-to-date information. In this case, the agent uses only the last known position of its neighbor and considers the other agent as a fixed obstacle which has to be avoided to reach the asset. When, according to the communication scheme, it receives the update on its neighbor position, it has to steer to avoid the sonar overlaps, increasing the length of the path. Again, once the agents are close to the optimal positions smaller corrections are needed and less relevant are the propagation delays and the waiting periods.

Fig. 5: AUV trajectories using a round-robin communication scheme.

4. Conclusions

In this paper we have presented an algorithm for adaptive area coverage by a team of cooperating AUVs. We have shown through simulations the area coverage performance of the algorithm with respect to optimal geometric solutions, and with varying propagation delays. Investigations are on going to analytically guarantee the optimality of the approach proposed. Experimental testing is foreseen in September 2010.

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Assistance Tools for Operational Fuel Efficiency

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Abstract

In times of increasing fuel prices the operational fuel efficiency of ships is becoming more and more important. The ECO-Assistant is a modular tool for optimising different aspects of a Ship's operational fuel efficiency. This paper discusses two ECO-Assistant modules; the ECO-Trim-Assistant to allow the crew to sail the ship at optimum trim all the time by calculating the optimum trim angle for different operating conditions and the ECO-Energy-Assistant which enables the crew to monitor the energy consumption of the different consumers such as main and auxiliary engines, generators and pumps. The paper shows the fuel savings potential of utilising the ECO-Assistant onboard a ship. With assistance tools such as the ECO-Assistant the operational fuel efficiency of ships in service can be improved significantly without making expensive modifications to the vessel.

1. Introduction

In times of increasing fuel prices and environmental awareness the fuel efficiency of ships is becoming more and more important. For newly built ships it is becoming essential to optimise the fuel efficiency wherever possible to ensure competitiveness in the market. Even for existing ships modifications to increase fuel efficiency can have short payback periods. Such modifications can be for example the main engine modernisation to increase its fuel efficiency or replacing the bulbous bow with a new shape to reduce resistance for slow steaming operation. Although the payback period for such modifications might be short, capital investment is required to realise the modifications. Another option to increase the fuel efficiency without modifications to the vessel and hence requiring much less capital investment is to consider the operational efficiency.

The operational efficiency has many aspects which can be investigated to reduce fuel consumption. With the goal of providing the crew with one user-friendly tool to monitor and improve the operational fuel efficiency of the vessel, the idea of the ECO-Assistant was born. The ECO-Assistant is developed as a modular workbench environment to which modules for different functionality can be added. It offers a flexible tool to the customer to which modules can be added as they become available or be configured depending on the customer's preferences. The ECO-Assistant is a new initiative of FutureShip GmbH, a subsidiary of Germanischer Lloyd AG offering advanced engineering consultancy services. The tool is under development and this paper introduces the first two ECO-Assistant modules, the ECO-Trim-Assistant and the ECO-Energy-Assistant.

The ECO-Trim-Assistant is designed to inform the crew about the optimum trim for the vessel, considering the current operation condition. The trim has a significant effect on the resistance and hence the fuel consumption of the vessel. The optimum trim changes depending on the operating condition of the vessel which is taken into account by the ECO-Trim-Assistant. It is the first module that has been delivered to customers and it is already used onboard a variety of ship types. The second module presented in the paper is the ECO-Energy-Assistant, which is currently developed and tested. It enables the crew to monitor the energy consumption of the different consumers such as main and auxiliary engines, generators and pumps. Through the measured energy consumption, the efficiency of each component can be assessed. With this information inefficient consumers can be identified by the crew, problems can be detected and defects can be corrected.

2. Trim Assistant

The aim of the ECO-Trim-Assistant is to help the crew to sail their vessel at optimum trim for the current operating condition. The influence of trim on fuel consumption is known for quite some time.

However, there is no global optimum trim for a vessel. Besides the specific hull shape the optimum value depends on the operating parameters such as speed, displacement and water depth.

Unlike most other trim assistance tools, the ECO-Trim-Assistant does not use logged operational data to calculate the optimum trim, but utilises a comprehensive database of ship specific resistance data for different operating conditions to compute the optimum trim. The ECO-Trim-Assistant can be seen as a product consisting of two parts. The first part consists of generating a comprehensive database of ship specific data for the different operating conditions. The second part of the product is the ECO-Trim-Assistant module within the ECO-Assistant workbench environment which makes the optimum trim information available to the crew onboard the vessel in a simple format.

Compared to trim assistance tools based on logged operational data, the ECO-Trim-Assistant does not require interfacing with the onboard systems and no sensors to monitor operational parameters are required. The ECO-Trim-Assistant can be installed on any computer on the vessel so that no additional hardware and measurement equipment is required, which makes the tool very cost effective. The tool solely relies on the database input and the operational parameters entered by the crew. Of the operational parameters on which the optimum trim depends, the ECO-Trim-Assistant considers speed, displacement and water depth. Other secondary factors such as seaway are not evaluated by the tool and are therefore not required for input. It should be kept in mind that the ECO-Assistant provides information for the most fuel efficient sailing condition and naturally other constraints such as bending moment and cargo issues must still be taken into consideration by the crew and might not allow to utilise the full potential.

Vessel specific hydrodynamic data is required for the full range of operational conditions specified by the parameters speed, displacement (mean draft) and water depth. This results in a four-dimensional trim matrix. A typical parameter range of a trim matrix is shown in Table I. For this example 3360 data points are required to fill the trim matrix. It is therefore not economically to obtain the full trim matrix of the ship specific performance data through towing tank tests. Instead, an advanced automated simulation process is utilised.

2.1 Trim matrix analysis method

A trim matrix typically consists of more than 3000 data points. When choosing finer parameter spacings, trim matrices may easily have 5000 to 10000 data points. For the parameters speed, mean draft and water depth, the trim matrix can be defined as a rectangular domain. The feasible trim range of a vessel changes with its displacement (mean draft) as constraints such as minimum propeller

Table I: Typical trim matrix

Parameter	Range	Data points
Speed	12 – 26 kn	8
Mean draft	9 – 14.5 m	7
Water depth	45 – 150 m	6
Trim	-5.5 – 7.9 m	10

Fig. 1: Trim range change with mean draft

immersion and freeboard limitations need to be considered. The trim range is therefore defined as a function of mean draft as shown in Fig. 1.

To allow large numbers of simulations to be conducted, the automated process established for the fully parametric geometric hull shape optimisation, e.g. *Hochkirch and Bertram (2009)*, is used. Although no hull shape optimisation is conducted when calculating the trim matrix, the automated process for this task interfaces an optimisation tool with CFD codes and hydrostatic calculation software. The in-house optimisation tool FS-Optimiser is employed to drive the simulation process of exploring the trim matrix. FS-Optimiser and the other programs employed during the automated simulation process have a graphical interface and can also be run in batch mode for time consuming numerical computations on main frame computers. The programs can run in unlimited threading mode to make full use of parallel computing environments like HPC (high performance computing) clusters.

For calculating the hydrostatic properties FS-Equilibrium, the in-house workbench for analysis of equilibrium conditions of floating bodies in six degrees of freedom, is utilised. For this application, only a small subset of the functionality of FS-Equilibrium is employed.

For the performance assessment two types of flow codes are applied: A general purpose Rankine panel code, which solves the boundary value problem of potential theory and a fully viscous flow code dealing with the Reynolds-Averaged-Navier-Stokes equations (RANSE) in the entire flow domain. Both codes treat the flow around the ship hull establishing its dynamic equilibrium position with respect to trim and sinkage and computing the formation of the non-linear ship wave system while sailing. Special propeller models are implemented to simulate a self-propulsion test by balancing longitudinal forces and simulating the propeller effects on the ship's dynamic trim, its suction at the aftbody and its influence on the stern wave system. Lifting surfaces like keel, rudder, fins and stabiliser systems may be modelled as well.

The trim matrix is built primarily using the potential flow code outlined in section 2.1.1 to predict the performance. In the vast majority of cases resilient results are obtained. However, highly viscous effects such as an extensive recirculation zone at the stern cannot be modelled correctly. In such cases our viscous RANSE flow code takes effect for cross-comparison, either validating the potential flow based prediction or calibrating it. Full-scale viscous free-surface flow computations consume computational resources of orders higher than potential flow based computations. Hence, they are so far limited to a few prominent computational cases. Whenever available, the simulation results are also validated against existing towing tank data of tested operating conditions.

For the numerical simulations, an electronic model of the vessel's hull is required. In most cases the ship owner or charterer orders the ECO-Trim-Assistant and a digital hull model might not be in the client's possession and might not be obtainable from the shipyard. In such cases a digital hull model is recreated from physical drawings using the Computer Aided Engineering (CAE) system FRIENDSHIP-Framework, *Abt and Harries (2007)*.

2.1.1 Rankine panel code FS-Flow

A Rankine panel code is fast, robust and reliable and is the tool of choice for computation of the trim matrix. The in-house code FS-Flow has special interfaces with the other tools discussed. FS-Flow uses a panel representation of the hull (including lifting surfaces if applicable) and a portion of the free water surface. The source strength on each panel is adjusted to fulfil the various boundary conditions, namely zero normal velocity on the hull and kinematic and dynamic boundary conditions on the water surface. Lifting surfaces like keel, rudder and fins (e.g. in case of sailing yachts or stabiliser systems) are modelled in FS-Flow by lifting patches which carry in addition to the source panels also a dipole distribution, enforcing a Kutta condition at the trailing edge. The ship's dynamic floating position and the wave formation are computed iteratively. After each iteration step, the geometry of the free surface is updated and the sinkage, trim, heel and propeller thrust of the vessel

are adjusted. The calculations are considered to be converged when all forces and moments are in balance and all boundary conditions are fulfilled. Having determined the source strengths, the pressure and velocity at each point of the flow field can be calculated. The wave resistance can be either computed by integrating the pressure over wetted surface of the hull or from wave cut analysis, Heimann et al. (2008).

The viscous resistance component is considered in terms of a friction line in combination with the wavy wetted hull surface and a form factor is determined either from integration of the local velocity perturbations along the hull or by an accompanying boundary layer computation. Adding a correlation or roughness component and the wind resistance, both of which are case dependent, the total resistance is obtained. Finally, balancing the total resistance with the propeller thrust force the self propulsion condition is established yielding the required power for a certain operation condition. The power value, usually related to the machine or MCR power, enters the trim matrix.

2.2 Trim Assistant application

The ECO-Trim-Assistant application supplies the results of the complex analysis to the crew in an easy to use format. The ECO-Trim-Assistant application is a stand-alone tool and does not require interfacing with the ships systems and sensors. It can therefore be installed on any Windows based computer and no hardware installation is required. The parameters defining the operational condition are required by the tool as input and need to be entered by the crew.

Fig. 2: ECO-Trim-Assistant user interface

Fig. 2 shows the main user interface window of the ECO-Trim-Assistant application. The operational parameters required as input are the vessel's speed, the water depth (if it is confined) and the loading condition. The loading condition can be specified by entering the displacement or the draft at the aft and forward perpendicular (AP and FP) loading marks. In practice the operational parameters are often already entered in port when planning the next journey so that entering them manually is required and measuring them through sensors would not work.

Based on the input parameters the trim curve for the operating condition is displayed and the optimum trim is computed as shown in Fig. 2. The plot displays the approximate difference in power and fuel consumption for different trims relative to the optimum trim. The green plot background denotes the trim range for which the required power is less than 1% higher than at optimum trim. The yellow background indicates that the required power is between 1% and 3% higher and the red background that the difference is more than 3%. Trims in the grey background range have not been analysed for the trim matrix as they are considered to be not feasible.

The optimum trim is also displayed as a value together with the corresponding aft and forward draft for the specified displacement. The draft and trim values entered and displayed are that equivalent static values for the ship at rest since they can be measured and calculated more readily onboard the vessel. The hydrodynamic analysis when computing the trim matrix is conducted considering the dynamic sinkage and trim of the vessel.

To increase the crew's economical and ecological awareness the potential fuel oil and CO₂ savings, when sailing at the optimum instead of the current trim, are calculated as well. The current trim is calculated from the aft and forward perpendicular draft input values or can be entered directly.

2.3 Optimum trim variation

The variation of the optimum trim and the associated potential fuel savings are discussed in this section based on sample calculations for a container vessel. Fig. 2 shows the ECO-Trim-Assistant graphical interface for the vessel in the design condition. As can be expected the optimum trim is relatively close to level trim. Negative trim values denote bow down trim. For clarity the ship profile in the graphical interface in Fig. 2 shows the vessel's trim. Despite of the modest difference, 1.2% power can be saved by changing from level trim to optimum trim. This corresponds to a fuel saving of approximately 2.2 t per day and a reduction in CO₂ emissions of 7.4 t per day. Even in the case of this modest trim adjustment, the payback period of the system would be less than two months. For off-design operating conditions, the potential savings are much higher.

Fig. 3 shows the vessel operating at the same speed as in Fig. 2 but with 1 m more draft. The optimum trim is approximately 1.6 m further bow down. Compared to level trim this decreases the required power by 8.7%. It equates to potential fuel saving of 18 t per day and a reduction in CO₂ emissions of 59.4 t per day.

For the operating conditions in Fig. 2 and 3 the trim curve shows a parabolic shape with a clear optimum trim. The shape of the trim curve can however be more complex as shown in Fig. 4 for a slow steaming operating condition. The trim curve has two trim ranges where the required power is within 1% of the minimum required power. In between the two ranges close to level trim the required power is more than 3% higher than the minimum. Two effects, which have particular influence on the vessel's resistance, come into play here. The optimum immersion depth of the bulbous bow results in a resistance minimum for a certain bow down trim. The optimum immersion depth is primarily influenced by the vessel's speed due to the changing wave pattern. For different displacements (mean drafts) a constant immersion depth results in different trims. For the example in Fig. 4, the optimum immersion depth cannot be achieved and the optimum trim is at the trim range boundary. From the shape of the trim curve it can be expected that more bow down trim could further reduce resistance. However, the trim range is chosen to reflect the hydrodynamically feasible trim range and more bow

Fig. 3: Deep water trim curve for mean draft of 13.5 m and vessel speed of 24 kn

Fig. 4: Deep water trim curve for slow steaming operating condition

down trim would, for this loading condition, result in the immersion depth of the propeller becoming too small.

The second effect producing a local required power minimum at a bow up trim of approximately 4 m in Fig. 4 is the optimum transom height which best fits the stern wave system. Fig. 4 shows the crew on board the vessel the optimum trim for this operating condition and that there is a second local minimum at approximately 4m bow up trim which only requires 0.3% more power. This equates to an approximate difference in fuel consumption of only 0.3 t per day so that either trim range could be chosen depending on the crew's preference due to other vessel's particulars such as cargo distribution, longitudinal bending and manoeuvrability. It also shows the crew that it is most inefficient to operate the vessel between level trim and 1.9 m bow up trim.

In addition to the speed and the displacement of the vessel, the water depth is also considered in the trim matrix to account for changes to the optimum trim due to confined water operation. Fig. 5 shows the trim curves for six water depths for the vessel operating at design speed. The water depths are

Fig. 5: Trim curves for different water depths at design speed

Fig. 6: Trim curves for different water depths at maximum speed

given as water depth to draft ratios (h/T). For level trim the power requirement increases with reducing water depth. The increase in required power between a water depth of $h/T = 12$ and 3.7 is approximately 1.5%. The influence of water depth on the required power gets more significant as the vessel trims bow up. For bow down trims the increase in required power due to a reduction in water depth gets less significant and eventually reverses and the resistance decreases in shallow water. As a consequence the optimum changes with water depth towards a more bow down trim. In this case however, the influence on the required power is small.

The resistance change due to shallow water significantly depends on the operating condition. Fig. 6 shows the trim curves for different water depths at maximum speed instead of design speed (Fig. 5). The general trends of the trim curves at the two different speeds are similar, but the resistance reduction in shallow water for bow down trims is much more significant at maximum speed. At the optimum trim for $h/T = 3.7$, the required power is 5% less compared to deep water operation at the same trim. Fig. 6 also shows wave height contour maps for three trims at water depths of $h/T = 12$ and 3.7 . For all three trims an increased wave trough can be seen along the hull as a result of the squat effect. At the shown bow down trim the squat effect results in beneficial wave interference so that the stern wave system is reduced. For this operating condition the optimum trim changes with water depth by approximately 1.4 m. The required power can be reduced by approximately 1% if this change in optimum trim is considered in shallow water.

3. Energy Efficiency Monitoring Tool (EEMT)

Energy efficient operation of the vessel does not end with hydrodynamic optimisation. Aside for the savings that can be achieved through trim optimised operation of the vessel, the operation of the machinery aboard can be considered crucial for efficient vessel operation.

As a basis for optimisation, the instantaneous energy consumption for propulsion, auxiliaries, and other consumers has to be surveyed. The current situation aboard most commercial vessels is that fuel

consumption is analysed over relatively long time periods, usually one voyage. As a global efficiency metric, the *International Maritime Organization (IMO)* proposes the *Energy Efficiency Operational Index (EEOI)* defined by

$$EEOI = \frac{CO_2}{t \cdot km}$$

where

CO_2 = Total CO₂ emission emitted from the vehicle within the period

$t \cdot km$ = Total actual t-km transported within the same period.

This long-term data is suited for high level consumption analysis, e.g. as average over one year, and general transport efficiency evaluation. The long-term monitoring parameter has only limited functionality for in-depth analysis of operation and consumption of main engine and auxiliaries in different operational modes and conditions and implementation of improvements. A well loaded vessel with inefficient machinery and operation cannot be distinguished from a highly efficient vessel, which happens to be only partly loaded. Therefore this is only a key performance indicator for the transported goods, but does not allow for deeper efficiency evaluation of the vessel itself. Efficiency of the energy conversion in the systems can only be evaluated on microscopic or machinery level.

Only suitable tools for detailed analysis can be utilised for specific technical improvements. The presented *Energy Efficiency Monitoring Tool (EEMT)* is integrated in the ECO-Assistant workbench as the ECO-Energy-Assistant and gives an easy-to-use tool for quick perception of the current energy consumption and its time history. EEMT enables the display of the propulsive and electric power usage onboard, both instantaneous and as a time history over a given time period. The efficiency in energy conversion of the machinery gives additional insight into how the machinery operation can be optimised.

The EEMT is based on the simulation model of the ship machinery as presented in the COMPIT 2009 paper by *Freund et al. (2009)*. On board, mechanical power produced by the main engine for propulsion and electrical power generated by the auxiliary engines are measured in combination with the ambient conditions and the ship's navigational data. Fuel consumption and efficiency of energy conversion are obtained from the simulation model of the machinery, using the measurement data as input. Additional consumers can optionally be included in the simulation, enabling a deeper insight into the operation. For example, by including the auxiliary systems of the main engine, the effects of controllable pumps in cooling water systems can be quantified or the availability and demand of steam from waste heat recovery can be compared. This leads to the quantification of savings through retrofits and the potential savings in the actual operation of the vessel.

EEMT yields the consumption and efficiency time history for each energy converter. The history is available onboard at the EEMT display for quick evaluation of changes and stored in a database for analysis in retrospect onboard or ashore.

3.1 EEMT as short-term efficiency analysis tool

The onboard tool display is developed for graphical presentation of the current consumption, efficiency of energy conversion, and the respective timelines over arbitrary time periods. The graphical user interface of the pilot tool is displayed in Fig. 7. Instantaneous data are presented in the left frame in four main categories (1) for main engine, auxiliary engine, navigational and ship efficiency data. Each section can be called by mouse click, opening the respective timelines of variables of that category in the right frame. Additionally, an overview over the most important timelines can be opened in the right frame. For quick analysis of operation, traffic light symbols for the status are initialised (2). Deviations from predefined thresholds are displayed by colour changes from green (system OK) over yellow (attention) to red (check system for reason).

Fig. 7: Pilot onboard tool display, 1: subsections for detailed view, 2: traffic lights for quick notification, 3: Sankey diagram of energy flow

In Fig. 8 a screenshot of the pilot tool during sea passage is displayed. The overview window in the right frame displays the timelines of main engine power, electrical power, fuel oil mass flow, consumption per nautical mile and ship speed (from top). In the left frame, the instantaneous values are displayed, with traffic lights indicating a warning for high main engine power demand (indicating increased ship resistance) and low efficiency of electrical power generation. In this case, the high resistance is caused by shallow waters. The second traffic light indicates, from an efficiency point of view, unnecessary use of a second diesel generator, causing low load of 33% on each generator set and therefore low efficiency. The indicator calls for the evaluation if running the second generator set is necessary at that moment.

Fig. 8: Screenshot of the pilot installation during sea passage

3.2 Benefits for crew and ship management

The development of awareness for energy efficient ship operation can be considered crucial for success in consumption reduction (Cazzulo (2009)). Awareness can be developed if consequences of actions in operation are instantly displayed and the actual, instantaneous consumption of the machinery is clearly presented to the crew. Increases of power demand over time are visible in the timelines. By displaying this change, the crew has a tool to evaluate if this increase is caused by a necessary change in operation or external conditions, or by faulty operation of machinery.

Availability of consumption data in combination with cargo and navigational data enables the exact determination of a cargo's carbon footprint. The *Energy Efficiency Operational Index* can be calculated online and displayed dynamically as variation over time, compare Fig. 9. This displays the ship's performance in variation of the EEOI under varying operational modes and external influences, fluctuating by up to 20% of the mean value during the sea passage. By summing up these data, the annual IMO EEOI is automatically acquired. By shore-based use of the measured data, ship management and external consultants can analyse operational patterns and optimise them accordingly if required.

4. Conclusions

There is significant potential to improve the operational efficiency of ships and assistance tools can provide valuable information to achieve this. Two examples have been discussed in this paper; the ECO-Trim-Assistant and the ECO-Energy-Assistant (or EEMT). Together they give the crew a powerful tool for energy saving and direct feedback to their actions, enabling the crew to develop awareness of the energy efficiency of the current vessel operation..

A typical operational condition has been presented where the ECO-Trim-Assistant shows that the efficiency can be increased by 8.7% through sailing with the optimum trim instead of level trim. For other operating conditions the savings potential can be even higher.

Operational data, collected by the EEMT, is a starting point of a knowledge database for statistical analysis of 'best business practice', which requires comparable ship operations. Over time the knowledge database grows and turns into a more and more powerful tool for quick assessment of the energy efficiency of a ship's machinery system. Additionally, the collected data can serve as a starting point for the re-design of the vessel's operation and systems, including specific constraints which can be determined in dialogue between ship operator and analyst consultant.

Fig. 9: Timeline of the dynamic EEOI during 8 days of sea passage

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A 3D Packing Approach for the Early Stage Configuration Design of Ships

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Abstract

This paper presents a packing approach that generates three-dimensional ship configurations for application during early stage ship design. Combined with a search algorithm, the packing approach enables the rapid generation of a large and diverse set of feasible ship configurations suitable to investigate trade-offs between performances and, most importantly, between performances and costs. This, in turn, helps the naval architect to find a suitable balance between the ship's capability and affordability, before changes become prohibitively expensive during the later stages of the design process.

1. Introduction

Given recent budgetary pressures, the worlds' navies have become ever more focused on the affordability of current and future ships. Still, affordability is not achieved without effort and the design, procurement and operation of an affordable fleet requires proper attention to both costs and capability from the earliest moment on: during conceptual design. This early phase of the ship's design process offers naval architects the best chance to strike a suitable balance between affordability and capability.

Achieving a suitable balance, though very important, is not necessarily straightforward, as outlined by *Van Oers and Stapersma (2006)*, *Van Oers et al. (2007,2008,2009)*. One important reason lies in the fact that an assessment of both capability and costs requires the availability of a detailed definition of the ship's arrangement, i.e. the shape and size of envelope and superstructure well as the configuration of components and their connections.

Such detailed ship definitions require considerable human effort. As a result, the required level of detail is available relatively late, and most importantly, difficult to change once available. This makes the crucial investigation of multiple concepts time-consuming. These time constraints become prohibitive when one combines detailed ship definitions with the large changes common during early stage design. Nonetheless, the consideration of a large number of very different alternatives is essential if one is to find a proper balance between capability and affordability.

2. Motivation

To facilitate the investigation of multiple alternative ship configurations, the authors proposed an approach to maintain flexibility at a higher level of detail, *Van Oers et al. (2007,2008,2009)*. The approach uses two steps. In the first step, a packing approach in combination with a search algorithm is used to generate a large and diverse set of feasible ship configurations, *Van Oers et al. (2007, 2009)*. In the second step, the human can select the 'best' feasible configuration after a thorough consideration of all feasible designs, *Van Oers et al. (2008)*. Together, the two steps help maintain flexibility at a higher level of detail. Most importantly, the user controls how the two steps generate alternative configurations (shown in the double loop in Fig. 1). The search algorithm used by prototype application: NSGA-II, *Deb et al. (2002)*, was retained for use with the packing approach presented in this paper.

Fig. 1: Overall process: human steers search process using a double loop

A limited test case dealing with the generation of side-view arrangements of an offshore patrol vessel showed that –in principle- the approach is able to maintain flexibility at a higher level of detail. Fig. 2 and 3 illustrate the two steps of the approach. Fig. 2 shows one of the simplified two-dimensional ship designs produced by the packing approach discussed in *Van Oers et al. (2007,2009)*. Fig. 3 shows the polygons used by the selection approach discussed in *Van Oers et al. (2008)* to choose the design shown in Fig. 2.

Fig.2: A side-view configuration produced by the prototype packing approach

Fig.3: Selection decisions used to choose the configuration shown in Fig. 2

Though both Figs. 2 and 3 show that the approach has promise, they also illustrate its limited scope. For any meaningful application, both the packing approach and the selection approach need improvement. Of the two steps shown in Fig. 2 and 3, the selection approach is scalable and readily adapted for use on representative three-dimensional ship configurations. Modifying the packing approach to handle three-dimensional ship configuration is less straightforward, though.

This paper therefore discusses the steps necessary to develop a packing approach able to define and change practical three-dimensional ship configurations, i.e., the hull, superstructure, subdivision, components and connections, in order to provide sufficient information to assess the ship’s performance, capability and costs. Moreover, it should support the large changes common in early stage design, to prevent the increase in detail from reducing the magnitude of design changes.

The paper is structured in 9 Sections. Section 3 discusses why packing was used to model ship architecture. Section 4 discusses the set of geometrical objects that represent the hull, superstructure, subdivision, components and connections. Section 5 discusses packing requisites, i.e., rules governing overlap of objects, the design changes used for overlap management, and the sequence of application

of these changes. Subsequently, Section 6 discusses how these requisites integrate into a proper packing approach able to generate suitable ship configurations. The approach to assess feasibility is discussed in Section 7. As a closure, Section 8 illustrates the capability of the packing approach with the configuration design of a surface combatant, before concluding the paper in Section 9.

3. Packing as a model for ship architecture

Before discussing in detail the packing approach used to generate ship configurations, it is worthwhile to consider why this paper proposes packing a model for ship architecture. Packing problems form a well known class of mathematical problems which all relate to the allocation of a finite amount of supply to one or more items that consume part of this supply. For the early stage design applications discussed in this paper, the most important supplies are space, weight and energy following *Van der Nat (1999)* (manning was not considered in detail).

Fig. 4 to 6 show a simple spatial packing problem from *Dyckhoff (1990)*: a positioning space in Fig. 4 and objects to be packed inside this positioning space in Fig. 5. Fig. 6 shows the configuration of objects after packing them in the positioning space. Key issue is that some objects are not allowed to overlap, i.e., cannot occupy the same space simultaneously.

Fig.4: Positioning space used in a simple packing problem (from *Dyckhoff (1990)*).

Fig.5: Objects to be packed inside the positioning space in Fig. 4 (from *Dyckhoff (1990)*).

Fig.6: Objects packed inside the positioning space (from *Dyckhoff (1990)*).

How does this simple packing example relate to early stage ship design? Ships consists of a large number of systems, some of which are enclosed by a partially watertight envelope, others are located on the envelope whilst yet others are found outside of this envelope. Regardless configuration, one can always enclose both systems and envelope in a box of finite size, Fig. 7. In this paper, this imaginary box will serve as the positioning space in which the ship's systems, including the envelope and subdivision, will be packed (similar to a ship-in-a-bottle souvenir).

Fig.7: Objects representing a ship packed inside a box-shaped positioning space

Reasons to use a packing approach are three-fold. First, the developments presented benefit from earlier packing approaches (such as outlined in *Grignon (1999)*, *Van der Nat (1999)*, *Lee et al. (2002)*, *Blouin (2004)* and *Nick (2008)*). Second, packing the envelope enables one to vary the interaction between envelope and internal arrangement ('wrapping' according to *Andrews (1986)* and 'packing' following *Nick (2008)*). Third, packing uses overlap management rules that offer considerable flexibility to model relative positions between parts of the ship configuration. For example, overlap rules can adjust the propellers' positions such that they both align with the gearboxes (shaft inclination) and

have sufficient hull clearance, by requiring the propellers to overlap with specific areas in the positioning space.

The remainder of the paper discusses the packing process and its application. Section 4 starts by introducing the six types of objects used to represent the ship configuration.

4. Spatial Objects

The prototype packing approach in Fig. 2 uses simple, rectangular objects. For practical application the set of objects needs to be expanded. Therefore, six types of spatial objects are proposed: *envelope*, *subdivision*, *hard*, *soft*, *free space* and *connection*. Their definition concerns their most important spatial properties: shape and position, as well as the design changes used to manage overlap.

The object types used in this paper form an extension of the three types¹ of objects used by *Van Der Nat (1999)* for the packing application *SUBSPACE*. *Van Der Nat (1999)* proposes clustering a set of related components and connections into spatial objects based on the required degree of changeability (note that clustering takes places regardless of function, unlike *Andrews and Dicks (1997)*). The approach *how to cluster* components and connections into a coherent set of objects for the packing application in this paper is not discussed here; refer to *Wagner (2009)* and *Wagner et al. (2010)* for more details. The six types of spatial objects are introduced below.

Fig.8: Envelope object, comprising of a hull (blue) and an extended superstructure (pink)

- Envelope object. Section 3 explained that the envelope is packed like other objects, which therefore is defined as an object. It consists of a water-tight, streamlined hull part (blue in Fig 8) and a topside part (pink in Fig. 9). The superstructure extends from the hull's edge to the top of the positioning space. This extension provides sufficient space for sensors and weapon systems located in the superstructure.

Fig.9: Subdivision objects (bulkheads) used to limit flooding

- Subdivision object. Ships have decks and bulkheads to partition the envelope in compartments that contain and separate different systems onboard the ship. In addition, subdivision helps contain damage, e.g., blast and flooding (refer to Fig. 9).
- Hard object. Hard objects represent components and connections that cannot change shape without loss of function. As such, they resemble the Type I objects used by *Van der Nat (1999)*. Typical examples include the propulsion system (see Fig. 10) and weapons and sensors systems.

¹ Type I: length-based, Type II: area-based and Type III: volume-based

- Soft object. Soft objects also represent systems; however, they model systems that can change their shape without immediate loss of functionality. Soft objects are defined by either required surface area or volume (Type II and III objects used by *Van der Nat (1999)*). Accommodation, fluid tanks, Fig. 11, and vehicle decks can all be modelled as soft objects. Soft objects do have user-defined restrictions on some of their dimensions, e.g. minimum width.

Fig.10: Hard objects representing a propulsion system Fig.11: Soft objects representing a fluid tank

- Free space objects. Free space objects model the space around objects located on the edge of the envelope to provide an interface with the outside world. Free space objects have a fixed shape that does not change during the packing process. Common examples include the firing arcs of weapons and the viewing arcs of sensor systems (refer to the green object in Fig. 12).

Fig.12: A hard object (white) and a free space object (green) representing a VLS

- Connection objects. Ships contain a multitude of networks of connections that, together with components, ensure that the ship's systems work correctly. The connection object models such connections. The generation of networks is carried out using rule-based routing performed by Dijkstra's algorithm, following the approach outlined by *Asmara and Nienhuis (2006)*. Different rules generate different types of networks. Examples of connection objects include transport routes, access routes, up- and down-takes and ship services networks.

Fig.13: Transport route connecting flight deck to hangar

This completes the introduction of the six types of objects that will be packed in the positioning space. Having spatial objects is insufficient, however. Packing requires requisites which Section 5 discusses.

5. Packing requisites

5.1. The basis of packing: overlap rules: prohibited, required and permissible overlap

Overlap rules are essential for packing, for two reasons. First, packing becomes trivial without them. Second, proper overlap rules ensure the generation of correct ship configurations. To this end, the rules in Table I are proposed. Generally speaking, objects that represented physical systems (hard ob-

jects, soft objects and connection objects) are not allowed to overlap with each other. Free space objects, e.g., representing free space around an object, must remain clear of hard, soft and some connection objects, but may overlap with other free space objects. Refer to *Van Oers (2010)* for a detailed discussion of overlap rules.

Table I: Overlap rules used by the packing approach

Object type	Envelope	Subdivision	Hard	Soft	Free space	Connection
Envelope	permissible	required	required permissible prohibited	required	prohibited	required
Subdivision	-	permissible	prohibited permissible	prohibited permissible	permissible	permissible
Hard	-	-	prohibited	prohibited	prohibited	prohibited
Soft	-	-	-	prohibited	prohibited	prohibited
Free space	-	-	-	-	permissible	prohibited permissible
Connection	-	-	-	-	-	prohibited

Envelope and subdivision objects use more complex overlap rules. Hard objects may be located either inside (a gearbox) or outside the envelope (a propeller), or both (a vertical launch system that protrudes through the hull). This is modelled by declaring overlap between envelope and object to be required, prohibited or permissible, respectively. Furthermore, free space objects are not allowed to overlap with the envelope, in order to provide an interface between the ship's interior and the outside world. Subdivision is rather similar. A hard object, e.g., a gas turbine, is prohibited from overlapping with bulkheads to prevent loss of function. Soft objects, e.g., fuel tanks, are allowed to overlap with bulkheads. Some connection objects can overlap with free space objects, e.g., a route for helicopter transport, while others cannot, e.g., uptakes.

5.2. Design changes for overlap management: changeable objects.

Overlap rules must be enforced by overlap management. The packing approach uses three design changes to manage overlap. All are introduced below, using two objects that are prohibited to overlap as an example, Figs. 14 to 19.

1. **Change shape using an object's own shape function.** First option to remove overlap is changing the shape of the circle, e.g., by changing the circles radius, Figs. 14 and 15. This change uses a change in parameter value in combination with the object's own shape function (changing multiple parameter values concurrently is also possible). The shape function ensures a coherent object shape after overlap management, preventing unwanted shape alterations, e.g., changes that affect the streamline nature of hull part of the envelope object.

Fig.14: Prior to overlap management: circle and rectangle overlap

Fig.15: After overlap management: circle changes radius

2. **Changing shape by conforming an object's shape to the shape of another object.** An alternative shape change for overlap management sees part of the shape of one object being used by another object. For example, in Figs. 16 and 17, the circular object's shape is adjusted

such that the overlapping part is removed. As a result, part of the circular object's shape conforms to the shape of the box-like object. This shape change, i.e. the rectangular gap in the circular object's shape, can result in shapes that cannot be created by altering parameter values of the function defining the object's initial shape.

Fig.16: Prior to overlap management: circle and rectangle overlap

Fig.17: After overlap management: circle conforms its shape to that of the rectangle

3. **Change position of one of the objects.** This is the design change most commonly used by the references discussed in Section 3. In the example in Figs. 18 and 19, the position of the rectangular object is changed by moving it to the right, thereby removing the prohibited overlap. The approach in this paper uses the position changes outlined in *Van Oers (2007,2009)*. It places objects on an initial position determined by the search algorithm; overlap management subsequently shifts the object to the position closest to the initial position that complies with all overlap rules in Table I. This approach to position changes enables both a variable packing density and a variable level of detail, *Van Oers (2009,2010)*.

Fig.18: Prior to overlap management: circle and rectangle overlap

Fig.19: After overlap management: rectangle changes position

These three design changes are used by the six types of object to manage overlap. Table II provides an overview. How the six object types use three types of design changes is discussed below. Moreover, Fig. 20 to 24 show several practical examples of design changes used to manage overlap.

Table II: Design changes for overlap management (per object type)

Design changes	Change position	Change through shape function	Conform own shape	Change envelope shape
envelope	not relevant	yes	yes	not relevant
subdivision	yes	no	yes	no
hard	yes	no	no	yes
soft	yes	no	yes	no
free space	yes	no	no	yes
connection	not relevant	no	yes	no

- Envelope. Fig. 20 shows a change in hull type as well as a change in main dimensions. Another change, not shown, concerns the stretching of the parallel mid ship. All three changes are examples of the first type of shape change shown in Fig 14 and 15. Fig. 21 shows how the envelope's superstructure conforms its shape to that of a free space object to ensure that weapon systems have the required firing arcs. It is thus an example of a second type of shape change shown in Fig. 16 and 17. Such changes may not interfere with structural support, enclosure or the watertight integrity of the envelope.

- Subdivision. Bulkheads can both change shape as well as position to manage overlap. The bulkhead positions in Fig. 20 change to prevent overlap with the propulsion plant, while ensuring sufficient reserve buoyancy, Fig. 22 and 23. Refer to *Van Diessen (2007)* for the bulkhead positioning approach. Subdivision also uses shape conformation, e.g., the creation of a deck opening to remove overlap with a vertical launch system, Fig. 12.

Fig.20: Envelope change of hull type and length using its own shape function

Fig. 21: Envelope shape conformation to remove overlap with free space objects (yellow)

Fig.22: Bulkhead configuration without sufficient reserve buoyancy

Fig.23: Bulkhead configuration with sufficient reserve buoyancy after change in positions

- Hard object. The sole design change hard objects use are position changes (similar to Figs. 18 and 19).
- Soft object. Soft objects conform their shape to that of another object, while retaining their enclosed area or volume. Fig. 11 shows two fuel tanks whose shape conforms to that of the envelope. Soft objects can also change their position if a shape conformation leads to an insufficient enclosed area or volume.
- Free space object. Free space objects only change position (not their shape) to prevent overlap with other objects. Also, free space objects may change the envelope shape. Fig. 21 shows how the envelope conforms its shape to that of the free space objects (shown in yellow).

Fig.24: Shape conformation of a connection object to remove overlap with soft objects

- Connection object. Connection objects do not change their position during overlap management. Their position is fixed by the two objects they connect. Instead, the shape of the connection object is conformed to prevent it from overlapping with other objects. An example is shown in Fig. 24: the passageway is routed around accommodation objects to remove the overlap.

5.3. Application of design changes: sequential vs. concurrent

The question remains how objects will be packed such that they will form a coherent ship configuration complying with the overlap rules laid out in Table I. This process: overlap management, uses the design changes outlined in Section 5.2 to manage overlap while packing all objects. Still, one must consider how these design changes will be applied: sequential, concurrent or a mixture of both.

Generally speaking, the packing approach outlined in this paper packs objects in a sequential manner, following the prototype packing approach discussed in *Van Oers et al. (2007)* and *Van Oers et al. (2009)*. Main reason to retain the sequential packing is the simplification of the overlap management. The design changes discussed in Section 5.2 only have to be applied to a single object, whilst freezing all prior objects (sole exception being the envelope; to be discussed below). For example, only the position of the current object needs to change, instead of simultaneously changing several object positions at once.

Unfortunately, a purely sequential packing process does not work. Take the vertical launch system (VLS) in Fig. 12., for instance. In its most simple form, it can be modelled using two objects: a hard object (representing the VLS) and a free space object (representing the VLS' firing arc). Trying to pack the hard object first and the free space object second fails, as the two objects are not allowed to overlap (refer to Table I). Changing their relative position to comply with overlap rules also fails, as the VLS then does not have the required firing arc.

What is necessary is the option to pack a system of multiple objects concurrently, whilst disregarding overlap rules for objects within the current system. Then, the VLS can be modelled correctly using the same two objects with the correct relative position, while the overlap rules ensure the hard object does not overlap with prior objects inside and on the envelope, and the free space object ensures the envelope's shape is adjusted such that the required firing arc is achieved.

5.4. Establishing a proper sequence

Packing systems of objects in a sequential manner immediately raises the issue of sequence. The sequence of packing is user-defined and fixed during the packing process. Changing the sequence enables the naval architect to control the packing process, for instance to focus the search process. Among other things this enables a change in the interaction between envelope and internal systems discussed in Section 3, i.e., the envelope can be 'wrapped' (following *Andrews (1986)*) or packed (following *Nick (2008)*), depending on what seems most appropriate.

Nonetheless, the approach outlined in this paper positions the envelope as the very first object, i.e., follows a classic packing sequence. Main reasons to do so are two-fold. First, packing the envelope first ensures a coherent shape, while the extended superstructure provides ample space for arrangement of the ship's topside. Second, it removes the need to adjust the envelope's shape to that of other objects, which requires a complex mathematical approach to ensure a coherent hull shape (such as outlined in *Harries (1999)*). A future publication will explore the effects of different packing sequences, with a special focus on when to pack the envelope. Table II lists objects with the ability to change the envelope's shape after it has been packed. Safeguarding a correct superstructure shape while coping with such shape changes requires additional bookkeeping (discussed in Section 6; refer to *Van Oers (2010)* for more details).

The resulting order of packing follows the following sequence: envelope first, constrained objects second, subdivision third, followed by systems of objects ordered by size: large to small. The definitive superstructure shape (the black line in Fig. 21) is defined after packing the last system of objects. Sequence can also take into account the computational effort required to manage overlap; such objects generally are packed earlier. With the sequence of packing established, Section 6 considers how packing requisites discussed in this Section integrate into the overall packing approach.

6. Combining design changes into a coherent packing approach

The overall packing approach can now be introduced; it is shown in Fig. 25.

Fig.25: Overall outline of the packing approach

It consists of three steps: definition, packing and prediction; each is discussed below.

1. **Defining** concerns defining the initial shape, size and position (x, y and z-coordinates) of each object in the ship configuration, prior to overlap management. Definition uses both values for input parameters from the NSGA-II algorithm, as well as fixed, user-defined values. Different parameters result in different initial shapes and positions which result, crucially, in different configurations after overlap management.
2. **Packing** takes place by sequentially applying four steps to each system of objects until all systems are packed.
 - a. One must retrieve the initial shape and position of each object in the current system, as well as the overlap rules that apply (listed in Table I).
 - b. One must build an up-to-date positioning space for each object in the current system. To do so, the shapes and positions of all prior objects are retrieved. If overlap is prohibited, this information is used to block the space occupied in the positioning space. If overlap is required between two objects, the overlap rule inverses, i.e., the object is prohibited from overlapping with the space unoccupied by the other object. The sole object type requiring more attention when creating an up-to-date positioning space is the envelope. One must ensure that the superstructure part is adjusted such that prior objects required to overlap with the envelope stay enclosed, while other objects prohibited to overlap with the envelope remain outside the envelope. The approach used to this end is rather similar to the one outlined in *Van Oers (2009)*. The

main difference is that the topside's shape is adjusted in-between to consecutive bulkheads (refer to *Van Oers (2010)* for more details).

- c. One must manage overlap for the current system of objects being packed, using the design changes for overlap management discussed in Section 5.
- d. After packing: If overlap management is successful, the positions and shape of all objects in the system are stored so that they can be used to update the positioning space for subsequent systems of objects. If overlap management fails, the number of the system of objects that was unable to be placed is stored for use as a constraint by the search algorithm. Handling failure automatically is important, as the use of search algorithms precludes using human intervention for this purpose.

If successful, the sequential packing of all systems of objects results in a coherent ship configuration. This provides the input for the prediction tools used in the third step.

3. **Predicting.** Being able to pack all systems of objects goes some way towards establishing feasibility as the ship has sufficient space to accommodate all components and connections. Still, additional predictions are required to further establish the feasibility of the design. These predictions are discussed in Section 7. Some numerical results are returned to the search algorithm to help guide the search process towards promising feasible designs.

These steps: defining, packing and predicting, are applied to configure each individual ship in the set of the designs used by NSGA-II to search for feasible ship configurations. Moreover, the set of feasible designs produced by this search process is used for the selection process shown in the outer loop in Fig. 1. See *Van Oers et al. (2008)* for more details. With the overall packing approach discussed, Section 7 discusses how the feasibility of the ship configurations is established.

7. Assessing feasibility

The prototype approach shown in Fig. 2 used three simple feasibility criteria: comply with overlap rules and ensure the location of the centre of gravity falls within fixed, user-defined bounds (longitudinal and vertical). The lack of an actual hull form, the fixed dimensions of the envelope and the neglect of changes in weight or buoyancy led to a naive feasibility assessment.

Assessing feasibility for the ship configurations such as shown in Figs. 7 and 28 is rather more complicated. The first feasibility criterion: comply with overlap rules, is left unchanged. Four additional criteria are used: sufficient buoyancy (do not to exceed the design draft), sufficient reserve buoyancy (using floodable length curve), and sufficient initial stability, limited trim and heel at several loading conditions. Refer to *Van Oers (2010)* and *Wagner (2009)* for more details. If the ship configuration meets all feasibility requirements it will be available for consideration during the selection process, Fig 1. Speed requirements are not used as a direct feasibility criterion. Instead, the propulsion system is sized (the definition step in Fig. 25) using the assumed design draft; if this draft is not exceeded, the ship will should attain the required speed (endurance is treated similarly). Optionally, ballasting calculations can determine whether the use of ballast water helps in attaining the feasibility criteria.

A simple weight calculation provides input for the hydrostatics calculations. It estimates the ship's weight and centre of gravity (COG) based on the structural weight (dependent on the shape and size of the shell, decks and bulkheads) and the weight attributed to individual objects. Creating a weight estimate sensitive to both minor and large changes in ship configuration is not straightforward and warrants considerable attention. The simple weight estimate used for the results in this paper serves to illustrate whether the packing approach can handle changes in weight and COG caused by changes in configuration. No particular effort was spent on establishing the accuracy of the changes in weight and COG.

Section 8 considers whether the packing approach outlined in this paper is actually able to generate feasible three-dimensional ship configurations.

8. Application: configuration design of a frigate-type surface combatant

Two applications were carried out with the packing approach presented in this paper. The first: an off-shore deepwater drilling vessel was reported in *Wagner (2009)* and *Wagner et al. (2010)*. The second application concerns itself with a frigate-type surface combatant and will be discussed here. Main focus is to illustrate the packing approach's ability to change the entire ship configuration: hull, super-structure, subdivision as well as the arrangement of objects.

Table III: Overview of the most important systems of objects (not exhaustive)

Fight	Move	Hotel
NH-90 flight deck & hangar	Propulsion plant (CODOG)	Accommodation (20x)
Slipway for RHIB	Propellers	Galley
RHIB + crane (2x)	Rudders	Long room
Torpedo tubes	Bridge	Recreational Area (2x)
Vertical launch system	Down takes & Uptakes	Life rafts (4x)
3" Gun	Fuel tanks (4x)	Sick bay & Back-up sick bay
Machine guns (4x)	RAS positions	Fitness
CIWS RAM (2x)	Diesel generator plant (2x2)	Waste disposal
Harpoon SSM	Chilled water plant (2x)	Laundry
APAR radar	Ship Control Centre & Back-up	Storage (4x)
Towed array & Hull mounted sonar		
CIC & Back-up CIC		
Damage control centre (2x)		
Computing room (2x)		
20 foot containers		

The ship's configuration is modelled using by 491 objects clustered into 113 systems. For convenience sake, these systems are partitioned into three well know functional groups proposed by *Andrews et al. (1996)*: move, fight and hotel. Table III provides an overview of the most important systems onboard the ship. Some systems were constrained to focus the search process by preventing unwanted positions (e.g., the propulsion system was constrained to the tank top). The ship's feasibility requirements are shown in Table IV; the variation of the envelope object is listed in Table V.

Table IV: Feasibility requirements

Feasibility requirements	value	unit
Cruise speed	18	knots
Dash speed	30	knots
Endurance	4500	nm
Damage length for reserve buoyancy	15	% of L_{oa}
Initial stability (GM)	> 1.5	m
$\Delta LCB - LCG $	< 0.5	m
Actual draft – Design draft	≤ 0	m
Comply with overlap rules	-	-

Table V: Bounds on envelope shape changes

Envelope characteristics	Type 1	Type 2	unit
Hull type	Frigate-shape	OPV-shape	-
	Lower bound	Upper bound	unit
Length over all	100	140	m
Beam	12	18	m
Draft	4.4	6.8	m

The resulting configurational model was used to search for feasible ship configurations by running the NSGA-II search algorithm with 238 input parameters for 672 generations, with a population size of 60. In total 40320 designs were evaluated. 401 Designs met the feasibility requirements (1.0 %) shown in Table IV.

Two objectives were maximised: packing density and diversity. The latter measures how the most recent ship configurations differ from all prior configurations. Maximising diversity helps prevent a premature convergence of the search process encountered during the drill ship application discussed in Wagner (2009) and Wagner et al. (2010). Fig. 26 shows a scatter plot of the objective values.

Fig.26: Scatter plot of the two objectives: packing density vs. diversity

Fig.27: Influence of feasibility requirements on diversity in ship dimensions

Fig.:28 Eight feasible ship configurations from the set shown in Fig. 26 and 27, colours indicate functions: fight (red), move (yellow), hotel (green) and access (purple).

Eight of the feasible designs are shown in Fig. 28. Colours indicate the functional groups from Table III: fight (red), move (yellow) and hotel (green). Staircases and passageways are shown in purple. Note that free space objects were omitted from Fig. 28 for the purpose of clarity.

The eight designs in Fig. 28 use both available hull types. They have different main dimensions (also shown in Fig. 27) as well as markedly different superstructures. Also, subdivision and internal configuration of objects also differ considerably. Moreover, all designs meet speed and endurance requirements and carry the same weapons, sensors and crew, i.e., all have the same baseline capability. Summarised, Figs. 27 and 28 illustrate that the packing approach is indeed able to change the entire ship configuration while maintaining coherent ship configurations.

9. Conclusions & future research

This paper presents a packing approach intended for practical application during the early stage design of ships. Building upon earlier work by the authors, the packing approach can:

- Concurrently vary the entire ship configuration, i.e. hull, superstructure, subdivision, components and connections.
- Initiate these changes solely by changing the values of input parameters, enabling the use of search algorithms to search for feasible ship configurations.
- Assess the feasibility of these ship configurations, i.e., ensure they meet non-negotiable requirements on payload, speed, endurance, initial stability and reserve buoyancy.
- Generate a large set of feasible, three-dimensional ship configurations for consideration in the selection approach shown in Fig. 3 and discussed in *Van Oers et al. (2008)*.

Summarised, the packing approach presented in this paper addresses the issues that prevented the prototype approach discussed in Section 2 from being applicable in a day-to-day ship design environment, while still maintaining flexibility at a higher level of detail.

Future work is expected to focus on several topics, the most important ones are:

- Develop a weight estimation method sensitive enough to determine the impact of both large and small configuration changes on the ship's weight and centre of gravity.
- Expand the approach to handle the variation of the number and type of systems onboard. Among other things, this enables fleet design (distributing different systems over multiple platforms) as well as a variation of commonality within a single class of ships.
- Integrate additional performance prediction tools to evaluate and rank ship configurations, e.g., sea-keeping and vulnerability.

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Comparison of Modeling Techniques for Simulation of Fuel Consumption of Dredgers

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Abstract

For a Trailing Suction Hopper Dredger (TSHD), during its dredging process, both propulsion system and dredging system work dynamically, resulting in fluctuating operation of main diesel engine. In this study, various modeling techniques are examined to investigate the possibility and reliability of modeling techniques for fuel consumption simulation. By means of three example modeling strategies, in the discussion of the comparison study of simulation results and trial measurements, the advantages, disadvantages and efforts of both modeling and application are addressed.

1. Introduction

Trailing Suction Hopper Dredger (TSHD) is a special ship type. It operates in cycles, which consist of four stages, namely, sailing empty, dredging, sailing loaded and discharging. From operational point of view, in both sailing empty and sailing loaded stages, TSHD could be treated as a normal transport vessel, during which only the propulsion system works; while in the discharging stage, it could be somehow treated as a stationary discharge machine, since the pumps consume most of the energy (except for dumping, in this case, no extra energy is needed for discharging, TSHD is also treated as a normal transport vessel); And in dredging stage, the situation becomes very complex, both the propulsion system and dredging system are working together to achieve optimum production rate.

In addition, comparing to the other three stages, dredging stage of a TSHD is a pure dynamic process. The resistances of drag head, suction pipe and ship hull change continuously, causing the demanded propulsion power to fluctuate. Meanwhile, because of the variable density of sand/water mixture and the fluctuating dredging depth, the demanded power of the dredge pump changes continuously as well. Thus, the fluctuating propulsion power and the fluctuating dredge pump shaft power are two major parts which lead to fluctuating operation of main diesel engine. Consequently, the fuel consumption of main diesel engine is fluctuating. Furthermore, even for a certain TSHD, the operation of both the propulsion system and the dredge system varies from cycle to cycle, and due to the fluctuating condition of dredge material and dredge depth, each dredge cycle is unique and unrepeatable. Therefore, it is of importance to implement computer models to simulate the fuel consumption for TSHD during dredging process.

2. Models

In this study, the target dredger is a medium size TSHD, which equips with a single trailing suction pipe in its port side, as shown in Fig.1. Therefore, in order to assess the operation performance of both the dredging system and the propulsion system, the port side operation system was under investigated. As shown in Fig.2, the port side power train of this target TSHD is a typical diesel direct drive configuration. The main diesel engine, which has a rated power of 6000 kW, drives both the propeller and pump directly. In front, through a reduction gearbox, it drives an inboard dredge pump with the rated power of 3600 kW (trailing mode) or 5900 kW (pumping ashore mode); in the back, through another reduction gearbox, it drives a controllable pitch propeller which runs in fixed nozzles with a rated continuous power of 4000 kW during sailing stages.

There are many possible candidates of simulation models associated with the investigation of fuel consumption simulation. In marine engineering, the general trend is the growing complexity and scope of systems; the focus is more and more laid on total system rather than on individual components.

Fig.1: General arrangement of the target TSHD

Fig.2: Port side power train of the target TSHD

In *Grimmelius (2003)*, modeling techniques of physical system were categorized in four dimensions: one indicates the level of detail of the description of the actual processes (model level), the second indicates the time domain for which the model is developed (model time domain), the third indicates the time domain in which the model is to be used (application time domain) and the fourth indicates the amount and character of data required to get useful results from the model (model data). In this present study, off-line modeling is preferable, therefore, all models here are located inside the model zone indicated by Fig.3 and could be expressed in the following three dimensions:

- Model levels: simulation models discussed here are basically mathematical functions, which calculate outputs by given inputs, initial conditions and system parameters. The ways, in which the mathematical functions be derived, represent the understandability and the capacity of the model. More physical background being introduced or more physical guarantee being given, more ‘whitish’ the model could be. However, due to the complexity of the nature, even in fully developed ‘white’ models, semi-empirical equations cannot be avoided.
- Inputs: from modeling perspective, the amount of available data and their accuracy are often negative aspects. Theoretically, more accurate data available, more reliable model could be built. Another important and often be neglected aspect is the selection of required inputs. Especially when modeling based on regression theory, the character of inputs could play crucial roles.
- Dynamics (model time domain): for concept exploration and initial configuration determination, steady state simulation is enough, while in modeling of system behaviors, from which system dynamics often play an important role, dynamic simulation is obligated. In Fig.3, from steady state modeling to dynamic modeling, different levels of modeling strategies can be expected, such as, using transfer function with time constant to simplified transfer the calculation results from steady state part of the model to dynamic outputs or using differential equations which could be fully interpreted by physics. (Note: care must be taken in determining which part of dynamic behavior – fast or slow – is important for a specific application).

In this paper, three modeling strategies, which are different combinations of the modeling dimensions and represent different modeling techniques, are under investigated as examples to assess the possibilities and reliabilities of predicting and calculating fuel consumption from TSHD during its dredging process.

Fig.3: Three dimensions of model zone

2.1. Strategy I (black level + various inputs + various dynamical modeling)

Referring to the black box modeling theory in *Suykens (1998)*, black box model is a technical term for a system when it is viewed in terms of its input, output and transfer characteristics without any knowledge required of its internal workings.

2.1.1. Determination of model input and output

Since the operation system of TSHD could be simplified as a main diesel engine drives both the propulsion system and the dredging system, the inputs could be consequently divided into three categories: the inputs from propulsion system, the inputs from dredging system, and the inputs from main diesel engine, whereas the outputs is fuel consumption, Fig.4.

Fig.4: Configuration of model (strategy I)

When looking at the characters of inputs, from the propulsion system side, the propulsion power is determined by the propeller speed (n_{prop}) and the propeller pitch angle (θ_{prop}), and also be influenced by the speed of the vessel (v_{ship}). In addition, being different from transport vessels which could be treat as with fixed displacement during a certain voyage, for TSHD, during dredging process, material is transported into hopper continuously, resulting in continuously increase of displacement (m_{ship}), changing the hull resistance. Therefore, in propulsion system part, four inputs are selected and addressed. From the dredging system side, since the dredging conditions, namely the dredge depth (D_{drg}), the density of dredge material (ρ_{mixt}) and the angles of suction pipes (α_{lp} & α_{up}) determine the required power from dredge pump, apparently, they form an input group of pump shaft power simulation (as Group A); On the other hand, attention could be only paid to the operation of dredge pump, without taking account into the cavitation efforts inside pump, the pump power could be calculated by the pump speed (n_{pump}), the density and the velocity of the transported mixture (ρ_{mixt} & v_{mixt}). Thus, the pump operation parameters could also be chosen as another input group (as Group B). Furthermore, when taking into account the effects of cavitation in pump operation, on top of the pump operation parameters, additional parameters, such as the dredge depth (D_{drg}) and pipe angles (α_{lp} & α_{up}), are required. This is addressed in Group C.

Table I: Input groups for modeling strategy I

Group	Propulsion system	Dredging system	Main diesel engine
Steady-state modeling			
<i>Group A</i> (propulsion+dredging condition)	v_{ship} n_{prop} θ_{prop} m_{ship}	ρ_{mixt} D_{drg} α_{lp} α_{up} n_{pump}	n_{eng}
<i>Group B</i> (propulsion+pump operation)		ρ_{mixt} v_{mixt} n_{pump}	
<i>Group C</i> (propulsion+pump operation+cavitation)		ρ_{mixt} v_{mixt} n_{pump} α_{lp} α_{up}	
Dynamic modeling (Values at the current time and at the time step in the past are denoted as t and $t-1$, respectively)			
<i>Group D</i> (propulsion+dredging condition)	$v_{ship}(t)$ $n_{prop}(t)$ $\theta_{prop}(t)$ $m_{ship}(t)$	$\rho_{mixt}(t;t-1;t-2;t-3;t-4;t-5;t-6)$ $D_{drg}(t)$ $\alpha_{lp}(t)$ $\alpha_{up}(t)$ $n_{pump}(t)$	$n_{eng}(t)$
<i>Group E</i> (propulsion+pump operation)		$\rho_{mixt}(t;t-1;t-2;t-3;t-4;t-5;t-6)$ $v_{mixt}(t)$ $n_{pump}(t)$	
<i>Group F</i> (propulsion+pump operation+cavitation)		$\rho_{mixt}(t;t-1;t-2;t-3;t-4;t-5;t-6)$ $v_{mixt}(t)$ $\alpha_{lp}(t)$ $\alpha_{up}(t)$ $n_{pump}(t)$	
<i>Group G</i> (propulsion+pump operation)	$v_{ship}(t)$ $v_{ship}^3(t)$ $n_{prop}(t)$ $\theta_{prop}(t)$ $m_{ship}(t)$	$\rho_{mixt}(t;t-1;t-2;t-3;t-4;t-5;t-6)$ $n_{pump}(t)$ $n_{pump}^2(t)$ $n_{pump}^3(t)$ $v_{mixt}(t)$ $v_{mixt}^2(t)$ $v_{mixt}^3(t)$	$n_{eng}(t)$

In addition, when modeling dynamic behaviors of this system, it appears that not only the current conditions of inputs affect the current output, but also the recent past. For instance, when determining the density of the transported mixture, the information of recent past is of important. For the target TSHD, from drag head to dredge pump, there are suction pipes with the length in total about 52 m, and with the velocity of about 8 m/s through the suction pipes, the dredge material needs about 6s to travel from drag head to dredge pump. In other words, not only the current density of the dredge material in drag head, but also the density of the material, which is still travelling through the suction pipes, the so-call ‘past’ density, should be taken into account, as shown in Group D ~ Group G. (Note: in this study, only the “past values” of mixture density are introduced into inputs. A more sophisticate alternative should include the “past values” of other input parameters.)

One step further, by selecting inputs, an effective way to make the model more grayish is by not only including the involved parameters, but also, on top of gained knowledge, considering the physical

relationships between inputs and outputs. For instance, when concerning required power by pump shaft, it could be expressed by experience as a function of pump speed (n_{pump}), mixture flow rate (Q_{mixt}), mixture density (ρ_{mixt}) and water density (ρ_{water}) as shown in Eq.(1). Thus, Group G is introduced in this study to reveal how the “grayish” inputs impact the model quality.

$$P_{pump} = f(n_{pump}, n_{pump}^2, n_{pump}^3, Q_{mixt}, Q_{mixt}^2, Q_{mixt}^3, \rho_{mixt}, \rho_{water}) \quad (1)$$

2.1.2. Transfer characteristics

Artificial Neural Network (ANN) is used to build up the mathematic relationship between inputs and outputs, because of its capability of accommodating multiple input variables to predict multiple output variables and the advantage that it can be modeled without prior knowledge of the process relationships. In the past, ANN has been used in a number of applications successfully, ranging from the development of static and dynamical models, *Kalogirou (2000)* to sophisticated process control schemes, *Huang (2004)*, *Mesbahi (2000)*, and also be proved as a fast and accurate way of engine performance prediction, *Arcaklioglu (2005)*. Mathematically, ANN algorithm is described in Fig.5.

Fig.5: Mathematic algorithm of ANN, *Matlab (2008)*

Theoretically, in ANN model, neurons can use any differentiable transfer function to generate their outputs. Referring to back propagation, in this present study, three most commonly used transfer functions are implemented, namely, Log-Sigmoid transfer function (logsig(n)), Tan-Sigmoid transfer function (tansig(n)) and Linear transfer function (purelin(n)).

2.1.3. Network

In this study, two types of networks are used to create links between inputs and output.

- Feed-forward network, which includes weight connection from inputs to successive layers and from successive layers to outputs, Fig.6.

Fig.6: Architecture of Feed-forward network (Matlab 2008b, 2008)

- Cascade-forward network, which is similar to feed-forward network, but in addition includes weight connections from inputs to each hidden layer and from each hidden layer to the successive layers, Fig.7. These additional connections might improve the accuracy of which the network learns the desired complex relationship between inputs and outputs.

Fig.7: Architecture of Cascade-forward network, *Matlab (2008)*

2.1.4. Preparation

Prior to the implementation of ANN models, training process is obligated to ‘teach’ the model what the relationships between inputs and outputs are. Two independent datasets from on-board measurement were used to train and validate the model separately. For better training and validation, both the datasets are normalized in advanced by Eq.(2) with the same state information (X_{max} & X_{min}).

$$X_{ir} = \frac{X_i - X_{min}}{X_{max} - X_{min}} \quad (2)$$

To evaluate the training and validation process, a statistical parameter, the measure of fit (R^2) which lies between 0 and 1 is provided for all modeling outputs (zero indicates no fit, unity a perfect fit).

$$R^2 = \frac{n \sum_{i=1}^n y \hat{y} - (\sum_{i=1}^n y) \cdot (\sum_{i=1}^n \hat{y})}{\sqrt{\left[n \sum_{i=1}^n y^2 - (\sum_{i=1}^n y)^2 \right] \cdot \left[n \sum_{i=1}^n \hat{y}^2 - (\sum_{i=1}^n \hat{y})^2 \right]}} \cdot 100\% \quad (3)$$

2.1.5. Modeling

A group of models, which represent the combinations of seven input sets (Group A to Group G in Table I), three transfer functions, two networks (illustrated in Fig.6 and Fig.7) and various layers are built and tested in this study. The measure of fit of every tested model during both training stage and validation stage is illustrated in Fig.8. Conclusions from this modeling strategy are addressed:

- From the input dataset prospective, all the groups show good training results. However, input groups derived from pump operation generate more accurate validation outputs than other groups, probably because that, the dredging condition parameters only have indirect relations with the required power by the dredge pump, resulting in more complex relationship between the model inputs and outputs and deteriorating the accuracy;
- After introducing dynamic behavior into inputs, the accuracy of validation outputs improves;
- Enriching inputs by adding physical relationships between inputs and outputs could improve the accuracy of simulation.

Fig.8: Measure of fit from Group A ~ Group G

Therefore, among the tested candidates, the best configuration is addressed in Table II.

Table II: Representative model of Strategy I

Input dataset	Group G
Network	cascade-forward network
Nr of hidden layers	2
Nr. neurons in hidden layer	10, 10
Transfer functions	tansig, tansig

2.1.6. Simulation of fuel consumption

Fig.9: Comparison model outputs and measurements (strategy I)

Fig.10: Scatter plot of model outputs and measurements (strategy I)

The best configuration of modeling strategy I is implemented to simulate the fuel consumption (indicated by fuel rack position) during a trial dredging process. The comparison with measurement data is illustrated in Fig.9. In Fig.10, the scatter plot illustrates the quality of the model outputs by means of the curve fitting between measurements and the model outputs, in which R^2 is 66.6%.

2.2. Strategy II (grey level + fixed inputs + dynamical modeling)

As already shown by modeling strategy I, models in black level could lead to acceptable results in prediction of fuel consumption during dredging, however, the transfer characters (ANN) implemented in modeling strategy I are black, the transfer processes from inputs to outputs are invisible. Therefore, in this part, simulation model is moving towards to the direction of ‘white’ referring to Fig.3, in which physical interpretations are possible. Following *Grimmelius (2005)*, due to the complexity of the relations between inputs and outputs, the model is divided into two parts: a steady state parts, which consists of empirical equations, and a dynamic part consisting of first order system with gain one and approximated time constants. Fig.11 illustrates this configuration and refers to *Grimmelius (2005)* for more information.

Fig.11: Principle of modeling (strategy II)

2.2.1. Calculation of steady state part

In propulsion system side, the calculation of propeller shaft power is implemented based on four-quadrant Wageningen B-Screw Series theory (β Vs. C_Q^*) derived from *Kuiper (1992)*, *Roddy (2006)*. See Fig.12 as an example.

$$\beta = \arctan\left(\frac{v_A}{0.7\pi \cdot n_{prop} \cdot D_{prop}}\right) \quad (4)$$

$$C_Q^* = \frac{Q_{prop}}{\frac{1}{2}\rho_{water} \cdot (v_A^2 + (0.7\pi \cdot n_{prop} \cdot D_{prop})^2) \cdot \frac{\pi}{4} \cdot D_{prop}^3} \quad (5)$$

v_A is the advance ship speed, which is a function of vessel speed and thrust deduction factor (t), $v_A = v_{ship} \cdot (1-t)$. One step further, when concerning TSHD, during dredging, the total mass displacement increases because of the increasing hopper load, and meanwhile the thrust deduction factor depends on both the vessel speed and the total mass displacement, therefore, $v_A = f(v_{ship}, m_{hopper})$. Like wise, in this study, the relative rotative efficiency of the propeller (η_R) is also considered as a function of vessel speed and the total mass displacement: $\eta_R = f(v_{ship}, m_{hopper})$. Thus, by means of Eq. 6, the required power by propulsion ($P_{propulsion}$) is calculated.

$$P_{propulsion} = Q_{prop} \cdot n_{prop} \cdot 2\pi / \eta_R \quad (6)$$

Fig.12 C_Q^* of an example propeller family, with $D_{prop} = 4\text{m}$, 4 blades

In dredging system side, as introduced in Eq.(1), pump shaft power is a function of pump speed (n_{pump}), mixture flow rate (Q_{mixt}), mixture density in the pump (ρ_{mixt}) and water density (ρ_{water}). In this example model, as the case of one dredge pump, revising the formula proposed in *Braaksma (2008)* by replacing mixture flow rate (Q_{mixt}) with mixture velocity (v_{mixt}), a precise expression of pump shaft power calculation is:

$$\begin{aligned} P_{pump} &= P_{water} \frac{\rho_{mixt}}{\rho_{water}} \\ &= (c_{0p} n_{pump}^3 + c_{1p} n_{pump}^2 v_{mixt} + c_{2p} n_{pump} v_{mixt}^2 + c_{3p} v_{mixt}^3) \frac{\rho_{mixt}}{\rho_{water}} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The coefficients (c_{0p} , c_{1p} , c_{2p} and c_{3p}) are given by pump manufacturer and could be calculated by curve fitting a polynomial function to data from a pump test. Therefore, the numerical values of

required power by the dredge pump could be calculated with associated pump speed and mixture velocity.

Concerning the operation of diesel engine, from (Brussen, 2006), a fitting formula is used to describe the fuel consumption (relevant to the fuel consumption at 100% MCR) over the whole operational area by means of engine brake power (sum of pump shaft power and propeller shaft power plus transmission losses) and engine shaft speed:

$$m_{fuel}^* = (c_{0e} + c_{1e}P_b^* + c_{2e}(P_b^*)^2) \cdot (c_{3e} + c_{4e}n_{eng}^* + c_{5e}(n_{eng}^*)^2) \quad (8)$$

n_{eng}^* , m_{fuel}^* and P_b^* are relative values of engine shaft speed, fuel consumption and engine brake power to the nominal operation condition. Coefficients (c_{0e} , c_{1e} , c_{2e} , c_{3e} , c_{4e} and c_{5e}) could be derived from steady state engine operation conditions.

2.2.2. Transfer function

As shown in Fig.13, first order transfer functions with gain one and approximated time constants are implemented to simulate system dynamic behaviors.

Fig.13: Configuration of model (strategy II)

Table III: Comparison of R^2 between models of strategy II

Time constant	R^2
$\tau = 0.1s$	61.27%
$\tau = 0.5s$	64.07%
$\tau = 1.0s$	66.58%
$\tau = 5.0s$	52.04%
$\tau = 10s$	25.74%

Fig.14: Simulated fuel rack position with varies time constant (strategy II)

Fig.15: Scatter plot of model outputs and measurements ($\tau = 1.0s$) (strategy II)

There are three time constants needs to be matched. Due to lack of background knowledge, in this current study, all these three time constants are assumed to be the same and being matched by varies values. As shown in Fig.14, in each time constant case, the simulation results do not fit the measurement quite well. Probably this is due to the errors in calculation of the fit-factors used in empirical equations. There are two ways to improve it, one is by implementing more sophisticate empirical equations which could better reflect the relations between inputs and outputs; another way is to improve the curve fitting by more accurate method with more reference points. When concerning with the dynamic behavior, Fig.14 shows also the comparison between simulation results and the measurement. Clearly it illustrates that, although it is not possible to determine the precise time constant of this system, the trend could be observed, which is a small time constant results in overreacting to the disturbance while a large time constant delays the response. (Note: since there is no feed-back between the calculated outputs, changing one time constant does not influence the results for the other outputs, thus these three time constants could be matched separately.)

2.3. Strategy III (white level + multiple inputs + dynamical modeling)

One way to make the model become whitish is to involve physical first principles in every subsystem, by which all the functions of transfer characteristics are derived from physics and can be viewed. An overview of this kind of simulation model is shown in Fig.16, and based on previous research in Shi (2008), an example simulation model is built in Matlab/Simulink®.

Fig.16: Block diagram of model (strategy III)

Looking inside this model, not only given inputs, but also initial conditions and system parameters are required for implementation. They are contained in the input block and operation block respectively.

In the input block, four input signals (the set points), namely the engine speed ($n_{eng,set}$), propeller pitch angle ($\theta_{prop,set}$) and the pipe angles ($\alpha_{lp,set}$ & $\alpha_{up,set}$), are injected. In other words, to drive the model, the operational profile is loaded as initial inputs.

- Propulsion system. In the subsystem ‘ship’, with inputs of ship load (m_{ship} , which is determined by production rate and continuously increase during dredging process) and the vessel speed (v_{ship}), the ship moving resistance (R_{ship}) is generated; whereas in the subsystem ‘propeller’, by means of one control signal ($\theta_{prop,set}$) and two inputs, vessel speed (v_{ship}) and propeller shaft speed (n_{prop}), the propeller thrust (T_{prop}) and propeller shaft torque (M_{prop}) are gained. Thus, in ‘ship translation system’, based on Eq. (9), in every simulation step, the vessel speed is calculated.

$$v_{ship}(t) = \frac{1}{m_{ship}} \int_0^t (T_{prop} - R_{ship}) dt + v_{ship,int} \quad (9)$$

- Dredging system. A typical dredging system of a TSHD consists of four major parts: drag head, suction pipe, jet pump and dredge pump. For the target TSHD, because the jet pump is driven by the starboard main diesel engine, it is excluded; whereas, the simulation of drag head behavior is simplified by inputting the density of mixture (ρ_{mixt}) and dredge depth (D_{drg}) (both are recorded during the trial) into the model. Thus, only the pipeline system and dredge pump are simulated properly. In the subsystem ‘pipe’, by injecting initial and dredge profile, the pressure loss from drag head to dredge pump (p_{loss}) and the actual density of the mixture (ρ_{mixt}), which is in front of dredge pump, are calculated. While in the subsystem ‘pump’, by means of the inputs of mixture speed (v_{mixt}), mixture density (ρ_{mix}) and pump shaft speed (n_{pump}), three outputs are calculated in every simulation time step, namely the discharge pressure of pump (p_{dis}), the pump shaft torque (M_{pump}) and the mass of mixture (m_{mixt} , integration of production rate). In addition, the flow system is dealing with the balance between pump discharge pressure and required pressure for mixture transportation through suction pipes, see Eq.(10). If those two pressures are out of balance, mixture velocity changes, either accelerating or decelerating.

$$v_{mixt}(t) = \frac{1}{m_{mixt}} \int_0^t (p_{pump} - p_{pipe} - p_{loss}) \cdot A \cdot dt + v_{mixt,int} \quad (10)$$

- Main diesel engine. The main diesel engine model consists of two parts: governor and the engine core. In the governor, by means of a PID controller the difference between the desired engine speed ($n_{eng,set}$) and the actual engine speed (n_{eng}) is converted to the setpoint of fuel injection ($m_{fuel,set}$); while in the engine core, the engine output torque is calculated by Eq.(11) (a revised version of Eq. 6).

$$M_{eng}^* = 1 - c_{6e}(1 - n_{eng}^*) + c_{7e}(1 - n_{eng}^*)^2 - c_{8e}(1 - m_{fuel}^*) + c_{9e}(1 - m_{fuel}^*)^2 + 2c_{10e}(1 - n_{eng}^*) \cdot (1 - m_{fuel}^*) \quad (11)$$

- Finally, the whole system is connected by means of shaft rotation system, in which the shaft speed is generated by Eq. (12).

$$n_{shaft}(t) = \frac{1}{2\pi I} \int_0^t (M_{eng} - M_{prop} - M_{pump}) dt + n_{shaft,int} \quad (12)$$

This simulation model is validated by trial measurement as well. By implementing the trialing profile ($n_{eng,set}$, $\theta_{prop,set}$, α_{lp} & α_{up}), defining the system parameters and dredging conditions, the operation of port side power train is simulated. Fig.17 and Fig.18 illustrate the comparisons of engine speed and engine fuel rack position between model outputs and measurements as examples.

Because of the usage of steady state engine map, this model doesn't show good capability of simulation of dynamic behavior of engine, especially by comparing the engine speed from simulation results and measurement data, apparently, the dynamic behaviors are missing. However, in this study, the intension is to investigate the impact of dynamic load on fuel consumption and exhaust emissions during dredging, where the main engine would run approximately in a constant speed (normally in maximum speed), there would be only minor impact from engine speed; on the other hand, as shown in Fig.18 and Fig.19, the simulation results of fuel rack position fit much better with measurement, with $R^2 = 88.3\%$.

Fig.17: Comparison of simulation results and measurements on engine speed

Fig.18: Comparison of simulation results and measurements on fuel rack position

Fig.19: Scatter plot of model outputs and measurements of fuel rack position (strategy III)

3. Conclusion

Three different modeling techniques have been investigated in the current study as examples to reveal possibility and reliability of modeling the fuel consumption from TSHD during its dredging process. Basically, all the models developed here are mathematical functions, which are aiming to calculate the outputs by means of given inputs, initial conditions and system parameters. However, they represent different modeling techniques, and demonstrate some general conclusions:

1. In all the three dimensions of the model zone (inputs, dynamics and model levels), towards the direction shown in Fig.3, the resulted model is from pure black box which only applies to static calculation on specific case to pure white box which includes only nature character of a system (*of course, a pure white box does not exist due to the complex of nature itself and knowledge shortage of human being*);
2. As demonstrated by modeling strategy I, in black level, a large amount of measurements have to be performed in order to provide enough information for model training. In other words, it is only applied to the conditions, which are similar to the measurement condition. It is the so-called 'individual model'; on the other hand, because the mathematical functions used in white level modeling are derived from physical first principal, as shown by modeling strategy

- III, by changing the initial conditions and system parameters, it could apply to a wide range of applications, therefore it is the ‘universal model’;
3. From the inputs perspective, by enriching input parameters, the accuracy of simulation output could be improved, whereas, by adding physical relations between inputs and outputs into inputs, the model becomes more grayish and more accurate;
 4. In the direction of ‘Dynamic’, by adding ‘past value’ into inputs, developing recurrent model configuration, introducing transfer functions and integral functions, the model become capable in simulation of dynamic behaviors which makes is more reliable for system modeling;
 5. By introducing physical principles into model transfer characters, the model becomes more whitish and generates more reliable outputs. And, more complex construction would be expected.

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Nomenclature

c	coefficient & fit-factor	[-]
C_Q^*	propeller torque coefficient	[-]
D	depth	[m]
	diameter	[m]
m	mass	[ton & kg]
M	torque	[kN]
n	revolution speed	[rpm]
P	power	[kW]
p	pressure	[pa]
Q	flow rate	[m ³ /s]
R	resistance	[kN]
R^2	measure of fit	[%]
t	thrust deduction factor	[-]
T	thrust	[kN]
	torque	[kN]
v	velocity	[m/s]
\hat{y}	measured value	[-]
X	sample	[-]
y	simulation output	[-]
α	pipe angle	[deg]
β	advance angle of propeller	[deg]
η	efficiency	[-]
θ	propeller pitch angle	[deg]
ρ	density	[ton/m ³]
τ	time constant	[s]

Subscript

A	advanced
b	brake
dis	discharge
drg	dredging
dyn	dynamic
eng	main diesel engine
$hopper$	hopper
i	indicate of input data
int	initial condition
ir	normalized input data
$loss$	loss
lp	lower section of suction pipe
max	maximum value
min	minimum value
$mixt$	mixture
$prop$	propeller propulsion
$pump$	pump
R	relative rotative
set	set point
$shaft$	shaft
$ship$	ship
ss	steady state
up	upper section of suction pipe
$water$	water

Ship CAD Systems - Past, Present and Possible Future

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Abstract

The evolution of computer technology employed in ship design and building will be traced from pre-graphic to current database-centric data management systems. Four of the currently most employed ship modelling techniques will be presented, and their contribution to design spiral, production, and PLM phases documented. Nature and role of the ship model will be discussed, and the current understanding of its nature analyzed in historical perspective. Contribution to the ship model by each method will be reviewed, and a comparison made with certain technologies, methods and processes in other industries. Possible evolutions using existing software, technology, and modelling methods will be considered, and a near-future vision thereof presented. Finally, one possible vision of the future will be presented.

1. Introduction

Visualization has been used by pretty much all life forms since the very early existence of life. Consider for example the colours of leaves, the flying patterns of insects, smiling, and so on. For early humans, visualization served even more purposes: general communication (ex. the ancient hunter who did not count may have drawn a picture to show all the deer in the herd he had spotted earlier), concretisation of symbols (ex. representation of feelings, spiritual entities), communication of intentions (ex. the bone carver represents what the bone bracelet he is working on will look like, or a hunting plan).

Over the centuries, visualisation became an increasingly structuring agent in the life of human kind, coming to influence, if not dictate, behaviour. For example, consider aesthetics and fashion.

On the more technical side, but only just, visualization techniques have been extended over time to represent conceptual information buried in large data sets, the goal being to communicate it in a generally understandable fashion. Communicating information in a way easily understandable by the receiver is therefore a driving factor in the formatting thereof, which in turn still requires consideration of social, cultural and technical additional factors. Consider for example, the fundamentally different hierarchical structures of groups around the world (ex. companies) and how this affects information management and flow, the resistance against change in methods, and the inability to implement certain techniques if appropriate tooling is not available or mastered.

Drawings are one of many means used to communicate several types of information: shapes, quantities, sizes, procedures, methods, logical data, planning, implementation, desire, intention, etc.

Coming to the world of ships, only drawing of the finished product remain from the early days of ship design and building, which is not to say that plans, however rudimentary, were not actually drawn.

The transition from the raft to the dugout canoe may indicate an intuitive understanding of Archimedes's principle, but there seem to be no records, graphical or otherwise, of this process. So, we can only assume that this knowledge was passed on orally, or by example, which likely constituted quite a communication feat in the days of probably limited technical vocabulary.

Water craft drawings probably started in the early Naval Architects' mind, when he walked the forest to find braches naturally shaped like the hull he intended to build. Later, and this is probably another technological turning point, wood was actually bent to fit a given shape. This is possibly when the explicit documenting of craft building techniques started, hence the formal creative process we call "design", a notable later example being the "Encyclopédie de Diderot et d'Alembert".

Fig.1: Petroglyph of, possibly, a canoe with crew and paddles or oars, ca. 8000 BC.
source: US Forest Service, Tongass National Forest, Alaska

Fig.2: *Planche de Marine*, one of several figures illustrating and detailing a ship's construction from the *Encyclopédie de Diderot et D'Alembert*, 1765, <http://diderot.alembert.free.fr/>

Drawings had become commonplace by the Middle Ages, be it to sketch paintings or statues, or to show the paying ruler what his building would look like, or simply to carry out an estimate of cost or required space. In the ship world, while drawings seem to have established themselves as a standard document a little later, they have since remained what is possibly still today the one universal way to communicate pretty much all types of information. Then, at some point in the 1960s, computer technology gained recognition, and started replacing the tools used to draw and calculate, but not the drawings themselves.

The task of combining computers and the fundamental need of a generic human useable graphical representation of information, be it a technical drawing, a photorealistic rendering, text or a bar graph, is, in the author's opinion, an ill understood requirement, and has become one significant obstacle in the effective exploitation of existing technology in communicating information.

2. A brief history of the use of computers in ship design and ship building

This paper is not intended to exhaustively document or catalogue the enormous amount of technological development and ensuing software and hardware products produced over the past decades in the fields of computer aided ship design and ship building, but rather to present a significant glimpse thereof, and thereby provide enough background for the reader to put the conclusion in context.

Despite the existence of television since the mid-1920s, early computers were in general exclusively dedicated to computation, kept well out of the way, and offered no easily available graphical interface or display until the late 1970s. Some may recall the blind punch cards on the DEC-10 terminals, the ca. 1978 IBM advertising "we take the computer out of the back room", and the ca. 1980 arrival of the awe inspiring Tektronics green on black, very high resolution display.

Fig.3: Tektronics green-on-green 4000 dpi monitor

The lack of a graphical user interface for the computer, of video graphics and of computer generated pictures probably dictated the birth of CAD as a logical modelling tool. Software development work in the field of CAD took place concurrently in several countries around the world, and some of those programs continue to be developed and remain commercially available today.

As a measure of the speed of development in the field of computers, by 1983 touch screens were used to create and edit distributed systems models, and in some countries desktop computers had become almost commonplace. This is the time when a first fork in the road appeared: one way went the comparatively very much lower cost desktop computer with its small screen and fast growing peripheral accessory list, the other went the far more powerful mainframe (soon to become the still quite large mini computer) and its significantly fewer peripherals. Concurrently, and particularly in the desktop computer world, easy-to-use modem-accessed data banks, early (internet) search engines, spreadsheets, and actual drawing programs became generally available. Crash proof laptops with solid state memory, integrated modem and network capability were only a few months behind. Shoebox size Ink-Jet colour printers appeared in 1987.

Fig.4: The HP110 second generation portable computer set includes ink-jet printer and portable disc drives for a total weight of under 4 kg and several hours battery autonomy,
Source: University of Waterloo, California

By the late 1980s, the choice of how to use the now commonplace graphical environment created a second fork in the road: one way went the CAD-based modelling systems, the other went those using graphics as the display of logical modelling systems.

Another significant factor driving the development of certain programs was the poor quality and limited size of printed output, which was hard to use with, for example, optical cutting machines. While computer generated drawings could be of lesser graphical quality than hand-made ones without significantly impacting the industry, cutting machines required far better. Hand tracing and cutting, as

well as hand-drawn sheets destined to optical cutting machines were replaced by transferring the cutting instructions directly from the computer to the machine, hence the birth of "NC", or numerically controlled, machines. In this case, the drawing was eliminated from the process, probably the only such instance.

3. The four most used methods for creating ship data models

Today, four methods seem to be the most used in creating ship data models: plain drafting, logical modelling, CAD-supported logical modelling, and logic-supported graphical modelling. Some continue to exist since the early days; others have been born of advances in technology, graphical display technology in particular.

Due to the widespread and heterogeneous use of the terms, before discussing the methods in themselves it may be appropriate to define what the words data model, CAD, logical, etc. stand for in this paper:

- Data model: a collection of data and information defining, describing or otherwise referring to one object, or collection of objects, such as a ship.
- CAD (Computer Aided Design): software, methods and technology in general providing functions and tools used in the creation or generation of graphically representable, original data model components. CAD modelling is carried out using an interactive CAD environment, such as drawing programs, graphical libraries, etc.
- Logical: definitions or entities related to object, generally non-graphical, such as attributes, properties, relations, associations, etc. Logical modelling is carried out using macros, scripts and other generally non-graphical methods.

3.1. Plain drafting

Plain drafting is just that. This method consists of drawings, essentially in pure 2D, representing and depicting all that can be with such means. The only and completely manual method existing before the inception of computers, today generally implemented via drawing programs. While data and information are rather limited in scope, drawings are in general very portable as CAD files can be shared among different software programs more often than not.

3.2. Logical modelling

Logical modelling involves describing data and information, e.g. objects, their properties and attributes, using text organized in scripts, macros, tables, syntactically coded files, etc. This was the only computer based methods existing before video displays became common. As an example, consider the definition of a line by a name and its end point absolute coordinates, such as :

Line "*name of line*" x_1, y_1, z_1 x_2, y_2, z_2

Which for a line called "edge of beam" and going from 0,0,0 to 1,1,1, would read

Line "edge of beam" 0,0,0 1,1,1

It can easily be seen how a variant of the command would allow the bounding of an object by another object, etc. Logical modelling requires an intimate knowledge of the overall model and sharing of a lot of information with other working on the same model to avoid duplications, misrepresentations and other errors. Logical models tend to be virtually impossible to share among different, but otherwise identical in scope, programs.

3.3. CAD supported logical modelling

In this case, the modelling takes place in a CAD environment, for example drawing, solid modelling, etc. The software program sources data and information directly from the CAD interface and/or model itself, the best programs working interactively and transparently, and integrate the harvested information with other non-graphical information and data entered otherwise or elsewhere.

Software programs implementing this method may use a database for storage of data and information, and/or use the CAD files themselves for storage. While a database may be less immediately portable than a CAD file, it is a far more robust and reliable storage means. Moreover, a database can be easily interfaced if not integrated with other data management systems, while CAD files hardly lend themselves to such practices.

3.4. Logic supported graphical modelling

This method involves the use of logical programming, partly or wholly, and a more or less comprehensive display of the defined entities is provided. Modern logic supported graphical modelling sometimes allows the direct use of graphical entities, of course only once they have been defined logically. This way, the software helps somewhat in the writing of macros and scripts.

4. Contribution of the methods to the design spiral, building and PLM work phases,

Of course all methods contribute to every phase of a ship's life but, perhaps surprisingly, the use of computers does not per se translate into a greater contribution.

4.1. Contribution to the design spiral

In this phase, an important contribution is made by the immediate availability of data and information. In this respect, plain drafting and CAD based modellers tend to surpass other, more logical oriented methods for a good portion of the phase. In addition to the availability of drawings by definition, drafting and CAD based methods also generally support immediate conversion of drawings, data and information to neutral formats, for broad and easy sharing.

While perhaps more flexible in case of changes at an advanced stage of the design phase, the more logical modelling oriented methods often require a significant amount of setting up and definition work before their models can be so exploited and drawings, data and information can be produced. Drawings are also often produced in very rigid formats, which severely restricts further processing and exploitation thereof.

Some CAD based systems build a relational/associative model via the CAD interface itself, possibly providing the best of all worlds during this phase.

Many advantages offered by certain methods are similar to those pertaining to the production phase, and will be discussed there, a more traditional ground for the exercise.

4.2 Contribution to the production phase

The production phase, often simplistically identified with detailed engineering, culminates with the modelling of each and every component of the ship that will be manufactured from stock, such as plate and pipe parts, or which requires a construction drawing for its fabrication, for example a railing or a ladder, or which is to be sourced as a finished product, such as equipment and machinery.

The methods' features which most contribute to this phase include: propagation of repetitive and relational information, thereby logically linking similar and associated objects, ease of sharing data and information of all types with other programs, ease of integration of data and information coming

from external, heterogeneous sources, ease of model creation and drawing production, ease of data and information management, ease of cooperative work, ease of data and information extraction and reporting, etc.

Plain drafting will contribute the least to this phase, as it will require the largest amount of manual, error-prone and repetitive work, while providing neither data nor information management facilities, nor allowing any derivation of data and information whatsoever.

Interfacing or better still integrating CAD systems with other relevant data and information management system, such as ERP, project management, etc., is also a major, although yet underexploited, advantage offered by some systems. An open architecture, API endowed database is fundamental in this respect.

Another important requirement in this phase is the ability to track the ship's construction, integrate production feed back, data and information into the model's environment, and analyse it for a dynamic critical path review. Again, this is doable with an open, extensible or interfaceable database.

4.3. Contribution to the PLM phase

This is possibly the phase in the ship's life where most systems do not contribute as much as one would expect or hope. This is due to various factors, such as the inability to provide the model, related data and information in commonplace or even open file formats, to the modelling software not being portable or requiring significant training to be used, etc.

Possibly yet more than in the production phase, PLM will benefit from the integral ship model, combining CAD, logical and non-CAD information being available via an open architecture, commercial database, which will allow integration with other data and information management systems.

5. File formats, data structure, databases

In great part due to historical reasons, even some present-day software development strategic choices remain heavily influenced by past necessities. The risk, or choice, is to remain isolated in a data communication and management sense.

File formats, arbitrary object definitions and hence the inability to share models among ship modelling programs are a quasi-insurmountable obstacle in the exploitation of the ship model by the end user, the ship owner or manager.

The pure drafting method does not even produce a model to speak of, and its final product, drawings, simply provides reference documentation, with the additional caveat that more often than not drawing sets are not kept up to date during ship construction and later ship modifications.

In the case of ship modelling systems, object definition and file format are historically intimately related, and in many cases the early development environment has remained fundamentally unchanged over years of software development. Save for one or two more recently born software programs, ship modelling systems were developed at a time when CAD and video were either simply not commonly available or felt to be inadequate for the task, hence the perhaps forced choice of logical modelling already discussed. Moreover, until very recently, ship modelling applications were intended to serve the requirements of production only, with limited attention, if any, to design and PLM.

Great importance was placed on modelling and NC producing of structure, and lesser efforts dedicated to software for the modelling and production of distributed systems, which were instead handled by software developed for the process and energy industries. Such industrial programs were

often used in the ship industry, but not integrated with the structure modelling system. Distributed systems modelling also suffered, and continue to suffer, from the poor cousin's syndrome, and seem to be unavoidably reserved the back seat when allocating resources, or scheduling, let alone take priority over structure.

The inexistence of "standards" and the rather different cultural and technological environments in which software was developed led to programs performing the same tasks in a variety of, remarkably incompatible, ways. As the goal of ship modelling was reached with completion of the ship, the possibility of model sharing or re-use was probably never even considered.

Over the years, modelling programs grew more capable and more powerful, and the concept of pre-outfitting was born out of the need to lower costs and increasing capacity by shorten building time. Greater sophistication of existing software often also meant reduced flexibility in system adaptation, forcing the bridging of the gap between ship structural modelling and non-ship distributed systems modelling applications. This was achieved mostly by creating dedicated data exchange formats serving only two programs.

Moreover, many programs were being sold commercially, and development continued along existing lines, increasing software isolation and losing any chance there may have been of catering to some sort of object definition standards.

Software using a database to store geometry, topology and other data, as opposed to files, could provide the environment in which to potentially create a model complete in all its components, or least complete to the extents allowed by the available modelling capabilities.

The importance and ensuing benefits of sharing models was recently recognised, and attempts were made to create modern neutral file standards, such as STEP, an exercise which – after several years of work – has not yet produced an industry-wide practical outcome.

Today, model sharing is limited to some programs exporting and/or importing solid or similarly fashioned geometry, using CAD standards such as ACIS or Parasolids. However, no data or information is shared in this way. At least one program goes a few steps farther, by acquiring native geometry and, if exposed, corresponding logical information.

The intention to create the all-encompassing model was the birth of the much abused "product model" punch line, and a true result has yet to materialize.

6. The model

The "model", or to evoke the far more fashionable definition "product model", has been referred to a lot so far in this paper, but different readers will have attributed quite different meanings to this label. One general definition could go something like "a CAD model which includes all the parts making up the ship". However, "CAD" and "all" remain very generic ways of defining anything, let alone something as complex as a ship. A recent, even richer sounding, evolution of this definition is "building information model".

6.1. CAD data

"CAD" could be anything from a simplified sketch to a fully detailed, realistic, 3D model and "all" generally refers to those portions of the ship which the software being considered can model, in whichever way it can. "Information" is also a purpose-suited word, often used to convey the impression that there is more than one will really find, particularly in that the generally limited data set available tends to pertain solely to a sub-set of the "CAD" portion of the model. So, in order to avoid the debatable accuracy of many claims made in the commercial world, the less-specific but potentially more encompassing definition "ship model" was and will continue being used here.

Moreover, commercial promotion of software products and ground-breaking research tends to highlight the contents per se of the model, be they CAD or logical, and largely omit any consideration of the availability, usability and specific usefulness of such contents aside from the generation of only a part of the finished ship.

6.2. Non-CAD data

Stopping short of proposing to integrate the model with all the even remotely related available data in existence during the design, building and PLM phases, there still is a remarkable amount of non-CAD information which could, and should, be combined with the CAD model, within the model itself or to produce a non-CAD, integrated data set.

ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning) is the most evoked such data set, but a lot more is already available and commonly in use, albeit separately from the ship model, such as production feed back, production analysis, critical path forecasting and analysis, cost estimation and analysis, contingency planning, etc. It is only too evident that a lot of this data is very directly related to the design, production and PLM phases, but it is not directly attributable to the contents of the CAD model. On the other hand, non-geometrical relations can easily be established and exploited between CAD and non-CAD objects, data and information.

6.3. The ship model

Combining the ship's CAD model with related non-CAD data would yield what is probably the closest to the ship model. In turn, the ship model could be the live, integral part of a more far ranging model. Imagine for example a database of up-to-date ship loading and unloading capabilities, current machinery breakdowns, etc., being used to schedule port activities.

So, let us now use the definition "ship model" to represent a collection of ship-related data including CAD, CAD-related logical, and non-CAD-related data, without restrictions.

7. Relevance and role of ship model components

Throughout the discussion so far, the components of the ship model have been loosely collected into three very broad categories: CAD, logical and non-CAD. This seems to work well, and lends itself as an effective data set classing approach identifying three categories. We could then assign attributes to each category, such as "time critical", "static", "dependent", "independent", and so on.

7.1. CAD components

CAD components can be attributed all the attributes listed above, for example:

- time critical : a drawing, or a computer model used to derive a drawing, must be completed before a certain date in order not to hold up the classification process or even the building of the ship.
- static : once issued, a drawing is considered to be static, one needs not further verify its contents.
- dependent : the contents of a drawing or the objects making up a model are related and will influence / depend on to one another.
- independent : certain CAD quantities, such as the length of the ship, are and will remain independent of other data. For example the breadth of a Suez-max ship will not change even if a greater load carrying capacity were required and catered to.

The role of CAD is to show, symbolically or realistically, what the product being depicted or illustrated is to look like.

7.2. Logical components

Logical components also can take on all the attributes listed above:

- time critical: the power and torque curves of an engine will influence engine room design and propeller selection. The choice of the engine is therefore a time critical component.
- static: a given object can be mounted only in one way. This orientation will not be changed by anything else in the ship model.
- dependent: a weld detail will depend on the thickness and metal grade of the components being welded. Weld detail is a dependent component.
- independent: for a given ship, the wattage of the ship lights will remain unchanged irrespective of anything else.

Mostly due to the actual implementation scheme in software, the role of logical components is mainly limited to qualify CAD objects, although their role is actually far more varied and far reaching.

7.3. Non-CAD components

Non-CAD components also can take on all the attributes listed above:

- time critical: knowing which surface treatment must be applied to an object must be known in good time for the provisioning of the appropriate supplies and for the timely availability of that object during construction. Supply of the required consumables and ability to apply them is time critical.
- static: suppose an object can be delivered by rail only. The railroad's traffic schedule, sometimes fixed months in advance, is a static component.
- dependent: the material grade of a plate will depend on the thickness it can take at the location where it will be placed, and on the load it will be carrying. For example consider a thin, heavily loaded plate which must therefore be of high tensile strength steel. The ability to actually mount the plate depends on the availability of welders qualified for this type of metal.
- independent: something as simple as production feed-back often influences what goes on in the technical office and beyond, during the production phase itself. Consider the case of a fabrication gone wrong due to a design mistake, and the ensuing need to re-design it, re-source or re-build its parts, and re-fabricate it.

The role of non-CAD components is to add "external" data and information to the model which will influence any of the ship's phases, hence the CAD components as well. Anyway, the purpose of the exercise above is not to subdivide components into intersecting groups or classes, but rather to simply show how any of the above carefully worded definitions could be plausibly changed just slightly and that component becomes assigned to another group or changes attributes.

Possibly with very few exceptions, every component of a ship model, regardless of its nature, is relevant and potentially of critical importance due to the deep, cascading interaction between all components, direct or indirect. Therefore, it seems safe to state that a ship model should include the greatest quantity of components from the categories mentioned above, and that they should be accessible to anyone needing that information, in as neutral a format or fashion as possible in order to avoid needing to use the native software application.

8. Other industries

Methods, processes, analyses, etc. are all different ways to describe tools, or means to reach a goal. Tool is a convenient, modern word, and will be used here as the generic definition of choice. Many examples can be brought forward to illustrate technologies and methods being used in other industries

that would benefit the ship industry via the creation and management of the ship model, but, in the end, it is easy to condense them all by drawing an exquisite analogy, and in a very stimulating fractal fashion, with the search engine, a tool that permeates our modern world much deeper than most realize.

The very concept of the search engine, an old but increasingly important tool, provides the link between the opening discussion on communications, the processing of data and information during (at least) three main stages of all phases in a process, very early planning, under-way and emergency, and the varying nature of the data itself.

This ancient tool, already implemented in Babylon via clay tablets and much later with card indexes, can provide significant help far and beyond its current implementation, and this without requiring revolutionary computers or other inexistent technology.

8.1. Very early planning

During planning, use is made of uncertain or estimated data and information. Provisions are drawn and safety margins applied. The lesser the certainty about what is thought to be known, the greater the spectrum of possible outcomes is, and the greater the potential deviation from the objective goal. At this stage, the ability to identify and quantify information and its quality is crucial: estimated data can be used effectively if a measure is known of its presumed accuracy, inaccuracy, and impact. Ship weight estimation is a glaring example of this.

Drawings, low-detail CAD models and macroscopic data analysis are easily identified characteristics of the planning phase. In some circles, this is known as the concept and/or feasibility phase. This is when fundamental mistakes can be made. Let us use as an example the industrial process which cannot yield the product at the forecasted cost, a surprise discovered well after production got under way.

8.2. Under-way

This is when everything is supposed to proceed smoothly, according to plan. Once a process is under way, the main activity is monitoring and checking. Once again, drawings, more detailed CAD models and data analysis at various levels of detail are used to assess progress and the quality thereof.

8.3. Emergency

Many situations qualify as emergencies, but the common denominator is generally the immediate need for all potentially relevant data and information to be available and exploitable. Much can come from the CAD model, much cannot and will not. So, once again, drawings, CAD models, non-CAD data and data analysis tools will be sought after. Qualification of the need to have data and information of all types, have access to it, and be able to exploit it effectively and in a way useful to everyone needing it will be the last factor supporting the assessment and vision to follow.

9. What can be done today

A lot of technology exists today that can be put to use in creating, maintaining and exploiting the ship model: drawing software, 3D modelling software, open-architecture databases, etc. And, not least, the search engine analogy used above is easily applied in reverse, when dealing with input to the model.

Input can take many forms, and data can be of disparate nature: drawing entities, logical attributes and properties, non-CAD information, etc. Then, if input were identified, its relations to other objects in the model could be established, regardless of their respective natures. Logical modellers and some CAD modellers work this way, but input of non-CAD or not CAD-related data is often hampered, if not impossible.

So, input facilities are an integral part of the data management process. Graphical input techniques are probably by far the easiest and more intuitive channel, easily used by just about anyone, and allowing for direct, transparent input identification and management.

Now, let us consider the search engine again. The "finds" returned include both exact and approximate matches, as the search engine will purposely use inaccuracies to cater for what could be loosely defined input search criteria. (The engine is programmed to operate in a stringent fashion). Nonetheless, it is easy to gather substantial amounts of relevant information from a vast, unformatted amount of source data.

On the other hand, in the case of a ship model, the environment is far more regimented than the contents of the internet. This favours cross-matching and correct connections between objects, or groups of objects. In modelling work, stringent rules must be followed when defining objects, and even more so when defining dependencies and relations. In a given planning model, representative data will use fixed formats: dates, locations, etc. The list of examples of what is achieved already thanks to formal formatting is long: bar codes, report table formats, time sheets, ISO procedures, etc.

So, these being known quantities, the following would constitute a constructive step in assembling data from different sources and exploiting it in innumerable ways:

- having the data
- the data being available and accessible
- the data being readable and interpretable
- having information about data interconnection (this data pertains to that object but only on the day of the week defined in table so and so, . . .).

All the above exist today, but rarely as a useable, complete set. No sustainable reasons exist today to justify the persistence of such a restriction. Of course, as seen above, another factor is that in many cases similar (or even identical) objects will be defined in very different ways, thereby making the connection virtually impossible. This places an objective constraint on data sharing and exploitation, but one that can be circumvented and that need not persist either.

Search engines have been used every day since the existence of computers, for example to find a file containing a certain word. Today, there exist sophisticated query tools, file searchers, automated data assembly tools, etc. that can be employed, if the source data is available and can be searched thanks to documented formatting. So, a more effective exploitation of existing data and information, of varying nature, purpose and scope, is technically possible today, and would be more commonplace if source data were richer, more easily available and easier to access.

10. Conclusion

If the present paper were to be condensed in a few statements, these could be:

- while not a means for systematic or automated data and information management, drawings remain a fundamental corner stone in making information available to the real-world, wider ship audience, at all times, information without which not much would happen.
- non-CAD data is a dangerously overlooked, vital component of the ship model that can and should be used throughout the various phases of a ship's life. Combining and connecting this data with the CAD model provides a quasi-universal means of making it known, understood and exploitable.

Achieving the common goal of these two statements, e.g. making relevant information available in a way that is meaningful to the recipient, at all times starting from the earliest stage of concept design and until the latest stage of dismantling, requires software which easily allows:

- input of appropriate and relevant data and information, be it graphical, logical or non-CAD, via standard, non-proprietary interfaces and/or data tools.
- exploitation and generation of model-associated drawings, which must remain available for further formatting using standard, non-proprietary CAD tools.
- extraction of CAD related logical data for analysis, reporting, etc., also combined with non-CAD data, via standard, non-proprietary data management tools.

The software and hardware needed to accomplish the above exist today, off the shelf, and some ship CAD systems already provide the facilities, if not the tools, identified in this paper as being one avenue towards industry-wide exploitation of the existing, rich, ship data set.

A Decision Support Framework for the Concurrent Selection of Multiple Air Emission Controls

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Abstract

An increased focus on environmental performance in shipping will require a considerable investment in air emissions controls on both new and existing vessels in the coming years. This is a complex decision problem that goes beyond a simple, generalized cost-benefit assessment of each individual control technology. This is mainly due to the fact that different types of emissions calls for different, and often incompatible or conflicting, abatement technologies and that in order to meet the rather ambitious future reduction targets, several technologies need to be adopted concurrently. In this paper, a decision support framework for air emission control selection is proposed. The approach taken is that of providing a classification of the controls, enacting constraints towards and providing feedback on the interaction effects between technologies. This is then integrated into a decision support framework for concurrent air emission controls selection.

1 Introduction

Global warming and green operation have become an important driving force in different industries and on different levels. Regulatory incentives have been enforced to reduce emission to air from both land based and ocean going segments. The land based sector is currently more restricted than the ocean going, but we can expect more stringent regulatory enforcement in the shipping sector in the near future. The initiative to establish an Energy Efficiency Design Index *IMO (2009b)*, and an Energy Efficiency Operating Indicator, *IMO (2009a)*, are examples of such efforts. In addition the International Maritime Organisation (IMO) has currently enforced restrictions on the emissions of NO_x and SO_x, *IMO (2005)*. These regulatory incentives will make the need for emission control methods arise.

In this paper air emission reduction methods are referred to as air emission controls. Several different controls exist, some commercialised and implemented on a number of vessels, while some have not yet left the drawing table. One of the challenges for reducing emission in the shipping sector is the long lifetime of a vessel. Implementing new technologies on new designs can be far easier than retrofitting an older vessel to comply with today's and future environmental standards. Besides, some of the methods of emission reduction are costly investments and their presence can restrict a later technical modification to the machinery or vessel.

Meeting tighter environmental regulations and customer demands is a challenge for all stakeholders in the shipping sector. Decision support discussed through this work refer to the quest on investing in air emission controls or not, and in case which methods to implement. In this discussion the ship owner needs to define whether an operational, tactical or strategic effort is wanted. Besides, the key factors in such decisions will vary from one decision maker to the next. In addition, since a lot of uncertainty remains around the air emission controls, flexibility in the decision support model is necessary.

This report defines a methodology for supporting the ship owners in the decision process of reducing emissions to air. Firstly a classification of the different air emission controls is proposed and their interaction is studied. Then a decision support framework based on the provided classification is propounded.

2 Technical study

This chapter presents a study of methods utilized for controlling emissions to air from ships. The first section reflects on the definition of an air emission control, while the next section proposes a type of control classification. The last section discusses the incompatibilities and interactions that may occur when combining emission reduction measures.

2.1 Definition of air emission controls

The reference to the set of methods to reduce air emissions is termed differently in literature; *IMO (2009a)* refers to technological and operational potential for reduction of emissions, *Fournier (2006)* and *Corbett and Chapman (2006)* to control technologies while *ENTEC (2005a)* presents abatement technologies. For this decision support framework we needed a generic term that could include all the methods, being operational or technical. The term was supposed to take into consideration that emission reduction methods of today might be standardized on all vessels in the future, therefore the word abatement was not found suitable to all the measures. In conclusion, we decided to use air emission controls.

The term air emission controls can then be defined as any effort done by ship owners, operators or designers to reduce the amount of emission to air from a vessel. Some air emission controls, such as slide valves, are already commonly installed on engines; while there is a widely range of measures still in the research phase, where no real installations or testing have been conducted yet. When some new methods are expected to be created in the future, the ones already existing are likely to be improved, this being by having a better potential, being less space consuming or being less expensive. For instance, the price of the Selective Catalytic Reduction (SCR) is already much less than it was few years ago, *Corbett and Chapman (2006)*.

2.2 Classification of air emission controls

2.2.1 Existing classifications

The air emission controls can be classified in many different ways, the most common ones being by the pollutant type they aim to reduce or by the vessel system that they affect. *IMO (2009a)* defines the air emission controls into four categories, being: “Options for improving the energy efficiency”, “Renewable energy sources”, “Fuels with lower fuel-cycle CO₂ emissions” and “Emission-reduction technologies”. The “Options for improving the energy efficiency” are then divided in two main levels: Design and operation.

Similarly, *Wärtsilä (2009a)* has proposed four groups of measures to reduce energy consumption: Ship Design, Propulsion, Machinery and Operation & Maintenance, while *Fournier (2006)* has classified the emission control technologies into: In-engine and operational modification, Water-based controls, After-treatment on-board controls, Shore-side controls and Fuel switching.

For our purpose we needed a classification based on the principle of air emission reduction. A common characteristic of these classifications is that they are not based on emission calculation practice. This made us decide to create a classification more suitable to our decision support framework.

2.2.2 Classification approach

Firstly we classified the controls by the nature of how they reduce emissions. This due to the fact that emission estimation and hence emission reduction one of the most important steps when deciding upon air emission controls selection.

Some measures will change the fuel consumption while some others will act on the emission factor (C_f). The emission factor is depending on the engine type and the fuel used *Endresen et al. (2003)*, but not on the vessel's mission. The air emission controls modifying the C_f will be called abatement methods, while measures reducing the fuel consumption are here divided in three categories; renewable energy source, improving energy efficiency and energy saving by operation.

The proposed new classification is shown on Fig. 1. The explanation of the different categories is given in the following sections.

Fig. 1: Classification of the air emission controls according to the principle of emissions reduction

2.2.3 Changing the fuel consumption

Renewable energy sources are divided in wind power, solar power and wave power. Kites, wind sails, solar panels and utilisation of wave power are still not available on commercial basis.

Improving energy efficiency is here understood as carrying out the same amount of useful work, but using less energy. By burning less fuel the emission of exhaust gases are reduced. This category is sub-divided into three levels, according to the system of the ship that the control affects. The levels are design, propulsion and machinery. As an example, design measures can be air lubrication or lightweight construction; propulsion options can be advanced propeller blade sections and machinery measures such as Waste Heat Recovery (WHR).

Most of the design improvement options are best suitable for new designs, since they include mainly modifications to hull and superstructure, while most of the propulsion and machinery measures can be retrofitted to old vessels.

Energy saving by operation is also a category of measures making the vessel carrying out the same amount of useful work while using less energy. In this case the measures are operational and they do not affect the ship configuration. Those controls can be used on both new and old ships. Some examples of saving energy by operations are weather routing, optimisation of the vessel trim, energy management and hull coating.

A range of studies have focused on improving energy efficiency by operation. One example is the optimization of ship routing and scheduling, *Fagerholt et al. (2010)* and *Brønbo et al. (2006)*. Often these problems involve multiple stakeholders, such as owners, charterer, multi-model transport operators, shipper and receiver of goods, cargo sellers and buyers, port authorities and terminal operators *IMO (2009a)*. This may lead to sub-optimization in parts of the supply chain. Still, there is much to be gained on operational awareness in respect to energy saving, and hence cost savings for the operator, *Fagerholt et al (2010)*.

2.2.4 Changing the specific emission pollutant

Abatement methods are the fourth air emission control category, comprising technical measures regarding the machinery system. There is a range of different measures and techniques available from engine producers and specialised subcontractors.

Emission reduction by abatement methods is divided in two sub-levels, the pro-active methods and the re-active methods. Pro-active methods act on the fuel before combustion in the engine or the combustion process by itself (such as for instance reducing the fuel temperature in the combustion chamber); and re-active methods refer to techniques addressing the exhaust gas after combustion.

As can be seen in Fig. 2, the pro-active efforts are further divided in three sub-levels, fuel concept, fuel switch and technical abatement. Following is a description of each level.

Fig. 2: Classification of the abatement methods

By fuel concept it is referred to radical changes in the machinery due to switching fuel. Such measures can include the change from diesel engines to gas engines (LNG) or to biofuels. While other classification definitions consider switching to LNG as an improving energy efficiency measure, the authors included it to the abatement methods category since it will reduce the emission factor for CO₂, NO_x and SO_x but not aim at reducing the fuel consumption. Such extreme efforts are most appropriate for new designs, where potential solutions can be estimated. Indeed potential machinery solutions for fuel concept can vary in a great extent in respect to weight, size and cost. For older vessels this might compromise on the transportation capacity. In the case of changing from ordinary diesel combustion to LNG powering this is clearly the case.

Fuel switch is referred as switching from a high sulphur content fuel to a low sulphur content fuel. Fuel switch is included in the abatement methods category for the same reason than fuel concept; it will modify the emission factor for SO_x but not act on the fuel consumption. It is a pro-active emission reducing effort since by using a fuel with less sulphur content you reduce the emissions of SO_x created. Ordinarily, switching to a low-sulphur fuel does not impose any technical changes on the ship, merely higher fuel costs for the operator, *ENTEC (2005a)*. This is the main reason why those measures are in a different category than switching to LNG. There is though an increasing number of Sulphur Environmental Control Areas, *Balland et al. (2009)* and some ship owners can choose to run the engines on low sulphur fuel only when operating inside of these. This lead to the storage of two different fuel types on the ship, and some modifications on fuel storage tanks might be necessary, *ENTEC (2005c)*.

Pro-active technical abatement methods are technologies that modify the existing machinery in order to prevent the formation of a pollutant. They are available for implementation on both new designs and older vessels. Concerning NO_x, the pro-active technical abatements are mainly focused on reducing the peak temperature in the combustion process. Some examples of NO_x pro-active technical abatement are slide valves, advanced operational modifications, Direct Water Injection (DWI) and Humid Air Motor (HAM). Their descriptions are presented in *Balland et al. 2009*.

The re-active technical abatements are technologies that react on the exhaust from the combustion engine and reduce the amount of a targeted pollutant. Those technologies can be onboard the vessel such as the Sea Water Scrubbing (SWS) and the Selective Catalytic Reduction (SCR) but can also be in port such as Advanced Maritime Emissions Control System (AMECS) which is presented in *Fournier (2006)*.

2.3 Interactions between the different air emission controls

Since regulations on ship emissions to air are to be sharply strengthened in the next decade, to have the right to operate it might be necessary to implement several controls on the same ship. In this section we will study how the different air emission controls are interacting. First we will present their compatibility, and then their mutual influence.

2.3.1 Compatibility

Implementing one air emission control can prevent another one to be installed. This can occur firstly if the two controls have non-compatible functions. For instance, one cannot implement the operational measure “ballast optimization” on a ballast-free ship. We will in this chapter present how compatibility issues can be modeled mathematically, and what kind of non-compatibility parameters should be taken into consideration.

Let A be the set of air emission controls. Given two air emission controls i and j such that $(i, j) \in A$, the compatibility constraint can be formulated as follow in a mathematical model:

$$\partial_i + \partial_j \leq 2 - C_{ij} \quad \forall (i, j) \in A, \quad (1.1)$$

where

$\partial_i \in \{0, 1\}$ is a binary decision variable for implementing the air emission control i , with $i \in A$,
 $C_{ij} \in \{0, 1\}$ is a compatibility parameter for implementing both controls i and j , with $(i, j) \in A$,
 such as

$$C_{ij} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if the air emission controls are compatible} \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Two air emission controls can have compatible functions but still cannot be implemented at the same time. Indeed, some air emission controls can have some specific requirements that cannot always be fulfilled if another control is implemented. A specific need for a control could for instance be heat or low sulphur content in the fuel. As an example, the SCR technology requires the exhaust gas to have a high temperature (above 270°C) and the SWS have an important cooling effect on the exhaust, *ENTEC (2005c)*. Therefore their compatibility will require some investigation. On the other hand, Exhaust Gas Recirculation (EGR) can be used only with low sulphur content fuel, *ENTEC (2005b)*. So for this technology to be installed a fuel concept or fuel switch has to be already implemented onboard the vessel.

2.3.2 Mutual influence of the air emission controls

Two different air emission controls can be compatible, but interact on each other. In this section we identify the parameters that are influenced by the implementation sequence of the air emission controls and we propose a model to consider this influence factor in decision support.

The total emission reduction of the two controls cannot be assumed to be the sum of the potential emission reduction of each one, as shown in “Table 1-2 – Assessment of potential reductions of CO2 emissions from shipping by using known technology and practices” of the Second IMO GHG Study, *IMO (2009a)*. If two controls act on the same sub-system of the vessel then an interaction is likely to occur.

We can also assume that the costs, both operational and capital, of implementing a method are dependent on the controls already onboard the vessel; this because, for instance, there might be higher installation costs or a reduced lifespan of the control i.e. higher operational costs. To illustrate this fact we will take the example of the SCR technology. Its operational costs are depending on the sulphur content of the fuel used, *ENTEC (2005c)*. If the vessel is using a fuel with sulphur content less than 1.5% then the reactor needs to be rebuilt less often. Indeed, with a normal fuel (2.7% sulphur content) the reactor has to be rebuilt every 2.5 years due to sulphur poisoning, while only every 5 years with a $\leq 1.5\%$ sulphur fuel.

If we consider a parameter v_i in our case to be the costs or the emission reduction, the effect of implementing the air emission controls i would be as described in equation (1.2). The equation (1.3) is an illustration of its possible application.

$$v_i \partial_i + \sum_{j<i} I_{ij} x_{ij} \quad \forall i \in A, \quad (1.2)$$

where

v_i = parameter affected by air emission control i ,

$\partial_i = \{0,1\}$ is the decision variable for implementing the air emission control i , with $i \in A$,

I_{ij} = the influence parameter of implementing control j when i is already implemented,

$x_{ij} \in \{0,1\}$ = binary variable based on the implemented status of controls i and j , with $(i, j) \in A$, such as

$$x_{ij} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if only control } i, \text{ only } j \text{ or none of them are implemented} \\ 1 & \text{if both control } i \text{ and } j \text{ are implemented} \end{cases}$$

As an example of application we can have:

$$c_{tot} = \sum_i \left(c_i \partial_i + \sum_{j<i} I_{ij}^c x_{ij} \right) \quad (1.3)$$

where

c_{tot} = total costs for emissions reduction,

c_i = costs of the implementing control i ,

I_{ij}^c = the cost influence matrix of implementing j when i is already implemented.

To not add twice the effect of having the control i when installing j , we sum only for $j<i$. By doing this we consider the influence matrix as symmetric.

This model is limited to a two by two comparison. An extension in further work should investigate the interactions and the possible mathematical modeling for several controls combined as well as the order of implementation.

2.3.3 Combined interactions

The difference between non compatibility and important mutual influence is not always clear. The space requirement, for instance, could be interpreted in both ways. Indeed, if the space requirement of two controls is high, the measures are less likely to be able to be implemented at the same time. This could lead to non-compatibility of the two controls. But if we consider that we can always find space onboard a vessel, even if this leads to a reduction of the cargo capacity i.e. increasing the costs, then the space becomes an influence factor and will make the costs of the second control to implement sharply increase.

Another example is the redundant measures, like the Direct Water Injection and Humid Air Motor technologies. They are both dealing with lowering the temperature in the combustion chamber by

adding water into the chamber. The Direct Water Injection technology injects fresh water while the Humid Air Motor method uses sea water vapour, *ENTEC (2005b)*. Therefore the emission reduction of the second method installed is likely to be very small.

How to deal with this issue would be to combine compatibility and influence effects, by considering very high negative influence effects as non-compatibility. One way of modeling them together would be to use a single parameter matrix where the non-compatibility would be represented by a penalty coefficient, such as the big M method used in optimization problems. As an example, by using the notation of the section above, we will have $I_{ij}^c = M$ if i and j should not be implemented together and if the costs are to be minimized.

3 Decision support framework for selection of air emission controls

The following chapter presents an approach for decision support framework for the selection of air emission controls. The first section presents the emission control categories in a planning horizon. The second section introduces the defined decision support methodology, whilst further work and optional extensions to the approach are proposed in the last section.

3.1 Planning for the future

One of the main questions for the ship owners when deciding on air emission controls implementation is which period into the future to take into consideration when aiming at emissions reduction and regulation compliance. The four classes of air emission controls defined in Chapter 2 represent different decision planning horizons. Decisions are often referred to as strategic, tactic or operational. Strategic decisions are meant to last for a long period of time and have organizational impacts, *Mallach (1994)*. Tactical decisions generally takes place within the context of the strategically decision and affect the activities for a limited time into the future, *Mallach (1994)*. Operational decisions relates to short-time activities where tasks, goals and resources are defined by prior tactical and strategic decisions, *Mallach (1994)*. In maritime transportation tactical/operational planning is considered as studies involving short-term routing and scheduling problems, *Fagerholt et al. (2010)*. The strategic planning contributions are scarce, but some studies involving long-term decisions for ship operator as fleet size and mix planning have been carried out, *Fagerholt et al. (2010)*.

The emission control class of emission saving by operation will here represent decisions on a tactical/operational level, where the aim is to reach the emission reduction target on the next voyage or route. Depending on company policy the operational/tactical decisions could be on a ship owner or ship operator level.

Decision on ship design, as hull shape and propeller type are strategic decisions meant to last the vessel's lifetime. Decisions with direct impact on the ship's performance and with limited or no possibilities to cost-effectively be redone are here defined as strategic decisions and represented by improve energy efficiency and renewable energy source.

The fourth class, abatement methods, can be argued method specific dependent. System modifications are without doubt strategic decisions, whilst fuel switch between different bunker values on sulphur might be a decision based on fuel price or availability and can have a tactical/operational horizon.

3.2 Methodology

When deciding to implement air emission controls many aspects are to be taken into account. Fig. 3 presents an overview of what is expected as inputs, constraints, parameters and outputs for the decision support of installing controls. A more detailed approach is presented in Fig. 4 in the next chapter.

Fig. 3: Black box approach

The vessel inputs are specifications as main dimensions, machinery system, and design speed amongst others. Mission is the defined task the vessel is set to perform. More on interpretation of mission is discussed in the next section. Regulations are national and international regulations on emissions to air. The pollutant type that the regulations aim at controlling, the date of entry into force and the foundation for possible compliance, taxes or penalties, are important inputs.

The constraints relate to compliance between air emission controls and ship type, mission type or other air emission controls. The parameters refer to the impact the controls have on fuel consumption and specific emission pollutant, on investment and operational costs and the influence on emissions and costs when controls are combined.

Outputs from the black box of air emission controls are key performance indicators (KPI's) as change in fuel consumption, emissions, costs and possible vessel design changes. Such indicators will be of great importance for a ship owner or designer when deciding an approach for the future.

3.2.1 Approach

The process of reducing the air emissions can be divided in two steps. The first one is defining the target and the second is finding how to most efficiently reach it. The approach for the

Fig. 4: Approach for deciding target and creating possible solutions of combinations of air emission controls

selection of air emission controls is shown on Fig. 4. This approach is to be done for every combination of air emission controls.

The different parts of the flowchart: Target and decision basis, calculations of the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), compatibility check and update of the KPIs are defined below. The compatibility between the different air emission controls has been explained in section 2.3, therefore only the compatibility between the vessel and the controls will be described here.

The planned emissions target can naturally be to comply with the existing regulations. However you can also chose to comply with the regulations that will enter into force in a certain time horizon. This time horizon needs then to be selected and the target is a certain amount of pollutant. How to reach this target the most efficiently is then most likely costs dependent.

Besides air emission regulations and since many of the air emission controls reduce the fuel consumption, the motivation for lowering emissions can simply be to reduce the fuel costs. In addition, the selection of the target can also be motivated by the will of having a green image, or by some customer's requirements. Some trading segments are more exposed to a customer demand on green operation than others. An example is the car shipping industry, where the car vessels are the main transportation from producer to supplier, and to maintain a green facade to the customers the transportation by ships needs to be proclaimed environmental friendly.

In those three last cases the question of defining precisely your target is important. It can be a Δ emissions where your reference point can be you ship prior of any implementation or a baseline for your ship type. I can also be a Δ fuel consumption or a Δ costs. This target choice is dependent on the ship owner's motivations.

In the specific case of tradable quotas, the two steps of finding the target and to plan how to reach it are inter-connected. The target will not be a fixed number but will depend on the plan selected.

Initial measurement on KPI's

The initial situation for the vessel is given by key performance indicators (KPI's) as fuel consumption, amount of emission to air per pollutant type, capital and operational costs.

The ships mission is the task the ship is set to perform and is needed when evaluating the ships performance. The mission is defined as a set O of operational profiles, which again is defined as a set S of operational states, *Gaspar and Erikstad (2009)*. The operational state might be defined by speed (knots) and time (hours) or distance (nautical miles) or even service or capabilities, *Gaspar and Erikstad (2009)*. A development toward more advanced and complex machinery systems has been seen, *Gaspar et al. (2010)*, which gives an extra dimension of complexity when estimating performance on emissions to air. As in the study of Ship Machinery Configuration Comparison by *Larsen et al. (2009)* the power requirement per state and the engine mode (MCR) per engine can be assumed known. This is based on the assumption that estimations on load distribution and power requirement are found by means not further discussed in this work.

The fuel consumption F_f is found by formula (1.5), which is given for each fuel type f . The fuel consumption is summed for all engines e running on fuel type f . Total fuel consumption for engine e for all operational states s in all operational profiles o in a mission is given as F_o' . Fuel consumption per engine per operational state is found by the engines installed power $P_{l,e}$, the mode of the engine $m_{e,so}$ (MCR), time in state t_{so} and specific fuel oil consumption $SFOC_{efso}$.

Fuel consumption per fuel type

$$F_f = \sum_e F_o' = \sum_e \sum_o \sum_s P_{l,e} * m_{e,s_o} * t_{s_o} * SFOC_{e,f,s_o} \quad \forall f \in F, \quad (1.4)$$

where

F_f = Fuel consumption of fuel type f by all engines e for a mission,

F_o' = Fuel consumption of type f for one engine e for a mission,

P_l = Installed power for one engine e ,

m_{e,s_o} = Engine mode (MCR) for engine e in state s in operating profile o ,

t_{s_o} = Time spent in state s in operating profile o ,

$SFOC_{e,f,s_o}$ = Specific fuel consumption for engine e and fuel type f in state s in operating profile o .

The amount of emission per pollutant type is calculated as presented in equation (1.6). The emission factor $C_{p,f,e}$ is engine and fuel type dependent, which is why calculated fuel consumption from equation (1.5) can not directly be used for emission calculations.

Emission per pollutant type

$$E_p = \sum_f F_o' * C_{p,f,e} = \sum_e \sum_f F_f * C_{p,f,e} \quad \forall p \in P, \quad (1.5)$$

where

E_p = Emission of pollutant type p ,

$C_{p,f,e}$ = Emission coefficient factor for pollutant type p , engine e and fuel type f .

Capital and operational costs are just briefly discussed here, as a deeper insight in the economic aspects is outside the scope of this report, see for example *Eide (2009)*. For a ship owner, retrofitting an existing vessel by investing in an emission control represents an initial capital and a possible change in operational costs. Cost as a KPI will hence be the initial investing cost and the change in operational cost. For new buildings this can be interpreted slightly differently. New buildings are more adequate for emission controls and the investment costs can be highly different from the retrofitting costs, *IMO (2009)*. Also, for new buildings the list of optional emission controls is substantially longer than for retrofitting, *Wärtsilä (2009a)*.

Compatibility with the vessel

Before implementing an air emission control you need to check the compatibility between the control and the vessel. We defined three compatibility issues: ship type, mission and redundancy. Indeed, all air emission controls cannot be implemented on every ship type. *Wärtsilä (2009a)* defined for which ship types are the measures to reduce the energy consumption that they classified well suited. Besides, some air emission controls can be mission dependent, for instance the wind, wave or sun based technologies depend on the external conditions and therefore might not be always applicable. And in addition some controls can have already been implemented onboard the vessel. As an example, slide valves are supposed to be installed on all the vessels having a slow-speed two stokes engine built after 2000, *ENTEC (2005b)*.

For a specific vessel only a subset of all possible air emission controls known are up for evaluation for possible implementation. Let I_v , be the set of air emission controls compatible with the ship type v , I_o the set of air emission controls compatible with the mission o and I_A the set of air emission controls not already implemented in the vessel. I_v , I_o and I_A are subsets of the set I of all known air emission controls. The set of controls to investigate is hence I_{vOA} such that:

$$I_{VOA} = I_V \cap I_O \cap I_A \quad \text{and} \quad I_{VOA} \subset I$$

We could also consider some possible influence of the vessel on, for instance, the costs of implementing some air emissions controls. The costs can be dependent on the free space available on the vessel or its density. But those considerations are very ship specific and are not treated in this article.

Calculating targeted KPI's after of air emission control installations

Due to emission controls internal interactions and their impact on either the fuel consumption or the emission factor, estimating the resulting amount of emissions after investing in different controls can be a challenge.

Renewable energy source, improve energy efficiency and emission saving by operation

These air emission controls have an impact on the engine modes, for instance directly by slow speeding or by reducing resistance and hence same speed can be obtained at lower modes. From the calculations of initial performance the required power and engine modes were found for each operational state. Let us call this power requirement per state $P_{REQUIRED,s}$.

The assumption is that the power gained from the emission controls, called $P_{SAVING,s,i}$ can be subtracted from the original power requirement in the operational state. The hypothesis is that this results in a lower power demand, $P_{DEMAND,s}$ from the machinery, and hence recalculations on power distribution and load estimation are needed to find resulting engine modes (MCR).

Power demand per operational state

$$P_{DEMAND,s} = P_{REQUIRED,s} - \sum_i^I P_{SAVING,s,i} \quad (1.6)$$

where

$P_{DEMAND,s}$ = Power demand per operational state s after investing in air emission controls,

$P_{REQUIRED,s}$ = Power required per operational state s before investing in air emission controls,

$P_{SAVED,s,i}$ = Power saved per air emission control i per operational state s .

Implementing a set of air emission controls with no opposing synergies and hence no internal influence on the fuel consumption and emissions can be found by equations (1.5) and (1.6). These assumptions on independence are valid only for some of the controls; hence power and fuel savings or emission reductions can not be summed as above. Here we introduce the influence factor as defined in Chapter 2.3.2. Control dependent the influence factor describes combined impact on power saving and hence fuel consumption.

To ensure valid use of the influence factor there still remains investigation from different stakeholders to certify the combined effect. The combined effect might be ship dependent and ship owners should keep this in mind and not take results based on these calculations as final.

Abatement methods

The assumption is that control measures of this type have an impact on the emission factor for one or more pollutant type. The calculation of fuel consumption is hence as in equation (1.5). If just adding one pro- and one re-active measure, the emissions can be calculated as in equation (1.6), with respect to the new emission factors. Combining measures of pro- and pro-active or re- and re-active type's calls for influence factor introduction for estimating resulting emissions. The influence factor here represents the combined specific emission pollutant change from prior to and after installation of air emission controls with impact on the same pollutant type.

Decision basis

Once the target is defined and the possible options are determined, the next step is the decision making. To be adaptable to each customer's case, we chose to present a very open framework where the target and the decision basis are not specified, but freely chosen by the decision maker. Different tools can be used to support the decision process. In Chapter 3.3.3 the choice of an optimization problem is discussed.

3.3 Suggested further work

3.3.1 Timeline

The question on air emission control selection is a four dimensional quest, where the timeline can be vital. Deciding what controls to invest in should go together with when to or when not to invest in the control. As an example, compliance with today's regulations might be possible by direct installation of a given technology. Assuming that stringent regulations, which were not earlier taken into consideration by the ship owner, were to enter into force and that they were not met by this control alone; installing one or more additional controls would be required. There might be that these controls do not comply with the already installed control, and choosing a different control or approach the first time could have been of advantage. The uncertainty of the future must then be considered.

Addressing the problem of an uncertain future could be met by including a periodical timeline, where external driving forces were defined for each period. For the nearest future the periods could be smaller, for example spanning one year ahead, whilst they could be given as longer time periods further into the future. Any future period represents an uncertainty and risk, so shorter time periods for the closest future, where forecasting could be more reliable, and longer time periods further on could be a way of handling these elements in strategic planning.

For tactical and especially strategic decisions a timeline would be of most relevance. Developing a decision model based on a timeline is seen as an important further step in this investigation.

3.3.2 Scenarios of external influences

Developing a decision model with a time index could open for the possibilities of including other external aspect that could affect the decision. Such driving forces could, among others, be fluctuations in bunker costs, changes in vessel mission, introduction of new pollution regulations or the availability of new emission reducing technology.

Developing scenarios based on different storylines could provide the decision maker with extended knowledge and enhance the possibility for an informed decision. Scenarios are commonly used in decision processes and are an appropriate tool for analyzing driving forces and their future impact, *IPCC (2000)*. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) describes development and value of creating scenarios in their report on Emission Scenarios, *IPCC (2000)*. IMO also presented future emission scenarios in their report on Prevention of air pollution from ship, *IMO (2009)*. Keeping in mind that the future is highly uncertain, scenarios can represent different storylines and alternative images on how it might unfold.

3.3.3 Possible optimization model

Operational Research (OR) has been used in maritime transportation on fleet size, mix and scheduling problems. For a review it is referred to *Fagerholt et al. (2010)*. The hypothesis of this work is that such methods could be of advantage when searching for emission reducing solutions based on what and when to investigate in air emission controls.

The objective function in an optimization model would be defined by the chosen target, e.g. a percentage emission reduction during a given timeline by the most cost-effective solution. The problem is complex and reducing it might be beneficial. By introducing the binary knapsack problem as solution approach equation (1.7) could represent the objective function. This would be a reduction of the original problem, where minimizing costs of investing controls are the objective subjected to emission reduction at a given quantitative target. For definition on the knapsack problem it is referred to *Rardin (1998)*.

Minimize the costs of air emission investment

$$z = \min\left(\sum_i^I C_i * \sigma_i\right) \quad (1.7)$$

where

z = Costs of air emission control implementation, [€]

C_i = Cost for installing air emission control i , [€]

$\sigma_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if air emission control } i \text{ is installed} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$

It is important to point out that the implementation of air emission reduction controls is still subject to a lot of uncertainty, and therefore an optimization model might not be the best decision tool. As *Corbett and Chapman (2006)* discussed, a set of “preferred” solutions may be a better output of a model than one optimal alternative. However, if a stochastic approach is added the optimization model can then be of great use. This will be studied in a further work.

3.3.4 Implementation of decision support framework in a software tool

This decision support framework is currently in the starting phase of being implemented in a software tool in-house at Det Norske Veritas. This tool embraces the idea of a bottom up emission calculation, where mission definition and machinery configuration are one of the main factors taken into consideration. The tool allows for ship comparison with an extended database of the world’s fleet on ship design parameters.

4 Conclusion

Knowing which air emission controls to implement on a vessel and how the different controls influence each other is a real challenge for the ship owners.

In this paper we have presented a classification of air emission controls based on their emission reducing nature: Reducing fuel consumption or affecting the emission factor. Interactions as compliance and influence between controls and ship have been discussed. A method for modeling of these interactions has been proposed, together with a decision support framework. Important further work to enrich this framework has been outlined. Among others, these include timeline and uncertainty.

A lot of different factors can affect the implementation of a control. The ones judged the most important are presented in this work, this in order to establish an initial screening of the current knowledge on air emission controls.

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The SAFEGUARD project: Collection and Preliminary Analysis of Assembly Data for Large Passenger Vessels at Sea

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Abstract

In the past decade, significant effort has gone into planning and executing full-scale sea trials in an attempt to improve, calibrate and validate existing computer models that simulate evacuation on passenger ships. In September, 2009 two assembly exercises were conducted at sea onboard the RO-PAX ferry SuperSpeed 1 by team members of the EU-funded project SAFEGUARD. The exercises were conducted with passengers during routine sailings between the ports of Kristiansand, Norway and Hirtshals, Denmark. Between both trials, a total of 1,769 passengers were assembled; on day one, 902 passengers and on day two 867 passengers. As part of the data collection exercise, passenger response time was collected using video cameras and passenger movement was collected using a novel infra-red (IR) based position logging system. This paper briefly describes the development and testing of the data acquisition system and discusses preliminary results.

1. Introduction

Understanding how people behave in emergency situations within maritime settings is vital if we are to; design and develop evacuation efficient vessels and evacuation procedures, train crew in the management of evacuation situations, develop reliable ship evacuation models and regulate the design and operation of vessels. An essential component of this understanding is the collection and characterisation of realistic, representative human performance data. Unfortunately, little data relating to passenger response time or full-scale validation data in maritime environments exists. In the first International Maritime Organisation (IMO) document to specify protocols for the use of ship evacuation models in the analysis and certification of passenger ship design, IMO MSC Circ. 1033 (IMO, 2002), an arbitrary uniform random distribution was set to represent the response time behaviour of passengers. Deere *et al.* (2006) showed that this is unrepresentative of actual passenger response time and liable to produce incorrect or misleading conclusions concerning the suitability of ship design for evacuation. Galea *et al.* (2007) collected passenger response time data for a passenger ship at sea as part of the EU Framework V project FIRE EXIT (FIRE EXIT, 2005). This data was accepted by the IMO and used in the formulation of IMO MSC Circ. 1238 (IMO, 2007), the modified protocols for passenger ship evacuation analysis and certification. However, the response time data produced by FIRE EXIT related to only a single passenger vessel. As such the data cannot be considered representative of passenger ships in general. The IMO Fire Protection (FP) Sub-Committee in their modification of MSC Circ. 1033 at the FP51 meeting in February 2007 (IMO FP, 2007) invited member governments to provide, "...further information on additional scenarios for evacuation analysis and full scale data to be used for validation and calibration purposes of the draft revised interim guideline". To this end, project SAFEGUARD was proposed and successfully funded through the EU framework 7 programme. The project aims to address this IMO requirement by providing relevant full-scale data and proposing and investigating additional benchmark scenarios that can be used in certification analysis. Six full-scale data sets will be collected as part of SAFEGUARD - two trials on each of three different types of passenger vessels; one with cabins, one without cabins and a cruise liner.

This paper concentrates on the first two data sets collected on the first vessel - a large RO-PAX ferry without passenger cabins operated by Color Line AS called SuperSpeed 1, Fig. 1. The vessel can carry approximately 2000 passengers and crew and over 700 vehicles. It operates on the route

between Kristiansand in Norway and Hirtshals in Denmark, a trip of 3 hours and 15 minutes. The ship contains a mixture of passenger spaces spread over three decks including; business and traveller class seating areas (airline style seating), large retail and restaurant/cafe areas, bar areas, indoor and outdoor general seating areas and general circulation spaces. The ship has four assembly stations, three located on Deck 7 (assembly stations A, B and C) and one located on Deck 8 (assembly station D). Assembly stations B and C are located on the outer decks while assembly stations A and D are internal.

Fig.1: Color Line AS RO-PAX ferry SuperSpeed 1

Fig. 2: Example video camera mounting location (left) and mounting equipment with camera (right)

Fig. 3: IR field generating beacon (left) and IR logging tag (right)

Three types of data sets were collected in each trial. The first consisted of passenger response time and was collected using video cameras positioned throughout the vessel. In total, 30 battery powered mini digital video cameras were used to collect the response time data, Fig. 2. The cameras were placed at strategic locations throughout the vessel to record not only the time at which passengers responded, but also the nature of the activities that they were involved in at the time. The second type of data collected comprised validation data for ship based evacuation models. This consisted of starting locations of passengers, arrival time at the designated assembly areas and the paths taken by the passengers from the start location to the assembly location. This data was collected using a novel data acquisition system consisting of 30 Infra-Red (IR) beacons, each emitting unique IR signals and data logging tags that were worn by each passenger, Fig. 3. The third type of data consisted of a questionnaire that was completed by passengers after the assembly trial was over.

2. Data Collection Methodology

This section outlines the process of collecting validation data. Previous efforts at collecting comprehensive full-scale ship evacuation validation data have been less than successful due to the complication of the associated data analysis. Previous efforts have attempted to use video footage to manually track individuals through the vessel (*FIRE EXIT, 2005*). However, tracking individuals through the complex layout of a large passenger vessel is extremely time consuming. Depending on the complexity of the structure, the analyst may have to track an individual through tens of different video camera locations. Attempting to track a handful of individuals this way can be extremely tedious and prone to error. In the case of SuperSpeed, tracking almost 1000 passengers across three large decks would have been unthinkable! Automated video tracking systems also have problems as they require a 'birds eye' view of the targeted individuals if they are to accurately monitor an individual's progress through a particular location, making installation of the video equipment difficult due to the low head room often found on ships, *Boltes et al. (2010)*. Furthermore, the problem still persists of tracking individuals passing through many different camera locations.

A comprehensive investigation was undertaken of technologies that may be useful in addressing this problem. This identified two specific technologies - passive radio frequency identification (RFID) and infra-red (IR) position logging. Both systems rely on similar underlying concepts - devices are mounted throughout the structure that generate uniquely identified radio frequency or IR fields and passengers wear a device that allows for their unique identification as they move throughout the structure and pass through each field. If a sufficient number of unique fields are generated, then as a person moves around the structure, their tag either logs or permits the logging of the different field IDs and the time they were passed, Fig. 4.

Both systems rely on the population agreeing to wear a tag for the purposes of the trial. As the trial may take place at any time, the participant population must be prepared to wear the tag for an extended period of time (possibly all day/night) and so it must not interfere with normal activities, be comfortable, and if possible must blend in with their normal attire. For example, attaching the tags to a hat or cap, while ideal for detection, would not be acceptable.

However, there are fundamental differences between the RFID and IR systems, particularly the way in which the fields are generated and the way in which communication takes place between the tag and field for logging of position and time. The passive RFID technology examined, Fig. 5. relies on a pair of antennae that generate a radio frequency (RF) field with sufficient power to energise tags that enter it. The tags use the RF energy from the field to wirelessly transmit a signal to the receiving antennae (the same antennae that generate the RF field). The receiving antennae then sends the information to a processor that logs the tag's unique ID and the time at which the signal was received. For this system, the RFID tag acts as a passive device with no built-in power source and no data storage capacity. The data for people tracked is stored either by the component that generates the RF field or an attached computer. The main difficulty with this technology is that human bodies attenuate RF signals, sometimes in an unpredictable manner, thus making the placement of RFID antennae and tags of critical importance. In large crowds, especially, data can be lost creating inaccuracies in the

validation dataset. In a recent series of evacuation trials using RFID (*Hostikka et al., 2007 & Rinne et al., 2008*), it is suggested that read rates “will be better than 50% if proper alignment and measurement power of reader antennae is found through experiments” in crowded situations, *Hostikka et al. (2007)*. The success rate is also critically dependent on how the tag is worn, whether it is in contact with the skin, near metal objects or concealed by clothing. In addition, RFID systems tend to be bulky for temporary applications and logistics of setup becomes time consuming due to the need to carefully run cables and ensure suitable antennae orientations. Further, while RFID tags tend to be inexpensive in large quantities required for test series, they can be damaged relatively easily jeopardising the dataset quality. Considerable effort is required to select the correct tag and form factor for the planned application, in order to ensure the highest read-rate possible.

Fig. 4: Example of tracking system following individuals from a starting area to an assembly area or exit point via two different routes

Fig. 5: Example RFID system tested (left) and example of field test (right)

A series of tests was undertaken of a representative RFID system, first in a corridor at the University of Greenwich and then on-board the SuperSpeed vessel. The RFID system was manufactured by Alien Technology Corp. and consisted of an Alien model ALR-8800 reader and a pair of Alien model ALR-8610 circular polarised multistatic antennae (i.e. capable of both generating the RF field and

receiving tag transmission data for logging). This system was designed to operate in the European UHF band in the 865.7 - 867.5 MHz range with power levels of 2W ERP and is compliant with European radio regulations. The system was designed to read EPC Class 1 Generation 2 UHF tags. In addition to the RFID system, various types of EPC Class1, Gen2 UHF tags were purchased in different form factors, specifically; peel and stick labels, silicone rubber wristbands and plastic wrist/ankle hospital-style bands. The corridor tests consisted of some 12 people walking down a 1.89 m wide corridor of which all 12 were wearing the RFID tags. Trials with both wrist and ankle bands were undertaken. Subjects were asked to walk together past the antennae as a group keeping their speed, position and group density consistent from test to test, Fig. 5. Tag reads were stored on a computer for each test. The maximum read rate was 75% for tests where subjects were permitted to walk normally (i.e. with arms swinging by their side). One test case was conducted where the subjects were asked to fold their arms, thereby shielding the tags somewhat. For this test, it was found that the read rate decreased significantly to just 17%. A series of trials was also conducted in a passageway on-board the SuperSpeed. Unfortunately, the trials on-board SuperSpeed were conducted using only nine people wearing tags and so do not represent a reliable test under crowded situations, nevertheless, these trials returned an average read rate of 86%. The ship trials demonstrated that the RFID system could work within the confines of the metal environment of a passenger ship. The corridor tests suggest that read rates of up to 75% can be achieved using the RFID technology in crowded situations.

The IR technology examined, Fig. 3, relies on a beacon that generates an IR light field. As a tagged individual passes through the field, IR light sensors in the tag detect the IR light and log its ID and the time at which it was detected in the tag's own internal memory. For the IR system, no data is transmitted from the tag until it is presented to an IR data reader at a later date. Following the test, tags must be retrieved in order to determine the occupant's route data. The main disadvantage with this technology is that occupant route data is not collected unless tags are returned following the test. In addition, the IR tag is also considerably more expensive than the passive RFID tag, costing approximately 15 times more. This is very different than the (passive) RFID tags which, due to their low individual price and inability to log route data, do not need to be returned at the end of the tests. However, the IR tags, if collected after the trial, can be reused time and time again. In addition, the disadvantage of the IR tag turns into an advantage for the IR beacons. Since the path history of the individual is recorded in the tag itself, the IR beacons are less complex which reduces their cost (by a factor of approximately 60), as well as their size and power requirements compared to the RFID system. This allows many IR beacons to be placed through the structure, thus allowing for more granular definition of occupant routes. In addition, the beacons are much easier to set-up, greatly simplifying instrumentation setup and due to their reduced size, simplifying logistics involved in transporting the equipment to the test site.

The IR system was manufactured by RFID Centre Ltd. A modified version of their *TagMobile* system was employed which includes IR generating beacons and logging tags that are hung around the neck using a lanyard. The RFID Centre worked with FSEG to modify this system and make it more appropriate for use in evacuation study applications. This involved a redesign of the standard IR tag. The modified IR system was put through a similar series of tests as the RFID system. In corridor tests at the University of Greenwich, the beacon was mounted on one side of the corridor at a height of 2.13 m above the floor, facing perpendicular to the opposite wall. A total of ten tags were used and a group of 23 individuals was formed with the ten tags worn by subjects mixed throughout. The group was instructed to walk past the beacon keeping speed, position and group density consistent from test to test, Fig. 6. Subjects were asked to raise their hand when the tag indicated a successful read. These tests always returned a 100% read rate. Shipboard tests using the IR system involved 10 test subjects wearing the IR tags. These tests returned an average of 93.5% successful read rate however, as with the RFID trials on the ship, these trials were not under heavily crowded situations and so were not considered representative of the intended application. However, the tests demonstrated that the system could work in a shipboard environment.

Fig. 6: IR corridor test (a) tagged people (down arrows), IR beacon out of view (up arrow) and IR tag (circled) (b) tagged people raising hands when tag is detected with IR beacon out of view (circled)

Based on the results generated in the various trials, it was concluded that the IR-based tracking system was better able to accurately track large numbers of individuals in high-density crowds. While the RFID system provided reasonable read rates, performance of the IR system was superior in all cases. The success of the IR system is due in part to it not relying on direct line-of-sight between the beacon and the detector, the IR beams being readily reflected from surfaces and not distorted by human bodies. Furthermore, considering the logistical issues associated with using the two systems, the IR system was considered more versatile being; easier for setup and knock-down, not requiring external power supplies or cables, being relatively cheap to add additional fields and easier to transport. On completion of the trial, data is transferred from each retrieved tag to a computer via an IR reader. Software developed by the University of Greenwich's Fire Safety Engineering Group (FSEG) then reads the tag information and, for each tag, identifies when the participant passed a numbered beacon and when they arrived at the assembly station. Travel times, average travel speeds and levels of congestion can then be determined and associated with each beacon and hence beacon location. The data transfer process and path extraction are quick and reliable.

3. Results and Discussion

Both full-scale sea trials were conducted on the SuperSpeed's Kristiansand to Hirtshals crossing. While the passengers were aware that they would be involved in an assembly trial, they did not know at what time during the 3 hours and 15 minute crossing the trial would take place. Participation in the trials was not compulsory and children under the age of 12 were not permitted to take part. Passengers were given the IR tags as they boarded, together with an information sheet and asked to wear the IR tag at all times while on the vessel. The trials consisted of the ship's Captain sounding the alarm and crew moving the passengers into the designated assembly areas. The assembly trials were successfully conducted on the 4th at 08:20 and 5th at 08:19 of September 2009. On day 1 (results of day 2 within brackets) there were 1431 (1349) passengers on board of which 1296 (1243) were eligible to participate in the trial. In total some 1170 (1192) IR tags were issued (some passengers refused to participate) of which 902 (867) passengers with IR tags participated in the trial in some capacity. Of these, a number of passengers who had been issued IR tags changed their minds and decided not to participate and so handed back their tags. Others with tags simply refused to participate while others responded, but then did not immediately move off to the assembly stations and so were not counted in the assembly total. The 902 (867) participating passengers represents 70% (70%) of the passengers on board and 77% (73%) of the issued tags. In total 13 (0.5%) of the tags were lost together with 60 lanyards. The first assembly trial was completed in 12 min while the second assembly trial was completed in 10 min. The Captain determined the end of each assembly trial.

Considering in detail some data extracted from the second trial, it can be seen that in 10 min, 841 passengers were assembled. This included 345 passengers who were already in the assembly stations at the alarm and 496 passengers who made their way to the assembly stations. A breakdown of passenger distribution throughout the ship is provided in Figs. 7 to 9. These figures show, for Decks 7

to 9, the number of tagged passengers in each region when the alarm sounded and the number of passengers in the assembly stations on completion of the trial. The figures also show the proportion wearing tags that did not assemble. Table I provides an IR data summary of the number of passengers who assemble, indicating the starting deck and the deck on which they assembled.

Fig.7: Number of passengers in each region of Deck 7 for trial 2 at the alarm and number in each assembly station (AS) on completion of the trial as recorded by the IR system

Fig.8: Number of passengers in each region of Deck 8 for trial 2 at the alarm and number in each assembly station (AS) on completion of the trial as recorded by the IR system

The IR tag data was used to develop the arrival curve depicted in Fig. 10. It displays the characteristic shape of a typical arrival curve. Note that passengers (26 in total) who assembled after 10 min (600 min) were not considered to be participating in the trial. A similar curve is available for each unique assembly station.

Fig.9: Number of passengers in each region of Deck 9 for trial 2 at the alarm as recorded by the IR system

Table I: Number of passengers who assemble by starting deck and ending deck

		Starting Deck			Total
		Deck 7	Deck 8	Deck 9	
Ending Deck	Deck 7	139	124	70	333
	Deck 8	9	156	24	189
	Deck 9	0	0	0	0
Total		148	280	94	522

Fig. 11 presents three typical passenger paths reconstructed from the IR data – one in the bar area in the aft end of the ship (left), one in the general seating area just aft of midships and one in the restaurant in the fwd end of the ship (right). The passenger in the restaurant exited passing beacon 14 at 69 s after the sounding of the alarm, exiting the entrance to the dining area, passing beacon 12 at 89 s after the alarm and entering Assembly area D (end point), passing beacon 11 at 103 s after the sounding of the alarm. The passenger in the bar moved past beacon 3 on deck 8 at 39 s after the alarm and exited the bar by the stbd side past beacon 5 on deck 8 at 52 s after the alarm. The passenger then proceeded down the ship’s aftermost staircase and arrived at assembly station C at 179 s. after the alarm. The passenger just aft of midships passed beacon 9 at 77 s after the alarm and proceeded down the ship’s staircase amidships and entered assembly station A at 152 s after the alarm. This type of analysis is being performed for all tagged passengers who assembled and will enable an accurate data set to be prepared for model validation purposes, providing details of the routes taken by individual passengers, which assembly stations were used and associated assembly times. The data collected can also be used to generate approximate average travel speeds and in some cases population densities.

Travel speeds that can be determined from the IR data are only approximate as the size of a field, which is tuned as required for the specific location, can be between 4 m and 11 m wide. Population densities are determined using the field size and the number of people entering and leaving each field over a period of time. The accuracy of this measurement is improved if the flow is unidirectional and if densities are not extreme.

Population response times are being determined by analysis of the video footage. This analysis is determining not only the response times but also the nature of the activities in which the population was engaged during the response phase. This includes determining the number and type of information and action tasks completed by each individual during the response phase. Depicted in Fig. 12 is the response time distribution for people located only in the bar area of SuperSpeed. It displays the typical lognormal shape with a mean of 45.2 s and a standard deviation of 48.6 s. It is expected that a total of 950 passenger response times will be recorded for SuperSpeed 1 over both trials.

Fig. 10: Total assembly curve for trial 2 (the red line represents the end of the assembly trial as determined by the Captain)

Deck 8

Fig. 11: Paths taken by three passengers during assembly trial 2

Fig. 12: Response time distribution derived from both trials for population in the bar region

Questionnaire data analysis is ongoing and, where possible, will be linked to IR tag data. In total, 1534 questionnaires were collected (767 from each trial). Of these, 81% were fully completed (including the passenger's tag number which allows for linking of the questionnaire data to the IR data). The questionnaires were completed in three different languages – Norwegian (64%), German (31%) and English (5%).

4. Conclusions

Two passenger ship assembly trials have been conducted at sea involving a total of 1769 passengers in which data for passenger response time and route to the assembly stations have been successfully collected. The data collected from these trials is being used to formulate a validation data set for ship evacuation computer models and to produce a more representative response time distribution for passenger ship applications. As part of this project a new technology to track individuals through a complex structure, consisting of IR tags and beacons, was developed and tested. The technology is able to reliably track large numbers of people through complex structures, is relatively easy to setup and enables the rapid extraction of individual person trajectories.

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Efficient Design of Advanced Machinery Systems for Complex Operational Profiles

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Abstract

During the last decade offshore support vessels have faced a market with requirements for increasingly demanding operations, especially deep water and High North activities, an increased focus on environmental performance, as well as a higher degree of uncertainty in terms of contract horizon and predictability of future operations. As a result, we have seen a development towards more advanced and complex machinery systems, typically containing diesel-electric or diesel-hybrid engine configurations combined with azimuth and podded propulsion. While representing a significantly higher investment cost, these machinery solutions have increased their market share based on improved energy efficiency and higher degree of flexibility towards the complex, demanding and multi-faceted operational profiles that these vessels actually meet. Related to this development, there are two main issues that are addressed in this paper: First, how can we efficiently design these complex systems in the tendering phase of project development, based on the actual expected operating profile of the vessel? And second, how can the system performance, in terms of cost, energy efficiency, emissions, flexibility and availability, be documented towards the customer so as to increase the likelihood of winning the contract. Thus, the overall objective of the paper is to define a methodology and specify the structure of a tool that can fully or partially answer these questions. The paper will be based on an ongoing project within NTNU, with DNV and STX Europe as partners.

1. Introduction

Ships are designed to carry out one or more specific tasks. Why is it then that the owners (or designers) quite often seem not to spend adequate resources on describing and defining the very same tasks so that the design may be adapted accordingly, and by doing so miss out on the opportunity to match the vessel to the operations?

There are lots of answers to this question, and in most cases the reasoning behind is quite sound. Perhaps the Owner (or designer) does not know the specific trade yet or will operate the vessel on the spot market and thus has to go for the “market standard”, or perhaps the trade is uncomplicated and will not require any further demands on the vessel than what “normal” optimization of hull and machinery will provide. Or perhaps the vessel is just an asset to be traded, a financial instrument, and as such will just have to be suitable to any and all unspecified trades within the segment – at the lowest possible investment cost.

For vessels such as offshore support vessels (OSV), trades and operating duties are more complex and diverse than for most other ship types. The combined range of cargos, operating engine/system loads and operating conditions forms an almost infinite amount of potential operating states. Nonetheless, onboard logging of engine and propulsion data for vessels in operation has clearly indicated that there are normally several *clusters* of parameter combinations corresponding with typical operations or modes – as would also be expected. However, the data also show that the actual operating patterns are often not as expected or predicted in terms of a.o. power demand/consumption, and they are certainly not similar to the often stereotyped assumptions made at the design stage.

Our ability to optimize the design of the vessel, including the design and configuration of the machinery systems, to match the work that it will perform will clearly benefit from such operational feedback. This could be both important and beneficial for several reasons; very tangible are the

positive effects on the energy efficiency – the amount of useful work we are able to achieve for a given amount of energy – which will both reduce running costs and the environmental load, and hence also improve the competitiveness of the vessel. Somewhat less obvious are the improvements that we are able to implement in terms of system performance, operational flexibility, safety and risk reduction (or robustness); monitoring and mapping of operational data will provide a better understanding of how the different tasks or operations actually translate into engine and system loads.

For the sake of simplicity, let's say that the main motives for improving a vessel design are cost reduction, efficiency (which often is merely a variety of cost) and competitiveness (making sure that you secure the desired or at least a sufficient amount of business) – or some variety thereof. If we extend this line of reasoning, we would soon realize that whereas operating cost reductions and efficiency improvements will often require significant initial investments (increased construction costs) and/or the use of new and unproven technology, the resulting savings will mainly be on the fuel bill, i.e. the Owner will not see this directly. The only real motivation for the Owner to invest in improving vessel designs or operations is to make sure that his vessels are as good as or slightly better than the competition.

States of affairs will, as always, prevail until the motivation for change is strong enough. During the last business cycle (more or less), which will roughly translate to the last 5 years, the rules of engagement have changed for offshore vessels and general shipping alike. A three-headed motivational beast has emerged: Fuel price increases, financial realities (credit crunch, overcapacity, cost cutting, etc.) and a new environmental mindset percolating through our entire society - call it climate change, if you will. The results are cost-cutting initiatives trickling down the value chain from the oil companies to the operators and ship owners, a new range of environmental pressures and requirements that are brought to bear, all resulting in fiercer competition and enforcement of new operational demands: Fuel oil consumption must be documented for different duties, economic speed must be applied to reduce the fuel bill, higher utilization rates are sought everywhere. And, more importantly, supply chain efficiency projects are emerging.

The importance of this is chiefly that the vessel is increasingly viewed upon as a part of a bigger, integrated system, thus implying that the performance of the vessel should also be assessed on the basis of the operating profile (mission profile) defined by the total supply chain.

It now makes even more sense to monitor the vessel performance, but this time against the mission KPIs that are put in place. The incentives for the owners would also be there to invest in new machinery solutions, new equipment to save work time and increase the capacity – new optimized vessel designs in general. Examples abound: Hybrid propulsion system, use of fiber rope instead of steel rope (wires), cranes and winches with active heave comp, manipulators and cranes to assist heavy and dangerous deck work, more complex bulk cargo and chemicals solutions, and so on. All of these are investments that will have positive effects on the mission performance, and thus also on the bottom line of the Owner.

This paper will focus on the machinery configuration and –performance in light of these aforementioned issues. According to *Koch et al. (2009)*, 62.4 % of PSV/OSV newbuildings in 2008 had diesel-electric machineries. The picture is unfortunately clear, though: A simple search on SeaWeb, www.sea-web.com, covering vessels larger than 2.000 DWT built or contracted after the year 2000 of the “Offshore” vessel main type, returns 1434 vessels, with the following engine drive-type distribution:

Vessels total:	1434
Of which:	444 have diesel-electric drive (~ 32%)
	875 have mechanical drive (~ 65%)

Even if considering only vessels not yet delivered (02/2010), the numbers remain approximately the same. Extending the search to include smaller vessel will reduce the percentage of diesel-electric

solutions, which may indicate that the low-end market can not defend the extra investment in advanced systems. Looking at the market segment characterized by the *deeper, stronger, bigger*, as in the newer vessels designed for the ultra-deep waters of Gulf of Mexico and Brazil, this is where the hybrid drives and advanced solutions are entering the market. The complexity of these systems, both in terms of design and operation, together with the significantly higher investment costs, have made them rare birds until recently, but signs indicate that this might change.

2. Machinery Systems

2.1. OSV Missions

OSVs are among the ships with most complex operational profiles. The missions can change from one contract to another, and consist of a combination of the following tasks:

- Transport supplies
- Anchor handling
- Support offshore operations
- Towing
- Standby
- Specialized/Emergency (oil recovery, diving/ROV support, fire fighting)

Each of these tasks demands different loads for the machinery. A design toward the optimum in one mission may lead to an inferior performance in another.

2.2. Machinery Solutions

Nowadays, the main types of OSVs machineries are, based on *Beedall (2010)*, mechanical, diesel-electric and hybrid machinery solutions:

Mechanical solutions

This is the traditional solution, typically consisting of two main diesel engines each coupled to a propeller, via a reduction gear and propeller shafts. The electric power is typically generated via auxiliary engines (generator sets). Pros for these systems are lower initial cost, low complexity and excellent efficiency at the design condition. Cons are low efficiency at other load conditions (other than the design ratio), zero-pitch losses, and usually less electrical total power output. The physical requirements (volume and weight) are normally higher than other machinery solutions, and it is less flexible regarding component..

Diesel-Electric solutions

These machinery solutions use electric motors to drive the propellers. The motors are powered by diesel generators. Pros for these solutions compared with the mechanical ones are smaller size, weight and flexibility in location of components. They normally have lower noise and vibration levels, and have better energy efficiency when the operations vary greatly regarding power demand. Frequency controlled motors will provide operational flexibility and almost eliminate zero-pitch losses. The often larger number of smaller diesel engines (generator sets), which can be started and stopped as needed, is an advantage in terms of redundancy. It usually also has a higher power output potential. Cons are the higher investment cost and less energy efficiency when sailing long time at high velocities, due to the electric motor/generator losses. The generator sets are also often too large for harbor states where the electrical demand is quite low.

Hybrid solutions

This solution combines both mechanical and electric configurations. The electric motor and diesel engines are usually both connected the propeller via gear box. When sailing at low speed the electric propulsion is used, and the diesel one is used in high speed cases. Pros are the flexibility of the system which allows more optimal engine loads in low and high speed conditions, *Sortland (2008)*. It has

higher fuel saving potentials and all the other advantages of the previously mentioned systems at any speed. Cons are of course the investment costs and the higher number of components, which increases the complexity of operation and maintenance.

The selection criteria to consider are numerous and could be grouped into, *Beedall (2010)*:

- Operational criteria (e.g. speed, flexibility, reliability, maneuverability, noise, training)
- Design criteria (e.g. machinery location, hull form, weight, engine room area)
- Economic criteria (e.g. investment cost, operational costs; fuel consumption, emissions, maintenance)
- Industrial criteria (e.g. modularity, arrangement needed, maturity of components)

3. Methodology to Compare Machinery Configuration

3.1. Objectives

The overall objective of this approach is to enhance the machinery design process by making evaluation and comparison of different machinery configurations more effective in the early design phase.. It is a challenging task since there are many systems interacting. The variables, dependencies, constraints, considerations and uncertainties are numerous in the early design phase; finding the relevant and critical KPIs for evaluating a machinery configuration is a demanding task. The improvement is reached through the development of methods and tools to compare machineries in a proper way, focusing on relevant selection criteria. However, in this stage of the work, we did not use operations research techniques, or other classical optimization methods.

3.2. Assumptions

The focus of this approach is, as mentioned above, on how different machinery configuration with different prime movers can be compared and evaluated. The primary (or chosen) parameters for variation are the operational profile(s), engine/fuel type, engine size and the number of engines. Operations are purely defined by different power demands onboard, divided between propulsive, manoeuvring and (other) electrical power. Investment and maintenance costs for the machineries are not addressed. However, calculations of important cost factors such as fuel consumption and emissions are the core process of the method.

The detailed evaluation of the following issues are considered out of the scope:

- Propeller efficiency- and hull efficiency optimization
- How to estimate the power demands (for propulsion or any other energy consumers)
- Physical constraints such as weight and spatial requirement (engine room)
- Design and evaluations of the machinery supporting systems for fuel oil, lubricating oil, compressed air, cooling water, exhaust gas, etc.
- Integrated automation systems which obviously are important for safe and efficient operations are not dealt with; neither are limitations in electrical components such as switchboards

The range of factors not considered in this approach should be looked into in further work. On the other hand, these factors are typically not set/fixed in the early phase of the ship design process. One should be aware and keep this in mind to avoid sub-optimizing of some process steps which might lengthen the design process without actually increasing the accuracy.

3.3. Methodology

The proposed methodology to evaluate a machinery configuration is presented in Fig. 2. The explanation for each of the steps in the process is made in the following paragraphs.

Fig. 1: Process flowchart for machinery configuration comparison

1) *Operating States* – A mission is defined as set of operational profiles, *Gaspar et al. (2009)*. Each operational profile will consist of a set of states, i.e. certain tasks performed by the ship in a given time range. Each state corresponds with one unique work task such as “Anchor Handling” or “Sailing, loaded”. These tasks are defined by the type of vessels and/or the mission that it is performing, and represents the relation between mission, operational profiles and operational states, as observed in Fig. 2. Some states will lead directly to a power demand, whilst ship specific parameters are needed to get power demand in other states.

Fig. 2: Relation between missions, operational profiles and operational states

2) *Vessel performance* – Some of the power demand estimations can only be done when the characteristics of the vessel are known, e.g. when transforming forward speed to propulsive power demand. For the purpose of this paper the required power is assumed known.

3) *Power Demand* – The power demand is the summation of the value estimated in kilowatts (kW) for each of the tasks in each of the states. It has been divided in three main types:

- *Propulsive power*: The power for propulsive units (propellers) to obtain forward speed.
- *Manoeuvring power*: The load used by the thruster and other secondary propellers for positioning and manoeuvring which require energy to run electrical motors.
- *Electrical power*: Load used by all the electrical equipment on board, such as: cranes, pumps, lights, heating, air condition, cargo handling, etc.

For vessels with azimuthing pods instead of shafted propellers, the two first items are partly overlapping. This will then be a matter of definition for the analysis; for practical applications this should pose no problems.

There is also an “information gap” between the mission definition and the power generation demand in regard to transforming the mission defined work (speed, bollard pull, etc.) to the actual needed machinery power. Again – for the purpose of this paper we assume that this information is provided; the actual calculations per se are not necessarily complicated or comprehensive.

4) *Machinery Configuration* – In this process components are assembled to design a specific machinery configuration. The usual components in a typical machinery configuration are listed in the Table I. These are the components at the centre of attention in this process. Others such as turbines, boilers, bearings etc. should be included at a later stage to enable comparison of a wider range of configurations.

Table I: Main machinery components

Symbols	Component
	Propeller (CPP)
ME	Main Engine
T	Gear, transmission
G	Generator
—	Shaft
AE ⊕	Auxiliary Engine - Generator Set
M	Electric Motor
	Thruster
	Azimuth thruster

Abatement methods, or *emission reduction* methods, could also be incorporated in the process. A complementary paper on this subject is presented by *Balland et al. (2010)*. Engine types and their parameters, such as specific fuel oil consumption (SFC) and specific pollution emission (SPE), should be based on real-case data. The designer should be able to add and edit the components and its parameters. Components such as turbines and boilers are not considered in this phase of the development, however the methodology allows its implementation when the required connections and load distributions are known.

5) *Loss estimation* – The propulsion power demands deduced from the operating profiles is not equal to the power supplied by the engines, since the different components in the machinery have energy losses. For diesel-electric machineries it is quite common to factor in a total loss of approximately 8-10 % and for mechanical solutions around 2-4 %. In order to satisfy the power demands defined in the mission, these losses must be identified and compensated for when the total engine power output should be calculated. Any technical abatement methods applied to the machinery might also affect the machinery efficiency and should be taken into account.

6) *Load distribution* – When the total engine power has been estimated for each operating state, the individual engine loads must be found - the engine load distribution. The specific fuel oil consumption (SFOC) curve for each engine is essential in this process. The engines and the combination of engines should at all time be running as close as possible to the point where the fuel consumption per produced kW is at it lowest. In addition to an energy efficient and emission reducing

load distribution such a routine could take into consideration utilization or maintenance aspect. There are also a number of operational or regulatory restrictions in terms of optimizing the operation of a vessel on a purely technical basis that will come into play, amongst others regulations by the International Maritime Organization (IMO), Classification Societies and National Authorities. This could for instance be regulations regarding redundancy in operation of the auxiliary engines, restrictions on fuel oil, availability/redundancy for instance in the case of dynamic positioning (DP), and more.

The power management system (PMS) is programmed to ensure that there is sufficient power available at all time. This is obtained by controlling, monitoring and even predicting the power consumption and the engine/generator loads. When the generators do not produce sufficient power (or will not meet a predicted demand) the system automatically starts a new engine/generator. Some power management systems have additional functionality which aims at running the machinery system at the most energy efficient way at all time. These systems are commonly called energy management systems (EMS). An algorithm simulating these systems can be considered as input in this step, and should be studied in further work.

7) *Performance Measurement* – Evaluation of the extended machinery system performance requires a set of KPIs covering the relevant range or scope from purely technical to more operational indicators:

- Costs (capital and operational)
- Physical constraints/space requirements (weight, volume)
- Reliability (meantime between failures)
- Maintenance (complexity, time between scheduled)
- Serviceability/availability (service days, range of tasks)
- Robustness (redundancy, flexibility to handle different load conditions)
- Energy Efficiency (fuel consumption)
- Noise and vibration
- Air emissions (CO₂, SO_x, NO_x, particles)

The current focus is primarily on KPIs measuring fuel consumption, energy efficiency and lower emissions to the air – or actually on cost cutting, but this for a large part translates into lower fuel consumption and an improved environmental footprint anyway. Owing to the fact that people, companies, societies etc. have different preferences for selection criteria, the method covered in this paper only measures the difference between machineries. The weighting and influence each of the indicators is not dealt with.

As summary, the main inputs, outputs and constraints of the methodology can be observed in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Inputs, outputs and constraints taking into account in the methodology

4. Use Case Examples

The methodology can be applied as a support in decision processes, such as:

Defining the initial configuration: When designing and evaluating machinery configuration an usual issue to solve is: what will the effect of adding or changing the characteristics of a component be? For instance, it is possible measure the performance when replacing the main engines with a smaller and a larger engine.

Changing the operational profile: Further to the first issue: what will the machinery performance be if the *operating profiles* change (instead of the machinery configuration)? For instance, it can be used to measure the performance of a vessel when it is 30% of the time in supply mode, instead of 50%. Or the behavior when using it in a new contract that requires 50% of the time in standby. Albeit a slightly more difficult task, this could also be used to say something about the robustness of the solution and if it is sub-optimized for a particular operation mode.

Configuration Comparison: The methodology allows the comparison and evaluation of the performance of different machineries for different operating profiles. In this case is possible to compare two or more vessels for several operating profiles already defined.

As an example, the methodology is applied to an anchor handling tug supply vessel (AHTS) with two optional machinery configurations. The object of the case study is not to optimize as such, but to evaluate two particular solutions and thus illustrate the process and the gained decision support.

4.1. Operating States

The vessel of attention is given a mission of three operating profiles, each of one operating state (to simplify the case). The operating states are presented in Table II, with their duration in percentage of a total time span of one year.

Table II: Operating States of an AHTS

Operating State	Time [%]
State 1: Supply	40
State 2: Anchor handling	30
State 3: Towing	30

4.2. Vessel

The vessel data and performance taken from a typical AHTS (e.g., hull resistance curves) have not been looked into detail in this case. Nevertheless, the vessel type (AHTS) is working as a guideline and constraint throughout the process.

4.3. Power Demand

As previously mentioned the mission is defined by power demand in (kW) per operating state. This refers to the assumption that mission work such as speed, bollard pull etc. is already transformed to required power demand. The study of assessing power demand from a mission given by activities such as vessel speed and bollard pull (influenced by factors as weather and hull resistance) is outside the scope here. The power demands in this use case are observed in Table III.

Table III: Operating States and Power Demand

State	Total [kW]	Propulsion [kW]	Maneuvering [kW]	Electrical [kW]
Supply	3000	2700	0	300
A/H	4500	1350	1800	1350
Towing	4500	2250	1000	1250

4.4. Machinery Configuration

Two distinct machinery configurations based on typical machinery configurations found in existing AHTS vessels are used for the purpose of this example.

Machinery Configuration 1

The first configuration is a CODAD propulsion system (Combined Diesel and Diesel). Two medium speed marine diesel engines are arranged to supply power independently via reduction gearboxes through twin propeller shafts to two controllable pitch propellers. Each main engine is provided with one power take off/shaft generator, each of 800 kW via a step-up gearbox. The shaft generators are complete with clutch. The shaft generators are assumed to be of type PTO/GCR (power take off/gear constant ratio), allowing the main engine speed (rpm) to vary between 83 and 100 %. In addition to the shaft driven alternators, three marine diesel generators are arranged for electrical supply. They are arranged in parallel operation and each is of 1100 kW. Fig. 4 presents an illustration of the configuration and powering.

Fig. 4: Machinery Configuration 1

Machinery Configuration 2

The second configuration is based on the same machinery solution principle. Two medium-speed marine diesel engines are arranged to supply power via a reduction gear to the twin propeller shafts. Propellers are assumed the same as in configuration A. A PTO/GCR shaft generator of 1200 kW is provided for each main engine. Five generator sets of 400kW are installed in parallel operation. Exhaust gas re-circulation and seawater scrubbing are implemented as emission abatement methods. They reduce NO_x and SO_x respectively. Fig. 5 illustrates the configuration and powering.

Fig. 5: Machinery Configuration 2

4.5. Losses and Load Distribution

The load estimation method is assumed to take system efficiencies into account and find a suitable power generation distribution for satisfying state requirements for power. Only component efficiencies are considered in this case, meaning that the efficiency of a component is static and not depending on the connections between components. The load distribution algorithm is based in the logic presented in Table IV.

Table IV: Losses and load distribution

Component	Loss	Load Distribution
Propeller	-	Propeller losses can be taken into account as general losses or state related losses. In case of two propellers, propulsion demand is assumed divided equally amongst the propellers. The issue of propulsive efficiency for low loads/speeds <i>versus</i> high is relevant and should be addressed.
Main Engine	-	Power for satisfying propulsion demand is provided by the main engine. In case of two main engines, power is generated by shared load. SFOC curves based on test data are used for defining engine efficiency.
Gear	4 %	Losses in gearboxes are accounted for when in use.
Shaft Generator	3 %	Electric power is provided by the shaft generators. If there are two shaft generators in use, they are assumed equally loaded. If electrical power demand is not satisfied and max capacity is reached, the extra electrical power demand is supplied by equal loading on the generator sets (auxiliary engines). Component loss is taken account for as a percentage loss per energy equivalent.
Shafts	2 %	Shaft efficiency is taken account for in the model.
Generator Sets	3 %	Power for manoeuvring is provided by the generator sets. If electric power demand is not totally provided by shaft generators, generator sets thus provide the surplus.
Electric Motor	3 %	Only thrusters are considered when adding an electrical motor. They are for positioning, manoeuvring and powered by the generator sets. Electrical losses are accounted for.

4.6. Performance measurements

The machinery configurations ability to perform satisfyingly in regard to the given mission was the minimum criteria. Both configurations proved the ability to generate the required power for propulsion, maneuvering and electricity in each operating state.

The engines average utilization ratio is presented in Table V. The main engines of Configuration 1, have a slightly higher utilization ratio than the main engines in Configuration 2. From the shaft generator utilization ratio one can see that the shaft generators of Configuration 1 has a higher average operating efficiency than those of Configuration 2. Distributing the load so to utilize the shaft generators can prove to be more energy efficient because the main engine will operate at a higher ratio, and possibly a ratio closer to the engines designed ratio.

Table V: Load distribution in main and auxiliary engines per mission

Main Engines	Min load (%)	Max load (%)	Average load (%)
Configuration 1	52	67	59
Configuration 2	49	63	55
Generator Set			
Configuration 1	0	57	27
Configuration 2	0	94	44

Fig. 6 presents the fuel and lube oil consumption. The actual values are not in focus here, but Configuration 2 has lower fuel oil consumption than Configuration 1 for the same vessel operation.

Fig. 6: Compared oil consumption (left) and emissions (right)

Another main key indicator is the air pollution. Estimated CO₂, NO_x and SO_x values are presented in Fig. 6. Fuel oil consumption is commonly reflected in the emission output. As here, CO₂ emitted by Configuration 1 surpasses the CO₂ emissions by Configuration 2. Compared to Configuration 1 the NO_x and SO_x emissions from Configuration 2 are reduced to a great extent, due to the use of abatement methods. Recall that Configuration 2 had implemented exhaust gas re-cycling and seawater scrubbing for this purpose. A summary of the KPIs for the comparison is presented in Table VI.

Table VI: KPIs of the comparison

Outputs	Configuration 1	Configuration 2	Deviation (%)
Installed power [kW]	8730	7760	11
Fuel Oil Consumption [ton]	9020	8480	6
Lube Oil Consumption [kg]	9220	9160	1
CO ₂ [10 ² ton]	297	269	9
NO _x [ton]	510	238	53
SO _x [ton]	1804	424	76
Total Power Generation [kWh]	243e6	243e6	0
Loss [kWh]	920e3	810e3	12
Total Loss [%]	3.8	3.3	13
Usage of installed power [%]	45	45	0
Weight [tons]	75.7	80.3	-6

5. Structure of a tool

The images of this section are taken from an early-stage mock-up, and are presented with the intention to structure and exemplify a tool applying the methodology presented in Section 3.

We can define the software main functionalities as:

- Input a mission, with of several operational profiles
- Create/edit configuration
- Database of configurations, components and operational profiles
- Several schemes for the load distribution
- Graphs, charts and tables with the KPI's

The mission should be defined, with its operational profile and states. In duration and the total power demand. A database of standard and custom mission will be useful and should be gradually built though the use of the tool. Fig. 7 presents a mock-up of this tab.

Fig. 7: Mission tab

The software provides the designer with the possibility to base the new configuration on an existing one, Fig. 8. The designer is also provided with the features for adding and removing components to the new design. A visualization tool is provided to illustrate the component schematic.

Fig. 8: Machinery configuration tab

Estimating the load distribution for the power generating components can either be done automatically or be a manual input. (In fact, this would be the first draft logic for the PMS programming; the operational logic that the Owner or designer wants to add to the control rules of the PMS.) Fig. 9 illustrates the output of such load distribution estimation. They are given in tables and charts, and drill-down features are provided to enable the designer to analyze the whole machinery and each component

Fig. 9: Load estimation tab

The component library, Fig. 10, includes filtering features so to easily find the wanted component or similar components. A range of technical data is provided for each component in (the pop-up window at the figure). The results are presented in form of data and graphs, Fig. 11.

Fig. 10: Component library tab

Fig. 11: Results tab

6. Discussion

6.1 Usage of the Methodology

The main objective while developing the methodology was to make a contribution to the existing design methods for evaluating machinery configuration, by aiding the design tasks of the machinery system and documenting its performance in terms of cost, energy efficiency, emissions, flexibility and availability. At the same time, the main differences in our approach versus other approaches are described through the following three items:

1. We put a much higher emphasis on the Operational Profile context, on putting the ship into a value chain all the way from the start, and making all our assessment based on this viewpoint.
2. We introduce the Energy Efficiency and Emission evaluation parameters in the earliest stages of the design and use these as chief KPIs throughout the process
3. We introduce a structured/systematic evaluation of solutions at a very early stage instead of just assuming or adopting a solution that we will later only have the flexibility to tinker on

The methodology thus places itself in the bigger context of the tender design process. *Cuesta et al. (2009)* describes a tool to assist this process, called Pre-Contract Tool (PCT). It is based on the operational profile that a vessel will have, taking into account the fleet where it is inserted as well. Fig. 12 presents a flowchart of how the methodology in our work can be considered in the PCT approach.

Fig. 12: Process to insert machinery configuration comparison in the PCT tool

This process focuses on the ship design task as an integrated part of a maritime transport system, with the starting point in the mission definition of the ship, and iterating through the KPIs presented in the right column. The process is useful to improve designs in the tender phase, allowing the comparison of several configurations under diverse operational profiles. Existing designs can also be used as benchmark, and a database of KPIs values would be useful.

6.1 Extension of the Methodology

This work is based on an ongoing project, *Larsen et al. (2009)*, and the development of a tool presented in Section 4 is in process. Further studies are needed to improve the usability of the process. Main issues concern:

- Estimation of power demands given a task to be performed, a.o. based on analyses of onboard data measurements
- EMS and PMS routines able to efficiently estimate the load distribution in the early stages of design
- Integration of the methodology with the traditional vessel performance estimation, such as hull resistance and propeller efficiency
- Improved calculation to estimate the losses of each configuration, taking into account more components and its efficiency when operating under the given loads
- Optimization routines able to find a better configuration given a set of operational profiles

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Development of a Methodology for Calculating Production Times based on Parameters

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Abstract

Determination of realistic production times is a very crucial planning step in production planning because these times are basement for all flowing steps in production optimization like discrete event simulation. The following paper presents a method to generate precise production times by the use of CAD-Construction data. Therefore, the production processes has to be analyzed and the gathered information must be consolidated to useful parameters. This database must be merged with product data to generate production times for different workstations in a transparent way. To achieve that a program was developed to analysis the relevant product data. In a second step the program combines process data and product data in a semi automatic way. In that step Wizards and a rule based calculation tool were used to calculate the process times. Applying the presented method makes it possible to generate production times in a fast and transparent way without using complex tools like discrete event simulation for that purpose.

1 Introduction

The determination of production times plays a key role in the production planning process. The production time represents the capacity demand of the production program and is therefore essential for the balancing of capacity demand and available capacity. In the mass production industry methods like the MTM are established for the detailed determination of production times. In case of a one-of-a-kind manufacturer the effort for these methods are not reasonable.

The shipbuilding industry, as a typical one-of-a-kind manufacturer, is confronted with this problem. On the one hand the production times are needed to apply the methods of process optimisation in capacity planning. In the recent years diverse planning tools were developed, which are able to determine optimal capacity plans, *Steinhauer and Wagner (2007)*, *Czarnietzki (2008)*. These, in general simulation based, planning tools represent the production process in a very detailed way. This fact leads to an increased level of detail of the required input information (especially the production times) to utilize the planning tools full range of functions. On the other hand it is very time consuming to calculate the production times, because of the high diversity of complexity of the subassemblies in shipbuilding.

Thus, to make us of the simulation based planning tools and hence an improvement of the planning process, the determination of the production times is as critical as essential for the planning process, *Bentin et al. (2008)*.

This article focuses on the described problem and introduces a planning system, which enables the production planner determining production times. Regarding the increasing level of detail of the planning tools predominantly in the upstream production stages, the introduced planning system focuses on the plate- and panel-fabrication *Czarnietzki (2008)*. A fundamental issue during the development process of the planning system was the ability of the planner to comprehend the planning results. As a result of the high complexity of the simulation tools a decrease in comprehending the planning results on the part of the production planner was reported.

Hence the transparency of the planning systems and the results was a main criterion in the process of development. The following system requirements can be derived from the described problem:

- System-transparency
- Fast result generation
- Simple appliance
- High system-flexibility
- Interfaces to other planning tools (e.g. Plant Simulation; NC Programs)

The aim of the developed system is a semi-automatic generation on production times for the production stages plate- and panel-fabrication. Therefore the production processes are modelled in a database. Each process is assigned a process driver. The process driver is characterised by the fact that the duration of the process dominantly depends on its characteristics. Beside the process data an interface is developed, which enables automated processing of product-related data. Feasible product-related data are for example DXF- or DNC-Files as well as the manual input by the production planner. The output of the system is a transparent description of the production times for the examined product. These output data can, in turn, be used for capacity planning tools (e.g. Plant Simulation).

The basis of the system is the analysis of production processes and the development of the process drivers. Afterwards the logical data structure is developed as well as the interfaces for the input information. Finally the integration of the developed system into the production planning process is introduced.

2 Process Analysis

In the following the accomplished process analysis is presented, which is the basis for data structure and thus the planning system.

2.1 Determining relevant Processes

The first step is the comprehensive determination of the relevant processes in the plate- and panel-fabrication. Therefore all main- and ancillary processes are noted, which are necessary for the completion of the parts and sub-assemblies. Organisational conditioned down and idle times were not considered. The determination of these times is part of the capacity planning tools (Simulation).

As in the plate fabrication it is a manufacturing process, the process analysis took place at a single station (plasma cutting). However, the panel-fabrication is a multi-stage production process. The process analysis in this case included each station of panel line in particular.

In the next step the noted processes are categorised according to their time type. During the analysis the following time types are distinguished:

- Lead time
- Process time
- Handling time
- Post-processing time
- Servicing time

The process time constitutes the time type, in which the value adding in the proper sense occurs. The servicing processes are independent from the structure of the product and in general have to be done once a shift. As these processes demand capacity and have to be considered as fix, they are integrated in the calculation system. Fig. 1 shows each process that occurs at One-Side-Welding-Gantry in the panel-fabrication. The processes are carried out sequentially, what makes a consideration of parallel process unnecessary for this approach. According to Fig. 1 the process structure is defined for each relevant production resource.

Process description	Time type
Prepare backing	Lead time
Supply steel plate	Handling time
Adjust steel plate	Handling time
Tack steel plate	Lead time
End crater sheet welding	Lead time
Positioning welding device	Process time
One side welding	Process time
Positioning welding device	Process time
Clean seam	Post-processing time
Transfer panel	Post-processing time
Refill wire and flux	Servicing time
Clean machine	Servicing time

Fig. 1: Processes of a One-Side-Welding-Gantry (OSWG)

2.2 Process Driver

To enable a rule based determination of production times it is necessary to define the process drivers for every single process. In this case the approach of the activity based costing is applied by using the process driver as the characteristic proportional to the duration of the process. The activity based costing uses this approach in the same way by defining the cost driver of a process.

The process driver can be seen as an origin of duration time. The proportionality between the characteristics of the process driver and the duration of the process enables the planner, to determine the process times based on mathematical rules.

Within the scope of the analysis the process drivers for the processes were determined. The result is shown in Fig. 2. It is obvious that the duration of the processes depend on different structural characteristics of the product.

Fig. 2: Process drivers of the OSWG

2.3 Time Measurement

The topic of the last step of the analysis was the detailed time measurement of the processes considering the developed process structure. For each process the duration of singular execution in case of singular characteristics of the process driver was measured. This means for example, the duration of tacking on meter of steel plates was measured. Therefore the tack processes of a certain number of panels were measured and the time was divided by the length of the butt welds.

By use of these detailed process information it is possible to realise a rule based determination of production times based on product information and the process drivers. It has to be considered, that the process structure and especially the process durations fundamentally depend on the organisational structure of the production process. Thus for every production process a one-time process analysis is necessary to apply this method.

3 Development of a Calculating tool

After the process analysis has occurred the next step is to combine the product- and process-data to determine the production times. This process is explained more in detail in this passage.

Fig. 3 shows the concept of the calculation system from the data-import to the data export. The three main parts of the program are the data input, the calculation of the production times and the reporting and output data. All information are stored in one database with differed tables for input data (production data and process data) and of course one table to save the results of the process time calculation. The source code was generated in the .NET developer environment. This environment can combine different programming languages like C.# or Visual Basic and allows to integrate the program as a library in different other programs like SimControl, *Czarnietzki (2009)*, *Wanner and Bohnenberg (2008)*, or other tools for handling the simulation input and output data.

Fig. 3: Concept of the calculation program

The database for the following calculation contains on the one hand the knowledge about production-data and process. On the other hand the calculation needs product information. Therefore DNC and DXF data export from Nupas Cadmatic and Nestix is used to characterize the product (panel and plates) in the plate- and panel fabrication.

Fig. 4: Usage of Information's enclosed in DXF and DNC files

Fig. 4 illustrates the product information that could be achieved from CAD programs. For the developed solution it is possible to get information directly from Nupas Cadmatic as a DXF file. Furthermore the developed program can interpret already nested plates from nesting programs like Nestix. These data imports are needed in both cases. To generate data for the panel fabrication it is useful to take the Nupas Interface. For the plate fabrication it is more common to use the nested DNC File to consider all involved processes like the removal of cut-offs and scrap for the complete steel plate.

3.1 Data Input

According to the analyzed and needed processes a data import wizard was developed. This wizard leads the user in several steps through the complete calculation from the data input up to the result output.

Product data

To gather the needed production information' wizards were used. These wizards lead the user through different interfaces. In the first steps the adequate DNC-File is imported and analyzed. Then the planer uses the automatic generated information for the following steps. Here additional information are entered into the wizard in a manual way. Through an integrated DNC-File Viewer, Fig. 5, the user can quickly recognize the geometry of the panel or plate. With this visual support the planer is able to recognize and type in the missing information like the different kinds of welding seams and their length. Through the integrated verification / validation of all manual entered data the user is supported so the risk to do mistakes decreases a lot.

Fig. 5: Overview DNC-File Viewer for plate fabrication

Process data

The second import process is to save the analyzed product data. Therefore the planer has to configure once the single steps and processes for the different stations in the panel- and plate fabrication, Fig. 6. The required information is entered into formulas and rules. This is shown in Chapter 3.4. The process data must be changed only a few times. Once in the implementation phase of the program in a new production environment and after that a change of the process structure is only necessary when a machine is replaced or the process is changed.

3.2 Data structure

The product and process data are saved in different tables hosted in a Microsoft Access database. The chosen data structure considers a possible change in the process structures of the ship yards. Fig. 3 shows the data concept and the separation of incoming, internal and calculated data.

Input Data

The data tables for the incoming data were defined (rows and cols) according to the process analyses in chapter 2 and can be extended in all directions. Besides the data for the process drivers additional information as for example the paths for the DNC Files are also stored in the data tables. Timestamp information in each row allows a planning process with different users in one database.

Output Data

Output data is stored in a separate data table and includes all calculations for each sub assembly. In this table all calculated times for each defined process can be found and analyzed. For that reason the calculation program provides also a Wizard, Fig. 6.

However, we shall explain first how the calculation method works.

3.3 Calculation of detailed production times

For the calculation of the detailed production time of each part, the process times have to be combined with the characteristic of the part. Therefore, a set of rules was developed. Based on the process times and process drivers, these rules enable to determine production times concerning the individual parts characteristics.

Interpretation of rule based process data

The process data is integrated parameter-based into a database. Mathematical operators (+; -; *; /) as well as constraints (logical operators; if-statements and key words) can be used to combine the process parameters and the part characteristics. The column "planning time" is the result of the time measurement of each process concerning their process drivers. The following formula shows an exemplary calculation for a lead process on a welding station.

$$t_{prozess}(i) = \text{If}(\text{"\# of welding seams"} > 0; \text{planning time} * \text{\# of welding seams}; 0) \quad (1)$$

In the depicted example for each part, possessing a certain number of welding seams, the process time is calculated by multiplication of the number of welding seams and the planning time for preparing one welding seam. The mathematical operators and the constraints enable to model each process in particular. The examination of the formula happens in the formula interpreter, which constitutes an independent program library. This library is programmed in .NET (DLL) and can be expanded optionally.

By use of the formula interpreter and the process data inside the database the time for each process can be calculated. In the next step the process times for the single processes is added up to the entire production time for a part. This calculation is shown in Eq.(2).

$$t_{production} = \left(\sum_{j=0}^s \sum_{i=0}^n t_{prozess}(i) \right) * C \quad (2)$$

n- # of processes per station
s- # of stations
i,j – counter variable
C - allowance factor

Aktiviert	Station	Zeitart	Planzeit	Einheit	Berechnung mit Zahlen	Ergebnis [min]
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	UP	Prozesszeit	4	min/m	Wenn("0">0; 4 * ("0" + 0.6); 0)	0
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	UP	Prozesszeit	0	min	0 * "0"	0
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	UP	Prozesszeit	51,1	min	51,1 * "2"	102,2
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	UP	Nachbereitungszeit	2,5	min	2,5 * ("2" - 1)	2,5
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	UP	Prozesszeit	123	min	Wenn("False" = NEIN; 123; 0)	123
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	MBP	Vorbereitungszeit	52,7	min		52,7
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	MBP	Prozesszeit	0,3	min/m	0,3 * "123,5"	37,05
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	MBP	Prozesszeit	0,1	min/m	0,1 * "261,666300249484"	26,16663002494...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	MBP	Prozesszeit	1,3	min	1,3 * "10"	13
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	MBP	Prozesszeit	4,8	min	4,8 * "11"	52,8
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	MBP	Prozesszeit	1,2	min	1,2 * "3"	3,6

Fig. 6: Mask to validate the results

Reconstruct calculation

An additional function of the formula interpreter is a check of the formula's plausibility. This check guarantees that incorrect and illegitimate inputs do not lead to calculations of wrong planning results. At the End the user can also check all formulas with their used values. Therefore a Mask very similar to the process data input wizard shows all processes, their formulas and the result for each row, Fig. 6.

3.4 Output data

The calculated production times are represented to the user by the report function. For the subsequent usage, the results can be extracted directly from the database. Another possibility is the export function of an excel sheet containing the calculated production times. Fig. 7 shows the sequence of the planning steps and their implementation in .NET.

3.5 Further use of the results in operative production planning

The calculation system for production times was developed for the application in the operative production planning on a shipyard. It is used to determine the input information for the capacity planning and sequencing of jobs. Furthermore, the report function is useful base for the foreman on the shop floor. Here the results are used as target times for the workers. By listing every single process on the report, the transparency of the target time increases, leading to better acceptance on the shop floor.

4 Conclusion

The presented method of DNC / DXF-data evaluated on a base of parameters shows a possibility to generate accurate production-times very fast with the existent product- and process know-how.

Finally beheld some of the advantages are produced be the application of a calculating program:

- Availability of expertise and process know-how in a data base
- The combination of process data and product data expeditiously
- Extensibility of calculation with dynamic formulas
- Transparent way to reconstruct results
- Usability of data for further analysis
- Fast integration of further production areas

This data can be applied for different applications, by collimating the process know-how and expertise in a data base. The adoption of calculation in the simulation of the material-flow describes one of the possibilities. A complex calculation as a part of the simulation will be needless through the involvement of calculation results. Low simulation-period per run, a simple handling of data and a decrement of simulation model complexity result out of it. Only the production-times of particular work-stations or sub-processes have to be transferred into the simulation instead of complete data-sets and DNC files. Thereby complex procedures can be observed with coincident low effort for the simulation. The simulation-tool lead back to the core tasks, like the validation of planning variants, in this case. The figures of time calculated in the simulation process up to now, can be generated or reproduced by other groups of persons.

The decrease of the complexity grade in the simulation makes an addition of operating facilities and processes easy, which lead to simple decisions of investment or a risk analysis.

The planning efforts are reduced by 50% in comparison of the full-manual calculation of production-times.

Further developments covering the complete planning-process of ship-hull production and outfitting are planned.

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Multi-Level Hierarchical System Approach in Computerized Ship Design

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Abstract

The naval ship design process is challenged by the complexity of designing a system of systems, all of which interact with and influence the others. This challenge is further complicated by the interaction of the individual ship system of systems with the overall fleet architecture and the capabilities of existing and projected threats in a wide range of mission scenarios. Traditional ship design processes can be substantially enhanced by consideration of advancements in a number of fields including Operations Research, System Analysis, the Theory of Games and Meta Engineering. The efficient application of a System approach and appropriate methods in System Analysis of ship design processes are critical and remain a fertile area for innovation. We are advocates for a Multilevel Hierarchical System (MLHS) approach to the design process and associated tools development. The various elements of this proposed approach have been demonstrated and used effectively in practical applications. Combining them into one universal, systematic approach will enable the various Navy stakeholders to continually collaborate on both the development of the needed tools and the application of these tools during the design process.

1. Introduction

The naval ship design process is challenged by the complexity of designing a system of systems, all of which interact with and influence the others. This is further complicated by the interaction of the individual ship system of systems with the overall Fleet architecture and the capabilities of existing and projected threats in a wide range of mission scenarios. The Navy ship design community has been investigating approaches to achieve more integrated and effective design processes. Two underlying objectives that must be provided for an overall effective design process are:

- 1) to enable exploration of the entirety of the available design space to identify the best combination of capabilities and cost and
- 2) to maintain design flexibility for as long as possible as the level of detail of the design increases.

Jons and Wynn (2009) describe the need for Continuing, Collaborative, Concept Formulation (C3F) and propose that “operational concepts (ways) and systems concepts (means) should co-evolve as warfighters and designers/engineers work side by side constantly evaluating how to optimize capability (ie. the combinations of ways and means). The best combination then becomes the basis for both competitive procurement and operational doctrine”.

The Navy has an extensive set of computer-based tools to assist in both the assessment of operational concepts and in the design of ship systems. These tools range from system level tools through detailed discipline specific design and analysis tools. To facilitate integration of design data through the design processes, NAVSEA has selected the Leading Edge Architecture for Prototyping Systems (LEAPS) as the environment for integrating and managing the Product Model data that evolves through a design project. At this time, efforts are underway to maintain the interoperability with LEAPS, such that various tools draw their input requirements from LEAPS and populate back to LEAPS the design and analysis information that constitute the product model data content.

The process of integrating the operational/mission effectiveness tools with the design/engineering tools has always been a challenge due both to the organizational separation of the stakeholders and the computational demands of the various disciplines involved. Another problem is that necessary data is frequently not available or otherwise compatible with the mutual needs of the mission effectiveness models and design/analysis tools.

While the path for the integration of tools through a common product model is available, a systematic approach is needed to guide the development of tools that enable the search of the multi-disciplinary design space and to coordinate the use of a wide range of tools during collaborative design processes. The authors view the existing tool population and needed design processes to be best served by a hierarchical system. The uppermost level of this hierarchy is a collection of models and processes which support the collaborative exploration of the operational concepts – systems concepts design space. Each level below this represents a collection of processes at different levels of detail and fidelity starting from total system design processes and proceeding down to subsystem specific design processes. A systematic approach is outlined to accomplish the following two goals:

1. Support the development of models at the higher levels of the hierarchy based on the execution of tools at lower levels of the hierarchy.
2. Provide criteria based on an optimal range of characteristics determined at the upper levels of the hierarchy that can be passed down to lower levels of the hierarchy where they can be used during these more detailed design and analyses to guide the design while maintaining a maximum range of design flexibility at the lower levels.

The methods and techniques proposed in this approach have been demonstrated and used effectively in other applications. Combining them into one universal systematic approach will enable the various Navy stakeholders to continually collaborate in both the development of the needed tools and the application of these tools during the design process.

2 Ship design process characterization

Based on DOD System Engineering Process definitions¹, the Systems Engineering Process is usually presented in the following scheme:

Fig. 1: Traditional System Engineering Process

In this general construct, **System Need** (the process input) includes: Customer Needs/Objectives/Missions together with clarification of Measures of Effectiveness, Environments, and Constraints; Technologies; Program Decision Requirements; and Standards. **System Design** (the Process Output) initially includes: a Decision Data Base which contains the results of design space exploration and representative Physical Architectures. As the process matures the output should ideally include Optimized in multidisciplinary design space System Solutions resulting in a Baseline design and associated Specifications. The **Requirements Analysis and Functional Analysis** activities

¹ EIA Standard IS-632; formerly MIL-STD-499B)

are the subject of the Battle Force/ Warfare System Modeling. **The Synthesis Activity** with links back to **Requirements and Functional Analysis** through the actions of the **Systems Analysis and Control** function is the principle area where the MLHS approach of this paper applies. The proper understanding and control of these feedback links ensure that the desired collaboration between models used in the Synthesis Activity and those used in Requirements Analysis and Functional Analysis activities are achieved. It is self evident that the information generated in the **Synthesis** activity must be sufficient to run both **Mission Effectiveness** and **Cost Evaluation** tools in order to provide meaningful feedback signals.

The general Input at the Synthesis level would typically include: Payload / Cargo; Sustained Speed; Fuel Endurance at the Endurance Speed); Stores Endurance (# days); Design and Future Growth Margins; Survivability features; Habitability standards; Special requirements (e.g. arctic, etc); and Dimensional limitations. The general Output typically includes: Major subsystem description and design limits; Principal dimensions and hull form characteristics; General and Machinery Arrangement schemes; Weight estimate (1 to 3-digit depending on the maturity of the process); Area/volume summary; Intact stability check; Propulsion plant type and number of shafts; Electric plant capacity and number of generators; Speed and endurance fuel estimates; Crew size, Performance characteristics; Cost estimate (acquisition, life cycle and risk); and Selected Measure of Effectiveness (MOE).

For the purpose of implementing the Collaborative Concept Formulation process with the MLHS approach, the functionality of the **System Analysis** block in Fig. 1 needs modification. The MLHS approach emphasizes the collaborative nature of design concept formulation which requires greater information exchange than has formerly occurred between Synthesis and upper level Operation models. To support this iterative process, System Analysis should allow the execution of a number of specific functions including Coordination between the Synthesis and Operation Models, and execution of various Design Space Exploration and Optimization tasks. As a result of these considerations, the **System Analysis** activity should be viewed as the **Design Monitor** with the activities shown in Fig. 2. This figure shows the proposed changes between the conventional ship design activities associated with “System Analysis and Control” and the MLHS approach.

Fig. 2: Functionality of “System” block to support Concept Formulation process

3 System Monitor and C3F Process Control

Functionally, the system monitor in the C3F process needs to support design exploration and optimization, as well as, facilitate coordination in MLHS. It should help understand the behavior of design models, learn about and understand design alternatives, conduct trade-off studies, and,

ultimately, zero in on the best design(s) for concept formulation and subsystem design.

A Monitor should support grid computing and allow implementation of the following consecutive functions:

1. Design Process Integration: This is the process of linking all relevant design and analysis software tools together into an integrated engineering model. The Integration, which is often a difficult and time consuming task or not done at all, should be executed with maximum time efficiency. It should enable easy modification of the process and set up of model input.
2. Understand design model relationships and trends: After creating an integrated design model, the next step is to run the model to verify its accuracy, to visualize and understand overall trends, and to identify the most influential variables in the model. Design of Experiments (DOE) techniques assist in performing these tasks.
3. Explore the Design Space: After gaining a basic understanding of the model's behavior, the Monitor should include plotting and graphing tools to facilitate visualization of the design space and the interactive search for improved designs. To assess reliability and robustness of design solutions the Monitor may utilize Probabilistic Analysis tools.
4. Search for Optimal Designs: After exploring and understanding the design space, the Monitor should utilize robust optimization algorithms to find better designs. In the Set-Up of the design process, the goals and performance requirements or criteria and constraints of optimization task are specified, and the optimization algorithms will search for the designs
5. Perform Post-Optimization Analysis and Data Control Management. When the solution(s) are selected, it may be necessary to rerun some of the individual models to provide additional detail and develop graphics and material for reports. As described below, additional calculations are also required for Coordination Factors. These are the partial derivatives of selected functional design parameters that are used to maintain **System** optimality as lower levels of the hierarchy are developed. Finally, the Monitor should implement translation of data generated at the Synthesis and subsystems levels into a Product Model Data Base, e.g. LEAPS.

At present there are several commercial software systems available which have practically all required functionality described above. Candidate software systems for a MLHS Monitor to support the C3F process include the following:

- ModelCenter® and CenterLink®, developed by Phoenix Integration²,
- iSight®, developed by Engineous Software³
- FRONTIER® by Esteco⁴.

4 The Measure of Effectiveness (MOE) and Cost Estimate in C3F Process

The major goal of the C3F process for the Navy is to align individual ship requirements with fleet needs by optimally matching fleet operational concepts (Ways) and ship system performance (Means). Effectiveness can be defined as the extent to which a ship system meets its mission requirements. There are different ways of modeling Measure of Effectiveness (MOE), depending on either combat, military logistic or commercial transportation operations. The following addresses the development of MOE's. These examples can be easily extended to other scenarios.

1. The MOE can be developed by the hierarchical arrangement of the required capabilities of the ship and then applying a pair-wise comparison of the elements of the hierarchy. Application of the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) enables the calculation of the weights of the required capabilities. Pair-wise comparison of the performance of each alternative for each required capability leads to the MOE, *Brown and Salcedo (2003)*. The required capabilities of the ship for different types of missions are arranged in a hierarchical manner. The various mission types form the top level of this hierarchy. Different categories of capabilities neces-

² www.phoenix-int.com

³ www.engineous.com

⁴ esteco.com/images/brochure/OnePageDescription.pdf

sary for each type of mission from the next level. The actual capabilities that represent each category form the lowest level of hierarchy. These actual capabilities are called the Measures of Performance (MOP). For example, in the case of a logistic ship mission the top level characteristics could be: Expeditionary, Adaptable, Enduring, Fast, Resilient and Interoperable. The categories and attributes associated with these characteristics comprise the next level. For example, Platform Range, VSTOL Characteristics and Air Refueling apply to the Adaptable characteristic; Cargo Transfer Rate, Mission Response Time, Sortie Rate and Platform Speed apply to the *Fast* characteristic, and so on. A group of experts perform a pair-wise comparison of the elements of this hierarchy. In the pair-wise comparison each expert takes two elements of equal level of the hierarchy and on a relative scale they express their opinion regarding which of the two elements is important and how important it is compared to the other capability. Analytical hierarchy process theory is used to analyze the results of the pair-wise comparison to generate the relative weights of measures of performance for all the MOPs. These are normalized weights and the sum of these weights is equal to 1. Each of these MOPs may have a number of options to select from or, depending on Design Synthesis Model, are the functions of ship parameters. The MOE is defined as the sum of the products of MOP weights and values of all MOPs. In this approach MOE is a number between 0 and 1 describing the ship effectiveness for specified missions. There are a number of other types of global MOE criteria in addition to the simple normalization of the MOE as function of selected MOPs. Some of them are: different expressions of average values, minimax, Hurwitz, Hodge-Leman, Hermeir, product-type, Mushik-Muller, etc., *Gaikovich (2001)*

2. For most military logistic ship missions the Measures of Performance are determined using Discrete Event Simulation models. The MOE hierarchy is considered at the Squadron, Ship Platform and System/Component levels. The discrete event models require extensive data collection and model validation. One example of such a model is the Closure, Assemble, Employ and Reconstitute (CAESaR) model which allows evaluation of different Fleet architectures and operation scenarios to perform Logistic missions. The model is sensitive to a number of parameters including varying distances between CONUS, Advance Base, and Sea Base, varying ships (existing & new designs) and portion of troops and equipment prepositioned. The output of the CAESaR model is throughput times of fulfillment of transport tasks for certain operational scenarios based on the particular characteristics of the ship(s) modeled. A MOE can be the direct output of this type of model.
3. Stochastic war gaming simulation models, which in certain practical or simplified cases can be presented as analytical models can be used to develop a MOE. In these usually very complicated models, the MOE is usually the probability of successful outcome of combat duels or other combat tasks. One of the simplified examples is discussed below.
4. In commercial transport scenarios, the MOE is usually the Required Freight Rate (RFR) which is the output of Voyage and Economic models. Depending on the scenario (Door-to-Door service or transportation at fixed sea routes) Voyage models can be more or less complicated, including terminal and drayage simulation modeling, etc.

In many cases the direct use in the Collaborative Concept Formulation process of complex models, such as stochastic combat models, to establish the MOE is computationally impractical. To avoid the computational difficulties of complex models surrogate MOE Behavior Models can be used. Later in this paper we will discuss the general approach for building MOE Behavior Models. The general approach we advocate is based on Systematic Calculation Series and is generally applicable to any MOE Behavior Model. The fundamental idea is that in advance of implementing the Concept Formulation process, it is necessary to develop systematic series of potential parameters for the complex models used to establish the MOE. The output of these systematic calculations establishes a database containing values of MOE, either as single criterion or vector of various parameter values. A Behavior Model approximates the database. This allows a much simpler way to represent analytical models based on relationships between the MOE vector and various operational parameters and ship characteristics. These approximations can be done with well established techniques including regression analysis, kriging and neural network methods.

Below, the subject of collaboration in the C3F process is discussed, illustrating Effectiveness and Cost relationships. By Effectiveness we would understand MOE as the most probable result of MOE Behavior Modeling tools. For illustrative purposes we would denote Effectiveness by symbol “E” as criterion or vector of criteria, depending on ship concept parameters – vector “X”. In the text below we would omit dependence of E from numerous parametric input data (vector “S” in further discussions), which is considered to be known and unchangeable in the course of single cycle of Concept Formulation process.

Similarly, we would denote Ship Cost and Cost of Risk by symbol “C”, also dependent on “X” and omitting dependence on other input data. It is imperative that the methods of estimating various costs are tightly coupled with the design iteration process and are parametric in nature in order to support the needs of the Program Manager in terms of not only the basic design but design trade-offs in the course of Collaborative Concept Formulation process.

During the Collaborative Concept Formulation process a set of parametric cost models are employed. These cost models produce quick assessments of costs and risk, for design and mission trade-off alternatives. The cost models, being parametric, can follow the evolutionary design process. In C3F process, when many details of the design are not yet available, the cost models automatically provide statistically-synthesized values for missing parameters. Then, as the design matures, these default values can be replaced with values developed for the design

5. Cost-Efficiency Parametric Study in C3F Process

At Synthesis level of Ship Design Process the Cost-Efficiency type of the criteria are used and support the Collaborative Concept Formulation process. These criteria are accompanied with various types of functional constrains. The following text characterizes the general nature of the Cost-Efficiency type of criteria. Consider two types of the criteria:

1. Level of Cost is limited and the goal of optimization is to maximize the Efficiency. In this case of a single efficiency criterion, the problem is formulated in the following way:

$$\text{Max } E(X, N)$$

$$C(X, N) \leq C^*, \text{ where}$$

C; C* - The function of Cost, which can be acquisition and/or cost of risk or life cycle cost; Limited Cost level

N – The unknown number of ships in the fleet,

X – Vector of the optimized ship concept variables,

E – The functions of Efficiency.

2. Level of Efficiency function is limited and optimization is to minimize the Cost:

$$\text{Min } C(X, N)$$

$$E(X, N) \geq E^*, \text{ where}$$

E* - Limited Efficiency level

Let us assume that there are no other solutions for minimum of Cost, which correspond to each fixed E*, and which provide less Cost if level of E* increases. This is a reasonable assumption: more efficiency costs more. From this assumption we would conclude that the optimum is obtained at the condition $E(X, N) = E^*$. By analogy the solution for maximum efficiency would be obtained at $C(X, N) = C^*$.

Accordingly, by excluding $N = N(X, E^*)$ in two equations, we are coming to the problem, which can be formulated as

$$\text{Min } C(X, E^*).$$

As result of solving this problem we obtain optimal solution X_{opt} as function of E*: - $X_{\text{opt}}(E^*)$. If we substitute this solution in the expression $N = N(X, E^*)$, we receive $N_{\text{opt}}(E^*)$, optimal number of ships in the fleet.

Substituting these expressions of X_{opt} and N_{opt} , we receive $C_{\text{opt}}(E^*)$, optimal cost, which depend only

on required level of efficiency E^* .

With the above assumptions about $C_{opt}(E^*)$ and $E_{opt}(C^*)$ relationships (high efficiency costs more), these functions mutually define each other. This means that $E_{opt}(C^*)$ can be found from $C_{opt}(E^*)$ by solving the indirect equation $C_{opt}(E_{opt}) = C^*$ and vice versa.

As an example, *Hudiakov (1980)*, let us consider the operation of detecting an unmoving target in the sea within operation area Ω during the period of time T . Let the probability of discovery of this target be the criterion of operation efficiency. If the task is solved by the fleet with N ships, individual ship operations are independent from each other. In these assumptions the operation process is described by as Poisson process. The probability of discovery of the target by the fleet consisting of N ships can be expressed in the following way:

$$P(v, N) = 1 - e^{-2dvTN/\Omega}$$

v – Ships speed, and
 d – Range of ship detection means.

Understanding that the speed is a function of ship parameters and environmental factors in the particular operating area, let us assume that the speed of ship operations is equal to ship maximum speed. Let us also assume that detection range is independent on speed and other factors. In this assumption in order to increase the probability we need to maximize the maximum speed of the ship.

The Cost of the fleet can be expressed in the following formula:

$$C(v, N) = (A + bv^n)N,$$

Where A , b , n – coefficients, which can be obtained by approximation of relationships based on direct Cost calculations, which can be done with use of cost estimating methodology, described in for example *Deschamps and Greenwell (2009)*.

Omitting the mathematical operations by substituting one expression into another, we can find that optimal maximum speed can be expressed by the following formula:

$$v_{opt} = (A/(n-1)b)^{1/n},$$

which is reasonable because Ship Cost, as function of speed, increases faster than by linear law ($n > 1$). It can be also shown that optimal Cost as function of given Probability P^* can be expressed as

$$C_{opt}(P^*) = -k \ln(1 - P^*) \quad \text{with} \quad k = A (\Omega/2Td) n/(n-1) ((n-1)b/A)^{1/n}$$

It can be also shown that optimal value of probability of detection as function of level of Cost is defined by the formula:

$$P_{opt}(C^*) = 1 - e^{-C^*/k}, \text{ where } k \text{ is defined in the above formula.}$$

The relationships $C_{opt}(P^*)$ and $P_{opt}(C^*)$ are shown in the Fig. 3.

From above formulas, presented in Fig. . 3, it is seen that that the derivative $\delta P_{opt}(C^*)/\delta C^*$ consistently reduces with increase of C^* . It means that increase of ΔP_{opt} at small increase of ΔC^* , which is the additional funding resource, is reducing with increase of C^* . In the same way, the conclusion about $\delta C_{opt}(P^*)/\delta P^*$ is opposite: small increase of detection probability ΔP_{opt} leads to higher relative Cost increase ΔC^* . In more practical cases with fewer assumptions than the example above, the relationships $C_{opt}(P^*)$ and $P_{opt}(C^*)$ look as presented in Fig. . 4.

Fig. 3: Simplified relationships $P_{opt}(C^*)$ and $C_{opt}(P^*)$

Fig. 4: Relationships $E_{opt}(C^*)$ and $C_{opt}(E^*)$ with excess points

In comparison to the monotone curves in Fig. 3, the more realistic curves in Fig. 4 have excess points where the derivatives $\delta E_{opt}(C^*)/\delta C^*$ and $\delta C_{opt}(E^*)/\delta E^*$ have points of maximum and minimum and sign of the curves curvature changes. We can define these points as C^{**} and E^{**} .

The important conclusion is that when seeking the optimal ship concept parameters X_{opt} , at the conditions $E^* = E^{**}$ and $C^* = C^{**}$ then these parameters would define the ship concepts, for which maximum increase of efficiency is obtained at minimal cost increase. And simultaneously, for this particular ship concept the minimal cost increase corresponds to maximum increase of efficiency.

In mathematical interpretation if to associate Cost and Efficiency with “players” playing a game, where their interests are to optimize their own criteria, the points, described above have relation to “stability” points introduced in theory of games by famous Noble Prize winner John Nash.

In the general case, while solving any of the Cost-Efficiency tasks it is necessary to know C^* and E^* - the limits of funding resources and required efficiency. This data can be determined in most general, “upper-level” war fighters and DOD budget planning and simulation models, shown as Requirements and Functional Analysis blocks in Fig. 2. At the same time the system optimization is impossible without optimization of subsystems. This is a well-known methodological paradox. There are two ways to resolve it and both of them are the subject of Collaborative Concept Formulation process:

1. First, there is an opportunity that optimal ship concept parameters are not dependent on C^* and E^* . For example, it was this situation described above, when the optimal speed of ship operations did not depend on limited Cost and required probability of target detection. In this case there is no paradox. To check it, it is necessary to perform parametric study by optimizing the ship concept parameters at different C^* and E^* and make sure that X_{opt} does not depend on these values. This case will often occur where some other condition or requirement limits the characteristics of the ship and thus constrain the ship concept from meeting the lim-

its of C^* or E^* . An example is where a required transit passage limits the overall dimensions or capacity of the ship. Correspondingly, the first task in Collaborative Concept Formulation process is to investigate if ship concept parameters remain “stable” at different Cost-Efficiency required limits.

2. If the optimal ship concept parameters depend on limits C^* and E^* , then it is necessary to perform the iterative process or “Collaborative” – in terminology of C3F process. First, it is necessary to find the relationships $E_{opt}(C^*)$ or $C_{opt}(E^*)$. This task is recommended to be solved with the C3F Synthesis models, not going into details of the ship concept subsystems. These relationships are the input for various Functional analysis tasks and Operation Concepts Models, for which the ship concept is most likely one of the subsystems of the “upper-level” operation models. After exploring the Models of combat, military or commercial transportation operations with initial Cost-Efficiency relationships, new requirements for Cost and Efficiency levels are provided for another iteration of “Collaborative” process with more details at concept design subsystems level of Multilevel Collaborative Concept Formulation system.

The Cost-Efficiency relationships enable an effective negotiation process between the fleet operational concepts (Ways) and ship system performance (Means). Profiles can be generated that will visually show the impact of individual mission performance characteristics on the cost of the ship concept. These profiles can also be used to investigate the impact of changes to the performance characteristics on the ship cost, as well as, on other performance characteristics. Using these profiles, a best value combination of mission performance versus cost can be determined.

6. Convergence and Organization of Design Process

Traditional engineering design is typically based on a sequential approach involving several phases: definition of the design optimization task; mathematical modeling of the task with selection of the input variables and constraints on the output parameters; development of the algorithm and/or task solver; and analysis of the solution. Traditionally, the analysis in each discipline (e.g. structures) is performed separately because connections between each discipline are too complex and interrelated to solve simultaneously. Therefore, the overall problem of system design takes a sequential approach, where each subsystem or discipline is designed separately and various disciplines are optimized sequentially. The results of the previous subsystem’s design and optimization become the basis for further optimization problems. As a consequence, very limited possibilities are left to the last optimization problem; the first in design order subsystem dominates the final solution. This traditional approach is usually represented by the “design spiral”.

Following the “design spiral” approach, the convergence of the process is the simple balancing of the design in terms of major design constraints. It occurs when for example, the estimated weight equals the displacement of the ship at the design draft, or when the area available equals the area required. In an iterative collaborative concept formulation process a convergence to the optimal solution, not just a simply feasible solution is required. By optimal solutions we mostly understand the compromised solutions, being obtained in the course of parametric studies implementing data exchange with “corrective signals”, representing uncertainty in formulating firm and “reasonable” requirements.

In the ship design engineering process the term “convergence” actually means achieving the design goals with optimal values of measure of merits with feasible (from the point of design requirements and constrains) design solutions.

The convergence of the “Spiral Design” process cannot be mathematically proven, but is usually achieved in practice by artificial, intuitive interaction with the professional designer (naval architect), who implements his/her individual experience and historical data. Termination of iterations is based on personal experience of the designer, time, or resource limits, but not on the convergence upon formalized criterion.

Most importantly: design constraints, which bound the design space, are the function of design parameters, which are estimated at later stage/lower level of design hierarchy. At the ever-increasing amount of knowledge and details, the design constrains can change. The obvious consequence is that the design space changes and the optimum can migrate from one location in design space to another. In view of these circumstances the Method of Consecutive Iterations, which is the basis of “design spiral” approach, can be applied to C3F process with precautions: Consecutive iterations as method or ideology can converge (lead, obtain, ensure, etc) to the optimum or cannot, depending on the specifics (mathematical nature) of the particular task. For the tasks with strong correlation of parameters (different influence of one group of parameters on functions, defining the criteria or constraints of the task) the method of consecutive iteration would not converge to the optimum. Fig. 5 shows that consecutive iterations along any one variable at the fixed another one do not allow changing the point (X_1^*, X_2^*) , which is far from the “true” optimal solution, so that this point can be defined as “deadlock” of the process.

Fig. 5: Consecutive Iteration in Traditional Design Spiral Approach – Design Deadlock

Contrary to traditional “design spiral” approach, Multi-Level Hierarchical System approach allows achieving true convergence by implementing different coordination strategies; some of them are described below. Among them is Method of Design Budgets, when at lower level - subsystem design level it is allowed to search solutions with predefined at “upper-level” – Synthesis level budgets / resources in changing system constraints, dependent on subsystem design solutions, *Zaharov (1987)*. Another method is Criteria Coordination Method, *Pashin and Mizine (1981)*, based on relative design costs, which in mathematic interpretation are the Lagrange coefficients, showing the impact of changing the subsystem solutions on ship design system criteria (MOE, Cost, and Risk). Combination of these and some other methods can provide flexibility in organizing the design process at different levels of hierarchy and different computer-based models, thus ensuring (mathematically) convergence, at least at certain mathematical assumptions.

7. MLHS Design Process and Coordination Strategy

The design task at “upper-level” – synthesis model, for which we would assign the index “1”, can be described in mathematical form:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & X_2 = X_2^* \\
 & (X_1)_{\min} \leq X_1(X_2) \leq (X_1)_{\max} \\
 & G_1^j(X_1(X_2), S_1) \leq A_1^j(S_1); \\
 & \text{Minimize or Maximize } Z_1(X_1(X_2), S_1)
 \end{aligned}$$

- X_2 – Vector of the variables, which characterize ship concept subsystems and represent at ship concept synthesis level or at any “upper-level” model prototype, statistical or any other “given” information related to various subsystems or disciplines, integrated at synthesis level. Vector X_2^* is “given” or known information. For example, if X_2 is hull material, then X_2^* could be steel.
- S_1 – Vector of parameters, which define requirements and characterize the design environment of the ship concept. This may include standards, details of mission requirements (characteristics of payload items, voyage routes, etc.) and other general inputs that are intended to specify the overall design environment. At the subsystem level the S vector is similar, but may also include specification of additional standards and design options to be considered.
- X_1 – Vector of the optimized variables, which characterize ship concept at “upper-level” synthesis level of MLHS;
- G_1^j – Vector of the mission and physical characteristic constraints on the ship concept being defined at synthesis level.
- j – The index “ j ” is the index for specific constraints at synthesis and subsystem levels. At synthesis level the examples are stability, required areas and volumes for the payload should be not less than available or difference between required and available should be positive: difference between weights and displacement at design draft should not exceed the displacement margin; freeboard should not be less than Rules defined; Efficiency and Cost should not be less or more than the limits, which can be changed in the course of parametric studies; speed or required power should not be less than or more than installed; and so on. At subsystem level for Structure Design subsystem the constraints are building technology and material characteristics and footprint loads; for Hull Forms Optimization subsystem - mostly geometrical constraints, which come from the series, prototype or statistics restrictions and reflect considerations, which are not fully modelled. For Machinery Design Subsystem the constraints are electric balances at different operations, arrangement standards, like corridors and so on. These constraints may be varied with the fidelity of the design analysis. More fidelity requires less restrictions and constraints,
- A_1^j – the required value of the constraint G_1^j .
- Z_1 – vector of criteria, selected at synthesis level, which characterize the full vector of mission effectiveness and cost characteristics of the ship concept. These criteria, depending on their nature, should be either minimized or maximized.

There is definitely interrelation between criteria and constraints. At synthesis level we can choose Efficiency as criterion and put level of cost as constraint, or keep both as criteria. But besides these criteria there can be much more: we can seek to maximize the seakeeping index (of certain type), maneuvering capability (like composite maneuvering Nomoto index), Lift to Drag or transport efficiency.

These vectors are designed to support a Multi-Disciplinary and Multi-Objective Design and Optimization problem.

The example of vector X_1 is main ship dimensions, characteristics of general arrangement (number of holds, etc), ship hull forms and hull configuration parameters and so on.

Vector of subsystem variables X_2 can be presented as $X_2(x_2^k)$, where index k is the index of particular ship concept subsystem. For example, $k=1$ means subsystem of hull forms and propulsion design. Then x_2^1 means vector of hull forms parameters, parameters of propulsion system, etc. If $k=2$ means subsystem of ship structure design, then x_2^2 means scantling characteristics, material parameters, etc. If $k=3$ means subsystem of mechanical design, then x_2^3 means vector of mechanical system parameters, power distribution characteristics.

By $Z_1(X_1(X_2), S_1) = Z_1(z_1^m(X_1(X_2), S_1))$, we define synthesis “upper-level” system efficiency vector (Measure of Merits criteria), where each z_1^m would also depend on $X_1(X_2)$. Criteria vector can

include, for example⁵: $z_1^1 = 1/[\text{Mission Efficiency}]$; $z_1^2 = \text{Total Life Cost}$; $z_1^3 = \text{Powering or speed}$; $z_1^4 = \text{Structural Weight}$; $z_1^5 = 1/[\text{Payload \& Cargo Volumes}]$, etc. Design constraint functions also depend on $X_1(X_2)$.

The Multi Level Design System approach assumes that it is impossible to solve the optimization problem with all variables \mathbf{X} based on a global mathematical model and the design process is based on a decomposition of the global optimization model into different levels of Hierarchy System, as it is shown in Fig. 2 to 10.

Any of the tasks at “lower-level” of design hierarchy, at any of the ship concept design subsystems level, for which we would assign the index “2”, can be described in the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} X_1 &= X_1^* \\ S_2(X_1, G_1^j, Z_1) \\ (X_2)_{\min} &\leq X_2 \leq (X_2)_{\max}, \\ &\text{where } (X_2)_{\min} \text{ and } (X_2)_{\max} \text{ are functions of } X_1, G_1^j, Z_1 \\ G_2^j(X_2, S_2) &\leq A_2^j(S_2); \\ \text{Minimize or Maximize } &Z_2(X_2, S_2), \text{ where} \end{aligned}$$

The condition $X_1 = X_1^*$ describes decomposition scheme of the multilevel design system and reflects usual design practice. For example, when we develop the hulls forms we use main dimensions of the ship, which are previously defined at synthesis level of design system. The same with structural design, mechanical design and so on.

$S_2, X_2, G_2^j, A_2^j, Z_2$ are the same as in model of the synthesis level, but these vectors are the functions of the parameters of the “upper-level” model.

There are different ways of establishing reverse links between models at different levels of MLHS, which are based on methods of Theory of Large Systems, *Mesarovich (1970)*. There are two major ways of coordinating solutions between models at different levels of MLHS: Methods of design budgets and Method of criteria coordination⁶

The essence of the first Method of Design Budgets is that after solving the problem at synthesis level the limits A_2^j are determined. The examples are: Maximum allowable weight of the subsystem; the range of allowable centers of gravity for each of the subsystems; Maximum possible volume and length of machinery compartment, and so on. Practically, this is the usual approach, which is directly described in the Ship Design Manual, reflecting the established practice of Design Process organization.

This approach has distinctive disadvantages: The values of these budgets/limits cannot be justified and fully dependent on adequacy of the design subsystem model; and most importantly, such limits determine the subsystem solutions, which are not optimal in excessively constrained area of feasible solutions. The basis of these disadvantages is the absence of reverse link between the models at different levels of Design System.

Contrary to this approach, these links exist in Criteria Coordination Method. In this method the coordination is achieved by modifying the criteria of the subsystem model. Instead of Z_2 , the Criteria Coordination method uses the criteria vector Φ_2 , which is in the simplest form (omitting some of the dimensional coefficients between different parts of the modified criteria), can be presented as following:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Minimize or Maximize } \Phi_2 &= Z_2(X_2, S_2) + \sum \lambda_1^{j*} \Delta G_1^j(X_1(X_2^*), X_1(X_2)), \text{ where} \\ \lambda_1^j &\text{ are the so called Lagrange dual multipliers and are determined as} \\ \lambda_1^j &= \Delta Z_1 / \Delta G_1^j, \text{ where} \end{aligned}$$

⁵ Assuming that criteria are formulated to be minimized

⁶ In special literature this method is also called methods of delegating the responsibility

j - Index of global constraints in synthesis design model (or any “upper-level” model).

These multipliers are calculated in the assumption that the solutions in subsystem models X_2 can become different than being assumed initially at synthesis or “upper-level” X_2^* .

These Lagrange dual multipliers can be used for coordination strategies between the levels of the MLHS. As can be found in the formula for Φ_2 , the criteria coordination is provided by special modification of the criterions of the “lower-level” design subsystems.

The Concept Formulation Model, which is associated with the upper-level of MLHS, will generate a set of coordination factors that can be used by the design activities at the lower level to further analyze and refine the design. Some of these factors will be fixed constraints that the ship design must maintain above or below a specific value. Other factors will be provided in terms of cost efficiency relationships – Lagrange coefficients. Fig. 6 provides an example, *Pashin (1983)*, of such type of relationship, which were earlier studied by *Fisher (1973)*. In this case the relative cost of a change in metacentric height is shown. This figure shows the change of economical criterion with change of upper limit of ship intact stability constraint.

Fig. 6: Example Cost-Efficiency Coordination Factor

Here we assume that at “synthesis-level” model the vector of variables is $X_1=(x_1,x_2,x_3)=(\text{Block Coefficient, Length to Beam Ratio, Beam to Draft})$. The feasible area is determined by constraints, which include Weight & Volume Balance, Intact Stability, etc. The initial data for the general cargo ship was the following: Payload = 12,000 tons; Machinery Power = 14,600 kW; Cargo fraction = 1.86 m³/t; Required Range = 12,000 NM. Cost of a change in metacentric height is calculated as partial derivative of economical criterion, which is chosen as Ratio of Building Cost to Amount of Annual Cargo, \$/ton. In Fig. 6 the relative cost of intact stability, [\$/t / h/B] is about 1, where “h” is metacentric height, or \$18,000/centimeter. Similar calculations can be performed with other design constraints and in relation to other criteria. These coordination factors assumed to be known in the course of the subsystems design optimization, allowing modification of subsystem criteria Φ_2 .

In Φ_2 the sum operation is provided for each index j , which is the index of synthesis or “upper-level” task constraints, which at point X_1^{opt} are the equalities. For example, in the Fig. 7 the constraint with number $j=2$ would not be included in Φ_2 , because minimum and maximum limits of intact stability requirements cannot be fulfilled simultaneously. In other words we can say that for the constraints, which are not the equalities in the point X_1^{opt} , the coordination factors – Lagrange coefficients λ_1^j are equal to zero.

The subsystem design goal should be finding best solutions from the point of global system criteria. To achieve this goal a designer needs to use algorithms which allow calculation of the impact of a local design solution on “upper-level” design system criterion. This approach to coordinate the optimization in the MLHS process is shown in Fig. 7 for one of the criteria global $Z_1 = f(X_1, X_2)$. $G_1^1(X_1^{1,2}(X_2^*)) = A_1^1$ can correspond for example to the lower limit of the stability constraint (minimum metacentric height), G_1^2 – upper limit of initial stability, G_1^3 – payload/volume capability.

Z_1 , which is in this figure is shown as criterion f , and $G_1^{1,2,3}$ are the functions of variables of the synthesis model $X_1^{1,2}=X_1(x_1, x_2)$ (for example: ship length to beam and block coefficient). $X_1^{1,2}$ are optimized at fixed variables of subsystems X_2^* . The dashed line is the change of the boundary $G_1^3 = A_1^3$ when the parameters X_2 become not equal to X_2^* . It can happen at optimization of any subsystem at “2-level” of hierarchy after optimization at synthesis level. These changes can extend ($+\Delta G_1^j$) or reduce ($-\Delta G_1^j$) the feasible area of solutions at synthesis level of hierarchy. Correspondingly $\pm \Delta Z_1 = \pm \Delta f$ are the changes of synthesis level criterion as result of extension or reduction of the feasible area of design solution.

Fig. 7: “2-level” design subsystem influence on “upper-level” optimization task

The consequences of such modification are the following:

- Modified “lower-level” criterion should lead to such “local” solutions X_2 , which are most favorable from the point of the “upper-level” system efficiency – Vector Criteria minimize or maximize $Z_1(X_1(X_2), S_1)$
- “Local” criteria should penalize such X_2 , which reduce the feasible area in the synthesis or “upper-level” Task 1, Fig. 7. At the same time they should stimulate such X_2 , which increase the feasible area of the “upper-level”, synthesis design solutions
- The calculation of the subsystem-level criterion should be possible with minimum data from other subsystems, because in the MLHS the optimization of subsystems is provided simultaneously for all design subsystems at each level of hierarchy.

The reverse link or coordination factors in this approach result in changes of the synthesis or any “upper-level” models as result of $X_2 \neq X_2^*$. Direct coordination link is the Lagrange coefficients, used for special form of local criteria for “lower-level” models. The usage of Φ_2 in lower-level optimization subsystems allows achieving coordination of design solutions at different levels of MLHS.

The MLHS scheme is shown in Fig. 9. Unlike the Design Spiral approach, the coordination of design solutions at different subsystems is provided for the interest of the whole Multilevel Hierarchical System. Such a methodology can use traditional subsystem budgets for critical parameters, such as weight, space, power, and cost, as coordination factors which need to be defined at synthesis level of the MLHS. Subsequent analyses refine technically feasible subsystem design solutions, and compare the resulting parameters with budgeted values.

Fig. 8: Interaction between structural elements of Ship Design System based on Criteria Coordination Method

The information is then fed back to the Synthesis Design Model, as design integrator for the next process iteration. The various subsystem design processes will be guided by the coordination factors to optimal solutions from the Global System perspective, but there will likely be design inconsistencies created between the various subsystem designs. These inconsistencies will need to be resolved when the subsystem designs are returned to the synthesis design level. These inconsistencies may not be difficult to resolve, but they constitute general convergence problem of decomposed system. Here we are not going in details, which require consideration of various example cases. In general the convergence of decomposed solutions at different levels of hierarchy to the hypothetical solutions of non decomposed system (which is impractical even in view of any HPC capabilities) relates to the question of stability of Lagrange multiplies and has theoretical solutions in Theory of Games and Theory of Large Systems. Our analysis of assumptions at which such convergence could be proved mathematically showed that these assumptions in general do not contradict the mathematical nature of early stage of design relationships, some of which were mentioned in previous Cost-Efficiency analysis section. Practical, full automation of the coordination process is difficult and not necessary. As was explained earlier one of the important functions of the System Monitor is enabling calculation of Coordination factors in upper-level and particular at Synthesis-level optimization task in the course of DOE studies, where the impact and influence of different constrains and parameters are investigated. One of the important goals of the System Monitor is to maintain convergence of Design Process through coordination strategies.

Fig. 9: A simplified scheme of MLHS

It can be concluded that the goal of the MLHS approach in Collaborative Concept Formulation process is to ensure through reverse links and coordination factors such collaboration between the levels of the system that customers will formulate “Reasonable” requirements based on their understanding of the implications of these requirements on system overall criteria and on Cost-Efficiency relationships first of all. Thus, MLHS major goal is to assure that all decisions indeed are made in full awareness of the consequences to design subsystems and ship concept system as a whole.

8. Application of MLHS to the Collaborative Concept Formulation Process

A three level hierarchy will be used. The upper level of the hierarchy must support design and analysis from the overall force architecture perspective addressing both the operation of the total force, as well as, the characteristics and performance of the various systems that may be deployed with and supporting the force. At the lowest level of the hierarchy are processes generally associated with specific engineering disciplines and subsystems that support individual design and analysis activities required as part of an overall system design process. The mid level of the hierarchy is made up of multidisciplinary processes supporting the overall design and analysis of a specific system. The authors’ background and experience are primarily in ship design; therefore the primary focus of this section will be on the ship design process and the associated tool set. However, the general approach described here and in the previous Sections can be applied to the design of any type of system.

The context and objectives of the design processes performed at each level of the hierarchy, while consistent within the level, vary significantly between the levels. At the lowest level of the hierarchy, the objectives of these processes are to provide the most accurate design or analysis possible with a minimum of uncertainty. At the upper level of the hierarchy, the immense complexity of interactions between the many systems and operational scenarios to be considered, drive the objective to be the identification of optimal regions of characteristics for the systems and operational scenarios. This requires a comprehensive search of the overall design space combined with an effective process for identifying the optimal regions of the design space. At both ends of the hierarchy, the accuracy of the design process is controlled by the time available and the models available to perform the process.

The lowest level of the hierarchy contains the processes that provide the most accuracy of design and/or analysis. Therefore it is desirable to use the processes and tools available at the lowest level to support the processes performed at the mid and upper levels. Methods for applying the lower level processes and tools in the upper levels of the hierarchy have been demonstrated in a variety of contexts. This section will present guidelines for applying these methods in a manner to insure consistency of application and to allow for the development of a reusable library of process methods and tools to support the entire range of ship design activities. Applying these guidelines will allow the library of available process methods and tools to be extended over time as new operational concepts, system configurations, and technologies are identified.

Fig. 10: Concept Formulation Model Multi Level Hierarchy

The basic approach of this multi-level hierarchy is illustrated in Fig. 10. The context shown is intended to support a set of processes and tools that will help enable the Collaborative, Concept Formulation activities described by *Jons and Wynn (2009)*.

The following sections describe the working approach to the C3F Model. How it is built from up from the complex and accurate processes at the lower level and then how the results derived at the upper level are used to guide further design exploration and refinements at the lower level.

9. Behavior Models

A behavior model is a response surface or other form of surrogate model that represents the “behavior” of a lower level design subsystems and high fidelity discipline calculations in the upper level model in terms of a subset of the upper level design variables. An analysis of the overall objectives of the upper level model is used to identify the behavior models that are needed to support the overall objectives of the model.

In many cases the predictions required for the upper-level Concept Formulation process, are best predicted through the use of high fidelity solvers such as those found at the lower level of the MLHS hierarchy. In reality, the application of high-fidelity solvers typically makes solution of the optimization problem impractical.

Our approach for Concept Formulation process is similar to the practice of developing the Systematic Series of testing models. The way a Taylor series, Series 60 and other series were developed and used can be extrapolated for the Behavior Models, if to use systematic calculations for the series of design variants instead of the series of systematic models tested in the model basins. In case of testing models:

- Systematic series were specially developed to catch the influence of major design parameters (dimension ratios, hydrostatic coefficients)
- Interpolation of testing results was used to predict the behavior of the new designs at the assumption that the impact of most influential design parameters is accounted in model testing
- Use of systematic testing series brings real physics based data at early stages of design
- At later stages of design the difference between actual hull forms and systematic models geometry is evaluated by performing models tests with actual models and by application of sophisticated CFD calculations

All above is valid if we substitute testing models by calculations in the scope of high fidelity models. This idea was called Systematic Calculation Series (SCS) and has been applied in optimization studies of the multihull ship based on Multihull Synthesis Design model, *Hefazi et al. (2008)*. Such SCS were developed for resistance and seakeeping disciplines, which cannot be ignored in upper level synthesis model for medium size multihull in the course of mission oceanic operations.

The idea of using the Behavior Models in Concept Formulation process is to try to derive a model of the models. With this approach, the high-fidelity solver becomes the trainer for the simple analytical expressions, whose coefficients are unknown. This is the rationale of the Response Surface Methodology (RSM). In this method, a Design of Experiment (DOE) technique is applied, and only a few sample points (training points) are computed by using the high-fidelity solver. Starting with these values the approximated analytical expression is used as a Behavior Model in the optimization cycle and the multi-disciplinary optimization problem is solved by using this analytical approximation. Once an optimal point is selected, the high-fidelity model is applied to this configuration, and the quality of the RSM prediction is verified. This new point is added to the training points of the Behavior Model, and a new set of coefficients for the approximated expression of the high-fidelity objective function is now derived: the optimization problem can be solved again with a higher degree of accuracy. This way, the complexity of the optimization problem is reduced.

Behavior Models can be built from the multiple runs of the discipline specific program using polynomial regression, neural networks or kriging. The set of RSM applications in design process is presented in *Gougoulidis, (2008)*. In any case, the cost of this has been moved (and possibly reduced in the process) to the training set generation. The Behavior Models also offer the benefit of reuse. Through the use of the MLHS approach, libraries of Behavior Models can be developed and maintained. A library of Behavior Models which includes the data set they were based on will allow Behavior Models to be reused by other design studies and, if necessary their range extended by the incorporation of additional training points.

The ability to use Behavior Models in Concept Formulation in the framework of a MLHS and/or simultaneously for the Subsystems of the Ship Design Hierarchy will lead to an immediate improvement in continuing Concept Formulation design process.

10. Some Aspects of Application of MLHS Methods

Synthesis design tools that are used to explore the ship design trade space in the concept design phase (ASSET, PASS, and Multihull Synthesis Design Models) have been around for many years and are used widely by industry for monohull ships. While some synthesis tools have been developed for multihull ships, they are not nearly comparable in depth or level of fidelity to the monohull tools. They are used to develop point solutions of ship designs to populate and study the trade space. This process could be substantially enhanced by the application of the MLHS design process. Such design/optimization tools will be a valuable resource that is equally applicable to the design of future commercial or military vessels (dual-use) of monohull and multihull types.

The synthesis design tools at the upper-level of the design hierarchy consists of the definition of ship dimensions, general and payload arrangement, and hull forms and models of estimating weights, area/volumes required, structural characteristics, propulsion and ship service machinery, and other local ship systems such as: outfit, handling systems, etc. Seakeeping, power, and payload are primary functional relationships, which depending on the stage of the design, are computed at various degrees of fidelity and are integrated in the overall MLHS approach.

The MLHS notes feasible vs. infeasible design solutions based on assumed displacement vs. calculated weight; assumed vs. calculated electric load; stability requirements and a variety of internal and external dimensional constraints. The dynamic allocation of volumes and feasibility checks makes this synthesis model particularly well suited to MLHS upper-level models in support of the Concept Formulation process, where thousands of candidate design solutions may be examined.

At present the synthesis models capabilities include:

- The synthesis models can be run in a parametric study mode, and all results (intermediate and final) will be stored in the synthesis design database. This database is easily linked with other Multi-Disciplinary Design and Optimization Tools
- The database capabilities allow for easy expansion in future development of the synthesis models
- The development environment allows an experienced programmer to quickly build a user interface to new capabilities, so that most of the effort of building and enhancing the synthesis models will be related to ship modeling/synthesis algorithms, and not the user interface code and database code.
- The synthesis models can run being integrated with ASSET or as a standalone program with a suite of special purpose programs to be used in collaborative design and optimization studies.

The entire process is “managed” by System Monitor, which is at present time is based on commercially available software, such as Model Center or iSIGHT.

This MDO method to-date has been applied to several high-speed sealift ship concepts, *Hefazi et al.*

(2008), such as the basic Army and US Marine Corps requirements for the Joint High Speed Sealift Ship, and a notional sealift design based on the publicly available requirements for the joint high speed vessel (JHSV), where multi-objective optimization and parametric analysis of mission requirements were necessary. Each requirement has its distinct design space and constraints which are generally derived from the mission profile. The application of the synthesis level Concept Formulation tool, in the context of MLHS, consists of:

- Definition of the design space, constraints and measure(s) of efficiency
- Running the Systems Monitor to search the multi-dimensional design space using single or multi-objective optimization algorithms
- Construction and analysis of feasible and Pareto optimum solution sets
- Subsystem requirement definition and construction of coordination strategies corresponding to optimum measure(s) of efficiency

10. Conclusion

The Multi-Level Hierarchical System methodology provides a rational framework for structuring and utilizing available design tools throughout all phases of the ship design process. The methodology facilitates the use of high-fidelity design and analysis tools during early stage design and complex optimization processes through the application of Behavior Models. The methodology also provides a mechanism for the coordination of later stage subsystem or discipline specific design activities with an optimum design range identified through the exploration of multiple mission operating scenarios and ship design variants, while allowing and promoting flexibilities in the later stage subsystem / discipline specific design activities.

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Hull Maintenance Based on a 3D Model

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Abstract

Ship managers continuously monitor the vessels' structural condition in order to detect deficiencies in the hull structure early and to initiate maintenance actions if required. Typically, this monitoring is done through periodic visual inspections by dedicated crew members. Documentation of such inspections is in most cases based on textual description of any detected defects and of the location of photos taken in the tanks and cargo holds. This paper shows how the planning, preparing, executing, reporting and assessing of visual inspections of the hull structure can be supported by a 3D model of the respective vessel. The Hull Condition Data is thereby stored in a lifecycle database holding also the thickness measurement data captured during class renewal.

1. Introduction

Three-dimensional models of ships are today used in the design phase for basic design, production planning and for simulations such as intact stability, strength, or seakeeping analysis. In the operation phase of the vessel such models do not yet play a significant role. On the other hand, crew, superintendents, classification societies, cargo owners and others gather information about the condition of the ship's hull through periodic inspections. Thickness measurements in particular are used to assess the residual strength of plates, stiffeners and the hull girder. Today, typically neither measurement data nor visual inspection information is attached to a simulation model of the ship. Moreover, such data is not assembled to obtain a life cycle model of the ship. Consequently, it is hard to e.g. perform any of the following tasks

- to assess the residual strength through direct simulation,
- to evaluate trends in e.g. the severity of corrosion or the extent of coating breakdown in a particular tank,
- to compare corrosion in the same tank of sister vessels or
- to combine thickness measurement results and visual inspection information into a comprehensive assessment.

Even if simulation models for strength analysis exist from the design phase, these are not employed to arrive at a more detailed assessment of residual strength or remaining fatigue life. A major step to better exploit measurements and observations during operation phase is to associate all observed data to a product lifecycle model of the ship hull, see e.g. *Hamada et al. (2002)*, *Cabos et al. (2009)*. In particular, such a life cycle model must be capable to associate any inspection findings to its actual location in the ship.

This paper describes a procedure and associated software to obtain hull condition data attached to a 3D model through tools directly supporting the inspection process. Thereby, the inspection and assessment process is made more efficient, data quality increases and assessment can directly make use of the captured information.

2. Approach

Observations and measurements taken during inspections of the hull structure are today typically recorded on paper or possibly in electronic documents. This is done through tables or spreadsheets for thickness measurements or owner specific forms for visual inspections, such as tank or cargo hold inspections.

This procedure can be regarded as adequate, if only local assessments of the inspection results are requested. Examples are

- the assessment of a thickness measurement using criteria for the maximal diminution of the particular plate,
- assessment of the coating condition of one bulkhead in a tank to decide on its necessary coating repair,

In case the relation between different inspection results needs to be exploited, additional benefit can be drawn from the acquired data, thereby offering the chance to make ships safer based on the same number of observations. Examples are

- evaluation of the residual hull girder section modulus for assessment of the actual stress distribution,
- using observations (e.g. detected crack indications) on one ship to initiate inspection of the same structural part on the sister ships, and
- evaluation of changes in coating condition of a bulkhead over time in order to decide on the optimal schedule for coating renewal.

Such interrelations between inspection data, namely temporal, spatial, system, and fleet dependencies can only be exploited if these results

- are stored in a data management system which is capable of managing these relations and
- efficient means of the recording inspection results as data (and not only as text) are provided to inspectors.

In case the inspection process is performed in the traditional way (i.e. based on documents), capturing such interrelations typically cause significant additional effort. For example, thickness measurements taken onboard by the thickness measurement company need to be interpreted later in the office based on tables and sketches to find out their actual location and to transfer them to a model of the ship. It is therefore essential to find an easy-to-use and robust way to allow those members of staff who are in charge of the inspections today to record not only observations and measurements but also their locations. This data must then be stored in a way which allows interpretation in terms of trends or influence on the structural or mechanical systems. As a result, there is a clear need for tools making use of 3D models for inspection support. Data on measurements and observations should be held in an appropriate data management system instead of in documents. Moreover, data from different inspections and measurements should be integrated into a single database. For hull structures this refers to

- visual inspections of the hull structure, i.e. tanks, cargo holds, void spaces, ... which are performed by crew, superintendents, class surveyors and others,
- thickness measurements, and
- hull response measurements (stresses, accelerations, ...)

Furthermore, interpretation of such data is brought forward through analysis of environmental conditions such as cargo history, wave loads, temperature, humidity, and chemical composition of cargo.

Through Hull Lifecycle Programme (HLP) and its associated tools GL HullManager and GL Pegasus, Fig. 1, Germanischer Lloyd is following this track of data integration and process support through

- enabling inspectors to input information directly and through
- storing inspection data (not only documents) with its temporal and system context, in particular its actual location in the ship

This provides the basis for a comprehensive lifecycle management of the ship hull.

Fig. 1: Current and future data integrated in the HLP database and connected tools

Previous publications have concentrated on the support of the thickness measurement process using GL Pegasus, e.g. *Jaramillo et al. (2006)*. In this paper the focus is on the support for visual hull inspections.

3. Tool support for visual hull inspections

For seagoing vessels, regular periodic surveys by classification societies are mandatory to ensure that their technical condition is in accordance to required standards and that the vessels remain seaworthy. These surveys may include, for example, a large number of thickness measurements of the ship hull that are taken and evaluated in regular intervals.

In addition, ship managers continuously monitor the vessels' structural condition in order to detect deficiencies in the hull structure early and to initiate maintenance actions if required. Typically, this monitoring is done through periodic visual inspections by dedicated crew members. Main compartments, zones and structural members are inspected. All inspections are executed periodically, according to a prescribed schedule. Findings detected during an inspection are recorded and followed-up if required.

GL HullManager is a software package that has been developed to support planning, preparing, executing, reporting and assessing visual inspections of the hull structure of a vessel. It is based on a life cycle model of the ship including a 3D geometric representation of the particular vessel. The 3D model contains information about all plates, stiffeners and compartments and is the same model as used for thickness measurements with the software GL Pegasus. The data model for the definition of plates and stiffeners follows the Hull Condition Model (HCM), an open standard for the exchange of hull condition data based on results of the EC research project CAS, *Cabos et al. (2008)*.

GL HullManager consists of an onboard component installed on each vessel and one or more onshore components. The onboard databases are synchronized periodically with the onshore database, Fig. 2. While email is used as standard way of synchronisation, large data volumes like photos are typically exchanged by CD-ROM.

The hull maintenance activities supported by GL HullManager are now described in more detail, Fig. 3. Planning of hull inspections starts by creating an inspection strategy for each vessel describing scope and frequency, i.e. what has to be inspected and how often. This is done by fixing the frequency of inspections for each hull object, whether compartment, tank, deck, or hatch cover. The frequency differs by compartment type and depends on various factors. In general, all hull objects of a type have the same inspection frequency. However, exceptions can be defined if necessary and applicable. Furthermore, criteria are defined describing the scope of an inspection. This includes, for example,

corrosion, coating, deformation, cracks, but also the condition of anodes as well as cleanliness. Again, criteria can apply to all objects of a type as well as to an individual one. From the strategy a schedule of inspections is derived. This schedule is used to determine hull objects that are due or overdue for inspection.

Fig. 2: Onboard and onshore tasks and synchronization in GL HullManager

Fig. 3: Workflow in GL HullManager

If an object is selected for inspection, preparation takes place in the following way. The status of previous inspections including ratings and deficiencies is displayed in order to recall suspect areas. Furthermore an inspection form can be printed including graphical views of individual components like walls.

The actual inspection, e.g. in a tank, is performed using the generated paper form. Notes are taken as well as graphical annotations are taken on paper. Later, back the deck's office; results are copied from the forms into the software. This includes assigning structural ratings for, e.g., coating and corrosion status. Ratings are recorded into tables using a 3 level approach. Additionally, individual failures can be recorded and associated to a specific location in the 3D model. In this way, failures can be described unambiguously and photos can be attached to the point, where they have been taken. In addition to inspections of the structural elements, GL HullManager can be configured to support inspection of outfitting items such as ladders, pipes, closing appliances, handrails, fittings, etc. as long as they are localized through a compartment or structural member.

Fig. 4: Graphical markup and photos added to the 3D model of a vessel

After the captain's approval, the inspection results are transferred to the shore database. Onshore, the structural condition of a vessel can be assessed superintendents based on the specific 3D annotation of the failures detected on board. Thereby, GL HullManager helps ship operators to systematically ensure and document the structural integrity of their ships. Reporting functionality ensures improved communication with repair yards using sketches of the areas to repair. Through centrally storing the hull maintenance information onshore, the comparison between the hull statuses of different vessels becomes possible for the fleet manager.

Fig. 5: Ballast tank of a cape size ore carrier, colored by corrosion status

If during closer assessment, the need for a maintenance action is identified, a follow up action is created for the respective hull object. Such an action includes a priority, responsible person, and an optional due date. Within a maintenance action a number of related failures can be referenced.

4. Tool support for thickness measurements

Traditionally, thickness measurements are documented in the form of tables and graphical sketches whereas visual inspections are reported by textual descriptions and photos. For large ships, it is then difficult to obtain a fast overview about the actual status of the hull: where exactly did the chief mate

detect an indication of a crack? Which are the plates in the double bottom where the maximal thickness diminution is exceeded? Which influence does the detected corrosion have on the resulting longitudinal strength at the particular frame? All of these questions would be much easier to answer, if the actual location of inspection findings would be associated with a graphical representation of the vessel. Then, results would be easy to visualize and to transfer to simulation models for strength assessment.

By developing GL Pegasus, the thickness measurement process could significantly be improved in recent years. Experience has shown that the use of a 3D model of the ship can lead to both shorter preparation and reporting times for thickness measurement companies. Once such a model has been prepared, it seems on the other hand evident that it could also be used e.g. for tank inspections performed by crew.

Fig. 6: Example for planning and assessment of thickness measurements (simulation using random thickness values).

GL Pegasus and GL HullManager are part of a long term development roadmap which aims at integrating all information associated with the condition of the hull structure within one lifecycle database.

4. Data exchange from design to operation

A specific XML schema (HCM) forms the basis of the import interfaces of GL Pegasus and GL HullManager. It mainly contains the outer contours of the plates and the profiles as well as their grouping into structural members and compartments.

On the other side, the CAD system manufacturer AVEVA has also defined a set of XML schemas for the export of the steel structure data from their Tribon and AVEVA Marine products. They enable the exchange of structural members (plates and profiles) and their associated parameters on the same level of detail as in the steel plans. Thereby, those parts of the CAD model relevant to the lifecycle management can be exchanged without passing on information relevant to production.

In a trial project with the construction company Neptun - Stahlkonstruktions GmbH, Rostock, an XML file of a multi purpose vessel for Reederei Buss has successfully been exported by Neptun with the aid of the XML export interface of Tribon M3 Basic Design, Fig. 7. This file was then transformed into an HCM file by Germanischer Lloyd and finally used to initialize a 3D model for HLP within GL Pegasus, Fig. 8.

Fig. 7: Model of a multi purpose vessel as viewed within Tribon M3 Basic Design. Model courtesy of Neptun Stahlkonstruktions GmbH and Reederei Buss

Fig. 8: Model of a multipurpose vessel shown in GL Pegasus. The model was converted from Tribon M3 to the HCM format. Data courtesy of Neptun Stahlkonstruktion, Rostock and Reederei Buss.

For the successful utilisation of GL HullManager the compartment information, in addition to the steel structure, must also be exchanged. This data is not yet transferred via the Tribon XML export interface; it will be covered by future versions of the interface in the AVEVA Marine product line.

5. Hull inspection as a part of Ship Lifecycle Management

Efficient service and maintenance should take advantage of digital data management as deployed in the context of Lifecycle Management (LCM). Based on the dictum a ship is not a swimming truck but a swimming plant the term 'Ship Lifecycle Management' (SLCM) can be seen as a synonym for a ship specific Plant Lifecycle Management solution encompassing the compilation and management of all data accumulated during a ship's lifecycle, from design through operation until scrapping of the vessel.

The particular focus in this paper is on the data required for efficient servicing and maintenance of the ship hull. Ship Lifecycle Management also enables integration of individual software solutions which are relevant in this context. With this understanding of 'lifecycle management' there are substantial overlaps to well established terms within the industry, such as Product Data Management (PDM) or Product Lifecycle Management (PLM).

Product Data Management is a concept for the collection and management of data and documents that arise from product development and define the product. A part of these data can be made available to the downstream phase of the product lifecycle. The prerequisite for this is an integrated product model. Product Data Management is an integral part of Product Lifecycle Management which on the other hand also integrates the business management aspects of Enterprise Resource Planning (capital, production resources and staff). Plant Lifecycle Management differs from Product lifecycle management, by focusing on integration of configuration data, physical and technical data describing the parts of the plant model. The phases of a plant lifecycle are:

- Design,
- Construction,
- Erection,
- Commissioning,
- Operation, and
- Maintenance.

Ship Lifecycle Management

The servicing and maintenance of the vessel and its technical systems and components should therefore ensure that their operational ability can be maintained over the long term or, in the event of a failure, can be re-established quickly. The German standard DIN 31051 (*DIN 31051:2003-06*) sets out the basic service and maintenance measures in the following way:

- Inspection and monitoring of condition
- Maintenance
- Repair and overhaul
- Upgrading

For a ship, not only the systems and components are subject to scrutiny in this process but also the steel structure of the ship itself. During the lifetime of a ship the manufacturer is the service provider in regard to the maintenance schedule for systems and components, the maintenance management of the ship hull is typically not in the focus of the building yard. For a component, the maintenance instructions specified by the manufacturer include

- What has to be inspected?
- How often and when are specific maintenance procedures to be carried out?
- What is to be considered in case of a repair?

Inspection schedule and routines for the ship hull are mainly set up by IMO (see e.g. *IMO A.744*), administrative bodies, classification societies and the ship manager. In particular, inspection documentation is required by the cargo owners, e.g. through TMSA (*Oil Companies International Marine Forum*). Newbuilding shipyards are typically not involved in the maintenance procedures of the hull, and repair yards only act as a service provider in case of specific repair, overhaul or upgrading requests.

This results in the following requirements for an SLCM data model:

- use data from design, construction and erection to initialize data model
- multiple views of the ship and its systems and components (plant structure)
- multiple relationships between the plant structure elements
- globally unique identifier
- differentiation between part, component and system description
- hierarchical typing of plant structure elements (super- and subtypes)
- differentiation between inherent and process-specific attributes and parameters:
 - o inherent: manufacturer, serial number, installation data etc.
 - o process-specific: nominal power, operation hours, calculation data, operational data,

- measurement data etc.
- time limited validity of data

The GL SLCM is able to store the entire description of ship. This includes technical parameters, calculation values, schedules and many others. This flexible data model is able to deal with manifold and permanently changing information. If a user searches for specific inspection result of the engine room, it is no longer necessary to look for it in large list-based paper documents.

Inspection data of the hull or other systems is now also linked to the ship data. Therefore, it is possible to identify the findings on board a specific ship or to find all ships, where a particular problem has occurred. Because all data is held in a central database, it will become possible to cross-check information between different ships. Furthermore, changes are tracked by the system so that previous versions of the data of a ship can be recovered. The resulting model is shown in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9: Plant Structure Model

The master entity in this model is *Project*. It contains the general plant data like owner, manufacturer, year built etc. Potential sub-types are Ship (*Base Ship*), Lock, Offshore Plant, Wind Turbine etc. The

Project Part Instances is a relationship to all Equipment and Components (*Part Instance*) which are installed in this plant (*Project*). *Installed Systems* is the same for all installed machinery, electrical or piping systems (*System*). *Structural Systems* connects *Project* with defined superstructures of the supporting structure (*Structural System*) and *Locations* is a relationship to all defined zones or compartments (*Location*) in this plant.

Fig. 10: Hull Inspection Model as a part of the General Inspection Model

The relationship *Inspections* is the link between *Project* and all inspections which have been carried out to parts, single components, machinery, electrical or piping systems or at the supporting structures of this plant. *Monitoring Activities* is a relationship to all condition monitoring activities of technical objects in this plant.

Because the particular focus in this paper is on the data required for efficient inspection a detailed view on the inspection part of the SLCM is shown in Fig. 10. In the model context entity *Inspection* covers scheduled and unscheduled activities to collect the condition data for the maintenance process.

In this model the hull inspection is part of a more general solution. It is on the same level as Thickness Measurement, Machinery Inspection or Hazardous Material Inspection.

6. Hull condition model

In ship lifecycle process a simplified 3D model of steel structure is necessary. Such three-dimensional models are typically built-up in the hull detailed design and production preparation phases. Moreover detailed outfitting information is created. The amount of information available from design by far exceeds what is needed in the ship's lifecycle. Nevertheless ship owners can benefit significantly from such data, even if only a small subset of it is passed over from the design phase.

Fig. 11: Hull Structure Model

The starting point of the development of such a model should be the partial results of the standardization activities for the exchange of product model data (STEP) described in *Part 42 - Geometric and topological representation* (see *ISO 10303-42:1994*) and *AP 218 – Ship Structures* (see *ISO 10303-218:2004*). Both contain a substantial description of data structures but it is too large to implement it completely. For the practical use it is necessary to identify a suitable subset of them. The draft model shown in Fig. 11.

A Structural System is a part of the hull structure and may be one of the following:

- a built girder
- a corrugated structure or
- a plane or curved panel system.

It is an assembly structure and contains a set of plates and stiffeners (*Structural Parts*) and special attributes like name, type, description etc. The structural system and also the structural parts have their own geometrical description (*Shape Representation*) and can be located in particular (*Located Structural System/Located Structural Part*). The shape representation is a small subset of the Part 42 geometrical entities like *Curve*, *B-Spline Curve* and *Cartesian Point* and topological like *Edges* and *Vertexes* and their relationships like *Point Reference* or *Edge Curve Reference*.

7. Conclusions

Planned Maintenance Systems typically used onboard require only a limited amount of data for each component including identifiers, dates and textual job descriptions. For condition based maintenance of components more technical data need to be managed. In particular the changes of conditions over time need to be captured and evaluated systematically. Because of the large volume of data a software solution is necessary.

Maintenance of the hull structure can benefit significantly from the additional possibility to attach data, such as e.g. findings during inspections, to a 3D model of the actual hull structure. Thereby, onboard use of a tool for inspection reporting makes sure, that all acquired information is actually stored. Apart from allowing superintendents to locate the detected deficiencies, a systematic assessment becomes possible. Currently, GL HullManager is a specific software module to support visual crew inspections of the hull structure as the basis for condition based maintenance.

Through Hull Lifecycle Programme (HLP) and its associated software modules GL HullManager and GL Pegasus, a new ship lifecycle management methodology is introduced employing a 3D model of the ship to directly support hull inspections and their assessment. Today the 3D model is typically built up from the steel drawings passed to the owner by the yard.

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Requirements of a Common Data Model for Total Ship Lifecycle Data Management

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Abstract

This paper examines the requirements of the data model needed for total ship lifecycle data management, looking first at the four key phases of data creation and consumption in the ship lifecycle, suggesting ways to solve the challenges posed by these phases of collaboration. The paper looks at the management of documents in the change sensitive initial definition of the ship. This begins with the owner and the negotiation of the specification and general arrangement. It continues through the handover of supplier data and documentation to the yard and the reuse of this information down-stream in the operations of the ship. It includes the exchange of data with class societies for approval, and the management of their feedback, and the IP sensitive handover of data to ship owners for operations and maintenance purposes (including the use of hull condition monitoring). A closer look at some possible solutions to the problems will be presented, for example how AVEVA NET, XML standards and web services are being used to provide a standard way to collect suppliers' information and integrate it in the engineering modeling work of the yard. The paper will also explain how standards originally developed for the defense industry can benefit the management of change challenge in the contract specifications phase, and how data mining and post processing of the 3D model can provide a short cut to creating an Operations data model without sacrificing the Intellectual Property of the design office that created it. Finally the paper will explain how the adoption of WEB2.0 and social networking could provide a seamless team collaboration layer over the digital ship asset.

1. Introduction

In the marine business chain the introduction of the computer made its greatest impact primarily on shipbuilders whose design and production offices could make massive man-hour savings by the implementation of the earliest CAD CAM systems, which at that time were not much more than electronic drawing boards. Shipbuilders and design offices have continued this trend and in the complete chain of Ship Owners, Equipment suppliers, Design offices and Class societies are still the heaviest users of computers and software. Their offices now define highly detailed 3D models (Fig.1) of the ships they will build, allowing them to automatically produce production instructions for robots and automated production lines, and detailed work instructions for the ever more globally distributed work force that build and operate ships.

Till now this digital ship model has remained the Intellectual property of the design offices that produce them, their value being derived mostly from the deliverables that are more easily produced on the basis of this model. However as the other players in the ship lifecycle make more and more use of IT, the flow of data through the ship lifecycle become more and more important.

As the suppliers move off 2D Cad systems to powerful 3D mechanical CAD systems, Class societies move towards Computer Aided approval and away from paper drawings, and owners implement more and more digital asset management solutions , the need to stream line data entry and management of changes become ever more critical to the success of these business strategies.

2. The key business processes of data creation and consumption

For simplification purposes the ship lifecycle has been divided into five major phases. These phases, although distinct, are often highly concurrent.

Fig. 1: CAD model of engine room (Courtesy of Viktor Lenac)

2.1. Initial definition of the ship

During the initial definition of a vessel the critical data to be managed is in the form of electronic documents, such as lists of items in spreadsheets, word documents, emails and sometimes Faxes, where the key communication of contract & technical specifications are made. This information is highly change sensitive as the impact of any change made at this stage is at a maximum. In addition to change control the documents at this stage must be shared with the relevant parties but in a very secure way.

Today most organizations manage this data, via emails and a windows directory, often with an intelligent index, of sorts be it a Microsoft ACCESS database, or an EXCEL sheet with links. This method offers many improvement over the more traditional method of managing fax documents and signed paper documents such as , reduction in printing and faxing costs, transfer speeds and having an electronic audit trail of sorts, however the continuous emailing of evolving documents can result in many versions of documents existing as attachments on the email server, and as most email systems do not handle work flows or offer much in the way of control at an enterprise level, there is very little transparency on who has received and sent what and to whom.

Another problem experienced at this stage of the ship definition is the lack of granularity of documents. When specifications are captured in text form, a change to a very small number of characters can have a huge impact on final engineering man-hours and costs. Even if that document which contains the change is managed well in terms of revisions and comments explaining the changes the new text can still be overlooked when being used as the master source of data for many engineers working in parallel on these key documents. This is especially so when there are several changes to a document at one time, captured in a single revision.

An example of this would be changing the lifting capacity of a deck crane in one section of a document and the operating conditions of a pump in another section of the document. Even though these changes would be captured in email content and the comments on the revision block of a document itself, they can easily be over looked, resulting in huge changes needing to be made to the engineering too late in the ship design lifecycle.

Requirements management or system engineering systems are sometimes used, especially in Naval projects to manage these challenges. However they are highly specialized and often inappropriate for the management of the several key documents in the initial definition of a merchant vessel.

Data re-use is a key issue at this stage, ideally a data management system would allow a project engineer to access and analyze previous ship data, with the ultimate aim to take the relevant data, be it specifications, system diagrams drawings or even whole portions of a design model and reuse it as the basis for a new vessel.

Key Data Management Requirements at this stage include:

- Secure , but worldwide accessible collaborative environment for documents
- Master repository of documents, with back up etc
- Ability to view, and control documents of all formats without additional software
- Markup of documents in a collaborative environment
- Change control of documents, preferably at a granularity higher than one document, i.e. per section of a document.
- Automatic definition of an audit trail
- Secure sharing of documents

2.2 Engineering and Procurement of Major Equipment

The data and documentation from suppliers of major equipment has always been a hot topic in the lifecycle of a ship. Design offices need documents and drawings early, so that they can complete engineering work, whilst it is usually the legal obligation of the design office/shipyard to gather the documents together for handover to the ship's owner, where ship operatives such as marine engineers and superintendents, need maintenance and overhaul documents constantly kept up-to-date for safety critical reasons.

In the very early stages of ship definition, engineers and procurement personnel would invest huge amounts of time and effort to find documentation and drawings to allow the design and coordination of the machinery spaces to be started as early as possible. In the days of paper documentation this was more often than not based on historical data, such as data sheets and drawings stored in filing cabinets and shelving in the design office. This lack of data often resulted in sub optimum equipment use, simply for the reason that the design offices were not aware of a better alternative or did not have the up-to-date documents, or even the time to conduct an extensive search for suppliers and equipment.

This topic has been the subject of commercial endeavours to improve the process, most representing an online database of Shipbuilding materials and equipments, offering many thousands of components for download via an advanced technical search engine, Fig.2. These web databases were outdated by the time they were implemented, mostly due to suppliers quickly taking on the challenge of creating and maintaining their own websites and thus technical knowhow. Their presence however did accelerate marine equipments suppliers progress towards electronic documentation, and provided an example standard for the marine industry to exchange data, both commercial and technical.

Today equipment suppliers readily offer electronic data, sheets, 2D drawings and increasingly 3D CAD models, meaning engineers can now request documentation via email and receive the latest drawings, data sheets and other technical documentation in a few hours.

Unfortunately electronic documentation suffers many of the disadvantages of its paper predecessors, such as being out of data as soon as committed to an electronic file, encapsulating data on one single entity, therefore making it difficult to track changes to sub sections or chapters within documents. It also offers new challenges such as the inability to view all documentation with one unified method, i.e. many formats means many reader programs required to view the data.

Fig. 2: Example of a web based equipment portal, capturing the key attributes of an equipment

New electronic standard such as Adobe's PDF have gone a long way to solve these problems, including rich functionality such as document security, and now even the ability to view 3D CAD models, Fig.3.

Fig.3: Example of an equipment data package in Adobe's 3D PDF format. Example many thanks to Archnav (www.archnav.de) and Davit International.

However the industry has still not made much progress regarding a standard way to communicate the various attributes and commercial data associated with an equipment purchase or engineering negotiation.

This has a knock on effect when considering data management, for example many larger design offices will maintain a technical library to aid in the equipment selection process and procurement departments maintain records of suppliers, to analyse their performance. As there is no standard way to share technical and commercial data, these two databases must be manually created and maintained converting the assortment of data formats into one that can be searched and analysed. Another enabling factor to this process will be the use of UUID (Universally Unique Identifier) meaning each installed item of equipment would have a UUID and if shared correctly would allow all suppliers to know where their equipment is installed.

With a standard way to communicate and UUID's, the amount of data re-entry could be minimised, allowing the suppliers to take direct responsibility for their data, and working with a push principal to automatically update the databases of the shipyard for each project.

Fig.4: Example of the documents generated during the Equipment procurement and Commissioning process, courtesy of Hatlapa and Germanischer Lloyd

Key Data Management Requirements at this stage include:

- Open and adaptable to the needs of equipment suppliers, that range from huge globally corporations to small family operations.
- It must be able to handle a variety of formats, for both change control purposes and viewing and mark up.
- It must have a flexibility to allow data conversion from one format to another , but also being adaptable to standards that grow and adapt in time.
- Must handle a variety of CAD formats
- Must offer secure sharing fo documents
- Ability to view, and control documents of all formats, including paper
- Automatic definition of an audit trail
- Allow the definition of a document work flow, to ensure the relevant documents are received and sent at key points in the process
- Allow Secure sharing of documents

2.3 Exchange of data with Classification societies

Class Rules have long been available in electronic formats, bringing with it the key advantages of easier updates, reduced management costs, searching and indexing. These documents are subject to

periodical updates, usually managed in house by the classifications document management systems and published to Extra nets for customers. However it is the approval process itself that provides the most challenges regarding management of data for ship. Approvals are required at various levels across the engineering domain of shipbuilding, at the level of an individual component, at the level of a system design, during installation and construction and during sea trials and operations. At each of these levels, there is a variety of documents and data that needs to be transferred back and forth between the party who needs the approval and the approver.

The main goals of data management in this process are to ensure, all the information required to make the approval is received, up-to-date accurate and reviewed. The resulting feedback must then be processed and tracked to ensure that each and every comment from the approval body is acted upon and traceable.

In order to reduce manual input, the data mode that should handle these documents must be able to understand the multi dimensional nature of engineering documents. For example that s Pump can exist as a single component, which will have a specification, and its own engineering documentation, it won approval certificate. Yet that same pump can exist as an element of a system, and therefore be found on a P&ID or electrical diagram (considering the electrical motor as an integrated part of the pump) and in the same way that pump will be installed an commissioned and maintained, each lifecycle phase generating its own documentation and approval requirements. From this example it is easy to imagine that a data model must be able to recognise a master object of sorts and the various type of associations it can have to engineering documents, drawings, and logical groupings.

Moreover a data model should be designed to minimize the amount of data re entry in the execution of the approval process. Meaning that product structures, and attributes originally entered in the supplier side would be recognised by the shipyard and class and easily transferred

Once more the concept of UUID could be widely used here, allowing any individual item of equipment, or even plate of steel, to be identified uniquely across multiple systems and platforms in different enterprises.

Key Data Management Requirements at this stage include:

- A data model able to receive packages of information containing different files and to manage them individual for change.
- The ability to capture, and manage complex data, pertaining to engineering elements at differing granularities, i.e. individual items, whole systems, work packages, and so on
- The ability to understand the engineering intent of documents, i.e. to extrapolate , system attributes and components form Lists, and Diagrams
- The ability to handle comments and track that the required work is completed to remedy any discrepancies from the approval.

2.4 Design and Production documentation, and instructions

The digital ship model as mentioned in the introduction represents a huge investment in man hours. Its main purpose is to serve as a record of the design intent and this is the basis for the creation of production instructions and documentation. The more accurate and detailed this model the better the deliverables that can be derived from it.

The digital ship model initially needs to capture engineering intent in the form of lists of key components or as system specifications. At this stage the conceptual Equipments, Panels and systems are created purely on the basis of lists, diagrams and a general arrangement, meaning the data model needs to understand the content of these document types and be able to extrapolate the key engineering data from them. It goes without saying that these documents are generated in a variety of formats and therefore the data model must allow the reading –in of various formats.

When design offices begin creating diagrams and drawings there is a high level of concurrent engineering to keep the design cycle short, this suggests that the data model for data management be tightly integrated with the design system. When this is the case designer can continue to work on the creation of diagrams and drawings while in parallel checks can be made on the data for lifecycle management purposes.

The closely integrated data model becomes very important when considering change. When the engineering intent is captured from the various documents that define systems and so on, designers will have more information available to them to aid in decision making. At the most basic level having the original specifications of a system or latest regulations readily available will make the designers work more efficient. In more advanced scenarios, designers would make impact analysis when considering a change, and if all of the impacts are captured in the data model the decision making will be more accurate.

This ability to assess impact of change is vital further on in the engineering process where detailed design models are used to produce manufacturing deliverables, such as robot control data and assembly drawings. More often than not shipbuilding design systems manage the creation of model data but do not consider the many thousands of documents that are generated, from that model.

The lifecycle data management model must in this case understand what deliverables have been generated from what model data, and be able to trace where they have been sent, be that to a person or a machine for processing.

Due to the highly concurrent way of working and the huge number of changes taking place at any one time it is very difficult to get an overview of what is going on in the design process. This is most evident when walking around a design office, where there is an almost constant stream of phone calls between departments to gain information about why something was or wasn't done, or where something is. The data model not only needs to capture the network of information created during the ship design and build process but also needs to facilitate better communication on the basis of this information.

Key Data Management Requirements at this stage include:

- A data model able to extrapolate engineering intent from lists, diagrams, and other electronic documentation.
- Close integration with Design systems
- Ability to analyze impacts of change
- Change management
- Ability to have an overview of the data creation and consumption as a basis for improved communications within the design office.

2.5 Handover and operation

As mentioned in section 2.2, design offices and shipyards are legally committed to handover the certain documentation pertaining to a new vessel, to its owner. This documentation is a combination of drawings and lists generated during the design and construction of the vessel, for example the general arrangement, the fire escape plan, the system diagrams and so on, and documentation relating to the equipment supplied by external suppliers usually specialist equipment items such as engines, pumps, separators, electronic devices etc.

Traditionally this handover consists of a very large pile of drawings and papers, which takes significant effort on the part of the design office to collate and produce. Moreover once onboard the new vessel it requires more effort yet again to maintain and manage, the effort all the more challenging considering the vessel will be at sea where physical mailing services do not exist and email and internet services are still prohibitively expensive.

Recent moves by suppliers toward electronic documentation have been slow to adopt by owners, often as having paper copies is a legal requirement. However the advantages of having searchable documents and even drawings is begin to outweigh the reliability of a paper hard copy. Recently a new standard for ship documentation has been established, SHIPDEX is a sub set of the Aerospace and defence standard S1000D, and it works in principal by deconstructing electronic documents into data modules, which due to their higher granularity offer a higher degree of change management, and configurability. Clearly any data model to handle the complete lifecycle data management requirements must be able to work with this standard, particularly in the early phases of its adoption where not all data from suppliers will be available in this format.

As the information a ship operator needs are generated and consumed through the ships lifecycle from conception to construction and delivery there is today a high level of inefficiency in the creation of this information. It will often be created by the supplier only to be recreated in one of the design offices systems, and more often than not re created once more for onboard system, for example planned maintenance. This increases the chance for human error and almost certainly destroys any traceability of data from its original source.

The obvious solution to this is to manage and maintain one master project repository during the engineering and construction of the ship, and to handover a filtered version of this to the owners.

However this concept poses several challenges; the Intellectual property ownership of the model data, that need to add operation specific attributes to the original Engineering data and integration with external systems focused on, for example, asset management and other operational activities.

Key Data Management Requirements at this stage include:

- A data model able to build on engineering intent and capture as built data, with its own unique characteristics, but retaining a link to the as designed data.
- A data model which can support the industry standard such as SHIPDEX as well as data coming from un-standardized sources.
- The concepts required to avoid data re entry by enabling reuse of date without compromising the IP of design offices.
- UUID implementation

3 Technical solutions

The following sections summarize some of the technical solutions and concepts that can be implemented to manage data for the total lifecycle of a vessel.

3.1 The basic Platform

As we can see from the above analysis there are several key themes to the requirements for a common data model for total ship lifecycle management.

Shipbuilding today is a very global business, with major suppliers, ship owners, yards and design offices being widely spread around the world. Therefore any platform to manage data in a ships lifecycle must be globally accessible. We have also seen how the basic unit of shipbuilding lifecycle data is the document, which although the culprit form may data management challenges, is widely accepted and highly versatile in terms of the type of content and data it can contain, be that in the form of a drawing, diagram, data sheet, list etc. Therefore we can assume the platform for complete ship lifecycle management must contain these two basic elements.

One example of such a platform is Microsoft's, Windows SharePoint services (WSS) a web based document and content management system which is available free as part of any Windows server implementation.

Fig. 5: Ship documentation as managed by Share Point as a part of an AVEVA NET implementation

With the SharePoint platform alone, electronic documents can be uploaded to a web accessible portal where parties can view them and work on them if they have the required access rights and authoring applications.

As SharePoint evolves, its feature set has grown to include aspects of social computing such as the knowledge management enabling Wikis and Blogs. What was a relatively difficult application to customise and work with has become an industry standard for enterprise content management, the latest incarnations including user friendly work flow modellers, improved data models to work with documents and improved enterprise scalability.

The SharePoint platform is the basis of AVEVA NET, a web based lifecycle data management system, which extends the capabilities of Share Point with a data model dedicated to capturing the multidimensional aspect of engineering data and documents, and add solutions modules that support the business processes as stated above.

3.2 A data structure for engineering objects

We have read about the multi- dimensional nature of engineering objects, how one item maybe a single component on order form a supplier but also an integral part of a system, part of a 3D model and on a drawing all at the same time. We have also seen how the meta data associated with any engineering object changes throughout the lifecycle of an object, be it an object in conceptual

engineering stage, or a physical object installed on board a vessel undergoing sea trials, the meta data will change in its nature along the way.

This wide ranging set of requirements demand a flexible data model capable of classifying objects in many dimensions and able to evolve as the maturity of an object progresses.

One such data model is the EIWM (engineering information and workflow model) data model of AVEVA NET. EIWM is an ISO 15926 compliant data model which represents engineering data via a master class and attribute library, also known as the RDL (reference data library) XML template files which capture the technical description of a document, and any data files used as representations i.e. Drawings, Documents, photos, 3D models and so on.

Fig. 6: Example of how the EIWM data model can be used to make multi-dimensional associations

Fig. 7: Example of document that has been automatically associated to an Equipment item.
Courtesy of Hatlapa and GL

Although engineering objects are the focus of AVEVA NET, the EIWM model handles any number of object classes, such as those used to describe logical groupings of items, those used to describe an enterprise such as people and organisations, and other business objects.

This data model is highly flexible, as only the very upper levels of the RDL are fixed by the system. This means an enterprise can customise the classes of objects, the permissible associations and the attribute classes according to their business processes.

It is the association of objects to others that allows AVEVA NET to model the multidimensional nature of engineering data. Allowing for example a Pump to be classified as a Equipment and electrical motor simultaneously, meaning it can be represented in a drawing and a P&ID at the same time, or Identified as 'P-30045' and 'SB-FW Feed Pump' each of the associated object having its own associations in turn.

This data model is enhanced further by the use of datasets, which capture attribute data, for example, the attributes form the original system specification entered by the owner, the detailed technical parameters of the item delivered by an equipment supplier, the purchasing and logistics information form an ERP system, the measurement from a hull condition monitoring survey and so on.

3.3 Getting more out of documents

We have seen above how the EIWM data model can be used to model the multidimensional nature of engineering data. However one key disadvantage of existing data management systems is the effort taken to enter this data in the format required. In the ideal world, universal standards such as Shipdex would exist in all partners in the ship lifecycle and data entry would truly be of the create-once, refine nature.

However the reality is today the parties involved in the definition, construction and operation of a ship work with a multitude of data formats. However fortunately each company responsible for the delivery of data will deliver data in more or less a standard format, be that file type, document, layout or even details like font size. This means that a automated conversion form the supplied format to a homogeneous one for data management can be set up.

Systems like AVEVA NET offer data capture technologies called gateways. Gateways being a combination of software tools preconfigured to scrape or extrapolate engineering intent from a variety of data formats and sources.

One example would be the capture of data from a mechanical CAD system like CATIA. In this case an export of data in STEP and XML would be set up from CATIA, where the 3D geometry and attribute data would be stored respectively. If standardised, a corresponding converter program could be set up, or purchased from a software provider to convert the 3D data to a web viewable format, and in the same way a mapping made of the XML to present the data, and create the engineering objects in a neutral format for further data management.

Another CAD example is extracting data from AutoCAD drawings, which is achieved by scanning the structure of the drawing, for blocks, and distinct attributes recognisable in the AutoCAD file by certain tags, such as 'description' the gateway in this case creates an XML file in the EIWM format capturing the engineering content of the drawing, and associated it with a web viewable svg file created from the original AutoCAD drawing.

Likewise data from a system like SAP or MAXIMO's asset management system could be configured to create transfer files or reports, either in a familiar text format like excel, or in raw XML, which can in turn be converted to a format more suitable for lifecycle data management.

3.4 SOA building blocks

The above examples of how gateways can be configured and developed to capture data from disparate data sources are prime candidates for a Service Orientated Architecture (SOA) approach. Reuse of data conversion code captured in services. In the examples above we have seen a component of the data capture technology of AVEVA NET, however a system like AVEVA NET must not just capture data but also send data back to the source systems for updating or modifications, of course under change control. If the standard tasks can be identified they can be coded into web services and reused in various business processes.

A good example of this would be the Enterprise Integration Adaptor (EIA) service from AVEVA NET. It is a generic service that allows read and write access to AVEVA NET via the EIWM data model. You can give it a technical query based on the class library it will deliver formatted XML back as the result. Similarly you can use it to put XML in to edit the AVEVA NET Database. This is the basic building block of a SOA for lifecycle data management.

3.5 Breaking documents down in other ways

Another overarching requirement is the need to manage the change of documents at a more detailed level than a file. Again a data model like the AVEVA NET EIWM model and the gateways provide a potential solution to this. Referencing the method used by requirements management systems, AVEVA NET gateways can be used to break down document into data modules, and with the relevant configuration of the reference data library, these modules can be selected as the unit to be managed by the AVEVA NET change module.

3.6 Unique for everyone

Data reuse is a key requirements thought the lifecycle of ship data. Reuse of data, is not only efficient but reduces errors which can be a key factor to safety. Of course when considering data reuse we must ensure that the data is consistent and accurate. One factor inhibiting reuse is that each party who will work with the data regarding one physical object will use a different identifier for it. If we take the example of the Main engine, it will be identified as a main engine in the Ship Specification, it may evolve to an Engine type 6M50MC in the procurement department, be named ME1 by the design engineers in the shipyard, referred to as Order number 3838484 by the supplier.

A key enabler to data reuse in the lifecycle of ship data is the use of a universal Unique Identifier. Or UUID, by assigning a UUID to every Engineering item of significance, i.e. major equipment, a safety critical valve, a watertight bulkhead, the data related to it can be managed with far more efficiency. The concept is that the originator of that Engineering object would generate a UUID for it, with an off the shelf UUID generator. This UUID would then be the sole identifier for that item in the world, meaning that even if the supplier, the design office and the ship owner use different identifiers internally for it, it will have one ID in the data management world. This makes the implementation of a SOA approach far easier, and will be the key to automating data updates and cross enterprise data ownership and responsibility.

3.7 Suppliers staging area

One problem AVEVA often hear of from their shipyard customers is that there is no common method to gather equipment information; clearly the UUID as mentioned above contributes significantly to the cause of creating data once and refining never recreating. However it does not address the challenge of receiving uncontrolled heterogeneous data in and homogenising it for management in a single database of data management system.

Supplier UUID: 4fcb2e12-aaea-4f49-bcd2-82a95257f5d1
Supplier product denomination: ~~DD-D-CRMR21-40~~
Component UUID: 5C8642D2D5FF11D69CC30001023A9F7F
Component description: Life raft- rescue boat crane - Rescue boat / raft handling system
Technical specification : Davit outreach is 4.00 m and is suitable for RR 4.2 type boat or 25 persons carrying raft. SWL 11 kN (rescue), SWL 21 kN (raft). Right-hand execution.

Fig. 8: Example of UUID as implemented on a davit. Many thanks to Archnav (www.archnav.de)

Systems like SharePoint and AVEVA NET offer a solution in the form of so called supplier staging areas. The concept is that the shipyard opens up a SharePoint Site for each major supplier, where the supplier can enter data about various items they will supply in the format they are used to. For example one supplier may provide data in a simple PDF document originating from a paper scan. Another may have standardised on DXF drawings and tiff files, a recent trend is towards using PDF files as a container for multiple files of different formats. All of these documents and files must be stored in the shipyard repository, and with the configurable gateways mentioned above it is now possible to extract attribute and engineering intent from these documents.

When using PDF as containers, the files within the container would be checked into a SharePoint document library, checking for document and file consistency with add-on web parts from AVEVA NET. The files would then be scanned through AVEVA NET gateways to extract their engineering intent, typical use cases will be scanning a system diagram for symbol representing key equipment such as a Main Lube Oil Cooler or a Separator. In many cases additional data can be supplied in an XML format, which can now be extracted from CAD systems in a raw data form. The gateways to read such data need only be configured once; then the process generating data in AVEVA NET for ship design purposes will be fully automated.

The Shipdex standard is a perfect example of how data and format are being separated, allowing companies that use it to streamline the process of raw data transfer. If a supplier was providing Shipdex data modules for an equipment item, the AVEVA NET staging area for that supplier would check the files in, ensuring that duplicates do not exist, a gateway configured to read Shipdex data modules would be activated extracting key data from the files, such as Equipment order number, CAD images, weight and Centre of Gravity information, connection points and so on.

3.8 The handover phase

The handover of data from shipyards to ship owners is a task that is given the minimum of effort by the shipyard as it is not their core business, and thus needs to be as automated and as efficient as possible to ensure good quality data handover.

A system like AVEVA NET could offer many advantages to this process, not only is AVEVA NET a place to gather all of the documentation associated with a project, but its document classification abilities allow the documents which must be handed over to be managed, in that workflow and rules will ensure that they are all accounted for. As AVEVA NET captures native CAD data in the form of 3D models and drawings, the shipyard has a fantastic resource, which can be the basis of many added value services to the owner.

One such proposal is the handing over of the 3D model to owners. This model would ideally be web-viewable and compact enough to update over an internet connection. However, it must not contain too much detail to ensure the protection of the shipyard's Intellectual Property (IP). Most web-viewable formats such as JT or AVEVA's Vizstream do just that, by offering a light viewing format, which does not contain the actual geometry, but a simplification of it. This model can be used further downstream as the basis for Hull condition monitoring, refits, maintenance, safety training, virtual reality navigation, and many other valuable services.

If the shipyards are not comfortable with handing over their valuable 3D models, an interim solution could consist of the ability to at least scrape engineering data from the traditional documents delivered at handover, and reformatting this data for use in asset management or planned maintenance systems. This would avoid any IP issues as the design offices would not hand over any 3D model, only their normal drawings and lists, and it would avoid data re-entry by reusing the engineering documents as delivered. The AVEVA NET gateways as mentioned above provide exactly this functionality to get engineering data from Diagrams and complete arrangement drawings.

4 Summary

From the previous chapters and discussions we can see that a key need for a data model to cover data management for the complete lifecycle of a ship is flexibility, it must be able to handle an almost infinite range of relationships between data types, yet bearing in mind the lack of resources available to some of the smaller companies involved in shipping it must be easy to implement, and scalable.

The adoption of certain standards are key to operating an efficient total ship lifecycle management system, XML being a core part of that as well as initiatives like Shipdex, and ISO 15926. Combined with new concepts like a UUID for major components, SOA and web-based information management systems like AVEVA NET we can see that a new era of data management and the digital ship lifecycle model is about to bring huge efficiencies to the way we all work in the shipbuilding and operating process.

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